

U.S. GEOLOGICAL SURVEY-WRD
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Water Resources Data Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands Water Year 1993

U.S. GEOLOGICAL SURVEY WATER-DATA REPORT PR-93-1
Prepared in cooperation with the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico,
the Government of the U.S. Virgin Islands and other agencies

CALENDAR FOR WATER YEAR 1993

1992

OCTOBER							NOVEMBER							DECEMBER						
S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S
				1	2	3	1	2	3	4	5	6	7			1	2	3	4	5
4	5	6	7	8	9	10	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
11	12	13	14	15	16	17	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
18	19	20	21	22	23	24	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	20	21	22	23	24	25	26
25	26	27	28	29	30	31	29	30						27	28	29	30	31		

1993

JANUARY							FEBRUARY							MARCH						
S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S
					1	2		1	2	3	4	5	6		1	2	3	4	5	6
3	4	5	6	7	8	9	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
10	11	12	13	14	15	16	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
17	18	19	20	21	22	23	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	21	22	23	24	25	26	27
24	25	26	27	28	29	30	28							28	29	30	31			
31																				
APRIL							MAY							JUNE						
S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S
				1	2	3						1			1	2	3	4	5	
4	5	6	7	8	9	10	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
11	12	13	14	15	16	17	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
18	19	20	21	22	23	24	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	20	21	22	23	24	25	26
25	26	27	28	29	30		23	24	25	26	27	28	29	27	28	29	30			
							30	31												
JULY							AUGUST							SEPTEMBER						
S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S	S	M	T	W	T	F	S
				1	2	3	1	2	3	4	5	6	7				1	2	3	4
4	5	6	7	8	9	10	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
11	12	13	14	15	16	17	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
18	19	20	21	22	23	24	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	19	20	21	22	23	24	25
25	26	27	28	29	30	31	29	30	31					26	27	28	29	30		

Water Resources Data Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands Water Year 1993

by P.L. Díaz, Z. Aquino, C. Figueroa-Alamo, R.J. Vachier, and
A.V. Sánchez

U.S. DEPARTMENT OF THE INTERIOR
BRUCE BABBITT, Secretary

U.S. GEOLOGICAL SURVEY
Gordon P. Eaton, Director

PREFACE

This annual hydrologic data report of Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands is one of a series of annual reports that document hydrologic data gathered from the U.S. Geological Survey's surface- and ground-water data-collection networks in each state, Puerto Rico, the U.S. Virgin Islands, and the other Trust Territories. These records of streamflow, ground-water levels, and quality of water provide the hydrologic information needed by state, local and Federal agencies, and the private sector for developing and managing our Nation's land and water resources.

The report is the culmination of a concerted effort by dedicated personnel of the U.S. Geological Survey, Water Resources Division who collected, compiled, analyzed, verified, and organized the data, and who typed, edited, and assembled the report. In addition to the authors, who had primary responsibility for assuring that the information contained herein is accurate, complete and adheres to Geological Survey policy and established guidelines, the following personnel contributed significantly to the collection, processing and tabulations of the data:

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This report was prepared in cooperation with agencies of the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico, the Government of the U.S. Virgin Islands, and with other federal agencies under the general supervision of Allen L. Zack, District Chief, Caribbean District, San Juan, Puerto Rico.

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**SURFACE-WATER AND WATER-QUALITY STATIONS, IN DOWNSTREAM ORDER,
FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED IN THIS VOLUME**

VII

(Letter after station name designates type of data:
(d) discharge, (c) chemical, (b) biological, (s) sediment, (p) pesticide, (e) elevation, gage heights)

	Station number	Page
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN		
Río Guajataca at Lares (d,c,b)	50010500	48
Canal Principal de Diversiones at Lago Guajataca (c,b)	50011000	51
Río Guajataca above mouth near Quebradillas (c,b)	50011400	53
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Río Camuy near Bayaney (d)	50014800	57
Río Camuy near Hatillo (d)	50015700	58
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN		
Lago Garzas near Adjuntas (e)	50020100	60
Río Grande de Arecibo near Adjuntas (c,b)	50020500	62
Río Grande de Arecibo near Utuado (c,b)	50025000	64
Río Saliente at Coabey near Jayuya (d)	50025155	66
Río Caonillas above Lago Caonillas near Jayuya (c,b)	50026050	67
Lago Caonillas at Caonillas (e)	50026140	69
Río Grande de Arecibo below Lago Dos Bocas near Florida (c,b)	50027250	70
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Lago La Plata at Damsite (e)	50045000	136
Río de La Plata below La Plata Dam (d)	50045010	137
Río de La Plata at Highway 2 near Toa Alta (d,c,b,s,p)	50046000	142
 RIO HONDO BASIN		
Río Hondo at Flood Channel near Cataño (c,b)	50047530	148
 RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN		
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Lago de Cidra at Damsite near Cidra (e)	50047550	154
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**SURFACE-WATER AND WATER-QUALITY STATIONS, IN DOWNSTREAM ORDER,
FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED IN THIS VOLUME--Continued**

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Río Fajardo near Fajardo (d,c,b,p)	50071000	318
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Quebrada Guabá near Naguabo (d)	50074950	323
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RIO HUMACAO BASIN		
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**X SURFACE-WATER AND WATER-QUALITY STATIONS, IN DOWNSTREAM ORDER,
FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED IN THIS VOLUME--Continued**

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RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASIN		
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Río Grande de Añasco near San Sebastián (d,c,b,s)	50144000	409
Río Grande de Añasco near Añasco (c,b,p)	50146000	412
RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN		
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Río Culebrinas at Highway 404 near Moca (d)	50147800	418
Río Culebrinas near Aguada (c,b,p)	50149100	419

**SURFACE-WATER AND WATER-QUALITY STATIONS, IN DOWNSTREAM ORDER,
FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED IN THIS VOLUME--Continued**

XI

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Quebrada Cofresí Tributary near Isabela II (e)	50231000	423
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ST THOMAS, US VIRGIN ISLANDS		
Bonne Resolution Gut at Bonne Resolution (d)	50252000	510
Turpentine Run at Mount Zion (d)	50274000	511
ST JOHN, US VIRGIN ISLANDS		
Lameshur Bay Gut at Lameshur (d)	50292600	512
Fish Bay Gut at Fish Bay (d)	50294000	514
Guinea Gut at Bethany (d)	50295000	516
Cruz Bay Gut at Cruz Bay (e)	50295500	517
ST CROIX, US VIRGIN ISLANDS		
River Gut at River (e)	50332000	518
River Gut near Golden Grove (d)	50333500	519
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Well 182647066552400 Local number 202	455
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Well 182737066370900 Local number 204	456
RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN	
Well 182757066325600 Local number 206	457
Well 182710066303700 Local number 207	458
Well 182308066260400 Local number 210	459
RIO CIBUCO BASIN	
Well 182647066201700 Local number 70	460
Well 182615066235300 Local number 211	461
Well 182515066194000 Local number 212	462
Well 182330066185700 Local number 213	463
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Well 182413066044000 Local number 220	469
Well 182511066045401 Local number PN-2	470
Well 182435066052701 Local number PN-5	471
Well 182445066043401 Local number PN-6	472
Well 182437066040501 Local number PN-7	473
Well 182443066041502 Local number PN-8c	474
Well 182417066042700 Local number PN-10	475
Well 182349066032600 Local number PN-13	476
Well 182406066034700 Local number PN-19	477
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN	
Well 181550065593201 Local number 50	478
Well 182515065594100 Local number 222	479
Well 181513065554601 Local number CJ-TW3B	480
Well 181352066025300 Local number CJ-TW19A	481
RIO HUMACAO TO RIO SECO BASINS	
Well 175858066100200 Local number 6	482
Well 180415065513900 Local number 96	483

**U.S. Geological Survey
Water Resources Division
Caribbean District**

ERRATA

**WATER RESOURCES DATA - PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS,
WATER YEAR 1993**

1. The period of record for pages 75, 102, 144, 221, 246, 263, 303, 304, and 319 containing water-quality data, should read:

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

2. Substitute data on pages 412 and 413 with new data provided on the page accompanying this errata.
3. The heading for pages 445 through 448 should read:

**ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS
WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993**

4. Sediment data for water year 1993 for stations 50055170 Río Caguitas near Caguas and 50057000 Río Gurabo at Gurabo, which were not available for publication in this volume, can be obtained through the Caribbean District office. These data will be published in the water year 1994 Data Report. For information call (809) 749-4346.

The new address of the U.S. Geological Survey, Caribbean District is:

**Mailing: GSA CENTER
651 FEDERAL DRIVE
SUITE 400-15
GUAYNABO, P.R. 00965**

**Physical: GSA CENTER
HIGHWAY 28, KM 7.2
BLDG. 651, SUITE 400
GUAYNABO, P.R.**

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

Well 175829066232200 Local number 87	484
Well 180002066132200 Local number HW-TW-01	485
Well 180001066122002 Local number HW-TW-03C	486
Well 175947066130601 Local number HW-TW-05B	487
Well 175957066123400 Local number HW-TW-13	488
Well 175946066102000 Local number HW-TW-14	489
Well 180206066135500 Local number RM-05	490
Well 180104066152300 Local number RM-10	491

RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASINS

Well 180133066503300 Local number 132	492
Well 175900066354200 Local number 141	493

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

Well 180132067033800 Local number 143	494
Well 180627067080600 Local number CR-TW-1	495
Well 180628067075800 Local number CR-TW-2A	496
Well 180628067075801 Local number CR-TW-2B	497
Well 180628067075802 Local number CR-TW-2C	498
Well 180643067080400 Local number CR-TW-3	499
Well 180650067073700 Local number CR-TW-4	500
Well 180557067083100 Local number CR-TW-5	501
Well 180617067083300 Local number CR-TW-6	502
Well 180604067085100 Local number CR-TW-7	503
Well 180547067084800 Local number CR-TW-8	504
Well 180628067084300 Local number CR-TW-9A	505
Well 180547067073100 Local number CR-TW-10	506

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

Well 182442067091700 Local number 200	507
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ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

Well 174225064471900 Local number 1	528
Well 174225064472000 Local number 2	529
Well 174243064475100 Local number 3	530
Well 174245064475800 Local number 4	531
Well 174308064484400 Local number 6	532
Well 174525064460600 Local number 7	533
Well 174527064460100 Local number 8	534
Well 174532064460300 Local number 9	535
Well 174329064454700 Local number 10	536
Well 174303064481100 Local number 11	537
Well 174308064482800 Local number 12	538

XIV GROUND-WATER WELLS, BY BASIN, FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED--Continued

Page

Well 174316064480800 Local number 13	539
Well 174247064475701 Local number 14	540
Well 174319064454401 Local number 15	541

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

Well 182038064550300 Local number 6	542
Well 182036064545200 Local number 7	543
Well 182038064580000 Local number 8	544
Well 181917064524600 Local number 9	545
Well 182131064541000 Local number 10	546
Well 182035064550200 Local number 11	547

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

Well 182010064472600 Local number 1	548
Well 182109064460300 Local number 2	549
Well 182116064451000 Local number 3	550
Well 182044064454800 Local number 7	551
Well 182044064454900 Local number 8	552
Well 182044064455000 Local number 9	553
Well 182044064455200 Local number 10	554
Well 181956064464500 Local number 11	555
Well 182110064430000 Local number 12	556
Well 181950064422300 Local number 13	557
Well 182048064430400 Local number 14	558

DISCONTINUED STREAMFLOW STATIONS

The following continuous-record streamflow stations in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands have been discontinued or converted to partial-record stations. Daily streamflow or stage records were collected for the period of record shown for each station.

Station number	Station name	Drainage area (mi ²)	Period of record
50007000	Quebrada de los Cedros near Isabela	6.91	1970
50010600	Río Guajataca above Lago de Guajataca	--	1984-89
50011000	Canal Diversion Lago Guajataca	--	1970
50011200	Río Guajataca below Lago Guajataca	--	1969-70, 1984-87
50011400	Río Guajataca above mouth near Quebradillas	--	1969-70, 1984-89
50013000	Río Camuy near Lares	7.62	1969-71
50014000	Río Criminales near Lares	4.68	1969-70
50016000	Río Camuy near Camuy	--	1969-73
50021000	Río Pellejas at Central Pellejas	5.46	1968-70
50021050	Río Pellejas below Central Pellejas	7.89	1972-75
50021500	Río Pellejas near Utuado	9.55	1969-71
50023000	Río Viví near Central Pellejas	5.66	1969-75
50027200	Río Grande de Arecibo blw. Lago dos Bocas	169	1970-71
50029000	Río Grande de Arecibo at Central Cambalache	200	1969-83
50031500	Río Sana Muerto near Orocovis	3.68	1965-70
50035200	Río Grande de Manatí at Hwy 145 at Ciales	132	1972
50035950	Río Cialitos at Hwy 649 at Ciales	17	1970-82
50038360	Río Mavilla near Corozal	9.51	1969-70
50038600	Río Unibón near Morovis	5.29	1969-70
50038700	Río Morovis at Morovis	1.26	1968
50038900	Río Indio at Vega Baja	--	1963,66,71
50039600	Río Cibuco at Central San Vicente	--	1969-72
50043200	Río Usabon near Barranquitas	9.15	1968-69,71
50043400	Río Aibonito Tributary near Aibonito	1.13	1968-71
50044600	Río Guadiana near Naranjito	1.73	1971
50044650	Quebrada del Toro near Naranjito	0.54	1971
50044800	Quebrada Anones near Naranjito	2.32	1971
50045700	Río Lajas at Toa Alta	8.65	1966-75
50047820	Río de Bayamón at Hwy 174 near Bayamón	31.90	1966
50048000	Río de Bayamón at Bayamón	71.90	1963-67
50049310	Quebrada Josefina at Piñero Avenue	3.84	1988-91
50053050	Río Turabo at Borinquen	7.89	1984-90
50054000	Quebrada de las Quebradillas near Caguas	6.25	1969-71,73
50055650	Quebrada Caimito near Juncos	0.82	1984-87
50056000	Río Valencianc near Las Piedras	6.85	1971
50056900	Quebrada Mamey near Gurabo	2.30	1984-92
50058300	Quebrada Arena near Caguas	--	1971
50061300	Río Canovanillas near Loíza	14.40	1968-73
50062500	Río Herrera near Colonia Dolores	2.75	1968-72
50063300	Río Espíritu Santo near El Verde	2.23	1968-73
50065700	Río Mameyes at Hwy 191 at Mameyes	11.80	1967-85
50072000	Río Fajardo at Fajardo	21.60	1960-63
50073200	Río Daguaó at Daguaó	2.26	1966-82
50073400	Quebrada Palma at Daguaó	4.84	1972-77
50074000	Río Santiago at Naguabo	4.99	1966-82
50075500	Río Blanco at Florida	11.00	1966-82
50076000	Río Blanco near Florida	12.30	1983-85
50077000	Río Blanco at Río Blanco	17.60	1973-77
50077400	Río Blanco at Colonia La Fe	18.80	1967-70
50078500	Río Anton Ruiz at Central Pasto Viejo	4.33	1968
50081500	Río Humacao near Humacao	9.23	1973
50082000	Río Humacao at Hwy 3 at Humacao	17.30	1983-85
50082200	Río Humacao near La Suiza	19.90	1965-66, 1969-71
50082800	Río Guayanés near Colonia Laura	4.69	1969-82
50083500	Río Guayanés near Yabucoa	17.20	1969-71
50084000	Río Limones near Yabucoa	7.89	1969-71
50085100	Río Guayanés at Central Roig	26.60	1965-66, 1968,70, 1965-66, 1968-69
50086100	Río del Ingenio at Comunas	5.50	1965-66, 1968-69
50086500	Río Guayanés at Playa Guayanés	34.00	1965-66, 1968-71
50087200	Cafío Santiago near Central Roig	6.04	1965-71

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1993

DISCONTINUED STREAMFLOW STATIONS--Continued

Station number	Station name	Drainage area (mi ²)	Period of record
50091000	Río Maunabo at Maunabo	12.40	1965, 67, 1969-82
50091200	Río Maunabo near Maunabo	12.70	1971-72
50091400	Río Jacaboá near Lamboglia	4.13	1965-73
50091700	Río Chico at Patillas	6.82	1965, 1969-72
50091800	Río Chico at Providencia	4.90	1965, 1967-69, 1971
50094200	Río Grande de Patillas at Patillas	27.90	1967, 1969, 1971
50094300	Río Grande de Patillas at Providencia	29.00	1971
50094400	Río Nigua at Pitahaya	5.86	1965, 1969, 1970-71, 1973
50095200	Río Guamaní at Guayama	8.22	1969-71
50095500	Río Guamaní near Guayama	12.30	1969-70
50099000	Quebrada Aguas Verdes near Salinas	0.39	1989
50106500	Río Coamo near Coamo	46.00	1967-68 1984-85, 1986
50106900	Río Coamo below Lago Coamo near Coamo	65.40	1967-68
50107200	Río Coamo at mouth near Santa Isabel	69.30	1967-68
50108200	Río Descalabrado at Las Ollas	13.90	1965, 1967-71
50108500	Río Descalabrado near Santa Isabel	18.10	1966-67
50111200	Río Toa Vaca near Villalba	21.40	1966-70
50111700	Río Jacaguas near Juana Díaz	53.20	1966-68
50111750	Río Jacaguas below Quebrada Guanábana	56.30	1989
50112100	Río Jacaguas near Arús	59.60	1966-67
50112600	Río Inabón at Coto Laurel	--	1967-71
50113100	Río Guayo near Coto Laurel	11.80	1965, 1968-71
50113500	Río Inabón near Arús	30.20	1964-65
50114400	Río Bucaná near Ponce	25.60	1965-81
50114700	Río Bucaná near Playa de Ponce	28.40	1964-67
50115900	Río Portugués at Hwy 14 at Ponce	--	1965-82
50116500	Río Portugués at Highway 2 Bypass at Ponce	20.50	1964-65
50119000	Río Matilde at Ponce	19.40	1965-66
50121000	Río Tallaboa at Peñuelas	24.20	1959-82
50122000	Río Tallaboa at Tallaboa	31.50	1959-63
50124000	Río Guayanilla nr Guayanilla	18.50	1961-69
50124500	Río Guayanilla at Guayanilla	20.80	1971-82
50125900	Río Duey above Diversion near Yauco	8.93	1977-80
50126150	Río Yauco above Diversion Monserrate near Yauco	27.20	1978-85
50128000	Río Yauco near Yauco	45.50	1962-64, 1977-85
50129000	Río Loco near Yauco	8.50	1963-67
50129500	Río Loco near Guánica	21.00	1963-69
50129900	Laguna Cartagena near Boquerón	--	1984-86
50130320	Quebrada Mamey at Joyuda	0.38	1986-88
50136000	Río Rosario at Rosario	16.40	1975-86
50141000	Río Yahuecas near Adjuntas	15.40	1980-85
50145000	Río Grande de Añasco at El Espino	108.00	1959-66, 1961-63
50147000	Río Culebrinas at San Sebastian	16.70	1960-82
50276000	Turpentine Run at Mariendal	2.97	1963-69, 1978-86

INTRODUCTION

The Water Resources Division of the U.S. Geological Survey, in cooperation with local and federal agencies obtains a large amount of data pertaining to the water resources of the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico and the Territory of the U.S. Virgin Islands each water year. These data, accumulated during many water years, constitute a valuable data base for developing an improved understanding of the water resources of the area. To make these data readily available to interested parties outside the Geological Survey, the data are published annually in this report series entitled "Water Resources Data for Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands, 1993."

This report includes records on both surface and ground water. Specifically, it contains: (1) Discharge records for 81 streamflow-gaging stations, stage only for 12 gaging stations, daily sediment records for 21 streamflow stations, 112 partial-record or miscellaneous streamflow stations, stage records for 11 reservoirs, and (2) water-quality records for 16 streamflow-gaging stations, and for 42 ungaged streamsites, 11 lake sites, 2 lagoons, and 1 bay; and (3) water-level records for 86 observation wells.

Water-resources data for Puerto Rico for calendar years 1958-67 were released in a series of reports entitled "Water Records of Puerto Rico". Water-resources data for the U.S. Virgin Islands for the calendar years 1962-69 were released in a report entitled "Water Records of U.S. Virgin Islands." Included were records of streamflow, ground-water levels, and water-quality data for both surface and ground water.

Beginning with the 1968 calendar year, surface-water records for Puerto Rico were released separately on an annual basis. Ground-water level records and water-quality data for surface and ground water were released in companion reports covering periods of several years. Data for the 1973-74 reports were published under separate covers. Water-resources data reports for 1975-76, 1977, 1978, 1979-80, 1981-82, 1983, 1984, 1985, 1986, 1987, 1988, 1989, 1990, 1991 and 1992 water years consist of one volume each and contain data for streamflow, water quality and ground water.

Publications similar to this report are published annually by the Geological Survey for all States. These official Survey reports have an identification number consisting of the two-letter State abbreviation, the last two digits of the water year, and the volume number. For example, this volume is identified as "U.S. Geological Survey Water-Data Report PR-93-1". These water-data reports are for sale in paper copy or in microfiche by the National Technical Information Service, U.S. Department of Commerce, Springfield, Virginia, 22161. Beginning with the 1990 water year, all water-data reports will also be available on Compact Disc-Read Only Memory (CD-ROM). All data reports published for the current water year for the entire Nation, including Puerto Rico and the Trust Territories, will be reproduced on a single CD-ROM disc.

Additional information, including current prices, for ordering specific reports may be obtained from the District Chief at the address given on back of the title page or by telephone (809) 749-4346. A limited number of CD-ROM discs will be available for sale by the Books and Open-File Reports Section, U.S. Geological Survey, Federal Center, Box 25425, Denver, Colorado 80225.

COOPERATION

The U.S. Geological Survey has had cooperative agreements with organizations of the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico and the Territory of the U.S. Virgin Islands for the systematic collections of water resources data since 1958. Organizations that supplied data are acknowledged in the station descriptions. Organizations that assisted in collecting data through cooperative agreements with the Survey are:

- Puerto Rico Environmental Quality Board
- Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority
- Puerto Rico Department of Agriculture
- Puerto Rico Industrial Development Company
- Puerto Rico Department of Housing
- Puerto Rico Highway Authority
- Puerto Rico Department of Natural Resources
- Puerto Rico Department of Health
- Puerto Rico Electric and Power Authority
- Puerto Rico Legislature
- Puerto Rico Civil Defense
- Water Resources Research Institute, College of the Virgin Islands
- U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority

Funds were also provided by the Corps of Engineers, U.S. Army, for the collection of records at seven gaging stations published in this report.

SUMMARY OF HYDROLOGIC CONDITIONS

Precipitation

Precipitation throughout Puerto Rico during the 1993 water year (October 1992 to September 1993) averaged about 103 percent of normal. However, precipitation was 98 percent of normal in northern Puerto Rico, 106 percent of normal in southern Puerto Rico, 105 percent of normal in eastern Puerto Rico, and 105 percent of normal in western Puerto Rico. Monthly average precipitation islandwide for the 1993 water year and for the 30-year reference period 1951-1980 used to define normal rainfall, as reported by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, are listed in table 1.

Table 1. Islandwide monthly precipitation and annual averages for the 1993 water year and the 30-year reference period, 1951-80

Month	1993 Water Year (inches)	30-year normal (inches)
OCT	6.40	7.74
NOV	8.94	5.95
DEC	5.23	4.32
JAN	3.91	3.08
FEB	1.92	2.35
MAR	2.03	2.62
APR	6.76	4.63
MAY	8.02	6.48
JUN	5.36	5.58
JUL	5.91	5.48
AUG	4.23	7.28
SEP	6.51	7.78
TOTAL	65.22	63.29

Surface Water

Streamflow at the four index stations in Puerto Rico generally was above normal during water year 1993 although no significant floods occurred during the year. Figure 1 compares monthly-mean flows at the four index stations on the Río Grande de Añasco, the Río Grande de Manatí, the Río Inabón, and the Río Fajardo during water year 1993 with the long-term median of monthly-mean flows. Maximum and minimum monthly flows for each of these index stations for the period of record are also shown in figure 1.

In the western area, the Río Grande de Añasco near San Sebastián had monthly-mean flows that exceeded the long-term median of monthly-mean flow every month except July and August which had monthly-mean flows of 76 and 77 percent of the long-term median.

Unshaded area indicates range between highest and lowest monthly mean discharges for the period of record prior to water year 1993.

Figure 1.--Monthly mean discharge of selected streams in Puerto Rico.

In the northern area, streamflow at the index station on the Río Grande de Manatí at Highway 2, was above normal during much of the year and the monthly-mean flow in April and May were 325 and 322 percent of the long-term median of monthly-mean flows. Monthly-mean flows were below the long-term median of monthly-mean flows in October, March, and August with 72 to 98 percent of the long-term median.

In the southern area, monthly-mean flow at the Río Inabón at Real Abajo index station was above the long-term median of monthly-mean flow most of the water year 1993. During May the monthly-mean flow at this site was 475 percent of the long-term median. Only during December, August, and September were monthly-mean flows below the long-term median of monthly-mean flows.

In the eastern area, streamflow at the Río Fajardo near Fajardo index station, was above the long-term median of monthly-mean flow during November, December, January, and July, but was below the long-term median during much of the year. At the beginning of water year 1993, monthly-mean flow in the Río Fajardo was only 27 percent of the long-term median of monthly-mean flow. From November to January monthly-mean flows ranged from 122 to 330 percent of the long-term median. In February and March streamflow declined seasonally and monthly-mean flows were below normal. In August, the monthly-mean flow at this station was the lowest of record.

Ground-Water Levels

Ground-water levels in the major aquifers of Puerto Rico followed a seasonal trend associated with rainfall patterns during water year 1993. Water levels generally rose as significant rainfall events recharged the coastal aquifers. Record-high water levels were recorded at several wells in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands (table 2).

Ground-water levels in the north coast limestone aquifer, at the Sabana Hoyos index well (fig. 2) rose from November to early January 1993. Water levels in this well then declined until late April, when above normal rainfall reversed the trend. Water levels were relatively stable from mid-May until early August, but declined gradually during late August and September.

Ground-water levels in the south coast alluvial aquifer at the Alomar index well (fig. 2) were relatively stable during October and November 1992, but declined about 3.4 feet, from December 1992 to April 1993. Water levels rose about a foot in this well during May as a result of above normal rainfall along the south coast, but remained relatively stable from June to September 1993, except for fluctuations, due to ground-water withdrawals for public, irrigation, and industrial uses. Water levels in this well were about 2 feet lower at the end of the water year than at the start of the water year.

Ground water in observation well 11 at Guinea Gut, St. John in U.S. Virgin Islands rose sharply in response to rainfall events during November and December 1992 and January, February, and June 1993 (fig. 2). From February to mid-June 1993 the water levels in Guinea Gut well declined about 12.5 feet in response to below normal rainfall in the area.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1993

Table 2. Highest ground-water levels recorded during 1993 water year and previous high ground-water levels at selected wells in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands.

[PR, Puerto Rico; St.T, St. Thomas; St.J, St. John; mm-dd-yy, month-day-year; ft-blsd, feet below land-surface datum; mm-yy, month-year; +, above land-surface datum]

Well name or number	Local number	Location	1993 highest water level (ft-blsd)	Date (mm-dd-yy)	Previous highest water level (ft-blsd)	Date (mm-dd-yy)	Period of record (mm-yy)
Salto 1	165	PR	38.40	07-12-93	38.75	09-23-92 09-26-92	1-82 to 9-93
La Esperanza 2	PN-2	PR	8.01	12-30-92 12-31-92	8.07	06-08-92 06-09-92 06-10-92	6-89 to 9-93
Salud Mental 5	PN-5	PR	25.37	02-05-93	26.20	11-21-89 11-22-89	4-89 to 9-93
Las Américas 10	PN-10	PR	+2.30	01-09-93 01-10-93 01-11-93 01-12-93	+2.04	10-22-90	10-89 to 9-93
Jardín Botánico 3	PN-19	PR	3.35	12-30-92	4.04	06-09-92	6-91 to 9-93
CJ-TW 19A	CJ-TW 19A	PR	22.78	07-27-93	23.78	11-16-91	9-91 to 9-93
CR-TW-1	CR-TW-1	PR	+4.75	10-12-92	+3.11	09-08-92	7-92 to 9-93
CR-TW-2A	CR-TW-2A	PR	+4.00	10-12-92	+2.06	09-15-92	7-92 to 9-93
CR-TW-2B	CR-TW-2B	PR	+4.34	10-10-92	+2.71	09-08-92	6-92 to 9-93
CR-TW-2C	CR-TW-2C	PR	+3.94	10-10-92	+1.96	09-15-92	6-92 to 9-93
CR-TW-3	CR-TW-3	PR	+5.40	10-11-92	+4.24	09-15-92	3-92 to 9-93
CR-TW-4	CR-TW-4	PR	2.99	10-12-92	3.55	09-26-92	6-92 to 9-93
CR-TW-5	CR-TW-5	PR	2.12	10-12-92	3.78	09-15-92	7-92 to 9-93
CR-TW-6	CR-TW-6	PR	1.44	10-12-92	4.00	09-15-92	6-92 to 9-93
CR-TW-7	CR-TW-7	PR	11.15	10-12-92	14.20	09-15-92	6-92 to 9-93
CR-TW-8	CR-TW-8	PR	5.60	10-05-92	7.02	09-25-92	6-92 to 9-93
CR-TW-9A	CR-TW-9A	PR	+0.24	10-12-92	1.36	09-09-92	7-92 to 9-93
CR-TW-10	CR-TW-10	PR	2.98	10-12-92	5.17	09-15-92	7-92 to 9-93
VIEO-6	8	St.T	22.79	01-21-93	23.27	10-14-91	10-91 to 9-93
VIEO-4	14	St.J	9.57	01-06-93 01-07-93	9.95	06-05-92	5-91 to 9-93

Figure 2.—Ground-water levels at selected wells in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands.

Water Quality

In water year 1993, the U.S. Geological Survey, in cooperation with local government agencies, collected water-quality data at 72 surface-water station in Puerto Rico. The water-quality data collected at these stations included the major chemical constituents and several additional constituents that are listed in table 3. The highest concentration of these additional constituents detected during water year 1993 and the stations which these concentrations were detected are summarized in table 3.

Table 3. Surface-water quality stations in Puerto Rico with highest concentration of selected constituents during water year 1993 [All constituent concentrations are in milligrams per liter; MBAS, Methylene blue active substance]

Station number	Station name	Constituent	Concentration
50010500	Río Guajataca at Lares	Sulfide	1.6
50475300	Río Hondo at Flood Channel near Cataño	Boron	5.0
50083500	Río Guayanés near Yabucoa	Manganese	1.1
50116200	Río Portugués at Ponce	Iron	21
50011000	Canal Diversión at Lago Guajataca	Zinc	.31
50091800	Río Chico at Providencia	Cyanide	.03
50091800	Río Chico at Providencia	Phenols	.10
50055250	Río Caguitas at Highway 30 at Caguas	MBAS	.009

The presence of high concentrations of fecal coliform (FC) and fecal streptococci (FS) bacteria continued to be the principal surface-water quality problem in Puerto Rico during water year 1993. A bacteria concentration exceeding one million colonies per hundred milliliters of raw water was determined for a water sample collected at the station on Río Piedras at Río Piedras (50049100). This station is located in the San Juan metropolitan area, which has the highest population concentration in Puerto Rico. In addition to the effluent from the San Juan metropolitan area Río Piedras also receives from the areas in the upper basin sewage treatment plants service in urban and suburban. The main sources of contamination in surface-water systems in Puerto Rico are discharges of liquid wastes from industrial and municipal sources. The highest concentration of fecal coliform and fecal streptococci bacteria in surface waters in Puerto Rico generally were in heavily populated an industrialized areas of the island.

Suspended sediment concentrations were monitored at 19 stations in Puerto Rico during the 1993 water year as part of the cooperative program between the U.S. Geological Survey and various Commonwealth and Federal agencies. High suspended sediment concentrations are a common problem in many streams in Puerto Rico. Most of the streams with high suspended sediment concentration were related to land use, especially construction of urbanizations and roads, agriculture and activities where soil movement was involved. The high suspended sediment concentrations affects the water quality for drinking water and decrease the storage capacities of reservoirs used for water supply.

SPECIAL NETWORKS AND PROGRAMS

Hydrologic Bench-Mark Network is a network of 57 sites in small drainage basins around the country whose purpose is to provide consistent data on the hydrology, including water quality, and related factors in representative undeveloped watersheds nationwide, and to provide analyses on a continuing basis to compare and contrast conditions observed in basins more obviously affected by the activities of man.

National Stream Quality Accounting Network (NASQAN) is a nationwide data-collection network designed by the U.S. Geological Survey to meet many of the information needs of government agencies and other groups involved in natural or regional water-quality planning and management. The 500 or so sites on NASQAN are generally located at the downstream ends of hydrologic accounting units designated by the U.S. Geological Survey Office of Water Data Coordination in consultation with the Water Resources Council. The objectives of NASQAN are (1) to obtain information on the quality and quantity of water moving within and from the United States through a systematic and uniform process of data collection, summarization, analysis, and reporting such that the data may be used for, (2) description of the areal variability of water quality in the Nation's rivers through analysis of data from this and other programs, (3) detection of changes or trends with time in the pattern of occurrence of water-quality characteristics, and (4) providing a nationally consistent data base useful for water-quality assessment and hydrologic research.

The National Trends Network (NTN) is a 150-station network for sampling atmospheric deposition in the United States. The purpose of the network is to determine the variability, both in location and in time, of the composition of atmospheric deposition, which includes snow, rain, dust particles, aerosols, and gases. The core from which the NTN was built was the already-existing deposition-monitoring network of the National Atmospheric Deposition Program (NADP).

The National Water-Quality Assessment (NAWQA) Program of the U.S. Geological Survey is a long-term program with goals to describe the status and trends of water-quality conditions for a large, diverse, and geographically distributed part of the Nation's ground- and surface-water resources, and to identify, describe, and explain the major natural and human factors that affect these observed conditions and trends.

Assessment activities have begun in more than one-third of the study units and ultimately will be conducted in 60 study units (major watersheds and aquifer systems) that represent a wide range of environmental settings nationwide and that account for a large percentage of the Nation's water use. A wide array of chemical constituents will be measured in ground water, surface water, streambed sediments, and fish tissues. The coordinated application of comparative hydrologic studies at a wide range of spatial and temporal scales will provide information for decision making by water-resources managers and a foundation for aggregation and comparison of findings to address water-quality issues of regional and national interest.

Radiochemical Programs is a network of regularly sampled water-quality stations where samples are collected to be analyzed for radioisotopes. The streams that are sampled represent major drainage basins in the conterminous United States.

Tritium Network is a network of stations which has been established to provide baseline information on the occurrence of tritium in the Nation's surface waters. In addition to the surface-water stations in the network, tritium in the Nation's surface waters. In addition to the surface-water stations in the network, tritium data are also obtained at a number of precipitation stations. The purpose of the precipitation stations is to provide an estimate sufficient for hydrologic studies of the tritium input to the United States.

EXPLANATION OF RECORDS

The surface- and ground-water records published in this report are for the 1993 water year that began October 1, 1992 and ended September 30, 1993. A calendar of the water year is provided on the inside of the front cover. The records contain streamflow data, water-quality data for surface and ground water, and ground-water-level data. The locations of the stations and wells where the data were collected are shown in figures 3 to 10. The following sections of the introductory text are presented to provide users with a more detailed explanation of how the hydrologic data published in this report were collected, analyzed, computed, and arranged for presentation.

Station Identification Numbers

Each data station, whether streamsite or well, in this report is assigned a unique identification number. This number is unique in that it applies specifically to a given station and to no other. The number usually is assigned when a station is first established and is retained for that station indefinitely. The systems used by the U.S. Geological Survey to assign identification numbers for surface-water stations and for ground-water well sites differ, but both are based on geographic location. The "downstream order" system is used for regular surface-water stations and the "latitude-longitude" system is used for wells.

Downstream Order System

Since October 1, 1950, the order of listing hydrologic-station records in Survey reports is in a downstream direction along the main stream. All stations on a tributary entering upstream from a main-stream station are listed before that station. A station on a tributary that enters between two main-stream stations is listed between them. A similar order is followed in listing stations in first rank, second rank, and other ranks of tributaries.

As an added means of identification, each hydrologic station and partial-record station has been assigned a station number. These are in the same downstream order used in this report. In assigning station numbers, no distinction is made between partial-record stations and other stations; therefore, the station number for a partial-record station indicates downstream order position in a list made up of both types of stations that may be established; hence, the numbers are not consecutive. The complete 8-digit number for each station such as 50028000, which appears just to the left of the station name, includes the 2-digit part number "50" plus the 6-digit downstream order number "028000."

Latitude-Longitude System

The 8-digit downstream order station numbers are not assigned to wells and miscellaneous sites where only random water-quality samples or discharge measurements are taken.

The well and miscellaneous site numbering system of the U.S. Geological Survey is based on the grid system of latitude and longitude. The system provides the geographic location of the well or miscellaneous site and a unique number for each site. The number consists of 15 digits. The first 6 digits denote the degrees, minutes, and seconds of latitude, the next 7 digits denote degrees, minutes, and seconds of longitude, and the last 2 digits (assigned sequentially) identify the wells or other sites within a 1-second grid. The numbers shown in the grid correspond to the local numbers assigned to each well as visited in the field. An example is well 16 (fig. 12).

Figure 4.--Location of fecal streptococci bacteria concentration at sampled sites.

Figure 6.--Location of water-quality stations in Puerto Rico.

Figure 7.--Location of low-flow partial-record stations in southwest Puerto Rico.

Figure 8.--Location of ground-water stations in Puerto Rico.

Figure 9.--Location of surface-water stations in the U.S. Virgin Islands.

Figure 10.--Location of ground-water stations in the U.S. Virgin Islands.

Figure 11.--Location of surface-water stations in Vieques and Culebra Islands.

Figure 12.--Grid showing system for numbering wells and miscellaneous sites (latitude and longitude).

Records of Stage and Water Discharge

Records of stage and water discharge may be complete or partial. Complete records of discharge are those obtained using a continuous stage-recording device through which either instantaneous or mean daily discharges may be computed for any time, or any period of time, during the period of record. Complete records of lake or reservoir content, similarly, are those for which stage or content may be computed or estimated with reasonable accuracy for any time, or period of time. They may be obtained using a continuous stage-recording device, but need not be. Because daily mean discharges and end-of-day contents commonly are published for such stations, they are referred to as "daily stations."

By contrast, partial records are obtained through discrete measurements without using a continuous stage-recording device and pertain only to a few flow characteristics, or perhaps only one. The nature of the partial record is indicated by table titles such as "Low-flow partial records." Records of miscellaneous discharge measurements or of measurements from special studies, such as low-flow seepage studies, may be considered as partial records, but they are presented separately in this type of report. Location of all complete-record stations for which data are given in this report are shown in figures 5 and 8.

Data Collection and Computation

The data obtained at a complete-record gaging station on a stream or canal consists of a continuous record of stage, individual measurements of discharge throughout a range of stages, and notations regarding factors that may affect the relationships between stage and discharge. These data, together with supplemental information, such as weather records, are used to compute daily discharges. The data obtained at a complete-record gaging station on a lake or reservoir consist of a record of stage and of notations regarding factors that may affect the relationship between stage and lake content. These data are used with stage-area and stage-capacity curves or tables to compute water-surface areas and lake storage.

Continuous records of stage are obtained with analog recorders that trace continuous graphs of stage or with digital recorders that punch stage values on paper tapes at selected time intervals or electronic satellite data collector platforms that receive stage values at selected time intervals. Measurements of discharge are made with current meters using methods adapted by the Geological Survey as a result of experience accumulated since 1880. These methods are described in standard textbooks, in Water-Supply Paper 2175, and in U.S. Geological Survey Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations, Book 3, Chapter A6.

In computing discharge records, results of individual measurements are plotted against the corresponding stages, and stage-discharge relation curves are then constructed. From these curves, rating tables indicating the approximate discharge for any stage within the range of the measurements are prepared. If it is necessary to define extremes of discharge outside the range of the current-meter measurements, the curves are extended using: (1) logarithmic plotting; (2) velocity-area studies; (3) results of indirect measurements of peak discharge, such as slope-area or contracted-opening measurements, and computations of flow-over-dams or weirs; or (4) step-backwater techniques.

Daily mean discharges are computed by applying the daily mean stages (gage heights) to the stage-discharge curves or tables. If the stage-discharge relation is subject to change because of frequent or continual change in the physical features that form the control, the daily mean discharge is determined by the shifting-control method, in which correction factors based on the individual discharge measurements and notes of the personnel making the measurements are applied to the gage heights before the discharges are determined from the curves or tables. This shifting-control method also is used if the stage-discharge relation is changed temporarily because of aquatic growth or debris on the control. At some stations the stage-discharge relation is affected by changing stage; at these stations the rate of change in stage is used as a factor in computing discharge.

In computing records of lake or reservoir contents, it is necessary to have available from surveys, curves or tables defining the relationship of stage and contents. The application of stage to the stage-content curves or tables gives the contents from which daily, monthly or yearly changes then are determined. If the stage-content relationship changes because of deposition of sediment in a lake or reservoir, periodic surveys may be necessary to redefine it. Even when this is done, as time between the last survey increases, the contents computed may increase in error. Discharges over lake or reservoir spillways are computed from stage-discharge relationships much as other stream discharges are computed.

For some gaging stations there are periods when no gage-height record is obtained, or the recorded gage height is so faulty that it cannot be used to compute daily discharge or contents. This happens when the recorder stops or otherwise fails to operate properly, intakes are plugged, the float is loose in the well, or for various other reasons. For such periods, the daily discharges are estimated from the recorded range in stage, previous or following record, discharge measurements, weather records, and comparison with other station records from the same or nearby basins. Likewise, daily contents may be estimated from operator's logs, previous or following record, inflow-outflow studies, and other information. Information explaining how estimated daily-discharge values are identified in station records is included in the next two sections, "Data Presentation" (REMARKS paragraph) and "Identifying Estimated Daily Discharge."

Data Presentation

Streamflow data in this report are presented in a new format that is considerably different from the format in data reports prior to the 1992 water year. The major changes are that statistical characteristics of discharge now appear in tabular summaries following the water-year data table and less information is provided in the text or station manuscript above the table. These changes represent the results of a pilot program to reformat the annual water-data report to meet current user needs and data preferences.

The records published for each continuous-record surface-water discharge station (gaging station) now consist of four parts, the manuscript or station description; the data table of daily mean values of discharge for the current water year with summary data; a tabular statistical summary of monthly mean flow data for a designated period, by water year; and a summary statistics table that includes statistical data of annual, daily, and instantaneous flows as well as data pertaining to annual runoff, 7-day low-flow minimum, and flow duration.

Station manuscript

The manuscript provides, under various headings, descriptive information, such as station location; period of record; historical extremes outside the period of record; record accuracy; and other remarks pertinent to station operation and regulation. The following information, as appropriate, is provided with each continuous record of discharge or lake content. Comments to follow clarify information presented under the various headings of the stations descriptions.

LOCATION.--Information on locations is obtained from the most accurate maps available. The location of the gage with respect to the cultural and physical features in the vicinity and with respect to the reference place mentioned in the station name is given.

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DRAINAGE AREA.--Drainage areas are measured using the most accurate maps available. Drainage areas are updated as better maps become available.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--This indicates the period for which there are published records for the station or for an equivalent station. An equivalent station is one that was in operation at a time that the present station was not, and whose location was such that records from it can reasonable be considered equivalent with records from the present station.

REVISED RECORDS.--Because of new information, published records occasionally are found to be incorrect, and revisions are printed in later reports. Listed under this heading are all the reports in which revisions have been published for the station and the water years to which the revisions apply. If a revision did not include daily, monthly, or annual figures of discharge, that fact is noted after the year dates as follows: "(M)" means that only the instantaneous maximum discharge was revised; "(m)" that only the instantaneous minimum was revised; and "(P)" that only peak discharges were revised. If the drainage area has been revised, the report in which the most recently revised figure was first published is given.

GAGE.--The type of gage in current use, the datum of the current gage, and a condensed history of the types, locations, and datums of previous gages are given under this heading.

REMARKS.--All periods of estimated daily-discharge record will either be identified by date in this paragraph of the station description for water-discharge stations or flagged in the daily-discharge table. (See next section, "Identifying Estimated Daily Discharge.") If a remarks statement is used to identify estimated record, the paragraph will begin with this information presented as the first entry. The paragraph is also used to present information relative to the accuracy of the records, to special methods of computations, to conditions that affect natural flow at the station and, possibly, to other pertinent items. For reservoir stations, information is given on the dam forming the reservoir, the capacity, outlet works and spillway, and purpose and use of the reservoir.

COOPERATION.--Records provided by a cooperating organization or obtained for the Geological Survey by a cooperating organization are identified here.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Included here is information concerning major floods or unusually low flows that occurred outside the stated period of record. The information may or may not have been obtained by the U.S. Geological Survey.

REVISIONS.--If a critical error in published records is discovered, a revision is included in the first report published following discovery of the error.

Although rare, occasionally the records of a discontinued gaging station may need revision. Because, for these stations, there would be no current or, possibly, future station manuscript published to document the revision in a "Revised Records" entry, users of data for these stations who obtained the record from previously published data reports may wish to contact the District office to determine if the published records were ever revised after the station was discontinued. Of course, if the data were obtained by computer retrieval, the data would be current and there would be no need to check because any published revision of data is always accompanied by revision of the corresponding data in computer storage.

Manuscript information for lake or reservoir stations differs from that for stream stations in the nature of the "Remarks" and in the inclusion of a skeleton stage-capacity table when daily contents are given.

Data table of daily mean value

The daily table of discharge records for stream-gaging stations gives mean discharge for each day of the water year. In the monthly summary for the table, the line headed "TOTAL" gives the sum of the daily figures for each month; the line headed "MEAN" gives the average flow in cubic feet per second for the month; and the lines headed "MAX" and "MIN" give the maximum and minimum daily mean discharges, respectively, for each month. Discharge for the month also is usually expressed in cubic feet per second per square mile (line headed "CFSM"); or in inches (line headed "IN"); or in acre-feet (line headed "AC-FT"). Figures for cubic feet per second per square mile and runoff in inches or in acre-feet may be omitted if there is extensive regulations or diversion or if the drainage area includes large noncontributing areas.

Statistics of monthly mean data

A tabular summary of the mean (line headed "MEAN"), maximum (line headed "MAX"), and minimum (line headed "MIN") of monthly mean flows for each month for a designated period is provided below the mean values table. The water years of the first occurrence of the maximum and minimum monthly flow are provided immediately below those figures. The designated period will be expressed as "FOR WATER YEARS ____-____, BY WATER YEAR (WY)," and will list the first and last water years of the range of years selected from the PERIOD OF RECORD paragraph in the station manuscript. It will consist of all of the station records within the specified water years, including complete months of record for partial water years, if any, and may coincide with the period of record for the station. The water years for which the statistics are computed will be consecutive, unless a break in the station record is indicated in the manuscript.

Summary statistics

A table titled "SUMMARY STATISTICS" follows the statistics of monthly mean data tabulation. This table consists of four columns, with the first column containing the line headings of the statistics being reported. The table provides a statistical summary of yearly, daily, and instantaneous flows, not only for the current water year but also for the previous calendar year and for a designated period, as appropriate. The designated period selected, "WATER YEARS ____-____," will consist of all of the station records within the specified water years, inclusive, including complete months of record for partial water years, if any, and may coincide with the period of record for the station. The water years for which the statistics are computed will be consecutive, unless a break in the station record is indicated in the manuscript. All of the calculations for the statistical characteristics designated ANNUAL (see line headings below.), except for the "ANNUAL 7-DAY MINIMUM" statistic, are calculated for the designated period using complete water years. The other statistical characteristics may be calculated using partial water years.

The date or water year, as appropriate, of the first occurrence of each statistic reporting extreme values of discharge is provided adjacent to the statistic. Repeated occurrences may be noted in the REMARKS paragraph of the manuscript or in footnotes. Because the designated period may not be the same as the station period of record published in the manuscript, occasionally the dates of occurrence listed for the daily and instantaneous extremes in the designated-period column may not be within the selected water years listed in the heading. When this occurs, it will be noted in the REMARKS paragraph or in footnotes. Selected streamflow duration curve statistics and runoff data are also given. Runoff data may be omitted if there is extensive regulation or diversion of flow in the drainage basin.

The following summary statistics data, as appropriate, are provided with each continuous record of discharge. Comments to follow clarify information presented under the various line headings of the summary statistics table.

ANNUAL TOTAL.--The sum of the daily mean values of discharge for the year. At some stations the annual total discharge is adjusted for reservoir storage or diversion. The adjusted figures are identified by a symbol and corresponding footnotes.

ANNUAL MEAN.--The arithmetic mean of the individual daily mean discharges for the year noted or for the designated period. At some stations the yearly mean discharge is adjusted for reservoir storage or diversion. The adjusted figures are identified by a symbol and corresponding footnotes.

HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN.--The maximum annual mean discharge occurring for the designated period.

LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN.--The minimum annual mean discharge occurring for the designated period.

HIGHEST DAILY MEAN.--The maximum daily mean discharge for the year or for the designated period.

LOWEST DAILY MEAN.--The minimum daily mean discharge for the year or for the designated period.

ANNUAL 7-DAY MINIMUM.--The lowest mean discharge for 7 consecutive days for a calendar year or a water year. Note that most low-flow frequency analyses of annual 7-day minimum flows use a climatic year (April 1 - March 31). The date shown in the summary statistics table is the initial date of the 7-day period. (This value should not be confused with the 7-day 10-year low-flow statistics).

INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW.--The maximum instantaneous discharge occurring for the water year or for the designated period. Note that secondary instantaneous peak discharges above a selected base discharge are stored in District computer files for stations meeting certain criteria. Those discharge values may be obtained by writing to the District Office. (See address on back of the title page of this report.)

INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE.--The maximum instantaneous stage occurring for the water year or for the designated period. If the dates of occurrence for the instantaneous peak flow and instantaneous peak stage differ, the REMARKS paragraph in the manuscript or a footnote may be used to provide further information.

INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW.--The minimum instantaneous discharge occurring for the water year or for the designated period.

ANNUAL RUNOFF.--Indicates the total quantity of water in runoff for a drainage area for the year. Data reports may use any of the following units of measurements in presenting annual runoff data:

Acre-foot (AC-FT) is the quantity of water required to cover 1 acre to a depth of 1 foot and is equivalent to 43,560 cubic feet or about 326,000 gallons or 1,233 cubic meters.

Cubic feet per second per square mile (CFSM) is the average number of cubic feet of water flowing per second from each square mile of area drained, assuming the runoff is distributed uniformly in time and area.

Inches (INCHES) indicates the depth to which the drainage area would be covered if all of the runoff for a given time period were uniformly distributed on it.

10 PERCENT EXCEEDS.--The discharge that is exceeded by 10 percent of the flow for the designated period.

50 PERCENT EXCEEDS.--The discharge that is exceeded by 50 percent of the flow for the designated period.

90 PERCENT EXCEEDS.--The discharge that is exceeded by 90 percent of the flow for the designated period.

Data collected at partial-record stations follow the information for continuous-record sites. Data for partial-record discharge stations are presented in a table of discharge measurements at low-flow partial-record stations. These measurements are generally made in times of drought to give better areal coverage to those events. Those measurements and others collected for some special reason are called measurements at miscellaneous sites.

Identifying Estimated Daily Discharge

Estimated daily-discharge values published in the water-discharge tables are identified by flagging individual daily values with the letter symbol "e" and printing a table footnote, "e Estimated."

Accuracy of the Records

The accuracy of streamflow records depends primarily on: (1) The stability of the stage-discharge relation or, if the control is unstable, the frequency of discharge measurements; and (2) the accuracy of measurements of stage, measurements of discharge, and interpretation of records.

The accuracy attributed to the records is indicated under "REMARKS." "Excellent" means that about 95 percent of the daily discharges are within 5 percent of the true; "good," within 10 percent; and "fair," within 15 percent. Records that do not meet the criteria mentioned, are rated "poor." Different accuracies may be attributed to different parts of a given record.

Daily mean discharges in this report are given to the nearest hundredth of a cubic foot per second for values less than 1 ft³/s; to the nearest tenth between 1.0 and 10 ft³/s; to whole numbers between 10 and 1,000 ft³/s; and to 3 significant figures for more than 1,000 ft³/s. The number of significant figures used is based solely on the magnitude of the discharge value. The same rounding rules apply to discharges listed for partial-record stations and miscellaneous sites.

Information used in the preparation of the records in this publication, such as discharge-measurement notes, gage-height records, temperature measurements, and rating tables are on file in the Caribbean District office. Also, most of the daily mean discharges are in computer-readable form and have been analyzed statistically. Information on the availability of the unpublished information or on the results of statistical analyses of the published records may be obtained from the District office.

Records of Surface-Water Quality

Records of surface-water quality ordinarily are obtained at or near stream-gaging stations because interpretation of records of surface-water quality nearly always requires corresponding discharge data. Records of surface-water quality in this report may involve a variety of types of data and measurement frequencies.

Classification of Records

Water-quality data for surface-water sites are grouped into one of three classifications. A continuing-record station is a site where data are collected on a regularly scheduled basis. Frequency may be once or more times daily, weekly, monthly, or quarterly. A partial-record station is a site where limited water-quality data are collected systematically over a period of years. Frequency of sampling is usually less than quarterly. A miscellaneous sampling site is a location other than a continuing or partial-record station, where random samples are collected to give better areal coverage to define water-quality conditions in the river basin.

A careful distinction needs to be made between "continuing records" as used in this report and "continuous recordings," which refers to a continuous graph or a series of discrete values punched at short intervals on a paper tape. Some records of water quality, such as temperature and specific conductance, may be obtained through continuous recordings; however, because of costs, most data are obtained only monthly or less frequently. Locations of stations for which records on the quality of surface water appear in this report are shown in figure 6.

Arrangement of Records

Water-quality records collected at a surface-water daily record station are published immediately following that record, regardless of the frequency of sample collection. Station number and name are the same for both records. Where a surface-water daily record station is not available or where the water quality differs significantly from that at the nearby surface-water station, the continuing water-quality record is published with its own station number and name in the regular downstream-order sequence. Water-quality data for partial-record stations and for miscellaneous sampling sites appear in separate tables following the table of discharge measurement at miscellaneous sites.

On-site Measurements and Sample Collection

In obtaining water-quality data, a major concern needs to be assuring that the data obtained represent the in situ quality of the water. To assure this, certain measurements, such as water temperature, pH, and dissolved oxygen, need to be made onsite when the samples are taken. To assure that measurements made in the laboratory also represent the in situ water, carefully prescribed procedures need to be followed in collecting the samples, in treating the samples to prevent changes in quality pending analysis, and in shipping the samples to the laboratory. Procedures for onsite measurements and for collecting, treating, and shipping samples are given in publications on "Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations," Book 1, Chap. D2; Book 3, Chap. C2; Book 5, Chap. A1, A3, and A4. Detailed information on collecting, treating, and shipping samples may be obtained from the Geological Survey District office.

One sample can define adequately the water quality at a given time if the mixture of solutes throughout the stream cross section is homogeneous. However, the concentration of solutes at different locations in the cross section may vary widely with different rates of water discharge, depending on the source of material and the turbulence and mixing of the stream. Some streams must be sampled through several vertical sections to obtain a representative sample needed for an accurate mean concentration and for use in calculating load. All samples obtained for the National Stream Quality Accounting Network (see definitions) are obtained from at least several verticals. Whether samples are obtained from the centroid of flow or from several verticals, depends on flow conditions and other factors which must be evaluated by the collector.

Chemical-quality data published in this report are considered to be the most representative values available for the stations listed. The values reported represent water-quality conditions at the time of sampling as much as possible, consistent with available sampling techniques and methods of analysis. In the rare case where an apparent inconsistency exists between a reported pH value and the relative abundance of carbon dioxide species (carbonate and bicarbonate), the inconsistency is the result of a slight uptake of carbon dioxide from the air by the sample between measurement of pH in the field and determination of carbonate and bicarbonate in the laboratory.

For chemical-quality stations equipped with digital monitors, the records consist of daily maximum, minimum, and mean values for each constituent measured and are based upon hourly punches beginning at 0100 hours and ending at 2400 hours for the day of record. More detailed records, when available, (hourly values) may be obtained from the U.S.G.S. District office whose address is given on the back of the title page of this report.

Water Temperature

Water temperatures are measured at most of the water-quality stations. In addition, water temperatures are taken at time of discharge measurements for water-discharge stations. For stations where water temperatures are taken manually once or twice daily, the water temperatures are taken at about the same time each day. Large streams have a small diurnal temperature change; shallow streams may have a daily range of several degrees and may follow closely the changes in air temperature. Some streams may be affected by waste-heat discharges.

At stations where recording instruments are used, either mean temperatures or maximum and minimum temperatures for each day are published. Water temperatures measured at the time of water-discharge measurements are on file in the District office.

Sediment

Suspended-sediment concentrations are determined from samples collected by using depth-integrating and pumping sediment samplers. Samples usually are obtained at several verticals in the cross section, or a single sample may be obtained at a fixed point and a coefficient applied to determine the mean concentration in the cross sections.

During periods of rapidly changing flow or rapidly changing concentration, samples may have been collected more frequently (twice daily or hourly). The published sediment discharges for days of rapidly changing flow or concentration were computed by the subdivided-day method (time-discharge weighted average). Therefore, for those days when the published sediment discharge value differs from the value computed as the product of discharge times mean concentration times 0.0027, the reader can assume that the sediment discharge for that day was computed by the subdivided-day method. For periods when no samples were collected, daily discharges of suspended sediment were estimated on the basis of water discharge, sediment concentrations observed immediately before and after the periods, suspended-sediment loads for other periods of similar discharge, and computed by the subdivided-day method using the transport curves.

At other stations, suspended-sediment samples were collected periodically at many verticals in the stream cross section. Although data collected periodically may represent conditions only at the time of observations, such data are useful in establishing seasonal relations between quality and streamflow and in predicting long-term sediment-discharge characteristics of the stream.

In addition to the records of suspended-sediment discharge, records of the periodic measurements of the particle-size distribution of the suspended sediment are included for some stations.

Laboratory Measurements

Sediment samples, samples for biochemical-oxygen demand (BOD), samples for indicator bacteria, and daily samples for specific conductance are analyzed locally. All other samples are analyzed in the Geological Survey laboratories in Denver, Co. or Ocala, Fla. Methods used in analyzing sediment samples and computing sediment records are given in TWRI, Book 5, Chap. C1. Methods used by the Geological Survey laboratories are given in TWRI, Book 1, Chap. D2; Book 3, Chap. C2; Book 5, Chap. A1, A3, and A4.

Data Presentation

For continuing-record stations, information pertinent to the history of station operation is provided in descriptive headings preceding the tabular data. These descriptive headings give details regarding location, drainage area, period of record, type of data available, instrumentation, general remarks, cooperation, and extremes for parameters currently measured daily. Tables of chemical, physical, biological, radiochemical data, and so forth, obtained at a frequency less than daily are presented first, and tables of "daily values" of specific conductance, pH, water temperature, dissolved oxygen, and suspended sediment then follow in sequence, when these parameters are studied.

In the descriptive headings, if the location is identical to that of the discharge gaging station, neither the LOCATION nor the DRAINAGE AREA statements are repeated. The following information, as appropriate, is provided with each continuous-record station. Comments that follow clarify information presented under the various headings of the station description.

LOCATION.--See Data Presentation under "Records of Stage and Water Discharge;" same comments apply.

DRAINAGE AREA.--See Data Presentation under "Records of Stage and Water Discharge;" same comments apply.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--This indicates the periods for which there are published water-quality records for the station. The periods are shown separately for records of parameters measured daily or continuously and those measured less than daily. For those measured daily or continuously, periods of record are given for the parameters individually.

INSTRUMENTATION.--Information on instrumentation is given only if a water-quality monitor temperature record, sediment pumping sampler, or other sampling device is in operation at a station.

REMARKS.--Remarks provide added information pertinent to the collection, analysis, or computation of the records.

COOPERATION.--Records provided by a cooperating organization or obtained for the Geological Survey by a cooperating organization are identified here.

EXTREMES.--Maximums and minimums are given only for parameters measured daily or more frequently. None are given for parameters measured weekly or less frequently, because the true maximums or minimums may not have been sampled. Extremes, when given, are provided for both the period of record and for the current water year.

REVISIONS.--If errors in published water-quality records are discovered after publication, appropriate updates are made to the Water-Quality File in the U.S. Geological Survey's computerized data system, WATSTORE, and subsequently by monthly transfer of update transactions to the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's STORET system. Because the usual volume of updates makes it impractical to document individual changes in the State data-report series or elsewhere, potential users of U.S. Geological Survey water-quality data are encouraged to obtain all required data from the appropriate computer file to insure the most recent updates.

The surface-water-quality records for partial-record stations and miscellaneous sampling sites are published in separate tables following the table of discharge measurements at miscellaneous sites. No descriptive statements are given for these records. Each station is published with its own station number and name in the regular downstream-order sequence.

Remark Codes

The following remark codes may appear with the water-quality data in this report:

<u>PRINTED OUTPUT</u>	<u>REMARK</u>
E	Estimated value
>	Actual value is known to be greater than the value shown
<	Actual value is known to be less than the value shown
K	Results based on colony count outside the acceptance range (non-ideal colony count)
L	Biological organism count less than 0.5 percent (organism may be observed rather than counted)
D	Biological organism count equal to or greater than 15 percent (dominant)
&	Biological organism estimated as dominant

Records of Ground-Water Levels

Only ground-water level data from a basic network of observation wells are published herein. This basic network contains observation wells so located that the most significant data are obtained from the fewest wells in the most important aquifers.

Data Collection and Computation

Measurements of water levels are made in many types of wells under varying conditions, but the methods of measurement are standardized to the extent possible. The equipment and measuring techniques used at each observation well ensure that measurements at each well are of consistent accuracy and reliability.

Each well is identified by means of (1) a 15-digit number that is based on latitude and longitude and (2) a local number that is provided for local needs. See figure 10.

Water-level records are obtained from direct measurements with a steel tape or from the graph or punched tape of a water-stage recorder. The water-level measurements in this report are given in feet with reference to land-surface datum (lsd). Land-surface datum is a datum plane that is approximately at land surface at each well. If known, the elevation of the land-surface datum is given in the well description. The height of the measuring point (MP) above or below land-surface datum is given in each well description. Water levels in wells equipped with recording gages are reported for every day and as an instantaneous observation at noon.

Water levels are reported to as many significant figures as can be justified by the local conditions. For example, in a measurement of a depth to water of several hundred feet, the error of determining the absolute value of the total depth to water may be a few tenths of a foot, whereas the error in determining the net change of water level between successive measurements may be only a hundredth of a few hundredths of a foot. For lesser depths to water, the accuracy is greater. Accordingly, most measurements reported to a hundredth of a foot, but some are given to a tenth of a foot or a larger unit.

Data Presentation

Each well record consists of three parts, the station description, the data table of water levels observed during the water year and a graph of the water levels for the current water year and other selected period. The description of the well is presented first through use of descriptive headings preceding the tabular data. The comments to follow clarify information presented under the various headings of the well description.

LOCATION.--This paragraph follows the well-identification number and reports the latitude and longitude (given in degrees, minutes, and seconds); a landline location designation; the hydrologic-unit number; the distance and direction from a geographic point of reference; and the owner's name.

AQUIFER.--This entry designates by name (if a name exists) and geologic age the aquifer(s) open to the well.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--This entry describes the well in terms of depth, diameter, casing depth and/or screened interval, method of construction, use, and additional information such as casing breaks, collapsed screen, and other changes since construction.

INSTRUMENTATION.--This paragraph provides information on both the frequency of measurement and the collection method used, allowing the user to better evaluate the reported water-level extremes by knowing whether they are based on weekly, monthly, or some other frequency of measurement.

DATUM.--This entry describes both the measuring point and the land-surface elevation at the well. The measuring point is described physically (such as top of collar, notch in top of casing, plug in pump base and so on), and in relation to land surface (such as 1.3 ft above land-surface datum). The elevation of the land-surface datum is described in feet above (or below) sea level; it is reported with a precision depending on the method of determination.

REMARKS.--This entry describes factors that may influence the water level in a well or the measurement of the water level. It should identify wells that also are water-quality observation wells, and may be used to acknowledge the assistance of local (non-Survey) observers.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--This entry indicates the period for which there are published records for the well. It reports the month and year of the start of publication of water-level records by the U.S. Geological Survey and the words "to current year" if the records are to be continued into the following year. Periods for which water-level records are available, but are not published by the Geological Survey, may be noted.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--This entry contains the highest and lowest water levels of the period of published record, with respect to land-surface datum, and the dates of their occurrence.

A table of water levels follows the station description for each well. Water levels are reported in feet below land-surface datum and all taped measurements of water level are listed. For wells equipped with recorders, daily values tables are published for the instantaneous water-level observation at noon. The highest and lowest water levels of the water year and their dates of occurrence are shown on a line below the table. Because all values are not published for wells with recorders, the extremes may be values that are not listed in the table. Missing records are indicated by dashes in place of the water level. A hydrograph for a selected period of record follows each water-level table.

Records of Ground-Water Quality

Records of ground-water quality in this type of report differ from other types of records in that for most sampling sites they consist of only one set of measurements for the water year. The quality of ground water ordinarily changes only slowly; therefore, for most general purposes one annual sampling, or only a few samples taken at infrequent intervals during the year, is sufficient. Frequent measurement of the same constituents is not necessary unless one is concerned with a particular problem, such as monitoring for trends in nitrate concentration. In the special cases where the quality of ground water may change more rapidly, more frequent measurements are made to identify the nature of the changes.

Data Collection and Computation

The records of ground-water quality in this report were obtained mostly as a part of special studies in specific areas. Consequently, a number of chemical analyses are presented for some counties but none are presented for others. As a result, the records for this year, by themselves, do not provide a balanced view of ground-water quality Statewide. Such a view can be attained only by considering records for this year in context with similar records obtained for these and other counties in earlier years.

Most methods for collecting and analyzing water samples are described in the "U.S. Geological Survey Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations" manuals listed on a following page. The values reported in this type of report represent water-quality conditions at the time of sampling as much as possible, consistent with available sampling techniques and methods of analysis. All samples are obtained by trained personnel. The wells sampled are pumped long enough to assure that the water collected comes directly from the aquifer and has not stood for a long time in the well casing where it would have been exposed to the atmosphere and to the material, possibly metal, comprising the casings.

Data Presentation

The records of ground-water quality, when available, are published in a section titled QUALITY OF GROUND WATER immediately following the ground-water level records. Data for quality of ground water are listed alphabetically by County, and are identified by well number. The prime identification number for wells sampled is the 15-digit number derived from the latitude-longitude locations. No descriptive statements are given for ground-water-quality records; however, the well number, depth of well, date of sampling, and other pertinent data are given in the table containing the chemical analyses of the ground water. The REMARK codes listed for surface-water-quality records are also applicable to ground-water-quality records.

ACCESS TO WATSTORE DATA

The U.S. Geological Survey is the principal Federal water-data agency and, as such, collects and disseminates about 70 percent of the water data currently being used by numerous State, local, private, and other Federal agencies to develop and manage our water resources. As part of the U.S. Geological Survey's program of releasing water data to the public, a large-scale computerized system has been developed for the storage and retrieval of water data collected through its activities. The National Water-Data Storage and Retrieval System (WATSTORE) was established in 1972 to provide an effective and efficient means for the processing and maintenance of water data collected through the activities of the U.S. Geological Survey and to facilitate release of the data to the public. A variety of useful products, ranging from data tables to complex statistical analyses such as Log Pearson Type III, can be produced using WATSTORE. The system resides on the central computer facilities of the U.S. Geological Survey at its National Center in Reston, Virginia, and consists of related files and data bases.

* Station Header File - Contains descriptive information on over 440,000 sites throughout the United States and its territories where the U.S. Geological Survey collects or has collected data.

* Daily Values Files - Contains over 220 million daily values of streamflow, stages, reservoir contents, water temperatures, specific conductances, sediment concentrations, sediment discharges, and ground-water level.

* Peak Flow File - Contains approximately 500,000 maximum (peak) streamflow and gage-height values at surface-water sites.

* Water-Quality Data - Contains approximately 2 million analyses of water samples that describe the chemical, physical, biological, and radio-chemicals characteristics of both surface and ground water.

* Ground-Water Site Inventory Data Base - Contains inventory data for over 900,000 wells, springs, and other sources of ground water. The data includes site location, geohydrologic characteristics, well-construction history, and one-time field measurements such as water temperature.

In 1976, the U.S. Geological Survey opened WATSTORE to the public for direct access. The signing of a Memorandum of Agreement with the Survey is required to obtain direct access to WATSTORE. The system can be accessed either synchronously or asynchronously. The requestor will be expected to pay all computer costs he/she incurs. Direct access may be obtained by contacting:

U.S. Geological Survey
National Water Data Exchange
421 USGS National Center
Reston, Virginia 22092

In addition to providing direct access to WATSTORE, data can be provided in various machine-readable formats on magnetic tape or 5-1/4 inch floppy disk; and, as noted in the introduction, on CD-ROM discs. Beginning with the 1990 water year, all water-data reports will also be available on Compact Disc-Read Only Memory (CD-ROM). All data report published for the current water year for the entire Nation, including Puerto Rico and the Trust Territories, will be reproduced on a single CD-ROM disc. Information about the availability of specific types of data or products, and user charges, can be obtained locally from each of the Water Resources Division's offices. (See address on the back of the title page). A limited number of CD-ROM discs will be available for sale by the Books and Open-File Reports Section, U.S. Geological Survey, Federal Center, Box 25425, Denver, Colorado 80225.

DEFINITION OF TERMS

Terms related to streamflow, water-quality, and other hydrologic data as used in this report, are defined below. See also the table for converting inch- pound units to the International System of units (SI) on the inside of the back cover.

Acre-foot (AC-FT, acre-ft) is the quantity of water required to cover 1 acre to a depth of 1 foot and is equal to about 326,000 gallons or 1,233 cubic meters.

Adenosine triphosphate (ATP) is an organic, phosphate-rich, compound important in the transfer of energy in organisms. Its central role in living cells makes it an excellent indicator of the presence of living material in water. A measure of ATP therefore provides a sensitive and rapid estimate of biomass. ATP is reported in micrograms per liter of the original water sample.

Algae growth potential (AGP) is the maximum algal dry weight biomass that can be produced in a natural water sample under standardized laboratory conditions. The growth potential is the algal biomass present a stationary phase and is expressed as milligrams dry weight of algae produced per liter of sample.

Aquifer is a geologic formation, group of formations, or part of a formation that contains sufficient saturated permeable material to yield significant quantities of water to wells and springs.

Artesian means confined and is used to describe a well in which the water level stands above the top of the aquifer, tapped by the well. A flowing artesian well is one in which the water level is above the land surface.

Bacteria are microscopic unicellular organisms, typically spherical, rodlike, or spiral and threadlike in shape, often clumped into colonies. Some bacteria cause disease, while others perform an essential role in nature in the recycling of materials; for example, by decomposing organic matter into a form available for reuse by plants.

Total coliform bacteria are a particular group of bacteria that are used as indicators of possible sewage pollution. They are characterized as aerobic or facultative anaerobic, gram-negative, nonspore-forming, rod-shaped bacteria which ferment lactose with gas formation within 48 hours at 35°C. In the laboratory these bacteria are defined as all the organisms which produce colonies with a golden-green metallic sheen within 24 hours when incubated at 35°C \pm 1.0°C on M-Endo medium (nutrient medium for bacterial growth). Their concentrations are expressed as number of colonies per 100 mL of sample.

Fecal coliform bacteria are bacteria that are present in the intestines or feces of warm-blooded animals. They are often used as indicators of the sanitary quality of the water. In the laboratory they are defined as all organisms which produce blue colonies within 24 hours when incubated at $44.5^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.2^{\circ}\text{C}$ on M-FC medium (nutrient medium for bacterial growth). Their concentrations are expressed as number of colonies per 100 mL of sample.

Fecal streptococcal bacteria are bacteria found also in intestines of warm-blooded animals. Their presence in water is considered to verify fecal pollution. They are characterized as Gram-positive, cocci bacteria which are capable of growth in brain-heart infusion broth. In the laboratory they are defined as all the organisms which produce red or pink colonies within 48 hours at $35^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ on KF-streptococcus medium (nutrient medium for bacterial growth). Their concentrations are expressed as number of colonies per 100 mL of sample.

Bed material is the unconsolidated material of which a streambed, lake, pond, reservoir, or estuary bottom is composed.

Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) is a measure of the quantity of dissolved oxygen, in milligrams per liter, necessary for the decomposition of organic matter by microorganisms, such as bacteria.

Biomass is the amount of living matter present at any given time, expressed as the mass per unit area or volume of habitat.

Ash mass is the mass or amount of residue present after the residue from the dry mass determination has been ashed in a muffle furnace at a temperature of 500°C for 1 hour. The ash mass values of zooplankton and phytoplankton are expressed in grams per cubic meter (g/m^3), and periphyton and benthic organisms in grams per square meter (g/m^2).

Dry mass refers to the mass of residue present after drying in an oven at 105°C for zooplankton and periphyton, until the mass remains unchanged. This mass represents the total organic matter, ash and sediment, in the sample. Dry-mass values are expressed in the same units as ash mass.

Organic mass or volatile mass of the living substance is the difference between the dry mass and the ash mass and represents the actual matter. The organic mass is expressed in the same units as for ash and dry mass.

Wet mass is the mass of living matter plus contained water.

Bottom material: See Bed material.

Cells/volume refers to the number of cells of any organism which is counted by using a microscope and grid or counting cell. Many planktonic organisms are multicelled and are counted according to the number of contained cells per sample, usually milliliters (mL) or liters (L).

Chemical oxygen demand (COD) is a measure of the chemically oxidizable material in the water, and furnishes an approximation of the amount of organic and reducing material present. The determined value may correlate with natural water color or with carbonaceous organic pollution from sewage or industrial wastes.

Chlorophyll refers to the green pigments of plants. Chlorophyll a and b are the two most common green pigments in plants.

Color unit is produced by one milligram per liter of platinum in the form of the chloroplatinate ion. Color is expressed in units of the platinum-cobalt scale.

Contents is the volume of water in a reservoir or lake. Unless otherwise indicated, volume is computed on the basis of a level pool and does not include bank storage.

Control designates a feature downstream from the gage that determines the stage-discharge relation at the gage. This feature may be a natural constriction of the channel, an artificial structure, or a uniform cross section over a long reach of the channel.

Control structure as used in this report is a structure on a stream or canal that is used to regulate the flow or stage of the stream or to prevent the intrusion of salt water.

Cubic foot per second (ft³/s) is the rate of discharge representing a volume of 1 cubic foot passing a given point during 1 second and is equivalent to 7.48 gallons per second or 448.8 gallons per minute or 0.02832 cubic meters per second.

Cubic foot per second-day (ft³/s/day) is the volume of water represented by a flow of 1 cubic foot per second for 24 hours. It is equivalent to 86,400 cubic feet, approximately 1.9835 acre-feet, about 646,000 gallons, or 2,445 cubic meters.

Cubic feet per second per square mile (CFSM) is the average number of cubic feet of water flowing per second from each square mile of area drained, assuming that the runoff is distributed uniformly in time and area.

Discharge is the volume of water (or more broadly, volume of fluid plus suspended sediment), that passes a given point within a given period of time.

Instantaneous discharge is the discharge at a particular instant of time.

Mean discharge (MEAN) is the arithmetic mean of individual daily mean discharges during a specific period.

Annual 7-day minimum is the lowest mean discharge for 7 consecutive days for a calendar year or a water year. Note that most low-flow frequency analyses of annual 7-day minimum flows use a climatic year (April 1 - March 31). The date shown in the summary statistics table is the initial date of the 7-day period. (This value should not be confused with the 7-day 10-year low-flow statistic.)

Dissolved refers to that material in a representative water sample which passes through a 0.45 um membrane filter. This is a convenient operational definition used by Federal agencies that collect water data. Determinations of "dissolved" constituents are made on subsamples of the filtrate.

Dissolved-solids concentration of water is determined either analytically by the "residue-on-evaporation" method, or mathematically by totaling the concentrations of individual constituents reported in a comprehensive chemical analysis. During the analytical determination of dissolved solids, the bicarbonate (generally a major dissolved component of water) is converted to carbonate. Therefore, in the mathematical calculations of dissolved-solids concentration, the bicarbonate value, in milligrams per liter, is multiplied by 0.492 to reflect the change.

Diversity index is a numerical expression of evenness of distribution of aquatic organisms. The formula for diversity index is:

$$d = - \sum_{i=1}^s \frac{n_i}{n} \log_2 \frac{n_i}{n}$$

Where n_i is the number of individuals per taxon, n is the total number of individuals, and s is the total number of taxa in the sample of the community. Diversity index values range from zero, when all the organisms in the sample are the same, to some positive number, when some or all of the organisms in the sample are different.

Drainage area of a stream at a specified location is that area, measured in a horizontal plane, enclosed by a topographic divide from which direct surface runoff from precipitation normally drains by gravity into the stream above the specified point. Figures of drainage area given herein include all closed basins, or noncontribution areas, within the area unless otherwise noted.

Drainage basin is a part of the surface of the earth that is occupied by a drainage system, which consists of a surface stream or a body of impounded surface water together with all tributary surface streams and bodies of impounded surface water.

Gage height (G.H.) is the water-surface elevation referred to some arbitrary gage datum. Gage height is often used interchangeably with the more general term "stage," although gage height is more appropriate when used with a reading on a gage.

Gaging station is a particular site on a stream, canal, lake, or reservoir where systematic observations of hydrologic data are obtained.

Ground-water station is a well at which observations of ground-water level are made, either continuously by recorder, or periodically by hand. In addition, various chemical or physical parameters may be obtained, usually on a periodic basis.

Hardness of water is a physical-chemical characteristic that is commonly recognized by the increased quantity of soap required to produce lather. It is attributable to the presence of alkaline earths (principally calcium and magnesium) and is expressed as equivalent calcium carbonate (CaCO_3).

Hydrologic Bench-Mark Network is a network in small drainage basins around the country whose purpose is to provide consistent data on the hydrology, including water quality, and related factors in representative undeveloped watersheds nationwide, and to provide analyses on a continuing basis to compare and contrast conditions observed in basins more obviously affected by the activities of man.

Hydrologic unit is a geographic area representing part or all of a surface drainage basin or distinct hydrologic feature as delineated by the Office of Water Data Coordination on the State Hydrologic Unit Maps; each hydrologic unit is identified by an eight-digit number.

Land-surface datum (lsd) is a datum plane that is approximately at land surface at each ground-water observation well.

Measuring point (MP) is an arbitrary permanent reference point from which the distance to the water surface in a well is measured to obtain the water level.

Metamorphic stage refers to the stage of development that an organism exhibits during its transformation from an immature form to an adult form. This developmental process exists for most insects, and the degree of difference from the immature stage to the adult form varies from relatively slight to pronounced, with many intermediates. Examples of metamorphic stages of insects are egg-larva-adult or egg-nymph-adult.

Methylene blue active substances (MBAS) are apparent detergents. The determination depends on the formation of a blue color when methylene blue dye reacts with synthetic anionic detergent compounds.

Micrograms per gram ($\mu\text{g/g}$) is a unit expressing the concentration of a chemical element as the mass (micrograms) of the element per unit mass (gram) of material analyzed.

Micrograms per liter ($\mu\text{g/L}$, $\mu\text{g/L}$) is a unit expressing the concentration of chemical constituents in solution as mass (micrograms) of solute per unit volume (liter) of water. One thousand micrograms per liter is equivalent to one milligram per liter.

Milligrams per liter (MG/L , mg/L) is a unit for expressing the concentration of chemical constituents in solution. Milligrams per liter represent the mass of solute per unit volume (liter) of water. Concentration of suspended sediment also is expressed in mg/L , and is based on the mass of sediment per liter of water-sediment mixture. Conversion of chemical concentrations in Mg/L to milliequivalents per liter can be done by using the factors in table 4.

Table 4. Factors for conversion of chemical constituents in milligrams per liter to milliequivalents per liter.

<u>Ion</u>	<u>Multiply by</u>	<u>Ion</u>	<u>Multiply by</u>
Aluminum (Al+3)*.....	0.11119	Iodide (I-1).....	0.00788
Ammonia as NH ₄ +1.....	.05544	Iron (Fe+3).....	.05372
Barium (Ba+2).....	.01456	Lead (Pb+2).....	.00965
Bicarbonate (HCO ₃ -1)....	.01639	Lithium (Li+1).....	.14411
Bromide (Br-1).....	.01251	Magnesium (Mg+2).....	.08226
Calcium (Ca+2).....	.04990	Manganese (Mn+2)*....	.03640
Carbonate (CO ₃ -2).....	.03333	Nickel (Ni+2).....	.03406
Chloride (Cl-1).....	.02821	Nitrate (NO ₃ -1).....	.01613
Chromium (Cr+6)*.....	.11539	Nitrite (NO ₂ -1).....	.02174
Cobalt (Co+2)*.....	.03394	Phosphate (PO ₄ -3)....	.03159
Copper (Cu+2)*.....	.03148	Potassium (K+1).....	.02557
Cyanide (CN-1).....	.03844	Sodium (NA+1).....	.04350
Fluoride (F-1).....	.05264	Strontium (Sr+2).....	.02283
Hydrogen (H+1).....	.99209	Sulfate (SO ₄ -2).....	.02082
Hydroxide (OH-1).....	.05880	Zinc (Zn+2)*.....	.03060

*Constituent reported in micrograms per liter; multiply by factor and divide results by 1,000.

National Stream Quality Accounting Network (NASQAN) is a nationwide data-collection network designed by the U.S. Geological Survey to meet many of the information needs of government agencies and other groups involved in natural or regional water-quality planning and management. The 500 or so sites in NASQAN are generally located at the downstream ends of hydrologic accounting units designated by the U.S. Geological Survey office of Water Data Coordination in consultation with the Water Resources Council. The objectives of NASQAN are (1) to obtain information on the quality and quantity of water moving within and from the United States through a systematic and uniform process of data collection, summarization, analysis, and reporting such that the data may be used for, (2) description of the areal variability of water quality in the Nation's rivers through analysis of description of the areal variability of water quality in the Nation's rivers through analysis of data from this and other programs, (3) detection of changes or trends with time in the pattern of occurrence of water-quality characteristics, and (4) providing a nationally consistent data base useful for water-quality assessment and hydrologic research.

National Trends Network (NTN) is a network for sampling atmospheric deposition in the United States. The purpose of the network is to determine the variability, both in location and in time, of the composition of atmospheric deposition, which includes snow, rain, dust particles, aerosols, and gases. The core from which the NTN was built was the already-existing deposition-monitoring network of the National Atmospheric Deposition Program (NADP).

Organism is any living entity.

Organism count/area refers to the number of organisms collected and enumerated in a sample and adjusted to the number per unit area habitat, usually square meters (m²), acres, or hectare. Periphyton, benthic organisms, and macrophytes are expressed in these terms.

Organism count/volume refers to the number of organisms collected and enumerated in a sample and adjusted to the number per sample volume, usually milliliters (mL) or liters (L). Numbers of planktonic organisms can be expressed in these terms.

Total organism count is the total number of organisms collected and enumerated in any particular sample.

Parameter Code is a 5-digit number used in the U.S. Geological Survey computerized data system, WATSTORE, to uniquely identify a specific constituent. The codes used in WATSTORE are the same as those used in the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency data system, STORET. The Environmental Protection Agency assigns and approves all requests for new codes.

Partial-record station is a particular site where limited streamflow and/or water-quality data are collected systematically over a period of years for use in hydrologic analyses.

Particle-size is the diameter, in millimeters (mm), of a particle determined by either sieve or sedimentation methods. Sedimentation methods (pipet, bottom-withdrawal tube, visual-accumulation tube) determine fall diameter of particles in either distilled water (chemically dispersed) or in native water (the river water at the time and point of sampling).

Particle-size classification used in this report agrees with recommendations made by the American Geophysical Union Subcommittee on Sediment Terminology. The classification is as follows:

<u>Classification</u>	<u>Size (mm)</u>	<u>Method of analysis</u>
Clay.....	0.00024 - 0.004	Sedimentation
Silt.....	.004 - .062	Sedimentation
Sand.....	.062 - 2.0	Sedimentation or sieve
Gravel....	2.0 - 64.0	Sieve

The particle-size distributions given in this report are not necessarily representative of all particles in transport in the stream. Most of the organic matter is removed and the sample is subjected to mechanical and chemical dispersion before analysis in distilled water. Chemical dispersion is not used for native water analysis.

Percent composition is a unit for expressing the ratio of a particular part of a sample or population to the total sample or population, in terms of types, numbers, mass or volume.

Periphyton is the assemblage of microorganisms attached to and living upon submerged solid surfaces. While primarily consisting of algae, they also include bacteria, fungi, protozoa, rotifers, and other small organisms.

Pesticides are chemical compounds used to control undesirable organisms. Major categories of pesticides include insecticides, miticides, fungicides, herbicides, and rodenticides.

Picocurie (PC, pCi) is one trillionth (1×10^{-12}) of the amount of radioactivity represented by a curie (Ci). A curie is the amount of radioactivity that yields 3.7×10^{10} radioactive disintegrations per second. A picocurie yields 2.22 dpm (disintegrations per minute).

Plankton is the community of suspended, floating, or weakly swimming organisms that live in the open water of lakes and rivers.

Phytoplankton is the plant part of the plankton. They are usually microscopic and their movement is subject to the water currents. Phytoplankton growth is dependent upon solar radiation and nutrient substances. Because they are able to incorporate as well as release materials to the surrounding water, the phytoplankton have a profound effect upon the quality of the water. They are the primary food producers in the aquatic environment, and are commonly known as algae.

Blue-green algae are a group of phytoplankton organisms having a blue pigment, in addition to the green pigment called chlorophyll. Blue-green algae often cause nuisance conditions in water.

Diatoms are the unicellular or colonial algae having a siliceous shell. Their concentrations are expressed as number of cells per milliliter (cells/mL) of sample.

Green algae have chlorophyll pigments similar in color to those of higher green plants. Some forms produce algae mats or floating "moss" in lakes. Their concentrations are expressed as number of cells per milliliter (cells/mL) of sample.

Zooplankton is the animal part of the plankton. Zooplankton are capable of extensive movements within the water column and are often large enough to be seen with the unaided eye. Zooplankton are secondary consumers feeding upon bacteria, phytoplankton, and detritus. Because they are the grazers in the aquatic environment, the zooplankton are a vital part of the aquatic food web. The zooplankton community is dominated by small crustaceans and rotifers.

Primary productivity is a measure of the rate at which new organic matter is formed and accumulated through photosynthetic and chemosynthetic activity of producer organisms (chiefly, green plants). The rate of primary production is estimated by measuring the amount of oxygen released (oxygen method) or the amount of carbon assimilated by the plants (carbon method).

Milligrams of carbon per area or volume per unit time [mg C/(m².time)] for periphyton and macrophytes and [mg C/(m³.time)] for phytoplankton are units for expressing primary productivity. They define the amount of carbon dioxide consumed as measured by radioactive carbon (carbon 14). The carbon 14 method is of greater sensitivity than the oxygen light and dark bottle method, and is preferred for use in unenriched waters. Unit time may be either hour or day, depending on the incubation period.

Milligrams of oxygen per area or volume per unit time [mgO / (m².time)] for periphyton and macrophytes and [mgO / (m³.time)] for phytoplankton are the units for expressing primary productivity. They define production and respiration rates as estimated from changes in the measured dissolved-oxygen concentration. The oxygen light and dark bottle method is preferred if the rate of primary production is sufficient for accurate measurements to be made within 24 hours. Unit time may be either the hour or day, depending on the incubation period.

Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) are industrial chemicals that are mixtures of chlorinated biphenyl compounds having various percentages of chlorine. They are similar in structure to organochlorine insecticides.

Radiochemical program is a network of regularly sampled water-quality stations where samples are collected to be analyzed for radioisotopes. The streams that are sampled represent major drainage basins in the conterminous United States.

Recoverable from bottom material is the amount of a given constituent that is in solution after a representative sample of bottom material has been digested by a method (usually using an acid or mixture of acids) that results in dissolution of readily soluble substances. Complete dissolution of all bottom material is not achieved by the digestion treatment and thus the determination represents less than the total amount (that is, less than 95 percent) of the constituent in the sample. To achieve comparability of analytical data, equivalent digestion procedures would be required of all laboratories performing such analyses because different digestion procedures are likely to produce different analytical results.

Return period is the average time interval between occurrences of a hydrological event of a given or greater magnitude, usually expressed in years. May also be called recurrence interval.

Runoff in inches (IN, in) shows the depth to which the drainage area would be covered if all the runoff for a given time period were uniformly distributed on it.

Sediment is solid material that originates mostly from disintegrated rocks and is transported by, suspended in, or deposited from water; it includes chemical and biochemical precipitates and decomposed organic material, such as humus. The quantity, characteristics, and cause of the occurrence of sediment in streams are influenced by environmental factors. Some major factors are degree of slope, length of slope, soil characteristics, land usage, and quantity and intensity of precipitation.

Bed load is the sediment that is transported in a stream by rolling, sliding, or skipping along the bed and very close to it. In this report, bed load is considered to consist of particles in transit within 0.25 ft of the streambed.

Bed load discharge (tons per day) is the quantity of bed load measured by dry weight that moves past a section as bed load in a given time.

Suspended sediment is the sediment that at any given time is maintained in suspension by the upward components of turbulent currents or that exists in suspension as a colloid.

Suspended-sediment concentration is the velocity-weighted concentration of suspended sediment in the sampled zone (from the water surface to a point approximately 0.3 ft above the bed) expressed as milligrams of dry sediment per liter of water-sediment mixture (mg/L).

Mean concentration is the time-weighted concentration of suspended sediment passing a stream section during a 24-hour day.

Suspended-sediment discharge (tons/day) is the rate at which dry mass of sediment passes a section of a stream or is the quantity of sediment, as measured by dry mass or volume, that passes a section in a given time. It is calculated in units of tons per day as follows: concentrations (mg/L) x discharge (ft³/s) x 0.0027.

Suspended-sediment load is a general term that refers to material in suspension. It is not synonymous with either discharge or concentration.

Total sediment discharge (tons/day) is the sum of the suspended-sediment discharge and the bed-load discharge. It is the total quantity of sediment, as measured by dry mass or volume, that passes a section during a given time.

Total-sediment load or total load is a term which refers to the total sediment (bed load plus suspended-sediment load) that is in transport. It is not synonymous with total-sediment discharge.

7-day 10-year low flow (7Q10) is the discharge at the 10-year recurrence interval taken from a frequency curve of annual values of the lowest mean discharge for 7 consecutive days (the 7-day low flow).

Sodium-adsorption-ratio (SAR) is the expression of relative activity of sodium ions in exchange reactions within soil and is an index of sodium or alkali hazard to the soil. Waters range in respect to sodium hazard from those which can be used for irrigation on almost all soils to those which are generally unsatisfactory for irrigation.

Solute is any substance that is dissolved in water.

Specific conductance is a measure of the ability of a water to conduct an electric current. It is expressed in microsiemens per centimeter at 25°C. Specific conductance is related to the type and concentration of ions in solution and can be used for approximating the dissolved-solids content of the water. Commonly, the concentration of dissolved solids (in milligrams per liter) is about 65 percent of the specific conductance (in micromhos). This relation is not constant from stream to stream, and it may vary in the same source with changes in the composition of the water.

Stage-discharge relation is the relation between gage height (stage) and volume of water per unit of time, flowing in a channel.

Streamflow is the discharge that occurs in a natural channel. Although the term "discharge" can be applied to the flow of a canal, the word "streamflow" uniquely describes the discharge in a surface stream course. The term "streamflow" is more general than "runoff" as streamflow may be applied to discharge whether or not it is affected by diversion or regulation.

Substrate is the physical surface upon which an organism lives.

Natural substrate refers to any naturally occurring emersed or submersed solid surface, such as a rock or tree, upon which an organism lives.

Artificial substrate is a device which is purposely placed in a stream or lake for colonization of organisms. The artificial substrate simplifies the community structure by standardizing the substrate from which each sample is taken. Examples of artificial substrates are basket samplers (made of wire cages filled with clean streamside rocks) and multiplate samplers (made of hardboard) for benthic organism collection, and plexiglass strips for periphyton.

Surface area of a lake is that area outlined on the latest U.S.G.S. topographic map as the boundary of the lake and measured by a planimeter in acres. In localities not covered by topographic maps, the areas are computed from the best maps available at the time planimeted. All areas shown are those for the stage when the planimeted map was made.

Surficial bed material is that part (0.1 to 0.2 ft) of the bed material that is sampled using U.S. Series Bed-Material Samplers.

Suspended (as used in tables of chemical analyses) refers to the amount (concentration) of the total concentration in a water-sediment mixture. It is associated with the material retained on a 0.45-micrometer filter.

Suspended, recoverable is the amount of a given constituent that is in solution after the part of a representative water-suspended sediment sample that is retained on a 0.45 um membrane filter has been digested by a method (usually using a dilute acid solution) that results in dissolution of only readily soluble substances. Complete dissolution of all the particulate matter is not achieved by the digestion treatment and thus the determination represents something less than the "total" amount (that is, less than 95 percent) of the constituent present in the sample. To achieve comparability of analytical data, equivalent digestion procedures are required of all laboratories performing such analyses because different digestion procedures are likely to produce different analytical results.

Determinations of "suspended, recoverable" constituents are made either by analyzing portions of the material collected on the filter or, more commonly, by difference, based on determinations of (1) dissolved and (2) total recoverable concentrations of the constituent.

Suspended, total is the total amount of a given constituent in the part of representative water-suspended sediment sample that is retained on a 0.45 um membrane filter. This term is used only when the analytical procedure assures measurement of at least 95 percent of the constituent determined. A knowledge of the expected form of the constituent in the sample, as well as the analytical methodology used, is required to determine when the results should be reported as "suspended, total."

Determinations of "suspended, total" constituents are made either by analyzing portions of the material collected on the filter or, more commonly, by difference, based on determinations of (1) dissolved and (2) total concentrations of the constituent.

Taxonomy is the division of biology concerned with the classification and naming of organisms. The classification of organisms is based upon a hierarchial scheme beginning with Kingdom and ending with Species at the base. The higher the classification level, the fewer features the organisms have in common. For example, the taxonomy of a particular mayfly, Hexagenia limbata, is the following:

Kingdom.....	Animal
Phylum.....	Arthropoda
Class.....	Insecta
Order.....	Ephemeroptera
Family.....	Ephemeridae
<u>Genus.....</u>	<u>Hexagenia</u>
<u>Species.....</u>	<u>Hexagenia limbata</u>

Thermograph is an instrument that continuously records variations of temperature on a chart. The more general term "temperature recorder" is used in the table heading and refers to any instrument that records temperature whether on a chart, a tape, or any other medium.

Time-weighted average is computed by multiplying the number of days in the sampling period by the concentrations of individual constituents for the corresponding period and dividing the sum of the products by the total number of days. A time-weighted average represents the composition of water that would be contained in a vessel or reservoir that had received equal quantities of water from the stream each day for the year.

Tons per acre-foot indicates the dry mass of dissolved solids in 1 acre-foot of water. It is computed by multiplying the concentration of the constituent, in milligrams per liter by 0.00136.

Tons per day (T/DAY) is the quantity of a substance in solution or suspension that passes a stream section during a 24-hour period.

Total is the total amount of a given constituent in a representative water-suspended sediment sample, regardless of the constituent's physical or chemical form. This term is used only when the analytical procedure assures measurement of at least 95 percent of the constituent present in both the dissolved and suspended phases of the sample. A knowledge of the expected form of the constituent in the sample, as well as the analytical methodology used, is required to judge when the results should be reported as "total." (Note that the word "total" does double duty here, indicating both that the sample consists of a water-suspended sediment mixture and that the analytical method determined all of the constituent in the sample.)

Total discharge is the total quantity of any individual constituent, as measured by dry mass or volume, that passes through a stream cross-section per unit of time. This term needs to be qualified, such as "total sediment discharge," "total chloride discharge," and so on.

Total, recoverable is the amount of a given constituent that is in solution after a representative water-suspended sediment sample has been digested by a method (usually using a dilute acid solution) that results in dissolution of only readily soluble substances. Complete dissolution of all particulate matter is not achieved by the digestion treatment, and thus the determination represents something less than the "total" amount (that is, less than 95 percent) of the constituent present in the dissolved and suspended phases of the sample. To achieve comparability of analytical data, equivalent digestion procedures are required of all laboratories performing such analyses, because different digestion procedures are likely to produce different analytical results.

Tritium Network is a network of stations which has been established to provide baseline information on the occurrence of tritium in the Nation's surface waters. In addition to the surface-water stations in the network, tritium data are also obtained at a number of precipitation stations. The purpose of the precipitation stations is to provide an estimate sufficient for hydrologic studies of the tritium input to the United States.

Water year in Geological Survey reports dealing with surface water supply is the 12-month period, October 1 through September 30. The water year is designated by the calendar year in which it ends and which includes 9 of the 12 months. Thus, the year ending September 30, 1980, is called the "1980 water year."

WDR is used as an abbreviation for "Water-Data Report" in the REVISED RECORDS paragraph to refer to State annual hydrologic-data reports (WRD was used as an abbreviation for "Water-Resources Data" in reports published prior to 1976).

Weighted average is used in this report to indicate discharge-weighted average. It is computed by multiplying the discharge for a sampling period by the concentrations of individual constituents for the corresponding period and dividing the sum of the products by the sum of the discharges. A discharge-weighted average approximates the composition of water that would be found in a reservoir containing all the water passing a given location during the water year after thorough mixing in the reservoir.

WSP is used as an abbreviation for "Water-Supply Paper" in references to previously published reports.

The U.S. Geological Survey publishes a series of manuals describing procedures for planning and conducting specialized work in water-resources investigations. The material is grouped under major subject headings called books and is further divided into sections and chapters. For example, Section A of Book 3 (Applications of Hydraulics) pertains to surface water. The chapter, the unit of publication, is limited to a narrow field of subject matter. This format permits flexibility in revision and publication as the need arises.

The reports listed below are for sale by the U.S. Geological Survey, Books and Open-File Reports Section, Federal Center, Box 25425, Denver, Colorado 80225 (authorized agent of the Superintendent of Documents, Government Printing Office). Prepayment is required. Remittance should be sent by check or money order payable to the U.S. Geological Survey. Prices are not included because they are subject to change. Current prices can be obtained by writing to the above address. When ordering or inquiring about prices for any of these publications, please give the title, book number, chapter number, and "U.S. Geological Survey Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations."

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**Surface and Quality-of-Water
Records
for Puerto Rico**

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Figure 13.--Río Guajataca basin.

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50010500 RIO GUAJATACA AT LARES, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'01", long 66°52'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010001 at bridge on Highway 111, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from Quebrada Anón, and 0.4 mi (0.6 km) east of Lares.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.16 mi² (8.18 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1959 to February 1962 (annual low-flow measurements only), January 1963 to April 1969 (monthly measurements only), May 1969 to December 1970 (February to May 1971 and March 1974 to November 1989, monthly measurements only), December 1989 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 935 ft (285 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. Small diversion above station for sewage treatment plant; effluent re-enters stream below station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	22	29	4.5	1.9	5.6	1.1	e3.7	3.1	14	3.1	2.3	12
2	12	17	3.9	1.6	2.5	1.4	3.0	4.1	9.7	3.1	2.3	3.9
3	7.9	13	4.0	1.6	2.0	1.1	3.4	42	9.0	3.0	2.4	1.7
4	6.3	12	3.3	1.4	1.7	1.3	2.3	12	7.4	3.0	2.2	2.4
5	5.9	10	3.0	1.6	1.8	.92	1.9	5.3	7.1	2.6	2.0	16
6	5.4	9.2	2.8	1.4	1.6	.88	3.6	35	7.7	2.7	3.1	30
7	5.0	8.2	2.6	1.4	1.6	.82	1.8	48	5.5	2.3	2.4	37
8	5.3	7.6	2.4	1.4	1.6	.76	1.9	24	9.8	2.7	1.9	14
9	4.5	7.1	2.4	1.2	1.5	.82	1.5	17	22	2.2	1.9	6.1
10	14	7.1	2.7	1.1	1.5	.82	1.5	10	7.1	2.2	2.2	8.7
11	6.6	6.4	2.2	1.1	1.5	e.90	12	7.9	8.9	2.3	3.2	4.2
12	4.9	5.9	2.1	1.1	1.5	e1.2	3.9	6.5	13	2.7	2.0	3.0
13	4.4	5.7	11	1.1	1.4	e.80	19	4.9	8.3	2.0	1.7	3.6
14	4.0	11	7.8	1.0	1.4	e.84	11	4.8	5.8	2.7	1.6	2.2
15	3.8	7.2	4.7	1.1	1.3	e.86	20	4.3	5.0	2.8	1.5	1.9
16	23	5.8	2.5	1.1	1.3	e.82	6.2	15	5.6	3.3	14	1.5
17	23	5.8	2.8	1.2	1.4	e.86	11	6.2	4.6	3.2	2.6	1.4
18	33	12	2.4	1.2	1.3	e.85	18	4.8	4.3	2.7	2.1	1.5
19	27	5.7	2.2	1.2	1.3	e.83	5.1	4.3	7.6	2.8	6.3	6.1
20	19	4.6	3.0	1.1	2.3	e.80	7.2	6.0	5.4	2.7	2.0	1.8
21	14	4.4	2.7	1.7	1.7	e.82	14	3.5	4.3	2.5	1.8	1.0
22	14	4.3	2.7	2.0	1.2	e.82	18	14	4.1	9.1	1.8	1.9
23	15	3.9	2.1	.94	1.5	e.78	13	15	4.0	3.6	1.7	2.4
24	14	3.8	1.9	.86	.99	e.79	6.1	5.6	4.3	4.0	1.7	1.7
25	11	3.8	1.8	.85	1.0	e.81	5.6	4.3	3.8	1.9	10	2.0
26	10	4.9	2.3	1.2	.92	e.85	3.7	3.8	3.5	6.8	3.8	3.5
27	9.5	6.1	1.9	.94	.96	e.80	3.0	3.5	3.5	2.4	2.0	1.5
28	8.5	3.9	1.7	1.8	1.0	e1.5	11	22	3.2	1.7	4.8	2.8
29	22	8.8	13	7.3	---	e1.5	12	6.2	11	2.6	9.1	1.4
30	25	7.6	4.1	3.4	---	e.96	4.5	27	4.5	2.3	14	1.2
31	33	---	2.4	2.3	---	e5.6	---	27	---	2.2	16	---
TOTAL	413.0	241.8	108.9	49.09	45.37	33.91	228.9	397.1	214.0	93.2	126.4	178.4
MEAN	13.3	8.06	3.51	1.58	1.62	1.09	7.63	12.8	7.13	3.01	4.08	5.95
MAX	33	29	13	7.3	5.6	5.6	20	48	22	9.1	16	37
MIN	3.8	3.8	1.7	.85	.92	.76	1.5	3.1	3.2	1.7	1.5	1.0
AC-FT	819	480	216	97	90	67	454	788	424	185	251	354
CFSM	4.22	2.55	1.11	.50	.51	.35	2.41	4.05	2.26	.95	1.29	1.88
IN.	4.86	2.85	1.28	.58	.53	.40	2.69	4.67	2.52	1.10	1.49	2.10

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1969 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	18.6	10.1	3.72	2.53	2.20	2.27	4.30	9.87	7.00	4.22	5.13	10.7													
MAX	33.7	16.7	7.31	6.83	5.37	6.38	7.63	12.8	9.73	9.85	9.88	15.7													
(WY)	1991	1971	1971	1971	1971	1971	1993	1993	1970	1969	1991	1990													
MIN	11.9	6.51	1.35	.66	.93	1.01	1.31	3.86	3.18	2.03	3.34	5.95													
(WY)	1971	1991	1991	1991	1992	1970	1970	1992	1992	1990	1970	1993													

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1969 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	1586.45		2130.07			
ANNUAL MEAN	4.33		5.84		6.20	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					8.05	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					4.70	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	33		Oct 18		216	
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.61		Mar 23		.47	
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.67		Mar 17		.51	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW					5300	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			463		Oct 7 1990	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	3150		4220		4490	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.37		1.85		1.96	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	18.68		25.08		26.67	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	10		14		14	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	2.4		3.2		3.6	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.88		1.1		.94	

e Estimated

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50010500 RIO GUAJATACA AT LARES, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'01", long 66°52'24", at bridge on Highway 111 (km 32.9), 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from Quebrada Anon, and 0.4 mi (0.6 km) northeast of Lares plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.16 mi² (8.18 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-71, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992										
30...	1115	8.1	215	6.9	22.5	32	4.8	56	13	K2200 2100
DEC 15...	0940	4.3	212	7.3	22.0	11	4.8	56	20	25000 47000
FEB 1993										
17...	0945	1.2	233	7.4	21.0	2.1	4.4	50	11	K620 2400
APR 15...	1035	3.4	254	7.2	21.0	49	7.8	91	19	K18000 K41000
JUN 17...	0855	4.8	236	7.1	22.5	23	7.6	87	<10	K1700 3500
SEP 22...	1115	1.0	258	7.3	23.5	1.6	7.3	85	16	850 2000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CACO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FLD (MG/L AS CACO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1992											
30...	73	2	19	6.3	10	0.6	3.4	78	<0.5	11	10
DEC 15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	74	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--
APR 15...	100	5	32	5.8	11	0.5	3.5	95	1.6	15	11
JUN 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	89	--	--	--
SEP 22...	98	4	28	6.5	13	0.6	2.8	90	--	12	10

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
30...	<0.10	25	126	2.76	56	1.99	0.010	2.00	0.020	--
DEC 15...	--	--	--	--	6	1.67	0.030	1.70	0.060	0.74
FEB 1993										
17...	--	--	--	--	3	1.89	0.010	1.90	0.160	0.94
APR 15...	<0.10	22	157	1.44	40	1.15	0.050	1.20	0.140	0.36
JUN 17...	--	--	--	--	12	0.68	0.020	0.70	0.030	0.17
SEP 22...	0.20	31	170	0.46	2	1.19	0.010	1.20	0.030	0.77

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50011000 CANAL PRINCIPAL DE DIVERSIONES AT LAGO DE GUAJATACA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'02", long 66°55'27", off Highway 476 at Lago Guajataca outlet, 3.0 mi (4.8 km) southwest of Segunda Unidad Baldorioty de Castro, and 5.3 mi (8.5 km) south of Quebradillas Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-64, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
27...	1105	E55	317	7.1	27.0	1.2	0.2	2	12	34	29
DEC 16...	1245	E55	315	7.1	26.0	0.80	1.2	58	12	K4	K8
FEB 1993											
23...	1240	E55	312	7.4	25.5	0.70	1.6	20	67	10	10
APR 27...	1450	E55	293	6.7	24.5	1.4	0.5	36	29	K160	K110
JUN 15...	1200	E55	310	7.0	25.0	1.0	0.4	18	<10	40	94
SEP 10...	1145	E55	330	7.4	26.0	1.4	0.7	21	<10	28	30

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY TOT WH FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
27...	130	4	48	3.3	5.4	0.2	1.8	160	<0.5	9.7	6.6
DEC 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	78	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
APR 27...	140	12	50	3.5	5.6	0.2	2.1	180	0.8	8.4	8.0
JUN 15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
SEP 10...	140	11	50	4.2	5.7	0.2	1.9	130	--	6.3	7.9

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
27...	<0.10	7.7	160	--	4	--	<0.010	<0.050	0.330	0.27
DEC 16...	--	--	--	--	<1	0.090	0.010	0.100	0.360	0.24
FEB 1993										
23...	--	--	--	--	<1	0.090	0.010	0.100	0.080	0.42
APR 27...	0.10	4.5	190	--	1	0.090	0.010	0.100	0.030	0.57
JUN 15...	--	--	--	--	11	0.090	0.010	0.100	0.060	0.24
SEP 10...	0.10	7.2	174	--	5	1.49	0.010	1.50	0.010	0.89

E = estimate
K = non-ideal count

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50011400 RIO GUAJATACA ABOVE MOUTH NEAR QUEBRADILLAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°28'31", long 66°57'46", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, on left bank at ford 1.7 mi (2.7 km) upstream from bridge on highway 2, 1.6 mi (2.6 km) west of Quebradillas plaza, 2.1 mi (3.4 km) upstream from Atlantic Ocean, and 6.6 mi (10.6 km) downstream from Lago Guajataka.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992										
28...	1320	33	393	7.9	26.5	0.50	7.2	105	<10	K140 380
DEC 28...	0830	45	391	7.3	23.5	0.50	5.8	68	37	510 1500
FEB 1993										
24...	1240	7.1	475	7.4	25.0	0.50	4.4	53	<10	200 170
MAY 06...	0910	140	318	7.9	24.5	6.9	7.8	112	14	70 310
JUN 16...	1230	22	425	7.2	25.0	6.5	7.2	89	<10	K62000 38000
SEP 24...	0940	9.8	430	7.5	25.5	0.40	4.4	53	<10	220 2100

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
28...	250	25	72	7.2	15	0.5	1.1	180	<0.5	9.4	26
DEC 28...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	210	--	--	--
MAY 06...	150	3	54	3.6	5.9	0.2	1.8	140	<0.5	8.7	9.1
JUN 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
SEP 24...	210	11	74	6.6	11	0.3	2.2	170	--	6.3	18

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
28...	<0.10	6.6	253	22.5	<1	0.720	0.010	0.720	0.020	0.18
DEC 28...	--	--	--	--	6	1.49	0.010	1.50	0.220	0.68
FEB 1993										
24...	--	--	--	--	<1	2.29	0.010	2.30	0.010	0.19
MAY 06...	0.10	4.2	171	64.8	7	2.49	0.010	2.50	0.030	0.27
JUN 16...	--	--	--	--	20	1.79	0.010	1.80	0.010	0.19
SEP 24...	0.30	6.7	227	6.0	5	0.09	0.010	1.00	0.020	1.8

K = non-ideal count

Figure 14.--Río Camuy basin.

RIO CAMUY BASIN

50014600 RIO CAMUY AT TRES PUEBLOS SINKHOLE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'42", long 66°49'29", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, at Parque de las Cavernas del Río Camuy, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) southeast from Escuela Segunda Unidad de Santiago Palmer, 4.7 mi (7.6 km) west from Observatorio de Arecibo and 4.8 mi (7.7 km) northeast from Plaza de Lares.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Datum of gage is 612.21 ft (186.602 m), above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	92	100	50	32	44	20	26	33	71	38	21	80
2	68	70	43	31	33	20	22	31	58	36	21	45
3	55	63	41	30	33	19	20	118	54	36	20	34
4	47	61	42	30	30	18	19	116	51	34	19	28
5	47	58	41	29	28	18	19	72	49	33	19	68
6	45	56	46	29	27	18	18	84	48	33	19	229
7	47	55	40	29	28	18	20	135	47	33	21	299
8	41	53	39	29	27	17	25	106	51	33	19	179
9	42	52	38	28	26	18	27	81	58	31	19	129
10	62	52	38	27	25	18	21	69	51	30	22	111
11	54	50	38	27	25	19	32	63	46	30	19	84
12	45	47	37	27	25	24	43	58	58	31	20	73
13	43	47	85	27	25	18	49	54	60	29	18	70
14	42	46	99	27	24	16	69	52	48	29	17	68
15	41	48	73	27	24	16	51	49	45	31	17	64
16	59	49	43	26	23	16	71	84	44	32	31	62
17	114	51	38	26	23	16	108	76	42	28	26	64
18	121	46	37	26	23	15	81	59	41	27	20	61
19	107	56	35	25	22	14	62	54	46	26	21	60
20	70	45	34	25	24	14	49	55	48	26	26	63
21	58	44	33	24	26	15	82	54	43	26	21	57
22	58	44	33	25	23	14	68	65	41	35	19	57
23	67	43	33	26	22	13	73	152	40	44	19	63
24	64	42	32	25	e22	13	48	94	39	30	18	65
25	60	42	31	26	21	16	46	69	38	29	22	58
26	56	41	33	25	22	14	57	65	38	26	39	58
27	59	41	34	25	21	29	33	59	37	28	21	62
28	56	42	32	24	21	29	55	73	37	25	33	68
29	57	51	38	35	---	19	78	63	42	23	37	80
30	119	60	49	33	---	70	47	96	49	22	55	60
31	105	---	35	34	---	61	---	80	---	22	68	---
TOTAL	2001	1555	1320	859	717	645	1419	2319	1420	936	767	2499
MEAN	64.5	51.8	42.6	27.7	25.6	20.8	47.3	74.8	47.3	30.2	24.7	83.3
MAX	121	100	99	35	44	70	108	152	71	44	68	299
MIN	41	41	31	24	21	13	18	31	37	22	17	28

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1990	1991	1992	1993	1990	1991	1992	1993	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	87.4	52.8	34.9	25.6	23.3	24.6	44.6	76.6	47.1	33.2	43.8	66.8
MAX	112	55.9	42.6	27.7	27.0	34.4	47.3	80.7	70.3	43.1	66.0	83.3
(WY)	1991	1992	1993	1993	1991	1992	1993	1992	1992	1991	1991	1993
MIN	64.5	50.7	29.8	21.6	17.5	18.5	41.8	74.2	32.1	20.7	24.7	48.4
(WY)	1993	1991	1991	1991	1992	1991	1992	1991	1991	1990	1993	1992

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1990 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	16457	
ANNUAL MEAN	45.1	47.7
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN		49.2
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN		45.1
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	299	Sep 7 1993
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	13	Mar 23 1993
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	14	Mar 18 1993
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW	902	Sep 7 1991
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE	11.86	Sep 7 1991
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW	13	Mar 23 1993
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	73	84
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	38	38
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	19	19

e Estimated

RIO CAMUY BASIN

50014800 RIO CAMUY NEAR BAYANEY, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'48", long 66°49'04", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, on left bank at Highway 488, 1.4 mi (2.2 km) southeast of school at Santiago, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) northwest from Escuela Manuel A. Rivera at Bayaney and 9.1 mi (14.6 km) upstream from Atlantic Ocean.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 341 ft (104 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	191	193	112	e100	e84	e34	69	116	148	71	39	165
2	139	118	77	e90	e66	e34	e129	106	104	69	38	98
3	111	99	71	e82	e58	e33	76	349	90	64	37	62
4	89	112	78	e76	e56	e32	43	315	81	58	36	55
5	87	92	72	e72	e50	e33	39	155	76	57	35	123
6	79	86	67	e68	e49	e32	37	249	70	57	35	489
7	90	82	63	e66	e48	e31	38	358	67	55	41	893
8	76	79	57	e66	e50	e31	47	273	73	55	37	486
9	75	78	55	e61	e46	e32	68	177	85	54	35	247
10	105	77	53	e58	45	e33	45	146	70	53	43	238
11	106	76	52	e57	43	e32	59	123	59	53	36	148
12	79	73	51	e56	42	49	138	111	123	52	39	101
13	75	81	192	e54	41	37	128	101	156	49	36	87
14	72	78	298	e54	39	34	164	95	86	47	35	84
15	70	74	184	e52	39	35	135	95	66	51	33	74
16	88	82	89	e50	38	33	240	156	62	54	50	e120
17	241	81	75	e50	37	35	286	152	58	49	68	e230
18	234	79	70	e52	37	34	303	102	98	46	43	e170
19	187	83	66	e48	36	33	195	105	78	47	38	e90
20	99	75	64	e52	40	32	175	106	85	46	52	e110
21	74	101	65	e49	47	33	348	131	70	46	39	e72
22	72	81	69	e52	38	33	229	159	70	61	34	e66
23	102	73	66	e52	e37	31	236	357	65	105	34	e90
24	94	66	64	e52	e37	31	169	215	63	66	34	e120
25	77	64	73	e50	e36	34	154	149	61	57	35	e96
26	68	66	114	e47	e35	32	176	135	59	52	77	e100
27	76	101	88	e46	e35	44	106	117	58	53	51	e80
28	74	82	95	e54	e34	79	420	203	58	47	41	e76
29	67	149	e120	e66	---	40	307	151	58	43	83	e150
30	214	158	e180	e62	---	166	172	196	85	40	117	e210
31	198	---	e130	e68	---	169	---	191	---	40	134	---
TOTAL	3409	2739	2910	1862	1243	1371	4731	5394	2382	1697	1485	5130
MEAN	110	91.3	93.9	60.1	44.4	44.2	158	174	79.4	54.7	47.9	171
MAX	241	193	298	100	84	169	420	358	156	105	134	893
MIN	67	64	51	46	34	31	37	95	58	40	33	55

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1984 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993		
MEAN	208	123	70.3	49.8	46.4	47.7	112	193	106	79.7	91.6	153
MAX	427	244	97.4	80.9	78.3	66.0	202	624	141	109	135	273
(WY)	1986	1986	1988	1988	1987	1992	1986	1986	1992	1989	1989	1984
MIN	81.6	74.9	49.7	33.1	29.2	35.7	61.4	43.2	79.4	54.7	47.9	99.2
(WY)	1988	1989	1989	1991	1992	1991	1990	1989	1993	1993	1993	1992

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1984 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	33404	34353	
ANNUAL MEAN	91.3	94.1	106
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			179
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			89.3
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	549	May 23	893
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	25	Mar 2	31
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	25	Feb 29	32
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			2570
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			12.77
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			30
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	187		182
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	74		70
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	29		36

e Estimated

RIO CAMUY BASIN

50015700 RIO CAMUY NEAR HATILLO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'44", long 66°49'56", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) southwest of Hatillo plaza, and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) southeast of Camuy plaza, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) south of Planta de Purificación, and 3.3 mi (5.5 km) upstream from Atlantic Ocean.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 13 ft (4 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	269	299	247	126	e96	44	82	244	271	78	46	223
2	203	158	124	110	e80	44	144	199	148	75	45	154
3	131	113	108	98	e69	43	141	611	123	82	44	75
4	87	189	125	92	e67	41	56	1130	111	69	43	65
5	83	119	161	86	e61	42	47	304	102	65	42	109
6	72	101	109	82	e58	41	41	388	93	64	42	506
7	86	92	98	80	e58	40	50	840	89	63	48	1650
8	70	87	85	79	59	40	117	709	89	62	42	1420
9	68	85	80	74	57	41	91	302	113	61	41	431
10	69	88	77	71	55	42	56	255	119	60	48	357
11	156	83	74	69	53	41	86	190	84	60	41	271
12	72	79	71	67	53	55	209	161	149	59	44	138
13	67	97	105	65	52	45	126	140	328	58	40	116
14	65	160	900	63	50	40	187	126	187	54	39	129
15	61	94	445	63	49	41	215	122	109	59	38	99
16	59	100	164	61	48	40	304	178	90	62	50	143
17	270	94	124	59	48	40	482	293	81	55	68	281
18	397	87	113	61	47	38	588	131	203	52	51	206
19	380	107	104	58	46	37	391	127	182	53	49	111
20	146	88	104	e60	52	35	331	155	161	53	57	129
21	90	166	99	e58	66	37	602	197	108	52	47	88
22	84	134	111	e62	51	35	580	304	98	54	41	81
23	142	94	107	e62	48	34	417	684	89	143	42	107
24	162	82	103	e62	48	34	359	447	81	78	40	141
25	103	77	105	e60	47	37	248	256	76	63	39	118
26	86	82	321	e56	46	35	341	205	72	54	77	123
27	92	231	182	e55	45	45	149	155	70	59	57	99
28	103	165	192	e64	44	79	1420	282	68	53	41	93
29	85	279	263	e76	---	44	1850	342	68	48	93	181
30	295	363	388	e72	---	231	592	223	94	47	143	257
31	355	---	165	e82	---	278	---	346	---	46	161	---
TOTAL	4408	3993	5454	2233	1553	1719	10302	10046	3656	1941	1699	7901
MEAN	142	133	176	72.0	55.5	55.5	343	324	122	62.6	54.8	263
MAX	397	363	900	126	96	278	1850	1130	328	143	161	1650
MIN	59	77	71	55	44	34	41	122	68	46	38	65

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1984 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993		
MEAN	354	187	93.4	63.9	66.7	67.5	207	386	147	106	117	212
MAX	735	439	176	131	134	88.1	411	1586	218	161	180	376
(WY)	1986	1986	1993	1988	1987	1992	1986	1986	1992	1990	1989	1989
MIN	116	115	51.4	46.2	34.1	49.2	70.5	59.5	105	62.6	54.8	117
(WY)	1988	1989	1992	1989	1992	1988	1992	1989	1991	1993	1993	1992

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1984 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	47842	54905	
ANNUAL MEAN	131	150	168
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			335
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			129
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1250	May 23	8150
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	31	Feb 28	25
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	31	Feb 28	35
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			5620
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			19.78
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			33
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	303	304	318
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	79	86	82
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	34	43	42

e Estimated

Figure 15.--Río Grande de Arecibo basin.

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN
50020100 LAGO GARZAS NEAR ADJUNTAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°08'20", long 66°44'29", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, in power gate tower of Garzas Dam on Río Vacas, 1.7 mi (2.7 km) upstream from Río Garzas, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) southwest of Adjuntas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--15.6 mi² (40.4 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1988 to May 1989, March to September 1993.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 2,400.00 ft (731.520 m) above mean sea level. Prior to May 25, 1988 at datum 2,376.80 ft (724.449 m), May 25 to July 13, 1988 at datum 2,338.08 ft (712.647 m), July 14, 1988 to May 25, 1989 at datum 2,337.82 ft (712.560 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lake is formed by earthfill dam completed in 1943. Outflow from lake controlled by vertical-lift sluice gate and fixed-crest concrete spillway. Spillway elevation, 2,415.00 ft (736.09 m). Lake is used for irrigation and power production. Operated by P.R. Electric Power Authority. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation 2,417.66 ft (736.903 m), May 27, 1993; minimum elevation, 2,364.79 ft (720.788 m), Aug. 23, 1988.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR WATER YEARS 1989, 1993.--Water Year 1989: Maximum elevation 2,414.76 ft (736.019 m), Jan. 23; minimum elevation, 2,365.84 ft (721.108 m), May 2.
Water Year 1993: Maximum elevation 2,417.66 ft (736.903 m), May 27; minimum elevation, 2,412.26 ft (735.257 m), May 18.

Capacity table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
2,364	660	2,415	4,082
2,382	1,500	2,418	4,411
2,394	2,250		

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1988 TO SEPTEMBER 1989
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	A	A	A	A	2412.73	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
2	A	A	A	A	2412.50	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
3	A	A	A	A	2412.25	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
4	A	A	A	A	2412.00	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
5	A	A	A	A	2411.76	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
6	A	A	A	A	2411.51	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
7	A	A	A	A	2411.24	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
8	A	A	A	A	2410.97	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
9	A	A	A	A	2410.73	2409.31	A	A	A	A	A	A
10	A	A	A	A	2410.47	2409.43	A	A	A	A	A	A
11	A	A	A	A	2410.20	2409.57	A	A	A	A	A	A
12	A	A	A	A	2409.94	2410.14	A	A	A	A	A	A
13	A	A	A	A	2409.50	2410.24	A	A	A	A	A	A
14	A	A	A	A	A	2411.30	A	2395.91	A	A	A	A
15	A	A	A	A	A	2411.32	A	2391.84	A	A	A	A
16	A	A	A	A	A	2411.30	A	2391.68	A	A	A	A
17	A	A	A	A	A	2411.50	A	2393.20	A	A	A	A
18	A	A	A	A	A	2411.71	A	2391.69	A	A	A	A
19	A	A	A	2414.31	A	2411.74	A	2391.69	A	A	A	A
20	A	A	A	2414.55	A	2411.82	A	2391.81	A	A	A	A
21	A	A	A	2414.67	A	2411.71	A	2391.70	A	A	A	A
22	A	A	A	2414.72	A	2411.77	A	2390.98	A	A	A	A
23	A	A	A	2414.72	A	2411.58	A	2390.21	A	A	A	A
24	A	A	A	2414.50	A	2411.85	A	2389.23	A	A	A	A
25	A	A	A	2414.28	A	2411.92	A	2389.22	A	A	A	A
26	A	A	A	2414.07	A	2412.12	A	A	A	A	A	A
27	A	A	A	2413.86	A	2412.38	A	A	A	A	A	A
28	A	A	A	2413.64	A	2412.74	A	A	A	A	A	A
29	A	A	A	2413.42	---	2412.79	A	A	A	A	A	A
30	A	A	A	2413.20	---	2412.73	A	A	A	A	A	A
31	A	---	A	2412.97	---	2412.78	---	A	---	A	A	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
MAX	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
MIN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

A No gage-height record

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50020100 LAGO GARZAS NEAR ADJUNTAS, PR-Continued

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	A	A	A	A	A	A	2414.80	2414.83	A	2414.62	2414.75	2414.72
2	A	A	A	A	A	A	2414.57	2414.86	A	2414.61	2414.67	2414.66
3	A	A	A	A	A	A	2414.54	2414.96	2414.72	2414.62	2414.65	2414.65
4	A	A	A	A	A	A	2414.53	2414.30	2414.72	2414.58	2414.64	2414.65
5	A	A	A	A	A	A	2414.53	2414.39	2414.73	2414.63	2414.64	2414.65
6	A	A	A	A	A	A	2414.53	2414.34	2414.71	2414.64	2414.64	2414.65
7	A	A	A	A	A	A	2414.51	2414.43	2414.70	2414.67	2414.63	2414.68
8	A	A	A	A	A	A	2414.52	2414.70	2414.71	2414.60	2414.63	2414.67
9	A	A	A	A	A	A	2414.69	2414.93	2414.69	2414.57	2414.64	2414.65
10	A	A	A	A	A	A	2414.83	2414.33	2414.63	2414.56	2414.63	2414.76
11	A	A	A	A	A	A	2414.88	2413.75	2414.62	2414.65	2414.63	2414.67
12	A	A	A	A	A	A	2414.80	2413.26	2414.63	2414.58	2414.61	2414.66
13	A	A	A	A	A	A	2414.87	2413.22	2414.62	2414.68	2414.61	2414.76
14	A	A	A	A	A	A	2414.88	2413.18	2414.61	2414.62	2414.61	2414.68
15	A	A	A	A	A	A	2414.95	2413.17	2414.75	2414.58	2414.65	2414.76
16	A	A	A	A	A	A	2414.82	2413.18	2414.61	2414.57	2414.71	2414.80
17	A	A	A	A	A	2414.56	2414.79	2412.46	2414.57	2414.55	2414.65	2414.71
18	A	A	A	A	A	2414.71	2414.79	2412.72	2415.04	2414.54	2414.63	2414.70
19	A	A	A	A	A	2414.76	2414.78	2412.75	2414.77	2414.53	2414.61	2414.65
20	A	A	A	A	A	2414.76	2414.78	2412.95	2414.67	2414.51	2414.60	2414.67
21	A	A	A	A	A	2414.77	2414.39	2413.89	2414.65	2414.48	2414.62	2414.73
22	A	A	A	A	A	2414.77	2414.32	2414.20	2414.63	2414.55	2414.75	2414.77
23	A	A	A	A	A	2414.78	2414.31	2414.51	2414.62	2414.52	2414.77	2414.49
24	A	A	A	A	A	2414.52	2414.47	2414.58	2414.60	2414.58	2414.66	2414.57
25	A	A	A	A	A	2414.52	2414.60	2414.43	2414.59	2414.55	2414.65	2414.71
26	A	A	A	A	A	2414.66	2414.72	2414.73	2414.58	2414.52	2414.66	2414.83
27	A	A	A	A	A	2414.76	2414.66	A	2414.58	2414.48	2414.70	2414.81
28	A	A	A	A	A	2414.79	2414.88	A	2414.63	2414.67	2414.65	2414.84
29	A	A	A	A	---	2414.80	2415.03	A	2414.61	2414.74	2414.64	2414.77
30	A	A	A	A	---	2414.66	2414.95	A	2414.62	2414.75	2414.63	2414.85
31	A	---	A	A	---	2414.77	---	A	---	2414.75	2414.64	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	2414.69	---	---	2414.60	2414.65	2414.71
MAX	---	---	---	---	---	---	2415.03	---	---	2414.75	2414.77	2414.85
MIN	---	---	---	---	---	---	2414.31	---	---	2414.48	2414.60	2414.49

A No gage-height record

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50020500 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO NEAR ADJUNTAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'54", long 66°44'12", at Highway 135 bridge, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) upstream from Lago Adjuntas, and 1.5 mi (2.4 km) northwest of Adjuntas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--12.7 mi² (32.9 km²) this does not include 6.0 mi² (15.6 km²) above Lago Garzas.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969-74, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FFCAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS. / 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FFCAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992										
15...	1105	76	276	7.2	22.0	1.9	6.6	95	15	K820 3400
DEC 14...	0920	65	594	7.3	21.0	2.6	6.1	71	24	5700 58000
FEB 1993										
09...	0945	18	330	7.5	20.0	1.0	7.0	87	<10	240 480
APR 20...	1020	19	324	7.5	23.5	1.3	8.0	92	23	380 K1800
JUN 04...	0945	41	270	7.3	24.0	1.8	7.6	73	16	K750 510
SEP 21...	1100	30	293	7.5	24.5	3.0	7.7	93	<10	2400 710

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
15...	130	30	28	14	44	2.0	3.8	89	<0.5	12	30
DEC 14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	77	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
APR 20...	100	9	27	7.9	20	0.9	2.4	110	<0.5	7.0	31
JUN 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	95	--	--	--
SEP 21...	100	6	27	8.5	18	0.8	2.3	100	--	10	25

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
15...	<0.10	29	225	46	<1	0.880	0.030	0.910	0.140	0.16
DEC 14...	--	--	--	--	9	0.590	0.010	0.600	0.030	0.27
FEB 1993										
09...	--	--	--	--	<1	1.06	0.040	1.10	0.020	0.38
APR 20...	0.10	28	189	9.71	1	0.850	0.050	0.900	0.030	0.67
JUN 04...	--	--	--	--	28	0.720	0.080	0.800	0.040	0.16
SEP 21...	0.10	25	176	14.0	13	0.880	0.020	0.900	0.010	0.39

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50025000 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO NEAR UTUADO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'11", long 66°41'59", at bridge near Highway 10 at km 56.4, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) downstream from Río de Caguana, and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) north of Utuado plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--66.0 mi² (170.9 km²) this excludes 6.0 mi² (15.5 km²) upstream from Lago Garzas to Río Guayanés in the Río Tallaboa basin.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1959-74, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH SATUR-ATION) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS. / 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1992	20...	180	242	7.1	26.5	26	6.0	74	<10	5500	3200
DEC	14...	168	194	7.2	24.0	6.9	5.2	62	34	4600	K110
FEB 1993	10...	59	238	7.6	21.0	3.7	8.4	82	19	K1800	330
APR	16...	184	180	6.9	22.0	4.3	8.3	80	<10	38000	42000
JUN	10...	149	175	7.0	23.5	250	8.1	78	18	58000	41000
SEP	16...	79	250	7.4	27.0	5.3	9.0	112	<10	3400	280

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992	83	9	22	6.9	12	0.6	2.5	84	<0.5	17	15
DEC	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	70	--	--	--
FEB 1993	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	94	--	--	--
APR	100	2	33	5.1	8.0	0.3	1.2	60	<0.5	8.0	9.0
JUN	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	59	--	--	--
SEP	98	6	27	7.5	13	0.6	2.3	75	--	18	12

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDEd (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992	0.10	27	153	74.3	19	1.07	0.030	1.10	0.120	0.18
DEC	--	--	--	--	48	0.390	0.010	0.400	0.030	0.27
FEB 1993	--	--	--	--	16	0.490	0.010	0.500	0.010	0.19
APR	0.10	20	120	59.8	13	0.190	0.010	0.200	0.010	0.59
JUN	--	--	--	--	537	0.590	0.010	0.600	0.030	0.57
SEP	<0.10	27	152	32.4	16	0.290	0.010	0.300	0.010	0.29

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50025155 RIO SALIENTE AT COABEY NEAR JAYUYA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'48", long 66°33'49", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 2.0 mi (3.2 km) southeast of Jayuya, 1.4 mi (2.2 km) northeast of Hacienda Gripiñas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--9.25 mi² (23.96 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1989 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 1,706 ft (520 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	27	88	31	20	35	12	6.7	e110	49	16	10	22
2	20	55	28	20	23	12	6.5	e280	40	16	10	13
3	17	43	28	19	22	e11	6.5	e120	35	24	9.9	11
4	47	39	26	19	19	e10	14	e54	31	19	9.4	161
5	129	35	23	19	18	e9.6	6.3	e35	28	16	9.3	29
6	136	31	21	20	17	e9.5	6.2	e26	26	16	9.2	17
7	55	28	20	20	17	e9.4	6.2	e23	25	31	9.1	14
8	40	26	19	17	16	e12	8.3	e21	25	19	8.8	14
9	55	25	19	16	16	e10	8.2	e24	46	16	9.8	14
10	68	24	19	16	16	e8.8	7.4	e27	27	15	9.6	14
11	38	24	18	16	15	e8.4	e80	e23	23	79	8.9	15
12	27	24	18	16	15	e8.0	e24	e20	21	31	8.7	11
13	22	24	17	16	15	e8.0	e150	e17	20	34	8.5	11
14	22	26	20	16	15	e7.8	e60	e33	21	29	8.3	10
15	20	34	22	16	14	e7.6	e54	e27	23	19	8.4	9.8
16	31	58	19	15	16	e7.8	e58	e19	22	17	63	9.9
17	37	25	20	15	15	e8.0	e22	e16	19	16	14	28
18	26	27	19	14	14	e8.3	e19	e14	18	15	11	22
19	21	46	21	15	14	8.2	e15	e13	68	15	9.7	17
20	19	106	19	14	17	13	e12	e13	56	14	9.3	13
21	17	34	18	14	17	12	e12	e13	26	14	9.6	12
22	24	36	23	15	13	8.7	e10	e15	23	16	10	11
23	87	31	20	17	12	8.3	e9.4	e220	21	16	10	27
24	199	29	20	16	12	8.3	e16	e98	19	14	9.4	21
25	91	27	19	15	12	8.5	e20	e160	18	13	8.9	14
26	42	25	48	14	12	8.4	e12	e88	17	16	8.6	12
27	37	26	33	15	11	8.1	e11	e56	17	14	10	11
28	30	68	27	65	11	7.9	e210	56	18	12	18	25
29	203	74	26	95	---	7.8	e390	44	20	11	13	18
30	123	39	23	29	---	7.8	e130	130	20	11	45	41
31	86	---	21	30	---	7.2	---	81	---	11	48	---
TOTAL	1796	1177	705	664	449	282.4	1390.7	1876	822	605	435.4	647.7
MEAN	57.9	39.2	22.7	21.4	16.0	9.11	46.4	60.5	27.4	19.5	14.0	21.6
MAX	203	106	48	95	35	13	390	280	68	79	63	161
MIN	17	24	17	14	11	7.2	6.2	13	17	11	8.3	9.8
AC-FT	3560	2330	1400	1320	891	560	2760	3720	1630	1200	864	1280
CFSM	6.26	4.24	2.46	2.32	1.73	.98	5.01	6.54	2.96	2.11	1.52	2.33
IN.	7.22	4.73	2.84	2.67	1.81	1.14	5.59	7.54	3.31	2.43	1.75	2.60

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1989 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	42.1	27.5	14.7	22.3	12.4
MAX	70.5	40.0	22.7	48.1	16.0
(WY)	1991	1991	1993	1992	1993
MIN	11.6	10.5	8.07	7.19	6.00
(WY)	1992	1992	1992	1990	1993

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1993 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1989 - 1993

	1992 CALENDAR YEAR	1993 WATER YEAR	1989 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	11515.2	10850.2	
ANNUAL MEAN	31.5	29.7	22.3
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			29.7
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			14.3
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	450	390	450
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	6.6	6.2	2.4
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	7.6	7.2	3.4
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		3260	3260
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		11.89	11.89
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW		6.2	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	22840	21520	16130
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.40	3.21	2.41
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	46.31	43.64	32.71
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	61	57	42
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	20	19	14
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	10	8.9	6.1

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50026050 RIO CAONILLAS ABOVE LAGO CAONILLAS NEAR JAYUYA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°13'26", long 66°38'22", 300 ft (91 m) off Highway 531, 700 ft (213 m) upstream from Lago Caonillas, 3.3 mi (5.3 km) northwest of Jayuya plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--40.4 mi² (104.6 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION) (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
19...	0945	115	175	7.6	22.0	23	6.6	76	17	4700	3900
DEC 30...	0900	74	173	8.0	21.0	26	4.0	46	34	41000	25000
FEB 1993											
19...	0915	27	209	7.7	21.5	1.7	4.6	53	<10	200	240
APR 26...	1010	27	220	7.6	25.0	7.7	9.4	82	<10	K830	270
JUN 02...	1035	176	173	7.4	24.0	5.0	7.5	90	92	K860	320
SEP 21...	0900	56	198	7.4	23.0	31	8.0	94	<10	3100	2500

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
19...	76	8	20	6.3	11	0.3	1.4	98	<0.5	15	14
DEC 30...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	90	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	76	--	--	--
APR 26...	86	9	23	6.9	13	0.6	1.7	66	<0.5	15	13
JUN 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	57	--	--	--
SEP 21...	78	5	20	6.8	10	0.5	1.7	70	--	14	11

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDEED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
19...	<0.10	23	130	40.4	34	0.920	0.020	0.940	0.050	0.25
DEC 30...	--	--	--	--	16	0.490	0.010	0.500	0.010	0.59
FEB 1993										
19...	--	--	--	--	7	0.590	0.010	0.600	0.010	0.19
APR 26...	0.10	24	136	9.93	14	0.190	0.010	0.200	0.030	0.27
JUN 02...	--	--	--	--	33	0.290	0.010	0.300	0.010	0.39
SEP 21...	0.20	23	129	19.4	33	0.490	0.010	0.500	0.010	0.19

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50026140 LAGO CAONILLAS AT CAONILLAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°16'43", long 66°39'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, at Lago Caonillas Dam on Río Caonillas, 2.9 mi (4.7 km) northeast of Plaza de Utuado, 0.3 mi (0.6 km) west from Iglesia Santa María del Monte Carmelo, and 1.8 mi (3.0 km) northwest from Hacienda Carbonell.

DRAINAGE AREA.--48.4 mi² (125.4 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1991 to current year.

GAGE.--Water stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Caonillas was completed in 1948. The dam is a concrete gravity structure with a total length of 815 ft (248 m), a maximum height of 235 ft (72 m), and a maximum base width of 195 ft (59 m). Nonoverflow sections on each abutment have a total length of 603 ft (184 m). The dam is the main unit of Caonillas Hydroelectric Project, and provides 49,000 acre-feet (60 hm³) of usable storage for power generation at Caonillas Power Plant No. 1 located 2.5 mi (4.0 km) downstream from the dam. The dam is owned by Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation, 825.39 ft (251.58 m), June 7, 1993; minimum elevation, less than 771.00 ft (235.00 m), many days during water year 1991.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 825.39 ft (251.58 m), June 7; minimum elevation, 779.50 ft (237.59 m), Mar. 13.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
705	0	800	27,982
750	8,421	830	46,161

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	792.83	813.96	820.15	818.06	805.18	791.93	784.61	801.39	A	820.45	814.87	794.97
2	793.17	814.89	820.38	817.98	804.68	791.74	784.78	803.82	A	820.10	814.25	794.28
3	793.32	815.57	820.60	818.03	804.04	791.20	784.96	807.94	824.89	819.84	813.66	794.42
4	793.24	815.22	820.83	818.22	803.09	789.99	785.13	809.68	824.79	820.11	812.61	795.08
5	792.97	815.72	821.03	818.20	802.11	788.70	785.30	810.44	825.06	820.20	811.42	795.85
6	794.39	815.90	821.22	818.09	801.47	787.36	785.47	812.23	825.30	819.90	810.34	796.32
7	793.80	816.24	821.40	817.48	800.92	785.94	785.62	813.32	825.25	A	809.62	796.31
8	794.61	816.55	821.24	816.67	799.78	784.60	785.83	814.01	825.22	A	808.88	795.98
9	795.49	816.16	820.36	816.82	799.23	783.64	786.19	814.65	825.18	819.43	807.60	796.04
10	795.96	816.49	819.78	816.74	798.72	782.91	786.42	815.24	825.13	819.15	806.29	796.23
11	795.74	816.80	819.95	815.97	798.09	781.47	787.03	815.72	824.88	819.36	805.15	796.44
12	796.20	817.14	820.10	815.04	797.47	780.70	787.90	816.13	824.25	819.35	803.74	796.50
13	796.57	817.09	820.57	814.59	796.90	779.93	788.82	A	824.18	819.06	802.44	796.65
14	796.81	817.16	821.29	814.29	796.99	A	790.59	A	824.00	818.46	801.42	796.61
15	796.16	817.42	821.71	813.50	796.84	A	791.91	A	823.85	818.36	801.45	796.63
16	796.79	817.93	821.93	812.53	796.35	779.96	792.89	A	823.56	818.04	800.78	796.80
17	798.35	817.27	822.17	812.29	795.77	780.22	793.33	A	823.25	817.41	800.66	796.94
18	799.21	816.69	822.38	812.07	795.18	781.26	793.64	A	822.98	817.21	799.84	796.90
19	799.74	816.95	822.58	811.19	794.53	781.50	793.92	A	823.08	816.43	798.89	797.29
20	800.11	816.62	822.77	810.22	794.25	781.74	794.23	A	823.55	816.39	797.90	797.28
21	799.45	817.02	822.57	809.21	794.05	782.05	794.49	A	823.29	815.99	797.07	796.80
22	799.87	817.35	821.97	809.34	794.09	782.27	794.72	A	822.99	A	796.78	796.66
23	800.50	817.64	821.53	809.46	793.90	782.49	794.92	A	822.70	A	796.26	795.84
24	802.79	817.91	820.69	809.56	793.16	782.73	795.22	A	822.42	A	794.41	796.22
25	803.96	818.16	820.11	809.67	792.25	782.96	795.47	A	822.07	A	794.35	796.32
26	804.58	818.38	819.83	809.12	791.60	783.20	795.67	A	821.68	A	793.40	796.05
27	805.37	818.63	820.00	808.06	791.70	783.57	795.85	A	821.36	A	793.46	795.11
28	805.91	819.08	819.79	807.48	791.78	783.79	796.19	A	821.14	A	793.60	795.03
29	808.91	819.48	819.29	807.70	---	783.99	798.48	A	820.94	815.99	793.92	795.26
30	810.24	819.85	818.58	805.62	---	784.20	799.84	A	820.76	815.65	794.23	795.48
31	811.69	---	818.09	805.98	---	784.42	---	A	---	815.22	794.67	---
TOTAL	24768.73	24511.27	25444.89	25199.18	22324.12	---	23729.42	---	---	---	24863.96	23882.29
MEAN	798.99	817.04	820.80	812.88	797.29	---	790.98	---	---	---	802.06	796.08
MAX	811.69	819.85	822.77	818.22	805.18	---	799.84	---	---	---	814.87	797.29
MIN	792.83	813.96	818.09	805.62	791.60	---	784.61	---	---	---	793.40	794.28

A No gage-height record

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50027250 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BELOW LAGO DOS BOCAS NEAR FLORIDA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'50", long 66°40'02", at pedestrian bridge, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) downstream from Lago Dos Bocas and 6.6 mi (10.6 km) west of Florida plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--169 mi² (436 km²) does not include 6.0 mi² (15.6 km²) above Lago Garzas.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1970-71, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
22...	0850	710	179	6.9	26.5	36	4.6	57	<10	540	410
DEC											
29...	0935	21	191	7.5	23.5	11	2.2	26	31	220	310
FEB 1993											
10...	1000	E800	209	7.0	24.0	8.1	5.4	32	27	K690	50
APR											
21...	1045	1660	180	6.6	24.0	120	6.3	24	27	200	320
JUN											
10...	1030	E2000	181	6.4	26.0	53	5.6	60	12	K190	300
SEP											
16...	1245	E600	192	4.7	27.0	13	4.9	59	<10	220	K160

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
22...	69	7	19	5.3	8.5	0.4	2.5	64	<0.5	11	9.6
DEC											
29...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	70	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	72	--	--	--
APR											
21...	60	4	16	4.8	9.6	0.5	2.5	64	<0.5	10	9.7
JUN											
10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	64	--	--	--
SEP											
16...	75	10	20	6.1	9.2	0.5	2.2	59	--	12	10

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
22...	0.10	20	114	219	13	0.940	0.030	0.970	0.050	0.35
DEC										
29...	--	--	--	--	17	0.690	0.010	0.700	0.030	0.67
FEB 1993										
10...	--	--	--	--	12	0.590	0.010	0.600	0.030	0.07
APR										
21...	0.10	18	109	490	29	0.170	0.030	0.200	0.130	0.37
JUN										
10...	--	--	--	--	16	0.590	0.010	0.600	0.030	0.37
SEP										
16...	0.10	21	116	188	25	0.630	0.070	0.700	0.210	0.63

E = estimate
K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50027750 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO ABOVE ARECIBO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'22", long 66°41'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) upstream from Río Tanamá, 3.6 mi (5.8 km) south of Arecibo and 4.9 mi (7.9 km) above mouth, and 10.4 mi (16.7 km) downstream from Lago Dos Bocas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--200 mi² (520 km²), approximately, of which an undetermined amount does not contribute directly to surface runoff.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1982 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 30 ft (9 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Flow regulated by Lago Dos Bocas Dam 10.4 mi (16.7 km) upstream from gage. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	486	275	148	269	628	226	194	265	e160	170	164	478
2	487	723	478	281	733	391	80	e450	e145	58	241	444
3	431	283	487	265	291	438	60	e620	477	539	514	436
4	485	503	500	305	532	440	64	e625	372	275	334	87
5	552	662	119	255	312	330	59	e490	90	54	453	54
6	460	741	108	134	256	60	74	e320	174	162	292	225
7	639	411	65	401	228	173	58	e440	510	322	155	831
8	734	91	356	512	664	170	81	e110	462	321	449	617
9	772	508	739	607	453	49	79	e390	393	522	101	591
10	613	522	593	481	472	72	69	e350	461	110	649	652
11	525	363	324	185	95	472	72	e400	413	325	763	364
12	691	414	77	563	102	607	245	e300	117	455	493	74
13	414	157	63	498	253	643	416	e120	616	392	766	49
14	593	97	364	496	249	662	397	e200	519	472	287	170
15	694	147	1330	664	62	624	645	e120	529	313	60	418
16	520	57	478	273	195	135	856	e200	260	295	176	263
17	111	538	625	70	270	232	451	e440	63	70	423	307
18	608	572	688	505	299	93	507	e420	121	45	381	337
19	607	363	329	501	374	66	452	e300	222	299	373	277
20	686	478	122	628	188	183	281	e140	311	609	86	147
21	522	250	424	547	161	79	500	288	686	96	67	e354
22	611	134	346	196	123	70	542	608	603	202	56	e622
23	422	91	275	69	176	161	317	332	709	69	254	e508
24	155	420	269	151	363	214	154	292	129	45	197	e342
25	77	352	584	67	351	499	72	244	78	40	733	e56
26	64	84	436	327	205	159	552	e300	174	40	404	e49
27	264	244	423	241	62	78	696	e490	239	37	250	642
28	304	192	500	352	47	68	295	e510	467	519	57	263
29	203	102	616	411	---	63	358	e480	557	230	50	394
30	777	283	772	210	---	73	476	e320	243	158	217	129
31	579	---	616	567	---	81	---	e220	---	209	306	---
TOTAL	15086	10057	13254	11031	8144	7611	9102	10784	10300	7453	9751	10180
MEAN	487	335	428	356	291	246	303	348	343	240	315	339
MAX	777	741	1330	664	733	662	856	625	709	609	766	831
MIN	64	57	63	67	47	49	58	110	63	37	50	49
AC-FT	29920	19950	26290	21880	16150	15100	18050	21390	20430	14780	19340	20190
CFSM	2.43	1.68	2.14	1.78	1.45	1.23	1.52	1.74	1.72	1.20	1.57	1.70
IN.	2.81	1.87	2.47	2.05	1.51	1.42	1.69	2.01	1.92	1.39	1.81	1.89

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1982 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	704	614	320	264	246	228	408	670	393	277	279	485
MEAN	704	614	320	264	246	228	408	670	393	277	279	485
MAX	1984	1413	570	437	428	351	617	2000	683	374	474	1080
(WY)	1986	1986	1988	1988	1988	1985	1986	1986	1987	1988	1988	1984
MIN	221	247	90.3	167	111	114	207	185	195	161	154	266
(WY)	1992	1992	1992	1989	1992	1987	1984	1989	1990	1990	1990	1992

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1982 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	123358	122753	
ANNUAL MEAN	337	336	408
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			729
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			279
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	2030	May 24	1330
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	33	Feb 4	37
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	50	Feb 14	68
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			2800
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			7.51
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			18.22
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	244700	243500	295500
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.69	1.68	2.04
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	22.94	22.83	27.71
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	674	623	814
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	292	312	281
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	48	69	63

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE ARRECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'02", long 66°46'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on downstream side of left abutment of bridge on Highway 111, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) upstream from natural tunnel, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) northeast of Angeles, and 5.8 mi (9.3 km) northwest of Utuado.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.4 mi² (47.7 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1944 to June 1958 (daily stage and two to four measurements per month by Puerto Rico Water Resources Authority), November 1959 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Datum of gage is 938.32 ft (286.000 m) above mean sea level. Datum of gage was lowered 3.00 ft (0.914 m) on Oct. 1978. Prior to Nov. 17, 1966, non-recording gage and Nov. 17, 1966 to Sept. 30, 1978 recording gage, both at present site.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e157	e82	39	29	51	20	21	45	50	24	17	88
2	e98	e64	38	27	30	21	19	77	45	24	17	63
3	e65	61	43	27	34	19	18	106	42	23	17	44
4	97	65	39	27	27	19	17	61	40	24	17	34
5	77	57	44	26	26	19	17	66	37	25	17	57
6	62	55	42	26	25	19	19	60	36	24	26	342
7	51	53	36	27	24	20	17	70	35	26	21	221
8	112	52	35	28	23	20	32	54	35	25	17	e106
9	e62	51	34	25	23	24	19	61	42	22	33	e71
10	345	50	33	25	22	23	19	53	39	21	28	87
11	e109	48	33	25	21	24	43	46	35	23	22	68
12	e78	47	32	25	22	21	44	42	38	22	20	52
13	87	50	59	25	21	19	66	40	33	20	17	52
14	108	56	112	24	21	19	241	38	30	23	16	44
15	76	50	64	25	20	23	e54	38	29	20	17	40
16	87	64	38	23	23	21	37	58	30	21	62	38
17	112	53	35	22	28	20	59	41	26	18	29	37
18	e114	47	33	22	21	19	41	37	25	18	22	e38
19	78	46	34	22	21	18	e35	36	51	18	21	e36
20	66	53	34	21	29	18	e33	38	40	19	19	e44
21	61	46	33	21	27	17	e94	32	28	20	19	e36
22	84	46	36	e22	22	17	47	31	26	26	19	e50
23	80	44	34	e25	21	16	38	108	25	23	19	56
24	82	43	32	e25	20	17	37	51	24	23	17	43
25	77	41	31	e24	20	21	32	83	24	20	19	37
26	e68	40	51	e22	20	17	26	91	23	20	19	38
27	e59	47	40	e21	19	37	36	65	23	18	16	35
28	e54	52	34	e21	19	34	33	119	22	17	72	37
29	55	44	35	46	---	19	96	68	50	16	104	34
30	126	41	32	59	---	72	72	91	35	17	56	31
31	77	---	30	48	---	33	---	66	---	16	46	---
TOTAL	2864	1548	1245	835	680	706	1362	1872	1018	656	861	1959
MEAN	92.4	51.6	40.2	26.9	24.3	22.8	45.4	60.4	33.9	21.2	27.8	65.3
MAX	345	82	112	59	51	72	241	119	51	26	104	342
MIN	51	40	30	21	19	16	17	31	22	16	16	31
AC-FT	5680	3070	2470	1660	1350	1400	2700	3710	2020	1300	1710	3890
CFSM	5.02	2.80	2.18	1.46	1.32	1.24	2.47	3.28	1.84	1.15	1.51	3.55
IN.	5.79	3.13	2.52	1.69	1.37	1.43	2.75	3.78	2.06	1.33	1.74	3.96

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1960 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1960	1961	1962	1963	1964	1965	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993			
MEAN	81.1	69.9	43.2	29.3	25.1	24.8	37.7	59.2	43.0	37.4	47.0	74.5																									
MAX	195	159	121	50.1	40.5	71.2	142	193	116	65.7	110	177																									
(WY)	1990	1969	1966	1966	1961	1972	1969	1963	1979	1981	1979	1961																									
MIN	25.4	29.3	21.5	18.0	13.2	11.0	9.70	12.4	16.5	19.5	24.3	27.6																									
(WY)	1963	1979	1965	1974	1965	1984	1984	1977	1977	1976	1976	1986																									

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1960 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	16471.5	15606	
ANNUAL MEAN	45.0	42.8	47.8
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			71.1
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			29.9
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	345	Oct 10	2170
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	9.6	Mar 24	6.5
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	11	Mar 18	7.4
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			6770
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			15.15
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			6.6
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	32670	30950	34600
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.45	2.32	2.60
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	33.30	31.55	35.26
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	83	77	84
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	36	34	33
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	15	19	17

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: January 1968 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.--US D-49 Sediment sampler since October 1968. Automatic sediment sampler since 1990.

REMARKS.--Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis and during high flow events. Estimates for period of missing daily record were made from a sediment transport curve developed from a period of record over 5 years.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean, 20,400 mg/L November 27, 1968; minimum daily mean, 0 mg/L during water year 1985.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily, 167,000 tons (152,000 tonnes) May 18, 1985, minimum daily, 0.0 ton (0.0 tonne) several days during many years.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean, 1,680 mg/L October 10, 1992; minimum daily mean, 2.0 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily, 9,700 tons (8,800 tonnes) October 10, 1992; minimum daily, 0.10 ton (0.09 tonne) several days.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MP (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992										
26...	0940	63	156	7.0	23.0	14	5.2	61	<10	K1400 3000
DEC 18...	0905	33	161	7.4	19.5	3.2	7.4	83	22	310 1500
FEB 1993										
25...	0955	19	166	7.9	19.5	1.2	6.2	69	<10	80 260
MAY 03...	0955	53	127	6.9	22.0	84	4.1	61	28	K8000 2100
JUN 18...	1005	26	185	7.6	23.5	2.4	8.6	99	<10	K1600 280
SEP 22...	0940	37	152	7.3	22.5	4.2	8.5	97	<10	K1400 1600

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
26...	63	10	16	5.6	7.3	0.4	2.3	56	<0.5	9.3	7.7
DEC 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	54	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
25...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	59	--	--	--
MAY 03...	43	6	11	3.7	5.7	0.4	2.7	56	<0.5	10	6.3
JUN 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	59	--	--	--
SEP 22...	53	9	13	5.0	6.9	0.4	2.6	78	--	12	8.3

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	e157	1050	e1440	e82	178	e55	39	14	1.4
2	e98	206	e59	e64	63	e11	38	9	.90
3	e65	75	e14	61	26	4.5	43	35	6.2
4	97	284	282	65	31	5.3	39	68	7.2
5	77	175	38	57	31	4.8	44	73	12
6	62	83	15	55	24	3.5	42	37	4.9
7	51	48	7.2	53	15	2.1	36	10	.99
8	112	952	1380	52	10	1.3	35	5	.53
9	e62	140	e28	51	9	1.2	34	5	.51
10	345	1680	9700	50	8	1.1	33	5	.49
11	e109	232	e78	48	8	1.0	33	5	.44
12	e78	83	e18	47	8	1.0	32	5	.43
13	87	135	60	50	26	4.5	59	119	58
14	108	340	263	56	67	13	112	431	357
15	76	153	34	50	64	9.5	64	108	26
16	87	228	87	64	112	27	38	32	3.5
17	112	314	161	53	98	17	35	16	1.4
18	e114	315	e215	47	39	5.1	33	11	.94
19	78	150	35	46	22	2.8	34	10	.90
20	66	63	12	53	52	10	34	10	.90
21	61	17	2.8	46	22	2.9	33	10	.90
22	84	149	49	46	9	1.2	36	9	.84
23	80	162	47	44	9	1.1	34	8	.72
24	82	161	46	43	9	1.0	32	8	.68
25	77	145	34	41	7	.77	31	8	.73
26	e68	118	e27	40	5	.53	51	66	15
27	e59	59	e9.6	47	45	7.2	40	40	4.7
28	e54	30	e4.4	52	70	11	34	15	1.4
29	55	23	3.5	44	67	8.9	35	7	.68
30	126	469	598	41	21	2.3	32	5	.45
31	77	143	32	---	---	---	30	5	.40
TOTAL	2864	---	14779.5	1548	---	217.60	1245	---	511.13

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	29	4	.35	51	82	18	20	14	.75
2	27	4	.30	30	17	1.4	21	13	.70
3	27	4	.30	34	9	.74	19	11	.57
4	27	4	.29	27	6	.49	19	10	.52
5	26	4	.28	26	5	.35	19	10	.52
6	26	4	.27	25	5	.34	19	9	.47
7	27	5	.43	24	4	.29	20	7	.40
8	28	8	.64	23	4	.24	20	5	.30
9	25	11	.75	23	4	.24	24	4	.25
10	25	14	.95	22	3	.19	23	4	.29
11	25	13	.86	21	3	.16	24	15	1.3
12	25	9	.59	22	3	.18	21	8	.50
13	25	6	.43	21	3	.17	19	5	.26
14	24	5	.36	21	3	.16	19	5	.26
15	25	6	.39	20	3	.16	23	5	.33
16	23	6	.38	23	9	1.2	21	5	.29
17	22	6	.37	28	21	2.0	20	5	.27
18	22	6	.36	21	7	.41	19	4	.23
19	22	6	.36	21	7	.41	18	5	.24
20	21	7	.42	29	16	1.5	18	6	.29
21	21	7	.40	27	12	.87	17	7	.33
22	e22	6	e.34	22	2	.15	17	6	.27
23	e25	6	e.40	21	2	.11	16	5	.22
24	e25	6	e.40	20	2	.10	17	5	.27
25	e24	7	e.45	20	3	.15	21	7	.42
26	e22	8	e.48	20	6	.33	17	10	.48
27	e21	8	e.46	19	12	.59	37	58	15
28	e21	10	e.55	19	14	.72	34	40	5.2
29	46	59	9.8	---	---	---	19	11	.60
30	59	114	38	---	---	---	72	195	106
31	48	74	21	---	---	---	33	108	11
TOTAL	835	---	81.36	680	---	31.65	706	---	148.53

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	21	40	2.4	45	59	8.5	50	15	2.1
2	19	8	.39	77	252	93	45	9	1.1
3	18	5	.26	106	349	183	42	8	.90
4	17	4	.20	61	92	17	40	7	.76
5	17	3	.16	66	111	35	37	6	.66
6	19	9	.73	60	103	24	36	5	.53
7	17	9	.45	70	140	37	35	4	.38
8	32	51	16	54	45	7.7	35	3	.33
9	19	12	.69	61	58	11	42	32	6.3
10	19	11	.60	53	54	9.4	39	45	5.6
11	43	69	20	46	19	2.3	35	7	.68
12	44	78	11	42	13	1.5	38	19	2.6
13	66	191	123	40	11	1.1	33	9	.91
14	241	1030	4750	38	9	.92	30	5	.40
15	e54	82	e15	38	8	.80	29	5	.40
16	37	29	2.8	58	81	25	30	5	.38
17	59	121	34	41	36	4.6	26	5	.34
18	41	100	13	37	13	1.2	25	5	.36
19	e35	30	e3.0	36	7	.68	51	68	12
20	e33	15	e1.3	38	5	.51	40	24	3.0
21	e94	422	e293	32	5	.43	28	10	.76
22	47	61	9.5	31	5	.43	26	6	.46
23	38	45	7.8	108	454	296	25	4	.30
24	37	37	5.7	51	90	15	24	5	.32
25	32	24	2.3	83	234	132	24	7	.47
26	26	16	1.2	91	275	139	23	9	.55
27	36	39	6.9	65	271	50	23	8	.50
28	33	34	3.9	119	583	682	22	7	.44
29	96	320	249	68	135	27	50	77	27
30	72	145	37	91	306	205	35	41	5.6
31	---	---	---	66	46	9.2	---	---	---
TOTAL	1362	---	5611.28	1872	---	2020.27	1018	---	76.13

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	24	12	.76	17	5	.24	88	443	431
2	24	9	.57	17	7	.31	63	104	23
3	23	10	.60	17	9	.40	44	57	7.2
4	24	11	.66	17	10	.46	34	32	3.3
5	25	11	.68	17	10	.47	57	114	42
6	24	10	.60	26	18	1.5	342	1420	7320
7	26	15	1.3	21	10	.59	221	971	2740
8	25	11	.85	17	8	.36	e106	261	e92
9	22	4	.26	33	55	18	e71	79	e18
10	21	3	.20	28	27	3.2	87	176	80
11	23	3	.19	22	16	1.2	68	95	20
12	22	2	.16	20	16	.97	52	24	3.4
13	20	2	.10	17	12	.56	52	43	7.3
14	23	2	.11	16	11	.50	44	36	4.5
15	20	2	.12	17	9	.40	40	13	1.3
16	21	2	.11	62	104	25	38	9	.91
17	18	2	.10	29	29	2.7	37	6	.63
18	18	2	.10	22	11	.68	e38	7	e.77
19	18	2	.13	21	8	.47	e36	10	e.98
20	19	3	.18	19	6	.33	e44	10	e1.2
21	20	4	.20	19	5	.25	e36	10	e.98
22	26	12	1.1	19	3	.15	e50	58	e14
23	23	10	.69	19	2	.10	56	133	24
24	23	4	.28	17	2	.10	43	60	7.6
25	20	5	.28	19	8	.63	37	50	5.0
26	20	5	.25	19	12	.67	38	41	4.1
27	18	5	.26	16	6	.29	35	32	3.2
28	17	6	.28	72	636	607	37	24	2.4
29	16	7	.30	104	432	564	34	17	1.7
30	17	6	.29	56	89	19	31	14	1.1
31	16	5	.25	46	63	12	---	---	---
TOTAL	656	---	11.96	861	---	1262.53	1959	---	10861.57
YEAR	15606		35613.51						

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN
50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued
WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
		OCT 1992					
01...	1727	865	5310	12400	46	--	61
10...	1703	5030	22800	310000	19	16	28
APR 1993							
14...	1730	4770	13400	172000	27	32	36
AUG							
28...	1758	397	8290	8890	19	27	36
SEP							
06...	1720	1780	12800	61700	19	25	33

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
	OCT 1992						
01...	77	--	79	89	94	98	99.4
10...	36	45	57	69	82	94	99.8
APR 1993							
14...	46	56	71	83	92	97	99.4
AUG							
28...	61	79	90	96	98	99	100
SEP							
06...	42	52	62	76	88	96	99.8

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDEED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1992					
01...	1627	237	1640	1050	88
01...	2107	170	3310	1520	93
08...	1915	241	4680	3040	91
10...	1803	1650	9570	42600	69
14...	1910	420	2180	2470	66
18...	1717	615	1810	3000	85
FEB 1993					
01...	1356	38	101	10	96
APR					
14...	2055	231	7130	4450	91
21...	1553	290	1140	893	80
MAY					
02...	1857	251	821	556	85
02...	2113	130	1560	548	89
03...	1550	212	1030	590	92
03...	1745	230	1620	1010	89
06...	1107	45	128	16	98
23...	1730	413	1630	1820	82
AUG					
10...	0806	27	381	28	99
SEP					
01...	1650	197	4600	2450	76
06...	1805	2820	11600	88300	58

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028400 RIO TANAMA AT CHARCO HONDO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'52", long 66°42'52", Hydrologic Unit 21010002 on right bank at abandoned power house at Charco Hondo, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) upstream from mouth, and 4 mi (6 km) south of Arecibo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--57.6 mi² (149.2 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1969 to June 1971, October 1981 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 60 ft (18 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Diversion 0.8 mi (1.3 km) upstream for municipal supply of Arecibo.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	236	e162	e120	e83	e180	40	53	106	107	50	35	130
2	158	e150	e110	e78	e110	42	45	111	98	48	36	103
3	96	e140	e131	e78	e130	41	48	230	103	49	36	78
4	103	e180	e120	e78	e100	39	41	223	88	45	36	62
5	139	e153	e139	e76	e72	39	41	126	76	44	36	123
6	82	e140	e130	e76	e58	40	41	159	e74	43	43	540
7	81	e139	e120	e80	e52	40	45	273	e72	43	43	447
8	156	e139	e110	e82	e48	40	77	256	e72	49	37	296
9	119	e130	e100	e72	e45	44	81	149	e74	42	35	e122
10	388	e130	e98	e72	e44	42	47	130	84	40	67	e150
11	196	e129	e99	e72	42	49	44	105	66	41	38	e120
12	149	e129	e93	e72	41	56	101	99	69	47	42	e93
13	e150	e140	e160	e72	41	42	97	93	99	40	36	e93
14	e171	e170	e320	e68	40	41	290	80	99	42	35	e79
15	e160	e140	e200	e72	40	43	e135	76	65	42	36	e70
16	e160	e230	e110	e68	39	42	e82	118	61	42	82	e68
17	e240	e180	e100	e66	50	46	e130	144	56	38	69	e66
18	e250	e169	e95	e66	42	42	e90	82	68	37	46	111
19	e160	e160	e98	e66	40	40	e80	69	101	35	43	165
20	e149	e220	e100	e62	46	40	e77	78	95	35	39	129
21	e140	e180	e94	e62	55	40	e241	71	63	36	37	81
22	e165	e170	e108	e66	44	41	e244	68	57	44	37	80
23	e175	e160	e100	e74	40	45	e84	179	54	64	39	103
24	e180	e153	e94	e74	40	46	e78	168	52	40	38	96
25	e165	e150	e90	e71	40	54	e68	123	50	39	35	77
26	e145	e140	e140	e68	43	49	e60	162	49	40	39	87
27	e130	e150	e110	e64	42	48	79	137	48	48	36	70
28	e120	e172	e90	e64	41	88	123	222	47	37	86	77
29	e150	e140	e97	e200	---	47	176	257	55	35	153	94
30	e251	e130	e90	e269	---	104	199	153	89	34	127	71
31	e190	---	e86	e160	---	104	---	148	---	34	73	---
TOTAL	5154	4675	3652	2631	1605	1514	2997	4395	2191	1303	1570	3881
MEAN	166	156	118	84.9	57.3	48.8	99.9	142	73.0	42.0	50.6	129
MAX	388	230	320	269	180	104	290	273	107	64	153	540
MIN	81	129	86	62	39	39	41	68	47	34	35	62
AC-FT	10220	9270	7240	5220	3180	3000	5940	8720	4350	2580	3110	7700
CFSM	2.89	2.71	2.05	1.47	1.00	.85	1.73	2.46	1.27	.73	.88	2.25
IN.	3.33	3.02	2.36	1.70	1.04	.98	1.94	2.84	1.42	.84	1.01	2.51

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1969 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	
MEAN	170	145	82.0	55.3	45.8	39.9	73.0	139	88.0	68.0	74.8	115										
MAX	335	260	219	90.8	85.1	70.0	141	371	179	120	125	216										
(WY)	1990	1982	1982	1982	1971	1971	1986	1986	1970	1969	1991	1984										
MIN	72.1	71.5	36.4	22.3	16.7	16.6	25.9	15.8	23.3	22.0	37.4	59.7										
(WY)	1983	1988	1989	1989	1989	1988	1989	1989	1989	1989	1987	1986										

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1969 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	36827	35568	
ANNUAL MEAN	101	97.4	88.8
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			124
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			51.3
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	483	May 23	540
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	29	Mar 14	34
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	31	Mar 13	35
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			8010
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			15.48
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			27
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	73050	70550	64340
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.75	1.69	1.54
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	23.78	22.97	20.95
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	180	170	180
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	77	78	66
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	37	40	28

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50029000 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO AT CENTRAL CAMBALACHE, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'20", long 66°42'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, at bridge on unimproved road, about 500 ft (152 m) upstream from Central Cambalache, near Highway 2, 8.3 mi (13.4 km) downstream from Dos Bocas Reservoir, 1.9 mi (3.1 km) downstream from Rio Tanamá, and 1.6 mi (2.6 km) southeast of Arecibo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--200 mi² (520 km²), approximately.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1963-66, 1969 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
23...	0745	E500	203	7.1	25.5	31	6.0	72	<10	K820	3900
JAN 1993											
04...	1025	145	301	7.1	24.0	2.7	0.6	7	34	280	K110
FEB											
12...	0900	109	286	7.7	24.0	3.5	5.4	63	<10	490	360
APR											
23...	0910	200	224	7.1	24.0	140	6.6	77	86	2200	2500
JUN											
14...	0945	191	275	7.3	25.0	16	7.0	83	<10	4100	2500
SEP											
15...	1000	E500	225	7.0	25.8	8.2	7.0	81	31	K 760	340

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
23...	86	2	26	5.1	7.5	0.4	2.1	110	<0.5	9.2	8.2
JAN 1993											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
FEB											
12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
APR											
23...	98	11	32	4.3	6.8	0.3	2.4	93	<0.5	9.7	8.5
JUN											
14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
SEP											
15...	98	7	30	5.5	8.6	0.4	2.3	82	--	11	10

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
23...	<0.10	19	144	--	5	0.700	0.010	0.710	0.030	0.17
JAN 1993										
04...	--	--	--	--	41	0.690	0.010	0.700	0.020	0.58
FEB										
12...	--	--	--	--	9	0.490	0.010	0.500	0.010	0.29
APR										
23...	0.10	13	133	71.6	57	0.430	0.080	0.500	0.080	0.52
JUN										
14...	--	--	--	--	22	0.390	0.010	0.400	0.010	0.59
SEP										
15...	<0.10	18	141	--	15	0.690	0.010	0.700	0.020	1.6

E = estimate
K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50029000 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO AT CENTRAL CAMBALACHE, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1992 23...	0.20	0.91	4.0	0.060	<1	<100	<10	<1	<1	<10
JAN 1993 04...	0.60	1.3	5.8	0.030	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 12...	0.30	0.80	3.5	0.030	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 23...	0.60	1.0	6.8	0.120	<1	<100	20	<1	3	<10
JUN 14...	0.60	1.1	4.7	0.030	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 15...	1.6	2.3	10	0.030	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA-NESE, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE-NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE, TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY-LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB-STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1992 23...	490	5	60	<0.10	<1	<1	30	<0.01	6	<0.01
JAN 1993 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 23...	1400	<1	80	<0.10	<1	<1	20	<0.01	2	<0.01
JUN 14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP 15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR-DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI-AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI-ELDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO-SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993 26...	0945	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010

DATE	ENDRIN WATER UNFLTRD REC (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA-CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA-CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH-OXY-CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL-PARA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993 26...	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH-THA-LENES, POLY-CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER-THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX-APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI-THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993 26...	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

Figure 16.--Río Grande de Manatí basin.

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50030460 RIO OROCOVIS AT OROCOVIS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°13'25", long 66°23'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on right bank, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) south of junction of Highways 155 and 156 in Orocovis, 600 ft (183 m) upstream from Río Batijas, and 250 ft (76 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 599.

DRAINAGE AREA.--5.03 mi² (13.03 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1981 to September 1982, October 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 500 ft (152 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Low flow affected by diversions for water supply. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e.70	1.1	8.6	2.3	3.4	1.1	1.3	37	7.1	4.0	1.5	1.1
2	e.30	.75	5.3	1.8	1.3	1.4	1.1	121	5.7	3.6	1.8	1.3
3	e.30	11	3.3	1.9	2.5	1.1	.91	57	5.6	3.6	1.5	1.4
4	e.20	8.1	2.0	1.7	1.3	1.3	1.1	21	5.0	4.8	1.3	24
5	e9.0	4.7	1.4	1.5	e1.1	1.4	1.5	13	4.7	3.8	1.6	25
6	54	1.7	1.2	1.5	e1.0	1.4	1.8	10	4.2	3.6	1.2	26
7	6.9	1.2	1.0	4.8	e.74	1.5	1.7	9.2	3.9	3.2	1.2	16
8	1.5	.85	1.1	2.6	e.70	.93	6.3	8.4	6.4	3.3	1.5	4.1
9	.72	.71	.92	1.7	e.80	1.1	2.4	9.7	4.9	2.5	1.9	2.5
10	.40	.57	.76	1.4	e.60	1.1	2.5	8.6	4.6	2.7	1.8	2.5
11	.26	.44	.74	1.3	e.64	1.1	6.5	7.9	3.5	16	2.5	2.0
12	.23	.47	.94	1.5	e.74	.89	7.2	7.3	3.6	9.8	1.6	2.8
13	.21	.38	.97	1.4	e.70	.85	61	6.6	3.2	7.6	1.4	1.6
14	.42	.35	12	1.4	e1.0	.98	23	13	3.9	9.7	1.0	2.1
15	.63	.33	9.2	.95	e.98	.92	31	8.2	4.2	4.4	1.6	1.6
16	.29	.52	3.5	.88	e1.7	1.4	18	6.6	3.9	3.6	24	1.3
17	.28	.47	3.2	.73	2.7	1.4	13	5.1	2.3	3.3	5.4	9.0
18	5.3	.35	2.3	.83	1.9	1.7	5.1	5.0	2.3	3.8	2.5	1.8
19	2.7	.34	1.9	.75	1.2	1.3	e2.0	3.9	24	4.3	2.2	.93
20	.70	3.6	2.0	.88	7.8	1.4	e2.0	4.6	21	3.7	1.7	1.0
21	.27	1.4	1.7	.67	5.4	1.4	e1.7	4.8	7.4	2.1	1.7	.91
22	.40	4.7	2.9	1.2	2.2	1.5	e1.8	4.7	5.6	4.4	1.8	.96
23	43	5.1	2.3	1.7	2.8	1.7	e1.2	99	4.4	5.3	8.3	5.6
24	16	1.8	3.1	.67	1.5	1.4	e5.0	32	4.6	5.5	2.0	4.6
25	7.8	.91	2.9	.79	1.2	2.1	e3.0	25	3.8	3.3	1.6	1.0
26	2.3	.58	51	.60	1.2	1.4	e1.7	21	3.7	3.0	1.3	.91
27	17	7.1	21	.90	1.0	1.6	e1.4	13	3.8	3.2	1.4	.86
28	9.1	67	8.8	5.5	1.0	1.3	119	9.7	4.2	2.4	2.6	8.2
29	6.1	71	5.6	14	---	1.3	229	8.2	3.9	2.2	2.5	3.5
30	6.2	31	4.1	2.4	---	1.2	77	7.4	4.1	2.0	1.6	1.0
31	2.3	---	3.0	4.5	---	1.2	---	6.8	---	1.7	1.5	---
TOTAL	195.51	228.52	168.73	64.75	49.10	40.37	630.21	594.7	169.5	136.4	85.5	155.57
MEAN	6.31	7.62	5.44	2.09	1.75	1.30	21.0	19.2	5.65	4.40	2.76	5.19
MAX	54	71	51	14	7.8	2.1	229	121	24	16	24	26
MIN	.20	.33	.74	.60	.60	.85	.91	3.9	2.3	1.7	1.0	.86
AC-FT	388	453	335	128	97	80	1250	1180	336	271	170	309
CFSM	1.25	1.51	1.08	.42	.35	.26	4.18	3.81	1.12	.87	.55	1.03
IN.	1.45	1.69	1.25	.48	.36	.30	4.66	4.40	1.25	1.01	.63	1.15

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1981 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001
MEAN	22.9	7.69	6.59	7.90	2.38	1.86	7.12	14.5	5.44	3.76	4.48	12.2
MAX	58.0	15.2	15.8	34.3	2.97	2.46	21.0	31.8	15.2	8.40	12.3	39.6
(WY)	1990	1991	1982	1992	1992	1990	1993	1981	1992	1991	1989	1989
MIN	4.59	2.19	1.69	1.47	1.75	1.30	1.32	1.42	1.16	1.45	1.03	1.72
(WY)	1992	1992	1989	1989	1993	1993	1982	1989	1982	1982	1982	1992

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1981 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	3749.42	2518.86		
ANNUAL MEAN	10.2	6.90	7.82	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			9.35	1992
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			6.17	1982
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	415	Jan 5	229	Apr 29
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.20	Oct 4	.20	Oct 4
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.33	Oct 11	.33	Oct 11
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			1570	Apr 29
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			10.38	Apr 29
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	7440	5000	5670	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.04	1.37	1.56	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	27.73	18.63	21.13	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	17	13	13	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	2.1	2.1	2.2	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.86	.74	1.1	

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50030700 RIO OROCOVIS NEAR OROCOVIS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'20", long 66°22'58", at flat low bridge about 300 ft (91 m) northwest of Highway 568, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) north of Orocovis plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--10.1 mi² (26.2 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water year 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992										
15...	0850	9.4	313	7.9	22.0	16	5.9	72	11	3400 2400
DEC 02...	0840	18	238	6.7	22.0	84	5.0	60	<10	2100 3900
FEB 1993										
18...	1120	8.8	270	8.2	22.0	7.6	7.0	83	<10	2500 K180
APR 22...	0905	7.9	313	7.7	21.0	46	7.5	92	10	K1700 3400
JUN 11...	1115	11	283	8.0	24.5	32	7.5	99	<10	3000 280
SEP 17...	1300	6.0	287	7.8	25.5	1.8	8.3	105	<10	1200 660

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CACO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CACO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1992											
15...	120	2	28	11	12	0.5	1.7	130	<0.5	11	10
DEC 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	98	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
APR 22...	140	12	35	12	14	0.5	1.8	130	<0.5	11	14
JUN 11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	95	--	--	--
SEP 17...	120	5	30	10	12	0.5	1.8	100	--	11	15

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
15...	0.10	31	172	4.36	8	0.970	0.030	1.00	0.060	0.44
DEC 02...	--	--	--	--	27	1.39	0.010	1.40	0.030	0.47
FEB 1993										
18...	--	--	--	--	8	0.990	0.010	1.00	0.010	0.49
APR 22...	0.10	34	200	4.26	45	1.18	0.020	1.20	0.010	0.92
JUN 11...	--	--	--	--	<1	1.06	0.040	1.10	0.080	0.92
SEP 17...	0.10	35	175	2.83	13	0.75	0.050	0.800	0.120	1.2

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50031200 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI NEAR MOROVIS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°17'45", long 66°24'47", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on right bank, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) downstream from Quebrada Perchas, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) upstream from Río Sana Muerto, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) south of Morovis.

DRAINAGE AREA.--55.2 mi² (143.0 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1965 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and concrete control. Elevation of gage is 440 ft (134 m), from topographic map. Feb. 2, 1966 to Apr. 27, 1967, staff gage read twice daily.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Public water-supply pumpage, about 300 ft (91 m) above the station, influences low-flow discharges. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	97	39	116	87	176	34	21	530	93	53	50	40
2	56	35	91	76	85	38	21	730	89	50	50	37
3	33	51	66	74	78	35	20	402	85	57	47	34
4	106	156	55	76	63	32	19	207	81	59	44	82
5	305	133	47	66	56	31	19	173	75	49	44	102
6	284	74	44	69	49	32	18	160	74	47	45	211
7	154	56	39	126	46	31	18	146	70	48	43	185
8	75	45	35	141	43	32	109	185	74	59	40	139
9	48	43	35	91	41	32	165	490	78	46	40	72
10	41	39	33	76	39	32	160	220	74	45	40	56
11	60	36	31	67	38	28	322	178	65	143	42	53
12	32	55	28	66	39	29	238	155	63	150	41	43
13	25	102	28	61	40	29	383	138	61	79	38	39
14	24	65	105	58	36	28	436	153	59	102	36	38
15	29	45	213	54	35	28	356	137	58	68	37	43
16	41	54	93	51	42	42	304	124	66	58	202	65
17	171	67	88	50	63	51	241	117	54	54	133	194
18	275	54	85	47	42	41	180	111	52	49	64	227
19	187	48	70	44	37	33	127	106	110	47	50	255
20	101	47	58	44	47	33	151	104	169	48	44	141
21	55	61	49	43	71	31	189	102	94	47	39	78
22	53	95	81	50	51	30	165	106	78	80	41	58
23	104	156	89	78	41	35	107	270	66	125	67	e92
24	158	104	93	51	40	36	87	189	60	128	43	176
25	169	76	101	48	37	29	93	169	57	108	37	81
26	90	60	492	45	37	25	74	178	53	85	37	68
27	56	169	270	42	36	25	68	137	51	76	36	79
28	69	290	175	44	34	22	203	120	52	60	47	99
29	62	196	142	181	---	20	949	115	56	54	64	88
30	93	182	119	99	---	30	506	108	80	53	67	66
31	50	---	101	128	---	33	---	104	---	53	55	---
TOTAL	3103	2633	3072	2233	1442	987	5749	6164	2197	2180	1663	2941
MEAN	100	87.8	99.1	72.0	51.5	31.8	192	199	73.2	70.3	53.6	98.0
MAX	305	290	492	181	176	51	949	730	169	150	202	255
MIN	24	35	28	42	34	20	18	102	51	45	36	34
AC-FT	6150	5220	6090	4430	2860	1960	11400	12230	4360	4320	3300	5830
CFSM	1.81	1.59	1.80	1.30	.93	.58	3.47	3.60	1.33	1.27	.97	1.78
IN.	2.09	1.77	2.07	1.50	.97	.67	3.87	4.15	1.48	1.47	1.12	1.98

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1965 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1965	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	
MEAN	165	155	117	83.5	65.9	69.1	117	171	65.5	49.2	58.8	93.4																		
MAX	1037	491	522	191	179	226	412	915	173	157	435	386																		
(WY)	1971	1971	1966	1992	1969	1972	1969	1985	1987	1979	1979	1979																		
MIN	24.0	28.3	27.9	24.7	23.4	12.7	10.6	23.6	16.9	18.5	9.70	25.0																		
(WY)	1978	1974	1984	1984	1984	1984	1984	1977	1977	1977	1984	1977																		

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1965 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	32289		34364			
ANNUAL MEAN	88.2		94.1		102	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					248	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					40.3	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	2480	Jan 5	949	Apr 29	17100	May 18 1985
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	17	Sep 28	18	Apr 6	5.7	Aug 20 1984
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	20	Sep 11	19	Apr 1	6.8	Aug 18 1984
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			6040		48000	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			6.56		17.89	
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			17		4.4	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	64050		68160		73670	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.60		1.71		1.84	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	21.76		23.16		25.03	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	170		181		179	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	48		61		51	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	26		33		24	

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50031200 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI NEAR MOROVIS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1968 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992	15...	27	269	7.8	27.0	6.4	6.4	80	11	K190	K140
DEC	02...	93	245	6.7	24.0	72	6.0	71	12	580	1800
FEB 1993	18...	41	265	7.7	22.0	23	6.8	77	<10	1800	710
APR	22...	130	220	7.4	24.0	100	8.8	104	13	K8000	13000
JUN	11...	65	262	7.7	25.5	2.0	8.5	103	<10	K620	K60000
SEP	23...	47	257	7.7	25.5	6.5	6.8	82	<10	1000	200

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD MG/L AS CaCO3	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET MG/L AS CaCO3	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992	88	8	21	8.7	11	0.5	2.0	120	<0.5	11	12
DEC	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	98	--	--	--
FEB 1993	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--
APR	86	10	20	8.8	12	0.6	2.1	78	<0.5	9.0	13
JUN	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	98	--	--	--
SEP	100	15	25	10	11	0.5	2.5	110	--	9.5	14

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992	<0.10	26	145	10.6	3	0.580	0.020	0.600	0.070	0.33
DEC	--	--	--	--	67	0.490	0.010	0.500	0.010	0.19
FEB 1993	--	--	--	--	25	1.67	0.030	1.70	0.060	1.4
APR	<0.10	25	137	48.0	135	1.27	0.030	1.30	0.050	0.85
JUN	--	--	--	--	3	0.96	0.040	1.00	0.080	1.3
SEP	0.10	27	165	20.9	19	0.76	0.760	0.040	0.800	1.5

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50032290 LAGO EL GUINEO AT DAMSITE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'41", long 66°31'36", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, at damsite on Río Toro Negro, 3.0 mi (4.8 km) northwest from Villalba plaza and 1.9 mi (3.1 km) northeast of Cerro Maravillas. The reservoir itself fixes the territorial limits between the Municipality of Ciales and Orocovis.

DRAINAGE AREA.--1.64 mi² (4.25 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Guineo was completed in 1931. It provides a maximum storage of approximately 2,180 ac-ft (2.688 hm³) for power and irrigation. Waters are discharged through an outlet power tunnel into the Río Toro Negro and conveyed to the head water works of Toro Negro Hydroelectric Plant No.2, for energy generation at Toro Negro Hydroelectric plant No.1, and are discharged into the Guayabal Reservoir to be later used for irrigation at South Coast Irrigation System. The dam is rockfill with a vertical concrete corewall, rock toes, and riprap facing of upstream slope, with a total length of 565 ft (172 m), a maximum structural height of 125 ft (38 m) to top of corewall. At a maximum reservoir water surface elevation the uncontrolled morning-glory tunnel spillway crest has an elevation of 2,966 ft (904 m) above mean sea level and a design capacity of 7,000 ft³/s. The dam is owned by Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation 2,961.70 ft (902.73 m), Oct. 21, 1990; minimum elevation, 2,919.79 ft (899.95 m), May 27, 1988.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 2,961.21 ft (902.58 m), Oct. 23; minimum elevation, 2,936.10 ft (894.92 m), Sept. 4.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
2,872	0	2,943	1,029
2,919	361	2,950	1,308
2,925	491	2,961	1,852

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	2952.02	2960.76	2959.95	2955.10	2955.61	2956.13	2956.54	2960.23	A	2954.59	2947.40	2937.32
2	2952.18	2960.72	2959.58	2955.24	2955.77	2956.17	2956.34	2960.45	2960.18	2954.21	2946.46	2936.97
3	2952.32	2960.72	2959.25	2955.36	2955.91	2956.20	2956.36	2960.63	2959.99	2954.06	2945.16	2936.67
4	2953.31	2960.72	2958.87	2955.00	2956.03	2956.25	2956.39	2960.56	2959.56	2954.21	2944.25	2937.87
5	2954.01	2960.71	2958.47	2954.80	2956.12	2956.29	2956.24	2960.53	2958.80	2954.34	2943.26	2938.24
6	2955.82	2960.71	2958.67	2954.90	2956.22	2956.32	2956.08	2960.55	2959.00	2953.94	2942.86	2938.43
7	2956.77	2960.71	2958.21	2954.99	2956.30	2956.35	2956.09	2960.44	2958.72	2953.53	2942.30	2938.14
8	2957.25	2960.71	A	2955.07	2956.40	2956.40	2955.89	2960.55	2958.55	2953.11	2942.39	2938.43
9	2958.99	2960.71	A	2955.15	2956.48	2956.41	2955.91	2960.78	2958.46	2952.57	A	2938.66
10	2959.51	2960.70	A	2955.23	2956.56	2956.31	2956.03	2960.70	A	2952.07	2940.93	2939.04
11	2959.87	2960.70	A	2955.31	2956.64	2956.35	2956.13	2960.68	A	2952.80	2940.52	2939.24
12	2960.17	2960.69	A	2954.91	2956.74	2956.39	2956.04	2960.47	A	2952.49	2940.00	2939.40
13	2960.40	2960.73	A	2954.97	2956.28	2956.42	2956.49	2960.19	A	A	2939.19	2939.54
14	2960.63	2960.75	A	2955.09	2956.36	2956.46	2956.50	2960.24	A	A	A	2939.67
15	2960.70	2960.69	A	2955.16	2956.42	2956.52	2956.39	2959.92	A	A	A	2939.80
16	2960.72	2960.78	A	2954.95	2956.54	2956.56	2956.45	2959.75	A	2952.18	A	2940.09
17	2960.73	2960.38	2955.55	2954.47	2956.62	2956.58	2956.72	2959.30	A	2951.78	A	2941.90
18	2960.69	2960.08	2955.67	2954.53	2956.68	2956.62	2956.89	2958.88	A	2951.91	2939.68	2943.19
19	2960.69	2959.78	2955.81	2954.08	2956.74	2956.64	2957.06	2958.44	A	2951.35	2939.29	2943.54
20	2960.69	2960.72	2955.95	2954.16	2956.02	2956.69	2957.12	2958.22	A	2950.89	2939.22	2944.18
21	2960.69	2960.30	2956.07	2954.24	2956.10	2956.72	2957.53	2959.28	A	2950.39	2938.51	2944.43
22	2960.74	2960.60	2956.23	2954.34	2956.16	2956.75	2957.64	2959.21	A	2950.09	2938.63	2943.91
23	2960.82	2960.20	2956.35	2953.86	2956.22	2956.67	2957.70	2960.28	A	2949.69	2938.24	2944.49
24	2960.87	2959.80	2956.04	2953.92	2956.29	2956.71	2957.77	2960.20	2956.39	2948.75	2937.81	2944.78
25	2960.72	2959.80	2956.18	2953.98	2956.01	2956.75	2957.82	2960.16	2956.10	A	2937.44	2945.01
26	2960.71	2960.01	2955.95	2954.04	2955.97	2956.79	2957.65	2960.73	2955.73	A	2936.92	2945.22
27	2960.70	2960.21	2956.09	2954.14	2956.02	2956.83	2957.70	2960.57	2955.87	A	2936.88	A
28	2960.70	2960.13	2955.68	2955.34	2956.07	2956.85	2958.45	2960.28	2955.74	2948.33	2937.63	A
29	2960.78	2960.81	2955.50	2956.39	---	2956.88	2959.57	A	2955.39	2947.82	2937.86	A
30	2960.72	2960.25	2955.10	2956.08	---	2956.70	2959.96	A	2955.00	2947.20	2937.71	A
31	2960.76	---	2954.99	2955.87	---	2956.71	---	A	---	2947.31	2937.49	A
MEAN	2958.89	2960.49	---	2954.86	2956.26	2956.53	2956.98	---	---	---	---	---
MAX	2960.87	2960.81	---	2956.39	2956.74	2956.88	2959.96	---	---	---	---	---
MIN	2952.02	2959.78	---	2953.86	2955.61	2956.13	2955.89	---	---	---	---	---

A No gage-height record

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50032590 LAGO DE MATRULLAS AT DAMSITE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'46", long 66°28'50", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, in concrete house at damsite, and 5.8 mi (9.3 km) southwest of Orocovis.

DRAINAGE AREA.--4.46 mi² (11.55 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Matrullas was completed in 1934. The dam is an earthfill structure about 120 ft (37 m) height, a top width of 30 ft (9 m) and a length of 710 ft (216 m), and has a maximum storage capacity of about 4,274 ac-ft (5.220 hm³) at top of dam elevation. The Matrullas Dam is owned by the Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority and is part of the Toro Negro Hydroelectric Project; a project developed by the P.R.E.P.A. for the primary purpose of generating electric power. Discharges from the Power Plants are collected by the Jacaguas River which flows into Guayabal Dam, at which dam they are regulated for irrigation of lands served by the Juana Díaz Canal. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation 2,413.56 ft (735.65 m), Jan. 6, 1992; minimum elevation, 2,392.81 ft (729.33 m), Sept. 10, 1989.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 2,412.38 ft (735.29 m), Apr. 29,30 and May 3; minimum elevation, 2,403.93 ft (732.72 m), Sept. 28.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
2,338	2	2,399	1,845
2,360	302	2,415	2,945

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	2410.22	2411.85	2411.54	2410.73	2409.30	2411.19	2411.13	2412.05	2411.72	2410.33	2407.49	2406.21
2	2410.22	2411.67	2411.44	2410.95	2409.27	2411.20	2410.99	2412.37	2411.65	2410.14	2407.56	2406.04
3	2409.99	2411.72	2411.38	2411.19	2409.25	2411.20	2411.06	2412.01	2411.52	2409.93	2407.66	2405.82
4	2409.62	2411.54	2411.30	2411.17	2409.08	2411.21	2411.16	2411.81	2411.50	2409.98	2407.81	2406.14
5	2409.98	2411.36	2411.19	2411.09	2408.87	2411.21	2411.12	2411.72	2411.66	2410.15	2407.97	2406.87
6	2411.19	2411.24	2411.37	2411.13	2408.93	2411.27	2411.09	2411.67	2411.72	2410.15	2407.91	2406.99
7	2411.43	2411.08	2411.37	2410.96	2409.12	2411.37	2411.05	2411.65	2411.58	2410.09	2407.94	2406.83
8	2411.50	2411.15	2411.22	2410.63	2409.10	2411.38	2411.02	2411.73	2411.46	2409.99	2408.07	2406.62
9	2411.40	2411.13	2411.05	2410.25	2409.11	2411.37	2411.12	2411.77	2411.34	2409.84	2408.02	2406.35
10	2411.23	2411.01	2410.85	2410.25	2409.15	2411.36	2411.22	2411.73	2411.17	2409.59	2407.82	2406.21
11	2411.16	2410.95	2410.63	2410.43	2409.21	2411.35	2412.08	2411.70	2410.99	2409.87	2407.55	2406.02
12	2411.31	2410.91	2410.46	2410.33	2409.26	2411.34	2411.64	2411.73	2410.72	2410.02	2407.34	2405.69
13	2411.25	2410.70	2410.61	2410.05	2409.15	2411.40	2411.56	2411.66	2410.83	2410.09	2407.16	2405.41
14	2411.18	2410.40	2410.67	2410.70	2409.19	2411.47	2411.60	2411.77	2410.81	2410.27	2407.16	2405.12
15	2411.21	2410.50	2410.70	2409.23	2409.33	2411.46	2411.62	2411.58	2410.66	2410.12	2407.26	2404.82
16	2411.13	2410.90	2410.61	2408.85	2409.44	2411.45	2411.59	2411.44	2410.51	2409.88	2407.72	2404.53
17	2411.03	2411.13	2410.41	2408.50	2409.49	2411.37	2411.65	2411.37	2410.27	2409.62	2407.73	2404.29
18	2411.11	2411.07	2410.17	2408.54	2409.51	2411.24	2411.66	2411.23	2410.08	2409.63	2407.64	2404.32
19	2411.09	2410.95	2410.27	2408.42	2409.57	2411.15	2411.63	2411.07	2410.59	2409.47	2407.50	2404.46
20	2411.06	2411.44	2410.53	2408.13	2409.87	2411.26	2411.52	2410.90	2411.21	2409.22	2407.28	2404.40
21	2411.01	2411.47	2410.46	2407.69	2410.21	2411.37	2411.45	2410.74	2411.29	2409.01	2406.94	2404.18
22	2410.97	2411.63	2410.32	2407.57	2410.33	2411.48	2411.50	2410.64	2411.41	2408.86	2406.70	2404.15
23	2411.74	2411.51	2410.11	2407.52	2410.39	2411.46	2411.48	2412.07	2411.31	2408.73	2406.64	2404.19
24	2411.72	2411.39	2409.86	2407.55	2410.44	2411.38	2411.62	2411.78	2411.18	2408.51	2406.48	2404.03
25	2411.75	2411.23	2409.96	2407.49	2410.62	2411.28	2411.65	2411.85	2411.04	2408.54	2406.31	2404.22
26	2411.60	2411.29	2410.24	2407.51	2410.79	2411.18	2411.51	2411.73	2410.87	2408.71	2406.13	2404.27
27	2411.56	2411.13	2410.67	2407.64	2410.94	2411.26	2411.39	2411.65	2410.96	2408.63	2406.07	2404.02
28	2411.41	2411.84	2410.75	2407.95	2411.10	2411.35	2411.94	2411.81	2410.90	2408.41	2406.30	2404.02
29	2411.30	2412.14	2410.68	2409.07	---	2411.31	2412.38	2411.66	2410.72	2408.20	2406.50	2404.10
30	2411.43	2411.69	2410.57	2409.30	---	2411.33	2411.94	2411.77	2410.53	2407.95	2406.49	2404.02
31	2411.45	---	2410.53	2409.31	---	2411.27	---	2411.78	---	2407.56	2406.36	---
MEAN	2411.10	2411.27	2410.71	2409.33	2409.64	2411.32	2411.48	2411.63	2411.07	2409.40	2407.21	2405.14
MAX	2411.75	2412.14	2411.54	2411.19	2411.10	2411.48	2412.38	2412.37	2411.72	2410.33	2408.07	2406.99
MIN	2409.62	2410.40	2409.86	2407.49	2408.87	2411.15	2410.99	2410.64	2410.08	2407.56	2406.07	2404.02

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 2409.95 MAX 2412.38 MIN 2404.02

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50034000 RIO BAUTA NEAR OROCOVIS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'10", long 66°27'18", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on left bank, at bridge on Highway 157 (12.1 km), and 4.2 mi (6.8 km) west of Orocovis.

DRAINAGE AREA.--16.7 mi² (43.3 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1959 to April 1966 (annual low-flow measurements only), February to September 1969 (occasional measurements only), October 1969 to September 1982, October 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Datum of gage is 772.82 ft (235.556 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	21	69	76	31	38	e9.6	9.1	e138	33	e18	10	e9.8
2	11	64	52	29	21	e13	9.1	e354	30	e16	10	e10
3	11	61	41	29	21	e12	9.2	e165	e27	e17	10	e12
4	8.6	60	35	28	18	e11	9.5	e68	25	e22	9.8	e200
5	e93	47	33	27	16	e10	9.4	e43	23	e17	9.7	e210
6	e143	38	30	28	15	10	9.1	33	22	e16	9.8	e220
7	e85	33	28	33	14	9.7	9.3	28	21	e15	9.7	e90
8	36	28	26	33	13	9.4	9.3	26	21	e16	9.6	25
9	42	26	25	27	13	9.5	11	30	21	e13	9.6	17
10	32	24	25	25	13	9.2	11	e33	20	12	9.6	14
11	39	23	24	24	12	9.0	100	29	18	e29	9.6	14
12	18	22	23	24	12	9.0	29	24	17	e26	9.8	12
13	13	22	24	23	12	9.1	181	21	17	17	9.2	10
14	e49	21	e59	24	12	9.1	76	41	16	26	9.0	10
15	e81	20	e67	22	12	9.2	e68	33	18	16	9.2	10
16	e28	27	38	22	12	9.6	e62	24	20	14	45	10
17	23	37	33	22	14	9.8	e29	19	16	13	e21	20
18	25	24	30	22	12	9.4	e28	17	15	12	13	16
19	22	23	28	22	11	9.1	19	16	48	12	12	14
20	20	50	27	21	33	9.6	15	16	e75	12	11	12
21	16	62	25	21	29	9.5	15	16	e30	11	10	12
22	e15	59	36	22	15	8.8	13	19	23	e13	10	10
23	e194	79	36	24	12	9.3	12	e274	19	e16	13	20
24	e194	49	34	22	11	11	20	e124	18	13	e11	26
25	e112	34	31	22	11	12	25	e196	17	13	e11	19
26	e55	28	101	20	10	9.7	15	e115	16	13	e10	16
27	110	27	104	20	10	9.4	13	e66	e17	e15	e11	13
28	101	e195	61	21	9.5	9.0	254	e91	e19	12	e22	25
29	58	e194	45	64	---	9.3	485	e59	e18	11	e21	23
30	68	144	37	37	---	10	170	43	e19	11	e14	14
31	48	---	34	34	---	11	---	39	---	11	e13	---
TOTAL	1771.6	1590	1268	823	431.5	305.3	1725.0	2200	699	478	392.6	1113.8
MEAN	57.1	53.0	40.9	26.5	15.4	9.85	57.5	71.0	23.3	15.4	12.7	37.1
MAX	194	195	104	64	38	13	485	354	75	29	45	220
MIN	8.6	20	23	20	9.5	8.8	9.1	16	15	11	9.0	9.8
AC-FT	3510	3150	2520	1630	856	606	3420	4360	1390	948	779	2210
CFSM	3.42	3.17	2.45	1.59	.92	.59	3.44	4.25	1.40	.92	.76	2.22
IN.	3.95	3.54	2.82	1.83	.96	.68	3.84	4.90	1.56	1.06	.87	2.48

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1969 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	96.8	58.9	30.4	21.2	14.2	15.9	28.9	51.0	20.5	17.0	22.2	53.4													
MAX	392	205	108	83.4	30.9	59.9	80.2	179	78.6	104	152	149													
(WY)	1971	1971	1971	1992	1971	1972	1980	1981	1979	1979	1979	1979													
MIN	15.8	8.14	8.95	6.62	6.26	5.57	6.23	7.05	4.10	5.22	6.76	9.82													
(WY)	1976	1974	1992	1973	1977	1977	1977	1973	1977	1974	1976	1992													

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1993 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1969 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	15451.2	12797.8																							
ANNUAL MEAN	42.2	35.1																							
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN																									
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN																									
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	922	Jan 6	485	Apr 29	3870	Oct 9	1970																		
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	7.2	Jan 2	8.6	Oct 4	3.0	Jul 23	1977																		
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	7.9	Aug 29	9.2	Mar 9	3.4	Jul 20	1977																		
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			2430	Apr 29	17800	Oct 9	1970																		
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			12.58	Apr 29	21.90	Oct 9	1970																		
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			8.4	Oct 5	2.8	Jul 23	1977																		
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	30650	25380																							
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.53	2.10																							
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	34.42	28.51																							
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	82	68																							
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	20	21																							
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	8.6	9.7																							

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50035500 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 149 AT CIALES, RP

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'46", long 66°28'06", at bridge on Highway 149, about 800 ft (244 m) upstream from confluence with Río Cialitos, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) north of Ciales plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--136 mi² (352 km²) this excludes the 6 mi² (15.5 km²) upstream from Lago El Guineo and Lago de Matrullas, flow from which is diverted to Río Jacaguas.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
21...	1155	102	223	7.6	26.5	5.1	8.4	100	14	K1700	260
DEC 22...	1130	100	262	8.0	23.1	29	8.1	92	11	3900	2900
MAR 1993											
04...	1040	133	224	8.3	24.0	2.9	7.4	88	<10	50	190
APR 29...	1400	1980	194	7.2	26.5	162	10.0	124	13	57000	6500
JUN 23...	1215	136	223	8.2	28.5	5.6	8.3	106	14	4400	K930
AUG 20...	1300	209	269	8.1	27.0	14	7.2	90	<10	3100	870

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
21...	85	1	21	7.9	10	0.5	2.4	82	<0.5	10	11
DEC 22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	93	--	--	--
MAR 1993											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
APR 29...	130	5	24	16	74	3	4.5	64	<0.5	--	--
JUN 23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
AUG 20...	92	37	22	8.9	12	0.5	2.5	100	--	9.5	13

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDE (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
21...	0.10	24	136	37.3	23	0.720	0.020	0.740	0.040	0.16
DEC 22...	--	--	--	--	9	0.430	0.070	0.500	0.030	0.37
MAR 1993										
04...	--	--	--	--	2	0.290	0.010	0.300	0.020	0.68
APR 29...	0.10	27	227	1214	<1	0.390	0.010	0.400	0.030	0.27
JUN 23...	--	--	--	--	18	0.590	0.010	0.600	0.020	0.18
AUG 20...	0.10	27	155	87.4	16	0.290	0.010	0.300	0.030	0.37

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN
 50035950 RIO CIALITOS AT HIGHWAY 649 AT CIALES, PR
 WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'18", long 66°28'28", 100 ft (30 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 649, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) upstream from mouth, and about 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west of Ciales plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.0 mi² (44.0 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969-71, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
21...	1340	5.7	235	7.1	25.5	13	8.3	100	70	3600	2200
DEC 21...	1300	12.2	312	7.9	23.2	2.4	7.8	95	<10	4500	3500
MAR 1993											
04...	1145	5.0	420	8.3	26.5	11	8.5	86	<10	540	K870
MAY 03...	1515	72	318	7.6	22.0	15	8.0	91	16	460	330
JUN 23...	1350	3.6	213	7.7	26.5	12	8.2	81	<10	K900	250
AUG 20...	1405	4.0	194	7.2	23.5	82	6.0	70	22	K60000	6800

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CACO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CACO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1992											
21...	97	1	28	6.6	10	0.4	3.3	96	<0.5	6.9	10
DEC 21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	70	--	--	--
MAR 1993											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--
MAY 03...	64	0	19	4.1	8.6	0.5	1.8	120	<0.5	7.1	9.5
JUN 23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	98	--	--	--
AUG 20...	95	2	27	6.8	12	0.5	2.0	81	--	6.5	11

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
21...	0.10	29	151	2.33	--	0.680	<0.010	0.680	0.020	0.28
DEC 21...	--	--	--	--	15	1.49	0.010	1.50	0.010	0.19
MAR 1993										
04...	--	--	--	--	<1	1.59	0.010	1.60	0.020	--
MAY 03...	0.10	24	146	28.5	24	1.18	0.020	1.20	0.040	0.16
JUN 23...	--	--	--	--	9	0.990	0.010	1.00	0.010	--
AUG 20...	<0.10	30	155	1.67	8	0.820	0.020	0.840	0.030	0.67

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50038100 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR MANATI, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, SATUR-ATION (%)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)
OCT 1992											
23...	1125	505	256	7.2	28.5	160	5.4	68	K6800	K2000	110
DEC 21...	0915	228	286	6.5	23.0	6.0	5.0	57	4200	4900	120
FEB 1993											
22...	1025	251	242	7.4	22.5	20	4.4	55	K18000	2200	100
APR 30...	1025	560	200	6.8	22.7	240	8.0	91	K60000	K120000	70
JUN 25...	0950	183	285	7.2	29.0	1.7	5.7	73	27000	370	120
SEP 23...	1210	168	256	7.2	28.1	43	6.7	86	K7600	400	110

DATE	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)
OCT 1992											
23...	91	31	7.0	10	0.4	2.3	140	9.1	11	0.10	21
DEC 21...	130	36	7.1	11	0.4	2.4	120	8.8	13	<0.10	22
FEB 1993											
22...	120	29	6.9	10	0.4	2.1	96	8.1	12	<0.10	21
APR 30...	100	22	3.7	7.2	0.4	3.2	79	8.6	10	0.10	15
JUN 25...	130	36	7.3	11	0.4	1.9	120	8.0	12	0.10	21
SEP 23...	88	33	7.3	10	0.4	2.2	110	9.7	11	0.10	21

DATE	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 180 DEG. C DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NH4)	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHORUS DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHORUS ORTHO, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHATE, ORTHO, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS PO4)
OCT 1992											
23...	157	156	213	0.880	0.360	0.46	0.50	0.240	0.060	0.060	0.18
DEC 21...	184	170	105	0.800	0.080	0.10	0.40	0.260	0.80	0.040	0.09
FEB 1993											
22...	157	152	103	0.950	0.060	0.08	0.40	0.130	0.070	0.090	0.28
APR 30...	140	112	169	0.960	0.530	0.68	2.2	0.300	0.230	0.210	0.64
JUN 25...	174	173	85	0.720	0.050	0.06	0.40	0.120	0.080	0.060	0.18
SEP 23...	158	162	73	1.00	0.080	0.10	--	--	0.050	0.060	0.18

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50038100 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR MANATI, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

DATE	ALUM- INUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AL)	ARSENIC DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS BA)	BERYL- LIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS BE)	CADMIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CR)	COBALT, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CO)	COPPER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CU)	IRON, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS PB)	LITHIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS LI)
OCT 1992 23...	<10	<1	39	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	6	13	<1	<4
DEC 21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993 22...	80	1	36	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	2	66	<1	<4
APR 30...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 25...	20	<1	40	<0.5	<1	2	<3	2	22	<1	<4
SEP 23...	50	<1	43	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	5	73	<1	<4

DATE	MANGA- NESE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS HG)	MOLYB- DENUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MO)	NICKEL, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS NI)	SELE- NIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AG)	STRON- TIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SR)	VANA- DIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS V)	ZINC, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS ZN)
OCT 1992 23...	8	<0.1	<10	<1	<1	<1.0	150	<6	<3
DEC 21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993 22...	17	<0.1	<10	2	<1	<1.0	150	8	17
APR 30...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 25...	22	0.1	<10	2	<1	<1.0	160	6	4
SEP 23...	22	<0.1	<10	<1	<1	<1.0	160	<6	<3

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50038100 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR MANATI, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDEDED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
DEC 1992					
21...	0915	228	40	24	81
FEB 1993					
22...	1025	251	57	39	92
APR					
30...	1025	560	705	1065	76
JUN					
25...	0950	183	10	5	25
SEP					
23...	1210	168	74	34	94

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993										
23...	1005	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010

DATE	ENDRIN WATER UNFLTRD REC (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993									
23...	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993									
23...	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

LAGUNA TORTUGUERO BASIN

50038200 LAGUNA TORTUGUERO OUTLET NEAR VEGA BAJA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°28'29", long 66°26'50", at bridge on Highway 686, 4.2 mi (6.8 km) northeast of Manatí.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1964-66, 1969-71, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992									
02...	0830	12	1470	7.1	29.0	6.2	79	34	K80 K70
DEC									
09...	0830	12	1240	6.4	26.5	6.0	73	30	50 60
FEB 1993									
08...	0830	19	1090	7.8	26.0	5.2	63	33	K100 K300
APR									
19...	0840	4.04	1330	7.7	27.5	5.8	72	37	K175 540
MAY									
27...	1150	7.39	1150	7.6	29.0	6.4	82	48	660 53
SEP									
07...	1215	8.35	1180	7.5	30.4	5.6	70	35	100 70

DATE	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD MG/L AS CACO3	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDEDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
02...	120	<0.5	<1	0.550	0.010	0.560	0.400	0.50	0.90	1.5
DEC										
09...	140	--	4	0.390	0.010	0.400	0.230	0.67	0.90	1.3
FEB 1993										
08...	130	--	7	0.780	0.020	0.800	0.440	1.4	1.8	2.6
APR										
19...	130	<0.5	5	0.980	0.020	1.00	0.090	1.0	1.1	2.1
MAY										
27...	120	--	5	1.08	0.020	1.10	0.330	1.1	1.4	2.5
SEP										
07...	120	--	6	0.580	0.020	0.600	0.200	1.1	1.3	1.9

DATE	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)	IRON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	MANGA-NESE, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY-LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB-STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1992										
02...	6.5	<0.010	90	<10	50	10	<10	<0.010	3	0.06
DEC										
09...	5.8	0.010	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993										
08...	12	0.010	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR										
19...	9.3	0.030	100	10	120	20	<10	<0.010	4	0.10
MAY										
27...	11	<0.010	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP										
07...	8.4	0.010	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

K = non-ideal count

Figure 17.--Río Cibuco basin.

RIO CIBUCO BASIN
50038320 RIO CIBUCO BELOW COROZAL, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969-76, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992										
07...	0905	9.5	392	7.0	26.0	5.0	5.9	72	<10	K1200 540
DEC 23...	0825	21	333	7.2	23.0	--	6.6	77	--	5000 4900
FEB 1993										
05...	0900	153	359	8.0	21.0	7.1	6.0	56	43	4600 5100
APR 14...	0930	53	262	7.3	22.5	89	8.2	89	15	K19000 3600
MAY 25...	0855	43	291	7.1	24.0	16	7.5	67	30	K13000 K12000
SEP 02...	1140	9.8	324	7.4	25.0	1.0	7.9	72	<10	3400 2400

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CACO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1992											
07...	83	6	20	8.1	11	0.5	2.4	79	<0.5	7.7	14
DEC 23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
APR 14...	98	0	24	9.2	13	0.6	4.2	94	<0.5	17	16
MAY 25...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	98	--	--	--
SEP 02...	140	3	36	12	22	0.8	3.3	98	--	16	24

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
07...	0.20	21	132	3.39	4	2.25	0.050	2.30	0.110	0.39
DEC 23...	--	--	--	--	17	--	<0.010	0.360	0.020	--
FEB 1993										
05...	--	--	--	--	<1	--	<0.010	0.300	0.020	--
APR 14...	0.10	23	163	23.3	86	1.25	0.050	1.30	0.070	0.53
MAY 25...	--	--	--	--	24	--	<0.010	0.170	0.080	0.72
SEP 02...	0.10	34	206	5.46	4	--	<0.010	0.270	0.030	--

K = non-ideal count

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50039500 RIO CIBUCO AT VEGA BAJA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'53", long 66°22'29", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, on left bank, at bridge on Hwy 2, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) downstream from Rio Indio, and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) east of Vega Baja.

DRAINAGE AREA.--99.1 mi² (256.7 km²), of which 25.4 mi² (65.8 km²), does not contribute directly to surface runoff.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1973 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 7.79 ft (2.374 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Flood of Dec. 11, 1965 reached a stage of 26.2 ft (7.99 m), datum unknown, discharge about 28,000 ft³/s (793 m³/s).

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	92	26	222	175	250	57	39	549	193	78	80	55
2	64	24	159	144	e65	56	31	934	154	77	77	53
3	205	27	122	125	e52	53	30	452	140	101	73	47
4	53	452	109	114	e52	50	30	289	127	80	71	45
5	81	234	93	101	e51	48	29	226	118	58	69	59
6	66	97	70	157	e50	46	28	478	108	53	71	67
7	38	61	66	250	e50	45	28	1260	110	68	65	102
8	33	49	58	146	e50	42	48	623	115	103	62	81
9	34	53	e54	114	49	42	239	1190	114	59	62	48
10	29	51	e60	98	48	41	259	515	107	53	68	56
11	48	41	e57	88	47	41	502	444	109	225	60	55
12	30	36	e57	90	47	41	1040	337	87	245	60	43
13	27	151	e70	84	47	38	312	273	83	84	58	51
14	26	344	e98	81	44	36	682	325	84	63	59	45
15	25	62	e112	72	43	35	632	245	79	54	63	41
16	24	59	e58	66	43	53	511	333	79	53	171	206
17	54	65	e70	65	65	80	381	294	73	49	138	115
18	90	52	e60	60	49	54	152	216	68	47	69	482
19	133	48	e62	55	50	41	104	193	135	48	60	598
20	41	56	e62	53	123	36	216	181	196	49	55	320
21	30	125	e57	53	187	35	775	199	105	50	54	117
22	29	54	e179	60	91	34	513	189	89	77	52	82
23	52	135	187	149	66	33	181	623	88	136	63	79
24	58	92	225	69	60	70	120	443	78	264	51	180
25	41	71	464	88	56	50	97	429	73	174	49	79
26	31	49	1110	76	55	38	76	360	65	176	49	95
27	40	624	792	59	56	35	122	399	64	226	46	90
28	28	952	e536	57	56	35	392	297	62	119	47	217
29	26	793	e460	62	---	36	1610	232	107	93	62	118
30	47	537	392	115	---	40	3260	204	109	90	56	119
31	29	---	232	122	---	69	---	218	---	84	58	---
TOTAL	1604	5420	6353	3048	1902	1410	12439	12950	3119	3136	2078	3745
MEAN	51.7	181	205	98.3	67.9	45.5	415	418	104	101	67.0	125
MAX	205	952	1110	250	250	80	3260	1260	196	264	171	598
MIN	24	24	54	53	43	33	28	181	62	47	46	41
AC-FT	3180	10750	12600	6050	3770	2800	24670	25690	6190	6220	4120	7430
CFSM	.52	1.82	2.07	.99	.69	.46	4.18	4.22	1.05	1.02	.68	1.26
IN.	.60	2.03	2.38	1.14	.71	.53	4.67	4.86	1.17	1.18	.78	1.41

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1973 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	
MEAN	165	189	185	96.6	91.1	93.5	172	220	78.2	56.2	84.4	121										
MAX	559	523	1316	209	190	339	671	655	245	162	461	450										
(WY)	1986	1980	1982	1988	1988	1990	1987	1985	1987	1979	1979	1979										
MIN	45.9	40.0	30.5	36.3	32.6	24.3	16.2	24.7	12.8	15.5	21.2	27.3										
(WY)	1974	1974	1979	1984	1977	1984	1984	1977	1977	1977	1978	1991										

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1973 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	36541	57204		
ANNUAL MEAN	99.8	157		130
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN				236
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN				49.3
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	2930	Jan 6	3260	Apr 30
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	19	May 15	24	Oct 16
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	22	May 9	30	Oct 28
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			12900	Apr 30
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			17.35	Apr 30
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			22	Nov 2
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	72480	113500		94230
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.01	1.58		1.31
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	13.72	21.47		17.83
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	210	385		232
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	42	70		61
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	25	39		26
e Estimated				

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50039500 RIO CIBUCO AT VEGA BAJA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1972 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
02...	1110	41	413	7.4	27.0	50	5.2	64	14	3300	970
DEC 09...	1040	55	474	7.2	24.0	17	3.7	43	25	450	710
FEB 1993											
08...	1040	52	439	7.7	24.5	5.2	4.6	54	17	420	260
APR 19...	1200	114	404	7.4	24.5	29	6.9	81	15	730	2600
JUN 07...	1125	104	413	7.6	27.0	12	6.9	85	15	440	64
SEP 15...	1300	44	357	7.6	28.0	1.4	7.2	91	<10	390	150

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
02...	160	17	52	7.6	14	0.5	5.1	150	<0.5	17	24
DEC 09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	200	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--
APR 19...	170	23	54	8.9	12	0.4	3.8	160	<0.5	20	20
JUN 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	170	--	--	--
SEP 15...	170	14	54	9.4	18	0.6	3.2	150	--	13	22

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
02...	0.20	15	225	25.1	<1	1.51	0.090	1.60	0.130	0.47
DEC 09...	--	--	--	--	10	1.42	0.080	1.50	0.130	0.57
FEB 1993										
08...	--	--	--	--	16	1.21	0.090	1.30	0.210	0.89
APR 19...	0.10	19	234	71.9	27	1.18	0.020	1.20	0.080	0.62
JUN 07...	--	--	--	--	11	1.23	0.070	1.30	0.100	1.6
SEP 15...	0.10	20	230	27.3	9	1.11	0.090	1.20	0.180	0.52

K = non-ideal count

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Figure 18.--Río de la Plata basin.

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50039990 LAGO CARITE AT GATE TOWER

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'46", long 66°05'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on top of a concrete tower at diversion tunnel on Carite Reservoir, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) northwest from Escuela Carite Chino, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) northeast from Central Hidroeléctrica de Carite Num. 1 and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) northeast from Escuela Segunda Unidad.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.20 mi² (21.24 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1989 to current year.

GAGE.--Water stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Carite Dam was completed in 1913. The operation of the reservoir is controlled by the utilization of water to meet the demands for domestic, industrial and agricultural purposes in the Guayama Area. The dam is an earthfill with crest elevation of 1,806 ft (550 m) above mean sea level, with a structural height of 104 ft (32 m) and a length of 500 ft (152 m). The dam has a capacity of approximately 11,310 acre-feet (13.9 hm³). The Dam is operated by the Puerto Rico Electric and Power Authority. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation 1,787.61 ft (544.86 m), Jan. 5, 1992; minimum elevation, 1,761.48 ft (536.90 m), June 13, 14, 1990.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation 1,782.22 ft (543.22 m), July 24; minimum elevation, 1,766.95 ft (538.57 m), Apr. 29.

Capacity Table

(based on Data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
1,746	0	1,775	6,194
1,760	2,471	1,780	7,704
1,769	4,561	1,790	11,048

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	1780.71	1776.73	1775.35	1773.53	1773.62	1771.50	1769.16	1767.47	1767.86	1774.73	1781.41	1781.19
2	1780.58	1776.59	1775.28	1773.53	1773.61	1771.53	1769.05	1768.04	1767.85	1774.83	1781.40	1781.15
3	1780.44	1776.43	1775.31	1773.51	1773.54	1771.42	1768.95	1768.04	1767.72	1775.07	1781.38	1781.11
4	1780.33	1776.43	1775.26	1773.47	1773.48	1771.35	1768.82	1767.94	1767.69	1775.12	1781.37	1781.06
5	1780.19	1776.28	1775.18	1773.43	1773.43	1771.35	1768.72	1767.95	1767.66	1775.15	1781.34	1781.08
6	1780.12	1776.31	1775.06	1773.44	1773.38	1771.27	1768.60	1767.86	1767.58	1775.16	1781.34	1781.05
7	1780.00	1776.23	1774.96	1773.48	1773.32	1771.20	1768.49	1767.73	1767.56	1775.30	1781.32	1781.01
8	1779.88	1776.09	1774.86	1773.42	1773.25	1771.14	1768.43	1767.64	1767.52	1775.35	1781.30	1780.97
9	1779.78	1775.96	1774.73	1773.41	1773.16	1771.08	1768.49	1767.56	1767.44	1775.25	1781.27	1780.99
10	1779.62	1775.82	1774.59	1773.40	1773.11	1771.02	1768.41	1767.45	1767.46	1775.23	1781.26	1781.02
11	1779.51	1775.67	1774.49	1773.35	1773.05	1770.97	1768.31	1767.32	1767.42	1781.91	1781.26	1780.98
12	1779.37	1775.53	1774.35	1773.29	1773.12	1770.89	1768.20	1767.21	1767.37	1781.82	1781.23	1780.92
13	1779.24	1775.40	1774.25	1773.23	1773.06	1770.86	1768.27	1767.13	1767.37	1781.73	1781.21	1780.87
14	1779.08	1775.23	1774.14	1773.17	1772.98	1770.79	1768.21	1768.19	1767.51	1781.51	1781.17	1780.83
15	1778.94	1775.19	1774.01	1773.12	1772.94	1770.68	1768.13	1768.16	1768.04	1781.53	1781.25	1780.83
16	1778.81	1775.07	1774.06	1773.03	1772.85	1770.59	1768.03	1768.07	1768.10	1781.53	1781.89	1780.83
17	1778.70	1774.93	1774.02	1772.99	1772.69	1770.50	1767.97	1767.98	1768.14	1781.45	1781.72	1780.78
18	1778.54	1774.91	1773.91	1772.92	1772.59	1770.42	1767.87	1767.92	1769.78	1781.41	1781.62	1780.75
19	1778.47	1774.81	1773.84	1772.86	1772.50	1770.38	1767.80	1767.82	1772.82	1781.42	1781.55	1780.66
20	1778.31	1774.85	1773.76	1772.79	1772.39	1770.32	1767.74	1767.74	1773.49	1781.42	1781.49	1780.63
21	1778.17	1774.84	1773.68	1772.71	1772.28	1770.22	1767.64	1767.86	1773.63	1781.41	1781.44	1780.59
22	1778.04	1774.81	1773.64	1772.77	1772.14	1770.12	1767.53	1767.84	1773.96	1781.97	1781.43	1780.55
23	1777.87	1774.73	1773.57	1772.71	1772.03	1770.03	1767.43	1767.84	1774.11	1781.90	1781.52	1781.19
24	1777.76	1774.71	1773.51	1772.66	1772.01	1769.93	1767.38	1767.78	1774.18	1782.02	1781.50	1781.21
25	1777.67	1774.58	1773.45	1772.69	1771.92	1769.84	1767.26	1767.90	1774.32	1781.77	1781.45	1781.19
26	1777.49	1774.45	1773.59	1772.65	1771.86	1769.75	1767.17	1767.89	1774.42	1781.67	1781.42	1781.14
27	1777.35	1774.82	1773.57	1772.70	1771.78	1769.64	1767.11	1767.87	1774.50	1781.61	1781.38	1781.15
28	1777.25	1774.97	1773.50	1772.81	1771.69	1769.55	1767.03	1767.87	1774.57	1781.56	1781.33	1781.17
29	1777.12	1775.00	1773.47	1773.66	---	1769.46	1767.46	1767.86	1774.64	1781.50	1781.27	1781.18
30	1777.01	1775.20	1773.45	1773.66	---	1769.37	1767.43	1767.86	1774.71	1781.46	1781.27	1781.50
31	1776.84	---	1773.45	1773.66	---	1769.25	---	1767.84	---	1781.45	1781.21	---
MEAN	1778.81	1775.42	1774.20	1773.16	1772.78	1770.53	1768.04	1767.79	1770.31	1779.52	1781.39	1780.99
MAX	1780.71	1776.73	1775.35	1773.66	1773.62	1771.53	1769.16	1768.19	1774.71	1782.02	1781.89	1781.50
MIN	1776.84	1774.45	1773.45	1772.65	1771.69	1769.25	1767.03	1767.13	1767.37	1774.73	1781.17	1780.55

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50043000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT PROYECTO LA PLATA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'37", long 66°13'44", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at upstream side of bridge on Highway 173, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) northeast of Proyecto La Plata, and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) upstream from Rio Usabón.

DRAINAGE AREA.--63.0 mi² (163.2 km²), excludes 8.2 mi² (21.1 km²) upstream from Carite Reservoir, the flow of which is diverted to Rio Guamaní.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1958 (occasional measurements only), February 1959 to March 1960 (monthly measurements only), April 1960 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 850 ft (259 m), from topographic map. Prior to Mar. 29, 1961, wire-weight gage read twice daily at same site and datum.

REMARKS.--Records poor. The Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority operates a pumping plant about 5 mi (8 km) upstream which can divert as much as 23 ft³/s (0.65 m³/s) into Cidra Reservoir. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e35	e17	e100	e35	e30	e13	e8.5	e170	e19	e30	e32	e21
2	e27	e16	e80	e42	e25	e13	e9.0	e330	e19	e25	e30	e20
3	e23	e17	e65	e33	e22	e13	e9.0	e80	e18	e27	e29	e19
4	e20	e18	e70	e30	e20	e12	e9.0	e45	e16	e35	e28	e19
5	e80	e21	e50	e28	e18	e12	e9.0	e35	e15	e30	e27	e90
6	e200	e19	e45	e27	e16	e12	e8.6	e32	e14	e27	e26	e100
7	e120	e27	e42	e40	e15	e11	e8.2	e30	e14	e25	e25	e120
8	e35	e22	e40	e47	e14	e11	e15	e28	e13	e24	e24	e50
9	e27	e17	e37	e42	e14	e11	e35	e45	e13	e26	e24	e30
10	e25	e16	e37	e35	e13	e10	e60	e35	e14	e23	e23	e25
11	e23	e24	e36	e33	e12	e10	e80	e30	e14	e1200	e22	e35
12	e21	e19	e35	e31	e12	e9.8	e55	e27	e14	e500	e23	e25
13	e20	e30	e36	e30	e12	e9.8	e90	e25	e15	e200	e22	e21
14	e21	e25	e37	e27	e12	e9.6	e100	e230	e16	e70	e21	e19
15	e20	e20	e60	e26	e13	e10	e70	e70	e20	e40	e21	e17
16	e19	e20	e40	e25	e12	e11	e90	e40	e50	e34	e450	e21
17	e21	e18	e41	e24	e12	e11	e50	e32	e70	e31	e170	e25
18	e40	e22	e42	e23	e13	e10	e65	e27	e50	e30	e80	e30
19	e35	e25	e41	e22	e13	e9.8	e35	e24	e300	e30	e35	e35
20	e55	e160	e38	e21	e13	e9.6	e25	e23	e450	e33	e30	e25
21	e30	e70	e37	e20	e14	e9.4	e28	e22	e500	e45	e27	e35
22	e25	e55	e40	e19	e14	e9.2	e22	e21	e150	e200	e27	e23
23	e22	e65	e45	e35	e15	e9.2	e18	e65	e170	e550	e40	e300
24	e170	e35	e42	e27	e15	e9.4	e15	e70	e70	e140	e28	e200
25	e140	e25	e50	e25	e15	e9.5	e14	e45	e55	e130	e25	e100
26	e35	e24	e330	e28	e14	e9.6	e13	e100	e45	e80	e23	e50
27	e22	e600	e170	e25	e14	e9.0	e13	e50	e35	e60	e22	e27
28	e18	e700	e70	e90	e13	e9.0	e30	e37	e32	e50	e21	e23
29	e20	e200	e40	e300	---	e8.8	e300	e30	e28	e42	e40	e40
30	e23	e250	e32	e100	---	e8.6	e250	e25	e25	e38	e30	e42
31	e17	---	e30	e60	---	e8.5	---	e21	---	e35	e24	---
TOTAL	1389	2577	1858	1350	425	318.8	1534.3	1844	2264	3810	1449	1587
MEAN	44.8	85.9	59.9	43.5	15.2	10.3	51.1	59.5	75.5	123	46.7	52.9
MAX	200	700	330	300	30	13	300	330	500	1200	450	300
MIN	17	16	30	19	12	8.5	8.2	21	13	23	21	17
AC-FT	2760	5110	3690	2680	843	632	3040	3660	4490	7560	2870	3150
CFSM	.82	1.57	1.09	.79	.28	.19	.93	1.09	1.38	2.24	.85	.97
IN.	.94	1.75	1.26	.92	.29	.22	1.04	1.25	1.54	2.59	.98	1.08

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1960 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	207	181	101	66.1	45.7	33.9	50.7	105	94.7	85.0	135	154
MAX	2164	831	565	519	195	120	323	594	629	489	642	975
(WY)	1971	1978	1971	1992	1989	1972	1971	1985	1970	1961	1961	1960
MIN	7.82	12.1	9.16	7.78	7.65	4.72	6.61	6.66	4.93	5.30	9.45	11.9
(WY)	1969	1982	1990	1990	1990	1977	1977	1968	1977	1977	1967	1967

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1993 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1960 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL		29500.2		20406.1		
ANNUAL MEAN		80.6		55.9		103
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN						368
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN						31.3
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN		8000	Jan 5	1200	Jul 11	20300
LOWEST DAILY MEAN		7.1	Sep 13	8.2	Apr 7	2.6
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM		7.7	Sep 9	8.8	Apr 1	3.2
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW						73600
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE						36.39
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)		58510		40480		74720
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)		1.47		1.02		1.88
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)		20.03		13.85		25.57
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS		75		100		159
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS		19		27		29
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS		9.4		12		9.0

e Estimated

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50043000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT PROYECTO LA PLATA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS. / 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1992											
08...	0955	29	272	7.3	26.5	56	6.0	75	17	2700	520
DEC 03...	0840	50	315	6.6	25.0	71	5.6	68	12	410	640
FEB 1993											
11...	0910	12	484	7.8	24.0	4.9	4.2	50	17	K130	K190
APR 13...	0900	15	424	7.5	24.5	5.2	6.2	75	13	K710	68
JUN 08...	0935	13	570	7.7	27.5	3.5	7.6	97	<10	K130	220
AUG 31...	1315	23	387	7.9	31.0	0.30	7.0	93	16	1700	60

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
09...	94	4	24	8.3	19	0.9	2.6	95	<0.5	12	16
DEC 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
APR 13...	150	0	37	14	34	1	2.9	150	<0.5	19	31
JUN 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
AUG 31...	150	3	34	15	37	1	2.6	120	--	43	190

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
08...	0.20	18	156	12.2	34	0.710	0.070	0.780	0.160	0.44
DEC 03...	--	--	--	--	10	0.940	0.060	1.00	0.020	0.48
FEB 1993										
10...	--	--	--	--	7	1.88	0.020	1.90	0.020	0.68
APR 13...	0.20	23	251	10.2	43	1.09	0.110	1.10	0.120	0.48
JUN 08...	--	--	--	--	<1	1.26	0.040	1.30	0.050	0.55
AUG 31...	0.20	22	416	25.8	<1	0.950	0.050	1.00	0.040	0.66

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50043800 RIO DE LA PLATA AT COMERIO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°13'23", long 66°13'30", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank 50 ft (15 m) upstream from bridge off Highway 167 in the Town of Comerio, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) southwest of Comerio High School, and 0.2 mi (0.3 km) northeast of Plaza de Comerio.

DRAINAGE AREA.--109 mi² (282 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Datum of gage is 604.2 ft (184.160 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	69	31	194	65	99	27	16	411	57	50	83	52
2	52	30	146	78	64	26	17	975	56	45	77	50
3	44	31	120	63	58	26	17	699	54	45	74	43
4	38	34	128	59	54	25	17	179	51	61	71	44
5	175	40	105	54	48	25	17	107	47	48	65	192
6	670	35	92	51	44	24	16	86	46	41	65	246
7	326	52	83	77	39	23	15	79	45	38	63	337
8	86	41	76	83	37	23	49	70	46	40	59	101
9	63	31	71	60	36	21	90	116	48	40	57	65
10	50	30	71	54	36	21	104	96	49	37	55	60
11	43	46	69	49	36	21	326	83	47	e3060	54	84
12	40	35	67	47	36	20	192	71	48	e1130	55	59
13	38	56	67	46	36	20	314	59	50	e131	53	48
14	39	48	72	43	38	19	333	604	48	e64	52	45
15	38	37	107	44	34	20	263	261	57	e50	52	43
16	36	38	81	44	33	22	332	113	169	e44	1080	49
17	41	34	77	42	33	22	127	87	85	e43	369	67
18	78	41	81	41	32	22	165	72	63	e43	143	74
19	62	47	79	40	32	20	70	66	e1620	e43	96	92
20	107	328	73	41	33	20	64	65	e1770	e43	77	53
21	53	154	71	40	34	20	72	61	e312	e67	68	69
22	43	98	72	41	34	18	56	63	373	e217	64	51
23	41	125	83	68	33	17	43	167	217	772	99	841
24	322	69	79	53	31	18	37	190	105	1420	82	646
25	256	48	81	46	30	18	35	110	79	582	65	121
26	69	43	636	54	30	18	34	257	62	250	57	85
27	41	1100	316	48	28	17	32	184	52	181	52	60
28	33	1380	98	61	28	17	196	107	49	139	94	53
29	29	389	69	610	---	17	1080	87	50	113	107	80
30	43	503	57	180	---	16	733	67	55	102	76	80
31	32	---	54	109	---	16	---	59	---	92	59	---
TOTAL	3057	4974	3475	2391	1106	639	4862	5651	5810	9031	3523	3890
MEAN	98.6	166	112	77.1	39.5	20.6	162	182	194	291	114	130
MAX	670	1380	636	610	99	27	1080	975	1770	3060	1080	841
MIN	29	30	54	40	28	16	15	59	45	37	52	43
AC-FT	6060	9870	6890	4740	2190	1270	9640	11210	11520	17910	6990	7720
CFSM	.91	1.53	1.03	.71	.36	.19	1.49	1.68	1.78	2.69	1.05	1.20
IN.	1.05	1.71	1.19	.82	.38	.22	1.67	1.94	1.99	3.10	1.21	1.33

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1989 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	281	96.9	58.1	192	96.3	43.0	58.3	110	71.1	100	65.5	214			
MAX	866	166	112	732	247	75.7	162	263	194	291	114	729			
(WY)	1991	1993	1993	1992	1989	1989	1993	1992	1993	1993	1993	1989			
MIN	40.6	42.6	23.9	22.8	24.4	20.6	22.3	25.3	16.0	19.0	26.5	51.2			
(WY)	1992	1990	1990	1990	1990	1993	1991	1989	1991	1989	1991	1991			

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1993 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1989 - 1993

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1989 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	53229	48409	
ANNUAL MEAN	145	133	109
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			133
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			45.0
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	14600	3060	14600
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	14	15	10
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	16	16	11
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		14800	127000
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		12.85	29.22
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW		15	10
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	105600	96020	78920
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.34	1.22	1.00
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	18.25	16.60	13.64
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	136	262	152
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	40	57	37
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	21	26	17

e Estimated

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50043800 RIO DE LA PLATA AT COMERIO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1989 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1989 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USD-77 and automatic sediment sampler.

REMARKS.--Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a week basis and during high flow events.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 8,800 mg/L Jan. 05, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L few days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 950,000 tons (862,000 tonnes) Jan. 05, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 0.06 ton (0.05 tonne) Aug 20, 1990.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,340 mg/l June 11, 1993; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e19,000 tons (e17,200 tonnes) July 11, 1993; Minimum daily mean .15 tons (.14 tonnes) Mar. 08, 1993.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	69	242	48	31	21	1.7	194	107	62
2	52	128	18	30	32	2.5	146	86	33
3	44	60	7.4	31	49	4.3	120	78	26
4	38	25	2.6	34	62	5.9	128	55	19
5	175	98	190	40	69	7.0	105	35	9.8
6	670	505	1740	35	75	7.2	92	21	5.1
7	326	278	328	52	78	11	83	11	2.5
8	86	134	33	41	48	5.7	76	5	1.0
9	63	99	18	31	24	2.0	71	3	.67
10	50	68	9.4	30	17	1.5	71	4	.76
11	43	48	5.7	46	16	1.9	69	4	.75
12	40	34	3.6	35	14	1.3	67	3	.64
13	38	25	2.6	56	33	10	67	2	.45
14	39	19	2.0	48	18	2.3	72	15	3.4
15	38	94	9.8	37	16	1.6	107	44	12
16	36	12	1.1	38	15	1.5	81	33	7.5
17	41	8	.82	34	15	1.4	77	15	3.1
18	78	95	36	41	15	1.8	81	15	3.1
19	62	180	33	47	15	1.8	79	55	11
20	107	74	24	328	155	189	73	105	21
21	53	23	3.7	154	117	56	71	124	24
22	43	17	1.9	98	88	22	72	124	24
23	41	16	1.8	125	62	22	83	124	26
24	322	176	500	69	30	6.1	79	124	26
25	256	307	237	48	19	2.5	81	124	27
26	69	165	35	43	18	2.1	636	445	1760
27	41	90	11	1100	544	5150	316	178	224
28	33	36	3.2	1380	534	2990	98	47	13
29	29	27	2.1	389	225	253	69	28	5.3
30	43	23	2.7	503	297	449	57	24	3.7
31	32	20	1.8	---	---	---	54	28	4.0
TOTAL	3057	---	3313.22	4974	---	9214.1	3475	---	2359.77

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50043800 RIO DE LA PLATA AT COMERIO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	65	34	6.3	99	48	14	27	13	.93
2	78	36	8.3	64	37	6.4	26	11	.74
3	63	17	2.9	58	24	3.7	26	8	.57
4	59	12	1.9	54	11	1.6	25	6	.45
5	54	15	2.1	48	6	.84	25	5	.33
6	51	18	2.4	44	5	.66	24	4	.25
7	77	33	9.0	39	5	.52	23	3	.18
8	83	37	8.9	37	4	.45	23	2	.15
9	60	23	3.8	36	4	.38	21	3	.20
10	54	15	2.0	36	3	.34	21	4	.22
11	49	10	1.3	36	3	.34	21	5	.30
12	47	6	.83	36	4	.38	20	8	.46
13	46	24	2.9	36	4	.43	20	11	.57
14	43	4	.48	38	4	.47	19	12	.61
15	44	4	.48	34	3	.32	20	12	.63
16	44	4	.47	33	4	.35	22	12	.69
17	42	3	.40	33	6	.53	22	11	.67
18	41	3	.33	32	8	.74	22	10	.54
19	40	4	.48	32	10	.88	20	8	.43
20	41	11	1.3	33	11	.94	20	6	.32
21	40	9	.96	34	11	1.0	20	6	.35
22	41	6	.68	34	12	1.1	18	9	.45
23	68	5	.92	33	12	1.1	17	10	.46
24	53	4	.64	31	12	1.0	18	10	.47
25	46	4	.49	30	12	.98	18	10	.48
26	54	3	.48	30	13	1.0	18	11	.49
27	48	3	.39	28	14	1.1	17	14	.62
28	61	17	.42	28	14	1.0	17	16	.73
29	610	264	861	---	---	---	17	25	1.1
30	180	46	22	---	---	---	16	41	1.8
31	109	75	25	---	---	---	16	59	2.6
TOTAL	2391	---	1011.13	1106	---	42.55	639	---	18.79

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50043800 RIO DE LA PLATA AT COMERIO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	16	82	3.6	411	332	753	57	33	5.0
2	17	92	4.2	975	579	2330	56	26	3.9
3	17	74	3.4	699	455	1220	54	28	4.0
4	17	48	2.2	179	95	51	51	38	5.0
5	17	30	1.4	107	51	15	47	47	6.0
6	16	19	.81	86	17	3.8	46	48	6.0
7	15	11	.42	79	29	6.0	45	45	5.4
8	49	22	6.5	70	28	5.4	46	42	5.1
9	90	41	13	116	52	22	48	38	5.0
10	104	53	19	96	28	7.0	49	35	4.5
11	326	338	573	83	39	8.7	47	32	3.9
12	192	491	288	71	46	8.6	48	29	3.6
13	314	390	348	59	45	7.4	50	26	3.4
14	333	202	214	604	393	1460	48	23	2.9
15	263	145	179	261	129	114	57	22	3.6
16	332	182	192	113	93	29	169	87	52
17	127	102	39	87	85	19	85	38	9.5
18	165	144	73	72	80	15	63	27	4.7
19	70	131	27	66	72	13	e1620	1340	e7290
20	64	97	17	65	57	9.9	e1770	699	e5540
21	72	85	15	61	40	6.6	e312	106	e97
22	56	63	9.1	63	28	4.8	373	205	322
23	43	46	5.5	167	86	78	217	123	92
24	37	34	3.4	190	104	68	105	74	22
25	35	25	2.4	110	51	16	79	72	15
26	34	19	1.7	257	124	124	62	71	11
27	32	15	1.3	184	104	60	52	69	9.4
28	196	113	204	107	210	65	49	68	8.9
29	1080	872	6790	87	63	14	50	64	8.5
30	733	463	1210	67	55	9.9	55	54	7.6
31	---	---	---	59	44	7.1	---	---	---
TOTAL	4862	---	10246.93	5651	---	6551.2	5810	---	13556.9

e Estimated

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50043800 RIO DE LA PLATA AT COMERIO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	50	42	5.4	83	8	1.8	52	109	15
2	45	33	4.1	77	8	1.7	50	106	14
3	45	26	3.2	74	8	1.7	43	103	12
4	61	18	3.1	71	10	1.8	44	100	12
5	48	14	1.8	65	11	1.9	192	173	195
6	41	8	.96	65	11	1.9	246	136	153
7	38	5	.52	63	10	1.6	337	200	376
8	40	4	.41	59	7	1.1	101	86	25
9	40	4	.42	57	5	.76	65	72	13
10	37	3	.36	55	4	.59	60	61	9.8
11	e3060	863	e19000	54	4	.58	84	40	9.3
12	e1130	698	e5810	55	4	.58	59	28	4.5
13	e131	84	e35	53	4	.56	48	25	3.1
14	e64	58	e11	52	9	1.3	45	27	3.3
15	e50	42	e5.7	52	39	5.7	43	31	3.7
16	e44	32	e3.8	1080	442	2450	49	35	4.5
17	e43	23	e2.7	369	222	288	67	37	7.2
18	e43	15	e1.7	143	131	52	74	27	5.3
19	e43	9	e1.0	96	123	32	92	33	8.3
20	e43	6	e.76	77	117	24	53	22	3.2
21	e67	22	e9.5	68	113	20	69	32	6.7
22	e217	119	e110	64	112	20	51	26	3.7
23	772	439	1060	99	111	31	841	490	5500
24	1420	805	4540	82	107	25	646	415	1450
25	582	246	549	65	87	15	121	65	23
26	250	35	25	57	58	8.7	85	42	9.5
27	181	19	9.5	52	58	8.4	60	33	5.3
28	139	15	5.5	94	111	29	53	24	3.3
29	113	13	4.0	107	116	36	80	16	3.4
30	102	11	2.9	76	114	25	80	65	15
31	92	8	2.1	59	112	17	---	---	---
TOTAL	9031	---	31209.43	3523	---	3104.67	3890	---	7897.1
YEAR	48409		88525.79						
e	Estimated								

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50043800 RIO DE LA PLATA AT COMERIO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
APR 1993							
29...	1630	1630	5680	25000	29	40	48
29...	1720	4760	3990	51300	44	53	59
MAY							
01...	1815	1480	2120	8470	53	60	64
JUN							
19...	0620	2030	2030	11100	46	52	57
JUL							
11...	1445	13100	5430	192000	41	49	56
11...	1510	14800	21600	863000	14	17	19

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
APR 1993							
29...	58	70	82	92	97	99	100
29...	71	81	91	98	99	99.6	100
MAY							
01...	76	83	96	99	100	100	100
JUN							
19...	67	76	91	98	99	99.5	100
JUL							
11...	69	79	92	97	99	99.6	100
11...	24	31	41	57	78	96	99

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN
 50043800 RIO DE LA PLATA AT COMERIO, PR--Continued
 WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1992					
19...	0830	53	360	52	99
APR 1993					
05...	1510	17	320	15	99
21...	1315	58	58	9.1	91
29...	1630	1630	734	3230	92
29...	1810	3450	5930	55200	79
29...	2320	2220	831	4980	94
MAY					
01...	1840	1520	1510	6200	96
03...	0730	837	299	676	98
JUN					
18...	1930	58	3420	536	91
19...	0840	1540	1700	7070	99
20...	1315	1220	191	629	98
JUL					
11...	1345	5200	3690	51800	86
11...	1815	5790	1460	25600	97
AUG					
16...	1230	149	2970	1190	73

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50044000 RIO DE LA PLATA NEAR COMERIO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'33", long 66°12'28", at bridge on Highway 156, 0.56 mi (0.9 km) upstream from dam, about 2.0 mi (3.2 km) northeast of Comerio plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--139 mi² (360 km²), excludes 8.2 mi² (21.1 km²) upstream from Carite Reservoir, the flow of which is diverted to Río Guamaní.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS. / 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
14...	1025	44	358	8.0	26.0	15	7.8	95	15	K10000	3200
DEC 08...	0955	57	381	7.5	23.5	19	7.2	84	<10	2700	K1200
FEB 1993											
04...	0940	75	338	8.0	21.0	11	5.4	63	<10	K740	340
APR 07...	0835	20	418	7.9	24.5	3.1	8.4	100	<10	510	K190
MAY 26...	0950	193	352	7.7	23.5	20	8.0	96	16	2100	2600
SEP 20...	1300	86	375	7.9	27.5	66	7.6	97	18	K800	K1400

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
14...	140	3	34	14	27	1.0	2.7	130	<0.5	17	27
DEC 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
APR 07...	160	9	36	16	26	0.9	2.8	160	<0.5	19	32
MAY 26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
SEP 20...	120	0	27	12	18	0.7	4.0	140	--	13	19

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
14...	0.10	27	233	27.7	3	0.640	0.030	0.670	0.050	0.25
DEC 08...	--	--	--	--	15	0.980	0.020	1.00	0.030	0.57
FEB 1993										
04...	--	--	--	--	8	1.33	0.070	1.40	0.170	8.4
APR 07...	0.20	28	256	13.8	1	1.33	0.070	1.40	0.090	1.0
MAY 26...	--	--	--	--	21	0.710	0.090	0.800	0.170	1.7
SEP 20...	0.20	27	191	44.4	48	0.980	0.020	1.00	0.040	0.56

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50044830 RIO GUADIANA AT GUADIANA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'08", long 66°13'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at left bank downstream side of river, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) East of Plaza de Naranjito, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) west from intersection of roads 167 and 164 at km 8.9 and 2.9 mi (4.7 km) northwest from Represa Comerio.

DRAINAGE AREA.--9.19 mi² (23.80 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 230 ft (70 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	3.4	3.3	8.6	15	13	7.1	3.8	268	25	15	8.7	4.9
2	2.7	3.2	6.9	13	7.7	7.7	3.6	321	21	16	8.4	5.1
3	2.5	4.2	5.7	12	9.3	6.6	3.7	122	20	21	7.8	4.8
4	2.4	28	6.1	11	7.1	6.1	3.6	50	18	14	7.6	4.5
5	7.0	11	4.9	25	6.3	5.8	3.9	65	16	12	7.7	4.7
6	6.5	5.3	5.1	18	5.7	5.7	3.8	234	15	11	7.6	38
7	3.4	5.2	4.2	65	5.3	5.4	3.9	149	15	30	7.4	9.4
8	3.5	4.4	4.1	37	5.0	5.6	62	58	17	15	7.3	5.6
9	3.3	4.2	4.0	18	4.8	5.4	26	240	16	11	7.8	5.1
10	3.6	4.1	3.8	13	4.7	5.2	16	97	21	11	7.2	4.9
11	3.3	2.9	3.8	12	4.5	5.1	130	60	14	181	6.9	4.8
12	3.1	8.6	3.5	12	4.6	5.1	30	41	13	46	6.4	4.3
13	2.9	9.2	3.1	12	4.5	4.9	156	29	14	20	6.1	4.4
14	3.1	8.1	16	10	4.1	4.5	159	103	13	14	6.3	5.4
15	2.9	30	26	9.1	4.1	4.5	124	37	12	14	7.1	6.9
16	2.7	17	7.2	8.6	4.1	10	145	27	11	12	78	14
17	18	8.5	9.7	7.8	4.4	7.7	47	23	10	11	14	9.2
18	23	9.7	11	7.6	4.6	5.7	17	18	11	9.7	8.3	59
19	7.9	8.2	7.2	7.2	4.2	4.9	10	16	63	9.2	7.3	100
20	3.8	5.8	6.7	7.2	23	4.6	48	15	46	9.3	6.4	54
21	3.0	4.9	5.8	6.9	12	4.5	64	14	17	9.7	6.2	13
22	4.4	33	10	22	8.7	4.3	30	29	19	21	8.9	9.0
23	30	17	7.4	16	8.0	6.8	14	204	13	27	8.5	74
24	12	11	30	9.3	7.1	9.9	10	78	12	92	6.3	32
25	8.3	7.0	40	11	6.5	6.2	8.3	81	11	20	5.8	12
26	4.8	6.0	309	8.1	6.6	4.7	6.9	96	10	22	5.8	9.8
27	4.4	202	78	6.8	6.7	4.5	6.3	75	10	16	5.7	74
28	3.8	59	93	6.7	6.3	4.3	60	51	34	11	6.2	31
29	4.3	18	72	15	---	4.2	222	37	34	10	6.2	15
30	4.1	13	39	12	---	4.2	155	33	33	9.4	6.1	17
31	3.8	---	22	24	---	4.0	---	31	---	9.2	5.3	---
TOTAL	191.9	551.8	853.8	458.3	192.9	175.2	1572.8	2702	584	729.5	295.3	635.8
MEAN	6.19	18.4	27.5	14.8	6.89	5.65	52.4	87.2	19.5	23.5	9.53	21.2
MAX	30	202	309	65	23	10	222	321	63	181	78	100
MIN	2.4	2.9	3.1	6.7	4.1	4.0	3.6	14	10	9.2	5.3	4.3
AC-FT	381	1090	1690	909	383	348	3120	5360	1160	1450	586	1260
CFSM	.67	2.00	3.00	1.61	.75	.61	5.70	9.48	2.12	2.56	1.04	2.31
IN.	.78	2.23	3.46	1.86	.78	.71	6.37	10.94	2.36	2.95	1.20	2.57

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1991	1992	1993	1992	1993	1993	1993	1991	1991	1991	1992	1991
MEAN	36.5	13.3	17.6	24.2	14.9	10.8	25.8	41.2	10.0	14.0	7.80	11.8
MAX	98.7	18.4	27.5	42.5	31.7	13.7	52.4	87.2	19.5	23.5	9.53	21.2
(WY)	1991	1993	1993	1992	1991	1992	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993
MIN	4.51	7.32	5.67	14.8	6.39	5.65	11.6	7.49	5.21	4.51	5.76	3.95
(WY)	1992	1992	1992	1993	1992	1993	1991	1991	1991	1992	1991	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1990 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	5596.7		8943.3			
ANNUAL MEAN	15.3		24.5		19.0	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					24.5	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					12.4	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	536	Jan 5	321	May 2	536	Jan 5 1992
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	2.4	Oct 4	2.4	Oct 4	2.4	Oct 4 1992
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	2.7	Sep 10	3.1	Oct 10	2.7	Sep 10 1992
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			2190		6670	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			9.06		13.36	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	11100		17740		13750	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.66		2.67		2.06	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	22.65		36.20		28.05	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	26		61		33	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	5.1		9.3		7.2	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	3.1		4.1		3.3	

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN
50044830 RIO GUADIANA AT GUADIANA, PR--Continued
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1990 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: August 01, 1990 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USD-77 and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,300 mg/L Oct. 16, 1990; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L few days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 18,000 tons (16,300 tonnes) Jan. 05, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 0.00 ton (0.0 tonne) several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

Water Year	Suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		Suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1993	1,090 (May 02)	1 (Several days)	2,920 (May 06)	.01 (Several days)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	3.4	5	.06	3.3	10	.08	8.6	8	.21
2	2.7	4	.03	3.2	4	.04	6.9	13	.24
3	2.5	3	.02	4.2	7	.08	5.7	8	.14
4	2.4	3	.01	28	75	9.6	6.1	9	.16
5	7.0	12	.84	11	103	3.6	4.9	10	.13
6	6.5	26	.58	5.3	47	.68	5.1	11	.17
7	3.4	13	.13	5.2	19	.27	4.2	9	.11
8	3.5	8	.07	4.4	10	.11	4.1	9	.10
9	3.3	5	.04	4.2	9	.09	4.0	10	.10
10	3.6	3	.03	4.1	9	.10	3.8	16	.16
11	3.3	3	.03	2.9	6	.05	3.8	22	.23
12	3.1	4	.04	8.6	16	1.5	3.5	26	.25
13	2.9	5	.04	9.2	15	.44	3.1	14	.13
14	3.1	4	.03	8.1	12	.26	16	35	7.9
15	2.9	3	.02	30	73	16	26	78	9.1
16	2.7	3	.02	17	35	2.6	7.2	41	.85
17	18	39	5.3	8.5	18	.45	9.7	27	.83
18	23	80	14	9.7	23	.60	11	21	.68
19	7.9	93	2.4	8.2	23	.54	7.2	14	.27
20	3.8	40	.42	5.8	7	.11	6.7	10	.16
21	3.0	19	.14	4.9	6	.09	5.8	9	.15
22	4.4	10	.13	33	62	9.2	10	18	.67
23	30	936	276	17	29	1.6	7.4	15	.28
24	12	184	5.9	11	19	.69	30	71	11
25	8.3	25	.61	7.0	9	.16	40	90	13
26	4.8	15	.21	6.0	9	.16	309	1280	2420
27	4.4	10	.11	202	724	1280	78	206	47
28	3.8	10	.09	59	146	30	93	324	122
29	4.3	10	.13	18	35	2.0	72	154	35
30	4.1	10	.10	13	18	.61	39	85	10
31	3.8	11	.11	---	---	---	22	40	2.4
TOTAL	191.9	---	307.64	551.8	---	1361.71	853.8	---	2683.42

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50044830 RIO GUADIANA AT GUADIANA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)		DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)		DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	15	26	1.1	13	36	1.5	7.1	11	.21
2	13	17	.58	7.7	25	.52	7.7	11	.24
3	12	9	.30	9.3	18	.45	6.6	13	.21
4	11	6	.19	7.1	16	.31	6.1	12	.20
5	25	46	6.4	6.3	17	.28	5.8	12	.18
6	18	35	2.1	5.7	15	.22	5.7	10	.16
7	65	165	44	5.3	15	.20	5.4	10	.14
8	37	85	10	5.0	13	.17	5.6	8	.12
9	18	30	1.6	4.8	12	.16	5.4	6	.09
10	13	12	.42	4.7	11	.14	5.2	6	.09
11	12	5	.17	4.5	8	.10	5.1	9	.12
12	12	6	.19	4.6	6	.08	5.1	10	.14
13	12	6	.20	4.5	5	.07	4.9	10	.13
14	10	7	.20	4.1	6	.07	4.5	10	.13
15	9.1	10	.25	4.1	9	.09	4.5	12	.14
16	8.6	10	.24	4.1	9	.10	10	17	.54
17	7.8	10	.19	4.4	10	.11	7.7	16	.33
18	7.6	5	.12	4.6	10	.13	5.7	11	.17
19	7.2	7	.14	4.2	11	.14	4.9	7	.09
20	7.2	12	.22	23	58	8.0	4.6	4	.05
21	6.9	18	.32	12	19	.63	4.5	4	.05
22	22	49	4.3	8.7	13	.30	4.3	4	.04
23	16	33	1.8	8.0	16	.35	6.8	16	.46
24	9.3	19	.45	7.1	23	.45	9.9	17	.77
25	11	13	.39	6.5	28	.51	6.2	9	.16
26	8.1	6	.15	6.6	25	.43	4.7	9	.11
27	6.8	4	.07	6.7	15	.27	4.5	9	.10
28	6.7	5	.09	6.3	11	.19	4.3	10	.11
29	15	27	5.2	---	---	---	4.2	11	.13
30	12	20	.83	---	---	---	4.2	11	.13
31	24	58	17	---	---	---	4.0	8	.09
TOTAL	458.3	---	99.21	192.9	---	15.97	175.2	---	5.63

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50044830 RIO GUADIANA AT GUADIANA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	3.8	9	.10	268	792	1250	25	44	3.0
2	3.6	14	.15	321	1090	1220	21	18	1.0
3	3.7	18	.18	122	279	120	20	13	.62
4	3.6	20	.19	50	45	6.4	18	8	.38
5	3.9	17	.17	65	159	72	16	6	.26
6	3.8	11	.10	234	891	2920	15	5	.20
7	3.9	10	.10	149	364	198	15	6	.23
8	62	194	194	58	158	36	17	8	.39
9	26	53	6.4	240	847	1020	16	9	.39
10	16	31	2.4	97	237	64	21	34	3.7
11	130	433	470	60	106	18	14	28	1.0
12	30	68	9.9	41	29	3.3	13	30	1.1
13	156	555	1060	29	28	2.1	14	25	.82
14	159	619	850	103	330	298	13	16	.53
15	124	365	336	37	50	5.6	12	10	.33
16	145	453	399	27	16	1.2	11	7	.21
17	47	109	18	23	13	.76	10	10	.27
18	17	28	1.3	18	12	.56	11	20	.98
19	10	16	.48	16	11	.43	63	147	27
20	48	133	47	15	8	.32	46	105	17
21	64	202	77	14	9	.34	17	25	1.2
22	30	60	5.8	29	62	20	19	30	1.5
23	14	19	.73	204	623	1480	13	43	1.6
24	10	21	.52	78	194	45	12	45	1.5
25	8.3	35	.80	81	209	51	11	43	1.3
26	6.9	27	.49	96	275	94	10	43	1.1
27	6.3	12	.21	75	181	37	10	43	1.2
28	60	149	79	51	111	15	34	89	19
29	222	809	1350	37	78	8.0	34	89	20
30	155	437	292	33	60	5.1	33	95	11
31	---	---	---	31	67	6.9	---	---	---
TOTAL	1572.8	---	5202.02	2702	---	8999.01	584	---	118.81

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50044830 RIO GUADIANA AT GUADIANA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	15	31	1.3	8.7	2	.05	4.9	5	.07
2	16	27	1.9	8.4	3	.07	5.1	4	.05
3	21	52	4.4	7.8	5	.11	4.8	2	.03
4	14	19	.73	7.6	6	.13	4.5	1	.01
5	12	10	.33	7.7	5	.11	4.7	1	.02
6	11	12	.34	7.6	4	.08	38	105	54
7	30	68	15	7.4	4	.07	9.4	16	.53
8	15	25	1.0	7.3	6	.12	5.6	5	.08
9	11	17	.50	7.8	13	.26	5.1	5	.08
10	11	20	.64	7.2	18	.36	4.9	5	.06
11	181	684	876	6.9	16	.28	4.8	4	.06
12	46	38	7.4	6.4	9	.17	4.3	3	.04
13	20	6	.35	6.1	7	.12	4.4	3	.04
14	14	8	.31	6.3	5	.09	5.4	3	.04
15	14	10	.33	7.1	14	.30	6.9	18	1.4
16	12	14	.42	78	220	92	14	29	3.9
17	11	23	.61	14	26	1.2	9.2	16	.86
18	9.7	24	.61	8.3	11	.22	59	190	109
19	9.2	16	.39	7.3	8	.13	100	373	427
20	9.3	49	1.5	6.4	8	.13	54	117	25
21	9.7	13	.55	6.2	8	.13	13	23	.87
22	21	44	5.3	8.9	11	.43	9.0	13	.31
23	27	63	6.5	8.5	14	.35	74	565	661
24	92	388	309	6.3	6	.10	32	70	9.4
25	20	28	1.8	5.8	4	.06	12	20	.70
26	22	38	4.8	5.8	4	.06	9.8	16	.40
27	16	24	1.3	5.7	4	.06	74	282	298
28	11	8	.24	6.2	4	.06	31	70	7.5
29	10	6	.18	6.2	5	.09	15	26	1.1
30	9.4	5	.14	6.1	8	.13	17	39	3.2
31	9.2	3	.09	5.3	8	.11	---	---	---
TOTAL	729.5	---	1243.96	295.3	---	97.58	635.8	---	1604.75
YEAR	8943.3		21739.71						

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50044830 RIO GUADIANA AT GUADIANA , PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDEDED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM	
DEC 1992								
26...	1235	593	18800	30100	22	33	51	
APR 1993								
14...	1500	141	4820	1830	30	40	60	
14...	1610	638	5170	8900	31	38	47	
MAY								
01...	1725	1140	4770	14700	34	44	59	
06...	2000	1820	16100	79100	25	32	37	
23...	1325	624	8110	13700	23	37	43	
DATE		SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
DEC 1992								
26...	51	68	82	93	97	98.6	100	
APR 1993								
14...	60	70	84	92	97	99	100	
14...	38	67	79	89	95	98.7	99	
MAY								
01...	68	76	90	96	98	99	100	
06...	48	57	70	80	86	90	97	
23...	57	70	82	94	98	99	100	

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50044830 RIO GUADIANA AT GUADIANA, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDEED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
NOV 1992					
13...	1735	10	95	2.6	99
DEC					
26...	1255	1540	9810	40790	70
26...	1650	500	1040	1400	92
28...	1325	60	1150	186	85
28...	1450	124	1330	445	76
APR 1993					
29...	1900	619	1390	2320	89
MAY					
01...	1540	584	3250	5120	91
06...	2115	1190	3750	12050	75
23..	1455	963	1950	5070	91

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50044850 RIO GUADIANA NEAR NARANJITO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'39", long 66°13'28", at steel-cross-bridge 0.8 mi (1.3 km) northwest of Highway 164, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) upstream from mouth and about 2.0 mi (3.2 km) northeast of Naranjito plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--4.0 mi² (10.3 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water year 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH SATUR-ATION) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992										
14...	0805	3.3	398	7.5	24.0	1.2	7.7	90	<10	K1000 2300
DEC 08...	0750	5.6	360	6.6	22.0	14	3.7	42	13	360 530
FEB 1993										
04...	0750	9.2	351	8.1	21.0	2.7	6.6	75	25	3300 8200
APR 07...	1025	4.2	369	7.7	24.5	1.5	7.5	88	<10	430 1300
MAY 26...	0810	56	263	7.5	23.5	18	7.9	96	26	K6600 5100
SEP 20...	1500	32	238	6.6	27.5	40	3.3	41	10	510 4100

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB TOT (MG/L AS CACO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT (MG/L AS CACO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1992											
14...	130	21	31	13	17	0.7	2.3	130	<0.5	17	25
DEC 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
APR 07...	150	--	34	15	19	0.7	2.8	130	<0.5	16	25
MAY 26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
SEP 20...	100	--	23	11	14	0.6	2.9	100	--	15	14

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
14...	0.10	27	198	1.76	3	2.29	0.010	2.30	0.040	0.16
DEC 08...	--	--	--	--	12	1.37	0.030	1.40	0.080	0.42
FEB 1993										
04...	--	--	--	--	7	1.29	0.010	1.30	0.010	0.69
APR 07...	0.10	25	215	2.44	33	1.59	0.010	1.60	0.020	0.38
MAY 26...	--	--	--	--	25	0.870	0.030	0.900	0.050	0.45
SEP 20...	0.10	23	163	14.1	31	1.19	0.010	1.20	0.010	0.39

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50045000 LAGO LA PLATA AT DAMSITE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'40", long 66°14'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 2.9 mi (4.7 km) at northeast of Plaza de Naranjito, 2.7 mi (4.3 km) West of Road 167, km 15.3, Buena Vista, Bayamón, 5.2 mi (8.4 km) east of Plaza de Corozal.

DRAINAGE AREA.--181 mi² (469 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1989 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago La Plata first construction phase was completed in 1974 and the second construction phase to provide the spillway with bascule gates was completed in October 1989. The maximum storage is 37,000 ac-ft (45.6 hm³) and its purpose is the supply of water for domestic and industrial use. La Plata Dam is a concrete gravity structure located across the Río de la Plata, the dam has an overall length of 774 ft (236 m) and a maximum height of about 131 ft (40 m). The dam spillway is provided with 6 bascule gates. The spillway crest has a total clear length of 690 ft (210 m), an elevation of 155 ft (47 m). The Dam is owned and operated by Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation, 167.02 ft (50.91 m), Jan. 5, 1992; minimum elevation, 144.88 ft (44.16 m), Oct. 29, 1991.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 166.12 ft (50.63 m), Sept. 23; minimum elevation, 145.86 ft (44.46 m), Apr. 8.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
98.43	2,760	164.05	28,550
131.24	11,360	170.61	33,160
154.60	22,720	175.52	37,040

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	154.07	154.48	154.99	155.06	154.92	152.52	147.33	159.57	158.06	158.19	161.86	163.47
2	153.98	154.31	155.00	155.10	154.85	152.39	147.09	159.52	158.10	157.97	161.82	163.24
3	153.84	154.32	154.99	155.09	154.84	152.21	146.91	158.65	158.11	157.97	161.81	163.18
4	153.66	154.82	155.03	155.05	154.85	152.04	146.70	158.85	158.06	157.87	161.82	163.12
5	153.55	154.89	155.01	155.10	154.77	151.88	146.47	159.36	157.98	157.73	161.83	163.26
6	155.48	154.82	154.94	155.13	154.71	151.71	146.22	161.16	157.92	157.55	161.12	163.95
7	155.17	154.78	154.88	155.31	154.66	151.53	146.00	159.31	157.88	157.54	161.04	164.21
8	155.00	154.80	154.82	155.05	154.56	151.34	146.27	159.27	157.87	157.45	161.00	164.41
9	154.84	154.74	154.80	154.94	154.47	151.16	147.01	159.26	157.99	157.32	161.01	164.45
10	154.83	154.68	154.75	154.91	154.37	150.98	147.51	157.48	158.07	157.21	160.95	164.34
11	154.70	154.66	154.69	154.91	154.27	150.81	150.36	158.12	158.01	159.34	160.86	164.41
12	154.53	154.64	154.58	154.93	154.18	150.62	152.21	158.46	157.92	159.58	160.76	164.41
13	154.35	154.71	154.51	154.91	154.11	150.43	154.33	158.63	157.90	159.46	160.70	164.38
14	154.24	154.87	154.80	154.89	154.02	150.29	156.81	159.14	157.86	159.40	160.33	164.05
15	154.10	155.10	155.10	154.88	153.91	150.12	157.21	158.26	157.77	159.25	159.29	164.06
16	153.93	154.93	154.97	154.87	153.83	150.07	156.88	158.61	157.93	159.05	162.50	164.09
17	153.83	154.83	154.95	154.86	153.74	150.01	157.34	158.78	158.01	158.88	162.89	164.13
18	154.05	154.85	154.96	154.83	153.64	149.87	157.70	158.84	158.04	158.65	163.27	164.48
19	154.20	154.87	154.98	154.81	153.49	149.72	157.68	158.81	159.60	158.46	163.45	164.85
20	154.42	155.19	154.94	154.79	153.48	149.50	158.16	158.78	158.89	158.22	163.49	164.77
21	154.42	154.94	154.90	154.77	153.44	149.33	158.63	158.72	158.86	158.02	163.56	164.77
22	154.31	155.09	154.93	154.93	153.36	149.14	158.84	158.86	159.19	158.21	163.67	164.81
23	154.81	155.05	154.95	155.02	153.25	148.99	158.80	160.40	159.21	160.06	163.88	166.02
24	155.28	154.93	155.12	154.95	153.20	148.88	158.68	159.66	159.01	163.24	164.03	165.12
25	155.02	154.82	155.17	154.97	153.09	148.73	158.54	159.54	158.80	162.73	163.97	164.54
26	154.87	154.77	155.75	154.92	152.95	148.53	158.40	160.14	158.59	162.81	164.02	164.22
27	154.77	156.64	155.14	154.89	152.80	148.33	158.30	159.23	158.40	162.32	163.76	164.64
28	154.69	155.41	155.19	154.88	152.66	148.13	157.99	159.15	158.54	162.04	163.76	164.78
29	154.57	155.05	155.23	155.16	---	147.95	160.52	159.12	158.67	161.92	163.99	164.94
30	154.53	155.10	155.11	154.93	---	147.73	159.46	157.80	158.48	161.92	164.06	164.96
31	154.51	---	155.10	154.94	---	147.51	---	157.95	---	161.90	163.77	---
MEAN	154.47	154.90	154.98	154.96	153.94	150.08	153.81	159.01	158.32	159.43	162.40	164.34
MAX	155.48	156.64	155.75	155.31	154.92	152.52	160.52	161.16	159.60	163.24	164.06	166.02
MIN	153.55	154.31	154.51	154.77	152.66	147.51	146.00	157.48	157.77	157.21	159.29	163.12

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50045010 RIO DE LA PLATA BELOW LA PLATA DAM, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'45", long 66°14'17", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 2.8 mi (4.5 km) west of Road 167, km 15.3, Buena Vista, Bayamón, 5.0 mi (8.0 km) east of Plaza de Corozal, 3.0 mi (4.8 km) northeast of Plaza de Naranjito.

DRAINAGE AREA.--173 mi² (448 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1989 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 164 ft (30 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Regulation at all stages by Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority reservoir upstream from gage. Gage-height satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.02	.43	350	149	201	3.5	1.0	758	61	198	137	96
2	.04	.46	207	150	146	3.5	1.0	1890	63	178	135	70
3	.06	.72	170	142	104	2.3	.97	1400	65	161	80	4.1
4	.09	9.4	153	125	80	1.9	.94	279	68	157	53	3.0
5	.10	43	146	105	36	2.3	.91	98	74	147	67	2.6
6	139	30	106	125	18	2.6	.91	989	74	136	279	96
7	661	15	52	232	6.3	2.7	.91	1800	66	123	102	267
8	191	17	26	365	3.3	2.6	1.4	757	63	118	78	3.6
9	69	11	16	166	3.1	2.5	3.2	749	70	107	75	2.9
10	23	2.7	8.6	115	3.1	2.6	2.7	207	74	94	73	31
11	10	.68	4.6	75	3.4	2.7	5.2	32	78	3680	71	3.0
12	.63	.50	3.2	60	3.7	2.3	5.2	42	75	996	69	2.2
13	.21	3.3	3.1	54	4.3	1.8	3.0	66	68	481	32	2.1
14	.14	45	3.9	50	3.4	1.6	.91	729	65	462	155	94
15	.12	106	128	40	3.4	1.4	392	721	79	313	460	2.6
16	.11	190	135	29	3.6	1.7	733	85	113	281	709	2.2
17	.11	107	80	21	3.7	2.0	100	88	77	259	400	1.8
18	.13	75	63	15	3.7	1.7	170	124	82	237	5.7	125
19	.14	91	49	10	3.6	1.5	300	141	1050	201	4.7	201
20	.19	172	37	7.3	3.7	1.3	267	141	1990	203	32	274
21	.27	361	25	5.8	3.7	1.2	223	142	404	192	4.2	51
22	.08	221	28	14	3.6	1.1	198	140	278	115	3.0	2.2
23	2.0	291	36	112	3.5	1.5	215	464	330	299	2.6	454
24	56	202	90	105	3.6	1.6	224	798	232	430	2.2	1340
25	552	136	193	97	3.5	1.4	208	457	194	662	34	451
26	179	66	755	76	3.5	1.3	193	324	167	474	3.7	263
27	54	1320	667	51	3.6	1.2	175	845	158	452	54	67
28	11	2000	487	26	3.5	1.1	428	554	131	268	9.2	2.3
29	.71	608	491	606	---	1.1	1080	307	125	203	8.3	2.1
30	.22	626	293	389	---	1.0	1910	118	219	143	5.6	56
31	.34	---	186	189	---	1.0	---	56	---	137	92	---
TOTAL	1950.71	6751.19	4992.4	3706.1	665.8	58.0	6934.34	15301	6593	11907	3236.2	3972.7
MEAN	62.9	225	161	120	23.8	1.87	231	494	220	384	104	132
MAX	661	2000	755	606	201	3.5	1910	1890	1990	3680	709	1340
MIN	.02	.43	3.1	5.8	3.1	1.0	.91	32	61	94	2.2	1.8
AC-FT	3870	13390	9900	7350	1320	115	13750	30350	13080	23620	6420	7880
CFSM	.36	1.30	.93	.69	.14	.01	1.34	2.86	1.27	2.22	.60	.77
IN.	.42	1.45	1.07	.80	.14	.01	1.49	3.29	1.42	2.56	.70	.86

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1989 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	344	91.9	61.5	442	64.2
MAX	1107	225	161	1581	222
(WY)	1991	1993	1993	1992	1991
MIN	.048	.16	.14	.19	.27
(WY)	1992	1992	1990	1990	1992

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1989 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	80405.26	66068.44	
ANNUAL MEAN	220	181	136
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			182
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			37.8
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	27400	3680	27400
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.00	.02	.00
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.00	.13	.00
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		16700	127000
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		16.43	34.76
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	159500	131000	98700
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.27	1.05	.79
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	17.31	14.22	10.71
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	222	463	246
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.89	69	2.3
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00	1.2	.00

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50045010 RIO DE LA PLATA AT BELOW LA PLATA DAM, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1990 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1989 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- Automatic sediment sampler and DH-48.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 2,180 mg/L Jan. 06, 1992; Minimum daily mean, <.05 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 362,000tons (328,000tonnes) Jan. 06, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 0.00 ton (0.00 tonne) several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

Water Year	Suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		Suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1993	382 (July 11)	1 (Several days)	10,700 (July 11)	<.01 (Several days)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	.02	2	<.01	.43	2	<.01	350	37	46
2	.04	2	<.01	.46	2	<.01	207	6	3.3
3	.06	2	<.01	.72	2	<.01	170	5	2.5
4	.09	2	<.01	9.4	3	.10	153	4	1.9
5	.10	2	<.01	43	5	.56	146	4	1.6
6	139	6	4.2	30	3	.27	106	4	1.2
7	661	6	11	15	2	.09	52	4	.63
8	191	6	3.2	17	2	.09	26	4	.31
9	69	5	1.0	11	2	.06	16	4	.18
10	23	4	.27	2.7	2	.01	8.6	4	.11
11	10	2	.09	.68	2	<.01	4.6	4	.05
12	.63	1	<.01	.50	2	<.01	3.2	4	.04
13	.21	1	<.01	3.3	2	.02	3.1	4	.04
14	.14	1	<.01	45	5	.71	3.9	4	.04
15	.12	1	<.01	106	7	2.8	128	9	3.5
16	.11	1	<.01	190	11	5.6	135	9	3.4
17	.11	1	<.01	107	8	2.5	80	6	1.7
18	.13	1	<.01	75	7	1.5	63	4	.71
19	.14	1	<.01	91	8	1.9	49	4	.51
20	.19	1	<.01	172	9	5.3	37	4	.39
21	.27	1	<.01	361	13	13	25	4	.26
22	.08	1	<.01	221	9	5.5	28	4	.28
23	2.0	1	.02	291	12	9.3	36	4	.36
24	56	5	1.5	202	11	5.9	90	7	1.9
25	552	15	23	136	10	3.5	193	11	5.9
26	179	10	5.2	66	7	1.3	755	16	32
27	54	6	.98	1320	158	1610	667	17	32
28	11	4	.11	2000	261	1770	487	22	27
29	.71	3	<.01	608	95	177	491	16	22
30	.22	3	<.01	626	95	162	293	13	12
31	.34	2	<.01	---	---	---	186	11	5.3
TOTAL	1950.71	---	50.57	6751.19	---	3779.01	4992.4	---	207.11

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50045010 RIO DE LA PLATA BELOW LA PLATA DAM, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	149	10	4.0	201	4	2.1	3.5	11	.11
2	150	8	3.1	146	4	1.6	3.5	9	.08
3	142	8	3.3	104	4	1.1	2.3	7	.05
4	125	8	2.8	80	3	.77	1.9	5	.03
5	105	8	2.8	36	3	.32	2.3	4	.02
6	125	9	3.0	18	3	.16	2.6	3	.02
7	232	11	7.9	6.3	3	.06	2.7	2	.02
8	365	12	12	3.3	3	.03	2.6	2	.02
9	166	9	4.9	3.1	3	.02	2.5	1	.01
10	115	8	2.6	3.1	3	.02	2.6	1	.00
11	75	7	1.6	3.4	3	.02	2.7	1	.00
12	60	7	1.1	3.7	3	.03	2.3	1	.01
13	54	6	.97	4.3	3	.05	1.8	2	.01
14	50	6	.82	3.4	4	.04	1.6	2	.00
15	40	6	.65	3.4	4	.04	1.4	2	.00
16	29	6	.46	3.6	4	.04	1.7	2	.01
17	21	6	.33	3.7	4	.04	2.0	2	.02
18	15	6	.24	3.7	4	.04	1.7	2	.01
19	10	6	.17	3.6	5	.04	1.5	2	.00
20	7.3	6	.13	3.7	5	.05	1.3	2	.00
21	5.8	6	.10	3.7	5	.05	1.2	2	.00
22	14	6	.22	3.6	5	.05	1.1	2	.00
23	112	8	2.5	3.5	7	.07	1.5	2	.00
24	105	7	2.2	3.6	9	.09	1.6	2	.00
25	97	6	1.5	3.5	11	.11	1.4	2	.00
26	76	6	1.3	3.5	13	.13	1.3	2	.00
27	51	6	.84	3.6	14	.14	1.2	2	.00
28	26	6	.44	3.5	13	.13	1.1	2	.00
29	606	21	38	---	---	---	1.1	2	.00
30	389	5	5.7	---	---	---	1.0	2	.00
31	189	4	2.1	---	---	---	1.0	2	.00
TOTAL	3706.1	---	107.77	665.8	---	7.34	58.0	---	0.42

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50045010 RIO DE LA PLATA BELOW LA PLATA DAM, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SRDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SRDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SRDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	1.0	2	<.01	758	101	590	61	6	1.1
2	1.0	2	<.01	1890	260	1580	63	7	1.1
3	.97	2	<.01	1400	196	908	65	7	1.2
4	.94	2	<.01	279	35	48	68	7	1.2
5	.91	2	<.01	98	23	6.5	74	7	1.4
6	.91	2	<.01	989	115	2150	74	7	1.4
7	.91	2	<.01	1800	233	2410	66	7	1.2
8	1.4	2	.01	757	109	227	63	7	1.1
9	3.2	2	.01	749	114	243	70	7	1.3
10	2.7	2	.01	207	31	35	74	7	1.5
11	5.2	2	.04	32	6	.49	78	7	1.6
12	5.2	2	.04	42	5	.70	75	7	1.5
13	3.0	2	.02	66	6	1.2	68	7	1.3
14	91	7	2.4	729	88	447	65	7	1.2
15	392	43	329	721	53	166	79	7	1.6
16	733	92	493	85	6	1.3	113	8	2.8
17	100	8	2.1	88	4	1.1	77	7	1.5
18	170	10	5.3	124	4	1.5	82	7	1.7
19	300	12	9.3	141	5	1.9	1050	131	762
20	267	12	9.6	141	5	1.9	1990	236	1490
21	223	12	7.8	142	5	1.9	404	13	16
22	198	12	6.4	140	5	1.9	278	12	9.1
23	215	12	7.0	464	11	23	330	13	12
24	224	12	7.1	798	18	39	232	11	7.0
25	208	12	6.4	457	14	17	194	11	5.7
26	193	11	5.7	324	12	11	167	10	4.6
27	175	11	5.2	845	18	44	158	10	4.2
28	428	50	387	554	15	24	131	9	3.2
29	1080	120	2320	307	13	11	125	9	3.3
30	1910	233	2590	118	9	3.3	219	11	6.6
31	---	---	---	56	6	.82	---	---	---
TOTAL	6934.34	---	6193.43	15301	---	8997.51	6593	---	2349.4

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50045010 RIO DE LA PLATA BELOW LA PLATA DAM, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	198	11	5.8	137	3	1.1	96	86	55
2	178	10	5.0	135	3	1.1	70	14	38
3	161	10	4.4	80	3	.70	4.1	3	.04
4	157	10	4.2	53	3	.42	3.0	2	.02
5	147	10	3.8	67	4	.92	2.6	2	.02
6	136	9	3.4	279	50	236	96	4	3.9
7	123	9	3.0	102	15	4.3	267	9	13
8	118	9	2.8	78	8	1.7	3.6	2	.02
9	107	8	2.4	75	7	1.4	2.9	2	.02
10	94	8	2.0	73	7	1.4	31	3	1.5
11	3680	382	10700	71	7	1.3	3.0	2	.02
12	996	141	721	69	7	1.3	2.2	2	.02
13	481	82	107	32	4	.49	2.1	2	.02
14	462	83	113	155	7	5.6	94	15	70
15	313	12	9.9	460	14	19	2.6	4	.03
16	281	8	6.5	709	20	52	2.2	3	.02
17	259	5	3.5	400	12	20	1.8	2	.00
18	237	3	1.9	5.7	3	.05	125	6	4.7
19	201	3	1.6	4.7	2	.03	201	10	5.6
20	203	3	1.6	32	4	1.3	274	11	11
21	192	3	1.5	4.2	4	.05	51	6	1.4
22	115	3	.90	3.0	3	.03	2.2	2	.02
23	299	9	11	2.6	3	.02	454	56	480
24	430	13	17	2.2	3	.02	1340	175	1260
25	662	28	50	34	4	1.5	451	76	96
26	474	14	18	3.7	3	.02	263	45	32
27	452	14	17	54	4	3.9	67	13	4.1
28	268	11	8.8	9.2	3	.07	2.3	3	.03
29	203	10	7.4	8.3	3	.06	2.1	2	.02
30	143	6	2.5	5.6	3	.04	56	4	3.0
31	137	3	1.1	92	15	96	---	---	---
TOTAL	11907	---	11838.00	3236.2	---	451.82	3972.7	---	2079.50
YEAR	66068.44		36061.88						

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50046000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT HWY 2 NR TOA ALTA, PR
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'41", long 66°15'39", at Highway 2, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) downstream from Rio Lajas, and 1.6 mi (2.6 km) northwest of Toa Alta, 11.3 mi (18.2 km) downstream from Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority reservoir.

DRAINAGE AREA.--208 mi² (539 km²), exclude 8.2 mi² (21.2 km²) upstream from Lago Carite, flow from which is diverted to Rio Guamanf.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958 to current year

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, SATUR-ATION (%)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	
OCT 1992	05...	1115	16	472	7.4	30.0	0.30	6.9	90	K900	500	190
DEC	24...	0805	58	405	7.0	25.0	13	4.0	84	K1800	K1800	160
FEB 1993	01...	0835	139	342	7.6	25.0	0.50	5.0	69	K760	700	140
APR	05...	0915	17	461	7.2	27.0	20	5.2	124	240	64	190
JUN	09...	0915	70	428	7.1	27.5	8.0	3.4	72	K19000	K2100	190
SEP	07...	0900	500	340	8.1	29.2	5.2	3.9	57	5200	1000	150

DATE	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	
OCT 1992	05...	130	59	11	23	0.7	3.3	200	19	33	0.20	18
DEC	24...	210	49	8.8	18	0.6	2.8	160	17	23	0.10	15
FEB 1993	01...	160	36	11	17	0.6	2.6	130	15	20	0.10	19
APR	05...	130	56	13	23	0.7	3.2	180	22	36	0.10	18
JUN	09...	160	57	11	20	0.6	3.0	160	20	26	0.10	17
SEP	07...	120	40	12	19	0.7	6.8	140	22	19	0.10	19

DATE	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 180 DEG. C DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NH4)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHORUS DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHORUS ORTHO, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHORUS ORTHO, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS PO4)	
OCT 1992	05...	289	291	12.2	0.770	0.030	0.04	0.40	0.190	0.180	0.160	0.49
DEC	24...	250	228	35.7	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993	01...	193	203	76.2	0.360	0.070	0.09	0.40	0.140	0.100	0.100	0.31
APR	05...	292	284	13.0	0.390	0.040	0.05	0.30	0.110	0.090	0.110	0.34
JUN	09...	259	249	47.1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP	07...	228	218	294	0.160	0.080	0.10	0.50	0.070	0.070	0.050	0.15

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50046000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT HWY 2 NR TOA ALTA, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

DATE	ALUM- INUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AL)	ARSENIC DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS BA)	BERYL- LIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS BE)	CADMIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CR)	COBALT, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CO)	COPPER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CU)	IRON, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS PB)	LITHIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS LI)
OCT 1992											
05...	10	<1	50	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	4	9	2	<4
DEC											
24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
01...	80	1	35	<0.5	2	<1	<3	2	14	<1	<4
APR											
05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN											
09...	30	2	57	<0.5	1	<1	<3	2	33	1	<4
SEP											
07...	90	1	45	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	3	11	5	<4

DATE	MANGA- NESE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS HG)	MOLYB- DENUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MO)	NICKEL, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS NI)	SELE- NIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AG)	STRON- TIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SR)	VANA- DIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS V)	ZINC, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS ZN)
OCT 1992									
05...	62	<0.1	<10	3	<1	<1.0	270	12	15
DEC									
24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993									
01...	34	0.2	<10	1	<1	<1.0	150	<6	8
APR									
05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN									
09...	78	<0.1	<10	2	<1	<1.0	220	7	5
SEP									
07...	25	<0.1	<10	2	<1	<1.0	150	9	7

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50046000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT HWY 2 NR TOA ALTA, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1992					
05...	1115	16	16	0.67	95
DEC 1993					
24...	0805	58	18	2.77	96
FEB					
01...	0835	139	20	7.43	75
APR					
05...	0915	17	44	2.0	65
JUN					
09...	0915	70	31	5.76	95
SEP					
07...	0900	168	48	22	75

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993										
29...	0930	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010

DATE	ENDRIN WATER UNFLTRD REC (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993									
29...	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993									
29...	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

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Figure 19.--Río Hondo to Río Puerto Nuevo basins.

RIO HONDO BASIN

50047530 RIO HONDO AT FLOOD CHANNEL NEAR CATANO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'13", long 66°09'36", at Rio Hondo Channel, 800 ft (245 m) below junction with Rio Hondo, 0.9 mi (1.5 km) downstream from bridge on de Diego Expressway and 1.1 mi (1.8 km) above mouth.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH SATUR-ATION) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS. / 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
NOV 1992	05...	--	940	7.3	28.0	24	4.3	54	58	K140000	22000
JAN 1993	05...	--	16000	8.1	26.0	9.0	11.6	140	72	2100	K450
MAR 1993	08...	--	25000	8.2	24.5	2.0	7.0	82	370	20000	20000
MAY 1993	04...	--	3500	6.9	28.5	31	3.1	39	46	41000	32000
JUN 1993	21...	--	7600	7.1	27.5	0.80	4.0	50	120	15000	19000
AUG 1993	24...	--	39000	7.8	31.5	20	4.7	62	670	25000	6900

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARBONATE (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
NOV 1992	700	26	66	129	1099	17	41	110	<0.5	290	2100
JAN 1993	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
MAR 1993	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
MAY 1993	430	29	51	74	580	12	23	89	<0.5	170	990
JUN 1993	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
AUG 1993	3800	18	270	770	6500	46	180	160	--	1700	11000

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
NOV 1992	0.20	10	3800	--	24	0.090	0.010	0.100	4.40	2.6
JAN 1993	--	--	--	--	18	0.080	0.020	0.100	8.90	6.1
MAR 1993	--	--	--	--	4	0.060	0.040	0.100	6.60	5.4
MAY 1993	0.20	8.4	1950	--	41	0.060	0.040	0.100	2.80	3.6
JUN 1993	--	--	--	--	16	0.150	0.050	0.200	4.20	4.9
AUG 1993	2.1	3.7	20500	--	87	0.350	0.050	0.400	0.70	3.4

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN
 50047535 RIO DE BAYAMON AT ARENAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'11", long 66°07'18", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at left bank, 2.61 mi (4.20 km) southeast of plaza de Cidra, 0.56 mi (0.90 km) southwest from Escuela Segunda Unidad de Bayamón, and 2.70 mi (4.34 km) northeast from Central Cayey.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.45 mi² (1.16 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1992 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 1,378 ft (420 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992
 DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1											.06	.07
2											.10	.06
3											.09	.11
4											.07	.08
5											6.2	.08
6											2.9	.13
7											.75	.09
8											.36	.10
9											.21	.95
10											.14	.12
11											.28	.08
12											.18	.06
13											.17	.05
14											.24	.05
15											.23	.05
16											.13	.77
17											.11	2.3
18											.10	1.0
19											.11	12
20											.10	17
21											.08	5.0
22											.06	2.4
23											.06	1.5
24											.06	.93
25										.18	.06	.60
26										.09	.21	.39
27										.07	.13	.18
28										.06	.82	.12
29										.06	.14	.11
30										.06	.07	.10
31										.06	.13	---
TOTAL											14.35	46.48
MEAN											.46	1.55
MAX											6.2	17
MIN											.06	.05
AC-FT											.28	.92
CFSM											1.03	3.44
IN.											1.19	3.84

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1992, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	---	.46	1.55
MAX	---	.46	1.55
(WY)	---	1992	1992
MIN	---	.46	1.55
(WY)	---	1992	1992

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047535 RIO DE BAYAMON AT ARENAS, PR-Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.10	.19	1.9	1.1	.16	.12	.05	10	.24	.15	.22	.15
2	.09	.18	1.1	.84	.12	.12	.05	17	.24	.18	.23	.16
3	.08	.27	1.8	.72	.14	.11	.05	3.2	.22	.20	.21	.17
4	.07	.81	1.0	.59	.13	.11	.05	1.1	e.21	.16	.19	.15
5	.09	.35	.56	.50	.16	.12	.04	.73	e.20	.13	.22	.16
6	3.2	.69	.30	1.3	.19	.12	.04	.71	e.18	.13	.20	.27
7	1.5	.55	.21	1.5	.18	.13	.04	.52	e.17	.16	.19	.14
8	.55	.32	.15	1.1	.20	.12	.26	.40	e.16	.17	.19	.19
9	.16	.37	.13	1.3	.12	.12	.27	.66	e.16	.13	.19	.14
10	.15	2.4	.11	.83	.11	.11	.13	.74	.14	.12	.23	e.25
11	.12	.19	.10	.39	.16	.09	.10	.45	.13	28	.24	e.13
12	.09	.11	.10	.31	.31	.08	.17	.35	.12	3.5	.20	e.12
13	.10	.11	.12	.26	.44	.07	.51	.29	.14	1.1	.19	e.11
14	.10	.12	e.30	.75	.18	.08	e3.2	17	.14	.56	.19	e.12
15	.11	.11	e.16	.31	.15	.09	e2.3	2.2	.21	.27	.29	e.12
16	.11	.12	e.14	.26	.19	.08	e1.5	1.1	.15	.33	14	e.13
17	.15	1.0	e.16	.22	.12	.17	.50	.71	.10	.15	1.9	e.18
18	.22	1.1	e.17	.18	.12	.14	.20	.44	.13	.10	.72	e.30
19	.16	.80	e.16	.18	.12	.16	.13	.32	8.2	.09	.39	e.13
20	.13	.23	e.15	.13	.11	.11	.13	.30	5.0	.09	.28	e.25
21	.12	.10	e.14	.11	.17	.09	.17	.29	.91	.09	.24	e.13
22	.11	.61	e.20	.95	.12	.08	.11	.27	8.9	4.0	.45	e.11
23	.10	.41	e.15	.65	.10	.08	.07	.30	1.9	6.9	.67	e13
24	.71	.12	e.21	.32	.10	.09	.06	.28	.67	13	.25	1.5
25	.34	.11	e.20	.69	.10	.08	.07	.31	.34	2.7	.19	.39
26	.09	.11	e5.6	.35	.11	.07	.10	1.0	.22	1.3	.16	.24
27	.10	9.9	e1.0	.25	.12	.07	.07	.53	.16	.86	.15	.18
28	.11	7.4	e.81	.38	.12	.06	.20	.42	.13	.46	.15	.18
29	.11	4.2	.53	2.0	---	.05	2.3	.32	.14	.33	.15	.62
30	.13	6.1	.37	.53	---	.05	.71	.29	.21	.26	.15	.30
31	.19	---	1.5	.24	---	.05	---	.25	---	.24	.16	---
TOTAL	9.39	39.08	19.53	19.24	4.35	3.02	13.58	62.48	29.82	65.86	23.19	20.02
MEAN	.30	1.30	.63	.62	.16	.097	.45	2.02	.99	2.12	.75	.67
MAX	3.2	9.9	5.6	2.0	.44	.17	3.2	17	8.9	28	14	13
MIN	.07	.10	.10	.11	.10	.05	.04	.25	.10	.09	.15	.11
AC-FT	19	78	39	38	8.6	6.0	27	124	59	131	46	40
CFSM	.67	2.89	1.40	1.38	.35	.22	1.01	4.48	2.21	4.72	1.66	1.48
IN.	.78	3.23	1.61	1.59	.36	.25	1.12	5.17	2.47	5.44	1.92	1.65

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1992	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992	1993
MEAN	.30	1.30	.63	.62	.16	.097	.45	2.02	.99	2.12	.61	1.11
MAX	.30	1.30	.63	.62	.16	.097	.45	2.02	.99	2.12	.75	1.55
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992
MIN	.30	1.30	.63	.62	.16	.097	.45	2.02	.99	2.12	.46	.67
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992	1993

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1992 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	309.56		
ANNUAL MEAN	.85	.85	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN		.85	1993
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN		.85	1993
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	28	Jul 11	28 Jul 11 1993
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.04	Apr 5	.04 Apr 5 1993
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.05	Apr 1	.05 Apr 1 1993
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW	255	May 14	255 May 14 1993
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE	5.40	May 14	5.40 May 14 1993
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	614		614
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.88		1.88
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHRS)	25.59		25.61
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.4		1.5
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.19		.18
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.09		.08

e Estimated

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047540 RIO SABANA AT VISTA MONTE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'28", long 66°08'38", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at left bank, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) southeast of Plaza de Cidra, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) southwest from Escuela Segunda Unidad de Bayamón, and 0.4 mi (0.6 km) upstream from Lago de Cidra.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.80 mi² (2.07 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1992 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 1,345 ft (410 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1												.40
2												.39
3												.40
4											e.39	.34
5											14	.58
6											3.0	.94
7											.78	.44
8											.64	.57
9											.64	.66
10											.60	.34
11											.70	.33
12											.58	.32
13											.61	.32
14											.68	.33
15											.86	.37
16											.54	.64
17											.48	1.5
18											.45	.55
19											.42	6.5
20											.40	12
21											.38	4.1
22											.37	1.7
23											.37	.72
24											.35	.37
25											.35	.35
26											.39	.33
27											.34	.35
28											.69	.36
29											.46	.40
30											.35	.38
31											.39	---
TOTAL											---	36.98
MEAN											---	1.23
MAX											---	12
MIN											---	.32
AC-FT											---	.73
CFSM											---	1.54
IN.											---	1.72

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1992, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	---	1.23
MAX	---	1.23
(WY)	---	1992
MIN	---	1.23
(WY)	---	1992

e Estimated

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047540 RIO SABANA AT VISTA MONTE, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.41	.60	1.2	.84	.42	.23	.14	16	e.12	.13	e.47	.29
2	.42	.40	.97	.78	.41	.21	.15	23	e.12	.14	e.46	.31
3	.44	.88	1.2	.78	.44	.19	.15	3.8	e.12	.14	e.44	.26
4	.47	.80	.85	.76	.43	.19	.13	.58	e.12	.14	e.43	.23
5	7.7	.47	.75	.79	.42	.18	.14	.34	e.12	.13	e.54	.28
6	1.2	.52	.71	1.1	.40	.17	.14	1.9	e.12	.15	.57	.75
7	.51	.48	.65	1.6	.36	.17	.15	.29	e.12	.11	.55	.21
8	.47	.45	.68	.91	.32	.16	1.1	.28	e.12	.13	.50	.22
9	.50	.47	.76	.82	.34	.15	1.1	.79	e.12	.12	.51	.22
10	.50	3.2	.71	.70	.32	.15	.24	.53	.12	.12	.41	.37
11	.50	.54	.70	.64	.31	.14	.94	.36	.12	49	.44	.20
12	.69	.51	.81	.63	.39	.14	.20	.29	.11	5.3	.41	.18
13	.37	.54	.98	.56	.33	.13	1.7	.23	.12	1.2	.42	.17
14	.42	.55	1.3	.67	.29	.13	5.6	18	.12	.80	.40	.18
15	.44	.55	.83	.47	.29	.12	2.1	.77	.15	.68	.44	.18
16	.78	.57	.73	.45	.27	.13	.67	.32	.12	.65	16	.19
17	.60	1.7	.79	.42	.29	.16	.40	.23	.11	.58	.97	.28
18	1.6	.90	.80	.40	.29	.13	.32	.19	.16	.58	.48	.46
19	2.0	1.1	.77	.40	.27	.14	.38	.17	7.1	.59	.41	.20
20	.48	.71	.74	.41	.36	.13	.57	.15	6.2	.59	.36	.38
21	.52	.54	.68	.40	.29	.12	1.8	.14	.38	.58	.33	.19
22	.59	.73	.86	1.6	.29	.13	.34	.14	8.3	2.8	.46	.17
23	.67	.61	.72	.61	.29	.14	.35	.17	.71	2.7	.51	22
24	.77	.58	.88	.42	.28	.13	.34	.14	.30	20	.28	1.2
25	.54	.58	.87	.49	.27	.11	.37	.20	.21	2.2	.28	.25
26	.47	.60	9.2	.50	.27	.12	.33	.39	.18	1.0	.27	.18
27	.50	17	.71	.46	.26	.12	.43	.18	.16	.77	.50	.16
28	.50	4.5	.72	.48	.22	.12	1.5	.15	.14	e.61	.25	.15
29	.49	1.7	.80	2.3	---	.12	14	.14	.16	e.56	.27	.17
30	.46	3.9	.90	.54	---	.13	1.1	.13	.16	e.52	.28	.15
31	.60	---	1.1	.44	---	.13	---	.12	---	e.49	.30	---
TOTAL	26.61	46.68	34.37	22.37	9.12	4.52	36.88	70.12	26.21	93.51	28.94	30.18
MEAN	.86	1.56	1.11	.72	.33	.15	1.23	2.26	.87	3.02	.93	1.01
MAX	7.7	17	9.2	2.3	.44	.23	.14	.23	8.3	.49	.16	.22
MIN	.37	.40	.65	.40	.22	.11	.13	.12	.11	.11	.25	.15
AC-FT	53	93	68	44	18	9.0	73	139	52	185	57	60
CFSM	1.07	1.94	1.39	.90	.41	.18	1.54	2.83	1.09	3.77	1.17	1.26
IN.	1.24	2.17	1.60	1.04	.42	.21	1.71	3.26	1.22	4.35	1.35	1.40

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1992	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993
MEAN	.86	1.56	1.11	.72	.33	.15	1.23	2.26	.87	3.02	.93	1.12
MAX	.86	1.56	1.11	.72	.33	.15	1.23	2.26	.87	3.02	.93	1.23
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992
MIN	.86	1.56	1.11	.72	.33	.15	1.23	2.26	.87	3.02	.93	1.01
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1992 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	429.51		
ANNUAL MEAN	1.18	1.18	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN		1.18	1993
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN		1.18	1993
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	49	Jul 11	49 Jul 11 1993
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.11	Mar 25	.11 Mar 25 1993
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.12	Jun 6	.12 Jun 6 1993
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW	296	Sep 23	296 Sep 23 1993
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE	4.63	Sep 23	4.63 Sep 23 1993
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW	.11	Mar 23	.11 Mar 23 1993
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	852		852
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.47		1.47
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	19.97		19.99
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.2		1.4
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.42		.42
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.13		.14

e Estimated

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047550 LAGO CIDRA AT DAMSITE NEAR CIDRA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°11'57", long 66°08'29", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at Lago de Cidra Dam on Río de Bayamón, 1.9 mi (3.0 km) northeast of Plaza de Cidra and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) northwest of Escuela Segunda Unidad de Bayamón.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.26 mi² (21.39 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago de Cidra was completed in 1946. The maximum storage is 5,300 ac-ft (6.53 hm³) and provides supplemental water to metropolitan San Juan. The dam is a concrete gravity and earthfill structure approximately 541 ft (165 m) long between abutments with a maximum structural height of about 78.7 ft (24.0 m). The spillway portion of the dam, length 131 ft (40 m) and crest elevation 1,322 ft (403 m), is an ungated ogee crest located 131 ft (40 m) from the right abutment. This dam is owned by Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation 1,324.14 ft (403.60 m), July 11, 1993; minimum elevation 1,305.18 ft (397.82 m), Sept. 30, 1990.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 1,324.14 ft (403.60 m), July 11; minimum elevation, 1,311.77 ft (399.83 m), Apr. 8.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
1,305	1,970	1,319	4,400
1,309	2,610	1,322	5,200
1,312	3,100	1,328	6,920

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	1313.89	1314.79	1317.61	1317.82	1317.49	1316.27	1312.99	1316.80	1321.40	1322.32	1322.04	1320.83
2	1313.85	1314.68	1317.73	1317.81	1317.53	1316.34	1312.75	1316.74	1321.44	1322.37	1321.93	1320.77
3	1313.80	1314.73	1317.78	1317.79	1317.63	1316.30	1312.54	1318.09	1321.46	1322.42	1321.82	1320.72
4	1313.78	1314.85	1317.84	1317.76	1317.69	1316.28	1312.31	1318.18	1321.40	1322.44	1321.72	1320.66
5	1313.83	1314.96	1317.89	1317.77	1317.72	1316.26	1312.12	1318.25	1321.34	1322.45	1321.62	1320.62
6	1314.23	1315.04	1317.95	1317.78	1317.73	1316.24	1311.98	1318.61	1321.28	1322.47	1321.52	1320.64
7	1314.60	1315.05	1317.86	1317.93	1317.73	1316.07	1311.87	1318.74	1321.23	1322.49	1321.40	1320.59
8	1314.65	1315.06	1317.84	1317.92	1317.73	1316.94	1311.96	1318.81	1321.22	1322.52	1321.30	1320.56
9	1314.69	1315.04	1317.82	1317.92	A	A	1311.90	1319.02	1321.24	1322.51	1321.18	1320.50
10	1314.67	1315.32	1317.82	1317.89	A	A	1311.85	1319.17	1321.26	1322.48	1321.08	1320.54
11	1314.58	1315.24	1317.82	1317.87	A	A	1312.02	1319.25	1321.16	A	1320.97	1320.49
12	1314.54	1315.14	1317.77	1317.85	A	A	1312.12	1319.30	1320.98	1322.56	1320.85	1320.43
13	1314.60	1314.99	1317.64	1317.82	A	A	1312.52	1319.34	1320.83	1322.49	1320.73	1320.39
14	1314.62	1314.91	1317.74	1317.83	A	1315.00	1313.06	1320.70	1320.79	1322.43	1320.62	1320.38
15	1314.58	1314.86	1317.77	1317.78	A	1314.88	1314.06	1320.80	1320.84	1322.41	1320.53	1320.35
16	1314.49	1314.82	1317.74	1317.74	A	1314.87	1314.20	1320.83	1320.87	1322.40	1321.79	1320.34
17	1314.50	1314.99	1317.69	1317.70	A	1314.90	1314.28	1320.85	1320.86	1322.35	1321.82	1320.36
18	1314.58	1315.24	1317.63	1317.65	1317.64	1314.88	1314.33	1320.86	1320.79	1322.22	1321.82	1320.51
19	1314.64	1315.38	1317.57	1317.61	1317.51	1314.79	1314.32	1320.86	1321.54	1322.10	1321.74	1320.49
20	1314.86	1315.44	1317.51	1317.55	1317.44	1314.60	1314.36	1320.92	1321.76	1321.92	1321.64	1320.53
21	1314.94	1315.45	1317.40	1317.51	1317.27	1314.45	1314.60	1320.96	1321.80	1321.79	1321.55	1320.51
22	1314.96	1315.42	1317.29	1317.67	1317.09	1314.36	1314.62	1321.01	1322.16	1322.07	1321.55	1320.51
23	1315.01	1315.33	1317.10	1317.66	1316.91	1314.25	1314.62	1321.09	1322.24	1322.33	1321.50	1321.68
24	1315.07	1315.30	1316.90	1317.63	1316.65	1314.09	1314.61	1321.10	1322.28	1322.67	1321.42	1321.76
25	1315.16	1315.35	1316.71	1317.61	1316.46	1313.88	1314.60	1321.12	1322.25	1322.50	1321.36	1321.79
26	1315.19	1315.34	1317.78	1317.57	1316.39	1313.72	1314.62	1321.21	1322.13	1322.46	1321.28	1321.81
27	1315.17	1316.20	1317.83	1317.53	1316.31	1313.62	1314.55	1321.21	1322.15	1322.41	1321.24	1321.81
28	1315.10	1316.83	1317.82	1317.51	1316.29	1313.50	1314.58	1321.19	1322.17	1322.38	1321.14	1321.80
29	1315.02	1317.01	1317.83	1317.61	---	1313.36	1315.46	1321.26	1322.23	1322.34	1321.04	1321.83
30	1314.92	1317.43	1317.81	1317.57	---	1313.19	1315.60	1321.30	1322.28	1322.24	1320.95	1321.82
31	1314.85	---	1317.83	1317.53	---	1313.05	---	1321.35	---	1322.14	1320.89	---
MEAN	1314.62	1315.34	1317.66	1317.72	---	---	1313.51	1319.96	1321.51	---	1321.36	1320.87
MAX	1315.19	1317.43	1317.95	1317.93	---	---	1315.60	1321.35	1322.28	---	1322.04	1321.83
MIN	1313.78	1314.68	1316.71	1317.51	---	---	1311.85	1316.74	1320.79	---	1320.53	1320.34

A No gage-height record

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047560 RIO DE BAYAMON BELOW LAGO CIDRA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'04", long 66°08'26", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) downstream of Lago Cidra Dam on right bank, 2.1 mi (3.4 km) northwest of Plaza de Cidra.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.31 mi² (21.5 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 1,279 ft (390 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Regulation at all stages by Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority reservoir upstream from gage. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	21	21	2.5	9.2	8.1	7.1	8.7	5.3	4.4	3.3	16	15
2	26	22	6.2	9.0	8.2	7.2	33	4.1	4.3	3.6	17	15
3	26	24	19	8.8	6.9	7.5	34	3.6	4.3	5.1	17	15
4	17	9.3	11	8.8	5.7	7.2	31	3.6	29	7.0	16	14
5	9.1	2.6	10	8.8	9.7	7.1	23	3.7	14	7.3	16	15
6	10	10	11	8.6	16	6.9	15	5.1	13	7.9	17	15
7	9.9	14	27	9.3	16	35	9.3	3.4	14	9.5	16	15
8	10	14	16	8.6	15	22	16	3.8	8.2	10	16	15
9	10	19	11	8.5	16	7.0	23	3.8	4.0	9.9	17	15
10	28	39	11	8.3	16	8.3	11	3.6	4.2	8.6	16	15
11	41	37	11	8.2	14	35	4.4	3.6	36	632	17	15
12	26	37	21	8.1	7.7	35	4.3	3.5	56	143	16	15
13	20	38	55	8.0	5.3	35	6.6	3.6	55	24	16	13
14	20	18	24	8.2	5.4	35	4.8	7.7	19	13	16	11
15	20	9.9	9.2	8.0	6.4	17	11	3.7	4.0	6.3	16	10
16	20	10	6.1	7.9	11	9.4	3.5	3.6	4.0	5.7	12	9.9
17	20	10	6.2	8.2	10	9.0	3.6	3.5	16	7.7	5.5	9.9
18	23	5.0	6.2	8.3	10	8.3	3.8	3.8	49	17	5.9	12
19	13	2.8	5.9	8.4	6.0	22	8.6	3.6	17	17	14	9.4
20	6.9	17	6.0	8.8	4.1	35	12	3.8	4.1	17	14	7.7
21	4.7	23	16	8.5	9.6	26	3.8	3.8	4.0	17	14	5.6
22	6.8	49	32	8.6	9.7	15	3.6	4.0	3.8	19	15	5.5
23	6.3	51	39	8.2	9.7	20	3.6	4.0	3.7	11	15	6.1
24	6.5	32	41	8.1	10	35	3.5	4.1	3.6	104	12	5.5
25	6.3	8.6	39	8.1	10	34	3.5	4.3	28	43	11	5.2
26	13	8.7	39	8.1	14	24	3.6	5.8	51	19	12	5.1
27	21	12	9.6	8.2	14	16	13	4.3	3.4	13	14	7.6
28	23	9.7	9.2	8.3	7.1	16	14	4.4	3.6	7.9	15	11
29	23	10	9.7	7.9	---	17	11	4.3	3.3	7.5	15	11
30	22	6.0	9.4	8.0	---	16	3.8	4.4	3.4	15	15	10
31	21	---	9.5	8.2	---	16	---	4.1	---	15	15	---
TOTAL	530.5	569.6	528.7	260.2	281.6	591.0	330.0	127.9	467.3	1226.3	449.4	334.5
MEAN	17.1	19.0	17.1	8.39	10.1	19.1	11.0	4.13	15.6	39.6	14.5	11.1
MAX	41	51	55	9.3	16	35	34	7.7	56	632	17	15
MIN	4.7	2.6	2.5	7.9	4.1	6.9	3.5	3.4	3.3	3.3	5.5	5.1
AC-FT	1050	1130	1050	516	559	1170	655	254	927	2430	891	663
CFSM	2.06	2.28	2.05	1.01	1.21	2.29	1.32	.50	1.87	4.75	1.74	1.34
IN.	2.37	2.55	2.36	1.16	1.26	2.64	1.48	.57	2.09	5.48	2.01	1.50

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1991 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1991	1992	1993	1991	1992	1993	1991	1992	1993	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	18.8	33.5	19.9	27.6	23.3	18.7	15.4	8.82	15.2	23.6	18.3	13.8
MAX	20.5	41.2	30.4	59.6	36.5	23.7	23.0	12.2	17.8	39.6	27.5	16.0
(WY)	1992	1992	1992	1992	1991	1992	1992	1991	1992	1993	1991	1991
MIN	17.1	19.0	12.4	8.39	10.1	13.4	11.0	4.13	12.1	11.7	12.8	11.1
(WY)	1993	1993	1991	1993	1993	1991	1993	1993	1991	1991	1992	1993

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1991 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	7862.71		5697.0			
ANNUAL MEAN	21.5		15.6		20.2	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					24.7	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					15.6	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	981	Jan 6	632	Jul 11	981	Jan 6 1992
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.60	Aug 6	2.5	Dec 1	.60	Aug 6 1992
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	1.7	Aug 3	3.6	May 7	1.7	Aug 3 1992
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			2090	Jul 11	2090	Jul 11 1993
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			16.56	Jul 11	16.56	Jul 11 1993
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	15600		11300		14610	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.58		1.88		2.42	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	35.16		25.47		32.94	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	32		28		34	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	16		10		13	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	5.8		3.8		4.4	

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047560 RIO DE BAYAMON BELOW LAGO CIDRA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1991 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: November 1990 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- DH-48 and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 3,670 mg/L Jan. 05, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 6 mg/L Sep. 01, 1991.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 9,830 tons (8,920 tonnes) Jan. 05, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 0.04 ton (0.03 tonne) Aug 09-10, 1992.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

Water Year	Suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		Suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1993	473 (July 24)	13 (Several days)	269 (July 11)	.10 (Nov. 05)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
				MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	21	194	13	21	17	.98	2.5	15	.11			
2	26	430	29	22	16	.95	6.2	17	.28			
3	26	470	32	24	15	.98	19	19	.99			
4	17	438	21	9.3	14	.35	11	21	.61			
5	9.1	63	1.6	2.6	14	.10	10	23	.62			
6	10	24	.79	10	14	.41	11	24	.72			
7	9.9	21	.56	14	13	.46	27	25	1.9			
8	10	22	.56	14	13	.46	16	25	1.1			
9	10	22	.57	19	15	.80	11	25	.71			
10	28	22	1.6	39	39	3.9	11	25	.71			
11	41	21	2.2	37	75	7.5	11	24	.73			
12	26	19	1.4	37	70	7.0	21	23	1.2			
13	20	18	.90	38	36	3.5	55	21	3.0			
14	20	17	.88	18	20	.90	24	20	1.3			
15	20	17	.88	9.9	17	.42	9.2	20	.47			
16	20	17	.85	10	14	.34	6.1	20	.31			
17	20	16	.79	10	16	.53	6.2	20	.32			
18	23	28	2.3	5.0	13	.18	6.2	20	.33			
19	13	19	.77	2.8	17	.12	5.9	20	.31			
20	6.9	25	.55	17	22	1.1	6.0	20	.31			
21	4.7	13	.15	23	23	1.4	16	20	.82			
22	6.8	14	.24	49	23	3.0	32	20	1.8			
23	6.3	15	.22	51	23	3.1	39	20	2.1			
24	6.5	17	.30	32	22	1.9	41	20	2.0			
25	6.3	22	.35	8.6	19	.43	39	20	2.1			
26	13	32	1.2	8.7	17	.40	39	331	104			
27	21	34	1.7	12	23	1.2	9.6	90	2.4			
28	23	24	1.4	9.7	15	.36	9.2	87	2.0			
29	23	23	1.3	10	16	.45	9.7	82	2.0			
30	22	21	1.2	6.0	20	.53	9.4	67	1.6			
31	21	19	1.1	---	---	---	9.5	56	1.4			
TOTAL	530.5	---	121.36	569.6	---	43.75	528.7	---	138.25			

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047560 RIO DE BAYAMON BELOW LAGO CIDRA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)		DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)		DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	9.2	46	1.1	8.1	12	.26	7.1	12	.22
2	9.0	49	1.2	8.2	18	.37	7.2	8	.16
3	8.8	63	1.4	6.9	39	.66	7.5	7	.14
4	8.8	70	1.6	5.7	55	.79	7.2	7	.14
5	8.8	60	1.3	9.7	51	1.3	7.1	7	.14
6	8.6	35	.77	16	34	1.4	6.9	8	.14
7	9.3	19	.45	16	19	.75	35	59	5.3
8	8.6	14	.31	15	11	.44	22	40	2.4
9	8.5	12	.26	16	10	.40	7.0	15	.26
10	8.3	11	.23	16	10	.42	8.3	9	.33
11	8.2	10	.22	14	12	.43	35	60	5.6
12	8.1	10	.22	7.7	16	.33	35	60	5.6
13	8.0	10	.21	5.3	19	.26	35	60	5.5
14	8.2	12	.26	5.4	18	.24	35	60	5.6
15	8.0	16	.33	6.4	14	.24	17	39	2.2
16	7.9	20	.41	11	12	.34	9.4	28	.68
17	8.2	28	.59	10	11	.27	9.0	27	.62
18	8.3	38	.81	10	13	.33	8.3	27	.58
19	8.4	43	.92	6.0	14	.23	22	46	3.5
20	8.8	41	.94	4.1	15	.15	35	58	5.1
21	8.5	34	.77	9.6	14	.35	26	52	3.7
22	8.6	22	.51	9.7	13	.31	15	35	1.5
23	8.2	14	.29	9.7	12	.30	20	42	2.8
24	8.1	12	.24	10	10	.26	35	60	5.5
25	8.1	14	.30	10	10	.25	34	60	5.4
26	8.1	18	.37	14	11	.44	24	48	3.0
27	8.2	26	.56	14	14	.53	16	38	1.5
28	8.3	37	.79	7.1	14	.26	16	38	1.6
29	7.9	41	.85	---	---	---	17	38	1.6
30	8.0	33	.70	---	---	---	16	38	1.6
31	8.2	22	.48	---	---	---	16	38	1.6
TOTAL	260.2	---	19.39	281.6	---	12.31	591.0	---	74.01

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047560 RIO DE BAYAMON BELOW LAGO CIDRA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	8.7	26	.75	5.3	22	.48	4.4	20	.24
2	33	59	5.1	4.1	19	.20	4.3	20	.24
3	34	60	5.4	3.6	18	.18	4.3	20	.25
4	31	58	4.9	3.6	17	.16	29	51	6.6
5	23	223	10	3.7	17	.16	14	33	1.2
6	15	31	1.2	5.1	20	.40	13	29	1.1
7	9.3	13	.37	3.4	19	.19	14	25	.93
8	16	33	1.5	3.8	20	.21	8.2	19	.48
9	23	47	2.9	3.8	24	.27	4.0	18	.22
10	11	45	1.5	3.6	27	.28	4.2	18	.22
11	4.4	40	.43	3.6	31	.32	36	19	1.9
12	4.3	36	.38	3.5	32	.32	56	20	3.1
13	6.6	45	1.1	3.6	31	.31	55	24	3.6
14	4.8	56	.76	7.7	31	1.3	19	26	1.3
15	11	149	56	3.7	24	.25	4.0	32	.37
16	3.5	18	.18	3.6	23	.23	4.0	37	.44
17	3.6	16	.15	3.5	22	.22	16	48	2.2
18	3.8	15	.14	3.8	20	.23	49	57	7.6
19	8.6	15	.33	3.6	20	.22	17	67	3.4
20	12	15	.48	3.8	22	.23	4.1	72	.91
21	3.8	17	.17	3.8	24	.26	4.0	52	.62
22	3.6	20	.18	4.0	24	.28	3.8	32	.37
23	3.6	23	.21	4.0	25	.29	3.7	20	.21
24	3.5	26	.23	4.1	25	.30	3.6	18	.21
25	3.5	31	.27	4.3	26	.31	28	25	1.9
26	3.6	35	.31	5.8	27	.40	51	27	3.7
27	13	37	1.3	4.3	25	.32	3.4	27	.23
28	14	35	1.3	4.4	24	.30	3.6	23	.22
29	11	30	1.3	4.3	22	.27	3.3	23	.19
30	3.8	19	.20	4.4	21	.27	3.4	17	.14
31	---	---	---	4.1	20	.25	---	---	---
TOTAL	330.0	---	99.04	127.9	---	9.41	467.3	---	44.09

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047560 RIO DE BAYAMON BELOW LAGO CIDRA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	3.3	17	.14	16	32	1.4	15	45	1.7
2	3.6	18	.15	17	29	1.2	15	45	1.7
3	5.1	19	.26	17	27	1.2	15	43	1.6
4	7.0	20	.35	16	27	1.2	14	41	1.5
5	7.3	20	.35	16	29	1.2	15	42	1.6
6	7.9	19	.38	17	32	1.4	15	46	1.7
7	9.5	17	.42	16	36	1.6	15	48	1.8
8	10	16	.39	16	39	1.7	15	44	1.7
9	9.9	15	.35	17	39	1.7	15	37	1.4
10	8.6	15	.33	16	36	1.6	15	30	1.1
11	632	238	269	17	34	1.5	15	27	1.0
12	143	31	12	16	32	1.4	15	26	1.1
13	24	39	2.5	16	30	1.3	13	26	.86
14	13	48	1.8	16	29	1.2	11	26	.69
15	6.3	57	1.0	16	28	1.2	10	27	.71
16	5.7	61	.84	12	45	1.8	9.9	27	.68
17	7.7	61	1.3	5.5	57	.82	9.9	27	.69
18	17	60	2.6	5.9	65	.99	12	31	1.2
19	17	50	2.2	14	74	2.7	9.4	34	.80
20	17	34	1.5	14	80	3.0	7.7	40	.75
21	17	18	.79	14	82	3.1	5.6	46	.68
22	19	10	.46	15	82	3.1	5.5	53	.77
23	11	10	.30	15	81	3.1	6.1	70	1.2
24	104	473	172	12	73	2.3	5.5	58	.77
25	43	19	2.2	11	58	1.6	5.2	50	.66
26	19	20	1.0	12	46	1.4	5.1	49	.64
27	13	22	.82	14	40	1.4	7.6	48	.93
28	7.9	22	.45	15	37	1.4	11	47	1.3
29	7.5	21	.42	15	35	1.3	11	46	1.2
30	15	37	1.4	15	37	1.4	10	45	1.2
31	15	35	1.5	15	42	1.6	---	---	---
TOTAL	1226.3	---	479.20	449.4	---	51.81	334.5	---	33.63
YEAR	5697.0		1126.25						

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047560 RIO DE BAYAMON BELOW LAGO CIDRA PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
DEC 1992 26...	1330	125	4280	1440	58	66	76
MAY 1993 06...	1750	6.3	1540	26	70	79	--
JUL 11...	1055	297	1920	1540	69	76	80

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
DEC 1992 26...	83	87	98	98	99	100	100
MAY 1993 06...	85	91	98.6	99.2	99.5	99.9	99.9
JUL 11...	87	92	99.6	99.8	99.8	99.8	100

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047560 RIO DE BAYAMON BELOW LAGO CIDRA , PR--Continued
 WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
APR 1993					
08...	1730	32	206	18	99
MAY					
23...	1630	4.3	138	1.6	99
JUL					
11...	1025	135	1340	488	97

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047600 RIO DE BAYAMON NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'39", long 66°08'39", at bridge on Highway 156, and 2.9 mi (4.7 km) west of Aguas Buenas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.5 mi² (47.9 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-65, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION) (MG/L)	OXYGEN (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1992	07...	1210	17	285	7.7	25.0	10	8.2	100	<10	K800	700
DEC	03...	1055	40	281	7.4	23.0	74	5.6	66	28	K1700	3400
FEB 1993	11...	1050	26	283	8.0	23.5	3.4	4.8	57	<10	K160	300
APR	13...	1110	20	218	7.4	23.0	17	7.8	92	17	24000	43000
JUN	01...	1020	18	323	7.7	24.5	4.4	7.4	89	24	380	630
SEP	13...	1330	31	247	7.8	26.5	6.8	8.4	105	<10	590	710

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)	
OCT 1992	07...	100	1	25	9.6	15	0.6	2.7	100	0.8	8.1	16
DEC	03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
FEB 1993	11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
APR	13...	110	0	26	12	15	0.6	2.9	100	<0.5	12	19
JUN	01...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
SEP	13...	99	7	23	10	14	0.6	2.5	130	--	6.6	15

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	
OCT 1992	07...	0.10	25	161	7.41	<1	0.520	<0.010	0.520	0.030	0.27
DEC	03...	--	--	--	--	32	0.290	0.010	0.300	0.020	0.28
FEB 1993	11...	--	--	--	--	4	--	<0.010	0.400	<0.010	0.39
APR	13...	0.10	28	175	9.45	144	--	<0.010	0.200	<0.010	0.49
JUN	01...	--	--	--	--	18	0.590	0.010	0.600	0.020	1.2
SEP	13...	0.10	26	175	14.7	14	0.480	0.020	0.500	0.010	0.29

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047850 RIO BAYAMON NR BAYAMON, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'08", long 66°08'13", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, at rock quarry near Highway 174, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) south of colonia Santa Rosa and 4.7 mi (7.6 km) south of Bayamón.

DRAINAGE AREA.--41.8 mi² (108.3 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1964 to October 1970, June 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 98 ft (30 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Diversion to the Guaynabo water treatment plant, for municipal supply, made upstream from station (at Represa de San Juan). Flow is regulated by storage and release of water at Lago de Cidra (capacity 5,220 acre-ft), 10.5 mi (16.9 km) upstream. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.3	5.1	26	21	15	14	11	109	19	21	15	e9.3
2	6.8	3.9	15	19	15	15	11	274	17	20	14	e9.4
3	6.8	15	13	19	16	15	10	127	17	23	14	e9.2
4	6.4	96	13	19	16	14	11	44	16	23	14	e9.2
5	6.4	28	13	27	16	13	11	52	16	20	14	e9.4
6	7.4	8.1	11	30	15	13	e11	63	15	22	14	e70
7	13	7.5	11	91	15	13	e11	120	15	59	13	e30
8	12	6.0	11	63	15	14	e50	39	28	31	13	e16
9	8.8	6.3	10	23	15	14	e30	143	45	24	16	12
10	14	5.7	10	19	15	13	e21	86	42	24	14	9.6
11	12	5.1	9.9	18	15	13	e100	55	21	e150	13	19
12	6.4	7.0	10	18	15	13	e170	37	18	e60	12	10
13	5.5	25	9.9	18	16	13	153	29	19	e30	12	11
14	5.2	7.3	29	17	16	13	89	302	22	e25	13	9.4
15	5.5	92	25	17	16	13	150	91	18	e25	12	12
16	5.1	20	9.1	17	17	16	71	46	18	e21	197	16
17	5.3	15	10	16	19	15	19	35	16	e19	28	11
18	26	25	9.8	16	17	14	13	32	18	e18	11	81
19	13	37	9.7	16	16	13	11	30	e131	e17	9.6	47
20	6.5	13	8.6	16	18	13	121	28	e118	e16	10	96
21	5.6	11	8.3	16	19	13	88	27	e32	16	9.8	24
22	7.7	50	10	26	16	13	53	27	e24	27	10	11
23	14	55	9.7	41	15	15	19	e151	23	105	16	14
24	13	24	21	17	14	16	15	66	22	314	10	13
25	5.8	15	40	34	14	15	13	46	22	95	9.8	11
26	4.8	11	611	18	14	14	12	e75	21	108	9.3	10
27	4.2	414	119	16	14	13	22	120	21	49	10	63
28	3.9	164	83	16	14	12	56	54	22	e25	10	35
29	3.8	40	169	16	---	11	138	28	28	e18	9.8	22
30	4.6	185	40	17	---	11	97	23	24	15	9.5	16
31	13	---	35	16	---	11	---	e21	---	15	e9.3	---
TOTAL	259.8	1397.0	1410.0	733	438	418	1587	2380	868	1435	572.1	715.5
MEAN	8.38	46.6	45.5	23.6	15.6	13.5	52.9	76.8	28.9	46.3	18.5	23.8
MAX	26	414	611	91	19	16	170	302	131	314	197	96
MIN	3.8	3.9	8.3	16	14	11	10	21	15	15	9.3	9.2
AC-FT	515	2770	2800	1450	869	829	3150	4720	1720	2850	1130	1420
CFSM	.20	1.11	1.09	.57	.37	.32	1.27	1.84	.69	1.11	.44	.57
IN.	.23	1.24	1.25	.65	.39	.37	1.41	2.12	.77	1.28	.51	.64

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1964 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1964	1965	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	35.1	49.9	49.2	38.7	22.9	19.7	24.2	50.7	21.9	23.4	43.8	42.6																		
MAX	129	174	263	159	75.3	52.9	72.7	131	60.8	46.6	137	146																		
(WY)	1991	1970	1966	1969	1989	1990	1971	1966	1970	1970	1970	1989																		
MIN	4.30	7.91	5.19	5.30	4.75	3.58	5.36	6.88	4.26	5.98	15.0	6.02																		
(WY)	1969	1965	1968	1968	1965	1965	1965	1967	1967	1967	1991	1967																		

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1964 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	10137.8		12213.4			
ANNUAL MEAN	27.7		33.5		35.0	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					59.7	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					12.1	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1270		611		5500	
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.8		3.8		2.2	
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	5.5		5.5		2.4	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			3250		28000	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			10.47		20.20	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	20110		24230		25370	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.66		.80		.84	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	9.02		10.87		11.38	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	40		87		62	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	9.7		16		13	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	7.3		9.2		5.0	

e Estimated

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047990 RIO GUAYNABO NEAR BAYAMON, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°22'32", long 66°07'59", at bridge on Highway 833, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from Río de Bayamón, and 2.3 mi (3.7 km) southeast of Bayamón plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--73.2 mi² (189.6 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958, 1964, 1971-73, 1976, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
06...	0820	E10	456	7.0	31.0	2.8	4.0	50	12	3900	K620
DEC											
07...	0900	E10	464	6.5	24.0	9	4.7	55	24	4200	K2000
FEB 1993											
03...	0830	E10	409	7.6	24.5	11	3.6	42	37	460000	27000
APR											
12...	0750	E20	371	7.1	24.0	24	5.2	60	12	49000	48000
MAY											
25...	1205	169	191	6.7	26.0	140	5.9	71	57	60000	22000
SEP											
01...	1225	42	376	7.5	28.0	6.7	9.1	116	<10	60000	310

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
06...	160	3	46	12	27	0.9	3.5	170	0.6	15	35
DEC											
07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
APR											
12...	140	6	38	10	23	0.9	4.0	130	0.8	21	26
MAY											
25...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	72	--	--	--
SEP											
01...	160	0	41	13	23	0.8	2.5	170	--	15	24

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
06...	0.20	28	269	--	<1	0.400	0.020	0.420	0.060	0.34
DEC										
07...	--	--	--	--	7	0.270	0.030	0.30	3.10	0.80
FEB 1993										
03...	--	--	--	--	12	0.930	0.070	1.0	0.010	0.69
APR										
12...	0.10	22	222	--	26	0.460	0.040	0.500	0.010	0.49
MAY										
25...	--	--	--	--	208	0.540	0.060	0.600	0.010	0.69
SEP										
01...	0.20	27	248	28.1	12	0.240	0.060	0.300	0.010	0.39

E = estimate
K = non-ideal count

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50048510 RIO DE BAYAMON AT FLOOD CHANNEL AT BAYAMON, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'29", long 66°09'04", at bridge on Highway 890, 1.0 (1.6 km) downstream from bridge on Highway 2, and 3.2 mi (5.1 km) above mouth.

DRAINAGE AREA.--71.9 mi² (186.2 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

REMARKS.--Prior to 1979 sampling site was 0.8 mile (1.3 km) downstream but was changed because of flood channel construction.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
06...	1045	12	427	7.5	31.0	1.2	7.4	89	21	53000	40
DEC											
07...	1120	37	441	6.6	26.0	22	6.0	73	13	1600	280
FEB 1993											
03...	1010	57	430	7.6	25.0	3.2	5.0	56	19	670000	2400
APR											
12...	1005	104	305	7.1	25.0	120	6.6	90	14	54000	49000
MAY											
26...	1135	104	369	7.0	26.5	18	5.9	79	15	330000	3000
SEP											
01...	1430	40	383	8.0	30.0	3.7	6.9	92	<10	2400	220

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
06...	170	7	45	14	23	0.8	2.5	190	<0.5	17	31
DEC											
07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	170	--	--	--
APR											
12...	110	6	30	9.2	19	0.8	3.3	100	<0.5	16	21
MAY											
26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
SEP											
01...	150	1	39	12	21	0.8	2.4	160	--	15	25

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDEED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
06...	0.20	27	274	8.87	1	--	<0.010	<0.050	<0.010	0.40
DEC										
07...	--	--	--	--	12	0.440	0.160	0.600	1.40	0.70
FEB 1993										
03...	--	--	--	--	5	0.410	0.090	0.500	1.00	1.2
APR										
12...	0.10	20	179	50.1	129	0.340	0.060	0.400	0.010	1.1
MAY										
26...	--	--	--	--	32	0.740	0.060	0.800	0.110	0.30
SEP										
01...	0.20	27	212	22.9	10	0.410	0.090	0.500	0.240	1.1

K = non-ideal count

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SENORIAL, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'51", long 66°03'56", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank, in the Riberas of Señorial Housing area, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) west of Highway 176 and 2.7 mi (4.3 km) southwest of Río Piedras Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--7.49 mi² (19.40 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.--March 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 98.4 ft (30.0 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993 DAILY MEAN VALUES

Table with columns: DAY, OCT, NOV, DEC, JAN, FEB, MAR, APR, MAY, JUN, JUL, AUG, SEP. Rows include daily mean values and summary statistics like TOTAL, MEAN, MAX, MIN, AC-FT, CFSM, IN.

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1988 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

Table with columns: MEAN, MAX, (WY), MIN, (WY). Rows for years 1991, 1992, 1993, 1999, 2000.

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1993 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1988 - 1993

Table with columns: ANNUAL TOTAL, ANNUAL MEAN, HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN, LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN, HIGHEST DAILY MEAN, LOWEST DAILY MEAN, ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM, INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE, ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT), ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM), ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES), 10 PERCENT EXCEEDS, 50 PERCENT EXCEEDS, 90 PERCENT EXCEEDS.

e Estimated

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN
50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SEÑORIAL, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1988 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: April 1988 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USD-77 and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 24,600 mg/L Sep. 18, 1989; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L November 18, 1988.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e114,000 tons (e103,000 tonnes) Sep. 18, 1989; Minimum daily mean, 0.04 ton (0.03 tonne) May 6, 1990.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 6,300 mg/L Mar. 24, 1993; Minimum daily mean, 22 mg/l several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e28,400 tons (e25,000 tonnes) Mar. 24, 1993; Minimum daily mean, 0.18 ton (0.16 tonne) Mar. 15, 1993.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	15	122	5.0	54	926	705	23	232	14
2	14	109	4.0	20	265	63	14	132	4.9
3	14	106	4.0	143	3030	4430	17	198	21
4	17	189	16	292	6300	10300	13	142	12
5	15	137	5.6	40	557	86	8.7	67	1.6
6	13	114	3.7	21	262	22	8.4	66	1.4
7	14	114	4.1	13	143	6.7	7.8	68	1.4
8	95	1860	3110	10	120	3.8	7.7	68	1.4
9	32	405	43	18	293	25	7.7	68	1.4
10	89	1460	1150	14	159	7.7	8.3	68	1.4
11	25	293	24	11	101	3.3	9.1	66	1.7
12	16	143	6.9	14	139	13	9.2	73	1.9
13	13	102	3.6	21	261	28	11	113	8.8
14	14	120	5.1	12	107	3.8	159	3180	7170
15	13	89	3.5	24	350	146	68	998	445
16	21	272	49	11	119	4.0	22	222	13
17	14	104	3.8	59	2220	920	18	170	7.6
18	18	237	29	277	5060	25000	19	206	15
19	11	116	4.0	36	523	66	16	174	8.3
20	13	112	4.0	36	566	275	14	144	5.6
21	13	90	2.9	27	366	88	16	166	8.2
22	23	305	46	67	971	239	21	251	17
23	14	104	3.5	32	394	39	23	281	21
24	26	320	75	29	372	42	68	1130	572
25	14	129	5.1	24	300	28	65	1030	352
26	10	100	3.5	21	263	19	240	4910	5410
27	12	100	3.7	122	2280	1600	62	927	203
28	11	103	3.8	213	4360	10800	88	1510	732
29	10	86	2.7	41	558	81	143	2910	4310
30	41	624	361	91	1580	845	46	621	98
31	29	340	59	---	---	---	24	178	12
TOTAL	679	---	5044.5	1793	---	55889.3	1256.9	---	19472.6

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SEÑORIAL, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	16	124	5.5	7.8	64	1.3	4.3	27	.32
2	18	124	5.7	7.2	57	1.1	5.5	30	.44
3	17	198	9.3	7.2	40	.78	5.1	29	.39
4	16	187	8.4	e6.8	58	e1.1	5.3	28	.37
5	18	210	14	e6.2	56	e.94	5.3	26	.37
6	21	211	18	e6.4	54	e.94	5.1	27	.39
7	111	2070	2430	e6.2	51	e.86	4.5	26	.34
8	24	273	20	e6.0	50	e.82	4.2	25	.30
9	16	145	5.7	e6.0	50	e.82	4.8	23	.29
10	15	188	7.3	e5.6	46	e.70	4.5	23	.27
11	17	188	8.3	e6.6	56	e1.0	4.3	23	.27
12	20	230	19	e7.6	66	e1.4	4.1	22	.25
13	16	159	8.6	e6.0	50	e.82	4.3	22	.28
14	14	120	4.1	e5.0	40	e.54	3.4	23	.20
15	14	114	4.6	e4.8	38	e.50	3.1	22	.18
16	14	114	4.6	e4.6	36	e.44	25	342	128
17	13	108	3.4	7.9	61	2.9	5.3	39	.64
18	13	102	3.7	6.2	35	.56	6.0	24	.37
19	11	102	3.0	5.2	33	.46	5.8	30	.47
20	11	102	3.0	8.0	70	1.9	4.0	28	.29
21	11	96	2.7	6.1	36	.64	3.2	24	.21
22	69	1140	495	5.3	34	.48	4.7	23	.30
23	23	292	26	5.8	33	.50	8.9	92	5.8
24	12	162	6.5	5.6	31	.45	e168	6300	e28400
25	41	679	349	5.8	30	.49	e19	301	e560
26	11	92	2.6	5.9	33	.55	8.4	82	2.0
27	9.8	77	2.1	4.4	34	.40	7.9	41	.84
28	9.6	75	1.9	4.4	34	.40	6.1	38	.65
29	14	122	6.5	---	---	---	6.2	37	.66
30	11	88	2.7	---	---	---	6.3	37	.66
31	8.1	64	1.3	---	---	---	7.5	43	.89
TOTAL	634.5	---	3482.5	170.6	---	23.79	360.1	---	29106.44

e Estimated

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SEÑORIAL, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	7.7	52	1.0	16	185	11	6.5	51	.83
2	7.5	53	1.1	11	102	3.8	7.0	53	.99
3	7.7	52	1.1	71	1240	909	7.1	72	1.4
4	7.1	55	.95	22	257	21	6.1	31	.46
5	7.6	55	1.0	13	120	4.5	6.5	36	.56
6	6.6	54	.94	15	154	9.9	4.9	37	.47
7	8.3	80	2.5	49	796	484	5.7	42	.59
8	30	466	229	24	262	29	28	421	166
9	7.6	64	1.7	17	259	17	43	2110	1640
10	6.5	30	.57	21	332	24	11	94	2.8
11	e78	1780	e3190	16	167	8.0	8.2	68	1.6
12	12	110	3.9	11	79	2.4	7.7	63	1.4
13	57	971	512	9.6	226	6.5	17	200	28
14	24	219	19	20	243	25	20	226	32
15	7.6	51	1.2	9.1	83	2.3	10	107	3.5
16	6.4	36	.69	6.4	47	.80	8.2	64	1.5
17	5.7	26	.39	6.2	45	.79	7.4	61	1.3
18	4.4	23	.25	5.5	48	.74	8.8	95	5.0
19	4.4	22	.25	5.4	48	.74	177	2820	2180
20	34	512	170	6.1	44	.72	62	590	155
21	e90	2100	e3640	8.8	97	6.9	14	142	6.2
22	17	210	13	7.1	70	1.6	10	82	2.1
23	6.1	55	1.0	43	730	483	8.6	72	1.6
24	4.7	34	.41	36	526	134	8.4	74	1.7
25	6.5	65	4.8	14	146	6.6	6.0	59	1.2
26	4.8	29	.38	23	293	46	6.2	44	.72
27	4.4	23	.26	74	1280	598	7.0	44	.75
28	27	401	146	57	970	499	7.2	46	.88
29	e162	3590	e9970	18	191	11	24	373	114
30	e65	1020	e363	11	116	4.3	14	152	6.5
31	---	---	---	7.2	60	1.2	---	---	---
TOTAL	717.6	---	18276.39	653.4	---	3352.79	557.5	---	4359.05

e Estimated

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SEÑORIAL, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE	CONCEN-	DISCHARGE	DISCHARGE	CONCEN-	DISCHARGE	DISCHARGE	CONCEN-	DISCHARGE
	(CFS)	TRATION	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	TRATION	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	TRATION	(TONS/DAY)
		(MG/L)			(MG/L)			(MG/L)	
	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	7.3	66	1.3	6.3	36	.58	8.0	66	1.4
2	31	453	123	6.3	64	1.3	13	143	12
3	22	276	36	6.1	40	.72	7.6	66	1.4
4	10	106	3.5	5.4	42	.59	6.4	56	1.0
5	8.7	88	2.5	5.8	42	.59	23	323	85
6	7.8	58	1.0	6.5	69	1.5	e83	673	e819
7	129	2560	5760	5.9	54	1.0	12	123	5.4
8	20	217	13	5.7	46	.70	8.8	92	3.7
9	13	151	6.3	6.7	66	1.6	6.2	56	1.0
10	11	124	4.6	5.3	58	.95	41	702	518
11	359	7590	16900	5.6	37	.58	7.6	65	1.5
12	42	529	83	4.8	36	.43	5.7	48	.72
13	18	218	11	4.4	34	.40	21	329	85
14	12	133	5.1	6.2	66	1.6	6.8	46	.84
15	11	116	4.1	6.1	55	1.0	6.9	59	1.2
16	10	112	3.6	15	183	15	6.0	54	1.0
17	6.2	53	.92	6.3	51	.85	51	969	948
18	5.1	42	.59	5.5	44	.64	27	354	77
19	8.1	77	2.9	5.2	41	.55	9.4	87	3.1
20	5.4	41	.55	4.8	39	.50	5.7	37	.61
21	5.2	43	.75	6.7	69	1.2	16	193	47
22	85	1660	1950	6.0	42	.59	7.0	54	.94
23	110	1810	1090	5.3	42	.59	14	173	24
24	55	833	270	4.9	37	.46	6.5	77	1.5
25	13	133	6.1	4.9	39	.50	6.0	41	.62
26	133	2570	2960	4.5	37	.47	4.9	46	.73
27	19	206	16	4.6	36	.43	5.6	34	.46
28	6.6	53	.95	5.0	49	.90	32	482	143
29	5.2	40	.54	e120	1610	e2470	6.6	60	1.3
30	5.1	39	.50	14	146	6.6	19	273	68
31	5.6	39	.62	14	170	22	---	---	---
TOTAL	1179.3	---	29258.42	313.8	---	2534.82	473.7	---	2854.42
YEAR	8789.4		173655.02						

e Estimated

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN
50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SENORIAL, PR--Continued
WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
APR 1993							
20...	1345	833	3480	8640	38	45	58
JUN							
19...	0958	366	26200	25800	27	38	44

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
APR 1993							
20...	73	--	96	98	99.3	99.9	100
JUN							
19...	58	71	84	91	96	99	100

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SEÑORIAL, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDEDED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
MAY 1993					
10...	1130	12	149	4.8	99
JUN					
19...	0858	188	7240	3670	69
19...	2120	205	4810	2660	981

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048800 RIO PIEDRAS NEAR RIO PIEDRAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°22'15", long 66°03'40", at bridge on Winston Churchill Avenue in the El Señorial Housing area, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) west of Highway 176, and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) southwest of Río Piedras plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.17 mi² (20.9 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1972 to current year.

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1992	01...	0915	8.0	376	7.8	25.5	26	7.3	88	<10	230000	K12700
DEC 1992	15...	0930	21	275	7.2	24.0	2.7	6.3	79	<10	K8000	13000
FEB 1993	11...	0900	5.7	460	7.8	21.6	94	7.3	87	<10	600000	7400
APR 1993	07...	1335	4.7	410	7.8	30.5	1.8	10.9	143	<10	K10000	K1200
JUN 1993	01...	1145	6.1	440	7.9	31.0	5.1	7.8	100	21	300000	120000
AUG 1993	04...	1350	6.3	414	7.7	31.0	0.80	9.0	120	12	14000	3600

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)	
OCT 1992	01...	130	0	38	9.6	20	0.8	3.1	115	<0.5	28	28
DEC 1992	15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
FEB 1993	11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
APR 1993	07...	160	4	42	13	29	1	2.9	160	<0.5	16	33
JUN 1993	01...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
AUG 1993	04...	160	7	41	13	29	1	2.6	100	--	21	29

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	
OCT 1992	01...	0.20	24	220	4.72	7	0.680	0.040	0.720	0.220	0.38
DEC 1992	15...	--	--	--	--	1	0.780	0.020	0.800	0.030	0.17
FEB 1993	11...	--	--	--	--	--	0.600	0.090	0.690	0.300	0.50
APR 1993	07...	0.20	31	263	3.32	9	0.790	0.060	0.850	0.180	0.42
JUN 1993	01...	--	--	--	--	38	0.680	0.070	0.750	0.590	0.41
AUG 1993	04...	0.20	32	228	3.87	2	0.570	0.070	0.640	0.290	0.51

K = non-ideal count

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048800 RIO PIEDRAS NEAR RIO PIEDRAS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1992										
01...	0.60	1.3	5.8	0.170	<1	200	40	<1	<1	<10
DEC										
15...	0.40	4.1	18	0.810	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993										
11...	0.80	1.5	6.6	0.290	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR										
07...	0.60	1.5	6.4	0.320	2	200	50	<1	<1	<10
JUN										
01...	1.0	1.7	7.7	0.280	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG										
04...	0.80	1.4	6.4	0.260	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1992										
01...	1400	<1	150	<0.10	<1	<1	20	<0.010	<1	0.05
DEC										
15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993										
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR										
07...	150	<1	110	<0.10	<1	<1	10	<0.010	<1	0.19
JUN										
01...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG										
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993										
08...	1115	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.06	<0.010	<0.010

DATE	ENDRIN WATER UNFLTRD REC (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993									
08...	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993									
08...	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01	0.04	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50049000 RIO PIEDRAS AT RIO PIEDRAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'48", long 66°03'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, at bridge on Highway 1, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) southwest of the plaza in Rio Piedras, and 0.4 mi (0.6 km) downstream from diversion for water supply.

DRAINAGE AREA.--12.5 mi² (32.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1958 (maximum discharge measurement only), 1959-64 (annual low-flow measurements only), July 1971 to September 1982, October 1987 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 50 ft (15 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair. Low flow affected by diversions for water supply. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	8.2	41	27	26	12	12	12	14	8.3	7.6	11	7.2
2	9.9	19	19	32	13	11	12	12	8.7	23	11	8.9
3	8.2	187	24	32	16	11	13	46	9.1	23	11	8.6
4	15	866	27	30	12	12	12	15	8.7	9.4	10	8.5
5	7.0	58	16	41	12	12	12	11	9.1	9.5	9.8	18
6	5.8	40	15	44	11	13	11	14	8.5	9.9	9.9	184
7	6.7	30	13	140	12	12	16	71	8.4	158	9.8	16
8	68	28	12	35	13	11	47	21	22	17	9.7	14
9	14	35	10	28	12	11	14	18	37	12	10	9.2
10	47	29	10	28	13	12	12	18	19	12	9.3	42
11	12	21	10	29	11	11	95	13	12	474	9.3	11
12	8.1	49	10	38	15	11	17	11	12	37	9.4	9.6
13	6.8	39	12	30	8.8	11	44	10	31	18	8.9	21
14	13	21	423	32	8.2	10	36	19	19	17	10	11
15	8.1	40	139	18	10	9.9	14	11	38	21	11	11
16	35	20	23	15	11	47	12	9.3	11	15	17	11
17	9.4	75	21	15	21	14	20	9.2	10	13	8.5	61
18	26	443	22	16	11	12	11	8.6	10	12	8.4	21
19	7.0	70	21	16	12	12	10	8.6	206	14	8.3	21
20	8.6	139	16	15	22	11	41	9.1	53	11	8.1	9.5
21	8.5	60	19	17	13	11	132	10	14	11	8.7	20
22	18	137	26	93	11	13	18	9.3	14	123	9.0	10
23	32	53	27	22	12	20	10	87	11	126	8.1	17
24	22	47	106	18	11	226	9.3	41	13	54	7.9	11
25	11	39	61	35	13	25	9.8	18	10	15	7.9	9.0
26	8.3	33	313	17	12	14	9.6	28	9.6	118	7.6	9.8
27	26	167	70	17	11	14	8.9	146	9.8	24	8.1	13
28	8.1	369	104	15	11	13	35	40	9.7	12	8.5	21
29	8.1	90	169	17	---	13	361	13	20	11	65	9.7
30	115	86	51	13	---	13	105	10	9.5	12	12	15
31	20	---	30	12	---	13	---	8.6	---	11	9.5	---
TOTAL	600.8	3331	1846	936	350.0	640.9	1159.6	759.7	661.4	1430.4	352.7	639.0
MEAN	19.4	111	59.5	30.2	12.5	20.7	38.7	24.5	22.0	46.1	11.4	21.3
MAX	115	866	423	140	22	226	361	146	206	474	65	184
MIN	5.8	19	10	12	8.2	9.9	8.9	8.6	8.3	7.6	7.6	7.2
AC-FT	1190	6610	3660	1860	694	1270	2300	1510	1310	2840	700	1270
CFSM	1.55	8.88	4.76	2.42	1.00	1.65	3.09	1.96	1.76	3.69	.91	1.70
IN.	1.79	9.91	5.49	2.79	1.04	1.91	3.45	2.26	1.97	4.26	1.05	1.90

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1971 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	48.2	39.9	36.6	18.2	19.8	16.4	24.7	32.1	19.1	22.1	36.8	37.1											
MAX	122	133	133	34.7	98.9	42.5	64.0	121	59.7	55.6	120	112											
(WY)	1977	1978	1976	1992	1979	1972	1978	1979	1989	1989	1979	1989											
MIN	10.5	8.16	9.88	4.03	4.40	2.67	4.49	3.46	3.25	3.35	4.30	10.1											
(WY)	1992	1974	1977	1973	1977	1976	1974	1975	1974	1976	1976	1973											

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1971 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	14166.0	12707.5	
ANNUAL MEAN	38.7	34.8	29.5
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			54.2
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			11.9
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	866	866	2030
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	4.8	5.8	.26
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	6.1	8.2	.83
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		5960	10000
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		13.02	21.02
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	28100	25210	21350
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.10	2.79	2.36
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	42.16	37.82	32.03
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	97	69	53
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	12	13	12
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	6.9	8.7	3.4

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN
50049000 RIO PIEDRAS AT RIO PIEDRAS, PR--Continued
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1988 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1988 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USD-77 and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 13,000 mg/L Sep. 18, 1989; Minimum daily mean, 4 mg/L June 4, 1990.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 165,000 tons (150,200 tonnes) Sep. 18, 1989; Minimum daily mean, 0.09 ton (0.08 tonne) Sep. 24, 1991.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 4,460 mg/L Nov. 04, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 9 mg/L Aug. 23, 1993.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 21,200 tons (19,200 tonnes) Nov. 04, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 0.18 tons (0.16 tonnes) Aug. 23, 1993.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	20	87	13	17	53	2.4	12	35	1.6
2	12	39	1.6	69	438	306	13	24	.90
3	9.9	38	1.1	18	64	6.1	37	187	43
4	9.7	22	.64	14	53	2.7	14	33	1.5
5	12	39	2.1	9.0	25	.66	14	22	.73
6	7.0	14	.25	9.3	19	.49	12	23	.75
7	6.5	14	.25	30	166	66	8.9	22	.52
8	8.8	22	.98	41	205	48	15	42	2.2
9	5.9	14	.22	11	23	.71	14	38	1.9
10	5.4	13	.21	9.6	15	.38	8.8	24	.64
11	5.4	11	.16	7.4	14	.29	9.1	19	.43
12	5.5	12	.17	7.2	15	.28	16	59	7.4
13	5.7	10	.15	9.5	25	.72	8.9	24	.73
14	4.8	11	.14	6.9	17	.31	14	46	3.1
15	7.3	24	1.0	7.8	16	.32	7.6	17	.34
16	5.8	11	.16	17	58	6.0	20	93	28
17	4.9	10	.13	9.5	17	.47	7.3	17	.35
18	66	459	784	9.1	16	.40	7.8	15	.29
19	13	48	3.5	8.1	17	.35	7.1	15	.26
20	7.9	18	.37	8.3	19	.42	29	143	32
21	6.9	15	.28	201	821	2280	13	47	2.0
22	6.5	16	.33	76	535	425	13	51	2.3
23	8.7	19	.43	32	147	38	13	39	1.7
24	6.9	14	.28	43	232	78	9.1	16	.41
25	6.2	12	.19	9.9	26	.75	8.6	16	.40
26	9.4	28	1.6	12	34	1.9	9.6	17	.46
27	6.5	13	.20	15	58	6.0	13	40	2.4
28	6.2	13	.20	8.7	21	.50	9.6	21	.51
29	6.2	13	.20	8.9	20	.44	9.7	22	.58
30	26	127	30	9.9	20	.50	23	95	21
31	12	44	1.4	---	---	---	11	34	1.9
TOTAL	325.0	---	845.24	735.1	---	3274.09	408.1	---	160.30

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50049000 RIO PIEDRAS AT RIO PIEDRAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	9.7	81	3.5	8.8	16	.42	5.8	35	.54
2	7.7	18	.38	13	35	4.2	6.6	40	.66
3	7.5	27	.58	12	38	2.7	6.2	33	.55
4	6.3	11	.20	9.2	17	.47	11	38	3.0
5	455	2080	7290	8.6	16	.40	7.3	14	.27
6	168	1260	1460	8.1	16	.34	7.4	11	.25
7	14	41	1.6	8.6	16	.38	7.9	13	.29
8	9.6	25	.65	8.9	16	.40	7.4	13	.25
9	26	138	37	8.6	16	.37	6.8	13	.22
10	119	862	679	8.6	16	.34	7.9	13	.28
11	13	41	1.6	8.7	16	.37	8.5	14	.33
12	13	43	2.0	8.8	16	.38	7.6	14	.26
13	17	64	4.7	8.9	16	.37	9.0	15	.37
14	11	24	.63	8.9	16	.37	12	21	.69
15	10	23	.56	8.8	15	.39	8.3	27	.63
16	45	241	178	7.8	15	.33	8.7	36	.89
17	13	53	2.2	8.7	13	.32	15	37	1.6
18	11	44	1.3	7.5	13	.28	11	26	.78
19	8.4	41	.90	9.2	16	.39	10	20	.46
20	9.9	40	.97	6.5	15	.28	9.1	16	.40
21	8.3	40	.83	6.3	13	.20	9.8	17	.44
22	7.8	38	.73	20	88	14	7.2	17	.33
23	7.6	29	.55	7.3	13	.27	10	29	.96
24	8.2	21	.42	7.5	13	.27	7.8	14	.28
25	13	35	1.4	7.2	13	.27	7.9	15	.34
26	10	19	.51	7.4	13	.28	8.5	15	.36
27	9.2	19	.46	7.8	13	.28	8.2	15	.36
28	12	19	.65	7.0	15	.28	132	982	2540
29	8.8	17	.36	7.0	23	.44	13	47	2.2
30	8.6	16	.38	---	---	---	8.0	34	.75
31	8.7	16	.40	---	---	---	9.1	27	.75
TOTAL	1076.3	---	9672.46	255.7	---	29.79	395.0	---	2559.49

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50049000 RIO PIEDRAS AT RIO PIEDRAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	9.5	20	.53	202	1030	2500	95	591	1140
2	8.9	20	.48	149	1000	1370	23	92	7.6
3	9.2	20	.53	11	33	1.2	15	34	1.2
4	10	20	.55	6.9	11	.21	14	32	1.2
5	9.6	18	.45	5.7	10	.15	13	31	.95
6	10	17	.41	76	604	1020	23	97	18
7	12	19	.63	12	35	1.2	189	1200	2680
8	19	67	9.0	8.8	23	.59	114	815	652
9	15	51	4.1	14	49	8.4	30	120	12
10	21	86	11	17	57	4.7	19	69	5.1
11	13	41	2.0	14	38	1.8	12	31	.97
12	11	35	1.5	8.6	19	.43	15	46	2.9
13	6.8	14	.24	7.9	16	.32	11	28	.81
14	6.9	11	.21	7.8	15	.30	18	72	11
15	6.0	11	.16	8.3	15	.34	12	40	1.9
16	6.7	12	.22	122	789	1570	9.2	20	.45
17	7.2	13	.27	19	64	3.7	7.8	15	.27
18	13	47	4.5	87	553	850	6.9	13	.22
19	73	512	721	59	373	223	7.6	16	.32
20	13	45	3.7	24	86	7.9	8.1	19	.42
21	9.4	29	1.7	46	314	267	14	39	1.9
22	5.7	10	.14	15	48	2.1	9.9	19	.49
23	6.6	10	.18	167	1290	1800	9.7	19	.48
24	7.5	10	.21	127	922	980	8.8	17	.40
25	8.4	10	.23	31	148	18	8.2	14	.31
26	8.7	10	.24	354	2050	6250	7.9	13	.29
27	8.8	10	.26	54	287	62	7.8	16	.32
28	9.7	13	.34	31	141	18	7.2	19	.37
29	561	2210	15100	58	365	254	6.9	19	.34
30	121	854	1190	74	457	170	7.3	19	.38
31	---	---	---	29	127	17	---	---	---
TOTAL	1027.6	---	17054.78	1846.0	---	17402.34	730.3	---	4542.59

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50049000 RIO PIEDRAS AT RIO PIEDRAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	7.7	19	.38	33	137	26	9.6	65	2.7
2	7.6	19	.37	40	223	86	6.6	28	.48
3	8.3	14	.31	18	60	3.6	6.3	17	.28
4	14	49	6.4	20	78	8.2	6.3	13	.21
5	9.0	18	.45	155	1260	2910	8.2	18	.50
6	8.9	16	.39	16	127	6.4	59	399	584
7	8.1	16	.32	20	119	19	7.8	19	.43
8	41	207	45	8.3	21	.54	5.7	12	.17
9	56	324	119	222	1460	4610	5.5	11	.16
10	13	37	1.2	154	937	2090	5.4	12	.17
11	28	111	13	20	85	5.8	8.1	26	.82
12	12	33	1.1	15	46	2.4	5.6	11	.17
13	33	248	78	20	104	7.7	6.5	11	.20
14	43	389	137	274	1050	3790	6.2	11	.17
15	29	137	31	34	153	20	6.3	11	.16
16	17	61	5.0	19	64	4.9	5.8	10	.16
17	51	265	62	12	31	.99	17	64	6.6
18	13	35	1.2	9.7	26	.70	6.6	18	.38
19	11	26	.72	8.5	21	.48	18	104	54
20	105	581	690	10	16	.40	62	957	1410
21	21	71	4.4	324	1580	8860	16	65	10
22	18	66	4.3	30	120	13	6.7	15	.48
23	11	30	.99	38	219	80	99	393	918
24	76	528	310	10	30	.94	8.7	21	.52
25	18	63	4.3	8.5	19	.41	6.3	11	.17
26	13	57	3.1	8.3	17	.35	5.8	10	.15
27	123	614	1240	7.1	23	.42	5.0	10	.15
28	25	135	13	6.3	20	.30	4.8	10	.13
29	12	28	1.0	6.5	11	.19	5.4	10	.14
30	9.3	21	.51	20	102	47	85	244	379
31	124	810	1520	28	127	24	---	---	---
TOTAL	965.9	---	4294.44	1595.2	---	22619.72	505.2	---	3370.50
YEAR	9865.4		85825.74						

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50049000 RIO PIEDRAS AT RIO PIEDRAS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEDED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
NOV 1992							
18...	1345	2450	16000	106000	30	43	48
30...	1405	1190	3520	11300	37	43	48
DEC							
14...	2138	2890	9510	74000	34	45	50
26...	0050	602	5520	8980	40	48	57
APR 1993							
29...	1937	3240	5080	44500	32	37	41

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
NOV 1992							
18...	59	70	83	92	98	99	100
30...	56	67	77	90	98	99	100
DEC							
14...	63	74	84	92	98	99.7	100
25...	66	79	89	95	99	99.8	100
APR 1993							
29...	46	57	71	84	94	99	100

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50049000 RIO PIEDRAS AT RIO PIEDRAS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDEED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
NOV 1992					
18...	1445	3920	5270	55780	74
18...	1715	438	1500	1770	91
20...	1320	622	1480	2480	74
DEC					
14...	2008	1420	3220	12340	60
15...	0008	1130	2860	8720	71
24...	0930	291	2460	1930	95
24...	1245	291	810	636	99
25...	2350	296	1610	1290	89
26...	0505	304	2010	1650	91
APR 1993					
29...	1852	515	4650	6460	57
30...	0037	573	2580	3990	81

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50049100 RIO PIEDRAS AT HATO REY, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'34", long 66°04'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at bridge on Avenida Pifeiro at Expreso Las Américas, and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) southwest of Hato Rey.

DRAINAGE AREA.--15.4 mi² (39.9 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1970 to December 1987 (discharge measurements only), 1972 to December 1982 (maximum discharge only), January 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 16 ft (5 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Mean daily discharge affected by sewage discharges (approximately 2.0 ft³/s (0.06 m³/s)), 20 ft (6 m) upstream from gaging station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	18	83	100	84	47	23	e27	93	16	12	21	16
2	16	42	85	81	45	21	e30	82	15	66	20	18
3	16	343	e87	100	61	20	e29	164	15	58	21	16
4	44	1680	e117	83	40	20	e29	81	14	16	18	15
5	17	153	82	122	39	21	e27	62	15	14	16	31
6	19	150	78	126	34	21	e35	78	14	14	16	338
7	21	110	67	322	33	20	e60	229	14	264	15	61
8	101	102	70	113	30	18	e110	107	40	49	15	42
9	36	114	70	91	29	19	e35	94	62	26	15	25
10	85	93	71	91	29	29	e30	93	26	24	15	107
11	29	76	73	88	25	20	e250	75	13	862	15	19
12	17	175	73	107	37	23	e40	59	18	106	13	15
13	15	130	78	83	25	41	e110	52	82	43	12	41
14	26	85	e902	93	21	28	e90	78	31	39	13	15
15	16	123	286	79	21	24	e35	45	82	56	18	20
16	65	93	109	77	20	107	e30	36	24	24	40	16
17	22	199	104	73	55	44	e50	34	17	19	13	124
18	51	699	108	71	23	34	e27	29	20	17	12	30
19	19	154	117	71	22	33	e25	26	459	24	12	43
20	20	e328	99	69	60	32	e100	29	136	16	12	13
21	20	119	102	69	27	30	e300	32	28	31	16	43
22	38	e255	121	255	22	31	e26	24	28	267	17	13
23	85	109	123	102	23	48	19	201	19	362	14	41
24	65	e102	259	79	22	379	30	133	26	177	13	13
25	28	94	201	119	24	76	35	100	16	29	14	11
26	31	82	565	68	21	48	29	72	16	255	12	15
27	102	e308	204	60	21	44	39	393	16	72	13	27
28	30	e605	273	57	19	38	120	117	16	23	16	47
29	31	e231	323	74	---	37	685	35	51	18	111	14
30	185	e202	181	61	---	34	401	23	16	18	47	26
31	50	---	95	50	---	31	---	17	---	19	22	---
TOTAL	1318	7039	5223	3018	875	1394	2853	2693	1345	3020	627	1255
MEAN	42.5	235	168	97.4	31.2	45.0	95.1	86.9	44.8	97.4	20.2	41.8
MAX	185	1680	902	322	61	379	685	393	459	862	111	338
MIN	15	42	67	50	19	18	19	17	13	12	12	11
AC-FT	2610	13960	10360	5990	1740	2760	5660	5340	2670	5990	1240	2490
CFSM	2.80	15.4	11.1	6.40	2.06	2.96	6.26	5.72	2.95	6.41	1.33	2.75
IN.	3.23	17.23	12.78	7.39	2.14	3.41	6.98	6.59	3.29	7.39	1.53	3.07

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1988 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	63.7	82.3	61.1	51.5	39.0	35.4
MAX	134	235	168	97.4	80.2	53.8
(WY)	1991	1993	1993	1993	1991	1990
MIN	16.6	23.9	18.8	29.9	10.8	22.2
(WY)	1992	1991	1992	1989	1992	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1988 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	27647.4	30660	
ANNUAL MEAN	75.5	84.0	54.2
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			84.0
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			41.4
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1680	Nov 4	1680
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	6.9	Mar 1	11
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	7.8	Feb 26	14
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			6920
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			18.89
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	54840	60810	39270
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	4.97	5.53	3.57
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	67.66	75.04	48.46
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	196	183	120
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	25	39	23
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	9.9	15	12

e Estimated

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN
 50049100 RIO PIEDRAS AT HATO REY, PR
 WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'34", long 66°04'10", at bridge on Avenida Piñero at Expreso Las Americas, and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) southwest of Hato Rey.

DRAINAGE AREA.--15.4 mi² (39.9 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1971 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992	01...	1235	18	400	7.8	29.5	4.2	5.6	73	17	K700000 45000
DEC	15...	1210	78	410	6.9	25.0	11	6.2	81	20	K600000 K600000
FEB 1993	16...	1220	23	735	7.6	26.0	29	6.0	78	180	600000 K100000
APR	22...	1150	29	415	7.0	28.0	12	4.0	52	30	560000 52000
JUN	01...	1545	16	500	7.1	32.5	3.2	8.4	110	38	K80000 3700
AUG	04...	1125	22	460	7.8	26.5	0.20	11.0	145	17	K200000 K12000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)	
OCT 1992	01...	140	0	42	9.0	22	0.8	3.9	140	<0.5	25	27
DEC	15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--	
FEB 1993	16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	200	--	--	--	
APR	22...	130	1	35	9.4	21	0.8	3.5	120	<0.5	25	26
JUN	01...	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--	
AUG	04...	170	0	47	12	29	1	3.4	150	--	23	29

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	
OCT 1992	01...	0.20	22	235	11.4	<1	0.700	0.070	0.770	1.30	1.1
DEC	15...	--	--	--	--	9	0.800	0.100	0.900	0.590	1.3
FEB 1993	16...	--	--	--	--	65	0.790	0.010	0.800	0.020	0.48
APR	22...	0.20	23	215	16.8	1	1.21	0.090	1.22	1.10	1.1
JUN	01...	--	--	--	--	34	0.590	0.010	0.600	1.10	1.5
AUG	04...	0.20	27	268	15.9	2	0.520	0.080	0.600	1.50	1.4

K = non-ideal count

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50049820 LAGUNA SAN JOSE NO. 2 AT SAN JUAN, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'46", long 66°02'10", 0.2 mi (0.3 km) east of Ca-o de Martin Pe-a, and 650 ft (200 m) south of Isla Guachinango.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND- ARD UNITS)	PH TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TRANS- PAR- ENCY (SECCHI DISK (IN)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	DIS- SOLVED FECAL, (PER- CENT SATUR- ATION)	OXYGEN, FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	COLI- STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
NOV 1992									
05...	0800	13200	7.6	26.0	18	4.8	58	4700	K6000
JAN 1993									
05...	0820	32000	7.5	28.5	19.9	3.7	48	32000	7100
MAR									
08...	1000	21000	7.2	25.2	36	5.0	59	3900	K200
MAY									
04...	0930	12800	7.5	27.5	28	4.7	58	K12000	K730
JUN									
21...	1025	14000	7.7	27.6	26	6.1	76	K10000	--
AUG									
24...	1045	22500	7.1	30.5	37	2.0	24	K18000	K90000

DATE	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN,AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	PHOS- PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	CARBON, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS C)
NOV 1992										
05...	6	0.090	0.010	0.100	0.220	2.2	2.4	2.5	0.57	16
JAN 1993										
05...	28	--	<0.010	0.100	0.120	2.4	2.5	2.6	0.53	18
MAR										
08...	<1	--	<0.010	0.100	1.20	2.5	3.7	3.8	0.70	13
MAY										
04...	13	--	<0.010	0.100	0.050	2.4	2.4	2.5	0.31	11
JUN										
21...	15	0.070	0.030	0.100	0.110	1.8	1.7	1.8	0.26	13
AUG										
24...	4	--	<0.010	0.100	0.050	1.7	1.8	1.9	0.40	16

K = non-ideal count

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50049920 BAHIA DE SAN JUAN NO. 5 AT SAN JUAN, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION--Lat 18°26'37", long 66°05'11", 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west of Puente de la Constituci[n, and 0.5 mi (0.8 km) south from U.S. Naval Reservation.

DRAINAGE--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD--Water years 1974 to present.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TRANSPAR-ENCY (SECCHI DISK) (IN)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATURATION)	COLIFORMS, (PER-UM-MF) (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, (COLS. PER 100 ML)	ALKALINITY TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3)
NOV 1992										
05...	0915	11700	7.1	26.0	7	1.5	18	K6000	K6000	140
JAN 1993										
05...	0930	43000	7.3	24.6	14	1.8	21	320000	230000	150
MAR										
08...	1055	42100	7.6	26.0	30	4.0	48	360000	30000	120
MAY										
04...	1030	25400	7.2	28.0	7	1.4	18	46000	35000	130
JUN										
21...	1110	30000	6.9	28.4	24	0.2	2	160000	180000	120
AUG										
24...	1150	>50000	7.9	29.4	16	1.6	20	58000	K120000	120

DATE	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	CARBON, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS C)
NOV 1992											
05...	5	0.060	0.040	0.100	0.900	1.0	0.90	2.0	1.9	0.280	4.8
JAN 1993											
05...	12	0.090	0.010	0.100	0.640	0.06	0.70	0.80	--	0.080	2.4
MAR											
08...	15	0.090	0.010	0.100	1.20	2.0	3.2	3.3	--	0.300	5.2
MAY											
04...	70	0.070	0.030	0.100	1.70	1.5	3.2	3.4	--	0.310	3.1
JUN											
21...	17	0.230	0.070	0.300	2.20	0.60	2.8	3.1	14	0.410	2.0
AUG											
24...	19	0.160	0.040	0.200	0.78	0.32	1.1	1.3	5.8	0.140	4.7

K = non-ideal count

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Figure 20.--Río Grande de Loíza basin.

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50050300 QUEBRADA BLASINA NEAR CAROLINA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'27", long 65°58'28", at bridge on Highway 3, 1.4 mi (2.3 km) south of Valle Arriba Heights housing area, and 1.2 mi (1.9 km) west-southwest of Carolina plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--2.96 mi² (7.67 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1973 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
21...	1205	8.4	404	7.5	28.0	8.2	5.3	66	<10	K100000	K24000
DEC 16...	0900	6.3	418	7.5	23.9	32	6.5	87	<10	380000	53000
FEB 1993											
16...	0915	7.9	494	7.2	23.5	220	4.4	58	170	600000	250000
APR 15...	1410	4.7	558	7.3	28.5	3.3	3.2	41	20	K19000	24000
JUN 08...	1200	8.4	557	7.6	27.0	780	5.2	68	300	530000	950000
AUG 09...	1350	5.8	441	7.3	29.0	54	5.9	79	24	20000	K2900

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
21...	170	13	50	8.7	32	2	4.9	160	<0.5	26	30
DEC 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--
APR 15...	180	6	54	11	33	1	3.1	170	<0.5	23	40
JUN 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
AUG 09...	160	11	49	8.0	29	0.8	4.5	130	--	34	33

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
21...	0.40	21	398	9.02	<10	0.760	0.120	0.880	0.430	1.3
DEC 16...	--	--	--	--	41	0.330	0.070	0.400	0.140	0.36
FEB 1993										
16...	--	--	--	--	592	0.370	0.030	0.400	0.070	0.33
APR 15...	0.20	25	291	3.70	32	0.450	0.050	0.500	0.140	0.46
JUN 08...	--	--	--	--	6010	0.600	0.100	0.700	0.410	0.59
AUG 09...	0.10	22	253	3.96	46	0.260	0.040	0.300	0.130	0.37

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50050900 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT QUEBRADA ARENAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°07'10", long 65°59'22", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at intersection of Highways 181 and 9990, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from confluence with Rio Emajagua and about 7.1 mi (11.4 km) southwest of San Lorenzo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--6.00 mi² (15.54 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1977 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 640 ft (195 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e10	e12	e37	e40	e15	e9.4	6.4	202	12	15	30	23
2	e9.2	e9.7	e22	e25	e18	e8.4	6.2	178	11	16	27	28
3	e9.0	e10	e90	e22	e15	e7.9	6.0	49	9.8	32	24	28
4	e8.4	e61	e30	e21	e13	e7.5	5.8	24	9.1	17	22	18
5	e10	e19	e21	e17	e13	e7.5	5.8	60	8.7	13	21	17
6	e14	e58	e22	e24	e13	e7.4	5.7	27	8.3	11	20	15
7	e9.0	e33	e19	e27	e12	e7.5	5.2	15	8.0	32	19	15
8	e8.8	e16	e18	e23	e12	e7.2	6.4	17	8.7	25	19	25
9	e8.5	e12	e17	e21	e11	e7.2	8.3	107	8.0	14	18	24
10	e8.3	e11	e16	e20	e12	e7.0	6.4	32	19	12	20	63
11	e8.9	e9.9	e15	e18	e14	e7.0	5.2	18	11	e946	37	26
12	e8.4	e9.6	e15	e18	e17	e7.4	5.1	14	9.0	e120	20	18
13	e7.6	e9.2	e16	e17	e14	e7.8	13	12	15	62	18	17
14	e7.8	e8.5	e17	e18	e12	e7.6	10	299	98	50	17	15
15	e7.4	e13	e18	e16	e11	e7.8	6.3	40	137	43	22	14
16	e7.5	e10	e15	e15	e11	e7.2	19	24	40	192	302	48
17	e8.1	e25	e15	e15	e11	e8.2	30	19	18	47	54	18
18	e9.4	e81	e14	e14	e10	e8.6	7.1	17	248	38	30	57
19	e7.6	e44	e14	e16	e11	e10	6.6	15	498	46	25	17
20	e26	e42	e14	e13	e11	e9.4	18	15	155	59	22	40
21	e23	e17	e15	e13	e10	e8.0	9.1	14	41	53	20	16
22	e17	e32	e16	e23	e10	e7.0	6.5	14	205	235	70	18
23	e11	e17	e14	e15	e10	e6.8	33	14	46	215	139	335
24	e9.8	e54	e15	e27	e10	6.9	8.4	12	35	215	70	40
25	e60	e16	e22	e20	e9.0	8.2	6.8	16	24	85	33	20
26	e71	e13	e34	e18	e9.0	9.6	6.5	13	20	69	27	16
27	e14	e38	e21	e27	e9.2	7.6	9.1	12	17	53	23	15
28	e11	e121	e16	e54	e9.2	6.7	5.9	11	15	43	23	19
29	e22	e33	e30	e28	---	6.3	185	10	18	38	20	153
30	e16	e55	e25	e17	---	6.0	30	9.8	32	34	19	110
31	e16	---	e30	e15	---	5.8	---	9.5	---	32	32	---
TOTAL	464.7	889.9	683	657	332.4	236.9	482.8	1319.3	1784.6	2862	1243	1268
MEAN	15.0	29.7	22.0	21.2	11.9	7.64	16.1	42.6	59.5	92.3	40.1	42.3
MAX	71	121	90	54	18	10	185	299	498	946	302	335
MIN	7.4	8.5	14	13	9.0	5.8	5.1	9.5	8.0	11	17	14
AC-FT	922	1770	1350	1300	659	470	958	2620	3540	5680	2470	2520
CFSM	2.50	4.94	3.67	3.53	1.98	1.27	2.68	7.09	9.91	15.4	6.68	7.04
IN.	2.88	5.52	4.23	4.07	2.06	1.47	2.99	8.18	11.06	17.74	7.71	7.86

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1978 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	41.8	47.3	24.5	18.5	16.5	12.4	13.3	34.7	39.3	38.2	30.5	36.1				
MAX	123	122	55.2	56.1	38.0	33.1	27.1	77.5	122	92.3	90.0	94.3				
(WY)	1986	1988	1988	1992	1982	1989	1985	1985	1979	1993	1979	1979				
MIN	13.1	8.34	6.65	8.16	6.36	5.07	4.64	9.56	11.3	12.5	9.30	11.8				
(WY)	1990	1990	1990	1990	1979	1979	1979	1988	1985	1986	1991	1981				

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1978 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	9358.5		12223.6			
ANNUAL MEAN	25.6		33.5		29.5	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					49.6	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					14.5	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1000	Jan 5	946	Jul 11	1250	Oct 6 1985
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	5.0	Apr 28	5.1	Apr 12	3.1	May 7 1979
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	5.4	Apr 25	5.9	Apr 1	3.6	May 1 1979
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			7260		11700	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			12.40		14.78	
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			4.9		2.8	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	18560		24250		21340	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	4.26		5.58		4.91	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	58.02		75.79		66.71	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	44		58		50	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	14		16		15	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	6.6		7.5		6.9	

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'40", long 65°58'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from bridge on Highway 181, and 2.8 mi (4.5 km) southwest of San Lorenzo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.25 mi² (8.42 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 459 ft (140 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	2.5	1.6	20	20	4.5	1.6	1.1	12	3.0	1.9	4.1	3.2
2	2.4	1.6	15	11	6.3	1.6	1.1	16	2.6	2.1	3.5	2.7
3	2.4	1.9	11	9.2	5.0	1.9	1.2	8.4	2.2	6.0	3.0	3.1
4	2.0	6.7	8.7	7.8	4.4	1.8	1.1	3.5	1.9	2.7	2.9	2.6
5	1.7	3.0	7.2	5.8	4.3	1.8	1.1	3.3	1.7	1.9	2.9	3.3
6	14	8.0	6.0	5.0	4.2	1.8	1.1	2.4	1.6	1.6	2.7	2.4
7	7.6	7.0	5.1	7.7	4.2	1.7	1.1	1.9	1.5	1.7	2.4	2.3
8	4.0	3.3	4.5	5.8	4.0	1.6	1.9	2.0	1.6	3.3	2.9	2.9
9	3.3	2.6	4.1	7.6	3.9	1.6	1.9	8.4	2.6	1.7	3.0	3.2
10	2.7	3.1	3.8	5.1	3.9	1.8	1.5	4.7	4.7	1.6	3.9	11
11	2.3	2.2	3.6	4.1	4.4	1.7	1.3	3.4	2.8	e213	3.4	5.0
12	1.9	2.0	3.4	3.8	4.9	1.7	1.3	2.4	2.1	e18	3.5	3.3
13	1.7	1.9	3.4	3.4	5.2	1.9	1.7	1.9	2.5	10	3.2	2.9
14	1.8	1.8	5.8	7.0	4.1	1.8	2.1	19	17	6.7	2.8	2.8
15	1.7	7.4	5.3	4.0	3.7	2.1	1.5	9.3	11	5.3	4.7	2.7
16	1.8	3.7	3.6	3.8	3.5	1.8	1.6	4.4	5.0	7.5	78	6.3
17	1.9	3.7	3.3	3.7	3.4	2.4	1.3	2.9	2.2	4.7	16	3.3
18	1.9	14	3.2	3.3	3.4	2.1	1.1	2.2	13	4.2	9.3	5.3
19	1.9	10	3.1	3.5	3.3	2.4	1.3	1.7	48	4.0	7.1	3.2
20	2.3	6.7	3.2	3.4	3.3	1.9	1.3	1.7	26	3.9	5.7	3.0
21	1.9	5.5	3.0	3.3	3.1	1.7	1.4	1.5	11	3.4	4.9	2.4
22	1.7	4.8	5.3	3.6	2.9	1.4	1.1	1.3	10	36	4.9	2.1
23	2.0	3.5	3.6	3.9	2.4	1.3	1.1	1.4	6.3	32	9.1	8.2
24	3.0	2.9	3.4	3.7	2.4	1.3	1.1	1.3	6.0	22	4.8	4.7
25	3.2	2.4	5.1	4.2	2.0	1.4	1.0	1.7	3.7	12	4.2	2.8
26	3.0	2.2	20	4.0	2.0	1.4	1.3	6.8	2.8	17	3.7	2.3
27	2.0	11	7.9	5.4	2.2	1.3	2.3	8.4	2.2	16	3.2	1.9
28	1.8	34	5.1	6.5	1.9	1.1	1.5	5.3	1.9	8.5	2.8	2.0
29	1.7	10	9.6	11	---	1.0	6.8	3.5	2.1	6.5	2.6	3.2
30	1.7	24	6.4	5.9	---	.99	10	2.9	2.7	5.2	2.5	5.9
31	1.6	---	13	4.9	---	1.0	---	2.6	---	4.7	3.8	---
TOTAL	85.4	192.5	205.7	181.4	102.8	50.89	55.2	148.2	201.7	465.1	211.5	110.0
MEAN	2.75	6.42	6.64	5.85	3.67	1.64	1.84	4.78	6.72	15.0	6.82	3.67
MAX	14	34	20	20	6.3	2.4	10	19	48	213	78	11
MIN	1.6	1.6	3.0	3.3	1.9	.99	1.0	1.3	1.5	1.6	2.4	1.9
AC-FT	169	382	408	360	204	101	109	294	400	923	420	218
CFSM	.85	1.97	2.04	1.80	1.13	.51	.57	1.47	2.07	4.62	2.10	1.13
IN.	.98	2.20	2.35	2.08	1.18	.58	.63	1.70	2.31	5.32	2.42	1.26

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1984 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993		
MEAN	11.8	18.2	7.76	4.94	4.00	4.31	2.45	8.90	6.26	6.14	6.48	7.23
MAX	47.8	36.9	30.1	9.94	8.21	20.7	4.88	31.5	21.3	15.0	20.2	14.3
(WY)	1986	1985	1988	1992	1989	1989	1989	1985	1987	1993	1988	1985
MIN	2.75	2.49	1.49	1.79	1.32	1.64	.90	1.51	2.40	2.02	2.21	1.36
(WY)	1993	1990	1990	1990	1985	1993	1991	1990	1991	1986	1985	1990

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1984 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	2121.88	2010.39	
ANNUAL MEAN	5.80	5.51	7.39
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			12.3
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			2.50
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	194	Jan 5	213
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.72	Jan 4	.99
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	1.1	Mar 24	1.1
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			3730
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			11.20
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	4210	3990	5360
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.78	1.69	2.27
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	24.29	23.01	30.90
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	11	10	12
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	2.7	3.2	2.6
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.4	1.5	1.1

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR--Continued
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1985 to 1986 and water year 1989 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1984 to September 1986 and from October 1989 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.--

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 7,300 mg/L Oct. 06, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 4,940 tons (23,400 tonnes) May 17, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 0.0 ton (0.0 tonne) several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,150 mg/L Nov. 08, 1991; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, e2,860 tons (e2,580 tonnes) July 11, 1993; Minimum daily mean, <.01 ton several days.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	2.5	3	.02	1.6	5	.03	20	134	14
2	2.4	3	.02	1.6	8	.04	15	22	.96
3	2.4	3	.02	1.9	9	.05	11	12	.34
4	2.0	18	.12	6.7	18	.42	8.7	13	.29
5	1.7	3	.02	3.0	7	.07	7.2	11	.22
6	14	100	16	8.0	29	1.4	6.0	9	.15
7	7.6	13	.36	7.0	20	.63	5.1	6	.09
8	4.0	2	.02	3.3	5	.05	4.5	5	.06
9	3.3	1	.01	2.6	4	.03	4.1	5	.06
10	2.7	1	.01	3.1	3	.03	3.8	5	.05
11	2.3	2	.02	2.2	3	.02	3.6	4	.04
12	1.9	2	.01	2.0	3	.02	3.4	3	.03
13	1.7	3	.01	1.9	3	.02	3.4	2	.02
14	1.8	3	.01	1.8	4	.02	5.8	16	.73
15	1.7	3	.01	7.4	37	2.1	5.3	19	.36
16	1.8	4	.02	3.7	8	.09	3.6	3	.03
17	1.9	3	.02	3.7	13	.16	3.3	2	.01
18	1.9	2	.02	14	85	8.6	3.2	3	.02
19	1.9	1	.01	10	34	1.2	3.1	3	.02
20	2.3	1	.00	6.7	15	.34	3.2	3	.02
21	1.9	1	.00	5.5	8	.13	3.0	3	.02
22	1.7	2	.01	4.8	7	.10	5.3	17	.30
23	2.0	4	.02	3.5	7	.07	3.6	23	.24
24	3.0	6	.06	2.9	5	.04	3.4	15	.14
25	3.2	4	.03	2.4	2	.02	5.1	12	.18
26	3.0	4	.04	2.2	2	.02	20	73	7.3
27	2.0	3	.02	11	67	6.1	7.9	25	.60
28	1.8	3	.02	34	566	131	5.1	11	.16
29	1.7	3	.02	10	38	2.9	9.6	31	1.1
30	1.7	2	.01	24	107	12	6.4	15	.25
31	1.6	3	.01	---	---	---	13	54	4.0
TOTAL	85.4	---	16.97	192.5	---	167.70	205.7	---	31.79

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	20	66	5.8	4.5	7	.09	1.6	7	.04
2	11	7	.21	6.3	15	.39	1.6	7	.04
3	9.2	6	.15	5.0	8	.12	1.9	7	.04
4	7.8	7	.15	4.4	5	.06	1.8	5	.02
5	5.8	13	.20	4.3	5	.06	1.8	5	.02
6	5.0	17	.23	4.2	7	.08	1.8	5	.02
7	7.7	30	.92	4.2	8	.10	1.7	7	.03
8	5.8	24	.44	4.0	9	.10	1.6	9	.04
9	7.6	23	.66	3.9	7	.08	1.6	12	.05
10	5.1	8	.12	3.9	5	.06	1.8	13	.06
11	4.1	4	.06	4.4	6	.08	1.7	11	.05
12	3.8	3	.03	4.9	8	.11	1.7	6	.03
13	3.4	3	.02	5.2	7	.10	1.9	3	.02
14	7.0	19	.61	4.1	7	.07	1.8	2	.01
15	4.0	7	.08	3.7	6	.06	2.1	2	.01
16	3.8	5	.05	3.5	5	.05	1.8	1	<.01
17	3.7	5	.05	3.4	4	.04	2.4	1	<.01
18	3.3	5	.04	3.4	6	.05	2.1	2	.01
19	3.5	5	.05	3.3	7	.07	2.4	4	.02
20	3.4	5	.05	3.3	7	.07	1.9	4	.02
21	3.3	5	.04	3.1	5	.05	1.7	5	.02
22	3.6	4	.04	2.9	5	.04	1.4	4	.02
23	3.9	2	.03	2.4	6	.04	1.3	4	.02
24	3.7	1	.02	2.4	8	.05	1.3	4	.02
25	4.2	1	.02	2.0	9	.05	1.4	5	.02
26	4.0	3	.03	2.0	8	.04	1.4	5	.02
27	5.4	6	.09	2.2	8	.04	1.3	3	.01
28	6.5	9	.15	1.9	7	.04	1.1	2	<.01
29	11	42	2.0	---	---	---	1.0	2	<.01
30	5.9	16	.27	---	---	---	.99	2	<.01
31	4.9	10	.14	---	---	---	1.0	2	<.01
TOTAL	181.4	---	12.75	102.8	---	2.19	50.89	---	0.66

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
		MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	
1	1.1	1	<.01	12	48	2.3	3.0	4	.04	
2	1.1	1	<.01	16	84	7.5	2.6	5	.04	
3	1.2	1	<.01	8.4	20	.55	2.2	5	.04	
4	1.1	1	<.01	3.5	10	.10	1.9	4	.02	
5	1.1	3	.01	3.3	6	.05	1.7	4	.02	
6	1.1	3	.01	2.4	4	.03	1.6	4	.02	
7	1.1	3	.01	1.9	2	.01	1.5	4	.02	
8	1.9	3	.01	2.0	3	.01	1.6	4	.02	
9	1.9	3	.02	8.4	21	.57	2.6	6	.06	
10	1.5	3	.02	4.7	8	.12	4.7	10	.16	
11	1.3	4	.02	3.4	3	.03	2.8	4	.04	
12	1.3	5	.02	2.4	2	.02	2.1	2	.02	
13	1.7	4	.02	1.9	2	.02	2.5	3	.02	
14	2.1	2	.01	19	133	15	17	100	11	
15	1.5	2	<.01	9.3	28	.86	11	38	1.5	
16	1.6	2	.01	4.4	10	.13	5.0	12	.19	
17	1.3	3	.02	2.9	5	.04	2.2	8	.06	
18	1.1	3	.01	2.2	2	.01	13	91	84	
19	1.3	3	.01	1.7	2	<.01	48	314	43	
20	1.3	2	.01	1.7	2	<.01	26	126	12	
21	1.4	2	<.01	1.5	2	.01	11	23	.81	
22	1.1	3	<.01	1.3	3	.02	10	10	.24	
23	1.1	3	.01	1.4	4	.02	6.3	8	.15	
24	1.1	4	.02	1.3	5	.02	6.0	8	.12	
25	1.0	5	.02	1.7	5	.03	3.7	6	.07	
26	1.3	6	.03	6.8	26	1.1	2.8	3	.03	
27	2.3	3	.02	8.4	28	1.1	2.2	3	.02	
28	1.5	2	<.01	5.3	15	.27	1.9	3	.02	
29	6.8	27	1.3	3.5	8	.07	2.1	5	.03	
30	10	45	2.6	2.9	6	.05	2.7	4	.04	
31	---	---	---	2.6	4	.03	---	---	---	
TOTAL	55.2	---	4.21	148.2	---	30.07	201.7	---	153.80	

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
				MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	1.9		.01	4.1	5	.05	3.2	7	.06			
2	2.1	2	.01	3.5	5	.04	2.7	2	.02			
3	6.0	15	.37	3.0	10	.07	3.1	2	.02			
4	2.7	8	.06	2.9	12	.09	2.6	2	.02			
5	1.9	10	.05	2.9	10	.08	3.3	3	.02			
6	1.6	6	.03	2.7	5	.04	2.4	2	.02			
7	1.7	2	.02	2.4	2	.02	2.3	2	.02			
8	3.3	6	.08	2.9	7	.06	2.9	3	.03			
9	1.7	2	.01	3.0	8	.07	3.2	6	.05			
10	1.6	2	<.01	3.9	7	.07	11	37	1.4			
11	e213	1150	e2860	3.4	8	.07	5.0	10	.16			
12	e18	68	e5.3	3.5	7	.07	3.3	7	.06			
13	10	10	.28	3.2	7	.06	2.9	11	.08			
14	6.7	8	.15	2.8	6	.05	2.8	12	.08			
15	5.3	8	.12	4.7	13	.36	2.7	12	.10			
16	7.5	16	.43	78	812	289	6.3	17	.43			
17	4.7	8	.11	16	46	2.4	3.3	6	.06			
18	4.2	8	.10	9.3	7	.19	5.3	14	.44			
19	4.0	7	.08	7.1	3	.06	3.2	6	.06			
20	3.9	6	.07	5.7	3	.05	3.0	2	.01			
21	3.4	6	.06	4.9	8	.10	2.4	2	.02			
22	36	188	131	4.9	8	.10	2.1	2	.02			
23	32	185	30	9.1	18	.60	8.2	39	3.7			
24	22	102	10	4.8	3	.05	4.7	20	.29			
25	12	28	.96	4.2	3	.04	2.8	15	.12			
26	17	60	7.0	3.7	3	.03	2.3	10	.06			
27	16	67	5.0	3.2	5	.04	1.9	5	.02			
28	8.5	12	.27	2.8	9	.06	2.0	2	.01			
29	6.5	8	.14	2.6	10	.06	3.2	5	.06			
30	5.2	6	.09	2.5	10	.07	5.9	13	.29			
31	4.7	6	.08	3.8	10	.10	---	---	---			
TOTAL	465.1	---	3051.88	211.5	---	294.15	110.0	---	7.73			
YEAR	2010.39		3773.90									

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
NOV 1992 28...	0850	211	5460	3110	29	39	47

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
NOV 1992 28...	60	72	83	92	98	99	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
NOV 1992					
28...	0820	183	1790	884	85
MAY 1993					
14...	1100	50	485	65	87
JUL					
11...	0810	189	1670	852	85
11...	1035	86	3820	887	80
AUG					
16...	0720	145	3120	1220	97

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'24", long 65°58'38", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left downstream side of bridge on Highway 181, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from Río Grande de Loiza, and 1.5 mi (2.4 km) southwest of San Lorenzo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.74 mi² (9.69 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 330 ft (100 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	6.5	2.0	23	e11	2.7	e1.5	.86	e17	1.7	2.7	e3.7	2.2
2	5.6	1.7	13	e9.0	3.4	e1.6	.86	e8.0	1.6	2.3	e3.9	2.0
3	5.4	2.0	6.6	e7.0	3.3	e1.2	1.1	11	1.3	e6.5	3.4	2.0
4	5.1	7.7	5.8	5.9	2.7	e1.2	1.0	4.3	1.1	e4.4	3.2	2.0
5	5.5	3.4	4.2	5.8	2.7	e1.3	.87	3.6	.98	4.7	3.2	2.9
6	39	7.0	3.0	5.5	2.7	e1.2	.86	3.2	.93	3.2	3.4	2.1
7	5.8	8.1	2.7	5.7	2.7	e1.2	.76	1.8	.91	2.2	2.8	1.9
8	2.6	3.2	2.8	4.9	2.5	e1.2	.96	1.6	.86	3.0	2.8	2.0
9	2.2	2.4	2.5	5.2	2.5	e1.1	1.7	7.6	1.5	1.9	2.8	2.0
10	2.1	5.9	e2.5	4.7	2.5	e1.1	1.3	5.6	3.0	1.7	4.1	5.2
11	2.5	3.3	e2.4	4.4	2.5	1.2	.98	2.5	1.6	259	3.7	3.3
12	2.0	1.7	e2.3	4.1	e2.9	1.2	1.0	1.9	1.3	34	2.8	2.3
13	1.7	1.7	e3.8	3.9	e3.1	1.2	1.4	1.9	1.3	17	2.8	2.1
14	1.6	1.6	e3.5	5.3	e3.3	1.0	1.8	33	20	10	2.5	2.2
15	1.6	3.3	e2.5	3.7	e2.7	1.0	1.8	13	17	7.6	3.3	2.2
16	1.6	2.2	e2.2	3.9	e2.4	1.0	2.1	5.9	8.2	8.9	67	5.2
17	1.6	1.5	e2.1	3.9	e2.3	1.9	1.4	3.7	3.2	e6.5	15	3.0
18	1.6	26	e2.1	3.4	e2.2	1.6	1.2	2.7	16	e4.4	4.7	3.3
19	1.9	14	e2.1	3.4	e2.2	1.9	1.5	2.2	124	e3.7	3.4	3.6
20	4.0	4.5	e2.1	3.4	e2.2	1.8	.98	2.2	43	e2.8	3.0	e2.6
21	1.8	19	e3.5	3.2	e2.1	1.6	1.0	2.2	10	e2.3	2.5	e2.3
22	1.3	13	e2.5	3.2	e2.0	1.3	.98	1.9	12	70	4.2	e2.3
23	1.5	4.7	e2.3	3.4	e1.9	1.3	.91	1.8	5.8	76	7.6	e9.5
24	2.0	2.1	e10	3.0	e1.7	1.3	.78	1.9	5.0	38	5.3	e4.4
25	3.2	1.3	e7.0	2.8	e1.5	1.2	.74	1.9	4.1	15	4.1	e3.0
26	2.8	1.1	e5.0	2.8	e1.4	1.2	1.1	2.2	3.0	11	3.9	e2.5
27	2.1	26	e3.5	3.4	e1.3	1.1	4.0	6.7	2.4	e15	2.3	e2.3
28	1.8	124	e6.8	3.4	e1.4	.99	1.7	5.0	2.2	e8.6	2.2	e2.5
29	1.8	29	e4.5	4.9	---	.92	3.0	2.2	2.4	e5.2	2.0	e2.7
30	1.9	115	e13	3.3	---	.86	e12	1.9	3.6	e4.2	2.0	e4.7
31	2.2	---	e17	2.8	---	.86	---	1.8	---	e4.4	2.3	---
TOTAL	122.3	438.4	166.3	140.3	66.8	39.03	50.64	162.2	299.98	636.2	179.9	90.3
MEAN	3.95	14.6	5.36	4.53	2.39	1.26	1.69	5.23	10.0	20.5	5.80	3.01
MAX	39	124	23	11	3.4	1.9	12	33	124	259	67	9.5
MIN	1.3	1.1	2.1	2.8	1.3	.86	.74	1.6	.86	1.7	2.0	1.9
AC-FT	243	870	330	278	132	77	100	322	595	1260	357	179
CFSM	1.05	3.91	1.43	1.21	.64	.34	.45	1.40	2.67	5.49	1.55	.80
IN.	1.22	4.36	1.65	1.40	.66	.39	.50	1.61	2.98	6.33	1.79	.90

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1984 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993		
MEAN	10.3	15.0	5.88	5.28	3.45	3.49	2.69	8.25	6.90	5.92	5.50	9.96
MAX	36.2	33.4	22.8	23.4	10.3	17.4	6.60	35.8	15.0	20.5	14.4	29.0
(WY)	1986	1988	1988	1992	1984	1989	1985	1985	1984	1993	1988	1989
MIN	2.31	2.72	1.17	1.16	1.23	1.15	.88	1.53	1.78	1.58	1.95	1.88
(WY)	1987	1990	1990	1990	1990	1992	1984	1990	1991	1986	1985	1990

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1984 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	2607.15	2392.35	
ANNUAL MEAN	7.12	6.55	6.87
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			10.4
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			3.19
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	472	Jan 5	472
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.84	Apr 21	.29
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.98	Mar 28	.41
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		2370	9320
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		11.32	17.10
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW		.60	.26
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	5170	4750	4980
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.90	1.75	1.84
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	25.93	23.80	24.96
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	9.0	10	10
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.8	2.7	2.1
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.1	1.2	1.0

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- Water years 1984 to 1986 and water years 1989 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1984 to September 1986 and from October 1989 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.--

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 7,300 mg/L Oct. 06, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 11,100 tons (10,100 tonnes) Jan. 05, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 0.0 ton (0.0 tonne) several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 743 mg/L July 11, 1993; Minimum daily mean, 1.0 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 1,140 tons (1,030 tonnes) July 11, 1993; Minimum daily mean, <0.01 ton (<0.01 tonne) several days.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	6.5	2	.04	2.0	3	.02	23	111	11
2	5.6	2	.02	1.7	3	.02	13	100	3.3
3	5.4	2	.03	2.0	4	.03	6.6	44	.86
4	5.1	2	.02	7.7	62	1.4	5.8	19	.33
5	5.5	2	.02	3.4	30	.31	4.2	15	.16
6	39	97	72	7.0	21	.54	3.0	12	.10
7	5.8	19	.33	8.1	20	.57	2.7	8	.06
8	2.6	12	.09	3.2	6	.05	2.8	4	.03
9	2.2	8	.05	2.4	3	.02	2.5	2	.02
10	2.1	7	.04	5.9	8	.15	e2.5	2	e.02
11	2.5	6	.04	3.3	3	.03	e2.4	4	e.03
12	2.0	5	.04	1.7	3	.02	e2.3	4	e.03
13	1.7	6	.03	1.7	3	.02	e3.8	3	e.04
14	1.6	5	.02	1.6	3	.02	e3.5	4	e.03
15	1.6	4	.02	3.3	13	.19	e2.5	8	e.06
16	1.6	3	.02	2.2	16	.10	e2.2	12	e.07
17	1.6	3	.02	1.5	19	.07	e2.1	8	e.04
18	1.6	3	.02	26	94	14	e2.1	4	e.02
19	1.9	4	.02	14	37	1.7	e2.1	3	e.02
20	4.0	9	.19	4.5	12	.16	e2.1	3	e.02
21	1.8	6	.04	19	82	18	e3.5	4	e.04
22	1.3	3	.01	13	15	.73	e2.5	6	e.04
23	1.5	1	.00	4.7	3	.04	e2.3	5	e.04
24	2.0	2	.00	2.1	6	.04	e10	3	e.09
25	3.2	2	.02	1.3	8	.04	e7.0	3	e.06
26	2.8	3	.02	1.1	6	.02	e5.0	1110	e15
27	2.1	4	.02	26	81	16	e3.5	25	e.23
28	1.8	5	.03	124	424	463	e6.8	4	e.09
29	1.8	4	.02	29	47	14	e4.5	7	e.08
30	1.9	3	.02	108	200	314	e13	15	e.51
31	2.2	3	.02	---	---	---	e17	18	e.83
TOTAL	122.3	---	73.26	431.4	---	845.29	166.3	---	33.25

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	e11	17	e.49	2.7	5	.04	e1.5	3	e.02
2	e9.0	15	e.36	3.4	9	.10	e1.6	2	e.01
3	e7.0	13	e.23	3.3	10	.08	e1.2	1	e<.01
4	5.9	10	.17	2.7	7	.06	e1.2	1	e<.01
5	5.8	10	.15	2.7	7	.06	e1.3	1	e<.01
6	5.5	10	.16	2.7	6	.04	e1.2	3	e.01
7	5.7	10	.15	2.7	5	.04	e1.2	6	e.02
8	4.9	11	.14	2.5	5	.04	e1.2	7	e.02
9	5.2	9	.12	2.5	4	.03	e1.1	7	e.02
10	4.7	6	.08	2.5	4	.02	e1.1	6	e.02
11	4.4	5	.06	2.5	4	.03	1.2	6	.02
12	4.1	6	.07	e2.9	5	e.04	1.2	6	.02
13	3.9	7	.08	e3.1	5	e.04	1.2	6	.02
14	5.3	14	.24	e3.3	5	e.05	1.0	6	.02
15	3.7	11	.10	e2.7	6	e.05	1.0	5	.02
16	3.9	8	.09	e2.4	9	e.06	1.0	5	.02
17	3.9	6	.06	e2.3	8	e.05	1.9	5	.02
18	3.4	6	.06	e2.2	6	e.03	1.6	5	.02
19	3.4	11	.10	e2.2	4	e.02	1.9	5	.02
20	3.4	13	.11	e2.2	3	e.02	1.8	5	.03
21	3.2	8	.07	e2.1	2	e.02	1.6	4	.02
22	3.2	5	.04	e2.0	2	e.02	1.3	5	.02
23	3.4	3	.03	e1.9	2	e.02	1.3	6	.02
24	3.0	4	.04	e1.7	2	e<.01	1.3	6	.02
25	2.8	4	.04	e1.5	2	e<.01	1.2	5	.02
26	2.8	5	.04	e1.4	2	e<.01	1.2	5	.02
27	3.4	5	.04	e1.3	2	e<.01	1.1	5	.02
28	3.4	5	.04	e1.4	2	e.01	.99	4	.02
29	4.9	15	.21	---	---	---	.92	4	.02
30	3.3	12	.11	---	---	---	.86	5	.02
31	2.8	7	.06	---	---	---	.86	5	.02
TOTAL	140.3	---	3.74	66.8	---	0.97	39.03	---	0.55

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	.86	5	.02	e17	14	e.64	1.7	4	.02
2	.86	5	.02	e8.0	14	e.30	1.6	3	.02
3	1.1	5	.01	11	36	1.0	1.3	4	.02
4	1.0	5	.01	4.3	15	.17	1.1	7	.02
5	.87	5	.01	3.6	7	.07	.98	6	.02
6	.86	4	.01	3.2	5	.04	.93	5	.02
7	.76	3	.00	1.8	5	.03	.91	5	.02
8	.96	1	.00	1.6	5	.02	.86	5	.02
9	1.7	2	.00	7.6	18	.42	1.5	5	.01
10	1.3	3	.02	5.6	9	.14	3.0	7	.06
11	.98	4	.01	2.5	4	.02	1.6	5	.02
12	1.0	3	.00	1.9	3	.01	1.3	4	.02
13	1.4	3	.00	1.9	3	.02	1.3	4	.02
14	1.8	2	.01	33	114	32	20	54	5.5
15	1.8	2	.00	13	29	1.0	17	37	1.9
16	2.1	3	.01	5.9	12	.22	8.2	21	.58
17	1.4	3	.02	3.7	4	.04	3.2	13	.11
18	1.2	3	.01	2.7	5	.04	16	55	24
19	1.5	6	.02	2.2	5	.03	124	363	182
20	.98	7	.01	2.2	4	.02	43	124	25
21	1.0	3	.01	2.2	4	.02	10	26	.91
22	.98	3	.01	1.9	4	.02	12	31	1.1
23	.91	4	.02	1.8	4	.02	5.8	12	.19
24	.78	5	.02	1.9	4	.02	5.0	6	.08
25	.74	6	.02	1.9	4	.02	4.1	5	.05
26	1.1	7	.02	2.2	7	.04	3.0	5	.04
27	4.0	11	.14	6.7	17	.55	2.4	5	.03
28	1.7	6	.03	5.0	12	.21	2.2	5	.02
29	3.0	7	.06	2.2	6	.04	2.4	4	.03
30	e12	14	.46	1.9	5	.02	3.6	3	.04
31	---	---	---	1.8	4	.02	---	---	---
TOTAL	50.64	---	0.98	162.2	---	37.21	299.98	---	241.87

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	2.7	3	.02	e3.7	5	e.05	2.2	6	.03
2	2.3	3	.02	e3.9	3	e.03	2.0	6	.03
3	e6.5	14	e.25	3.4	2	.02	2.0	7	.04
4	e4.4	8	e.10	3.2	3	.03	2.0	8	.04
5	4.7	5	.06	3.2	7	.06	2.9	12	.09
6	3.2	11	.08	3.4	9	.08	2.1	17	.09
7	2.2	12	.08	2.8	8	.07	1.9	12	.06
8	3.0	7	.05	2.8	5	.04	2.0	4	.03
9	1.9	3	.01	2.8	2	.02	2.0	2	.02
10	1.7	2	.00	4.1	2	.02	5.2	21	.31
11	259	743	1140	3.7	2	.02	3.3	18	.18
12	34	81	9.2	2.8	6	.05	2.3	10	.06
13	17	23	1.3	2.8	9	.07	2.1	5	.03
14	10	8	.25	2.5	10	.06	2.2	4	.02
15	7.6	6	.13	3.3	12	.10	2.2	3	.02
16	8.9	5	.13	67	192	53	5.2	12	.15
17	e6.5	6	e.10	15	49	2.1	3.0	11	.08
18	e4.4	7	e.08	4.7	15	.27	3.3	8	.08
19	e3.7	7	e.07	3.4	3	.03	3.6	6	.07
20	e2.8	4	e.03	3.0	2	.02	e2.6	5	e.04
21	e2.3	2	e.01	2.5	2	.02	e2.3	5	e.04
22	70	129	120	4.2	7	.24	e2.3	6	e.04
23	76	186	69	7.6	14	.35	e9.5	30	e1.8
24	38	113	17	5.3	7	.11	e4.4	14	e.20
25	15	27	1.3	4.1	5	.05	e3.0	7	e.06
26	11	19	.61	3.9	4	.05	e2.5	4	e.03
27	e15	35	1.7	2.3	5	.02	e2.3	4	e.02
28	e8.6	15	.34	2.2	5	.03	e2.5	3	e.02
29	e5.2	10	.14	2.0	6	.04	e2.7	3	e.02
30	e4.2	10	.11	2.0	7	.04	e4.7	8	e.15
31	e4.4	8	.09	2.3	6	.04	---	---	---
TOTAL	636.2	---	1362.26	179.9	---	57.13	90.3	---	3.85
YEAR	2385.35		2660.36						

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
NOV 1992					
28...	0810	1370	1740	6440	98
MAY 1993					
14...	1045	147	1160	460	90
JUN					
14...	1000	45	560	68	98
JUL					
11...	0725	300	2720	2200	96
11...	1020	331	2060	1840	60
22...	1650	193	4890	2550	67
AUG					
16...	1033	111	274	82	95

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051310 RIO CAYAGUAS AT CERRO GORDO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'13", long 65°57'20", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at downstream side of bridge on Highway 912, at Barrio Cerro Gordo, 2.8 mi (4.5 km) south of San Lorenzo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--10.2 mi² (26.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1977 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 490 ft (150 m), from topographic map. Prior to Oct. 1, 1983, at site 2,000 ft (610 m) downstream at different datum.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Sand removal at a commercial level is practiced at times during the year. This takes place about one hundred feet downstream from the low water control. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	19	45	196	87	31	21	15	156	16	22	32	33
2	20	26	76	55	33	22	14	69	16	22	31	37
3	21	25	72	44	31	21	16	30	15	39	30	66
4	21	73	55	36	28	20	15	24	14	33	29	30
5	23	39	46	33	28	21	16	42	14	20	30	79
6	23	89	43	57	28	21	17	43	14	19	29	48
7	24	56	38	64	29	20	15	17	14	32	30	28
8	24	35	35	53	29	21	17	15	16	64	31	61
9	24	32	34	51	29	21	18	225	15	26	29	59
10	25	29	33	43	27	21	16	104	29	21	29	93
11	26	28	33	39	32	20	14	37	25	1130	33	64
12	25	26	33	38	34	21	14	24	17	177	30	36
13	25	36	33	34	34	24	14	21	46	90	25	32
14	24	29	33	37	26	23	17	210	255	61	25	32
15	24	43	33	33	24	24	16	57	139	46	29	28
16	27	34	32	34	24	22	14	23	64	104	390	75
17	29	74	32	32	24	26	13	16	25	48	104	33
18	28	99	32	33	23	24	14	14	149	35	48	54
19	27	75	32	39	23	31	17	13	649	33	34	36
20	27	57	33	31	24	29	14	16	290	32	27	32
21	205	43	36	29	23	25	14	15	69	32	27	27
22	76	63	34	41	22	21	13	15	55	280	30	30
23	36	55	32	43	25	20	13	15	35	253	78	202
24	55	75	35	33	25	20	13	15	36	128	33	127
25	75	49	39	98	22	22	14	24	25	66	27	54
26	38	41	80	42	22	22	20	29	21	53	23	29
27	28	62	49	54	22	20	23	85	20	49	22	24
28	26	264	34	70	21	17	15	53	19	37	24	33
29	27	77	85	186	---	17	77	22	20	33	20	131
30	26	195	65	48	---	16	74	17	32	32	21	190
31	40	---	44	34	---	15	---	15	---	33	35	---
TOTAL	1118	1874	1487	1551	743	668	582	1461	2154	3050	1385	1803
MEAN	36.1	62.5	48.0	50.0	26.5	21.5	19.4	47.1	71.8	98.4	44.7	60.1
MAX	205	264	196	186	34	31	77	225	649	1130	390	202
MIN	19	25	32	29	21	15	13	13	14	19	20	24
AC-FT	2220	3720	2950	3080	1470	1320	1150	2900	4270	6050	2750	3580
CFSM	3.54	6.12	4.70	4.91	2.60	2.11	1.90	4.62	7.04	9.65	4.38	5.89
IN.	4.08	6.83	5.42	5.66	2.71	2.44	2.12	5.33	7.86	11.12	5.05	6.58

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1977 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	64.2	74.4	47.0	30.0	26.7	21.9	20.8	50.1	49.4	45.7	47.4	55.7					
MAX	176	196	163	50.0	67.5	45.4	46.0	155	140	118	202	216					
(WY)	1986	1988	1988	1993	1984	1989	1985	1985	1979	1979	1979	1979					
MIN	14.4	19.2	12.5	14.6	11.0	11.3	10.7	9.68	14.4	16.0	14.5	16.9					
(WY)	1992	1982	1992	1990	1992	1992	1980	1990	1991	1990	1991	1980					

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1977 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	16713.1	17876															
ANNUAL MEAN	45.7	49.0								44.5							
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN										89.7							1979
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN										18.6							1990
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN				831	May 26		1130	Jul 11		2900						Aug 31	1979
LOWEST DAILY MEAN				8.5	Apr 10		13	Apr 17		7.1						Feb 4	1981
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM				9.0	Apr 5		14	Apr 17		8.6						Apr 7	1983
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW							5490	Jul 11		13200						Aug 31	1979
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE							17.33	Jul 11		9.44						Aug 31	1979
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW							13	Apr 16		7.1						Feb 4	1981
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	33150						35460			32250							
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	4.48						4.80			4.36							
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	60.95						65.19			59.29							
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	84						78			69							
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	27						31			24							
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	10						16			13							

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051800 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT HWY 183 NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°11'09", long 65°57'42", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at upstream side of bridge on Highway 183 by-pass, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) south from Plaza de San Lorenzo, 1.4 mi (2.2 km), southwest from Escuela Rafael Colón Garcia and 2.0 mi (3.2 km) northwest from Escuela Segunda Unidad de Carlos Zayas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--25.0 mi² (64.8 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 262 ft (80 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Water purification plant located about 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from gage. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	96	74	226	215	e84	48	27	250	50	e59	103	84
2	89	55	168	156	e98	50	28	306	46	e56	97	86
3	87	56	188	123	84	46	28	138	38	e101	89	103
4	80	143	141	113	72	44	29	81	38	e73	85	70
5	78	84	119	91	68	44	26	90	41	e54	83	105
6	134	164	110	122	69	44	27	93	41	e47	80	82
7	85	135	102	146	68	42	24	56	39	e55	77	65
8	75	78	97	132	64	42	29	50	41	e95	81	102
9	73	68	94	119	63	43	45	191	45	e54	74	107
10	69	65	91	110	61	40	36	133	61	e44	78	204
11	67	58	87	99	70	40	27	73	64	e1890	85	124
12	66	54	83	99	83	41	26	56	43	e262	76	82
13	61	63	85	90	e70	45	28	48	68	e204	67	74
14	61	54	88	98	e62	44	46	362	211	175	62	73
15	61	113	97	85	e60	45	34	145	226	155	70	67
16	62	75	84	84	e62	41	31	89	154	237	449	137
17	63	114	82	83	e64	51	e117	70	79	156	177	81
18	65	178	79	77	e58	50	e30	65	184	137	103	174
19	60	161	77	85	58	58	e36	57	e1300	129	87	95
20	71	126	75	74	59	54	e32	58	e668	120	81	96
21	130	107	75	70	57	47	e35	56	e327	118	78	69
22	92	105	85	e130	55	38	e27	53	e264	436	81	67
23	65	95	78	e86	55	36	37	52	e124	379	210	264
24	77	108	76	e150	57	38	25	53	e109	322	152	166
25	140	79	85	e110	53	39	24	61	e81	234	99	92
26	95	70	184	e98	49	45	34	97	e71	197	87	79
27	63	130	125	e120	50	40	50	105	e64	191	79	69
28	57	443	90	e300	50	35	29	86	e59	140	76	73
29	61	195	167	e120	---	32	139	57	e58	122	72	185
30	60	412	138	e94	---	30	139	50	e90	110	68	223
31	62	---	148	e84	---	29	---	46	---	105	91	---
TOTAL	2405	3662	3424	3563	1803	1321	1245	3127	4684	6457	3197	3298
MEAN	77.6	122	110	115	64.4	42.6	41.5	101	156	208	103	110
MAX	140	443	226	300	98	58	139	362	1300	1890	449	264
MIN	57	54	75	70	49	29	24	46	38	44	62	65
AC-FT	4770	7260	6790	7070	3580	2620	2470	6200	9290	12810	6340	6540
CFSM	3.10	4.88	4.42	4.60	2.58	1.70	1.66	4.03	6.25	8.33	4.13	4.40
IN.	3.58	5.45	5.09	5.30	2.68	1.97	1.85	4.65	6.97	9.61	4.76	4.91

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1990	1991	1992	1993	1990	1991	1992	1993	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	142	153	93.3	123	51.0	36.7	29.5	89.6	144	117	97.8	129
MAX	266	222	110	192	71.1	48.7	41.5	186	290	208	132	255
(WY)	1991	1992	1993	1992	1991	1991	1993	1992	1992	1993	1992	1992
MIN	77.6	113	82.6	62.9	21.0	17.4	16.8	35.1	47.8	66.0	48.6	59.7
(WY)	1993	1991	1992	1991	1992	1992	1992	1991	1991	1990	1991	1990

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1990 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	46830.0		38186			
ANNUAL MEAN	128		105		107	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					134	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					82.2	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	3380		1890		3380	
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	6.3		24		6.3	
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	7.4		27		7.4	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			14600		28200	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			21.50		27.36	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	92890		75740		77530	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	5.12		4.18		4.28	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	69.68		56.82		58.16	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	199		177		168	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	75		78		58	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	14		40		22	

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051800 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT HWY 183 NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1990 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: February 1990 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- DH-48 and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,570 mg/L Jun. 11, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 5 mg/L Several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 46,800 tons (42,400 tonnes) Jan. 05, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 0.20 ton (0.18 tonne) May 05, 1992.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

Water Year	Suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		Suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1993	2,750 (July 11)	4 (Several days)	e30,800 (July 11)	.73 (May, 23)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
				MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	96	19	4.8	74	74	16	226	448	396			
2	89	18	4.3	55	55	8.4	168	133	69			
3	87	21	4.9	56	53	8.2	188	142	81			
4	80	25	5.4	143	135	63	141	46	19			
5	78	26	5.4	84	82	20	119	11	3.6			
6	134	110	81	164	163	86	110	8	2.5			
7	85	64	17	135	115	48	102	7	2.0			
8	75	13	2.7	78	34	7.7	97	7	2.0			
9	73	13	2.7	68	17	3.0	94	8	2.1			
10	69	13	2.6	65	25	4.5	91	6	1.5			
11	67	13	2.4	58	35	5.9	87	4	.94			
12	66	12	2.2	54	37	5.4	83	4	.91			
13	61	12	1.9	63	35	6.1	85	4	.93			
14	61	12	2.0	54	35	5.4	88	4	1.1			
15	61	12	2.0	113	96	47	97	7	1.8			
16	62	13	2.1	75	49	11	84	7	1.8			
17	63	13	2.3	114	135	49	82	8	1.8			
18	65	19	3.2	178	172	110	79	7	1.5			
19	60	43	7.1	161	154	76	77	5	1.2			
20	71	71	15	126	69	25	75	4	.94			
21	130	137	82	107	62	22	75	4	.95			
22	92	83	28	105	63	17	85	6	1.3			
23	65	22	3.6	95	33	8.7	78	6	1.4			
24	77	48	20	108	85	29	76	5	1.0			
25	140	134	60	79	25	6.3	85	5	1.2			
26	95	54	20	70	6	1.2	184	165	129			
27	63	16	2.7	130	95	57	125	157	57			
28	57	18	2.7	443	467	1360	90	129	31			
29	61	19	3.1	195	205	124	167	171	82			
30	60	21	3.7	412	414	882	138	140	56			
31	62	20	3.4	---	---	---	148	152	70			
TOTAL	2405	---	400.2	3662	---	3112.8	3424	---	1022.47			

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051800 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT HWY 183 NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR---Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	215	152	90	e84	35	7.9	48	28	3.7
2	156	142	65	e98	38	9.9	50	28	3.8
3	123	137	48	84	38	8.5	46	29	3.6
4	113	116	35	72	33	6.3	44	33	4.0
5	91	88	20	68	33	6.1	44	34	4.2
6	122	101	36	69	37	6.9	44	28	3.4
7	146	142	60	68	46	8.4	42	21	2.5
8	132	79	34	64	45	7.8	42	16	1.8
9	119	17	4.9	63	27	4.5	43	20	2.4
10	110	7	2.1	61	17	2.7	40	29	3.2
11	99	6	1.8	70	21	4.0	40	41	4.5
12	99	6	1.6	83	28	6.2	41	43	5.0
13	90	6	1.6	e70	31	e5.9	45	45	5.3
14	98	4	1.3	e62	32	e5.4	44	47	5.7
15	85	4	1.1	e60	31	e5.0	45	49	6.0
16	84	5	1.3	e62	29	e4.8	41	51	5.6
17	83	6	1.4	e64	26	e4.4	51	50	6.6
18	77	7	1.5	e58	21	e3.3	50	49	6.6
19	85	6	1.5	58	18	2.8	58	45	6.6
20	74	6	1.2	59	19	2.9	54	42	6.1
21	70	6	1.2	57	22	3.3	47	37	4.8
22	e130	98	e47	55	24	3.5	38	37	3.7
23	e86	59	e14	55	25	3.9	36	39	3.9
24	e150	10	e4.1	57	26	4.1	38	52	5.4
25	e110	10	e3.0	53	27	3.9	39	62	6.5
26	e98	10	e2.6	49	27	3.7	45	60	7.6
27	e120	10	e3.2	50	27	3.6	40	52	5.9
28	e300	295	e239	50	27	3.6	35	49	4.6
29	e120	115	e37	---	---	---	32	49	4.3
30	e94	90	e23	---	---	---	30	56	4.8
31	e84	52	e12	---	---	---	29	79	6.5
TOTAL	3563	---	795.4	1803	---	143.3	1321	---	148.6

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051800 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT HWY 183 NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR---Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	27	97	6.9	250	248	307	50	8	1.1
2	28	87	6.9	306	312	516	46	13	1.5
3	28	62	4.9	138	109	54	38	15	1.5
4	29	47	3.6	81	78	18	38	15	1.5
5	26	26	1.9	90	85	21	41	12	1.3
6	27	60	4.4	93	56	17	41	9	.99
7	24	107	7.4	56	23	3.7	39	8	.84
8	29	124	10	50	17	2.4	41	10	1.1
9	45	110	13	191	181	141	45	15	1.8
10	36	88	8.3	133	76	29	61	28	5.4
11	27	81	6.1	73	41	9.1	64	38	7.7
12	26	75	5.3	56	21	3.3	43	20	2.3
13	28	78	6.0	48	20	2.7	68	53	15
14	46	110	13	362	326	865	211	208	179
15	34	151	14	145	143	63	226	220	175
16	31	183	16	89	57	14	154	127	66
17	e117	178	e56	70	24	4.7	79	68	14
18	e30	173	e16	65	17	2.9	184	250	543
19	e36	170	e20	57	14	2.2	e1300	1350	e6150
20	e32	170	e17	58	11	1.6	e668	563	1350
21	e35	174	e20	56	8	1.4	e327	72	e71
22	e27	187	e16	53	6	.96	e264	233	e183
23	37	148	13	52	5	.73	e124	110	e39
24	25	169	12	53	6	.94	e109	66	e19
25	24	122	8.5	61	10	1.7	e81	43	e9.3
26	34	107	10	97	38	9.7	e71	23	e4.5
27	50	105	14	105	78	32	e64	8	e1.5
28	29	101	8.2	86	74	21	e59	8	e1.2
29	139	134	131	57	19	3.0	e58	24	e4.3
30	139	176	71	50	7	1.0	e90	81	e20
31	---	---	---	46	6	.75	---	---	---
TOTAL	1245	---	540.4	3127	---	2150.78	4684	---	8871.83

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051800 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT HWY 183 NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR---Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	e59	80	e13	103	5	1.5	84	16	3.8
2	e56	63	e9.7	97	5	1.3	86	23	5.8
3	e101	49	e13	89	5	1.2	103	40	12
4	e73	36	e7.8	85	5	1.1	70	25	4.8
5	e54	25	e3.5	83	5	1.1	105	60	25
6	e47	18	e2.2	80	6	1.4	82	111	27
7	e55	35	e7.6	77	9	2.0	65	56	10
8	e95	86	e24	81	11	2.4	102	86	35
9	e54	31	e4.9	74	15	2.9	107	135	45
10	e44	20	e2.3	78	19	3.7	204	153	97
11	e1890	2750	e30800	85	55	15	124	74	28
12	e262	315	e244	76	38	9.1	82	41	8.9
13	e204	70	e39	67	19	3.4	74	27	5.4
14	175	31	15	62	17	2.8	73	20	3.8
15	155	11	4.5	70	40	9.3	67	17	3.2
16	237	237	187	449	501	936	137	109	52
17	156	39	18	177	51	29	81	56	12
18	137	17	6.1	103	20	5.6	174	176	197
19	129	13	4.3	87	21	4.8	95	115	32
20	120	9	2.9	81	21	4.5	96	67	16
21	118	8	2.5	78	20	4.3	69	76	15
22	436	1430	7150	81	30	7.5	67	65	12
23	379	419	443	210	168	114	264	270	899
24	322	216	196	152	162	74	166	166	91
25	234	58	42	99	50	14	92	61	16
26	197	33	22	87	19	4.7	79	21	4.7
27	191	88	50	79	17	3.5	69	12	2.2
28	140	41	16	76	14	2.7	73	15	3.3
29	122	20	6.7	72	11	2.0	185	196	139
30	110	8	2.5	68	10	1.8	223	219	147
31	105	6	1.7	91	12	3.0	---	---	---
TOTAL	6457	---	39341.2	3197	---	1269.6	3298	---	1952.9
YEAR	38186		59749.48						

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051800 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT HWY 183 NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
NOV 1992							
30...	0940	290	3980	3120	49	54	57
DEC							
01...	1401	583	33000	51900	7	8	9
MAY 1993							
14...	1020	1820	5580	27400	25	30	40
JUL							
11...	1150	2600	4570	32100	26	31	35
22...	1830	4230	2670	30500	36	40	44
SEP							
23...	1815	2930	22500	178000	10	12	14

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
NOV 1992							
30...	56	72	92	98	99.4	99.7	99.8
DEC							
01...	11	21	40	74	93	99.6	100
MAY 1993							
14...	54	71	86	96	99	99.8	100
JUL							
11...	45	60	74	93	97	99	99
22...	51	59	71	88	95	99	100
SEP							
23...	18	25	40	67	88	98	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051800 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT HWY 183 NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDEED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
NOV 1992					
18...	0935	83	351	79	99
DEC					
01...	1516	489	1640	2160	83
JAN 1993					
29...	1000	120	2670	865	99
APR					
19...	0940	44	368	44	94
JUN					
14...	0940	136	3110	1140	93
18...	2330	1590	4980	21380	55
19...	0530	945	498	1270	89
JUL					
11...	0930	2050	1730	9580	74
22...	2030	909	6680	16400	57
SEP					
23...	1815	2930	13000	102800	48

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053025 RIO TURABO ABOVE BORINQUEN, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'35", long 66°02'26", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank at Highway 765, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) south of Villa Borinquen, 8.1 mi (13.0 km) upstream from Rio Grande de Loiza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--7.14 mi² (18.49 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 492 ft (150 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	12	8.1	37	47	10	7.1	5.7	126	11	12	21	14
2	12	7.4	20	34	11	7.4	85.7	116	10	13	19	14
3	11	7.0	25	22	11	7.1	6.1	39	9.3	32	17	14
4	10	21	17	17	10	7.4	6.1	17	9.1	16	16	12
5	10	11	14	15	9.9	7.3	5.7	14	8.7	12	15	13
6	47	49	12	16	9.5	6.8	5.8	12	8.7	11	14	12
7	17	22	11	26	9.3	6.6	5.7	9.9	8.7	11	14	10
8	13	10	10	17	9.2	6.5	13	12	9.4	18	14	15
9	12	9.5	9.6	18	9.0	6.5	15	22	9.3	12	13	12
10	11	13	9.4	14	8.6	6.4	12	15	11	11	14	42
11	10	9.0	8.8	13	9.4	6.8	8.5	12	10	510	15	15
12	10	8.6	8.3	12	11	7.1	7.6	9.9	8.5	92	13	11
13	9.3	8.5	8.3	11	11	7.1	20	9.1	11	42	12	10
14	9.3	7.7	13	12	9.4	6.8	12	290	36	31	12	9.8
15	9.2	9.1	11	11	8.9	8.0	17	40	60	26	15	13
16	10	9.0	8.5	10	8.6	7.1	10	20	29	48	199	12
17	8.7	8.4	8.2	10	8.0	11	11	17	13	23	32	9.5
18	8.6	21	8.1	10	8.6	9.3	6.7	15	27	20	20	8.5
19	8.4	13	8.5	11	8.3	13	6.2	14	276	17	17	7.5
20	7.9	11	7.7	9.7	8.3	9.0	6.5	13	115	16	14	6.8
21	7.4	9.3	7.6	9.1	8.9	7.7	6.4	12	33	15	13	6.9
22	9.2	11	13	15	8.0	6.9	6.0	12	105	94	15	6.4
23	8.7	9.7	8.8	13	8.0	6.8	6.2	13	35	139	43	36
24	8.8	9.0	8.6	10	7.7	6.8	5.6	12	25	204	26	13
25	10	8.4	10	28	7.4	6.9	6.0	16	19	70	18	7.5
26	8.6	7.9	60	13	7.7	7.4	8.1	33	16	48	16	6.6
27	7.6	64	19	13	7.4	6.8	7.5	20	14	38	14	6.5
28	7.3	116	12	15	7.4	6.7	10	16	13	31	14	14
29	7.1	22	16	22	---	6.2	48	12	13	30	13	54
30	7.0	41	15	13	---	5.8	32	11	23	27	13	23
31	10	---	45	11	---	5.7	---	10	---	24	17	---
TOTAL	338.1	561.6	470.4	497.8	251.5	228.0	322.1	989.9	976.7	1693	708	435.0
MEAN	10.9	18.7	15.2	16.1	8.98	7.35	10.7	31.9	32.6	54.6	22.8	14.5
MAX	47	116	60	47	11	13	48	290	276	510	199	54
MIN	7.0	7.0	7.6	9.1	7.4	5.7	5.6	9.1	8.5	11	12	6.4
AC-FT	671	1110	933	987	499	452	639	1960	1940	3360	1400	863
CFSM	1.53	2.62	2.13	2.25	1.26	1.03	1.50	4.47	4.56	7.65	3.20	2.03
IN.	1.76	2.93	2.45	2.59	1.31	1.19	1.68	5.16	5.09	8.82	3.69	2.27

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1990	1991	1992	1993	1990	1991	1992	1993	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	23.3	25.1	17.7	21.7	12.6	9.83	8.21	20.5	27.8	27.5	19.3	19.7
MAX	48.2	37.9	23.1	47.5	18.1	11.6	10.7	31.9	48.9	54.6	22.8	28.1
(WY)	1991	1992	1991	1992	1991	1991	1993	1993	1992	1993	1993	1992
MIN	10.8	18.7	14.9	7.85	8.93	7.35	6.18	8.99	9.59	15.6	10.8	14.1
(WY)	1992	1991	1992	1990	1990	1993	1990	1990	1991	1992	1991	1990

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1993 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	8212.6	7472.1	
ANNUAL MEAN	22.4	20.5	20.9
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			24.0
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			18.1
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	605	Jan 5	605
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	5.1	Apr 29	4.1
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	5.5	Apr 24	4.4
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			3590
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			14.37
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			3.9
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-PT)	16290	14820	15110
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.14	2.87	2.92
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	42.79	38.93	39.68
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	38	34	32
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	12	11	11
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	7.3	7.0	6.0

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053025 RIO TURABO ABOVE BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1990 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: January 1990 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- DH-48 and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,030 mg/L July 11, 1993; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L Several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 4,920 tons (4,460 tonnes) Jan. 05, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 0.01 ton (0.01 tonne) Several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

Water Year	Suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		Suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1993	1,030 (July 11)	2 (Several days)	3,380 (July 11)	.04 (Several days)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	12	20	.67	8.1	12	.28	37	61	11
2	12	20	.62	7.4	12	.22	20	28	1.7
3	11	20	.57	7.0	12	.23	25	28	2.2
4	10	20	.54	21	26	2.3	17	14	.67
5	10	20	.57	11	8	.28	14	12	.42
6	47	296	96	49	76	20	12	11	.34
7	17	86	4.4	22	70	5.1	11	10	.29
8	13	24	.87	10	41	1.2	10	9	.23
9	12	12	.37	9.5	19	.47	9.6	8	.20
10	11	12	.34	13	15	.54	9.4	9	.22
11	10	14	.38	9.0	14	.32	8.8	10	.23
12	10	17	.43	8.6	12	.26	8.3	10	.22
13	9.3	18	.46	8.5	12	.25	8.3	10	.22
14	9.3	21	.52	7.7	12	.24	13	14	.70
15	9.2	24	.61	9.1	14	.32	11	14	.44
16	10	26	.63	9.0	17	.41	8.5	11	.24
17	8.7	26	.60	8.4	18	.40	8.2	10	.21
18	8.6	24	.55	21	35	4.0	8.1	8	.19
19	8.4	21	.48	13	14	.53	8.5	7	.16
20	7.9	17	.36	11	12	.34	7.7	5	.11
21	7.4	12	.24	9.3	16	.40	7.6	4	.08
22	9.2	9	.22	11	22	.62	13	17	.88
23	8.7	8	.22	9.7	23	.63	8.8	19	.47
24	8.8	9	.21	9.0	21	.49	8.6	17	.38
25	10	9	.28	8.4	20	.45	10	15	.40
26	8.6	13	.30	7.9	19	.39	60	128	66
27	7.6	18	.37	64	188	111	19	33	1.9
28	7.3	20	.38	116	246	384	12	29	.97
29	7.1	18	.33	22	25	1.8	16	28	1.2
30	7.0	13	.24	41	66	9.4	15	30	1.3
31	10	12	.43	---	---	---	45	73	14
TOTAL	338.1	---	113.19	561.6	---	546.87	470.4	---	107.57

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053025 RIO TURABO ABOVE BORINQUEN, PR---Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	47	73	12	10	5	.15	7.1	4	.08
2	34	37	4.5	11	3	.08	7.4	3	.06
3	22	23	1.4	11	2	.07	7.1	3	.06
4	17	17	.82	10	3	.08	7.4	2	.05
5	15	12	.48	9.9	3	.08	7.3	2	.04
6	16	8	.32	9.5	3	.09	6.8	2	.04
7	26	30	4.4	9.3	4	.11	6.6	2	.04
8	17	18	.93	9.2	5	.13	6.5	2	.04
9	18	11	.53	9.0	6	.14	6.5	2	.04
10	14	14	.54	8.6	6	.15	6.4	2	.04
11	13	9	.31	9.4	7	.17	6.8	2	.04
12	12	8	.28	11	6	.20	7.1	2	.04
13	11	8	.25	11	5	.17	7.1	2	.05
14	12	8	.25	9.4	4	.11	6.8	3	.06
15	11	8	.24	8.9	4	.11	8.0	3	.06
16	10	9	.24	8.6	4	.11	7.1	3	.06
17	10	10	.26	8.0	8	.17	11	3	.08
18	10	11	.31	8.6	8	.20	9.3	3	.08
19	11	10	.26	8.3	5	.12	13	3	.12
20	9.7	9	.23	8.3	3	.07	9.0	3	.07
21	9.1	7	.17	8.9	3	.08	7.7	3	.06
22	15	16	1.3	8.0	3	.07	6.9	3	.06
23	13	19	.74	8.0	4	.08	6.8	3	.07
24	10	16	.45	7.7	4	.08	6.8	4	.09
25	28	50	7.4	7.4	4	.08	6.9	5	.10
26	13	26	.97	7.7	4	.08	7.4	6	.12
27	13	17	.55	7.4	4	.08	6.8	7	.14
28	15	11	.40	7.4	4	.08	6.7	9	.15
29	22	25	1.7	---	---	---	6.2	8	.13
30	13	17	.66	---	---	---	5.8	7	.10
31	11	8	.26	---	---	---	5.7	6	.09
TOTAL	497.8	---	43.15	251.5	---	3.14	228.0	---	2.26

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053025 RIO TURABO ABOVE BORINQUEN, PR---Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	5.7	5	.09	126	445	400	11	6	.16
2	5.7	6	.10	116	279	197	10	6	.16
3	6.1	7	.12	39	55	8.0	9.3	6	.16
4	6.1	9	.15	17	16	.81	9.1	9	.22
5	5.7	11	.17	14	11	.43	8.7	8	.20
6	5.8	12	.17	12	10	.34	8.7	5	.12
7	5.7	7	.10	9.9	7	.20	8.7	5	.12
8	13	12	.80	12	11	.78	9.4	5	.12
9	15	19	1.7	22	29	2.0	9.3	5	.12
10	12	10	.51	15	15	.68	11	5	.14
11	8.5	6	.16	12	10	.33	10	5	.14
12	7.6	4	.09	9.9	7	.19	8.5	5	.12
13	20	25	4.6	9.1	8	.23	11	5	.16
14	12	10	.35	290	557	1340	36	52	11
15	17	18	1.9	40	52	7.0	60	112	57
16	10	10	.28	20	6	.38	29	38	5.1
17	11	15	.47	17	2	.09	13	11	.42
18	6.7	15	.26	15	2	.08	27	49	30
19	6.2	14	.23	14	2	.08	276	799	829
20	6.5	11	.20	13	2	.07	115	242	124
21	6.4	10	.16	12	2	.06	33	49	5.2
22	6.0	10	.16	12	2	.08	105	227	116
23	6.2	10	.16	13	4	.17	35	21	2.4
24	5.6	10	.15	12	6	.21	25	11	.73
25	6.0	8	.14	16	14	.70	19	8	.44
26	8.1	8	.19	33	52	15	16	8	.33
27	7.5	6	.12	20	23	1.6	14	12	.42
28	10	11	.56	16	13	.65	13	17	.58
29	48	103	62	12	6	.20	13	20	.84
30	32	44	11	11	6	.18	23	27	2.2
31	---	---	---	10	6	.17	---	---	---
TOTAL	322.1	---	87.09	989.9	---	1977.71	976.7	---	1187.60

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053025 RIO TURABO ABOVE BORINQUEN, PR---Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	12	10	.33	21	16	.84	14	7	.27
2	13	10	.33	19	17	.90	14	6	.23
3	32	43	6.5	17	16	.78	14	4	.18
4	16	19	.96	16	14	.58	12	4	.13
5	12	12	.38	15	13	.50	13	6	.19
6	11	10	.28	14	12	.45	12	11	.34
7	11	10	.31	14	13	.53	10	15	.40
8	18	20	1.2	14	13	.53	15	22	1.4
9	12	10	.33	13	10	.35	12	12	.45
10	11	9	.30	14	6	.23	42	65	17
11	510	1030	3380	15	4	.17	15	10	.46
12	92	23	7.2	13	4	.15	11	12	.35
13	42	13	1.6	12	4	.15	10	14	.38
14	31	8	.76	12	4	.12	9.8	13	.34
15	26	6	.43	15	11	.51	13	16	.89
16	48	77	23	199	593	632	12	11	.43
17	23	23	1.5	32	12	1.4	9.5	5	.12
18	20	17	.84	20	8	.46	8.5	5	.10
19	17	18	.80	17	12	.50	7.5	5	.10
20	16	19	.82	14	14	.52	6.8	5	.10
21	15	20	.81	13	15	.48	6.9	5	.09
22	94	283	329	15	17	.85	6.4	5	.08
23	139	384	220	43	77	19	36	74	41
24	204	365	309	26	34	3.3	13	10	.54
25	70	26	5.5	18	14	.65	7.5	5	.10
26	48	20	2.6	16	12	.52	6.6	5	.09
27	38	10	1.1	14	12	.42	6.5	5	.09
28	31	10	.87	14	11	.37	14	14	1.1
29	30	10	.80	13	10	.32	54	153	58
30	27	10	.73	13	10	.31	23	26	2.0
31	24	12	.75	17	9	.45	---	---	---
TOTAL	1693	---	4299.03	708	---	668.34	435.0	---	126.95
YEAR	7472.1		9162.90						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053025 RIO TURABO ABOVE BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR DECEMBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-	SEDI-	SEDI-	SED.	SED.	SED.
		CHARGE,		MENT,	MENT,	SUSP.	SUSP.
		INST.	MENT,	DIS-	FALL	FALL	FALL
		CUBIC	SUS-	CHARGE,	DIAM.	DIAM.	DIAM.
		FEET	SUS-	SUS-	PERCENT	PERCENT	PERCENT
		PER	PENDE	PENDE	FINER	FINER	FINER
		SECOND	(MG/L)	(T/DAY)	.002 MM	.004 MM	.008 MM
MAY 1993							
01...	1345	470	3690	4680	49	60	70
01...	1810	418	3790	4280	43	51	58
JUL							
11...	1312	1610	11500	50000	23	28	31

DATE	SED.						
	SUSP.						
	FALL	FALL	SIEVE	SIEVE	SIEVE	SIEVE	SIEVE
	DIAM.						
	PERCENT						
	FINER						
	THAN						
	.016 MM	.031 MM	.062 MM	.125 MM	.250 MM	.500 MM	1.00 MM
MAY 1993							
01...	81	89	97	99	99.7	99.9	100
01...	71	86	96	99	99.4	99.7	100
JUL							
11...	38	47	61	77	88	96	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
 50053025 RIO TURABO ABOVE BORINQUEN, PR--Continued
 WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1992					
06...	1605	265	14300	10230	32
06...	1955	60	935	154	98
NOV					
25...	1345	8.6	394	9.1	96
FEB 1993					
08...	1434	9.6	85	2.2	77
APR					
15...	1753	10	448	12	98
MAY					
01...	1325	530	2520	3610	95
JUN					
13...	1200	13	1150	40	98
JUL					
11...	0912	564	2230	3400	94
SEP					
24...	1540	10	391	11	99

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

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50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'33", long 66°00'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank 250 ft (76 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 189, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) downstream from Río Turabo, and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) east of Plaza de Caguas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--89.8 mi² (232.6 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1959 (low-flow measurement only), February to November 1959 (monthly measurements only), December 1959 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 143.28 ft (43.672 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Records good except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	93	98	559	518	99	60	e35	848	72	108	148	121
2	90	77	324	282	99	61	34	1150	72	104	139	111
3	84	113	284	232	115	57	38	343	64	189	130	136
4	82	238	232	196	92	52	35	149	59	156	120	103
5	80	156	188	166	87	53	32	111	57	100	120	130
6	362	208	163	180	84	52	33	186	54	86	117	184
7	235	238	147	232	84	50	33	121	51	95	110	107
8	108	117	133	222	80	49	33	90	54	183	115	101
9	94	98	126	176	79	48	70	343	64	105	107	166
10	91	216	121	157	75	52	70	252	77	85	115	265
11	90	104	115	137	78	49	49	124	86	6490	112	207
12	87	84	109	137	90	49	50	97	61	954	115	120
13	80	94	106	126	108	53	64	81	74	368	97	103
14	78	80	262	138	82	52	98	1880	451	264	93	105
15	77	148	205	120	74	52	277	323	363	215	96	94
16	78	124	117	114	71	e50	117	157	312	415	1780	181
17	78	189	109	111	73	e62	84	116	99	207	352	122
18	93	739	105	107	74	e61	57	104	111	169	177	328
19	94	286	103	115	69	e70	64	95	3730	151	145	157
20	88	174	98	99	70	e66	52	91	1600	139	127	128
21	174	160	100	92	71	e56	69	94	337	131	118	102
22	164	141	130	102	68	e46	51	86	563	1350	171	91
23	88	158	113	157	66	e44	49	84	263	1710	383	632
24	91	153	103	101	69	e47	55	88	199	1190	219	356
25	204	134	112	175	64	e48	45	86	146	464	149	152
26	139	115	1070	125	64	e54	52	179	126	310	132	120
27	86	446	286	116	66	e50	101	154	111	344	126	98
28	79	2200	153	144	60	e43	66	158	103	217	112	103
29	79	410	323	350	---	e39	388	92	103	185	103	316
30	86	1970	258	146	---	e37	308	77	160	167	101	393
31	77	---	476	113	---	e36	---	72	---	157	116	---
TOTAL	3429	9468	6730	5186	2211	1598	2509	7831	9622	16808	6045	5332
MEAN	111	316	217	167	79.0	51.5	83.6	253	321	542	195	178
MAX	362	2200	1070	518	115	70	388	1880	3730	6490	1780	632
MIN	77	77	98	92	60	36	32	72	51	85	93	91
AC-FT	6800	18780	13350	10290	4390	3170	4980	15530	19090	33340	11990	10580
CFSM	1.23	3.51	2.42	1.86	.88	.57	.93	2.81	3.57	6.04	2.17	1.98
IN.	1.42	3.92	2.79	2.15	.92	.66	1.04	3.24	3.99	6.96	2.50	2.21

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1960 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1960	1961	1962	1963	1964	1965	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993		
MEAN	379	316	232	149	110	89.8	84.7	254	262	233	257	256	1910	1131	714	559	291	306	226	863	1283	660	949	764	1971	1988	1988	1992	1984	1989	1985	1985	1979	1961	1979	1979
MAX (WY)	1971	1988	1988	1992	1984	1989	1985	1985	1979	1961	1979	1979	1971	1988	1988	1992	1984	1989	1985	1985	1979	1961	1979	1979	1971	1988	1988	1992	1984	1989	1985	1985	1979	1961	1979	1979
MIN (WY)	44.2	64.9	33.6	45.3	35.6	23.2	38.0	33.7	34.1	21.8	53.6	37.4	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1974	1975	1974	1967	1967	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1960 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	80283	76769	
ANNUAL MEAN	219	210	219
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			526
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			82.3
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	7930	Jan 5	6490 Jul 11
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	30	Apr 28	32 Apr 5
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	34	Apr 24	34 Apr 2
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			28400 Jul 11
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			20.49 Jul 11
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			29 Apr 8
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	159200	152300	158900
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.44	2.34	2.44
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	33.26	31.80	33.18
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	323	343	364
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	98	110	106
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	48	53	40

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1959 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1983 to September 1989.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USD-49 and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 14,500 mg/L Nov. 27, 1987; Minimum daily mean, 8 mg/L Jan. 23, 1992.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 227,000 tons (205,890 tonnes) Nov. 27, 1987; Minimum daily mean, 1.3 tons (1.2) July 14, 1985.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,660 mg/L July 11, 1993; minimum daily mean, 8 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 64,100 tons (58,200 tonnes) July 11, 1993; minimum daily 1.9 ton (1.7 tonnes) Oct. 05, 1992.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
09...	1115	93	254	7.5	28.0	12	6.9	87	<10	32000	K1500
DEC											
14...	1245	110	248	7.6	25.6	27	7.9	92	18	K6900	600
FEB 1993											
24...	1310	69	198	7.7	25.4	53	7.7	91	41	5300	250
APR											
16...	1215	100	263	6.6	24.5	300	4.4	52	20	K69000	44000
JUN											
17...	1530	97	254	6.9	29.9	24	6.8	84	20	K7400	4000
AUG											
12...	1310	97	220	7.1	30.1	20	5.5	76	<10	52000	240

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT PLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1992											
09...	75	0	19	6.7	21	1	2.3	82	<0.5	13	17
DEC											
14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	67	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	84	--	--	--
APR											
16...	70	1	17	6.6	18	0.9	2.8	57	<0.5	16	16
JUN											
17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	75	--	--	--
AUG											
12...	67	0	17	5.9	19	1	2.0	58	--	11	17

K = non-ideal count

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
09...	0.10	33	161	40.3	8	0.350	0.040	0.390	0.160	0.44
DEC										
14...	--	--	--	--	16	0.370	0.030	0.400	0.070	0.33
FEB 1993										
24...	--	--	--	--	73	0.450	0.050	0.500	0.140	0.46
APR										
16...	<0.10	22	133	35.8	502	0.600	0.100	0.700	0.410	0.59
JUN										
17...	--	--	--	--	36	0.260	0.040	0.300	0.130	0.37
AUG										
12...	0.10	33	150	39.3	25	0.330	0.070	0.400	0.140	0.36

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	93	27	6.8	98	66	18	559	254	564
2	90	20	4.8	77	52	11	324	155	146
3	84	14	3.2	113	60	23	284	131	109
4	82	11	2.4	238	124	90	232	103	65
5	80	9	1.9	156	90	43	188	30	16
6	362	202	621	208	140	108	163	18	8.0
7	235	139	114	238	127	92	147	17	7.3
8	108	82	25	117	75	26	133	17	6.3
9	94	48	12	98	62	17	126	15	5.1
10	91	43	11	216	141	92	121	13	4.2
11	90	37	9.0	104	141	40	115	11	3.4
12	87	32	7.6	84	73	17	109	10	2.9
13	80	26	5.7	94	35	8.8	106	10	2.7
14	78	21	4.5	80	24	5.3	262	76	244
15	77	21	4.4	148	73	56	205	79	63
16	78	25	5.1	124	150	52	117	18	5.7
17	78	29	5.9	189	113	78	109	18	5.1
18	93	46	13	739	460	1970	105	27	7.4
19	94	89	23	286	145	132	103	35	9.8
20	88	82	19	174	107	52	98	52	14
21	174	106	87	160	62	26	100	69	18
22	164	94	53	141	42	16	130	85	30
23	88	48	11	158	35	15	113	100	30
24	91	49	16	153	49	23	103	99	28
25	204	109	71	134	55	21	112	83	25
26	139	87	35	115	24	7.6	1070	502	3810
27	86	47	11	446	190	556	286	157	143
28	79	33	6.9	2200	910	11800	153	89	38
29	79	33	7.1	410	187	226	323	165	160
30	86	35	8.0	1970	793	8920	258	155	110
31	77	39	8.2	---	---	---	476	228	404
TOTAL	3429	---	1213.5	9468	---	24541.7	6730	---	6084.9

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	518	232	335	99	80	22	60	46	7.5
2	282	93	79	99	77	22	61	54	8.7
3	232	60	41	115	74	24	57	61	9.1
4	196	74	39	92	72	19	52	64	9.0
5	166	38	17	87	71	16	53	64	9.0
6	180	17	8.6	84	70	16	52	63	8.8
7	232	61	45	84	69	15	50	60	8.0
8	222	95	62	80	67	15	49	51	6.7
9	176	67	33	79	65	14	48	49	6.4
10	157	86	36	75	58	12	52	44	6.1
11	137	72	27	78	44	9.4	49	43	5.6
12	137	62	23	90	30	7.2	49	43	5.4
13	126	56	20	108	23	6.3	53	43	5.9
14	138	67	26	82	29	6.4	52	46	6.5
15	120	37	12	74	44	8.9	52	48	6.7
16	114	13	4.1	71	54	11	e50	53	e7.1
17	111	16	4.7	73	57	11	e62	75	e12
18	107	20	5.8	74	57	11	e61	95	e15
19	115	24	7.4	69	59	11	e70	92	e17
20	99	26	7.0	70	71	14	e66	77	e15
21	92	25	6.3	71	92	18	e56	57	e8.6
22	102	24	6.6	68	112	21	e46	41	e5.3
23	157	40	20	66	132	24	e44	32	e3.8
24	101	19	5.2	69	131	24	e47	28	e3.5
25	175	80	59	64	86	15	e48	29	e3.8
26	125	156	54	64	55	9.3	e54	30	e4.2
27	116	148	45	66	36	6.3	e50	31	e4.1
28	144	140	54	60	38	6.1	e43	31	e3.6
29	350	383	428	---	---	---	e39	32	e3.4
30	146	221	92	---	---	---	e37	33	e3.5
31	113	103	32	---	---	---	e36	33	e3.1
TOTAL	5186	---	1634.7	2211	---	394.9	1598	---	222.4

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
				MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	e35	34	e3.0	848	417	2130	72	15	2.9			
2	34	45	4.0	1150	503	3300	72	14	2.7			
3	38	50	4.9	343	171	191	64	14	2.3			
4	35	49	4.6	149	60	25	59	17	2.7			
5	32	46	4.0	111	39	12	57	25	3.8			
6	33	43	3.7	186	100	54	54	38	5.6			
7	33	42	3.8	121	73	26	51	58	8.0			
8	33	54	4.7	90	58	14	54	83	12			
9	70	53	10	343	246	303	64	98	17			
10	70	43	8.2	252	133	106	77	101	21			
11	49	39	5.2	124	79	27	86	98	23			
12	50	37	5.1	97	66	18	61	71	12			
13	64	47	11	81	54	12	74	56	13			
14	98	108	30	1880	1020	12500	451	205	411			
15	277	136	265	323	106	118	363	170	256			
16	117	114	38	157	62	27	312	192	269			
17	84	102	24	116	60	19	99	45	12			
18	57	94	15	104	55	15	111	78	50			
19	64	85	15	95	51	13	3730	1470	16400			
20	52	75	11	91	48	12	1600	652	4390			
21	69	98	18	94	44	11	337	179	169			
22	51	81	11	86	42	9.6	563	209	370			
23	49	44	5.6	84	41	9.3	263	133	97			
24	55	33	5.0	88	39	9.3	199	114	62			
25	45	30	3.6	86	37	8.9	146	83	34			
26	52	37	5.7	179	78	47	126	52	18			
27	101	60	17	154	90	40	111	28	8.5			
28	66	44	8.0	158	86	42	103	14	3.8			
29	388	229	848	92	36	8.9	103	21	6.4			
30	308	156	160	77	22	4.5	160	82	37			
31	---	---	---	72	17	3.2	---	---	---			
TOTAL	2509	---	1552.1	7831	---	19115.7	9622	---	22719.7			

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	108	44	13	148	46	18	121	46	15
2	104	33	9.4	139	30	11	111	111	35
3	189	74	47	130	16	5.8	136	194	68
4	156	69	33	120	11	3.4	103	142	41
5	100	23	6.3	120	9	2.9	130	95	38
6	86	14	3.2	117	9	2.8	184	102	63
7	95	62	20	110	8	2.6	107	61	18
8	183	100	51	115	8	2.6	101	45	13
9	105	66	19	107	10	2.7	166	87	43
10	85	56	13	115	10	3.1	265	133	120
11	6490	1660	64100	112	10	3.2	207	144	85
12	954	433	1350	115	11	3.4	120	88	29
13	368	169	174	97	13	3.3	103	52	15
14	264	59	46	93	13	3.1	105	30	8.8
15	215	12	7.0	96	25	7.1	94	15	4.0
16	415	154	278	1780	759	5310	181	82	44
17	207	123	69	352	217	246	122	71	24
18	169	77	35	177	51	27	328	280	907
19	151	45	18	145	20	8.0	157	81	38
20	139	24	9.0	127	17	5.9	128	53	18
21	131	11	3.9	118	13	4.2	102	31	8.6
22	1350	423	4960	171	64	37	91	18	4.4
23	1710	728	4120	383	622	689	632	241	1940
24	1190	759	2430	219	581	352	356	178	278
25	464	214	285	149	442	178	152	94	43
26	310	156	133	132	333	118	120	73	25
27	344	173	169	126	242	84	98	60	16
28	217	100	60	112	169	51	103	51	14
29	185	73	36	103	111	32	316	141	232
30	167	70	31	101	66	18	393	191	253
31	157	66	28	116	36	11	---	---	---
TOTAL	16808	---	78556.8	6045	---	7246.1	5332	---	4440.8
YEAR	76769		167723.3						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
DEC 1992							
26...	1911	1630	5830	25700	49	58	66
MAY 1993							
14...	0937	3740	3480	35100	44	54	63
JUN							
19...	0336	3470	2510	23500	44	44	62
JUL							
07...	1244	11500	2270	70500	43	52	59
23...	0032	1560	3270	13800	39	43	52
AUG							
16...	1125	4130	2520	28100	44	50	62

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
DEC 1992							
26...	77	88	95	98	99	100	100
MAY 1993							
14...	77	83	92	93	93	100	100
JUN							
19...	74	86	96	99	99.7	100	100
JUL							
11...	72	82	96	99	99.6	99.8	100
23...	69	84	89	--	99.1	99.4	99.6
AUG							
16...	73	81	96	98	99	99.5	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1992					
06...	1649	1550	1520	6360	99
NOV					
18...	1651	2430	1650	10820	99
18...	1742	2200	1540	9150	96
DEC					
01...	1615	1610	387	1680	99
26...	1637	4570	2170	26770	96
FEB 1993					
06...	1115	82	385	85	99
MAY					
01...	0710	236	838	534	100
01...	2220	1550	2200	9210	36
14...	1452	2840	1660	12730	97
JUN					
14...	1234	990	3180	8500	95
15...	2320	1530	625	2580	98
19...	0036	2650	341	2440	98
19...	0910	3860	1930	20110	77
JUL					
11...	1031	8770	1310	31020	98
11...	1256	12310	1440	47860	96
22...	1850	5540	748	11190	86
22...	2145	3970	1710	18330	96
24...	0850	2040	442	2430	95
AUG					
16...	0955	5060	3290	44950	24
16...	1811	1660	1140	5110	90

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055100 RIO CAGUITAS NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'48", long 66°05'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank 450 ft (137 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 777, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) southeast from Aguas Buenas, 3.9 mi (6.3 km) northwest from Caguas, and 2.1 mi (3.4 km) southwest from Las Carolinas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--5.30 mi² (13.72 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 394 ft (120 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.9	5.9	15	10	6.5	5.2	4.4	29	8.2	6.9	9.8	7.1
2	5.8	5.7	9.9	9.5	6.5	5.3	4.5	35	8.0	7.3	10	7.0
3	5.7	7.7	8.5	9.7	7.0	5.0	4.5	17	7.8	12	10	6.9
4	5.5	15	8.0	10	6.5	5.1	4.4	11	7.5	8.1	10	7.6
5	5.8	8.8	7.4	9.3	6.5	5.3	4.4	9.6	7.3	7.0	10	8.5
6	e23	6.6	7.1	8.9	6.4	5.4	4.4	22	7.1	6.7	10	13
7	e8.4	6.0	6.9	29	6.4	5.4	4.4	12	7.0	7.1	10	7.7
8	7.0	5.6	6.8	14	6.3	5.3	7.8	9.8	7.7	7.1	11	7.0
9	6.5	5.7	6.8	10	6.2	5.3	8.3	40	7.5	6.2	11	6.9
10	7.1	7.8	6.8	9.1	6.5	5.2	6.6	17	7.4	6.3	10	7.3
11	6.5	5.7	6.6	8.4	6.1	5.2	9.1	12	6.8	146	10	7.1
12	6.1	5.3	6.3	8.1	6.5	5.2	11	11	6.4	21	10	6.9
13	5.9	5.2	6.3	7.8	6.4	5.1	24	9.7	6.3	27	10	6.8
14	5.7	5.1	7.0	7.5	6.1	5.0	12	133	6.4	15	10	6.8
15	5.6	5.2	7.7	7.4	6.0	5.0	132	17	6.4	17	12	7.1
16	5.5	4.8	6.4	7.1	e7.4	5.8	16	10	6.4	12	61	9.2
17	5.6	8.1	6.2	7.2	6.9	5.6	8.3	9.0	6.1	9.9	13	7.2
18	7.7	19	6.1	7.1	6.5	5.4	6.9	8.2	6.1	9.5	9.7	92
19	6.5	8.1	6.1	6.9	6.4	6.0	6.2	7.7	21	9.3	8.9	12
20	7.1	6.3	6.0	6.8	6.5	5.2	19	7.5	18	9.2	8.2	15
21	6.0	5.7	6.0	6.6	6.1	4.9	12	7.2	7.8	9.0	8.2	8.5
22	6.4	13	7.4	14	5.7	4.9	9.2	7.1	7.7	35	11	7.6
23	8.0	7.9	6.4	11	5.5	5.5	7.5	19	6.9	48	11	11
24	6.6	6.8	7.1	7.7	5.4	5.2	6.9	9.1	6.6	50	8.5	8.0
25	6.2	6.1	18	7.6	5.3	5.0	6.6	9.9	6.7	17	8.2	7.4
26	5.8	5.7	149	7.2	5.4	4.9	6.6	28	6.8	13	8.0	7.6
27	5.7	51	17	7.1	5.3	4.8	8.0	13	6.9	12	7.7	7.3
28	5.6	46	11	7.1	5.1	4.7	10	10	8.5	11	7.6	10
29	5.9	13	21	7.6	---	4.6	17	8.8	7.2	10	7.5	13
30	5.6	65	13	6.7	---	4.5	12	8.7	11	10	7.5	8.4
31	6.1	---	12	6.6	---	4.5	---	8.3	---	9.5	7.3	---
TOTAL	210.8	367.8	415.8	283.0	173.4	159.5	394.0	556.6	241.5	575.1	347.1	337.9
MEAN	6.80	12.3	13.4	9.13	6.19	5.15	13.1	18.0	8.05	18.6	11.2	11.3
MAX	23	65	149	29	7.4	6.0	132	133	21	146	61	92
MIN	5.5	4.8	6.0	6.6	5.1	4.5	4.4	7.1	6.1	6.2	7.3	6.8
AC-FT	418	730	825	561	344	316	781	1100	479	1140	688	670
CFSM	1.28	2.31	2.53	1.72	1.17	.97	2.48	3.39	1.52	3.50	2.11	2.13
IN.	1.48	2.58	2.92	1.99	1.22	1.12	2.77	3.91	1.70	4.04	2.44	2.37

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1990	1991	1992	1993	1990	1991	1992	1993	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	11.0	8.49	9.43	11.0	5.48	6.00	6.41	7.91	4.86	8.41	7.05	7.23
MAX	20.9	12.3	13.4	16.7	8.00	8.87	13.1	18.0	8.05	18.6	11.2	11.3
(WY)	1991	1993	1993	1992	1991	1990	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993
MIN	5.30	5.76	5.59	7.19	3.51	3.60	3.19	2.48	3.40	3.74	5.14	5.01
(WY)	1992	1991	1992	1991	1990	1992	1992	1990	1991	1990	1991	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1990 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	2711.4	4062.5	
ANNUAL MEAN	7.41	11.1	8.26
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			11.1
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			6.22
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	235	Jan 5	235
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	2.4	May 10	1.8
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	2.6	Apr 24	1.9
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			2990
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			18.28
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			4.3
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	5380	8060	5980
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.40	2.10	1.56
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	19.03	28.51	21.17
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	8.7	16	11
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.3	7.3	5.1
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	2.9	5.3	3.0

e Estimated

50055100 RIO CAGUITAS NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1990 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: February 1990 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- DH-48 and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,690 mg/L July 11, 1993; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L Several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 3,730 tons (3,360 tonnes) Jan. 05, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 0.02 ton (0.03 tonne) Several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

Water Year	Suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		Suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1993	1,690 (July 11)	2 (Aug. 29)	1,890 (Apr. 15)	.05 (Aug. 29)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
				MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	5.9	12	.18	5.9	53	.86	15	212	11			
2	5.8	13	.20	5.7	53	.81	9.9	49	1.4			
3	5.7	14	.20	7.7	65	1.5	8.5	38	.86			
4	5.5	15	.22	15	151	8.7	8.0	36	.80			
5	5.8	15	.24	8.8	63	1.5	7.4	37	.74			
6	e23	327	e78	6.6	30	.55	7.1	35	.65			
7	e8.4	176	e4.1	6.0	29	.46	6.9	27	.50			
8	7.0	93	1.9	5.6	27	.40	6.8	20	.36			
9	6.5	33	.59	5.7	21	.31	6.8	16	.30			
10	7.1	27	.51	7.8	57	1.4	6.8	15	.27			
11	6.5	55	1.0	5.7	20	.30	6.6	14	.24			
12	6.1	37	.59	5.3	18	.26	6.3	13	.22			
13	5.9	26	.42	5.2	17	.25	6.3	14	.24			
14	5.7	22	.34	5.1	16	.22	7.0	27	.65			
15	5.6	20	.29	5.2	23	.32	7.7	28	.77			
16	5.5	18	.26	4.8	22	.30	6.4	12	.21			
17	5.6	17	.27	8.1	44	1.1	6.2	12	.20			
18	7.7	34	.97	19	335	43	6.1	12	.19			
19	6.5	32	.59	8.1	174	4.5	6.1	10	.16			
20	7.1	45	.96	6.3	50	.85	6.0	9	.15			
21	6.0	27	.43	5.7	46	.70	6.0	6	.11			
22	6.4	20	.34	13	155	12	7.4	38	.84			
23	8.0	46	1.8	7.9	51	1.1	6.4	49	.83			
24	6.6	30	.55	6.8	42	.75	7.1	44	.88			
25	6.2	28	.45	6.1	28	.45	18	274	36			
26	5.8	25	.38	5.7	19	.29	149	1270	1770			
27	5.7	21	.32	51	755	304	17	158	9.0			
28	5.6	15	.22	46	743	228	11	54	1.6			
29	5.9	11	.18	13	95	4.0	21	341	41			
30	5.6	10	.15	65	814	441	13	97	4.0			
31	6.1	26	.46	---	---	---	12	46	1.5			
TOTAL	210.8	---	97.11	367.8	---	1059.88	415.8	---	1885.67			

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055100 RIO CAGUITAS NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	10	25	.71	6.5	20	.33	5.2	6	.08
2	9.5	14	.35	6.5	20	.33	5.3	6	.09
3	9.7	23	.75	7.0	17	.31	5.0	8	.12
4	10	72	2.1	6.5	13	.23	5.1	14	.20
5	9.3	37	.99	6.5	10	.17	5.3	14	.20
6	8.9	46	1.1	6.4	7	.13	5.4	8	.11
7	29	714	153	6.4	7	.12	5.4	6	.08
8	14	113	4.8	6.3	6	.11	5.3	6	.09
9	10	40	1.2	6.2	5	.09	5.3	7	.11
10	9.1	17	.41	6.5	19	.38	5.2	8	.12
11	8.4	17	.39	6.1	18	.29	5.2	8	.11
12	8.1	17	.36	6.5	16	.28	5.2	6	.09
13	7.8	16	.33	6.4	20	.34	5.1	5	.07
14	7.5	13	.26	6.1	23	.37	5.0	5	.07
15	7.4	8	.17	6.0	24	.38	5.0	6	.08
16	7.1	8	.16	e7.4	19	e.37	5.8	7	.11
17	7.2	10	.20	6.9	16	.29	5.6	6	.10
18	7.1	12	.23	6.5	13	.23	5.4	6	.09
19	6.9	15	.28	6.4	10	.17	6.0	54	.97
20	6.8	18	.33	6.5	8	.14	5.2	33	.45
21	6.6	20	.35	6.1	8	.14	4.9	34	.44
22	14	152	13	5.7	10	.15	4.9	33	.41
23	11	116	4.2	5.5	12	.17	5.5	28	.37
24	7.7	27	.57	5.4	12	.17	5.2	19	.28
25	7.6	18	.37	5.3	11	.16	5.0	16	.21
26	7.2	19	.36	5.4	11	.15	4.9	13	.16
27	7.1	19	.35	5.3	9	.13	4.8	10	.12
28	7.1	18	.33	5.1	7	.10	4.7	8	.10
29	7.6	16	.33	---	---	---	4.6	12	.15
30	6.7	17	.31	---	---	---	4.5	27	.33
31	6.6	19	.32	---	---	---	4.5	27	.33
TOTAL	283.0	---	188.61	173.4	---	6.23	159.5	---	6.24

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055100 RIO CAGUITAS NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	4.4	30	.36	29	673	89	8.2	8	.18
2	4.5	30	.36	35	615	104	8.0	10	.21
3	4.5	30	.36	17	139	7.5	7.8	10	.21
4	4.4	30	.36	11	48	1.5	7.5	11	.22
5	4.4	30	.36	9.6	20	.51	7.3	17	.33
6	4.4	30	.36	22	429	65	7.1	25	.48
7	4.4	30	.36	12	83	3.0	7.0	30	.55
8	7.8	52	1.9	9.8	55	1.5	7.7	27	.54
9	8.3	55	1.7	40	626	120	7.5	21	.41
10	6.6	33	.61	17	162	8.5	7.4	16	.31
11	9.1	56	2.2	12	86	2.9	6.8	13	.23
12	11	181	7.3	11	59	1.7	6.4	11	.19
13	24	516	87	9.7	51	1.3	6.3	13	.21
14	12	470	15	133	1440	1450	6.4	21	.36
15	132	1400	1890	17	129	7.0	6.4	29	.51
16	16	181	11	10	25	.76	6.4	26	.46
17	8.3	67	1.5	9.0	5	.14	6.1	22	.35
18	6.9	79	1.5	8.2	4	.09	6.1	22	.36
19	6.2	70	1.2	7.7	5	.11	21	281	26
20	19	279	43	7.5	15	.30	18	170	18
21	12	96	3.9	7.2	31	.60	7.8	13	.28
22	9.2	63	1.7	7.1	34	.65	7.7	11	.22
23	7.5	47	.96	19	262	43	6.9	10	.19
24	6.9	35	.65	9.1	53	1.3	6.6	10	.18
25	6.6	27	.48	9.9	52	1.4	6.7	11	.20
26	6.6	26	.47	28	404	104	6.8	12	.22
27	8.0	33	.82	13	81	3.2	6.9	12	.22
28	10	61	3.4	10	16	.48	8.5	33	1.1
29	17	470	46	8.8	3	.07	7.2	33	.67
30	12	87	3.0	8.7	3	.07	11	108	4.8
31	---	---	---	8.3	5	.13	---	---	---
TOTAL	394.0	---	2127.81	556.6	---	2019.71	241.5	---	58.19

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055100 RIO CAGUITAS NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	6.9	27	.51	9.8	11	.28	7.1	11	.20
2	7.3	68	1.9	10	10	.25	7.0	12	.21
3	12	113	6.2	10	9	.24	6.9	12	.22
4	8.1	32	.74	10	8	.23	7.6	40	.95
5	7.0	15	.27	10	8	.22	8.5	49	2.0
6	6.7	9	.16	10	8	.22	13	152	14
7	7.1	29	.67	10	8	.22	7.7	143	3.2
8	7.1	37	.71	11	7	.21	7.0	102	1.9
9	6.2	30	.50	11	6	.17	6.9	75	1.4
10	6.3	28	.50	10	4	.11	7.3	54	1.0
11	146	1690	1290	10	3	.08	7.1	36	.73
12	21	329	27	10	3	.08	6.9	23	.43
13	27	788	76	10	3	.08	6.8	13	.24
14	15	151	7.5	10	3	.08	6.8	7	.14
15	17	108	13	12	3	.10	7.1	10	.25
16	12	30	.98	61	797	197	9.2	66	2.1
17	9.9	26	.69	13	82	3.3	7.2	30	.57
18	9.5	22	.55	9.7	23	.58	92	661	1080
19	9.3	21	.53	8.9	25	.57	12	104	4.0
20	9.2	21	.51	8.2	25	.56	15	449	67
21	9.0	16	.38	8.2	23	.50	8.5	40	.98
22	35	602	176	11	56	2.2	7.6	20	.42
23	48	626	119	11	72	2.3	11	55	4.7
24	50	662	197	8.5	27	.64	8.0	40	.92
25	17	26	1.3	8.2	8	.17	7.4	32	.64
26	13	18	.66	8.0	6	.14	7.6	32	.65
27	12	15	.47	7.7	6	.14	7.3	30	.60
28	11	14	.42	7.6	4	.08	10	75	3.5
29	10	14	.39	7.5	2	.05	13	160	9.1
30	10	15	.38	7.5	4	.08	8.4	42	1.0
31	9.5	14	.34	7.3	8	.16	---	---	---
TOTAL	575.1	---	1925.26	347.1	---	211.04	337.9	---	1203.05
YEAR	4062.5		10788.80						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055100 RIO CAGUITAS NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
APR 1993							
15...	1920	109	3760	1110	53	59	66
29...	1800	28	13000	970	26	31	35
MAY							
01...	1720	81	3170	693	53	63	67
06...	1900	65	2930	514	57	68	69
26...	1453	213	4480	2580	30	38	45
JUL							
22...	1845	176	4020	1910	43	51	58

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
APR 1993							
15...	75	82	94	98	99	99.8	100
29...	42	56	75	90	97	99.4	99.8
MAY							
01...	76	82	93	96	98	99	100
06...	82	83	98	99	99.6	100	100
26...	55	66	78	88	96	99	99.8
JUL							
22...	70	78	94	99	98.8	99.5	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055100 RIO CAGUITAS NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1992					
16...	1205	5.5	308	4.6	98
NOV					
25...	1455	6.1	145	2.4	99
DEC					
01...	1942	22	3820	227	94
JAN 1993					
07...	1832	83	2970	666	97
APR					
12...	1755	13	651	23	93
29...	2125	22	1510	90	96
30...	1140	11	161	4.8	81
MAY					
01...	1555	56	2400	363	86
06...	1745	12	2590	84	92
26...	1625	84	1660	376	95
JUL					
13...	2305	27	728	53	97
22...	2300	26	1050	74	98
SEP					
29...	1015	9.9	419	11	97

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055170 RIO CAGUITAS NEAR CAGUAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°13'59", long 66°02'53", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) southwest from Plaza de Caguas, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) northeast from Escuela Bunker, and 1.2 mi (1.9 km) northwest from Escuela Antonio S. Pedreira.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.27 mi² (21.42 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1992 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 216 ft (66 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1									e7.0	e5.1	e5.0	4.8
2									e6.6	e5.6	e5.2	4.5
3									e6.6	e5.2	e5.8	5.1
4									e6.4	e5.6	e8.0	5.4
5									e7.0	e5.6	e25	17
6									e6.2	e6.4	e120	13
7									e6.0	e5.4	e16	8.5
8									e8.6	e5.4	e8.2	7.5
9									e8.0	e6.4	e7.0	21
10									e15	e5.8	e6.2	6.5
11									9.5	e5.4	e5.8	5.4
12									13	e6.8	e6.0	4.9
13								e16	14	e5.4	e6.2	4.8
14								7.5	7.9	e5.0	e5.6	5.3
15								6.4	7.1	e4.9	e6.0	6.8
16								9.3	11	e5.4	e5.4	13
17								38	6.1	e7.4	e5.0	11
18								13	6.1	e11	e4.9	7.8
19								6.2	5.3	e7.2	e4.8	131
20								9.8	4.5	e6.0	e4.6	111
21								8.3	6.7	e5.6	e4.6	75
22								12	5.6	e7.8	e4.6	117
23								88	4.8	e11	e4.7	48
24								143	5.0	e6.8	e5.0	17
25								44	e5.4	e8.0	e4.8	12
26								25	e5.4	e10	e4.5	9.5
27								14	e5.2	e6.8	5.0	8.8
28								e10	e5.6	e6.8	5.0	8.4
29								e8.2	e5.8	e5.4	5.0	7.8
30								e7.6	e5.8	e4.8	5.2	8.0
31								e7.2	---	e5.0	6.6	---
TOTAL								---	217.2	199.0	315.7	705.8
MEAN								---	7.24	6.42	10.2	23.5
MAX								---	15	11	120	131
MIN								---	4.5	4.8	4.5	4.5
AC-FT								---	431	395	626	1400
CFSM								---	.88	.78	1.23	2.84
IN.								---	.98	.90	1.42	3.17

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1992, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	---	7.24	6.42	10.2	23.5
MAX	---	7.24	6.42	10.2	23.5
(WY)	---	1992	1992	1992	1992
MIN	---	7.24	6.42	10.2	23.5
(WY)	---	1992	1992	1992	1992

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055170 RIO CAGUITAS NEAR CAGUAS, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	9.0	8.3	57	22	11	7.8	5.6	94	11	11	16	11
2	8.5	6.6	27	20	11	7.6	5.5	130	11	11	15	11
3	8.1	32	17	18	13	6.9	5.9	43	10	15	15	11
4	7.9	51	16	18	10	6.8	5.8	20	9.9	11	15	13
5	6.8	23	12	18	10	6.6	6.1	18	9.9	9.5	15	17
6	106	11	12	16	9.7	6.0	6.2	68	9.0	9.2	14	22
7	44	8.5	9.9	106	9.7	6.4	6.3	31	8.9	14	14	14
8	14	7.5	9.3	44	9.5	6.5	11	18	9.9	11	14	12
9	11	7.8	9.1	21	9.3	6.7	18	111	9.7	8.8	13	11
10	26	32	8.8	19	9.1	6.3	13	41	10	8.4	14	11
11	14	8.4	8.6	18	9.4	5.8	12	22	9.8	447	14	11
12	8.9	6.8	8.0	17	9.4	5.4	18	18	9.7	56	13	9.2
13	7.3	6.4	7.7	16	9.8	5.9	43	16	9.8	67	13	10
14	6.7	5.9	37	15	8.6	6.0	17	307	12	32	13	9.9
15	6.6	6.1	20	14	8.5	5.6	251	32	13	31	15	11
16	6.0	6.2	9.5	14	12	6.3	53	18	11	22	168	15
17	6.0	42	9.3	13	12	6.7	19	15	9.5	16	24	11
18	e28	88	8.5	13	8.8	6.5	14	13	11	15	16	204
19	e12	25	8.2	13	8.4	6.4	12	13	80	17	14	25
20	e8.3	11	8.1	12	8.2	6.1	50	13	57	16	13	20
21	e7.0	9.0	7.5	12	8.6	5.5	25	12	16	16	13	11
22	7.6	23	17	27	8.5	5.6	19	12	16	111	36	9.5
23	7.3	15	9.5	37	8.3	6.1	13	49	12	163	24	16
24	9.3	9.9	11	14	7.4	6.6	13	16	11	139	15	13
25	7.5	8.0	40	13	6.9	6.2	12	14	11	38	14	9.4
26	6.2	7.5	401	13	7.0	6.4	16	57	10	25	13	11
27	5.9	147	103	12	6.7	6.2	25	22	9.8	21	13	9.4
28	5.4	239	32	12	6.7	5.7	21	16	12	18	12	20
29	6.7	44	115	12	---	6.0	86	13	12	17	13	27
30	6.1	227	52	11	---	5.9	33	13	15	17	12	14
31	5.7	---	56	11	---	5.6	---	12	---	17	12	---
TOTAL	419.8	1122.9	1147.0	621	257.5	194.1	835.4	1277	446.9	1409.9	625	599.4
MEAN	13.5	37.4	37.0	20.0	9.20	6.26	27.8	41.2	14.9	45.5	20.2	20.0
MAX	106	239	401	106	13	7.8	251	307	80	447	168	204
MIN	5.4	5.9	7.5	11	6.7	5.4	5.5	12	8.9	8.4	12	9.2
AC-FT	833	2230	2280	1230	511	385	1660	2530	886	2800	1240	1190
CFSM	1.64	4.53	4.47	2.42	1.11	.76	3.37	4.98	1.80	5.50	2.44	2.42
IN.	1.89	5.05	5.16	2.79	1.16	.87	3.76	5.74	2.01	6.34	2.81	2.70

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1992	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992	1992	1992	1993
MEAN	13.5	37.4	37.0	20.0	9.20	6.26	27.8	41.2	11.1	25.9	15.2	21.8
MAX	13.5	37.4	37.0	20.0	9.20	6.26	27.8	41.2	14.9	45.5	20.2	23.5
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992
MIN	13.5	37.4	37.0	20.0	9.20	6.26	27.8	41.2	7.24	6.42	10.2	20.0
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992	1992	1992	1993

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1992 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	8955.9		
ANNUAL MEAN	24.5		24.5
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			24.5
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			24.5
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	447	Jul 11	447
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	5.4	Oct 28	4.5
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	5.7	Mar 28	4.7
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW	3010	Sep 18	3010
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE	26.10	Sep 18	26.10
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	17760		17780
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.97		2.97
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	40.29		40.31
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	44		40
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	12		11
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	6.4		5.6

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055225 RIO CAGUITAS AT VILLA BLANCA AT CAGUAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'55", long 66°01'40", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, at C. 4 street Villa Blanca housing area at Caguas, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) upstream from Río Grande de Loiza, and 0.95 mi (1.53 km) northeast from Caguas Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--11.71 mi² (30.33 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 164 ft (50 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	17	18	54	34	23	16	7.3	93	27	26	e29	e22
2	17	13	37	34	22	17	6.2	106	24	30	e27	e22
3	17	76	29	30	30	15	6.6	45	22	36	e27	e21
4	18	59	31	30	23	14	6.0	29	20	28	e26	e25
5	15	34	25	29	25	14	6.5	27	17	23	e25	e27
6	251	25	26	27	25	13	6.4	51	16	21	e26	e42
7	90	20	22	85	24	13	9.4	35	15	37	e25	e26
8	27	18	20	43	23	12	16	26	15	33	e26	e24
9	24	17	18	30	22	11	23	80	17	20	e24	e24
10	48	76	18	28	21	11	18	39	18	21	e24	e26
11	28	21	17	28	21	10	19	31	16	851	e25	e23
12	19	16	17	29	22	9.5	25	26	17	71	e21	e22
13	15	16	16	27	22	9.8	40	24	20	88	e21	e22
14	18	15	42	25	18	10	31	597	35	51	e23	e22
15	15	17	34	26	17	9.9	473	57	41	48	e28	e25
16	14	14	20	25	24	15	49	39	25	41	e210	e31
17	14	61	23	25	23	16	25	33	18	31	e38	e25
18	48	84	21	25	17	15	17	31	27	e28	e28	e273
19	25	34	20	24	17	13	14	30	151	e28	e27	e40
20	16	21	21	25	16	13	46	33	75	e30	e27	e48
21	11	23	17	25	17	10	32	27	34	e27	e25	e27
22	16	29	34	44	16	10	25	25	44	e181	e75	e24
23	10	26	25	42	15	12	17	57	31	e168	e48	e35
24	17	24	27	28	15	13	15	33	28	e130	e29	e25
25	14	19	41	27	13	11	13	33	26	e54	e28	e24
26	9.8	17	876	27	15	11	28	78	24	e45	e25	e25
27	7.5	159	61	26	15	10	38	50	22	e38	e25	e23
28	5.8	398	37	25	13	8.7	34	35	26	e34	e24	e34
29	12	53	81	26	---	7.9	98	30	33	e32	e24	e42
30	8.5	300	48	24	---	7.4	50	28	38	e31	e24	e27
31	8.9	---	51	23	---	7.5	---	26	---	e30	e23	---
TOTAL	856.5	1703	1809	946	554	365.7	1194.4	1854	922	2312	1057	1076
MEAN	27.6	56.8	58.4	30.5	19.8	11.8	39.8	59.8	30.7	74.6	34.1	35.9
MAX	251	398	876	85	30	17	473	597	151	851	210	273
MIN	5.8	13	16	23	13	7.4	6.0	24	15	20	21	21
MBD	16	23	26	27	21	11	21	33	24	33	26	25
AC-FT	1700	3380	3590	1880	1100	725	2370	3680	1830	4590	2100	2130
CFSM	2.36	4.85	4.98	2.61	1.69	1.01	3.40	5.11	2.62	6.37	2.91	3.06
IN.	2.72	5.41	5.75	3.01	1.76	1.16	3.79	5.89	2.93	7.34	3.36	3.42

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1991 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1991	1992	1993	1991	1992	1993	1991	1992	1993	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	23.8	45.6	37.8	56.9	18.0	12.0	20.7	35.8	19.4	37.3	28.0	32.2
MAX	27.6	56.8	58.4	120	23.8	15.3	39.8	59.8	30.7	74.6	36.1	44.2
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1992	1991	1991	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992	1992
MIN	20.0	34.5	17.2	20.3	10.8	8.76	9.81	17.2	10.5	11.7	13.8	16.4
(WY)	1992	1992	1992	1992	1991	1992	1992	1991	1991	1992	1991	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1991 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	13220.3		14649.6			
ANNUAL MEAN	36.1		40.1		35.1	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					40.1	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					30.2	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1930	Jan 5	876	Dec 26	1930	Jan 5 1992
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	5.8	Oct 28	5.8	Oct 28	5.6	Jun 29 1991
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	6.9	Mar 7	6.6	Mar 31	5.9	Aug 3 1991
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			5860	Dec 26	13400	Jan 5 1992
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			16.23	Dec 26	19.91	Jan 5 1992
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	26220		29060		25460	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.08		3.43		3.00	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	42.00		46.54		40.78	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	44		53		42	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	15		25		16	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	8.1		13		7.8	

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055225 RIO CAGUITAS AT VILLA BLANCA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1991 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: December 1990 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- DH-48 and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,430 mg/L Jan. 05, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L Oct. 01, 1992.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 8,820 tons (8,000 tonnes) Jan. 05, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 0.08 ton (0.07 tonne) several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

Water Year	Suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		Suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1993	1,350 (May 14)	1 (Oct. 01, 1992)	2,900 (July 11)	.08 (Several days)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
				MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	17	1	1.0	18	38	3.2	54	96	16			
2	17	14	.62	13	29	1.1	37	64	6.8			
3	17	9	.42	76	265	165	29	45	3.6			
4	18	8	.38	59	108	19	31	47	4.3			
5	15	7	.29	34	54	5.4	25	36	2.5			
6	251	419	829	25	141	9.6	26	21	1.5			
7	90	257	200	20	213	11	22	23	1.4			
8	27	47	3.7	18	185	8.8	20	27	1.5			
9	24	81	6.3	17	166	7.8	18	31	1.5			
10	48	188	54	76	215	84	18	30	1.4			
11	28	224	17	21	38	2.2	17	28	1.3			
12	19	203	11	16	29	1.3	17	27	1.2			
13	15	184	7.5	16	26	1.1	16	23	.97			
14	18	142	6.9	15	24	.94	42	81	26			
15	15	101	3.9	17	118	6.4	34	84	9.4			
16	14	77	2.9	14	210	7.7	20	44	2.4			
17	14	50	1.9	61	328	82	23	27	1.7			
18	48	133	56	84	215	84	21	20	1.3			
19	25	64	4.9	34	199	19	20	38	2.1			
20	16	30	1.3	21	163	9.1	21	95	5.9			
21	11	24	.74	23	97	5.9	17	107	4.9			
22	16	45	2.3	29	50	4.5	34	71	7.8			
23	10	33	.93	26	50	3.9	25	39	2.7			
24	17	29	1.4	24	43	2.9	27	46	3.5			
25	14	42	1.6	19	36	1.8	41	70	10			
26	9.8	39	1.0	17	31	1.4	876	494	2630			
27	7.5	34	.72	159	516	615	61	114	24			
28	5.8	29	.45	398	533	1170	37	31	3.1			
29	12	31	1.3	53	115	20	81	164	50			
30	8.5	20	.46	300	764	1000	48	65	10			
31	8.9	17	.42	---	---	---	51	88	15			
TOTAL	856.5	---	1220.33	1703	---	3354.04	1809	---	2853.77			

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055225 RIO CAGUITAS AT VILLA BLANCA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	34	45	4.1	23	91	5.6	16	49	2.0
2	34	33	3.2	22	33	1.9	17	18	.83
3	30	14	1.1	30	54	4.9	15	19	.77
4	30	12	.96	23	32	2.0	14	18	.69
5	29	12	.94	25	19	1.3	14	18	.66
6	27	12	.88	25	18	1.2	13	18	.63
7	85	395	245	24	18	1.1	13	19	.69
8	43	76	9.6	23	17	1.1	12	29	.94
9	30	53	4.3	22	15	.92	11	42	1.2
10	28	38	2.9	21	15	.82	11	47	1.4
11	28	27	2.1	21	15	.81	10	18	.51
12	29	18	1.4	22	22	1.3	9.5	16	.41
13	27	14	1.0	22	31	1.8	9.8	23	.60
14	25	10	.69	18	41	2.0	10	23	.64
15	26	11	.81	17	46	2.1	9.9	21	.56
16	25	14	.95	24	56	4.2	15	20	.81
17	25	14	.98	23	29	1.8	16	19	.81
18	25	16	1.1	17	15	.69	15	17	.71
19	24	19	1.2	17	9	.43	13	18	.63
20	25	21	1.4	16	12	.50	13	25	.86
21	25	26	1.8	17	17	.75	10	35	.93
22	44	75	13	16	20	.87	10	42	1.2
23	42	72	9.0	15	25	.99	12	30	.99
24	28	41	3.2	15	34	1.4	13	16	.56
25	27	40	2.9	13	47	1.7	11	8	.25
26	27	40	2.9	15	58	2.3	11	6	.18
27	26	39	2.7	15	63	2.6	10	6	.18
28	25	38	2.6	13	68	2.4	8.7	5	.13
29	26	181	13	---	---	---	7.9	4	.08
30	24	184	12	---	---	---	7.4	4	.08
31	23	141	8.6	---	---	---	7.5	5	.11
TOTAL	946	---	356.31	554	---	49.48	365.7	---	21.04

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055225 RIO CAGUITAS AT VILLA BLANCA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	7.3	23	.46	93	263	139	27	10	.80
2	6.2	18	.31	106	228	91	24	16	1.0
3	6.6	8	.15	45	111	14	22	20	1.2
4	6.0	8	.13	29	77	6.0	20	24	1.3
5	6.5	10	.17	27	55	4.2	17	23	1.0
6	6.4	10	.17	51	130	27	16	20	.85
7	9.4	17	.93	35	257	25	15	17	.65
8	16	28	2.3	26	152	11	15	16	.64
9	23	33	2.5	80	255	63	17	15	.68
10	18	29	1.5	39	190	20	18	13	.60
11	19	32	2.5	31	167	14	16	12	.52
12	25	17	1.2	26	142	10	17	11	.48
13	40	47	10	24	106	6.9	20	23	2.1
14	31	45	4.0	597	1350	2270	35	63	9.7
15	473	406	1540	57	64	11	41	98	15
16	49	79	13	39	40	4.2	25	169	12
17	25	41	2.7	33	40	3.6	18	150	7.3
18	17	29	1.4	31	40	3.4	27	138	18
19	14	12	.44	30	41	3.3	151	373	212
20	46	77	21	33	59	5.7	75	143	43
21	32	59	5.7	27	42	3.1	34	34	3.2
22	25	42	2.8	25	35	2.4	44	71	9.4
23	17	32	1.5	57	116	40	31	44	3.7
24	15	28	1.2	33	57	5.1	28	52	3.8
25	13	23	.82	33	58	5.5	26	65	4.5
26	28	73	26	78	151	64	24	72	4.7
27	38	94	23	50	92	14	22	51	3.0
28	34	76	13	35	53	5.1	26	45	3.3
29	98	320	267	30	25	2.0	33	57	5.6
30	50	89	17	28	12	.86	38	61	6.6
31	---	---	---	26	11	.74	---	---	---
TOTAL	1194.4	---	1962.88	1854	---	2875.10	922	---	376.62

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055225 RIO CAGUITAS AT VILLA BLANCA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	26	43	3.1	e29	79	e6.1	e22	75	e4.4
2	30	57	5.0	e27	114	e8.5	e22	39	e2.3
3	36	61	6.4	e27	103	e7.4	e21	38	e2.2
4	28	47	3.6	e26	78	e5.5	e25	42	e2.8
5	23	27	1.7	e25	55	e3.7	e27	44	e3.2
6	21	14	.76	e26	48	e3.4	e42	66	e7.5
7	37	52	9.4	e25	50	e3.4	e26	43	e3.0
8	33	88	9.2	e26	58	e4.1	e24	41	e2.5
9	20	38	2.0	e24	58	e3.7	e24	41	e2.7
10	21	38	2.4	e24	49	e3.1	e26	37	e3.0
11	851	856	2900	e25	72	e5.1	e23	20	e1.3
12	71	92	22	e21	71	e4.0	e22	25	e1.5
13	88	171	85	e21	90	e5.1	e22	31	e1.8
14	51	89	14	e23	98	e6.2	e22	41	e2.4
15	48	80	13	e28	72	e7.7	e25	55	e3.7
16	41	74	8.7	e210	714	e534	e31	65	e5.4
17	31	57	4.7	e38	63	e6.6	e25	42	e2.8
18	e28	53	e4.0	e28	47	e3.6	e273	383	e834
19	e28	54	e4.0	e27	45	e3.3	e40	98	e11
20	e30	56	e4.5	e27	44	e3.1	e48	53	e6.8
21	e27	58	e4.3	e25	42	e2.8	e27	35	e2.6
22	e181	353	e514	e75	205	e109	e24	21	e1.3
23	e168	532	e380	e48	84	e12	e35	35	e3.3
24	e130	378	e254	e29	50	e4.0	e25	42	e2.8
25	e54	66	e11	e28	49	e4.0	e24	41	e2.7
26	e45	80	e10	e25	52	e3.8	e25	42	e2.8
27	e38	27	e2.8	e25	42	e2.8	e23	40	e2.5
28	e34	11	e1.0	e24	43	e2.8	e34	55	e5.0
29	e32	11	e.90	e24	46	e3.0	e42	69	e7.8
30	e31	11	e.92	e24	53	e3.4	e27	45	e3.3
31	e30	39	e3.1	e23	58	e3.6	---	---	---
TOTAL	2312	---	4285.48	1057	---	778.8	1076	---	938.4
YEAR	14649.6		19072.25						

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055225 RIO CAGUITAS AT VILLA BLANCA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR JULY 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
		NOV 1992 27...	1752	729	2770	5450	46
DEC 26...	1527	5690	1220	18700	67	74	82
APR 15...	1715	4460	4620	55600	48	57	74

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
	NOV 1992 27...	84	89	99	99.2	99.6	99.8
DEC 26...	85	87	97	98.2	98.7	99	99.5
APR 1993 15...	86	90	98.7	99	99.5	99.7	99.8

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055225 RIO CAGUITAS AT VILLA BLANCA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDEED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1992					
06...	1452	908	1200	2940	89
06...	2037	558	1040	1570	96
NOV					
25...	1430	19	500	26	81
27...	1722	559	1780	2690	97
27...	2107	344	1600	1490	99
DEC					
26...	1412	2140	654	3790	99
26...	1842	680	556	1020	99
JAN 1993					
07...	1552	291	1790	1410	87
APR					
29...	1645	538	2250	3270	91
MAY					
14...	1500	25	8290	560	88
JUN					
29...	1525	36	4790	466	99
AUG					
08...	1640	25	801	54	94
17...	1600	34	1320	122	98
26...	1000	25	7590	512	12

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055250 RIO CAGUITAS AT HIGHWAY 30 AT CAGUAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'11", long 66°01'26", at Highway 30 bridge, and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) east of Caguas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--14.1 mi² (36.5 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1972 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1992											
14...	1145	39	598	7.3	29.0	5.0	3.0	38	51	52000	3400
DEC 04...	1050	38	500	7.0	26.1	8.2	2.8	34	49	220000	2700
FEB 1993											
10...	1210	26	400	7.0	26.0	7.4	2.9	22	59	210000	29000
APR 12...	1245	28	650	6.3	28.0	2.4	1.4	18	50	57000	20000
MAY 25...	1300	27	300	7.4	28.0	4.5	3.7	48	56	K65000	K1600
AUG 05...	0930	62	555	6.8	27.5	26	4.6	53	55	35000	20000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
14...	120	16	39	15	30	2	4.3	160	<0.5	36	30
DEC 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
APR 12...	130	4	35	11	32	1	6.1	79	<0.5	39	41
MAY 25...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
AUG 05...	150	9	39	13	33	1	4.8	100	--	38	36

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
14...	0.20	28	296	31.2	<1	0.600	0.240	0.840	7.8	4.2
DEC 04...	--	--	--	--	12	0.490	0.210	0.700	15	2.0
FEB 1993										
10...	--	--	--	--	12	0.590	0.310	0.900	10	3.0
APR 12...	0.10	30	242	18.2	5	0.890	0.210	1.10	9.2	4.1
MAY 25...	--	--	--	--	18	0.440	0.160	0.600	5.7	3.8
AUG 05...	0.20	31	279	46.7	394	0.490	0.210	0.700	15	2.0

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'32", long 66°02'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, in the Bairoa Housing Area, 1.6 mi (2.6 km) northwest of Plaza de Caguas, 4.1 mi (6.6 km) east of Plaza de Aguas Buenas, and 0.9 mi (1.4 km) northwest of Escuela Pepita Garriga.

DRAINAGE AREA.--5.08 mi² (13.15 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 131 ft (40 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. Mean daily discharge affected by domestic discharge from nearby station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	3.4	8.1	e20	13	5.0	3.6	e3.1	e12	e8.9	5.8	7.0	4.6
2	3.4	3.7	e9.0	13	5.0	3.9	e2.9	e23	e8.2	7.2	6.8	4.7
3	3.4	4.7	e7.6	12	5.7	3.4	e2.7	e26	e7.5	8.1	6.8	4.7
4	3.3	27	e7.3	12	4.7	3.4	e2.8	e7.1	e6.4	6.2	6.6	8.7
5	7.2	8.0	e6.5	16	4.7	3.5	e2.8	e6.8	e5.9	5.7	6.6	6.8
6	73	5.9	e6.3	13	4.8	3.5	e2.7	e7.9	e5.6	5.4	6.5	6.4
7	7.9	5.7	e5.4	17	4.6	3.4	e3.0	e12	e5.4	14	6.4	5.0
8	5.4	e6.0	e4.9	e11	4.8	3.4	e5.4	e7.8	e5.9	6.1	6.4	4.7
9	4.0	e13	e4.6	e7.2	4.7	3.4	e7.4	e6.8	e7.0	4.8	6.1	6.1
10	16	e30	e4.5	e7.0	4.7	3.4	e6.0	e19	8.7	5.0	6.0	5.4
11	5.1	e8.0	e4.6	e7.2	4.5	3.5	e6.2	e9.0	7.0	80	6.1	4.6
12	3.5	e6.4	e4.5	e6.6	4.8	3.5	e8.0	e6.6	6.9	17	6.3	4.5
13	3.4	e6.2	e6.2	6.4	4.8	3.3	e13	e6.2	6.8	11	6.2	4.9
14	3.6	e6.4	e11	6.2	4.5	3.1	e20	e51	10	9.6	6.6	4.7
15	3.4	e6.0	e5.0	6.1	4.6	3.5	e12	e14	11	14	6.9	5.4
16	e3.5	e15	e5.4	6.0	7.8	4.8	e8.0	e10	8.1	10	24	6.8
17	e9.0	e29	e5.8	5.9	4.3	4.0	e6.8	e8.0	7.0	8.3	7.4	5.1
18	e19	e35	e5.2	5.7	3.8	3.5	e5.6	e6.0	7.1	7.9	6.3	112
19	e9.0	e11	e5.2	5.7	3.7	3.3	e6.7	5.7	27	7.7	6.1	35
20	e6.0	e8.4	e4.4	5.9	4.1	3.3	e6.0	5.7	20	7.2	5.7	20
21	e4.5	e9.0	e9.0	6.0	4.6	2.9	e6.5	5.5	9.4	7.2	5.3	e6.8
22	e6.4	e11	9.0	8.3	3.6	3.0	e5.0	5.4	9.3	14	22	e4.3
23	e4.0	e10	5.0	7.0	3.5	e4.0	e6.0	18	7.8	23	8.8	e6.2
24	e6.8	e8.6	6.2	5.0	3.7	e4.2	e4.9	7.4	7.1	24	6.2	e5.5
25	4.2	e7.2	5.9	5.9	3.6	e3.7	e5.2	7.9	6.9	11	5.7	e5.7
26	3.5	e15	e337	5.4	4.5	e3.6	e6.8	36	7.0	9.4	5.6	e5.1
27	3.5	e80	e23	5.2	3.6	e3.3	e9.0	18	6.7	8.4	5.3	e3.9
28	3.6	e150	e15	5.2	3.2	e3.2	e8.4	e11	10	7.8	5.2	e7.2
29	3.5	e20	e31	6.1	---	e3.2	e10	e10	7.3	7.5	4.9	e8.0
30	3.2	e113	e19	5.2	---	e3.2	e23	e9.0	7.4	7.1	4.9	e6.4
31	3.7	---	e17	5.2	---	e3.2	---	e9.7	---	7.1	4.7	---
TOTAL	239.4	667.3	610.5	247.4	125.9	108.2	215.9	388.5	259.3	367.5	225.4	319.2
MEAN	7.72	22.2	19.7	7.98	4.50	3.49	7.20	12.5	8.64	11.9	7.27	10.6
MAX	73	150	337	17	7.8	4.8	23	51	27	80	24	112
MIN	3.2	3.7	4.4	5.0	3.2	2.9	2.7	5.4	5.4	4.8	4.7	3.9
MED	4.0	8.8	6.2	6.2	4.6	3.4	6.1	9.0	7.2	7.9	6.3	5.4
AC-FT	475	1320	1210	491	250	215	428	771	514	729	447	633
CFSM	1.52	4.38	3.88	1.57	.89	.69	1.42	2.47	1.70	2.33	1.43	2.09
IN.	1.75	4.89	4.47	1.81	.92	.79	1.58	2.84	1.90	2.69	1.65	2.34

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1991 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1991	1992	1993	1991	1992	1993	1991	1992	1993	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	12.5	13.0	11.5	9.84	5.50	4.13	4.52	8.24	5.94	10.9	6.33	8.32
MAX	25.3	22.2	19.7	13.6	8.60	5.18	7.20	12.5	8.64	16.5	7.64	10.6
(WY)	1991	1993	1993	1992	1991	1991	1993	1993	1993	1991	1992	1993
MIN	4.30	7.48	4.63	7.91	3.47	3.49	2.61	5.96	4.37	4.40	4.09	4.50
(WY)	1992	1991	1992	1991	1992	1993	1992	1991	1991	1992	1991	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1993 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1991 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	3238.4	3774.5	
ANNUAL MEAN	8.85	10.3	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			8.42
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			10.3
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	337	Dec 26	337
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	2.1	Apr 29	2.1
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	2.2	Apr 24	2.2
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			1510
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			12.22
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	6420	7490	6100
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.74	2.04	1.66
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	23.71	27.64	22.52
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	11	17	13
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	3.8	6.2	4.7
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	2.5	3.5	3.0

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1991 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: November 1990 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- DH-48 and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 4,310 mg/L Dec. 26, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L Several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 3,910 tons (3,550 tonnes) Dec. 26, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 0.02 ton (0.02 tonne) Several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEARS 1991-93.--

Water Year	Suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		Suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1991	1,140 (Jul. 16)	7 (Several days)	1,350 (Jul. 16)	.06 (Several days)
1992	890 (Jan. 05)	2 (Several days)	433 (Jan. 05)	.02 (Several days)
1993	4,300 (Dec. 26)	2 (Several days)	3,910 (Dec. 26)	.02 (Apr. 03,1994)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1990 TO SEPTEMBER 1991

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	e4.7	---	---	e9.0	---	---	12	75	6.4
2	e4.1	---	---	e8.6	---	---	12	82	9.7
3	e4.7	---	---	e8.2	---	---	51	263	72
4	e5.0	---	---	e8.0	---	---	9.6	31	1.0
5	e4.5	---	---	e7.6	---	---	5.9	8	.13
6	e4.5	---	---	e7.2	---	---	5.1	7	.10
7	e14	---	---	e7.2	---	---	4.9	7	.10
8	e5.2	---	---	e7.0	---	---	4.6	7	.10
9	e4.4	---	---	e6.8	---	---	4.5	8	.10
10	e14	---	---	e6.6	---	---	4.4	10	.12
11	e7.2	---	---	e6.4	---	---	4.6	12	.15
12	e5.4	---	---	e6.2	---	---	4.8	14	.18
13	e7.0	---	---	e6.2	---	---	5.0	15	.20
14	e8.4	---	---	e6.0	---	---	20	169	57
15	e120	---	---	e6.0	---	---	14	172	36
16	e30	---	---	e22	---	---	5.0	15	.20
17	e16	---	---	6.4	---	---	4.6	8	.11
18	e94	---	---	5.7	---	---	4.8	10	.13
19	e40	---	---	5.8	23	.36	4.4	13	.15
20	e45	---	---	6.0	26	.57	4.4	15	.17
21	e130	---	---	11	54	5.4	4.4	16	.19
22	e22	---	---	7.3	29	.57	5.0	18	.24
23	e14	---	---	5.8	27	.48	4.6	20	.23
24	e23	---	---	6.0	24	.37	5.1	21	.28
25	e36	---	---	5.5	23	.35	4.9	22	.30
26	e54	---	---	6.1	24	.40	4.9	22	.30
27	e22	---	---	8.9	36	.93	5.0	22	.30
28	e15	---	---	5.9	24	.41	5.7	24	.58
29	e12	---	---	6.4	26	.55	22	132	31
30	e10	---	---	8.7	44	1.9	15	72	5.4
31	e9.4	---	---	---	---	---	57	298	83
TOTAL	785.5	---	---	224.5	---	---	319.2	---	305.86

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1990 TO SEPTEMBER 1991

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	35	200	63	5.6	11	.18	4.4	10	.12
2	7.4	29	.66	5.7	11	.16	4.2	10	.12
3	6.0	14	.23	5.2	10	.14	4.4	10	.13
4	5.1	10	.15	5.0	10	.14	4.7	16	.23
5	7.9	28	1.1	94	551	513	5.2	16	.30
6	10	82	3.7	11	45	1.7	5.8	21	.35
7	6.5	67	1.2	6.2	27	.50	4.6	18	.23
8	6.0	20	.27	5.2	20	.27	5.0	18	.24
9	17	87	8.0	4.8	18	.24	4.6	18	.21
10	21	134	24	4.7	20	.25	4.8	17	.21
11	8.1	35	.81	6.6	40	1.4	4.4	15	.19
12	7.9	35	.93	6.2	24	.51	4.2	14	.16
13	6.1	26	.44	5.5	27	.42	4.1	13	.14
14	5.8	15	.24	4.7	19	.24	4.3	13	.14
15	6.1	13	.21	4.8	11	.14	4.2	12	.13
16	5.9	13	.20	5.5	14	.56	4.2	11	.11
17	5.6	13	.19	4.5	15	.19	4.1	9	.09
18	5.7	13	.20	6.8	27	1.3	4.4	8	.09
19	5.7	13	.20	6.7	21	.43	4.1	6	.07
20	5.7	13	.20	5.0	15	.20	3.8	5	.06
21	5.7	13	.19	5.2	10	.15	3.8	5	.06
22	5.8	12	.18	4.7	5	.07	25	113	15
23	5.9	12	.19	4.8	5	.07	4.8	16	.21
24	5.9	12	.19	4.6	6	.08	4.2	21	.24
25	5.6	12	.18	4.8	8	.10	4.1	16	.17
26	5.4	12	.18	4.3	9	.10	9.2	55	4.1
27	5.3	11	.16	4.4	8	.10	4.8	20	.29
28	5.1	10	.14	4.4	8	.10	4.0	15	.15
29	5.0	10	.14	---	---	---	3.9	14	.14
30	4.9	11	.14	---	---	---	3.7	13	.13
31	6.0	11	.18	---	---	---	3.5	11	.11
TOTAL	245.1	---	107.80	240.9	---	522.74	160.5	---	23.92

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1990 TO SEPTEMBER 1991

DAY	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	3.7	10	.10	3.6	17	.16	3.1	10	.08
2	3.6	10	.09	3.4	16	.15	3.0	9	.07
3	3.6	8	.08	3.4	17	.16	2.9	8	.06
4	3.5	8	.08	3.5	18	.16	3.0	7	.06
5	3.5	7	.07	3.7	22	.22	3.6	14	.17
6	3.5	7	.06	3.7	15	.14	4.0	18	.22
7	3.5	6	.06	6.2	60	1.4	4.1	17	.39
8	7.2	27	1.4	11	48	4.2	3.3	12	.10
9	4.1	16	.19	5.2	21	.36	3.1	11	.09
10	3.4	13	.12	4.9	19	.38	3.0	9	.07
11	3.5	14	.13	4.6	20	.28	3.2	9	.08
12	6.4	25	1.0	4.0	31	.36	3.7	15	.17
13	5.2	20	.30	3.4	27	.25	2.9	11	.08
14	3.6	14	.13	3.3	23	.20	2.8	11	.08
15	3.8	16	.18	3.2	21	.18	2.7	11	.08
16	3.5	13	.12	3.2	19	.16	2.6	11	.08
17	3.4	14	.12	3.1	15	.12	2.6	11	.08
18	3.4	14	.12	9.4	42	1.9	2.8	11	.08
19	3.3	13	.11	55	307	137	3.0	11	.08
20	3.3	12	.10	7.3	144	3.5	2.9	11	.09
21	3.3	12	.10	3.8	66	.70	3.3	11	.10
22	3.2	12	.10	4.0	40	.45	3.1	11	.09
23	3.3	12	.10	3.0	31	.25	6.9	30	1.1
24	3.4	11	.10	3.0	27	.21	3.9	15	.17
25	3.3	11	.09	7.6	35	1.9	3.5	13	.12
26	3.2	10	.08	3.3	14	.13	3.7	12	.12
27	3.1	10	.08	3.1	14	.11	3.4	13	.11
28	3.1	8	.07	3.0	13	.11	3.6	13	.12
29	3.1	7	.06	3.0	11	.09	3.5	13	.12
30	4.7	18	.89	3.0	10	.08	34	912	353
31	---	---	---	3.0	10	.08	---	---	---
TOTAL	112.7	---	6.23	184.9	---	155.39	131.2	---	357.26

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1990 TO SEPTEMBER 1991

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	40	185	36	e4.2	28	e.32	e3.7	15	e.13
2	6.9	27	.54	e3.5	16	e.15	e3.8	15	e.14
3	5.6	21	.35	e3.2	15	e.12	e3.8	14	e.14
4	5.0	20	.26	e3.3	15	e.13	e3.7	13	e.13
5	4.5	18	.22	e3.5	14	e.14	e3.6	13	e.12
6	4.3	16	.18	e3.3	14	e.12	e3.4	12	e.12
7	28	235	87	e3.3	14	e.12	e3.5	12	e.12
8	8.0	176	3.9	e3.1	13	e.10	e3.7	12	e.12
9	4.8	162	2.1	e3.3	13	e.11	e3.9	12	e.12
10	4.0	144	1.6	e3.1	12	e.10	e3.8	11	e.11
11	4.0	117	1.2	e3.0	11	e.08	e3.8	10	e.10
12	3.9	88	.93	e2.9	11	e.08	e3.7	10	e.09
13	4.0	58	.61	e2.8	10	e.07	e3.7	8	e.08
14	3.6	28	.27	e2.9	8	e.07	e3.7	7	e.07
15	17	106	22	e2.8	8	e.06	e3.6	6	e.06
16	191	1140	1350	e3.1	10	e.08	e3.5	5	e.05
17	9.8	51	1.5	e3.2	10	e.08	e15	565	e80
18	79	513	443	e3.3	10	e.08	e4.8	232	e3.0
19	14	60	2.8	e3.2	10	e.08	e5.0	97	e10
20	7.2	31	.61	e3.1	10	e.08	e4.0	9	e.10
21	5.9	25	.40	e3.1	10	e.08	e3.9	13	e.20
22	20	85	13	e7.4	69	e20	e6.0	78	e21
23	e5.6	32	e.56	e5.2	21	e.32	e4.6	57	e4.5
24	e5.2	31	e.42	e4.3	15	e.17	e4.2	47	e.54
25	e4.8	28	e.35	e4.0	11	e.11	e3.8	43	e.47
26	e4.5	24	e.28	e3.8	8	e.09	e3.7	37	e.38
27	e4.3	21	e.24	e16	145	e34	e4.6	27	e.29
28	e7.0	67	e3.2	e6.4	36	e1.2	e4.4	20	e.24
29	e3.7	81	e1.0	e4.5	38	e.48	e6.4	31	e1.4
30	e3.5	28	e.26	e4.1	38	e.41	e5.8	19	e.27
31	e3.8	29	e.30	e3.9	15	e.14	---	---	---
TOTAL	512.9	---	1975.08	126.8	---	59.17	135.1	---	124.09

e Estimated

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992

DAY	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	e4.0	13	e.14	17	72	18	3.9	5	.06
2	e7.0	24	e.46	11	64	4.0	3.9	5	.06
3	3.9	23	.24	4.7	30	.39	e5.6	5	e.08
4	3.2	103	.91	4.8	25	.30	e6.4	6	e.10
5	4.0	18	.20	8.9	36	1.3	4.6	8	.11
6	3.2	16	.14	5.8	21	.33	4.3	13	.15
7	3.2	14	.11	18	78	7.7	3.9	14	.16
8	3.2	12	.10	57	268	67	3.8	13	.13
9	3.3	12	.10	21	89	8.4	3.9	11	.11
10	3.2	12	.10	6.7	29	.57	3.9	10	.10
11	3.1	11	.09	e5.3	18	e.25	3.9	8	.09
12	3.1	10	.08	e4.8	15	e.20	3.9	7	.08
13	3.0	10	.08	e4.6	15	e.18	e4.9	12	e.40
14	3.3	9	.09	e4.4	15	e.18	e5.2	15	e.21
15	3.8	8	.09	e4.2	15	e.18	4.0	10	.10
16	3.4	8	.08	e4.0	15	e.16	3.8	10	.10
17	3.3	9	.08	3.8	15	.16	3.7	10	.10
18	3.0	10	.09	3.8	15	.16	3.6	10	.09
19	3.0	10	.09	3.8	15	.16	3.6	8	.08
20	2.9	10	.08	3.9	14	.14	e15	60	e8.6
21	3.7	14	.18	9.2	37	3.3	e9.2	33	e1.5
22	5.0	17	.46	16	57	2.9	4.1	12	.14
23	4.6	16	.22	12	45	3.0	4.0	13	.13
24	3.3	10	.09	8.8	64	1.9	3.8	14	.14
25	3.0	9	.08	6.3	25	.43	3.8	15	.15
26	3.0	9	.08	6.1	20	.33	3.7	15	.15
27	2.9	9	.07	10	42	4.0	3.8	15	.15
28	2.7	8	.06	4.3	20	.24	3.8	15	.16
29	5.1	19	1.4	4.1	14	.15	3.8	15	.16
30	24	106	27	4.0	7	.09	3.8	15	.16
31	5.9	22	.42	---	---	---	3.8	16	.16
TOTAL	133.3	---	33.41	278.3	---	126.10	143.4	---	13.91

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE	CONCEN-		DISCHARGE	CONCEN-		DISCHARGE	DISCHARGE	
	(CFS)	TRATION	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	TRATION	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	TRATION	(TONS/DAY)
		(MG/L)			(MG/L)			(MG/L)	
	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
1	e3.8	16	e.16	e3.3	24	e.21	3.0	5	.04
2	e3.6	16	e.16	e3.4	23	e.22	2.8	4	.04
3	e3.6	16	e.16	e3.5	22	e.20	2.8	7	.06
4	e3.6	16	e.16	e3.5	18	e.16	2.8	7	.06
5	e180	890	e433	e3.5	14	e.13	2.8	7	.06
6	e100	458	e124	e3.5	12	e.12	2.8	7	.06
7	e10	49	e1.3	e3.4	15	e.14	2.8	8	.06
8	e6.0	48	e.77	e3.5	21	e.20	e2.6	8	e.06
9	e5.4	49	e.75	e3.6	27	e.27	e2.6	8	e.06
10	5.8	49	.77	e4.3	27	e.30	e2.7	7	e.06
11	4.1	50	.55	e3.6	22	e.21	e2.6	5	e.04
12	3.8	53	.54	e3.4	24	e.22	e2.5	4	e.03
13	4.1	55	.60	e3.4	29	e.27	e2.5	4	e.02
14	3.5	51	.49	e3.4	31	e.29	e2.4	4	e.02
15	3.2	45	.37	e3.3	25	e.22	e2.7	4	e.03
16	22	122	32	e3.5	16	e.15	e2.6	4	e.02
17	8.2	39	2.3	e3.4	12	e.12	e5.2	4	e.06
18	e4.4	24	e.25	e3.4	16	e.15	e2.8	4	e.04
19	e3.9	26	e.27	e3.4	24	e.22	e2.7	4	e.02
20	e3.8	25	e.25	e3.2	31	e.27	e2.6	12	e.08
21	e3.8	22	e.22	e3.3	36	e.31	e2.5	14	e.10
22	e3.7	18	e.18	e3.2	39	e.34	e2.5	19	e.13
23	e3.7	16	e.15	3.7	43	.42	e2.4	23	e.14
24	e3.7	17	e.16	4.0	32	.34	e2.3	17	e.10
25	e3.8	19	e.19	3.3	14	.12	e2.3	6	e.04
26	e3.7	20	e.17	3.2	6	.06	e2.3	3	e.02
27	e3.6	20	e.19	3.6	4	.04	e2.3	3	e.02
28	e3.6	19	e.18	3.5	4	.04	e33	171	e14
29	e3.6	20	e.19	3.4	4	.04	e4.0	26	e.32
30	e3.6	22	e.21	---	---	---	e2.7	21	e.16
31	e3.4	24	e.22	---	---	---	e2.4	14	e.09
TOTAL	423.0	---	600.91	100.7	---	5.78	115.0	---	142.03

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	e2.3	11	e.06	e2.5	10	e.06	5.1	7	.10
2	e2.4	7	e.05	e3.2	15	e.13	5.0	6	.09
3	e2.4	8	e.05	e2.7	21	e.16	4.0	5	.06
4	e2.4	15	e.09	e2.3	27	e.16	9.4	37	10
5	e2.3	25	e.15	e2.2	29	e.17	3.8	13	.13
6	e2.4	34	e.21	e2.6	23	e.16	4.8	15	.26
7	e2.7	34	e.24	e2.5	15	e.09	5.1	15	.24
8	e2.6	26	e.18	e2.3	8	e.05	5.6	18	.59
9	e2.4	15	e.09	e2.2	6	e.04	5.9	20	.60
10	e2.3	7	e.05	e2.1	5	e.03	5.5	18	.31
11	e2.4	6	e.04	e2.2	5	e.02	e4.5	20	e.24
12	e2.6	8	e.06	e3.0	4	e.04	e8.6	14	e.32
13	e2.4	11	e.07	e2.7	3	e.02	e8.2	21	e.46
14	e2.2	11	e.06	e2.4	3	e.02	e4.5	17	e.20
15	e2.2	8	e.05	e2.5	5	e.03	e3.8	5	e.06
16	e2.2	7	e.05	e3.5	12	e.11	e7.4	6	e.12
17	e2.4	10	e.07	e4.7	20	e.25	e4.1	8	e.10
18	e3.7	12	e.11	e3.4	26	e.23	e3.5	10	e.10
19	e7.4	26	e1.3	e4.3	28	e.32	e3.8	10	e.10
20	e3.5	26	e.24	e4.7	28	e.36	e3.8	10	e.10
21	e2.9	23	e.18	e6.4	27	e.46	e6.4	16	e.27
22	e2.5	21	e.14	e4.6	23	e.28	e4.2	13	e.15
23	e2.4	19	e.12	e32	18	e1.5	e4.5	5	e.07
24	e2.3	17	e.11	e30	14	e1.1	e3.8	6	e.07
25	e2.2	15	e.09	e14	12	e.44	e3.5	7	e.06
26	e2.2	14	e.08	e12	11	e.34	e3.2	6	e.06
27	e2.2	12	e.60	e10	9	e.24	e3.0	5	e.04
28	e2.2	10	e.06	7.9	8	.17	e3.0	4	e.04
29	e2.1	8	e.05	6.7	7	.14	e3.0	5	e.04
30	e2.2	7	e.04	5.9	7	.11	e2.9	7	e.06
31	---	---	---	5.3	7	.10	---	---	---
TOTAL	78.4	---	4.69	192.8	---	7.33	143.9	---	15.04

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
				MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	e2.8	10	e.07	3.6	5	.04	5.4	19	1.6			
2	e2.8	10	e.07	3.8	10	.12	3.4	14	.14			
3	e2.7	8	e.06	4.9	18	.35	3.2	5	.06			
4	e3.1	7	e.06	15	64	5.6	8.3	30	3.8			
5	e5.2	5	e.07	82	405	262	4.4	15	.24			
6	e3.0	3	e.03	18	171	18	11	41	4.5			
7	e2.8	2	e.02	9.5	84	4.1	49	248	249			
8	e5.2	2	e.02	5.8	21	.33	4.0	13	.17			
9	e3.2	2	e.02	4.7	15	.19	7.5	28	.91			
10	e3.0	2	e.02	4.5	8	.10	3.6	10	.09			
11	e12	4	e.12	5.7	12	.30	4.4	13	.40			
12	e7.6	2	e.04	5.1	8	.12	3.1	8	.07			
13	5.7	2	.04	4.4	7	.08	3.9	13	.51			
14	6.1	7	.19	4.9	6	.07	2.8	6	.06			
15	6.7	16	.38	4.4	5	.07	2.9	5	.04			
16	6.1	16	.67	4.2	4	.05	3.1	6	.05			
17	5.6	18	.30	4.3	3	.04	3.4	6	.05			
18	4.2	12	.15	4.3	3	.04	3.3	4	.03			
19	3.7	6	.07	4.0	4	.05	e88	402	e293			
20	3.5	3	.03	3.8	8	.08	e35	148	e14			
21	3.9	2	.03	3.6	8	.07	e10	35	e.94			
22	3.8	3	.04	3.7	4	.04	3.9	12	.14			
23	5.0	11	.30	3.4	3	.03	3.5	10	.09			
24	4.1	14	.18	3.8	6	.08	3.5	10	.09			
25	4.1	11	.11	3.2	3	.02	3.6	9	.09			
26	3.7	6	.06	3.4	4	.03	3.7	8	.08			
27	3.7	4	.04	e2.9	5	e.04	3.8	8	.08			
28	3.6	4	.04	e3.5	5	e.04	4.0	8	.08			
29	3.2	4	.04	e5.2	5	e.08	4.2	14	.16			
30	3.2	4	.04	e3.5	10	e.16	4.2	19	.21			
31	3.1	5	.04	3.8	12	.25	---	---	---			
TOTAL	136.4	---	3.35	236.9	---	292.57	294.1	---	570.68			
YEAR	2276.2		1815.80									

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	3.4	8	.08	8.1	29	1.5	e20	83	e4.5
2	3.4	8	.08	3.7	20	.21	e9.0	18	e.44
3	3.4	8	.08	4.7	23	.44	e7.6	19	e.39
4	3.3	8	.08	27	308	41	e7.3	20	e.40
5	7.2	31	3.0	8.0	119	2.9	e6.5	20	e.36
6	73	791	791	5.9	32	.54	e6.3	20	e.34
7	7.9	27	1.3	5.7	21	.33	e5.4	19	e.28
8	5.4	17	.45	e6.0	21	e.33	e4.9	17	e.23
9	4.0	11	.12	e13	17	e.58	e4.6	17	e.21
10	16	95	19	e30	12	e.94	e4.5	20	e.24
11	5.1	16	.27	e8.0	9	e.20	e4.6	25	e.31
12	3.5	7	.07	e6.4	8	e.14	e4.5	29	e.35
13	3.4	8	.07	e6.2	10	e.16	e6.2	28	e.46
14	3.6	10	.10	e6.4	15	e.26	e11	24	e.70
15	3.4	12	.12	e6.0	21	e.34	e5.0	22	e.30
16	e3.5	e19	e.18	e15	28	e1.1	e5.4	22	e.32
17	e9.0	e38	e.91	e29	36	e2.8	e5.8	20	e.31
18	e19	e50	e2.6	e35	78	e7.3	e5.2	16	e.23
19	e9.0	50	e1.2	e11	113	e3.3	e5.2	12	e.17
20	e6.0	47	e.75	e8.4	110	e2.5	e4.4	10	e.12
21	e4.5	45	e.54	e9.0	110	e2.7	e9.0	28	e.68
22	e6.4	40	e.68	e11	110	e3.3	e9.0	28	e.68
23	e4.0	33	e.35	e10	110	e3.0	e5.0	13	e.18
24	e6.8	26	e.47	e8.6	110	e2.6	e6.2	17	e.28
25	4.2	20	.24	e7.2	110	e2.1	e5.9	16	e.26
26	3.5	17	.16	e15	110	e4.5	e337	4300	e3910
27	3.5	13	.12	e80	577	e125	e23	102	e6.3
28	3.6	10	.10	e150	1480	e599	e15	56	e2.3
29	3.5	10	.11	e20	84	e4.5	e31	152	e13
30	3.2	11	.10	e113	964	e294	e19	112	e5.7
31	3.7	11	.10	---	---	---	e17	169	e7.4
TOTAL	239.4	---	824.43	667.3	---	1107.57	610.5	---	3957.44

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	13	134	4.9	5.0	6	.08	3.6	5	.06
2	13	117	4.1	5.0	5	.06	3.9	5	.05
3	12	106	3.6	5.7	13	.23	3.4	4	.03
4	12	98	3.0	4.7	6	.08	3.4	4	.03
5	16	102	5.5	4.7	9	.11	3.5	5	.05
6	13	47	1.9	4.8	11	.13	3.5	5	.05
7	17	71	4.0	4.6	12	.14	3.4	5	.04
8	e11	28	e.83	4.8	12	.14	3.4	5	.04
9	e7.2	20	e.38	4.7	11	.13	3.4	4	.04
10	e7.0	20	e.38	4.7	11	.13	3.4	5	.05
11	e7.2	20	e.38	4.5	8	.10	3.5	10	.09
12	e6.6	15	e.27	4.8	5	.07	3.5	12	.11
13	6.4	10	.17	4.8	4	.06	3.3	8	.08
14	6.2	10	.17	4.5	6	.07	3.1	6	.05
15	6.1	10	.17	4.6	8	.10	3.5	5	.04
16	6.0	10	.17	7.8	27	1.3	4.8	15	.33
17	5.9	10	.16	4.3	10	.12	4.0	8	.10
18	5.7	10	.16	3.8	5	.05	3.5	7	.07
19	5.7	10	.16	3.7	3	.03	3.3	7	.06
20	5.9	10	.16	4.1	4	.05	3.3	8	.07
21	6.0	10	.16	4.6	6	.08	2.9	11	.09
22	8.3	26	.94	3.6	8	.09	3.0	13	.11
23	7.0	20	.62	3.5	8	.08	e4.0	14	e.16
24	5.0	7	.10	3.7	8	.08	e4.2	12	e.13
25	5.9	12	.21	3.6	8	.08	e3.7	7	e.06
26	5.4	7	.10	4.5	13	.24	e3.6	4	e.04
27	5.2	7	.10	3.6	8	.08	e3.3	4	e.04
28	5.2	7	.10	3.2	10	.09	e3.2	5	e.04
29	6.1	17	.39	---	---	---	e3.2	5	e.05
30	5.2	7	.10	---	---	---	e3.2	5	e.05
31	5.2	7	.10	---	---	---	e3.2	5	e.04
TOTAL	247.4	---	33.48	125.9	---	4.00	108.2	---	2.25

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)		
										APRIL	
1	e3.1		4	e.04		e12	15	e.48	e8.9	7	e.18
2	e2.9		3	e.03		e23	15	e.94	e8.2	13	e.28
3	e2.7		3	e.02		e26	15	e1.1	e7.5	17	e.33
4	e2.8		5	e.04		e7.1	15	e.27	e6.4	19	e.32
5	e2.8		6	e.04		e6.8	14	e.25	e5.9	20	e.31
6	e2.7		7	e.05		e7.9	13	e.28	e5.6	22	e.32
7	e3.0		10	e.08		e12	12	e.39	e5.4	27	e.39
8	e5.4		12	e.17		e7.8	13	e.27	e5.9	33	e.52
9	e7.4		14	e.27		e6.8	19	e.34	e7.0	25	e.47
10	e6.0		15	e.23		e19	28	e1.4	8.7	12	.29
11	e6.2		15	e.26		e9.0	36	e.88	7.0	8	.16
12	e8.0		18	e.38		e6.6	43	e.76	6.9	7	.14
13	e13		22	e.77		e6.2	43	e.71	6.8	9	.16
14	e20		24	e1.3		e51	38	e5.2	10	37	2.5
15	e12		22	e.70		e14	33	e1.3	11	43	1.6
16	e8.0		17	e.37		e10	26	e.71	8.1	49	1.2
17	e6.8		13	e.24		e8.0	19	e.40	7.0	28	.56
18	e5.6		10	e.14		e6.0	14	e.22	7.1	23	.56
19	e6.7		9	e.16		5.7	11	.16	27	155	15
20	e6.0		14	e.22		5.7	8	.12	20	115	9.1
21	e6.5		19	e.33		5.5	6	.09	9.4	51	1.4
22	e5.0		19	e.24		5.4	5	.08	9.3	31	.71
23	e6.0		16	e.25		18	103	17	7.8	23	.50
24	e4.9		14	e.18		7.4	22	.47	7.1	20	.39
25	e5.2		14	e.19		7.9	17	.38	6.9	15	.28
26	e6.8		15	e.27		36	384	143	7.0	12	.21
27	e9.0		15	e.36		18	79	5.1	6.7	11	.21
28	e8.4		15	e.34		e11	27	e1.0	10	50	3.4
29	e10		15	e.40		e10	8	e.24	7.3	33	.72
30	e23		15	e.94		e9.0	7	e.17	7.4	49	.93
31	---		---	---		e9.7	5	e.15	---	---	---
TOTAL	215.9		---	9.01		388.5	---	183.86	259.3	---	43.14

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	5.8	44	.70	7.0	8	.15	4.6	10	.12
2	7.2	40	.82	6.8	7	.13	4.7	9	.11
3	8.1	30	.81	6.8	5	.10	4.7	7	.09
4	6.2	19	.35	6.6	5	.08	8.7	29	1.9
5	5.7	16	.26	6.6	6	.11	6.8	23	.60
6	5.4	16	.24	6.5	9	.16	6.4	21	.54
7	14	83	14	6.4	10	.18	5.0	14	.21
8	6.1	18	.33	6.4	10	.18	4.7	10	.12
9	4.8	13	.17	6.1	14	.24	6.1	16	.41
10	5.0	16	.29	6.0	21	.33	5.4	16	.26
11	80	785	401	6.1	25	.41	4.6	7	.10
12	17	76	4.4	6.3	22	.38	4.5	5	.06
13	11	28	.91	6.2	14	.23	4.9	11	.21
14	9.6	17	.46	6.6	10	.17	4.7	14	.18
15	14	57	5.8	6.9	13	.35	5.4	18	.43
16	10	27	.85	24	118	11	6.8	22	.79
17	8.3	15	.33	7.4	20	.47	5.1	14	.20
18	7.9	11	.24	6.3	11	.19	112	1500	2480
19	7.7	12	.24	6.1	10	.16	35	194	22
20	7.2	12	.24	5.7	10	.15	20	93	7.0
21	7.2	12	.24	5.3	10	.14	e6.8	31	e.59
22	14	56	4.2	22	136	27	e4.3	28	e.31
23	23	115	10	8.8	26	.72	e6.2	33	e.85
24	24	130	14	6.2	10	.17	e5.5	18	e.33
25	11	38	1.2	5.7	6	.10	e5.7	43	e1.9
26	9.4	31	.93	5.6	6	.09	e5.1	18	e.32
27	8.4	19	.47	5.3	6	.08	e3.9	9	e.10
28	7.8	10	.20	5.2	6	.08	e7.2	30	e1.3
29	7.5	9	.18	4.9	6	.08	e8.0	26	e.68
30	7.1	8	.17	4.9	8	.10	e6.4	24	e.56
31	7.1	8	.16	4.7	10	.12	---	---	---
TOTAL	367.5	---	464.19	225.4	---	43.85	319.2	---	2522.27
YEAR	3774.5		9195.49						

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR JULY 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDEDED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
DEC 1992							
26...	1540	330	3220	2870	54	62	72
MAY 1993							
26...	1631	243	3860	2530	27	41	48
SEP							
18...	1545	550	14600	21700	26	31	43
18...	1704	634	7700	13200	39	55	65

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
DEC 1992							
26...	75	84	94	97	99	99.5	99.6
MAY 1993							
26...	57	68	73	81	90	98	100
SEP							
18...	53	62	72	79	88	96	99
18...	74	78	89	92	95	99	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
 50055390 RIO BAIROA AT BAIROA, PR--Continued
 WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1992					
07...	1714	6.7	123	2.2	100
NOV					
28...	1621	150	777	315	99
MAY 1993					
26...	1359	88	565	134	76
JUL					
24...	0830	54	750	109	97
SEP					
18...	1720	614	10600	17500	78

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055400 RIO BAIROA NEAR CAGUAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'28", long 66°02'13", at bridge on Highway 1, about 2.5 mi (4.0 km) upstream from Río Grande de Loiza, and 1.4 mi (2.3 km) north of Caguas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--5.4 mi² (14.0 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958, 1962-66, 1973-74, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
07...	1240	2.7	300	7.4	26.1	53	6.5	82	19	35000	20000
DEC 07...	0915	6.6	430	7.7	22.7	29	6.6	79	<10	15000	K2700
FEB 1993											
11...	0745	7.9	498	7.8	22.3	2.7	6.5	77	<10	210000	6400
APR 12...	1445	9.0	420	7.1	26.5	28	4.7	58	18	K23000	24000
JUN 09...	1330	5.8	400	7.8	27.6	53	7.7	97	45	K44000	K160000
AUG 05...	1125	4.5	398	7.0	26.4	0.40	6.6	80	<10	K10000	K2600

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
07...	130	6	22	13	21	0.6	2.9	110	1.4	12	27
DEC 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
APR 12...	110	1	29	10	19	0.8	4.4	100	<0.5	19	25
JUN 09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
AUG 05...	150	5	37	15	24	0.8	3.7	120	--	18	28

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
07...	0.10	30	172	1.25	29	1.55	0.050	1.60	0.130	0.47
DEC 07...	--	--	--	--	16	0.230	0.130	0.360	8.70	2.3
FEB 1993										
11...	--	--	--	--	2	0.120	0.060	0.180	11.0	5.0
APR 12...	0.10	23	189	4.58	40	0.100	0.080	0.180	13.0	5.0
JUN 09...	--	--	--	--	515	0.510	0.100	0.610	6.80	2.5
AUG 05...	0.20	31	239	2.90	1	0.130	0.080	0.210	0.610	13

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055750 RIO GURABO BELOW EL MANGO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'02", long 65°53'07", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, 2.43 mi (3.91 km) northeast of Plaza de Juncos, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) southeast of Escuela La Placita and 0.35 mi (0.56 km) southwest of El Mango.

DRAINAGE AREA.--22.3 mi² (57.8 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 230 ft (70 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. Low-flow is affected by sewage discharges from a water treatment plant, 0.60 mi (0.96m) upstream from gaging station since 1990.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	21	4.1	32	27	14	5.5	4.3	134	8.1	13	14	12
2	12	2.5	17	18	31	5.4	4.1	111	7.5	21	12	9.3
3	5.1	24	11	20	28	5.2	3.9	21	7.4	94	11	7.7
4	3.6	122	17	21	15	5.1	4.2	12	6.8	31	11	7.7
5	3.5	18	10	21	11	5.1	4.2	8.6	6.2	15	10	69
6	16	47	71	33	10	4.9	7.2	8.3	5.6	11	9.8	29
7	8.3	44	11	84	9.8	4.8	5.3	7.5	5.0	40	9.1	11
8	3.7	6.6	6.0	48	9.1	4.8	5.3	6.9	14	93	8.6	150
9	3.3	8.6	4.5	31	8.5	4.8	6.5	140	35	20	8.0	56
10	3.0	59	4.0	28	8.2	4.8	5.1	36	35	12	7.8	81
11	2.3	7.5	3.4	21	7.6	4.6	4.2	12	16	1710	7.8	28
12	2.0	3.7	3.0	18	10	4.9	4.4	7.0	9.8	184	7.8	13
13	1.8	8.9	2.8	17	13	4.6	23	4.5	82	74	7.4	10
14	1.6	4.4	2.8	16	8.5	4.6	12	5.0	145	51	6.9	9.2
15	1.4	96	3.2	16	8.0	4.6	9.3	6.7	29	208	7.0	8.3
16	2.0	100	2.8	15	7.6	4.9	8.1	3.1	13	234	11	42
17	3.1	34	2.6	15	7.3	9.0	8.8	2.3	9.7	46	11	115
18	1.6	301	2.6	13	8.7	9.9	5.0	3.8	8.6	28	7.6	84
19	1.5	72	2.7	13	7.1	6.7	17	2.3	1290	22	6.4	40
20	1.8	16	2.5	12	6.9	6.2	9.1	1.4	417	19	6.3	18
21	2.5	15	2.2	11	14	6.5	16	1.8	55	16	6.0	12
22	1.6	134	3.3	14	9.8	4.9	7.5	1.3	33	328	5.5	11
23	1.5	34	3.6	e33	7.3	4.6	15	2.8	24	831	25	10
24	1.4	10	5.9	13	7.0	9.1	67	2.6	19	154	28	9.4
25	1.7	9.3	13	e23	6.3	9.0	13	5.3	16	55	23	11
26	1.5	7.3	302	17	6.2	6.1	7.7	4.7	13	107	10	9.9
27	1.1	282	27	19	6.2	5.5	6.3	40	12	62	7.6	9.8
28	1.2	666	12	e60	6.1	5.1	8.9	35	11	30	7.6	47
29	2.2	51	274	269	---	4.7	8.3	14	10	21	6.7	24
30	1.4	872	515	28	---	4.3	30	11	18	17	6.5	225
31	9.7	---	42	22	---	4.3	---	8.8	---	15	9.1	---
TOTAL	124.4	3059.9	1411.9	996	292.2	174.5	330.7	660.7	2361.7	4562	315.5	1169.3
MEAN	4.01	102	45.5	32.1	10.4	5.63	11.0	21.3	78.7	147	10.2	39.0
MAX	21	872	515	269	31	9.9	67	140	1290	1710	28	225
MIN	1.1	2.5	2.2	11	6.1	4.3	3.9	1.3	5.0	11	5.5	7.7
AC-FT	247	6070	2800	1980	580	346	656	1310	4680	9050	626	2320
CFSM	.18	4.57	2.04	1.44	.47	.25	.49	.96	3.53	6.60	.46	1.75
IN.	.21	5.10	2.36	1.66	.49	.29	.55	1.10	3.94	7.61	.53	1.95

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1990	1991	1992	1993	1990	1991	1992	1993	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	64.6	82.1	42.9	44.7	22.4	11.1	9.30	41.3	58.9	54.7	28.1	50.1
MAX	161	109	59.0	65.8	44.0	18.1	11.0	123	117	147	35.2	81.9
(WY)	1991	1992	1991	1992	1991	1991	1993	1992	1992	1993	1990	1992
MIN	4.01	35.5	24.1	32.1	10.4	5.63	7.52	4.83	14.7	12.8	10.2	34.9
(WY)	1993	1991	1992	1993	1993	1993	1990	1990	1991	1992	1993	1990

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1990 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	18842.0	15458.8	
ANNUAL MEAN	51.5	42.4	45.4
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			52.3
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			41.6
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	945	Sep 20	1710
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	1.1	Oct 27	1.1
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	1.4	Oct 22	1.4
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		5030	5870
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		16.82	17.38
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	37370	30660	32920
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.31	1.90	2.04
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	31.43	25.79	27.69
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	122	73	88
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	8.9	9.8	11
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	2.6	3.0	3.7

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50055750 RIO GURABO BELOW EL MANGO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1985 to 1986 and water year 1989 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: March 1990 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- DH-48 and automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,000 mg/L Oct. 21, 1990; Minimum daily mean, 4 mg/L April 7, 1991.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 7,110 tons (6,450 tonnes) Nov. 08, 1991; Minimum daily mean, 0.03 ton (0.02 tonne) May 22, 1993.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 657 mg/L June 19, 1993; Minimum daily mean, 7 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 4,800 tons (4,350 tonnes) July 11, 1993; Minimum daily mean, 0.03 ton (0.02 tonne) May 22, 1993.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	21	56	4.4	4.1	21	.25	32	100	9.2
2	12	33	1.5	2.5	18	.14	17	55	2.6
3	5.1	22	.30	24	57	7.3	11	39	1.2
4	3.6	19	.19	122	180	75	17	52	3.4
5	3.5	14	.12	18	52	3.4	10	37	1.1
6	16	41	5.2	47	92	35	71	107	54
7	8.3	32	.84	44	113	24	11	39	1.3
8	3.7	22	.23	6.6	28	.55	6.0	30	.48
9	3.3	22	.20	8.6	31	.82	4.5	27	.34
10	3.0	21	.17	59	85	25	4.0	24	.25
11	2.3	20	.13	7.5	35	.86	3.4	21	.20
12	2.0	18	.10	3.7	21	.20	3.0	20	.16
13	1.8	15	.07	8.9	33	.96	2.8	19	.14
14	1.6	15	.06	4.4	23	.27	2.8	18	.14
15	1.4	9	.04	96	158	105	3.2	18	.15
16	2.0	15	.10	100	232	112	2.8	18	.14
17	3.1	27	.25	34	79	11	2.6	18	.13
18	1.6	23	.10	301	282	434	2.6	18	.14
19	1.5	19	.08	72	129	32	2.7	17	.13
20	1.8	15	.08	16	50	2.5	2.5	15	.11
21	2.5	12	.08	15	48	2.3	2.2	14	.09
22	1.6	11	.05	134	195	84	3.3	17	.19
23	1.5	10	.04	34	83	11	3.6	20	.23
24	1.4	10	.04	10	53	1.4	5.9	25	.50
25	1.7	11	.05	9.3	34	.87	13	43	2.1
26	1.5	11	.05	7.3	32	.65	302	271	489
27	1.1	11	.04	282	208	486	27	67	6.9
28	1.2	13	.05	666	469	1250	12	40	1.3
29	2.2	16	.10	51	105	19	274	245	450
30	1.4	13	.05	872	484	2270	515	395	900
31	9.7	33	2.1	---	---	---	42	96	12
TOTAL	124.4	---	16.81	3059.9	---	4995.47	1411.9	---	1937.62

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055750 RIO GURABO BELOW EL MANGO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	27	68	5.2	14	12	.44	5.5	11	.16
2	18	47	2.5	31	48	9.5	5.4	10	.14
3	20	56	3.1	28	96	8.0	5.2	11	.15
4	21	59	3.6	15	47	2.0	5.1	15	.20
5	21	56	3.3	11	26	.82	5.1	20	.26
6	33	77	7.0	10	21	.59	4.9	21	.27
7	84	137	41	9.8	20	.51	4.8	19	.25
8	48	100	15	9.1	20	.48	4.8	16	.20
9	31	60	5.1	8.5	20	.46	4.8	12	.15
10	28	53	4.2	8.2	20	.45	4.8	10	.13
11	21	47	2.7	7.6	19	.40	4.6	9	.11
12	18	41	2.0	10	34	1.1	4.9	7	.09
13	17	36	1.6	13	36	1.4	4.6	7	.10
14	16	31	1.3	8.5	23	.52	4.6	12	.15
15	16	25	1.1	8.0	20	.44	4.6	27	.34
16	15	21	.83	7.6	18	.37	4.9	44	.57
17	15	20	.82	7.3	15	.30	9.0	45	1.1
18	13	21	.75	8.7	13	.30	9.9	31	.78
19	13	22	.74	7.1	12	.23	6.7	19	.36
20	12	23	.74	6.9	11	.20	6.2	14	.24
21	11	24	.73	14	42	1.8	6.5	12	.20
22	14	39	2.1	9.8	27	.77	4.9	15	.19
23	e33	61	e7.4	7.3	20	.39	4.6	22	.29
24	13	21	.77	7.0	19	.34	9.1	33	.87
25	e23	57	e4.8	6.3	18	.30	9.0	33	.82
26	17	50	2.4	6.2	17	.27	6.1	27	.47
27	19	51	2.8	6.2	16	.26	5.5	18	.28
28	e60	145	e51	6.1	14	.22	5.1	9	.13
29	269	268	318	---	---	---	4.7	9	.12
30	28	71	6.2	---	---	---	4.3	9	.11
31	22	35	2.5	---	---	---	4.3	9	.10
TOTAL	996	---	501.28	292.2	---	32.86	174.5	---	9.33

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055750 RIO GURABO BELOW EL MANGO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	4.3	8	.10	134	172	165	8.1	30	.66
2	4.1	8	.09	111	151	59	7.5	49	1.0
3	3.9	8	.09	21	53	2.7	7.4	60	1.2
4	4.2	10	.11	12	39	1.3	6.8	62	1.2
5	4.2	10	.12	8.6	21	.50	6.2	60	1.0
6	7.2	11	.21	8.3	22	.50	5.6	58	.87
7	5.3	8	.14	7.5	30	.61	5.0	53	.72
8	5.3	8	.14	6.9	28	.52	14	50	2.4
9	6.5	10	.17	140	171	175	35	79	9.8
10	5.1	10	.14	36	91	11	35	80	7.7
11	4.2	8	.11	12	48	1.7	16	67	3.2
12	4.4	7	.09	7.0	28	.55	9.8	58	1.7
13	23	49	6.5	4.5	21	.27	82	111	82
14	12	39	1.3	5.0	24	.39	145	199	112
15	9.3	36	1.1	6.7	34	.65	29	78	6.6
16	8.1	31	.70	3.1	17	.15	13	58	2.2
17	8.8	43	1.1	2.3	14	.09	9.7	53	1.4
18	5.0	24	.34	3.8	19	.23	8.6	55	1.6
19	17	52	4.1	2.3	14	.08	1290	657	3500
20	9.1	34	.88	1.4	13	.04	417	363	629
21	16	49	2.5	1.8	12	.06	55	103	18
22	7.5	29	.59	1.3	9	.03	33	77	6.8
23	15	46	2.6	2.8	15	.18	24	63	4.3
24	67	116	56	2.6	14	.17	19	55	3.0
25	13	42	1.7	5.3	23	.33	16	47	2.0
26	7.7	30	.65	4.7	22	.34	13	41	1.4
27	6.3	27	.46	40	67	18	12	33	1.0
28	8.9	32	.75	35	81	9.3	11	22	.63
29	8.3	22	.53	14	45	1.8	10	18	.48
30	30	67	10	11	35	.99	18	54	2.8
31	---	---	---	8.8	26	.66	---	---	---
TOTAL	330.7	---	93.31	660.7	---	452.14	2361.7	---	4406.66

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055750 RIO GURABO BELOW EL MANGO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	13	36	1.3	14	61	2.2	12	41	1.3
2	21	54	3.7	12	58	1.9	9.3	33	.85
3	94	138	47	11	54	1.8	7.7	41	.87
4	31	78	8.3	11	49	1.4	7.7	55	1.1
5	15	47	2.0	10	51	1.4	69	116	43
6	11	46	1.4	9.8	54	1.4	29	72	8.3
7	40	90	17	9.1	56	1.4	11	37	1.1
8	93	152	51	8.6	53	1.2	150	192	214
9	20	56	3.3	8.0	50	1.1	56	110	21
10	12	39	1.2	7.8	49	1.0	81	140	38
11	1710	640	4800	7.8	50	1.0	28	118	9.8
12	184	159	101	7.8	50	1.1	13	103	3.8
13	74	122	30	7.4	51	1.0	10	90	2.5
14	51	105	16	6.9	48	.91	9.2	79	2.0
15	208	177	386	7.0	38	.75	8.3	62	1.5
16	234	258	248	11	39	1.2	42	88	14
17	46	97	13	11	37	1.1	115	213	168
18	28	68	5.2	7.6	29	.58	84	165	59
19	22	58	3.5	6.4	27	.46	40	87	12
20	19	53	2.8	6.3	37	.63	18	51	2.5
21	16	49	2.2	6.0	48	.79	12	56	1.8
22	328	280	739	5.5	39	.63	11	76	2.2
23	831	531	1600	25	64	5.8	10	76	2.1
24	154	132	60	28	72	7.7	9.4	67	1.7
25	55	88	14	23	70	4.9	11	57	1.5
26	107	153	76	10	37	1.1	9.9	40	1.1
27	62	125	23	7.6	31	.68	9.8	30	.85
28	30	96	7.7	7.6	30	.62	47	79	31
29	21	85	4.8	6.7	29	.55	24	64	5.9
30	17	45	1.9	6.5	27	.48	225	312	432
31	15	66	2.6	9.1	39	1.0	---	---	---
TOTAL	4562	---	8272.9	315.5	---	47.78	1169.3	---	1084.77
YEAR	15458.8		21850.93						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50055750 RIO GURABO BELOW EL MANGO, PR--Continued
WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
		APR 1993 19...	0937	60	1340	217	71
MAY 01...	2003	620	1150	1920	72	75	80
JUN 19...	0953	4750	3380	43300	43	50	51

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
	APR 1993 19...	86	91	98	98.6	99.2	99.8
MAY 01...	84	88	99.7	98.8	99.3	99.6	100
JUN 19...	63	73	83	90	94	97	99.6

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
 50055750 RIO GURABO BELOW EL MANGO--Continued
 WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDEED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
NOV 1992					
15...	1313	351	1180	1130	97
16...	1315	14	125	4.7	100
16...	1754	329	233	207	97
16...	2017	318	1670	1430	98
28...	0109	321	266	231	100
JAN 1993					
28...	2326	174	1650	775	79
29...	0436	344	246	228	97
29...	1135	203	74	41	96
APR					
24...	1256	534	627	907	96
MAY					
01...	1813	521	478	672	91
02...	0327	322	227	197	95
09...	1607	754	848	1730	97
09...	1857	382	422	435	97
11...	1725	3.3	48	0.43	85

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'58", long 65°55'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank at Highway 919, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) upstream from Quebrada Don Víctor, 1.7 mi (2.7 km) upstream from Río Gurabo and 1.0 mi (1.6 km) south of Juncos.

DRAINAGE AREA.--16.4 mi² (42.5 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1971 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 320 ft (98 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Minor diversion from public water supply tank, 0.5 mi upstream, during low flow. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Approximate discharges (no stages were recorded) of major floods are as follows: Sept. 6, 1960, 37,100 ft³/s (1,050 m³/s), Oct. 9, 1970, 18,200 ft³/s (515 m³/s).

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	29	e17	73	92	22	18	8.4	e240	15	22	22	22
2	23	e18	49	58	47	19	8.5	e190	15	28	20	18
3	21	e44	50	45	36	18	9.5	e40	14	86	19	21
4	20	e27	81	49	23	18	8.1	e13	12	30	19	15
5	19	e50	48	36	22	18	7.7	17	12	21	20	50
6	20	99	45	37	20	18	8.8	14	11	19	19	23
7	20	48	34	72	20	20	7.4	12	11	21	18	17
8	19	24	30	44	19	19	7.5	11	e17	35	18	27
9	e19	23	29	40	19	19	9.5	132	e61	20	17	29
10	e19	24	26	35	18	19	7.8	42	e69	17	18	193
11	e18	20	25	29	19	20	7.1	20	23	1430	16	59
12	e18	18	23	28	20	18	8.0	15	16	121	15	23
13	e17	34	23	26	e22	19	94	14	23	53	14	22
14	e17	19	23	34	e20	17	18	39	61	48	13	20
15	e17	50	23	26	e18	16	9.7	20	e28	36	14	16
16	e17	34	21	26	e17	15	9.2	15	e25	42	32	88
17	e19	34	21	25	18	18	e16	14	e17	31	17	21
18	e19	84	20	25	17	17	e9.6	15	e15	27	14	32
19	e19	76	20	23	17	13	e31	13	e820	26	13	25
20	e20	35	20	22	17	12	e17	13	e106	25	13	26
21	20	27	20	20	17	12	e29	14	e70	23	12	18
22	24	32	20	22	16	10	e14	13	e58	341	15	18
23	20	25	19	24	16	9.9	e45	13	e47	507	48	18
24	22	22	22	20	17	13	e120	13	e38	109	42	24
25	e25	20	25	23	17	15	e25	20	e28	54	32	27
26	e19	19	130	20	17	12	e14	21	25	89	16	20
27	17	60	39	24	18	11	e11	48	23	69	13	16
28	18	224	26	26	17	9.8	e16	33	22	37	17	21
29	18	120	116	61	---	10	e40	18	22	30	13	19
30	e20	1140	148	29	---	9.3	e90	16	28	26	13	214
31	e23	---	219	24	---	8.3	---	14	---	24	18	---
TOTAL	616	2467	1468	1065	566	471.3	706.8	1112	1732	3447	590	1142
MEAN	19.9	82.2	47.4	34.4	20.2	15.2	23.6	35.9	57.7	111	19.0	38.1
MAX	29	1140	219	92	47	20	120	240	820	1430	48	214
MIN	17	17	19	20	16	8.3	7.1	11	11	17	12	15
AC-FT	1220	4890	2910	2110	1120	935	1400	2210	3440	6840	1170	2270
CFSM	1.21	5.01	2.89	2.09	1.23	.93	1.44	2.19	3.52	6.78	1.16	2.32
IN.	1.40	5.60	3.33	2.42	1.28	1.07	1.60	2.52	3.93	7.82	1.34	2.59

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1971 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983
MEAN	79.1	93.7	58.6	23.6	17.8	19.4	15.7	54.0	50.6	48.9	62.4	77.7	
MAX	293	461	550	77.0	47.9	39.7	41.7	268	188	163	231	255	
(WY)	1986	1988	1988	1992	1984	1973	1985	1985	1979	1981	1979	1979	
MIN	19.9	19.5	11.0	11.4	7.21	7.01	5.82	5.02	6.21	5.36	15.5	10.8	
(WY)	1993	1990	1990	1976	1974	1977	1991	1990	1977	1974	1980	1987	

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1971 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	15999.1	15383.1	
ANNUAL MEAN	43.7	42.1	50.4
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			121
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			17.1
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1150	Jan 5	9100
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.4	Apr 27	1.8
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	3.8	Apr 24	2.6
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			40000
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			25.63
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			1.4
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	31730	30510	36500
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.67	2.57	3.07
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	36.29	34.89	41.75
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	67	61	73
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	18	20	19
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	6.4	13	7.3

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1983 to 1986 and water year 1989 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1989 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- Automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,600 mg/L Oct. 06, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 46,300 tons (42,000 tonnes) May 18, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 0.01 ton (0.01 tonne) several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,780 mg/L July 11, 1993; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 16,200 tons (14,700 tonnes) July 11, 1993; Minimum daily mean, 0.10 ton (0.09 tonne) several days.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
				MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	29	2	.16	e17	15	e.69	73	98	20			
2	23	2	.12	e18	14	e.66	49	59	7.9			
3	21	2	.12	e44	33	e3.9	50	61	9.2			
4	20	2	.10	e27	26	e1.9	81	119	31			
5	19	2	.10	e50	62	e8.4	48	63	9.0			
6	20	2	.10	99	118	30	45	54	6.9			
7	20	2	.10	48	129	16	34	22	2.1			
8	19	2	.10	24	70	4.7	30	11	.89			
9	e19	2	e.13	23	30	1.9	29	11	.83			
10	e19	3	e.16	24	23	1.5	26	13	.87			
11	e18	3	e.14	20	15	.84	25	16	1.0			
12	e18	3	e.17	18	15	.71	23	18	1.1			
13	e17	4	e.18	34	69	8.4	23	18	1.1			
14	e17	8	e.36	19	44	2.3	23	17	1.1			
15	e17	13	e.59	50	75	19	23	16	.98			
16	e17	11	e.50	34	37	3.8	21	15	.83			
17	e19	7	e.36	34	35	3.3	21	14	.75			
18	e19	7	e.36	84	175	71	20	13	.67			
19	e19	7	e.36	76	161	44	20	12	.60			
20	e20	13	e.84	35	34	3.2	20	12	.62			
21	20	18	1.2	27	26	1.9	20	12	.68			
22	24	22	1.6	32	35	3.1	20	15	.81			
23	20	15	.81	25	29	2.0	19	15	.74			
24	22	13	.89	22	23	1.3	22	19	1.1			
25	e25	44	e3.0	20	15	.82	25	37	2.4			
26	e19	26	e1.3	19	12	.58	130	338	360			
27	17	21	.96	60	72	35	39	45	5.3			
28	18	21	1.0	224	406	532	26	24	1.6			
29	18	20	.95	120	190	299	116	241	132			
30	e20	19	e1.0	1140	1340	13700	148	258	139			
31	e23	17	e1.1	---	---	---	219	635	936			
TOTAL	616	---	18.86	2467	---	14801.90	1468	---	1677.07			

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	92	166	44	22	25	1.5	18	9	.44
2	58	85	14	47	69	21	19	9	.44
3	45	54	6.7	36	176	17	18	9	.43
4	49	60	8.6	23	79	5.0	18	10	.48
5	36	36	3.5	22	16	.93	18	11	.55
6	37	35	3.5	20	15	.81	18	14	.64
7	72	113	31	20	13	.66	20	16	.79
8	44	55	7.2	19	11	.54	19	16	.82
9	40	18	1.9	19	10	.52	19	16	.82
10	35	13	1.3	18	10	.46	19	17	.82
11	29	12	.89	19	8	.44	20	17	.87
12	28	10	.77	20	8	.44	18	16	.75
13	26	10	.69	e22	8	e.51	19	14	.75
14	34	31	3.4	e20	10	e.51	17	17	.75
15	26	30	2.1	e18	11	e.51	16	20	.88
16	26	21	1.5	e17	12	e.56	15	27	1.1
17	25	18	1.2	18	12	.57	18	18	1.1
18	25	14	.96	17	12	.56	17	26	1.3
19	23	13	.77	17	12	.56	13	15	.53
20	22	13	.73	17	12	.53	12	14	.44
21	20	11	.61	17	11	.47	12	13	.41
22	22	17	1.0	16	10	.42	10	13	.36
23	24	23	1.6	16	10	.43	9.9	13	.34
24	20	17	.94	17	10	.48	13	13	.39
25	23	21	1.4	17	10	.44	15	13	.40
26	20	18	1.0	17	10	.45	12	12	.38
27	24	16	1.1	18	8	.39	11	12	.37
28	26	23	1.6	17	8	.39	9.8	12	.32
29	61	116	21	---	---	---	10	12	.34
30	29	91	7.3	---	---	---	9.3	12	.31
31	24	54	3.5	---	---	---	8.3	12	.28
TOTAL	1065	---	175.76	566	---	57.08	471.3	---	18.60

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE	CONCEN-		DISCHARGE	CONCEN-		DISCHARGE	DISCHARGE	
	(CFS)	TRATION	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	TRATION	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	TRATION	(TONS/DAY)
		(MG/L)			(MG/L)			(MG/L)	
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	8.4	12	.27	e240	446	e289	15	8	.31
2	8.5	12	.27	e190	334	e171	15	7	.32
3	9.5	12	.30	e40	45	e4.9	14	6	.25
4	8.1	12	.26	e13	10	e.34	12	7	.26
5	7.7	12	.25	17	18	.87	12	10	.33
6	8.8	11	.26	14	28	1.0	11	12	.37
7	7.4	10	.20	12	22	.73	11	14	.43
8	7.5	9	.18	11	13	.41	e17	17	e.78
9	9.5	9	.24	132	237	291	e61	93	e41
10	7.8	9	.18	42	75	12	e69	101	e27
11	7.1	9	.18	20	27	1.4	23	20	1.2
12	8.0	9	.20	15	16	.77	16	14	.61
13	94	353	298	14	14	.51	23	19	1.3
14	18	28	1.8	39	98	17	61	121	30
15	9.7	8	.21	20	91	5.0	e28	30	e2.5
16	9.2	6	.20	15	34	1.4	e25	26	e1.8
17	e16	13	e.88	14	16	.60	e17	20	e.93
18	e9.6	6	e.16	15	6	.25	e15	16	e.67
19	e31	31	e2.6	13	6	.22	e820	1100	e4560
20	e17	13	e.60	13	6	.21	e106	162	e54
21	e29	28	e2.2	14	6	.26	e70	54	e11
22	e14	10	e.38	13	9	.33	e58	45	e7.1
23	e45	53	e6.4	13	10	.36	e47	40	e5.1
24	e120	188	e61	13	10	.37	e38	37	e3.8
25	e25	23	e1.6	20	19	1.3	e28	31	e2.4
26	e14	10	e.38	21	27	1.7	25	24	1.6
27	e11	7	e.20	48	37	9.3	23	18	1.1
28	e16	12	e.52	33	39	4.1	22	10	.62
29	e40	45	e4.9	18	17	.84	22	3	.19
30	e90	131	e32	16	14	.59	28	20	1.7
31	---	---	---	14	10	.37	---	---	---
TOTAL	706.8	---	416.82	1112	---	818.13	1732	---	4758.67

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	22	19	1.1	22	8	.50	22	19	1.2
2	28	29	2.6	20	7	.38	18	15	.90
3	86	130	46	19	7	.35	21	18	1.1
4	30	33	3.0	19	7	.34	15	11	.45
5	21	18	1.0	20	6	.29	50	65	15
6	19	12	.57	19	4	.22	23	23	1.6
7	21	6	.36	18	3	.16	17	13	.61
8	35	35	3.7	18	3	.13	27	27	3.3
9	20	17	.91	17	3	.12	29	31	3.1
10	17	14	.66	18	3	.16	193	367	486
11	1430	1780	16200	16	3	.14	59	118	28
12	121	153	69	15	4	.17	23	20	1.3
13	53	54	7.9	14	4	.16	22	19	1.2
14	48	55	7.1	13	4	.16	20	17	1.0
15	36	39	3.8	14	5	.20	16	12	.53
16	42	33	4.1	32	32	3.3	88	311	175
17	31	16	1.3	17	15	.75	21	19	1.2
18	27	16	1.1	14	14	.51	32	36	5.3
19	26	17	1.2	13	13	.46	25	25	2.1
20	25	17	1.1	13	12	.41	26	22	1.8
21	23	18	1.0	12	12	.37	18	15	.72
22	341	756	1970	15	14	1.0	18	10	.50
23	507	934	2180	48	100	14	18	10	.56
24	109	140	45	42	82	11	24	103	6.9
25	54	69	11	32	57	5.7	27	73	5.3
26	89	135	59	16	12	.55	20	17	1.0
27	69	115	25	13	10	.35	16	11	.47
28	37	37	3.9	17	12	.62	21	21	1.4
29	30	18	1.4	13	9	.32	19	12	.65
30	26	14	.90	13	8	.29	214	376	920
31	24	11	.68	18	8	.37	---	---	---
TOTAL	3447	---	20654.38	590	---	43.48	1142	---	1668.19
YEAR	15383.1		45108.94						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDEDED (MG/L)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDEDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. FINER THAN .008 MM
DEC 1992							
26...	1435	464	4020	504	44	55	61
31...	0735	803	7450	16200	37	43	51
APR 1993							
13...	1515	446	1640	1970	54	64	70
JUN							
19...	0900	3400	8990	82500	36	42	49
JUL							
22...	1810	597	7540	12200	38	43	49

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
DEC 1992							
26...	74	81	94	98	99	99.7	99.9
31...	64	77	91	96	98	99.2	99.7
APR 1993							
13...	79	80	92	97	99	99.8	99.9
JUN							
19...	64	76	88	94	97	98	99.5
JUL							
22...	56	69	86	96	99	99.6	99.9

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1992					
20...	1656	21	958	54	100
NOV					
18...	1945	188	342	173	90
19...	0105	197	374	199	98
27...	2000	214	383	221	97
27...	2220	235	341	216	98
DEC					
26...	1415	212	6210	3550	77
29...	1007	110	361	107	92
31...	0705	256	1240	857	97
31...	1225	238	679	436	99
FEB 1993					
03...	1650	28	162	12	96
ABR					
13...	1600	585	1510	2380	95
13...	1740	285	1320	1010	99
MAY					
09...	1630	933	1550	3900	95
15...	0737	20	104	5.6	97
JUL					
03...	1513	163	575	253	99
22...	2130	686	998	1850	94

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'30", long 65°58'05", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, at bridge on Highway 181, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) east of Gurabo, and 4.5 mi (7.6 km) upstream from Río Grande de Loiza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--60.2 mi² (155.9 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1958 (occasional low-flow measurements only), January to September 1959 (monthly measurements only), October 1959 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Datum of gage is 131.58 ft (40.106 m) above mean sea level. Prior to Oct. 1, 1989 datum 5.0 ft (1.5 m) higher.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. Minimum daily discharge used due to temporary regulation of flow during construction of pond upstream from station by A.A.A.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Approximate elevation to gage datum of the Aug. 4, 1945 flood, as pointed out by local residents, 26.6 ft (8.1 m), datum then in use.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	52	81	226	184	46	e32	e26	e450	24	46	57	45
2	45	61	151	125	53	e30	e25	e400	e25	64	54	37
3	26	86	124	113	114	e30	e24	e26	e25	196	50	37
4	21	202	154	106	58	e30	e25	e34	e23	93	46	27
5	20	136	128	85	48	e30	e25	e23	e20	48	45	74
6	31	121	144	96	42	e28	e43	e21	e20	37	45	88
7	81	180	112	134	39	e28	e33	e21	e19	46	40	38
8	44	88	87	144	41	e30	e33	e240	e20	126	38	118
9	46	76	78	91	43	e30	e39	e60	74	74	36	125
10	36	177	71	85	40	e30	e34	e40	121	41	36	156
11	37	93	67	71	40	e29	e26	e27	59	6200	34	136
12	31	70	63	66	47	e30	e27	e50	32	428	34	48
13	27	92	60	60	54	e29	100	e76	36	144	30	35
14	29	73	62	62	43	e29	91	e40	216	117	29	36
15	29	130	64	60	36	e29	115	e27	99	104	31	30
16	30	167	60	54	35	e30	62	e29	64	334	57	92
17	40	205	59	56	e35	e56	48	e25	37	106	48	112
18	61	515	57	50	e35	e60	29	e25	29	80	33	138
19	59	271	55	46	e36	e40	78	e27	2030	69	29	114
20	71	147	51	45	e33	e38	60	e25	991	67	28	117
21	62	120	50	40	e33	e40	56	e25	157	57	27	63
22	60	173	52	43	e34	e30	35	e25	105	681	58	42
23	50	146	54	68	e32	e28	39	e30	80	1390	94	41
24	51	93	53	44	e32	e56	115	36	69	335	80	46
25	73	85	72	44	e32	e54	77	43	58	149	80	38
26	55	76	481	51	e33	e36	39	70	51	159	52	57
27	50	240	169	39	e32	e33	e25	86	47	165	45	40
28	47	985	85	69	e32	e30	e70	127	43	94	37	51
29	66	213	269	360	---	e28	e130	48	31	76	31	103
30	55	2230	763	84	---	e26	e250	31	57	67	28	378
31	70	---	379	58	---	e26	---	25	---	62	34	---
TOTAL	1455	7332	4300	2633	1178	1055	1779	2212	4662	11655	1366	2462
MEAN	46.9	244	139	84.9	42.1	34.0	59.3	71.4	155	376	44.1	82.1
MAX	81	2230	763	360	114	60	250	450	2030	6200	94	378
MIN	20	61	50	39	32	26	24	21	19	37	27	27
AC-FT	2890	14540	8530	5220	2340	2090	3530	4390	9250	23120	2710	4880
CFSM	.78	4.06	2.30	1.41	.70	.57	.99	1.19	2.58	6.25	.73	1.36
IN.	.90	4.53	2.66	1.63	.73	.65	1.10	1.37	2.88	7.20	.84	1.52

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1960 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1960	1961	1962	1963	1964	1965	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993		
MEAN	204	209	163	63.4	46.2	39.9	42.8	152	137	125	173	224																								
MAX (WY)	1414	1045	863	204	131	97.5	93.9	746	468	376	610	1225																								
MIN (WY)	16.0	37.3	10.7	16.4	12.6	11.2	15.8	12.7	16.8	20.9	24.8	8.76																								
	1968	1974	1968	1968	1968	1965	1967	1990	1972	1967	1967	1967																								

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR			FOR 1993 WATER YEAR			WATER YEARS 1960 - 1993					
ANNUAL TOTAL	44901.0			42089								
ANNUAL MEAN	123			115			133					
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN							286					
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN							42.2					
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	2470	Jan 6		6200	Jul 11	21100	42.2	Sep 6	1960			
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	7.3	Apr 29		19	Jun 7	4.8	4.8	Sep 26	1967			
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	12	Apr 24		22	Jun 2	5.5	5.5	Sep 21	1967			
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW				17200	Jul 11	21100	21100	Sep 6	1960			
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE				23.77	Jul 11	27.70	27.70	Sep 6	1960			
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW						4.5	4.5	Feb 21	1968			
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	89060			83480			96680					
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.04			1.92			2.22					
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	27.75			26.01			30.12					
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	227			161			213					
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	50			52			50					
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	21			27			19					

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50057025 RIO GURABO NEAR GURABO, PR
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'56", long 65°59'04", at bridge on Highway 941, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) west-northwest from gaging station 50057000, and 1.0 mi (1.6 km) northwest of Gurabo plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--62.8 mi² (162.7 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MP (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992										
07...	1030	300	7.2	29.0	26	3.5	45	17	20000	2100
DEC 04...	0900	299	6.9	25.7	6.3	4.1	51	13	4500	550
FEB 1993										
10...	1310	403	7.6	27.0	11	4.8	60	21	20000	380
APR 12...	1030	285	7.2	27.5	14	2.8	35	19	K6500	21000
MAY 25...	1145	414	7.1	29.2	8.7	1.7	21	24	2300	K180
AUG 05...	0800	390	7.0	28.6	1.0	4.5	57	15	K900	200

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
07...	44	0	26	12	32	2	3.9	120	0.6	13	28
DEC 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
APR 12...	140	7	31	15	36	1	4.6	140	<0.5	21	38
MAY 25...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
AUG 05...	130	4	30	13	30	1	4.2	140	--	19	27

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
07...	<0.10	14	93	75	36	0.750	0.050	0.800	0.180	0.42
DEC 04...	--	--	--	--	14	0.440	0.060	0.500	0.670	0.23
FEB 1993										
10...	--	--	--	--	19	0.250	0.150	0.400	0.360	1.7
APR 12...	0.20	35	265	204	26	1.30	0.100	1.40	0.540	0.26
MAY 25...	--	--	--	--	22	0.750	0.050	0.800	0.610	0.69
AUG 05...	0.20	31	234	246	3	0.440	0.060	0.500	0.670	0.23

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50058350 RIO CAÑAS AT RIO CAÑAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°17'41", long 66°02'44", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at right bank, off road 798, upstream side of bridge on Highway 52, .5 mi (.8 km) northeast from Escuela Segunda Unidad de Francisco Valdés, and .8 mi (1.3 km) north of La Barra.

DRAINAGE AREA.--7.53 mi² (19.50 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 164 ft (50 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	3.5	4.2	44	16	9.1	4.3	3.3	53	9.8	4.9	4.9	2.9
2	2.8	2.6	30	17	9.1	4.8	3.8	67	9.8	5.5	4.1	2.9
3	2.7	6.9	23	13	12	4.9	3.8	9.0	7.4	6.8	4.1	3.0
4	2.7	77	20	9.1	7.9	4.9	3.8	4.4	6.2	5.1	4.1	7.4
5	6.8	17	14	18	7.8	4.9	3.8	14	6.2	3.9	4.1	5.6
6	8.3	6.2	12	16	7.8	4.9	3.5	5.4	6.2	3.8	4.0	17
7	4.2	4.6	9.8	25	7.2	4.9	3.6	4.5	6.2	99	3.7	4.6
8	47	4.1	9.4	13	7.1	4.7	36	7.0	27	41	3.5	2.9
9	24	4.6	9.2	8.5	6.7	4.4	16	15	68	33	16	3.3
10	153	4.1	8.1	7.6	7.2	4.0	6.8	8.2	30	31	4.2	2.8
11	39	2.9	7.2	6.7	7.3	3.8	18	5.8	15	236	3.4	8.1
12	9.8	3.4	6.2	7.2	9.0	3.8	15	4.0	11	48	4.1	2.9
13	6.0	5.4	5.9	7.2	8.8	3.7	37	3.2	10	18	3.7	2.8
14	23	14	43	7.2	7.8	3.5	11	55	38	12	3.6	2.8
15	6.8	5.8	28	6.7	8.5	3.5	6.3	12	26	12	3.4	3.4
16	5.7	3.6	6.9	6.7	26	4.9	6.3	7.7	15	9.4	19	3.9
17	6.2	9.7	8.4	7.1	9.6	4.5	4.3	5.9	6.3	7.0	4.6	2.9
18	43	32	8.8	6.1	7.4	4.4	3.7	5.5	7.1	7.9	3.9	47
19	16	8.0	13	5.7	7.4	4.0	3.5	5.2	134	6.7	3.5	17
20	6.2	25	7.8	6.2	7.2	3.8	27	5.4	70	5.3	3.4	34
21	5.1	9.0	7.3	6.2	7.2	3.7	14	5.7	22	5.2	3.2	e3.5
22	7.5	61	19	18	6.6	3.5	7.7	5.6	11	16	6.1	e3.0
23	3.6	9.9	8.5	13	5.3	3.9	5.8	11	8.2	48	5.3	e4.2
24	4.4	19	39	8.4	5.3	9.4	4.7	6.2	6.4	36	3.4	e3.2
25	3.7	3.9	38	13	5.2	5.8	4.0	7.0	5.5	15	3.2	e3.0
26	2.7	3.6	215	9.1	4.9	5.5	5.1	81	4.9	21	4.4	e3.1
27	2.6	257	60	8.7	4.9	5.9	18	42	4.9	12	6.3	e2.9
28	2.5	252	74	8.2	4.5	4.8	14	57	11	7.3	4.2	e5.8
29	2.2	67	67	12	---	4.1	29	19	12	6.0	3.3	11
30	3.7	162	42	8.5	---	3.8	15	12	6.4	5.3	3.2	20
31	7.2	---	42	8.8	---	3.1	---	10	---	5.3	3.1	---
TOTAL	461.9	1085.5	926.5	323.9	224.8	140.1	333.8	553.7	601.5	773.4	151.0	236.9
MEAN	14.9	36.2	29.9	10.4	8.03	4.52	11.1	17.9	20.0	24.9	4.87	7.90
MAX	153	257	215	25	26	9.4	37	81	134	236	19	47
MIN	2.2	2.6	5.9	5.7	4.5	3.1	3.3	3.2	4.9	3.8	3.1	2.8
AC-FT	916	2150	1840	642	446	278	662	1100	1190	1530	300	470
CFSM	1.98	4.81	3.97	1.39	1.07	.60	1.48	2.37	2.66	3.31	.65	1.05
IN.	2.28	5.36	4.58	1.60	1.11	.69	1.65	2.74	2.97	3.82	.75	1.17

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1990	1991	1992	1993	1990	1991	1992	1993	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	19.6	17.1	15.9	13.9	9.68	5.40	5.93	12.5	10.8	12.1	8.39	8.19
MAX	39.4	36.2	29.9	24.5	13.2	5.88	11.1	19.5	20.0	24.9	17.2	12.9
(WY)	1991	1993	1993	1992	1991	1992	1993	1992	1993	1993	1992	1992
MIN	4.60	7.18	5.78	6.76	7.91	4.52	3.53	3.32	4.06	3.40	4.36	5.62
(WY)	1992	1991	1992	1991	1992	1993	1990	1990	1990	1990	1990	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1990 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	5751.8	5813.0		
ANNUAL MEAN	15.7	15.9	12.6	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			15.9	1993
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			10.5	1992
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	266	Aug 9	257	Nov 27
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	2.2	Jul 27	2.2	Oct 29
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	2.6	Jul 25	3.1	Oct 23
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			1700	Nov 28
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			16.44	Nov 28
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			2.0	Oct 28
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	11410	11530	9120	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.09	2.12	1.67	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	28.42	28.72	22.72	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	32	37	19	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	6.2	6.8	5.4	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	3.2	3.4	3.3	

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50058350 RIO CAÑAS AT RIO CAÑAS, PR--Continued
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1990 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: March 1990 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- Automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 2,470 mg/L Nov. 27, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L September 11, 1991

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 4,920 tons (4,460 tonnes) October 17, 1990; Minimum daily mean, 0.02 ton (0.02 tonne) several days.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 2,470 mg/L Nov. 27, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 4 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 4,100 tons (3,720 tonnes) Nov. 28, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 0.03 ton (0.03 tonne) several days.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	3.5	11	.11	4.2	11	.15	44	43	5.4
2	2.8	11	.08	2.6	15	.11	30	34	2.8
3	2.7	11	.08	6.9	51	7.3	23	31	1.9
4	2.7	11	.08	77	615	208	20	27	1.3
5	6.8	29	2.2	17	100	7.0	14	22	.90
6	8.3	27	1.1	6.2	23	.38	12	18	.56
7	4.2	32	.39	4.6	15	.19	9.8	16	.45
8	47	381	207	4.1	13	.14	9.4	16	.41
9	24	113	16	4.6	11	.13	9.2	18	.41
10	153	1340	2240	4.1	10	.10	8.1	29	.60
11	39	201	32	2.9	9	.08	7.2	45	.83
12	9.8	28	.84	3.4	9	.15	6.2	53	.88
13	6.0	14	.23	5.4	16	.36	5.9	42	.67
14	23	108	19	14	62	9.6	43	279	124
15	6.8	31	.61	5.8	18	.70	28	142	27
16	5.7	28	.40	3.6	8	.09	6.9	24	.45
17	6.2	28	.54	9.7	35	2.1	8.4	22	.53
18	43	265	101	32	164	32	8.8	24	.79
19	16	66	4.6	8.0	26	.80	13	56	2.9
20	6.2	23	.36	25	143	44	7.8	20	.42
21	5.1	20	.26	9.0	39	1.3	7.3	20	.39
22	7.5	20	.42	61	336	108	19	78	6.4
23	3.6	20	.20	9.9	31	1.3	8.5	30	.68
24	4.4	16	.17	19	91	13	39	192	38
25	3.7	12	.13	3.9	9	.09	38	200	40
26	2.7	12	.09	3.6	9	.08	215	1630	2610
27	2.6	12	.08	257	2470	3990	60	333	60
28	2.5	11	.07	252	1720	4100	74	436	161
29	2.2	10	.06	67	205	42	67	473	260
30	3.7	12	.15	162	970	1260	42	139	20
31	7.2	26	.57	---	---	---	42	194	29
TOTAL	461.9	---	2628.82	1085.5	---	9829.15	926.5	---	3398.67

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50058350 RIO CAÑAS AT RIO CAÑAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	16	57	2.7	9.1	5	.12	4.3	22	.26
2	17	60	3.6	9.1	5	.12	4.8	28	.35
3	13	28	1.0	12	5	.17	4.9	30	.40
4	9.1	19	.47	7.9	7	.15	4.9	25	.33
5	18	83	13	7.8	8	.16	4.9	15	.20
6	16	71	7.4	7.8	8	.16	4.9	7	.10
7	25	108	12	7.2	8	.16	4.9	7	.09
8	13	31	1.4	7.1	8	.16	4.7	10	.12
9	8.5	13	.29	6.7	9	.16	4.4	10	.12
10	7.6	12	.23	7.2	10	.18	4.0	10	.11
11	6.7	11	.20	7.3	11	.24	3.8	10	.10
12	7.2	11	.21	9.0	15	.41	3.8	11	.11
13	7.2	11	.22	8.8	17	.43	3.7	13	.13
14	7.2	11	.20	7.8	14	.28	3.5	14	.14
15	6.7	10	.17	8.5	10	.25	3.5	14	.14
16	6.7	8	.16	26	117	21	4.9	14	.17
17	7.1	8	.15	9.6	35	1.1	4.5	13	.16
18	6.1	8	.13	7.4	23	.44	4.4	11	.13
19	5.7	8	.13	7.4	20	.38	4.0	7	.09
20	6.2	8	.14	7.2	20	.38	3.8	5	.06
21	6.2	9	.16	7.2	20	.38	3.7	5	.06
22	18	70	9.2	6.6	20	.36	3.5	7	.07
23	13	46	2.8	5.3	20	.28	3.9	9	.11
24	8.4	20	.44	5.3	19	.27	9.4	32	2.1
25	13	44	2.7	5.2	16	.22	5.8	28	.47
26	9.1	34	.92	4.9	11	.15	5.5	25	.35
27	8.7	34	.79	4.9	10	.13	5.9	28	.42
28	8.2	27	.61	4.5	15	.18	4.8	30	.40
29	12	19	.62	---	---	---	4.1	33	.36
30	8.5	7	.17	---	---	---	3.8	39	.39
31	8.8	5	.11	---	---	---	3.1	41	.35
TOTAL	323.9	---	62.32	224.8	---	28.42	140.1	---	8.39

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50058350 RIO CAÑAS AT RIO CAÑAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	3.3	25	.22	53	370	142	9.8	23	.59
2	3.8	9	.09	67	403	131	9.8	17	.45
3	3.8	8	.08	9.0	25	.81	7.4	15	.30
4	3.8	8	.08	4.4	10	.13	6.2	16	.26
5	3.8	8	.08	14	81	8.9	6.2	16	.26
6	3.5	8	.08	5.4	87	1.3	6.2	16	.26
7	3.6	8	.08	4.5	83	.96	6.2	16	.26
8	36	237	109	7.0	83	1.7	27	138	26
9	16	64	5.2	15	130	6.5	68	520	460
10	6.8	17	.40	8.2	98	2.2	30	143	16
11	18	80	9.2	5.8	90	1.4	15	56	2.7
12	15	59	7.4	4.0	89	.97	11	31	.86
13	37	209	68	3.2	88	.76	10	31	.86
14	11	37	1.5	55	376	147	38	227	83
15	6.3	11	.17	12	38	1.5	26	127	20
16	6.3	8	.15	7.7	19	.38	15	61	3.9
17	4.3	7	.09	5.9	16	.25	6.3	17	.30
18	3.7	7	.07	5.5	15	.23	7.1	25	2.1
19	3.5	7	.06	5.2	15	.21	134	880	384
20	27	135	24	5.4	15	.22	70	419	125
21	14	49	2.4	5.7	15	.24	22	73	4.2
22	7.7	36	.80	5.6	15	.24	11	33	1.1
23	5.8	24	.37	11	38	2.4	8.2	20	.43
24	4.7	14	.17	6.2	21	.36	6.4	20	.33
25	4.0	7	.08	7.0	19	.34	5.5	20	.28
26	5.1	11	.45	81	711	724	4.9	19	.25
27	18	82	11	42	194	23	4.9	17	.23
28	14	58	5.6	57	377	210	11	132	17
29	29	146	25	19	44	2.8	12	43	2.2
30	15	129	5.8	12	27	.86	6.4	21	.38
31	---	---	---	10	25	.70	---	---	---
TOTAL	333.8	---	277.62	553.7	---	1413.36	601.5	---	1153.50

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50058350 RIO CAÑAS AT RIO CAÑAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	4.9	15	.20	4.9	10	.13	2.9	4	.03
2	5.5	12	.17	4.1	10	.12	2.9	4	.03
3	6.8	12	.20	4.1	10	.11	3.0	4	.03
4	5.1	12	.18	4.1	10	.11	7.4	25	2.0
5	3.9	12	.13	4.1	10	.11	5.6	16	.39
6	3.8	12	.12	4.0	11	.12	17	92	32
7	99	1200	1810	3.7	13	.12	4.6	13	.24
8	41	202	25	3.5	12	.11	2.9	6	.04
9	33	141	13	16	80	16	3.3	6	.05
10	31	128	11	4.2	20	.24	2.8	6	.05
11	236	2060	2480	3.4	15	.15	8.1	33	4.3
12	48	245	40	4.1	15	.16	2.9	7	.06
13	18	53	3.2	3.7	14	.13	2.8	6	.05
14	12	10	.33	3.6	13	.14	2.8	6	.05
15	12	27	1.5	3.4	12	.11	3.4	10	.27
16	9.4	27	.76	19	97	7.1	3.9	9	.11
17	7.0	15	.28	4.6	50	.67	2.9	6	.04
18	7.9	15	.30	3.9	37	.38	47	833	485
19	6.7	15	.26	3.5	25	.23	17	61	3.3
20	5.3	15	.22	3.4	15	.13	34	199	67
21	5.2	15	.21	3.2	9	.07	e3.5	73	e.69
22	16	67	6.2	6.1	18	.58	e3.0	24	e.19
23	48	267	55	5.3	17	.30	e4.2	11	e.12
24	36	172	27	3.4	11	.09	e3.2	10	e.08
25	15	55	3.0	3.2	10	.08	e3.0	9	e.08
26	21	94	11	4.4	10	.11	e3.1	8	e.07
27	12	37	1.5	6.3	18	.77	e2.9	7	e.05
28	7.3	13	.25	4.2	8	.09	e5.8	40	e.64
29	6.0	10	.15	3.3	7	.07	11	38	1.3
30	5.3	10	.14	3.2	5	.05	20	88	17
31	5.3	10	.14	3.1	4	.04	---	---	---
TOTAL	773.4	---	4491.44	151.0	---	28.62	236.9	---	615.26
YEAR	5813.0	---	23935.57						

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50058350 RIO CAÑAS AT CAÑAS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
OCT 1992							
08...	1635	359	16200	15700	25	28	36
DEC							
26...	1520	295	3230	2570	37	41	44
MAY 1993							
05...	1520	48	4570	592	55	63	73
JUL							
07...	1325	961	20500	53100	37	45	48
SEP							
16...	1717	53	14900	2140	47	57	67

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
OCT 1992							
08...	45	58	76	88	97	99	100
DEC							
26...	51	57	67	77	87	91	93
MAY 1993							
05...	81	83	99	99.5	99.7	99.8	100
JUL							
07...	60	68	83	90	94	97	99
SEP							
16...	81	89	99	99.8	99.9	100	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
 50058350 RIO CAÑAS AT CAÑAS, PR--Continued
 WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDEED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1992					
08...	1755	172	2310	1070	98
14...	1718	82	805	178	97
NOV					
27...	1100	586	5610	8880	57
DEC					
26...	0215	224	1900	1150	88
APR 1993					
10...	0818	140	6.8	2.6	96
21...	1735	27	656	48	99
JUN					
15...	1600	13	2990	105	21
JUL					
07...	1445	411	8410	9330	99
11...	1415	615	1770	2940	91

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059000 LAGO LOIZA AT DAMSITE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'49", long 66°01'00", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at pumpsite at damsite, and 1.9 mi (3.1 km) south of Trujillo Alto plaza.

DRANAIGE AREA.--208 mi² (539 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1987 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lake is formed by Loiza Dam, a concrete structure completed in 1954. Useable capacity of impoundment is 30,000 acre-ft (37.0 hm³). Out flow from lake is controlled by five slide gates in powerplant and pump intake structure, four sluice gates, and concrete spillway with eight radial gates. Lake is used for municipal water supply and intermittent power generation. Gage-height satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation 147.42 ft (44.93 m), Sept. 18, 1989; minimum elevation, 125.86 ft (38.36 m), June 12, 1988.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation 134.88 ft (41.11 m), May 14; minimum elevation, 127.06 ft (38.73 m), Apr. 8.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents in acre-feet
98.4	5,000	128.6	18,000
111.5	8,900	137.8	26,000
120.4	13,000	147.6	35,000

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	133.15	133.28	133.08	133.28	134.33	133.51	128.83	133.47	133.72	134.05	133.61	133.72
2	133.25	133.26	132.58	132.73	133.71	133.43	128.51	133.33	133.64	133.53	133.00	132.48
3	133.29	133.52	133.35	133.41	134.06	133.32	128.27	134.25	133.53	133.55	133.20	132.64
4	133.32	133.61	133.00	132.79	134.14	133.17	128.01	134.45	133.41	133.96	133.34	132.72
5	133.34	133.26	132.92	133.25	134.18	133.03	127.74	134.15	133.29	134.06	133.50	133.22
6	133.62	132.97	133.10	133.68	134.22	132.92	127.48	134.03	133.11	134.08	132.92	132.78
7	133.40	133.10	133.03	133.63	134.24	132.74	127.24	134.17	132.96	133.64	133.02	132.92
8	133.08	133.30	133.13	133.09	134.24	132.61	127.20	134.21	133.01	133.62	133.16	133.28
9	133.30	133.39	133.13	133.51	134.22	132.46	127.24	134.01	133.45	133.68	133.30	132.84
10	133.00	133.60	133.13	132.97	134.24	132.30	127.24	133.97	133.67	133.32	133.40	133.66
11	133.15	133.12	133.13	133.22	134.24	132.12	127.16	134.14	133.71	132.57	133.48	132.82
12	133.21	133.20	133.13	133.45	134.30	131.92	127.18	134.20	133.65	133.87	133.58	132.96
13	133.21	133.35	133.13	133.62	134.40	131.74	127.78	134.18	133.57	132.83	133.62	133.04
14	133.28	133.49	133.13	133.83	134.42	131.60	128.21	134.00	133.79	132.85	132.76	133.12
15	133.26	133.03	133.21	133.96	134.40	131.42	130.65	133.98	133.69	132.84	132.83	133.20
16	133.24	133.41	133.35	134.09	134.42	131.32	130.97	134.20	134.27	133.00	133.27	133.70
17	133.21	133.55	133.48	133.70	134.38	131.20	130.99	134.28	134.35	132.94	132.99	133.04
18	133.55	132.83	132.97	133.78	134.31	131.12	130.89	134.32	133.96	133.28	133.25	132.86
19	133.31	133.68	133.02	133.88	134.23	131.02	130.90	133.82	133.73	132.86	133.39	133.48
20	133.34	133.54	133.10	133.97	134.19	130.94	131.02	133.82	134.02	133.10	133.49	133.10
21	133.50	132.92	133.14	134.01	134.15	130.82	131.18	133.80	133.73	133.25	133.55	133.32
22	133.32	132.96	133.46	133.17	134.09	130.62	131.12	133.76	133.68	132.97	133.37	133.40
23	133.31	133.44	132.86	133.53	134.01	130.51	130.98	133.96	134.22	133.33	133.11	132.86
24	133.31	132.68	133.10	133.65	133.93	130.45	131.00	134.02	133.73	132.77	133.63	133.58
25	133.61	132.90	133.47	133.99	133.79	130.29	130.96	134.06	133.94	133.35	132.97	132.62
26	133.30	133.02	132.97	134.15	133.77	130.13	130.86	133.58	134.10	132.75	133.17	133.00
27	133.28	132.78	133.13	133.47	133.71	129.97	131.05	134.08	134.21	133.13	133.36	133.40
28	133.28	132.90	132.72	133.73	133.57	129.79	131.17	133.74	134.39	132.97	133.44	132.58
29	133.27	133.05	133.58	133.71	---	129.55	132.53	133.82	133.65	133.43	133.50	133.42
30	133.27	132.80	132.68	134.05	---	129.33	133.43	133.82	133.95	133.01	133.54	132.92
31	133.27	---	133.28	134.19	---	129.09	---	133.78	---	133.33	133.62	---
MEAN	133.30	133.20	133.11	133.60	134.14	131.43	129.59	133.98	133.74	133.29	133.30	133.09
MAX	133.62	133.68	133.58	134.19	134.42	133.51	133.43	134.45	134.39	134.08	133.63	133.72
MIN	133.00	132.68	132.58	132.73	133.57	129.09	127.16	133.33	132.96	132.57	132.76	132.48

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
 50059000 LAGO LOIZA AT DAMSITE, PR
 WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'49", long 66°01'00", at pumphouse at damsite, and 1.9 mi (3.1 km) south of Trujillo Alto plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--208 sq mi (539 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (PER- CENT SATUR- ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM- ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992									
06...	1120	180	6.8	30.0	2.5	33	17	56	K10
DEC									
04...	1215	147	7.2	25.9	2.0	26	<10	580	410
FEB 1993									
09...	1040	314	8.3	26.2	1.7	22	<10	K700	K20
APR									
08...	1250	300	6.8	29.1	1.6	21	<10	42	32
MAY									
24...	1445	251	6.6	28.5	1.5	19	35	K820	570
AUG									
06...	1130	214	6.9	28.6	2.5	32	14	120	K4

DATE	ALKA- LITY WAT WH TOT FBT FIELD MG/L AS CACO3	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
06...	49	<0.5	12	1.35	0.050	1.40	0.190	0.71	0.90	2.3
DEC										
04...	43	--	<1	0.560	0.040	0.600	0.170	0.43	0.60	5.3
FEB 1993										
09...	170	--	<1	0.570	0.030	0.600	0.160	0.94	1.1	1.7
APR										
08...	120	<0.5	21	0.150	0.050	0.200	0.180	0.52	0.70	0.90
MAY										
24...	120	--	42	0.070	0.030	0.100	0.510	0.99	1.5	--
AUG										
06...	74	--	4	0.090	0.010	0.100	0.120	1.2	1.3	1.4

DATE	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1992										
06...	10	0.210	90	80	1200	260	100	<0.010	3	0.07
DEC										
04...	7.5	0.170	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993										
09...	4.0	0.220	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR										
08...	5.3	0.200	60	<10	100	340	40	<0.010	2	0.05
MAY										
24...	3.2	0.190	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG										
06...	6.2	0.20	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'33" , long 66°00'20", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank of Highway 175, 1.1 mi (1.8 km) downstream of Lago Loiza Dam.

DRAINAGE AREA.--209 mi² (541 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1986 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 32 ft (10 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Flow regulated by Lago Loiza Dam. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	12	20	10	8.2	14	9.3	8.4	5.5	249	11	10	11
2	287	23	739	8.2	14	9.3	8.1	13	725	11	9.8	12
3	337	21	6.2	8.3	14	9.5	8.0	4.2	475	12	9.6	11
4	15	19	5.7	8.9	15	9.7	7.5	3.5	628	12	9.7	11
5	16	19	5.2	12800	16	9.7	7.4	3.2	14	129	1880	11
6	15	18	215	7210	17	9.6	7.2	8.8	232	12	220	393
7	15	1070	6.8	479	154	9.4	8.3	5.8	469	11	366	11
8	16	5350	6.6	415	13	9.5	8.2	3.6	27	11	9.4	343
9	16	1570	6.9	170	12	9.3	7.4	3.8	827	165	288	11
10	16	694	7.2	637	11	9.3	6.2	5.1	358	13	11	9.7
11	16	108	7.5	142	11	9.3	5.5	3.6	400	12	452	9.7
12	16	187	7.3	22	10	8.9	4.7	3.6	909	12	7.7	9.7
13	196	64	7.0	19	9.7	8.9	4.5	3.4	788	12	8.0	9.7
14	8.2	140	6.8	269	9.3	9.3	3.7	3.5	410	12	11	9.7
15	7.9	4.9	185	8.9	9.3	9.3	3.8	3.4	295	12	468	10
16	7.9	4.9	7.9	125	9.3	9.3	4.4	8.1	237	12	10	10
17	7.8	231	7.5	5.7	9.3	10	4.4	5.3	485	200	10	500
18	7.7	5.0	7.5	187	9.1	11	4.7	17	22	14	11	9.5
19	7.8	4.9	7.5	6.5	9.2	10	11	222	21	12	11	551
20	7.8	5.1	7.8	6.7	11	9.9	7.4	11	240	12	12	3380
21	8.0	400	155	6.8	9.3	8.9	4.7	10	1100	184	11	2190
22	7.8	318	8.6	7.0	9.3	8.9	4.4	10	21	441	12	283
23	7.9	5.6	8.2	7.3	9.3	8.9	4.1	2010	15	10	12	272
24	8.0	210	8.2	7.8	9.3	8.9	4.0	3400	302	12	12	11
25	8.0	220	8.3	94	9.3	8.9	3.7	864	10	10	11	155
26	8.0	11	8.5	12	9.2	8.9	3.7	3550	10	9.3	12	8.6
27	8.0	298	8.5	12	8.9	8.9	3.3	478	10	10	12	8.2
28	8.0	223	8.2	12	9.1	9.1	3.1	233	10	393	12	184
29	8.0	217	8.2	13	8.9	9.5	4.1	29	10	9.8	12	10
30	263	11	8.2	13	---	8.8	8.5	241	10	9.1	11	10
31	23	---	8.2	14	---	8.5	---	208	---	15	12	---
TOTAL	1385.8	11472.4	1498.5	22735.3	459.8	288.7	174.4	11370.4	9309	1800.2	3943.2	8454.8
MEAN	44.7	382	48.3	733	15.9	9.31	5.81	367	310	58.1	127	282
MAX	337	5350	739	12800	154	11	11	3550	1100	441	1880	3380
MIN	7.7	4.9	5.2	5.7	8.9	8.5	3.1	3.2	10	9.1	7.7	8.2
AC-FT	2750	22760	2970	45100	912	573	346	22550	18460	3570	7820	16770
CFSM	.21	1.83	.23	3.51	.08	.04	.03	1.75	1.48	.28	.61	1.35
IN.	.25	2.04	.27	4.05	.08	.05	.03	2.02	1.66	.32	.70	1.50

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1987 - 1992, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992
MEAN	352	785	608	211	103	73.5
MAX	842	2732	2603	733	242	299
(WY)	1991	1988	1988	1992	1989	1989
MIN	44.7	88.6	30.0	5.05	4.52	6.45
(WY)	1992	1990	1990	1990	1990	1990

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1991 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1992 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1987 - 1992
ANNUAL TOTAL	29801.9	72892.5	
ANNUAL MEAN	81.6	199	274
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			652
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			44.5
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	5350	Nov 8	51200
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.4	Sep 24	2.1
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	4.9	Aug 12	3.7
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			76300
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			33.32
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	59110	144600	198900
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.39	.95	1.31
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	5.30	12.97	17.84
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	195	393	449
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	8.9	10	12
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	5.6	5.6	5.1

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	103	122	298	360	8.2	7.7	5.4	810	9.1	3.9	9.1	5.6
2	10	6.9	388	334	193	7.5	5.4	1090	8.7	178	198	353
3	9.0	9.2	9.6	5.3	12	8.1	5.1	7.1	8.5	155	8.5	5.9
4	9.5	348	245	263	10	8.2	5.3	7.1	8.2	6.7	7.8	5.7
5	9.9	214	142	5.0	10	8.3	5.2	127	8.7	3.9	7.8	7.4
6	277	207	12	4.6	10	7.8	5.1	120	8.3	3.9	179	303
7	275	129	180	234	9.6	7.7	4.8	9.2	8.5	264	7.7	7.0
8	235	8.3	9.9	293	9.2	7.5	5.9	8.9	8.7	138	7.1	5.8
9	11	7.5	9.4	4.9	8.4	7.6	5.4	287	8.6	51	7.3	237
10	286	151	9.3	188	8.1	7.1	4.8	243	8.3	101	7.4	6.8
11	13	162	9.2	5.6	8.0	7.3	4.8	15	8.1	11600	7.1	406
12	8.1	7.4	8.9	5.7	8.8	7.2	6.4	14	8.2	600	6.5	7.5
13	8.2	7.3	11	5.7	9.8	7.0	15	14	8.1	600	6.5	7.3
14	8.2	7.5	200	5.7	8.2	6.8	6.8	1470	363	205	217	7.4
15	8.2	212	271	5.8	8.2	7.0	6.3	201	261	170	6.9	7.5
16	9.3	8.4	10	5.9	8.2	7.8	6.2	12	7.8	411	935	8.6
17	9.2	177	10	153	8.4	7.5	6.0	12	6.5	167	252	253
18	8.9	1070	151	5.4	8.2	6.7	6.3	12	6.2	10	5.7	611
19	89	114	11	5.6	8.0	6.5	6.2	142	4200	173	5.4	6.9
20	9.5	187	9.7	5.8	7.7	6.2	7.4	14	1870	9.5	4.9	203
21	8.9	259	9.7	6.1	7.6	6.1	8.8	14	274	9.6	5.1	5.6
22	139	184	12	265	7.7	6.2	5.4	14	388	1410	330	5.6
23	8.0	7.4	178	9.0	7.5	6.0	4.1	15	7.7	2130	341	490
24	8.4	243	13	8.0	7.5	11	3.7	17	213	1120	5.3	11
25	8.3	6.3	12	9.6	7.5	7.3	3.6	15	5.2	215	217	337
26	175	6.1	1920	8.8	7.6	6.0	3.8	401	4.5	520	5.4	6.1
27	6.0	694	245	227	7.8	5.7	4.2	18	4.0	192	5.2	6.2
28	5.7	3020	195	9.5	7.9	5.6	3.6	272	3.7	182	5.5	294
29	5.7	376	201	430	---	5.5	6.4	11	224	10	9.2	6.0
30	15	3430	815	8.1	---	5.3	5.1	10	4.3	180	6.7	654
31	16	---	410	7.8	---	5.4	---	10	---	9.5	5.7	---
TOTAL	1793.0	11381.3	6005.7	2884.9	423.1	217.6	172.5	5412.3	7952.9	20829.0	2822.8	4270.9
MEAN	57.8	379	194	93.1	15.1	7.02	5.75	175	265	672	91.1	142
MAX	286	3430	1920	430	193	11	15	1470	4200	11600	935	654
MIN	5.7	6.1	8.9	4.6	7.5	5.3	3.6	7.1	3.7	3.9	4.9	5.6
AC-FT	3560	22570	11910	5720	839	432	342	10740	15770	41310	5600	8470
CFSM	.28	1.82	.93	.45	.07	.03	.03	.84	1.27	3.21	.44	.68
IN.	.32	2.03	1.07	.51	.08	.04	.03	.96	1.42	3.71	.50	.76

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1987 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	303	717	539	195	90.3	64.0	43.9
MAX	842	2732	2603	733	242	299	112
(WY)	1991	1988	1988	1992	1989	1989	1987
MIN	44.7	88.6	30.0	5.05	4.52	6.45	5.75
(WY)	1992	1990	1990	1990	1990	1993	1990

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1987 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	77715.8	64166.0	
ANNUAL MEAN	212	176	258
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			652
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			44.5
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	12800	Jan 5	51200
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.1	Apr 28	2.1
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	3.7	Apr 23	2.2
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		45100	Jul 11
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		27.69	Jul 11
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	154100	127300	186900
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.02	.84	1.23
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	13.83	11.42	16.78
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	395	335	427
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	11	8.8	11
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	6.2	5.4	5.2

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- Water years 1987 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: December 1986 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.--- Automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 946 mg/L Jan. 06, 1993; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 98,600 tons (89,400 tonnes) Jan. 05, 1993; Minimum daily mean, 0.03 ton (0.02 tonnes) several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEARS 1992-93.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 274 mg/l October 21, 1990; minimum daily mean, 1 mg/l several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 4,920 tons (4,480 tonnes) October 21, 1990; minimum daily mean, 0.03 tons (0.02 tonnes) several days.

Water Year	Suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		Suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1992	946 (Jan. 06)	5 (Several days)	98,600 (Jan. 05)	.05 (Several days)
1993	831 (July 11)	5 (Several days)	55,100 (July 11)	.07 (Several days)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	11	23	.76	20	27	1.4	10	22	.63
2	8.9	41	512	23	27	1.7	739	53	761
3	337	31	90	21	25	1.4	6.2	17	.29
4	15	26	1.1	19	25	1.3	5.7	17	.26
5	16	26	1.1	19	25	1.3	5.2	17	.24
6	15	26	1.1	18	25	1.2	215	31	.84
7	15	25	1.1	1070	84	919	6.8	19	.34
8	16	25	1.1	5350	304	8270	6.6	18	.33
9	16	23	.98	1570	82	1050	6.9	18	.34
10	16	21	.88	694	52	261	7.2	18	.35
11	16	20	.85	108	27	44	7.5	18	.37
12	16	20	.86	187	33	93	7.3	18	.35
13	196	34	481	64	19	18	7.0	18	.34
14	8.2	14	.31	140	26	37	6.8	18	.34
15	7.9	10	.22	4.9	17	.22	185	37	.85
16	7.9	10	.22	4.9	16	.21	7.9	24	.49
17	7.8	10	.22	231	85	91	7.5	22	.43
18	7.7	10	.21	5.0	88	1.2	7.5	20	.40
19	7.8	10	.22	4.9	86	1.2	7.5	20	.40
20	7.8	10	.22	5.1	83	1.1	7.8	20	.43
21	8.0	10	.22	400	96	228	155	30	.47
22	7.8	10	.22	318	153	125	8.6	21	.48
23	7.9	10	.22	5.6	52	.98	8.2	20	.43
24	8.0	10	.23	210	54	89	8.2	17	.38
25	8.0	10	.23	220	40	87	8.3	13	.30
26	8.0	10	.23	11	24	.79	8.5	11	.26
27	8.0	10	.22	298	39	135	8.5	11	.24
28	8.0	10	.22	223	36	77	8.2	10	.21
29	8.0	10	.23	217	36	71	8.2	9	.20
30	263	28	509	11	24	.82	8.2	9	.20
31	23	29	2.0	---	---	---	8.2	8	.19
TOTAL	1106.7	---	1607.47	11472.4	---	11609.82	1498.5	---	986.22

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE LOIZA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	8.2	6	.15	14	16	.58	9.3	5	.13
2	8.2	5	.12	14	16	.59	9.3	5	.12
3	8.3	4	.10	14	16	.60	9.5	5	.13
4	8.9	4	.10	15	15	.59	9.7	6	.16
5	12800	753	98600	16	13	.54	9.7	7	.18
6	7210	946	30800	17	10	.46	9.6	8	.21
7	479	363	475	154	8	3.6	9.4	10	.24
8	415	264	300	13	8	.27	9.5	10	.26
9	170	248	124	12	8	.26	9.3	10	.26
10	637	139	722	11	8	.25	9.3	10	.26
11	142	126	60	11	8	.23	9.3	10	.25
12	22	99	6.3	10	7	.21	8.9	9	.22
13	19	97	5.1	9.7	6	.17	8.9	8	.20
14	269	100	192	9.3	6	.16	9.3	8	.20
15	8.9	88	2.1	9.3	6	.16	9.3	8	.20
16	125	85	44	9.3	6	.16	9.3	9	.22
17	5.7	73	1.2	9.3	6	.16	10	9	.27
18	187	69	58	9.1	5	.14	11	9	.27
19	6.5	54	.97	9.2	5	.12	10	8	.24
20	6.7	44	.79	11	6	.19	9.9	8	.21
21	6.8	34	.61	9.3	6	.16	8.9	8	.20
22	7.0	26	.48	9.3	26	.64	8.9	8	.20
23	7.3	22	.42	9.3	6	.16	8.9	8	.20
24	7.8	21	.43	9.3	6	.16	8.9	8	.20
25	94	20	5.6	9.3	6	.16	8.9	8	.20
26	12	20	.62	9.2	6	.15	8.9	8	.20
27	12	20	.63	8.9	6	.14	8.9	7	.18
28	12	19	.61	9.1	5	.14	9.1	7	.18
29	13	18	.62	8.9	6	.14	9.5	7	.18
30	13	16	.58	---	---	---	8.8	6	.15
31	14	16	.58	---	---	---	8.5	6	.14
TOTAL	22735.3	---	131403.11	459.8	---	11.29	288.7	---	6.26

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE LOIZA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	8.4	7	.15	5.5	8	.13	249	57	140
2	8.1	8	.18	13	9	.31	725	58	1200
3	8.0	10	.20	4.2	9	.10	475	45	517
4	7.5	12	.24	3.5	10	.08	628	51	741
5	7.4	10	.20	3.2	10	.09	14	25	1.0
6	7.2	7	.14	8.8	9	.20	232	42	114
7	8.3	5	.11	5.8	9	.15	469	46	456
8	8.2	5	.12	3.6	9	.08	27	28	2.4
9	7.4	5	.10	3.8	9	.09	827	81	988
10	6.2	5	.08	5.1	10	.14	358	43	375
11	5.5	5	.07	3.6	10	.10	400	39	433
12	4.7	5	.06	3.6	10	.09	909	71	1240
13	4.5	5	.06	3.4	10	.10	788	87	587
14	3.7	5	.05	3.5	10	.09	410	47	513
15	3.8	5	.06	3.4	10	.10	295	41	458
16	4.4	5	.06	8.1	10	.21	237	38	222
17	4.4	5	.06	5.3	10	.15	485	49	683
18	4.7	5	.06	17	10	.45	22	25	1.6
19	11	5	.16	222	42	91	21	19	1.1
20	7.4	5	.11	11	97	3.0	240	17	11
21	4.7	5	.06	10	96	2.7	1100	65	1360
22	4.4	5	.06	10	92	2.5	21	10	.58
23	4.1	5	.06	2010	157	1530	15	10	.41
24	4.0	5	.06	3400	365	3230	302	34	134
25	3.7	5	.05	864	354	1040	10	27	.75
26	3.7	6	.07	3550	270	3550	10	23	.61
27	3.3	7	.06	478	178	217	10	19	.50
28	3.1	7	.06	233	42	104	10	16	.44
29	4.1	7	.08	29	29	2.5	10	13	.36
30	8.5	7	.15	241	38	77	10	11	.28
31	---	---	---	208	43	80	---	---	---
TOTAL	174.4	---	2.98	11370.4	---	9932.36	9309	---	10182.03

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE LOIZA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	11	10	.29	10	11	.29	11	6	.20
2	11	10	.30	9.8	10	.27	12	6	.19
3	12	10	.30	9.6	10	.26	11	6	.18
4	12	10	.31	9.7	10	.27	11	6	.18
5	129	10	3.4	1880	21	252	11	6	.19
6	12	10	.31	220	6	3.8	393	10	45
7	11	10	.30	366	28	360	11	11	.32
8	11	10	.32	9.4	11	.25	343	27	324
9	165	26	51	288	108	204	11	9	.27
10	13	10	.34	11	275	8.5	9.7	10	.25
11	12	10	.32	452	147	163	9.7	10	.26
12	12	10	.32	7.7	69	1.4	9.7	10	.26
13	12	10	.33	8.0	50	1.0	9.7	10	.26
14	12	10	.33	11	41	1.3	9.7	10	.26
15	12	10	.32	468	44	136	10	10	.27
16	12	10	.32	10	34	.95	10	10	.28
17	200	25	63	10	27	.74	500	6	14
18	14	10	.38	11	21	.62	9.5	2	.05
19	12	8	.26	11	19	.58	551	36	528
20	12	7	.22	12	16	.48	3380	159	5760
21	184	21	53	11	12	.35	2190	125	1750
22	441	11	23	12	10	.32	283	40	245
23	10	10	.31	12	10	.32	272	100	276
24	12	10	.38	12	10	.32	11	106	3.0
25	10	10	.27	11	10	.29	155	85	73
26	9.3	10	.26	12	9	.28	8.6	70	1.6
27	10	10	.28	12	9	.29	8.2	54	1.2
28	393	25	138	12	8	.26	184	66	86
29	9.8	18	.47	12	8	.24	10	64	1.8
30	9.1	17	.41	11	7	.22	10	53	1.4
31	15	14	.55	12	7	.21	---	---	---
TOTAL	1800.2	---	339.60	3943.2	---	1138.81	8454.8	---	9113.42
YEAR	72613.4		176333.37						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE LOIZA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	103	27	31	122	26	32	298	281	367
2	10	22	.57	6.9	13	.28	388	268	372
3	9.0	20	.49	9.2	12	.46	9.6	58	1.8
4	9.5	21	.56	348	42	247	245	87	167
5	9.9	21	.55	214	26	107	142	20	32
6	277	40	144	207	21	93	12	22	.83
7	275	35	83	129	27	34	180	31	46
8	235	33	81	8.3	16	.41	9.9	20	.56
9	11	22	.64	7.5	14	.27	9.4	20	.52
10	286	37	80	151	25	37	9.3	20	.50
11	13	18	1.0	162	24	62	9.2	20	.49
12	8.1	16	.35	7.4	15	.29	8.9	20	.48
13	8.2	16	.36	7.3	15	.29	11	20	.62
14	8.2	16	.36	7.5	15	.30	200	30	86
15	8.2	16	.36	212	27	57	271	64	115
16	9.3	16	.44	8.4	18	.42	10	20	.54
17	9.2	16	.39	177	28	50	10	20	.54
18	8.9	16	.38	1070	58	498	151	27	32
19	89	29	23	114	49	22	11	21	.59
20	9.5	43	1.1	187	31	53	9.7	20	.52
21	8.9	38	.90	259	27	121	9.7	20	.52
22	139	30	52	184	28	44	12	20	.68
23	8.0	16	.36	7.4	18	.37	178	25	35
24	8.4	16	.39	243	25	113	13	22	.75
25	8.3	16	.34	6.3	15	.25	12	20	.68
26	175	21	62	6.1	15	.25	1920	76	1050
27	6.0	12	.19	694	54	179	245	33	65
28	5.7	11	.17	3020	105	1880	195	25	85
29	5.7	10	.16	376	31	202	201	28	96
30	15	17	1.3	3430	336	3980	815	61	207
31	16	20	1.4	---	---	---	410	36	134
TOTAL	1793.0	---	568.76	11381.3	---	7814.59	6005.7	---	2899.62

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE LOIZA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	360	34	133	8.2	17	.38	7.7	6	.13
2	334	29	188	193	27	49	7.5	6	.13
3	5.3	15	.22	12	23	.84	8.1	7	.16
4	263	23	121	10	21	.58	8.2	7	.15
5	5.0	16	.20	10	20	.54	8.3	7	.15
6	4.6	12	.15	10	20	.53	7.8	7	.14
7	234	27	50	9.6	25	.64	7.7	7	.14
8	293	34	73	9.2	35	.83	7.5	7	.14
9	4.9	17	.21	8.4	39	.88	7.6	7	.14
10	188	24	69	8.1	39	.81	7.1	7	.14
11	5.6	10	.15	8.0	36	.74	7.3	7	.14
12	5.7	10	.16	8.8	34	.77	7.2	7	.14
13	5.7	10	.16	9.8	31	.83	7.0	7	.13
14	5.7	10	.16	8.2	26	.56	6.8	7	.12
15	5.8	10	.16	8.2	21	.46	7.0	7	.12
16	5.9	10	.16	8.2	20	.44	7.8	7	.14
17	153	21	52	8.4	18	.41	7.5	7	.14
18	5.4	11	.16	8.2	15	.32	6.7	7	.12
19	5.6	11	.16	8.0	11	.23	6.5	6	.11
20	5.8	11	.17	7.7	10	.21	6.2	6	.10
21	6.1	11	.18	7.6	9	.19	6.1	6	.10
22	265	22	126	7.7	6	.13	6.2	6	.10
23	9.0	19	.47	7.5	5	.10	6.0	6	.09
24	8.0	16	.34	7.5	5	.10	11	12	.64
25	9.6	15	.42	7.5	5	.11	7.3	20	.41
26	8.8	15	.35	7.6	6	.12	6.0	20	.32
27	227	26	70	7.8	6	.12	5.7	20	.30
28	9.5	20	.54	7.9	6	.12	5.6	20	.30
29	430	33	248	---	---	---	5.5	20	.29
30	8.1	20	.43	---	---	---	5.3	20	.29
31	7.8	19	.40	---	---	---	5.4	33	.50
TOTAL	2884.9	---	1135.35	423.1	---	60.99	217.6	---	6.02

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE LOIZA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	5.4	32	.48	810	52	511	9.1	20	.48
2	5.4	30	.45	1090	63	275	8.7	18	.43
3	5.1	27	.37	7.1	17	.33	8.5	17	.40
4	5.3	25	.34	7.1	15	.29	8.2	17	.38
5	5.2	23	.32	127	25	41	8.7	16	.38
6	5.1	19	.26	120	24	25	8.3	16	.36
7	4.8	13	.18	9.2	21	.53	8.5	16	.37
8	5.9	10	.16	8.9	20	.48	8.7	16	.38
9	5.4	10	.15	287	33	58	8.6	15	.36
10	4.8	10	.13	243	42	54	8.3	15	.34
11	4.8	10	.13	15	24	1.0	8.1	15	.34
12	6.4	10	.18	14	24	.88	8.2	15	.32
13	15	18	1.3	14	24	.88	8.1	14	.30
14	6.8	18	.33	1470	47	339	363	20	95
15	6.3	14	.25	201	43	50	261	23	44
16	6.2	12	.21	12	23	.74	7.8	7	.18
17	6.0	12	.20	12	23	.74	6.5	5	.08
18	6.3	12	.21	12	23	.74	6.2	5	.08
19	6.2	11	.18	142	31	37	4200	88	1100
20	7.4	10	.20	14	24	.88	1870	210	1350
21	8.8	14	.46	14	24	.88	274	42	67
22	5.4	15	.25	14	24	.88	388	38	111
23	4.1	10	.11	15	21	.92	7.7	19	.47
24	3.7	10	.10	17	23	1.2	213	25	47
25	3.6	8	.08	15	25	1.0	5.2	16	.24
26	3.8	8	.07	401	36	191	4.5	13	.15
27	4.2	8	.07	18	23	1.1	4.0	10	.11
28	3.6	8	.08	272	26	57	3.7	8	.08
29	6.4	12	.27	11	20	.61	224	20	60
30	5.1	14	.20	10	20	.56	4.3	14	.18
31	---	---	---	10	20	.52	---	---	---
TOTAL	172.5	---	7.72	5412.3	---	1653.16	7952.9	---	2880.41

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE LOIZA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE	CONCEN-		DISCHARGE	DISCHARGE		CONCEN-	DISCHARGE	
	(CFS)	TRATION	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	TRATION	(TONS/DAY)	(CFS)	TRATION	(TONS/DAY)
		(MG/L)			(MG/L)			(MG/L)	
	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	3.9	10	.10	9.1	18	.43	5.6	10	.16
2	178	23	50	198	29	56	353	24	189
3	155	20	43	8.5	20	.45	5.9	13	.20
4	6.7	19	.47	7.8	18	.37	5.7	10	.15
5	3.9	14	.15	7.8	17	.36	7.4	10	.20
6	3.9	10	.10	179	28	51	303	24	136
7	264	28	68	7.7	19	.38	7.0	18	.36
8	138	20	43	7.1	17	.31	5.8	13	.20
9	51	21	12	7.3	15	.29	237	22	103
10	101	21	25	7.4	15	.28	6.8	18	.31
11	11600	831	55100	7.1	14	.26	406	29	233
12	600	52	147	6.5	14	.24	7.5	13	.24
13	600	43	292	6.5	13	.22	7.3	10	.19
14	205	32	64	217	26	68	7.4	10	.20
15	170	29	50	6.9	19	.37	7.5	10	.20
16	411	43	116	935	56	289	8.6	10	.24
17	167	30	45	252	25	112	253	25	127
18	10	21	.61	5.7	10	.15	611	34	338
19	173	31	42	5.4	10	.14	6.9	19	.37
20	9.5	20	.52	4.9	10	.13	203	24	94
21	9.6	20	.53	5.1	10	.14	5.6	15	.22
22	1410	59	711	330	26	135	5.6	14	.22
23	2130	93	711	341	31	181	490	27	271
24	1120	73	318	5.3	10	.14	11	18	.89
25	215	36	56	217	26	58	337	25	181
26	520	37	304	5.4	13	.19	6.1	15	.25
27	192	33	47	5.2	10	.14	6.2	15	.25
28	182	44	47	5.5	10	.15	294	25	126
29	10	50	1.4	9.2	14	.51	6.0	16	.29
30	180	38	45	6.7	14	.25	654	37	338
31	9.5	21	.53	5.7	12	.18	---	---	---
TOTAL	20829.0	---	58340.41	2822.8	---	956.08	4270.9	---	2141.14
YEAR	64166.0		78464.25						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE, PR--Continued
 WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI-MENT, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	SEDI-MENT, DIS-CHARGE, SUS-PENDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
JAN 1992							
05...	1805	16400	1730	76600	63	70	75
05...	1935	39400	1710	182000	65	70	73
MAY							
19...	1803	4110	2790	31000	30	38	44
23...	1526	4115	678	7530	38	--	50
25...	0148	4290	748	8660	50	59	--
26...	1623	6240	4510	76000	35	43	50
MAY 1993							
01...	1500	3770	3170	32500	35	40	51
JUL							
11...	1821	24200	7360	481000	39	43	51

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
JAN 1992							
05...	--	81	97	99	99	100	100
05...	79	81	98	99	99	100	100
MAY							
19...	58	71	85	94	97	99	100
23...	51	52	79	89	93	95	97
25...	63	73	91	96	98	99	100
26...	56	64	85	95	99	99	100
MAY 1993							
01...	64	77	90	97	98	99	99.6
JUL							
11...	64	74	93	99	99.8	99.9	100

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
 50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BLW DAMSITE, PR--Continued
 WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
NOV 1991					
20...	1120	5.1	83	1.14	98
21...	2014	7950	193	4140	90
22...	2217	13400	125	4520	85
JAN 1992					
05...	1750	14050	2280	86500	98
05...	1915	34500	1680	156000	99
05...	2155	74760	1970	398000	99
07...	1155	2860	365	2820	99
08...	1233	166	264	118	99
MAY					
23...	1531	4115	513	5700	83
23...	2234	3650	360	3550	72
25...	2150	4110	593	4110	94
26...	0335	30600	427	35300	99
JUL					
28...	1045	4950	489	6530	91
SEP					
23...	1520	33	175	16	99
OCT					
06...	1649	1860	1390	6980	93
APR 1993					
14...	1430	6.8	326	6.0	95
23...	1055	4.2	111	1.3	97
MAY					
01...	1515	9520	361	9280	75
02...	1913	12000	105	3410	87
JUL					
11...	1536	35900	680	65900	82
12...	1330	197	413	220	99

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059100 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW TRUJILLO ALTO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'35", long 66°00'15", 100 ft (30 m) downstream of Highway 181 bridge, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) northwest of Trujillo Alto plaza, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northeast of Lago Loiza Reservoir.

DRAINAGE AREA.--213 mi² (552 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1981 to current year.

REMARKS.--Flow controlled by Lago Loiza reservoir.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS./100 ML)
OCT 1992											
06...	0945	16	258	7.8	29.0	28	9.3	120	10	K500	K130
DEC 07...	1100	18	300	7.7	25.2	12	6.2	74	10	5500	480
FEB 1993											
09...	0950	15	430	7.1	25.6	27	10.8	131	15	2800	170
APR 08...	1115	15	440	7.9	32.0	2.3	12.2	160	11	280	K10
MAY 24...	1330	31	207	7.2	27.9	160	6.4	81	74	K130000	K120000
AUG 06...	1030	87	205	6.9	29.3	240	5.5	71	<10	K16000	570

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
06...	52	3	29	6.1	13	0.7	2.5	84	1.1	14	18
DEC 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	71	--	--	--
APR 08...	140	0	34	14	34	1	2.6	150	<0.5	19	33
MAY 24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	70	--	--	--
AUG 06...	120	5	15	11	25	1	2.9	46	--	24	29

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
06...	<0.10	21	130	5.62	12	0.870	0.020	0.890	0.030	0.47
DEC 07...	--	--	--	--	25	0.970	0.030	1.00	0.030	0.27
FEB 1993										
09...	--	--	--	--	33	0.480	0.020	0.500	0.060	0.44
APR 08...	0.20	26	253	10.1	6	0.270	0.030	0.300	0.070	0.73
MAY 24...	--	--	--	--	368	--	<0.010	0.100	0.030	0.27
AUG 06...	<0.10	35	210	49.3	18	--	<0.010	0.200	0.030	0.57

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50061000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAROLINA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°22'39", long 65°57'08", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on upstream right bank of Highway 3 bridge, at Km 11.5, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) southeast of Carolina Plaza, 3.3 mi (5.3 km) west of Canóvanas Plaza and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) southwest of Cerro San José.

DRAINAGE AREA.--243 mi² (629 km²).

WATER-STAGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1991 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 32.8 ft (10.0 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Flow regulated by Lago Loíza Dam. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum gage-height, 33.18 ft (10.113 m), Jan. 6, 1992; minimum, 3.91 ft (1.192 m), Aug. 6, 1991.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum gage-height, 27.31 ft (8.324 m), July 11; minimum 3.95 ft (1.204 m), June 5.

GAGE HEIGHT, FEET, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.90	6.18	6.28	6.36	4.76	5.06	5.18	6.68	4.60	4.71	4.92	5.08
2	5.43	5.61	6.81	6.15	5.30	5.47	5.31	8.61	4.58	5.62	5.88	6.11
3	5.44	5.53	4.93	4.96	5.51	5.85	5.44	5.78	4.53	4.83	5.01	5.21
4	5.53	7.91	6.11	5.90	5.33	6.06	5.55	4.88	4.50	5.48	4.97	5.14
5	5.26	6.67	5.04	5.14	5.27	6.23	5.69	5.59	4.48	4.77	4.99	5.19
6	5.78	6.04	5.48	5.05	4.97	6.38	5.81	5.29	4.47	4.79	5.70	6.09
7	6.24	6.24	5.68	6.38	4.87	6.51	5.90	5.22	4.54	5.96	5.04	5.54
8	6.29	5.76	5.23	6.26	4.80	6.63	6.05	4.91	4.62	5.04	5.00	5.06
9	5.33	5.31	4.98	4.97	4.75	6.67	6.37	5.79	4.69	5.64	5.02	5.76
10	6.01	5.98	4.83	5.82	4.63	6.20	6.54	6.29	4.71	5.44	5.00	5.11
11	5.82	5.92	4.84	5.01	4.64	5.78	6.67	5.02	4.69	14.75	4.98	6.05
12	5.02	5.45	4.85	4.89	4.77	5.63	7.11	4.80	4.68	8.96	5.01	5.32
13	4.95	5.61	5.03	4.85	4.75	5.53	6.36	4.95	4.70	6.57	5.00	5.29
14	5.01	5.51	6.32	4.75	4.79	5.44	5.45	7.61	5.52	6.47	5.70	5.33
15	5.10	6.03	6.78	4.65	4.85	5.50	5.12	6.08	5.58	5.43	5.28	5.33
16	5.17	5.41	5.44	4.69	4.96	5.79	5.16	4.82	5.37	6.90	7.45	5.36
17	5.20	5.46	5.33	5.55	4.94	6.19	5.05	4.77	4.72	5.69	6.33	6.47
18	5.88	7.84	5.92	4.77	4.99	6.43	4.97	4.67	4.62	5.29	5.21	6.44
19	5.75	6.66	5.07	4.74	5.01	6.62	4.95	5.32	11.36	5.85	5.13	5.97
20	5.16	6.53	4.79	4.74	5.09	6.73	5.01	4.67	9.97	4.99	5.10	6.08
21	5.03	6.42	4.85	4.71	5.50	6.82	5.32	4.65	6.25	5.00	5.19	5.40
22	6.08	6.74	5.05	5.81	5.27	6.91	5.38	4.64	6.13	6.93	6.13	5.25
23	5.45	5.77	5.51	5.36	4.95	6.81	5.16	4.75	5.48	10.77	6.13	5.59
24	5.46	6.14	5.63	4.95	4.87	5.96	5.08	4.92	5.51	8.60	5.21	6.21
25	5.39	5.14	5.17	4.97	4.91	5.56	5.14	4.90	4.83	6.54	5.85	6.15
26	5.97	5.00	9.61	4.82	5.07	5.04	5.26	5.76	4.62	6.24	5.08	5.28
27	5.19	6.04	7.45	5.33	5.04	4.97	5.35	5.59	4.69	6.24	5.10	5.16
28	5.20	10.98	6.47	5.34	5.03	4.96	5.45	6.07	4.68	5.68	5.15	5.77
29	5.19	6.90	6.75	6.79	---	5.00	5.85	4.73	5.30	5.09	5.20	5.64
30	5.92	10.11	8.30	5.00	---	5.09	6.55	4.69	5.15	5.83	5.20	6.47
31	5.95	---	6.78	4.75	---	5.12	---	4.66	---	4.97	5.14	---
MEAN	5.52	6.36	5.85	5.27	4.99	5.90	5.61	5.39	5.32	6.29	5.36	5.63
MAX	6.29	10.98	9.61	6.79	5.51	6.91	7.11	8.61	11.36	14.75	7.45	6.47
MIN	4.95	5.00	4.79	4.65	4.63	4.96	4.95	4.64	4.47	4.71	4.92	5.06

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50061800 RIO CANOVANAS NEAR CAMPO RICO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'08", long 65°53'21", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at center pier on downstream side of bridge, on paved secondary road, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) northeast of junction of Highways 185 and 186, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) south of Campo Rico, and 4.4 mi (7.1 km) south of Loíza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--9.84 mi² (25.48 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1967 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 225 ft (68 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	18	6.2	e22	43	16	9.3	6.4	229	9.5	6.9	13	6.7
2	16	5.7	e16	32	27	9.5	6.6	175	8.2	6.2	12	6.1
3	11	20	e14	29	37	9.1	6.7	30	7.9	11	12	5.9
4	8.4	96	49	27	e20	8.7	6.5	14	7.4	12	12	5.5
5	7.6	30	26	29	16	e8.4	6.7	11	6.9	6.8	11	37
6	9.4	14	32	35	14	e8.4	6.9	9.9	6.6	5.4	11	26
7	11	13	23	59	13	e8.4	7.1	8.9	6.2	8.2	10	13
8	9.3	9.8	19	39	13	e8.1	9.2	9.2	5.9	12	9.8	23
9	9.4	9.9	17	29	e12	8.2	8.3	42	6.3	8.3	9.5	24
10	9.7	e63	16	24	11	7.9	7.3	21	6.7	5.7	8.8	12
11	8.3	e13	14	23	11	7.9	7.0	15	6.4	701	8.8	8.7
12	7.9	e13	13	23	11	7.6	8.1	10	5.8	52	8.5	7.1
13	7.3	36	12	21	11	7.4	e12	8.9	5.7	19	7.8	7.0
14	10	14	16	22	10	7.5	e11	8.4	6.4	13	7.9	7.1
15	7.9	11	26	20	9.9	7.4	e9.8	9.8	6.3	18	8.3	6.6
16	7.0	40	15	19	10	9.6	9.6	8.4	6.3	39	13	21
17	7.2	25	14	18	9.9	13	7.0	7.6	5.5	15	9.9	39
18	12	52	14	17	9.8	9.0	6.2	7.4	4.9	11	7.5	38
19	8.1	31	15	17	9.9	8.4	5.8	7.4	156	10	6.9	26
20	13	32	13	17	15	7.9	6.3	6.9	99	9.8	6.5	19
21	7.5	108	12	16	24	8.2	9.4	6.9	16	9.7	6.3	13
22	7.0	135	36	20	16	7.3	6.6	6.9	11	92	6.8	10
23	8.6	50	20	30	12	8.2	6.7	8.1	8.9	286	13	10
24	7.0	32	28	18	11	10	6.0	8.4	8.9	81	8.7	11
25	6.7	23	32	31	10	8.6	5.9	27	7.3	36	7.2	8.9
26	6.2	e21	186	21	9.9	7.6	5.5	21	6.5	27	6.8	8.0
27	7.7	e159	49	20	9.9	6.9	5.3	39	6.1	26	6.4	12
28	8.0	e113	47	e32	9.7	6.5	5.6	31	5.6	19	6.5	13
29	6.2	e103	120	86	---	6.5	6.8	14	5.3	17	6.2	13
30	6.2	e79	199	29	---	6.5	41	12	7.2	15	6.2	102
31	9.4	---	46	20	---	6.7	---	10	---	14	7.2	---
TOTAL	279.0	1357.6	1161	866	389.0	254.7	253.3	824.1	456.7	1593.0	275.5	539.6
MEAN	9.00	45.3	37.5	27.9	13.9	8.22	8.44	26.6	15.2	51.4	8.89	18.0
MAX	18	159	199	86	37	13	41	229	156	701	13	102
MIN	6.2	5.7	12	16	9.7	6.5	5.3	6.9	4.9	5.4	6.2	5.5
AC-FT	553	2690	2300	1720	772	505	502	1630	906	3160	546	1070
CFSM	.91	4.60	3.81	2.84	1.41	.83	.86	2.70	1.55	5.22	.90	1.83
IN.	1.05	5.13	4.39	3.27	1.47	.96	.96	3.12	1.73	6.02	1.04	2.04

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1967 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	44.1	46.4	34.6	24.4	19.3	14.5	16.0	30.5	19.1	19.2	26.1	32.4															
MAX	273	125	116	62.4	48.4	36.2	53.2	93.2	63.7	63.7	137	103															
(WY)	1971	1985	1971	1969	1988	1969	1971	1969	1970	1979	1979	1979															
MIN	6.74	6.66	5.82	6.66	4.04	3.54	4.66	4.28	2.80	3.72	5.69	5.20															
(WY)	1968	1981	1968	1977	1977	1977	1984	1974	1974	1974	1991	1967															

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1967 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	8558.2	8249.5	
ANNUAL MEAN	23.4	22.6	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			27.6
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			58.0
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	376	Jan 5	11.0
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	4.0	Apr 25	3160
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	4.6	Apr 22	.80
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			1.5
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			15000
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			9.74
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	16980	16360	13.10
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.38	2.30	.80
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	32.35	31.19	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	40	39	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	11	10	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	5.9	6.4	5.3

e Estimated

Figure 21.--Northeastern river basins the Río Herrera to Río Antón Ruíz basins.

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063440 QUEBRADA SONADORA NEAR EL VERDE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'24", long 65°49'03", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, in Caribbean National Forest, at El Yunque, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) upstream from Río Espíritu Santo, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from Highway 186, and about 1.2 mi (1.9 km) south of El Verde.

DRAINAGE AREA.--1.01 mi² (2.62 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1983 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 1,230 ft (375 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e.17	e2.0	1.9	15	.24	.06	.09	36	.25	.34	.04	.05
2	e.16	e3.0	.95	12	1.2	.13	.09	73	.18	11	.03	.01
3	e.14	e3.5	.90	3.3	3.2	.07	6.6	13	.13	35	.02	.26
4	e.15	e4.6	28	2.0	.93	.04	.37	.55	.11	2.3	.02	4.0
5	e.15	e1.1	1.4	12	.44	.03	.24	1.8	.09	.47	.01	8.6
6	e.20	e.50	9.7	e36	.16	.03	.20	3.2	.08	.40	.01	8.5
7	e.25	e.26	.81	e60	.10	.02	.08	2.7	.08	30	.01	11
8	e.14	e.40	.46	e13	.07	.15	.12	5.6	.12	9.2	.01	12
9	e.14	e.60	.33	e6.8	.06	.03	16	16	.15	.71	.01	1.8
10	e.15	e4.0	.26	e7.8	.05	.01	3.5	1.5	4.1	.49	.01	.67
11	e.13	e.34	e.25	e5.2	.04	.01	.37	1.6	.34	e70	.03	.06
12	e.13	e.25	e.25	e4.1	9.9	.01	.24	.16	.14	e1.7	.01	.08
13	e.12	e.17	e.25	e4.1	.36	.01	17	.14	5.1	.22	.01	.15
14	e.12	e.17	e1.2	e3.5	.09	.01	3.4	23	.92	2.3	.00	.43
15	e.12	e.17	e1.2	2.9	.05	.05	1.5	.25	2.4	24	.39	39
16	e.12	e4.8	e.35	.91	.05	7.4	3.2	.08	1.4	10	6.4	39
17	e.11	e.42	e.52	.20	.05	1.2	3.4	.05	.25	.20	.47	8.2
18	e.11	e23	e.69	.10	.05	1.6	.39	.04	.52	.09	1.5	11
19	e.11	e3.2	.74	.12	.03	8.2	.35	.03	54	.12	1.7	3.2
20	e.12	e.94	.85	.07	51	.20	.84	.03	13	.08	.01	1.4
21	e.11	e17	.47	.04	e15	.06	1.3	.02	e1.0	.03	.01	1.1
22	e.12	e43	19	40	e4.0	.03	.19	.02	e18	15	3.6	3.0
23	e.11	e1.6	4.3	2.8	e1.0	15	.11	.18	2.1	39	1.7	2.2
24	e.10	12	25	2.3	e.15	12	.08	.35	3.4	14	.02	2.6
25	e.11	1.3	20	29	.14	1.4	.06	27	.94	.58	.01	.98
26	e.12	.83	61	.84	.16	.59	.13	17	.48	1.8	.02	1.2
27	e.12	30	14	3.1	.62	.39	.55	48	.31	1.6	.01	11
28	e.12	21	17	12	.10	.28	.35	2.8	.29	.13	.00	12
29	e.12	50	70	16	---	.18	21	.62	1.1	.08	.00	3.7
30	e.14	21	33	.69	---	.14	59	7.5	10	.05	.09	6.8
31	e2.7	---	50	.37	---	.10	---	.47	---	.05	.29	---
TOTAL	6.71	292.55	364.78	296.24	89.24	49.43	140.75	282.69	120.98	270.94	16.44	193.99
MEAN	.22	9.75	11.8	9.56	3.19	1.59	4.69	9.12	4.03	8.74	.53	6.47
MAX	2.7	50	70	60	51	15	59	73	54	70	6.4	39
MIN	.10	.17	.25	.04	.03	.01	.06	.02	.08	.03	.00	.01
AC-FT	13	580	724	588	177	98	279	561	240	537	33	385
CFSM	.21	9.66	11.7	9.46	3.16	1.58	4.65	9.03	3.99	8.65	.53	6.40
IN.	.25	10.78	13.44	10.91	3.29	1.82	5.18	10.41	4.46	9.98	.61	7.14

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1983 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	
MEAN	6.23	10.8	8.43	6.61	6.32	5.63	5.20	8.65	5.83	6.85	7.13	6.43
MAX	17.1	20.1	21.6	10.8	12.0	14.7	9.99	15.9	13.7	12.8	14.5	15.6
(WY)	1986	1985	1988	1988	1988	1990	1987	1992	1987	1983	1988	1989
MIN	.22	2.47	.95	3.41	1.59	1.59	1.09	4.02	.98	2.36	.53	2.34
(WY)	1993	1991	1990	1985	1992	1993	1984	1991	1985	1991	1993	1986

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1983 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	2399.74		2124.74			
ANNUAL MEAN	6.56		5.82		6.93	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					9.48	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					4.46	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	147	May 1	73	May 2	216	Dec 7 1987
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.09	Jul 7	.00	Aug 14	.00	Aug 14 1993
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.11	Oct 18	.01	Aug 4	.01	Aug 4 1993
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			792	Sep 15	2230	Dec 7 1987
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			7.56	Sep 15	9.42	Dec 7 1987
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			.00	Aug 14	.00	Aug 14 1993
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	4760		4210		5020	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	6.49		5.76		6.86	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	88.39		78.26		93.25	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	19		17		17	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.4		.47		2.8	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.17		.03		.48	

e Estimated

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063500 QUEBRADA TORONJA AT EL VERDE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'43", long 65°49'14", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, in Caribbean National Forest, at downstream side of culvert on Highway 186, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from Rio Espiritu Santo, and about 0.9 mi (1.4 km) south of El Verde.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.064 mi² (0.166 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1983 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder, crest-stage gage and concrete broad-V-notch crested weir. Elevation of gage is 876 ft (267 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.21	.24	e.60	6.8	.26	e.19	e.05	e.22	e.19	e.29	e.12	e.01
2	.20	.35	.36	3.7	.46	e.18	e.03	e12	e.24	e.92	e.09	e.01
3	.17	.42	.27	2.1	.68	e.18	e.03	e2.3	e.19	e4.1	e.07	e.03
4	.19	4.9	1.4	1.3	.32	e.43	e.03	e.29	e.18	e.54	e.06	e.33
5	.21	.23	.26	1.5	.24	e.40	e.02	e.22	e.17	e.31	e.05	e.08
6	.21	.12	1.2	3.4	.24	e.44	e.02	e.34	e.20	e.33	e.03	e.04
7	.20	.07	.20	5.0	.23	e.36	e.01	e.27	e.21	e5.8	e.02	e.07
8	.18	.08	.16	1.6	.21	e.54	e.03	e1.0	e.09	e1.1	e.03	e.04
9	.18	.14	.13	.91	.20	e.39	e.02	e1.1	e.19	e.44	e.04	e.02
10	.19	.74	.11	1.0	.19	e.24	e.01	e.31	e.17	e.38	e.05	e.02
11	.17	.09	.09	.74	.22	e.18	e.02	e.27	e.13	e11	e.06	e.01
12	.17	.07	.08	.59	.52	e.14	e.03	e.18	e.14	e1.7	e.05	e.01
13	.16	.06	.08	.59	.23	e.20	e1.3	e.19	e.21	e.77	e.05	e.07
14	.16	.05	.17	.51	.20	e.18	e.06	e.86	e.19	e.69	e.05	e.02
15	.16	.06	.18	.40	.21	e.20	e.02	e.23	e.30	e3.5	e.06	e1.7
16	.16	.81	.08	.39	.23	e.28	e.03	e.19	e.21	e3.6	e.28	e2.0
17	.15	.11	.07	.27	.23	e.16	e.04	e.22	e.15	e.67	e.06	e3.4
18	.15	3.3	.06	.20	.23	e.10	e.04	e.15	e.16	e.49	e.06	e.20
19	.15	.56	.06	.19	.22	e.19	e.03	e.11	e6.3	e.50	e.05	e.07
20	.16	.21	.05	.17	.49	e.10	e.07	e.21	e2.6	e.40	e.02	e.04
21	.15	1.9	.05	.15	1.7	e.11	e.07	e.11	e.45	e.33	e.03	e.03
22	.16	6.1	.85	3.8	e.50	e.08	e.05	e.25	e2.6	e1.2	e.06	e.03
23	.15	.81	.12	.71	e.27	e.17	e.04	e.25	e.45	e7.0	e.06	e.03
24	.14	.59	.76	.39	e.23	e.18	e.04	e.70	e.55	e3.8	e.03	e.04
25	.15	.25	1.8	4.0	e.21	e.09	e.05	e2.5	e.40	e.81	e.03	e.04
26	.16	.21	7.6	.45	e.21	e.04	e.06	e1.8	e.32	e.61	e.03	e.04
27	.16	2.0	.81	.44	e.21	e.07	e.06	e7.5	e.30	e.50	e.03	e.10
28	.16	3.4	1.5	.44	e.20	e.09	e.07	e1.0	e.34	e.34	e.03	e.10
29	.15	9.5	8.2	.85	---	e.08	e2.9	e.57	e.30	e.26	e.02	e.06
30	.17	e9.4	9.8	.30	---	e.10	e3.0	e.49	e.48	e.17	e.04	e.20
31	.33	---	11	.24	---	e.10	---	e.37	---	e.12	e.02	---
TOTAL	5.41	46.77	48.10	43.13	9.34	6.19	8.23	36.20	18.41	52.67	1.68	8.84
MEAN	.17	1.56	1.55	1.39	.33	.20	.27	1.17	.61	1.70	.054	.29
MAX	.33	9.5	11	6.8	1.7	.54	3.0	12	6.3	11	.28	3.4
MIN	.14	.05	.05	.15	.19	.04	.01	.11	.09	.12	.02	.01
AC-FT	11	93	95	86	19	12	16	72	37	104	3.3	18
CFSM	2.91	26.0	25.9	23.2	5.56	3.33	4.57	19.5	10.2	28.3	.90	4.91
IN.	3.35	29.00	29.82	26.74	5.79	3.84	5.10	22.44	11.41	32.66	1.04	5.48

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1983 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	
MEAN	.32	.69	.52	.38	.25	.23	.21	.41	.28	.36	.28	.29
MAX	1.35	1.56	1.55	1.39	.44	.63	.61	1.17	.61	1.70	.54	.61
(WY)	1986	1993	1993	1993	1988	1990	1987	1993	1987	1993	1988	1989
MIN	.059	.15	.091	.14	.092	.054	.035	.11	.056	.046	.054	.060
(WY)	1992	1991	1990	1986	1987	1992	1984	1991	1991	1991	1993	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1983 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	171.61	284.97	
ANNUAL MEAN	.47	.78	.35
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			.78
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			.17
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	11	Dec 31	12
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.03	Mar 15	.01
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.04	Mar 24	.02
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			33
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			1.94
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	340	565	254
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	7.81	13.0	5.84
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	106.40	176.68	79.40
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.81	1.9	.71
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.17	.20	.15
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.05	.03	.05

e Estimated

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063800 RIO ESPIRITU SANTO NEAR RIO GRANDE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'37", long 65°48'49", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at left abutment, on downstream side of bridge on Highway 966, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from Quebrada Jiménez, and 1.9 mi (3.1 km) southeast of Río Grande.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.62 mi² (22.33 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1959 to April 1963 (annual low-flow and occasional measurements only), August 1966 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 40 ft (12 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e20	e14	e90	e120	e35	e16	e9.8	e300	e17	e19	e24	e20
2	e20	e12	e60	e80	e45	e15	e9.8	e350	e16	e30	e22	e12
3	e15	e100	e50	e70	e70	e14	e15	e90	e14	e90	e21	e11
4	e15	e350	e180	e70	e40	e14	e11	e40	e13	e45	e20	e10
5	e16	e70	e60	e100	e35	e13	e10	e28	e12	e20	e20	e130
6	e16	e40	e90	e130	e30	e13	e18	e30	e12	e17	e18	e58
7	e19	e39	e60	e220	e28	e12	e10	e32	e11	e170	e17	e40
8	e15	e25	e40	e100	e27	e14	e10	e33	e12	e90	e16	e100
9	e15	e100	e32	e70	e26	e12	e19	e160	e15	e30	e16	46
10	e22	e200	e30	e56	e24	e12	e19	e50	e25	e20	e14	e50
11	e16	e35	e23	e58	e22	e12	e11	e35	e17	e500	e15	e20
12	e15	e40	e22	e60	e32	e12	e13	e25	e11	e110	e14	e13
13	e14	e45	e21	e58	e27	e12	e25	e23	e14	e35	e13	e19
14	e13	e25	e35	e66	e22	e11	e20	e30	e16	e30	e13	e18
15	e13	e25	e60	e54	e21	e11	e15	e25	e15	e80	e15	e130
16	e13	e140	e35	e58	e21	e45	e11	e20	e14	e90	e46	e160
17	e13	e80	e27	e45	e21	e35	e9.8	e18	e11	e29	e25	e120
18	e14	e220	e32	e40	e20	e20	e9.6	e17	e10	e25	e14	e60
19	e14	e100	e35	e40	e19	e14	e10	e17	e200	e22	e13	e50
20	e40	e80	e25	e35	e70	e12	e32	e16	e120	e20	e11	e25
21	e20	e150	e24	e30	e120	e13	e31	e18	e30	e17	e10	e18
22	e15	e400	e130	e150	e25	e11	e13	e15	e44	e100	e14	e16
23	e25	e100	e50	e80	e20	e25	e45	e19	e20	e350	e76	e16
24	e12	e110	e110	e60	e19	e50	e15	e19	e32	e150	e21	e25
25	e13	e80	e150	e170	e17	e19	e12	e76	e19	e58	e12	e18
26	e12	e76	e400	e62	e17	e15	e11	e60	e17	e54	e10	e15
27	e13	e350	e140	e90	e17	e14	e15	e115	e14	e50	e9.2	e35
28	e15	e300	e180	e100	e16	e12	e25	e70	e15	e45	e9.2	e50
29	e12	e250	e350	e220	---	e11	e40	e23	e14	e30	e9.8	e45
30	e11	e230	e300	e60	---	e10	e200	e26	e40	e25	e40	e100
31	e12	---	e130	e40	---	e10	---	e20	---	e25	e30	---
TOTAL	498	3786	2971	2592	886	509	695.0	1800	820	2376	608.2	1430
MEAN	16.1	126	95.8	83.6	31.6	16.4	23.2	58.1	27.3	76.6	19.6	47.7
MAX	40	400	400	220	120	50	200	350	200	500	76	160
MIN	11	12	21	30	16	10	9.6	15	10	17	9.2	10
AC-FT	988	7510	5890	5140	1760	1010	1380	3570	1630	4710	1210	2840
CFSM	1.86	14.6	11.1	9.70	3.67	1.90	2.69	6.74	3.17	8.89	2.28	5.53
IN.	2.15	16.34	12.82	11.19	3.82	2.20	3.00	7.77	3.54	10.25	2.62	6.17

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1966 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	
MEAN	63.2	87.1	75.8	53.2	50.2	40.6	45.1	70.4	47.1	52.5	61.0	56.8																	
MAX	202	196	179	119	117	153	119	185	120	114	123	191																	
(WY)	1971	1985	1971	1969	1982	1990	1981	1979	1970	1983	1988	1989																	
MIN	12.3	29.1	18.1	18.5	10.8	13.0	6.27	14.9	10.0	11.1	19.6	17.7																	
(WY)	1969	1982	1990	1977	1983	1977	1984	1973	1975	1975	1993	1971																	

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1966 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	20503.5		18971.2			
ANNUAL MEAN	56.0		52.0		59.1	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					98.6	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					37.3	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1010	May 1	500	Jul 11	2600	Dec 7 1987
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	5.0	Jul 7	9.2	Aug 27	4.1	Jul 3 1975
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	6.1	Jul 1	11	Mar 30	4.4	Jun 30 1975
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW					19200	Aug 13 1990
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE					15.74	Aug 13 1990
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	40670		37630		42780	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	6.50		6.03		6.85	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	88.48		81.87		93.08	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	140		124		125	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	21		25		26	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	9.0		12		11	

e Estimated

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063800 RIO ESPIRITU SANTO NEAR RIO GRANDE, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958, 1961-66, 1968 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992	08...	1250	14	8.0	28.5	2.0	7.8	100	<10	240	230
DEC	16...	1055	22	7.4	22.2	4.2	8.3	110	<10	410	30
FEB 1993	22...	1155	18	7.0	21.2	5.1	8.3	112	19	K700	290
APR	15...	1200	15	6.8	26.0	3.5	5.5	66	11	K130	2200
JUN	10...	1230	39	6.9	29.1	2.7	6.0	76	<10	280	450
AUG	09...	1200	16	6.8	28.3	2.9	5.3	67	<10	3500	2700

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992	40	0	8.8	4.3	8.7	0.6	0.50	43	<0.5	1.7	10
DEC	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	30	--	--	--
FEB 1993	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	21	--	--	--
APR	30	1	6.3	3.4	7.1	0.6	0.70	33	<0.5	2.4	10
JUN	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	23	--	--	--
AUG	44	0	9.5	4.9	9.6	0.6	5.5	47	--	1.9	15

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDEED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992	<0.10	22	82	3.18	3	0.080	0.020	0.100	0.040	0.36
DEC	--	--	--	--	<1	0.160	0.140	0.300	5.80	2.40
FEB 1993	--	--	--	--	<1	--	<0.010	0.100	0.010	0.19
APR	<0.10	18	68	2.81	12	--	<0.010	0.100	0.040	0.26
JUN	--	--	--	--	9	--	<0.010	0.100	0.010	0.29
AUG	<0.10	23	100	4.32	7	--	<0.010	0.100	0.010	0.19

K = non-ideal count

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50064200 RIO GRANDE NEAR EL VERDE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'54", long 65°50'30", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank 250 ft (7.6 m) upstream side of bridge at Hwy 960, 0.05 mi (0.08 km) southwest of junction of Highways 956 and 960, 1.1 mi (1.8 km) west of El Verde, and 2.7 mi (4.3 km) south of Rio Grande.

DRAINAGE AREA.--7.31 mi² (18.93 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1967 to December 1970, January 1972 to September 1982, August 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 131 ft (40 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	13	8.5	43	85	21	9.7	5.6	208	10	11	12	9.8
2	13	7.7	33	49	28	9.3	5.6	218	9.6	16	11	6.8
3	9.7	54	29	44	48	9.1	9.4	54	8.5	63	11	6.2
4	9.5	197	98	45	26	8.8	7.3	24	7.9	23	10	5.3
5	10	44	42	67	21	8.4	5.9	17	7.3	11	10	75
6	9.9	22	56	82	19	8.3	11	19	7.1	9.9	9.7	31
7	12	21	27	134	18	8.1	5.8	20	6.7	103	9.0	23
8	10	12	22	57	17	8.6	5.8	20	7.1	51	9.0	61
9	10	28	20	43	16	7.9	11	100	8.0	17	8.4	27
10	14	91	18	33	15	7.6	11	33	12	12	7.8	30
11	10	17	17	34	14	7.4	5.9	21	10	373	8.1	12
12	9.3	20	16	35	20	7.2	7.2	16	6.8	50	7.5	7.3
13	8.7	24	15	32	17	7.1	15	14	8.7	22	6.9	11
14	8.7	13	20	37	14	7.3	11	22	10	17	6.7	10
15	8.5	13	42	29	13	7.0	8.9	16	8.9	50	8.1	75
16	8.5	67	19	31	13	27	7.5	12	8.2	56	26	90
17	8.7	35	16	24	13	21	6.2	11	6.7	18	13	72
18	9.2	109	22	22	13	12	5.4	11	6.1	14	7.4	37
19	9.3	47	23	22	12	8.7	5.3	10	138	13	6.9	23
20	22	35	15	20	52	7.5	19	9.8	78	12	6.2	11
21	9.3	82	14	18	77	7.9	18	11	16	10	5.7	9.9
22	8.1	225	73	85	24	6.7	7.2	9.5	28	67	7.8	9.3
23	15	64	29	54	14	17	27	12	14	210	41	13
24	8.6	68	74	32	12	33	9.9	12	20	109	9.0	15
25	7.4	45	97	105	11	12	6.5	47	12	34	6.5	8.3
26	7.1	41	225	34	11	9.3	6.1	37	9.6	33	6.7	7.3
27	7.6	189	72	55	11	8.7	7.2	87	8.8	29	5.5	32
28	8.6	144	97	72	10	6.8	14	32	9.2	23	5.3	30
29	7.0	124	198	145	---	6.3	22	14	8.9	15	5.6	24
30	7.1	112	159	33	---	6.2	137	16	26	14	23	63
31	7.4	---	92	24	---	6.4	---	12	---	14	17	---
TOTAL	307.2	1959.2	1723	1582	580	318.3	424.7	1145.3	518.1	1499.9	327.8	835.2
MEAN	9.91	65.3	55.6	51.0	20.7	10.3	14.2	36.9	17.3	48.4	10.6	27.8
MAX	22	225	225	145	77	33	137	218	138	373	41	90
MIN	7.0	7.7	14	18	10	6.2	5.3	9.5	6.1	9.9	5.3	5.3
AC-FT	609	3890	3420	3140	1150	631	842	2270	1030	2980	650	1660
CFSM	1.36	8.93	7.60	6.98	2.83	1.40	1.94	5.05	2.36	6.62	1.45	3.81
IN.	1.56	9.97	8.77	8.05	2.95	1.62	2.16	5.83	2.64	7.63	1.67	4.25

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1967 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	64.1	73.7	51.8	44.0	31.3	22.5	30.3	58.8	33.2	38.6	44.5	49.6															
MAX	392	172	140	151	76.4	54.4	119	203	86.5	109	90.0	153															
(WY)	1971	1970	1971	1969	1969	1969	1978	1969	1968	1969	1968	1975															
MIN	8.45	14.3	13.8	10.1	5.80	4.50	8.55	10.2	6.22	9.05	7.39	12.4															
(WY)	1969	1981	1968	1977	1977	1977	1975	1974	1975	1991	1991	1967															

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1967 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	11346.3	11220.7	
ANNUAL MEAN	31.0	30.7	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			43.4
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			87.1
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	405	373	25.8
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.7	5.3	191
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	4.1	6.5	1991
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		2980	17400
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		11.62	15.50
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW		4.8	1.6
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	22510	22260	31410
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	4.24	4.21	5.93
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	57.74	57.10	80.58
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	71	75	84
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	16	14	18
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	6.5	7.1	7.2

RIO MAMEYES BASIN

50065500 RIO MAMEYES NEAR SABANA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'46", long 65°45'04", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, at bridge on Highway 988, 1.4 mi (2.3 km) west of Sabana, 2.0 mi (3.2 km) downstream from Río de la Mina, and 3.2 mi (5.1 km) southeast of Mameyes.

DRAINAGE AREA.--6.88 mi² (17.82 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1967 to December 1973, June 1983 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 275 ft (84 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	22	40	52	108	46	e28	28	145	75	34	50	e32
2	19	51	44	89	47	e39	26	250	53	51	56	e50
3	17	84	42	67	50	e32	51	127	48	121	53	e45
4	23	331	80	e56	48	e26	24	46	44	42	51	e84
5	25	68	41	e94	42	25	25	43	39	39	47	e45
6	49	65	86	e96	39	24	23	32	37	36	46	e110
7	28	48	37	e72	37	24	20	32	42	105	46	e100
8	25	40	33	e54	35	29	19	74	41	93	44	e52
9	26	48	30	e46	32	23	62	e205	42	66	42	e49
10	26	141	28	e46	31	22	35	e62	74	49	44	e35
11	21	36	28	e45	30	21	22	e35	37	342	47	e38
12	22	39	25	e43	97	20	22	e27	32	78	41	e36
13	20	35	25	50	44	26	31	e27	66	59	37	e35
14	19	49	28	52	34	21	26	159	39	83	34	e27
15	18	39	35	47	30	25	22	46	74	158	45	e60
16	19	85	26	45	27	83	38	35	49	152	76	e400
17	19	62	23	34	28	45	36	30	31	80	54	e100
18	19	181	25	29	28	32	51	30	37	69	69	e92
19	19	65	24	29	25	68	32	e28	274	60	73	e30
20	31	79	24	27	161	34	43	e33	e126	50	43	e26
21	21	70	23	24	129	26	32	e31	e43	46	34	e24
22	46	199	71	174	42	22	21	e28	77	101	53	e23
23	30	68	31	54	60	76	20	e28	42	218	66	e28
24	21	63	68	34	40	95	18	e31	39	103	38	e22
25	20	53	70	104	32	35	19	92	44	69	32	e52
26	19	40	246	36	e30	40	28	50	51	73	30	e21
27	19	101	73	57	e32	28	32	236	39	66	27	e40
28	18	108	87	105	e28	29	34	65	33	50	29	e30
29	25	145	678	178	---	24	65	40	45	47	28	e46
30	27	105	262	62	---	23	526	59	89	47	39	e52
31	61	---	146	53	---	24	---	68	---	48	65	---
TOTAL	774	2538	2491	2010	1304	1069	1431	2194	1762	2635	1439	1784
MEAN	25.0	84.6	80.4	64.8	46.6	34.5	47.7	70.8	58.7	85.0	46.4	59.5
MAX	61	331	678	178	161	95	526	250	274	342	76	400
MIN	17	35	23	24	25	20	18	27	31	34	27	21
AC-FT	1540	5030	4940	3990	2590	2120	2840	4350	3490	5230	2850	3540
CFSM	3.63	12.3	11.7	9.42	6.77	5.01	6.93	10.3	8.54	12.4	6.75	8.64
IN.	4.18	13.72	13.47	10.87	7.05	5.78	7.74	11.86	9.53	14.25	7.78	9.65

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1967 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	68.7	84.8	62.9	55.2	41.0	39.5	42.1	68.9	57.2	51.7	54.6	57.3															
MAX	240	191	164	105	68.0	79.7	83.1	147	112	93.4	81.4	166															
(WY)	1971	1985	1971	1969	1988	1990	1973	1970	1970	1969	1988	1989															
MIN	20.3	36.3	16.6	25.0	21.7	18.1	14.5	18.7	12.4	20.5	28.0	26.6															
(WY)	1969	1974	1990	1985	1968	1968	1984	1973	1985	1971	1985	1986															

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1967 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	21127	21431	
ANNUAL MEAN	57.7	58.7	57.8
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			78.0
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			41.2
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	754	May 1	2780
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	16	Apr 6	6.9
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	19	Feb 29	9.4
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			20500
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			13.19
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			5.1
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	41910	42510	41890
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	8.39	8.53	8.41
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	114.23	115.88	114.20
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	106	102	104
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	39	42	34
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	20	23	16

e Estimated

RIO SABANA BASIN

50067000 RIO SABANA AT SABANA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'52", long 65°43'52", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank along Highway 988, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) north of junction of Highways 988 and 983 in Sabana, and 3.3 mi (5.3 km) south of Luquillo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.96 mi² (10.26 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1979 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 260 ft (80 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	8.9	11	20	29	15	7.4	2.3	27	10	7.6	8.1	10
2	7.4	17	18	24	16	8.1	2.3	33	6.9	8.9	7.6	3.8
3	7.0	14	18	21	17	6.9	2.8	18	6.3	29	7.2	5.0
4	8.6	183	20	18	16	6.4	2.4	8.7	5.9	9.7	7.0	10
5	15	25	15	32	14	5.9	2.6	12	5.5	6.9	6.7	17
6	74	17	43	36	14	5.7	2.3	7.1	5.4	7.2	6.6	7.3
7	12	16	15	27	13	5.2	e2.6	4.5	5.2	35	6.5	78
8	11	13	14	17	13	5.3	e2.6	127	5.6	20	6.1	34
9	12	12	13	14	12	4.8	e2.6	185	6.0	8.8	6.3	13
10	9.3	28	12	14	12	5.4	e2.2	26	15	7.5	6.3	6.5
11	7.5	11	13	13	13	3.9	e2.4	17	5.9	234	5.9	5.8
12	7.7	11	11	13	29	3.9	e2.2	9.0	6.6	23	5.4	7.3
13	7.7	18	13	12	18	4.7	e2.2	7.2	20	12	5.3	6.2
14	7.2	44	19	15	13	3.9	e2.1	27	12	11	5.0	4.8
15	7.5	19	17	13	11	3.7	e2.1	8.5	18	74	5.8	8.6
16	7.5	30	14	14	11	9.7	e2.6	6.4	12	59	9.0	212
17	13	19	11	13	11	5.2	e3.0	5.8	5.9	14	6.0	16
18	9.9	66	12	12	12	3.6	e4.0	17	5.8	11	19	14
19	7.2	25	14	12	11	7.7	e6.0	6.1	241	10	15	8.1
20	7.7	32	12	12	14	3.4	e4.0	6.0	65	9.1	5.1	6.5
21	6.6	21	11	12	24	2.8	e2.3	5.5	13	8.8	4.6	5.9
22	7.0	50	26	46	11	2.6	2.0	5.4	18	36	5.0	6.3
23	6.8	22	13	22	11	3.3	2.0	6.5	10	170	7.9	12
24	6.6	18	19	14	10	7.2	2.0	21	8.5	25	7.9	9.1
25	6.6	16	20	20	9.1	3.5	1.9	31	7.8	15	4.7	24
26	6.5	15	140	14	8.7	2.9	2.1	13	7.4	12	4.2	8.3
27	6.5	35	25	18	8.7	2.6	2.8	126	6.9	11	4.1	15
28	6.2	55	22	63	7.9	2.7	2.3	22	7.4	9.9	4.1	13
29	10	73	454	61	---	2.7	6.1	10	8.5	9.3	4.1	53
30	11	49	152	19	---	2.5	278	10	21	8.8	5.3	46
31	37	---	38	16	---	2.3	---	8.0	---	8.6	12	---
TOTAL	358.9	965	1244	666	375.4	145.9	392.8	816.7	572.5	912.1	213.8	666.5
MEAN	11.6	32.2	40.1	21.5	13.4	4.71	13.1	26.3	19.1	29.4	6.90	22.2
MAX	74	183	454	63	29	9.7	278	185	241	234	19	212
MIN	6.2	11	11	12	7.9	2.3	1.9	4.5	5.2	6.9	4.1	3.8
AC-FT	712	1910	2470	1320	745	289	779	1620	1140	1810	424	1320
CFSM	2.92	8.12	10.1	5.43	3.39	1.19	3.31	6.65	4.82	7.43	1.74	5.61
IN.	3.37	9.07	11.69	6.26	3.53	1.37	3.69	7.67	5.38	8.57	2.01	6.26

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1980 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	21.9	32.5	25.3	13.2	11.8	12.1	12.9	34.6	21.8	15.6	17.0	17.1		
MAX	66.4	79.7	64.1	33.0	22.2	36.0	33.5	63.9	50.6	31.3	32.7	56.3		
(WY)	1986	1988	1982	1992	1988	1987	1990	1982	1987	1989	1988	1989		
MIN	6.48	8.15	3.92	6.12	2.94	3.78	2.20	14.8	4.70	5.84	6.39	7.23		
(WY)	1983	1981	1990	1986	1983	1980	1984	1990	1985	1986	1985	1987		

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1980 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	8002.7		7329.6			
ANNUAL MEAN	21.9		20.1		19.7	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					28.2	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					11.9	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	454		454		887	
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	2.2		1.9		.96	
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	2.9		2.2		1.0	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			4840		9600	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			16.11		19.74	
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW					.86	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	15870		14540		14270	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	5.52		5.07		4.97	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	75.18		68.85		67.59	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	36		34		36	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	11		11		8.7	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	6.2		3.6		2.9	

e Estimated

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°17'56", long 65°41'42", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank off Highway 976, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from Highway 977 bridge, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) downstream from Quebrada Peñón, 1.1 mi (1.8 km) northeast of Colonia Paraiso, and 3.3 mi (5.3 km) southwest of Fajardo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--14.9 mi² (38.6 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1960-61 (occasional low and peak-flow measurements only), March 1961 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Datum of gage is 137.60 ft (41.940 m) above mean sea level. Due to flood damage, gage datum has had changes as follows: Mar. 24, 1961 to May 5, 1969, 138.95 ft (42.352 m); May 6, 1969 to Mar. 16, 1972, 135.05 ft (41.163 m); Mar. 17, 1972 to Mar 25, 1975, 138.60 ft (42.245 m).

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Low flow affected by diversions for water supply about 400 m upstream from gaging station (estimated mean daily discharges is 9.0 ft³/s (0.255 m³/s). Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	35	25	67	106	15	8.7	16	159	31	19	27	40
2	21	59	54	87	14	12	15	128	14	18	27	23
3	16	90	53	72	16	10	20	57	12	84	26	44
4	e15	245	65	65	16	8.1	16	19	12	25	25	39
5	e30	61	51	133	14	7.9	14	26	11	18	24	131
6	e120	71	283	90	12	7.9	13	20	11	24	23	38
7	e21	57	73	59	12	7.6	12	12	10	65	22	212
8	e19	28	57	46	11	7.5	14	166	10	60	21	183
9	e24	42	51	45	11	7.2	14	478	11	22	24	52
10	e17	91	47	35	10	6.9	14	44	19	17	21	46
11	e14	24	45	34	9.6	7.2	12	27	13	641	22	31
12	e14	23	42	34	30	7.9	13	10	11	103	20	29
13	e13	22	41	32	14	8.3	12	9.7	27	37	19	31
14	e13	73	56	40	11	7.9	12	56	16	24	19	22
15	e13	77	51	29	9.5	7.9	11	13	24	132	25	102
16	e24	143	40	29	9.5	61	14	10	24	113	48	e743
17	e29	70	38	26	10	35	16	9.9	13	28	26	71
18	e17	268	36	24	14	23	215	43	15	21	23	61
19	e11	101	36	24	10	35	28	9.5	401	18	40	20
20	e18	90	39	22	90	26	32	9.0	157	15	20	14
21	e11	63	35	21	70	e19	21	8.9	38	13	19	13
22	e12	242	86	142	14	e17	12	8.5	80	125	17	12
23	e8.9	80	46	51	13	e58	11	11	29	445	38	16
24	e9.0	65	85	26	11	e72	9.6	25	25	103	30	13
25	e8.0	39	78	36	9.5	25	8.9	61	21	57	19	39
26	e7.4	32	406	24	9.2	35	9.0	30	19	59	17	12
27	6.6	185	107	34	10	21	11	312	17	47	15	32
28	6.4	235	122	199	8.7	21	11	57	16	37	18	18
29	7.6	186	1370	120	---	19	9.2	23	28	32	15	35
30	18	180	391	23	---	31	651	19	55	31	64	47
31	68	---	146	18	---	19	---	27	---	29	36	---
TOTAL	646.9	2967	4097	1726	484.0	640.0	1266.7	1888.5	1170	2462	790	2169
MEAN	20.9	98.9	132	55.7	17.3	20.6	42.2	60.9	39.0	79.4	25.5	72.3
MAX	120	268	1370	199	90	72	651	478	401	641	64	743
MIN	6.4	22	35	18	8.7	6.9	8.9	8.5	10	13	15	12
AC-FT	1280	5890	8130	3420	960	1270	2510	3750	2320	4880	1570	4300
CFSM	1.40	6.64	8.87	3.74	1.16	1.39	2.83	4.09	2.62	5.33	1.71	4.85
IN.	1.62	7.41	10.23	4.31	1.21	1.60	3.16	4.71	2.92	6.15	1.97	5.42

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1961 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1961	1962	1963	1964	1965	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	96.9	106	81.3	45.3	37.1	35.7	46.1	96.0	61.2	51.4	57.9	86.9																					
MAX	260	295	237	101	80.4	109	129	399	166	132	159	421																					
(WY)	1971	1975	1976	1969	1982	1987	1963	1979	1962	1969	1979	1989																					
MIN	19.1	30.8	14.9	15.4	10.8	9.70	4.02	17.7	10.0	12.5	25.5	19.1																					
(WY)	1969	1981	1990	1977	1983	1977	1984	1973	1985	1992	1993	1991																					

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1961 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	20160.3		20307.1			
ANNUAL MEAN	55.1		55.6		67.3	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					140	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					38.2	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1370		1370		8800	
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	4.0		6.4		1.0	
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	4.8		7.5		1.5	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	39990		40280		48770	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.70		3.73		4.52	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	50.33		50.70		61.39	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	118		116		128	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	22		24		34	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	7.4		10		12	

e Estimated

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1960 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
15...	1240	13	120	7.9	30.5	1.3	8.5	110	<10	K130	K100
DEC 03...	1100	50	108	7.6	25.9	4.3	8.4	105	<10	220	480
FEB 1993											
26...	1215	20	150	7.8	24.5	0.90	8.0	101	13	30	K110
APR 29...	1225	8.8	155	7.2	29.5	0.60	7.1	93	13	280	K150
JUN 18...	1230	16	153	7.0	30.0	0.40	7.5	99	<10	480	330
AUG 13...	1230	20	116	6.6	30.5	0.70	6.9	90	19	K150	230

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY TOT WH FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
15...	20	1	4.4	2.3	7.4	0.7	1.2	39	<0.5	7.1	9.0
DEC 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	36	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--
APR 29...	33	0	7.3	3.6	11	0.8	1.1	34	0.6	4.6	14
JUN 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	40	--	--	--
AUG 13...	32	2	6.9	3.5	13	1	1.3	52	--	3.6	14

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
15...	<0.10	16	60	3.24	<1	0.120	0.080	0.200	0.030	0.10
DEC 03...	--	--	--	--	<1	0.890	0.210	1.10	0.400	0.20
FEB 1993										
26...	--	--	--	--	<1	0.370	0.030	0.400	0.480	0.20
APR 29...	<0.10	26	88	2.09	<1	0.230	0.070	0.300	0.290	0.01
JUN 18...	--	--	--	--	5	0.380	0.020	0.400	0.450	0.05
AUG 13...	0.20	27	101	5.44	2	0.190	0.010	0.200	0.570	0.03

K = non-ideal count

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1992 15...	0.40	0.60	1.8	0.030	<1	<100	30	2	9	<10
DEC 03...	0.60	1.1	4.9	0.040	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993 26...	0.50	0.20	2.3	<0.010	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 29...	0.30	0.10	1.9	<0.010	<1	<100	30	<1	<1	<10
JUN 18...	0.60	0.40	2.7	0.040	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 13...	0.50	0.90	4.0	0.030	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1992 15...	2100	5	50	<0.10	<1	<1	60	<0.010	3	0.04
DEC 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993 26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 29...	70	<1	<10	<0.10	<1	<1	<10	<0.010	1	0.02
JUN 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993 09...	1030	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010

DATE	ENDRIN WATER UNFLTRD REC (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993 09...	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993 09...	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50072500 RIO FAJARDO BELOW FAJARDO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'35", long 65°38'47", 1.2 mi (1.9 km) southwest of Playa de Fajardo, and 0.5 mi (0.8 km) east of Fajardo plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--23.4 mi² (60.6 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992										
15...	0855	23	144	7.0	28.5	2.6	6.5	82	<10	250 K2100
DEC 03...	1245	26	140	7.4	26.0	2.9	8.2	92	49	460 780
FEB 1993										
26...	1345	32	150	7.2	25.5	6.7	8.2	93	49	460 780
APR 29...	1345	56	193	6.8	29.0	12	8.5	110	12	370 220
JUN 18...	1335	12	178	7.2	30.5	0.70	6.3	82	13	480 530
AUG 13...	1420	16	148	6.8	30.5	0.70	5.0	65	23	380 290

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CACO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CACO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1992											
15...	38	3	8.5	4.0	10	0.7	1.8	44	<0.5	8.2	16
DEC 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	43	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	43	--	--	--
APR 29...	40	--	8.9	4.3	14	1	1.3	41	0.6	6.6	16
JUN 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	44	--	--	--
AUG 13...	36	--	7.7	4.0	14	1	1.3	67	--	4.8	16

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
15...	0.10	21	91	5.7	<1	--	<0.010	<0.050	0.150	0.15
DEC 03...	--	--	--	--	6	0.280	0.020	0.300	0.120	0.38
FEB 1993										
26...	--	--	--	--	10	0.360	0.040	0.400	0.130	0.57
APR 29...	0.10	23	99	15.0	14	0.980	0.020	1.00	0.140	0.06
JUN 18...	--	--	--	--	4	0.440	0.060	0.500	0.130	0.77
AUG 13...	0.10	25	113	4.9	2	0.190	0.010	0.200	0.150	0.35

K = non-ideal count

RIO BLANCO BASIN

50074950 QUEBRADA GUABA NEAR NAGUABO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°17'02", long 65°47'20", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank, off Highway 191 at El Yunque Caribbean National Forest, 4.8 mi (7.7 km) southeast of Campamento Eliza Colberg, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) southeast of Mt. Britton, 2.0 mi (3.2 km) northwest of Pico del Este and 7.3 mi (11.7 km) southeast of Río Grande Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.05 mi² (0.13 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1992 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 2,100 ft (640 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1										.60	.64	.31
2										.59	.76	.29
3										.60	.67	.35
4										.63	.97	.40
5										.66	3.4	.38
6										.68	1.8	.37
7										.66	.59	.35
8										1.4	.43	.28
9										1.1	.30	.50
10										.95	.30	.28
11										.76	.88	.29
12										.80	.31	.24
13										.82	.57	.19
14										.83	.72	.23
15										.84	.37	.35
16										6.1	.34	.63
17										2.7	.38	.51
18										1.7	.31	.43
19										1.4	.33	.47
20										1.2	.30	1.7
21										1.1	.22	.68
22										.96	.18	.36
23									e.61	.86	.20	.50
24									.60	1.4	.25	.39
25									.59	1.3	.16	.26
26									.57	1.0	.26	.20
27									.62	1.3	.28	.16
28									.61	1.1	.22	.15
29									.59	.90	.23	.14
30									.64	.85	.33	.15
31									---	.79	.67	---
TOTAL									---	36.58	17.37	11.54
MEAN									---	1.18	.56	.38
MAX									---	6.1	3.4	1.7
MIN									---	.59	.16	.14
AC-FT									---	73	34	23
CFSM									---	9.83	4.67	3.21
IN.									---	11.34	5.38	3.58

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1992, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	---	1.18	.56	.38
MAX	---	1.18	.56	.38
(WY)	---	1992	1992	1992
MIN	---	1.18	.56	.38
(WY)	---	1992	1992	1992

e Estimated

RIO BLANCO BASIN

50074950 QUEBRADA GUABA NEAR NAGUABO, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.20	.40	e.37	e.60	e.29	e.22	.22	3.9	.28	.23	.23	.26
2	.18	.94	e.34	e.54	e.31	e.28	.22	2.3	.27	.33	.23	.22
3	.17	1.1	e.37	e.54	e.31	e.26	.49	.60	.29	.63	.22	.14
4	.16	2.7	e.74	e.40	e.31	e.25	.24	.34	.25	.25	.22	.13
5	.15	.62	e.40	e1.1	e.28	e.25	.26	.33	.23	.21	.22	.72
6	.23	.45	e1.1	e.80	e.27	e.25	.24	.31	.21	.29	.19	.20
7	.20	.29	e.34	e.78	e.26	e.24	.23	.27	.23	1.2	.18	.40
8	.17	.41	e.31	e.44	e.26	e.27	.24	.74	.25	.55	.19	.99
9	.21	.38	e.30	e.41	e.25	e.25	.24	.94	.26	.32	.20	.27
10	.19	1.2	e.29	e.41	e.24	e.24	.23	.43	.32	.34	.18	.33
11	.18	.30	e.29	e.41	e.24	.22	.21	.43	.23	4.0	.20	.18
12	.17	.46	e.29	e.37	e.40	.23	.24	.35	.23	.57	.18	.18
13	.18	.36	e.29	e.44	e.26	.26	.22	.33	.41	.48	.16	.26
14	.20	.32	e.31	e.41	e.23	.21	.22	.61	.24	.41	.17	.16
15	.21	.26	e.31	e.34	e.22	.21	.20	.31	.22	.94	.22	1.1
16	.24	1.0	e.28	e.44	e.21	.73	.19	.28	.19	.50	.31	1.1
17	.27	.35	e.29	e.34	e.20	.40	.16	.27	.18	.34	.15	.27
18	.28	1.0	e.30	e.34	e.20	.19	.17	.26	.27	.31	.20	.19
19	.26	.29	e.29	e.34	e.19	.20	.38	.27	1.8	.29	.18	.14
20	.30	.95	e.30	e.31	e1.6	.39	.59	.26	.54	.25	.14	.13
21	.30	.56	e.34	.30	e.60	.24	.31	.24	.28	.26	.13	.15
22	.77	1.6	e.27	e1.8	e.29	.19	.20	.23	.40	.96	.23	.14
23	.41	.38	.45	e.42	e.27	.58	.18	.25	.27	1.9	.28	.26
24	.28	.46	.53	e.36	e.25	.49	.20	.25	.27	.57	.17	.27
25	.27	.38	1.2	e.68	e.24	.30	.20	.81	.22	.42	.14	.17
26	.30	.28	2.3	e.31	e.25	.41	.26	.45	.23	.48	.13	.14
27	.27	1.3	.34	e.54	e.25	.27	.23	1.7	.22	.39	.13	.39
28	.26	.87	e.49	e1.3	e.23	.24	.40	.43	.23	.27	.14	.34
29	.25	2.3	e.74	e.90	---	.22	.34	.37	.32	.25	.12	.23
30	.25	e.98	e4.0	e.36	---	.25	2.2	.42	.35	.24	.24	.63
31	.37	---	e.72	e.30	---	.22	---	.32	---	.25	.18	---
TOTAL	7.88	22.89	18.89	17.03	8.91	8.96	9.71	19.00	9.69	18.43	5.86	10.09
MEAN	.25	.76	.61	.55	.32	.29	.32	.61	.32	.59	.19	.34
MAX	.77	2.7	4.0	1.8	1.6	.73	2.2	3.9	1.8	4.0	.31	1.1
MIN	.15	.26	.27	.30	.19	.19	.16	.23	.18	.21	.12	.13
AC-FT	16	45	37	34	18	18	19	38	19	37	12	20
CFSM	2.12	6.36	5.08	4.58	2.65	2.41	2.70	5.11	2.69	4.95	1.58	2.80
IN.	2.44	7.10	5.86	5.28	2.76	2.78	3.01	5.89	3.00	5.71	1.82	3.13

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1992	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992	1992	1992
MEAN	.25	.76	.61	.55	.32	.29	.32	.61	.32	.89	.37	.36
MAX	.25	.76	.61	.55	.32	.29	.32	.61	.32	1.18	.56	.38
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992	1992	1992
MIN	.25	.76	.61	.55	.32	.29	.32	.61	.32	.59	.19	.34
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1992 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	157.34	
ANNUAL MEAN	.43	.43
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN		.43 1993
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN		.43 1993
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	4.0 Dec 30	6.1 Jul 16 1992
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.12 Aug 29	.12 Aug 29 1993
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.15 Aug 24	.15 Aug 24 1993
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW	64 May 1	64 May 1 1993
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE	10.11 May 1	10.11 May 1 1993
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	312	312
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.59	3.59
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	48.78	48.81
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.80	.96
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.28	.30
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.18	.19

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Figure 22.--Southeastern river basins the Río Humacao to Río Seco basins.

RIO HUMACAO BASIN

50081000 RIO HUMACAO AT LAS PIEDRAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'27", long 65°52'11", Hydrologic unit 21010005, on left bank at downstream side of bridge on Highway 921, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) southeast of junction with Highway 30, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) downstream from Quebrada Blanca and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) south of Las Piedras.

DRAINAGE AREA.--6.65 mi² (17.22 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1958 to December 1967 (monthly discharge measurements), July 1974 to September 1977, October 1987 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 260 ft (79 m), from topographic map. Prior to July 1974, crest-stage gage at different datum. July 1974 to September 1977 at site 90 ft (27 m) upstream at present datum.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those above 1,000 ft³/s (28.3 m³/s) and estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	16	12	30	32	15	10	6.8	11	8.0	10	17	17
2	15	11	24	28	20	11	6.5	17	7.4	11	16	18
3	14	13	22	24	20	9.0	6.6	10	7.1	21	16	30
4	14	31	26	21	14	9.0	6.3	9.5	7.0	12	15	14
5	14	16	22	20	14	9.0	6.2	11	6.8	10	15	28
6	14	33	21	21	13	8.7	7.4	10	6.4	9.5	15	16
7	13	20	18	24	13	8.7	5.7	8.6	6.9	9.2	14	12
8	13	15	17	22	13	8.3	6.1	15	9.6	14	14	16
9	13	13	17	25	13	8.4	6.3	135	13	9.6	15	15
10	12	13	16	20	13	8.4	6.7	28	14	8.0	15	62
11	12	12	16	19	15	e10	5.5	14	11	335	14	29
12	12	12	16	19	14	e11	5.2	11	8.3	41	14	17
13	12	24	15	19	14	e10	13	10	9.6	20	13	15
14	12	13	15	20	12	e11	8.6	16	10	16	12	15
15	11	19	15	17	12	e9.6	7.6	12	14	13	13	16
16	13	18	14	19	11	e12	7.6	9.6	11	14	29	21
17	13	19	14	17	11	e11	7.3	9.8	8.2	12	16	14
18	12	26	15	18	11	e15	6.9	10	8.7	9.3	14	13
19	13	27	14	16	11	e14	21	8.9	239	8.4	13	12
20	12	20	14	16	12	e10	11	9.2	76	8.4	13	20
21	12	17	15	16	12	e8.0	9.7	8.9	21	8.8	12	12
22	14	20	15	18	11	e7.0	7.8	8.7	16	e204	13	12
23	12	16	14	18	12	e6.6	9.3	7.6	14	171	18	17
24	11	15	16	15	12	7.0	8.2	9.4	14	44	19	18
25	14	14	16	31	10	7.0	7.9	9.2	12	28	16	29
26	12	13	41	18	10	7.9	11	8.6	10	e34	14	18
27	11	21	20	18	10	6.9	11	16	9.4	e26	13	13
28	11	48	17	19	10	6.8	11	17	9.4	21	13	15
29	14	40	47	23	---	7.3	20	9.4	9.4	19	12	16
30	13	224	42	18	---	6.6	15	8.3	12	17	12	186
31	14	---	32	16	---	6.8	---	7.7	---	17	19	---
TOTAL	398	795	636	627	358	282.0	269.2	476.4	609.2	1181.2	464	736
MEAN	12.8	26.5	20.5	20.2	12.8	9.10	8.97	15.4	20.3	38.1	15.0	24.5
MAX	16	224	47	32	20	15	21	135	239	335	29	186
MIN	11	11	14	15	10	6.6	5.2	7.6	6.4	8.0	12	12
AC-FT	789	1580	1260	1240	710	559	534	945	1210	2340	920	1460
CFSM	1.93	3.98	3.09	3.04	1.92	1.37	1.35	2.31	3.05	5.73	2.25	3.69
IN.	2.23	4.45	3.56	3.51	2.00	1.58	1.51	2.66	3.41	6.61	2.60	4.12

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1974 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	
MEAN	32.8	42.6	34.6	19.9	14.8	11.4	9.24	15.3	15.9	19.8	19.3	30.7									
MAX	74.9	126	112	34.1	20.5	16.4	13.1	42.2	29.0	38.1	32.7	54.1									
(WY)	1975	1988	1988	1992	1988	1989	1976	1992	1992	1993	1977	1975									
MIN	12.8	17.0	11.5	10.8	11.0	9.10	5.88	7.26	5.91	7.95	9.45	10.0									
(WY)	1993	1990	1992	1990	1977	1993	1977	1990	1977	1990	1974	1990									

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1974 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	8341.5		6832.0			
ANNUAL MEAN	22.8		18.7		22.4	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					37.6	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					12.1	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	466		335		1670	
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	6.9		5.2		2.2	
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	7.3		6.1		2.8	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			1910		20800	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			6.13		34.40	
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			4.8			
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	16550		13550		16200	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.43		2.81		3.36	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	46.66		38.22		45.68	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	31		24		33	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	15		14		14	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	8.5		8.0		6.8	

e Estimated

RIO HUMACAO BASIN

50082000 RIO HUMACAO AT HIGHWAY 3 AT HUMACAO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18 08'49", long 65 49'37", at bridge on Highway 3, 300 ft (91 m) downstream from Quebrada Mariana, and 0.4 mi (0.6 km) south of Humacao.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.3 mi² (44.8 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-66, 1969 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (PERCENT SATURATION) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992										
16...	1145	12	498	7.2	30.5	6.2	4.8	63	35	40000 9300
DEC 17...	1100	6.4	317	6.6	25.3	1.8	6.1	80	<10	K600000 540000
FEB 1993										
12...	1245	7.5	313	7.2	29.0	11	7.4	96	23	600000 80000
APR 26...	1410	13	264	6.9	31.0	7.1	6.7	88	<10	23000 39000
MAY 26...	1310	4.3	329	7.2	28.0	4.5	6.1	78	42	21000 3800
AUG 10...	1300	17	301	6.8	32.0	2.9	4.3	56	15	33000 4500

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WH TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY, TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
16...	53	0	14	4.2	18	2	2.4	84	<0.5	12	19
DEC 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	70	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	80	--	--	--
APR 26...	94	5	26	7.1	29	1	2.1	93	<0.5	13	32
MAY 26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	89	--	--	--
AUG 10...	85	2	23	6.6	26	1	2.3	120	--	9.6	27

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
16...	0.10	32	210	6.80	12	0.740	0.030	0.770	0.250	0.53
DEC 17...	--	--	--	--	22	0.870	0.030	0.900	0.730	0.47
FEB 1993										
12...	--	--	--	--	19	0.760	0.040	0.800	1.30	0.40
APR 26...	0.10	39	204	7.16	11	0.680	0.020	0.700	0.310	0.29
MAY 26...	--	--	--	--	24	0.930	0.070	1.00	0.620	0.48
AUG 10...	0.10	39	206	9.46	11	0.980	0.020	1.00	0.250	0.15

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUAYANES BASIN

50083500 RIO GUAYANES AT YABUCOA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'33", long 65°54'03", at bridge on Highway 182, 1.4 mi (2.2 km) west-northwest of Yabucoa plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.2 mi² (44.6 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-62, 1968-70, 1980 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
19...	1150	17	175	7.4	26.5	3.6	6.7	81	<10	530	200
DEC 17...	0945	17	190	7.6	21.8	4.8	7.7	94	<10	760	210
FEB 1993											
12...	1420	50	111	7.2	24.5	76	6.8	78	29	K60000	K53000
MAY 03...	1200	24	200	7.1	24.0	73	7.6	90	29	500	390
JUN 07...	1315	20	209	7.2	27.5	5.5	7.4	88	<10	5200	4100
AUG 11...	1430	18	150	6.6	27.5	52	5.8	61	20	60000	9700

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
19...	29	0	2.8	0.6	4.3	0.7	1.5	64	<0.5	4.2	10
DEC 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	61	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	52	--	--	--
MAY 03...	34	1	8.7	3.1	11	0.8	2.2	28	<0.5	4.6	12
JUN 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	56	--	--	--
AUG 11...	44	0	11	3.9	14	0.9	1.6	46	--	3.6	12

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
19...	0.10	16	49	2.25	6	0.310	0.010	0.320	0.050	0.15
DEC 17...	--	--	--	--	88	0.190	0.010	0.200	0.020	0.48
FEB 1993										
12...	--	--	--	--	182	0.390	0.010	0.400	0.020	1.2
MAY 03...	0.10	27	85	5.56	384	0.290	0.010	0.300	0.040	0.40
JUN 07...	--	--	--	--	4	0.190	0.010	0.200	0.050	0.35
AUG 11...	0.10	33	107	5.20	126	0.370	0.030	0.400	0.080	0.30

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUAYANES BASIN

50083500 RIO GUAYANES AT YABUCOA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1992 19...	0.20	2.3	4.0	0.050	<1	300	<10	20	<1	130
DEC 17...	0.50	1.1	3.4	0.060	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993 12...	1.4	1.2	3.5	0.320	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 03...	0.44	0.40	3.1	0.070	<1	<100	30	<1	<1	10
JUN 07...	<0.20	--	--	0.040	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 11...	0.30	0.30	--	0.050	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA-NESE, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE-NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY-LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB-STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1992 19...	4600	12	1100	0.40	<1	<1	<10	<0.010	2	0.03
DEC 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993 12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAY 03...	3300	2	130	<0.10	<1	<1	<10	<0.010	1	0.02
JUN 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR-DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI-AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI-ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO-SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993 18...	1135	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010

DATE	ENDRIN WATER UNFLTRD REC (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA-CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA-CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH-OXY-CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993 18...	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH-THA-LENES, POLY-CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER-THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX-APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI-THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2, 4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993 18...	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

RIO GUAYANES BASIN

50086500 RIO GUAYANES ABOVE MOUTH AT PLAYA DE GUAYANES, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'45", long 65°49'42", at old railroad crossing, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) from mouth, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west of Playa de Guayanés, and 3.5 mi (5.6 km) northeast of Yabucoa plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--34.0 mi² (88.1 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
19...	1350	44	186	7.6	28.5	22	7.8	100	40	350	K13
DEC 23...	1030	59	168	7.6	25.6	14	6.3	84	11	1200	450
MAR 1993											
03...	1245	71	210	7.6	25.0	18	7.1	90	53	370	280
APR 26...	1200	54	185	7.3	31.0	11	7.7	100	<10	280	320
MAY 26...	1220	64	168	7.1	24.0	62	7.6	98	24	K17000	7000
AUG 10...	1110	48	185	7.0	30.5	12	4.9	59	<10	550	260

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
19...	48	0	12	4.7	11	2	3.2	62	<0.5	8.7	13
DEC 23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	62	--	--	--
MAR 1993											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	67	--	--	--
APR 26...	51	0	13	4.6	19	1	1.7	64	<0.5	5.0	15
MAY 26...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	62	--	--	--
AUG 10...	66	1	17	5.7	22	1	2.6	72	--	6.9	22

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDE (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
19...	<0.10	35	136	16.2	24	0.390	0.010	0.400	0.960	0.94
DEC 23...	--	--	--	--	12	0.490	0.010	0.500	0.160	1.9
MAR 1993										
03...	--	--	--	--	36	0.390	0.010	0.400	0.110	1.1
APR 26...	<0.10	38	135	19.8	8	0.290	0.010	0.300	0.030	0.47
MAY 26...	--	--	--	--	81	0.390	0.010	0.400	0.080	0.72
AUG 10...	0.10	37	156	20.2	27	0.380	0.020	0.400	0.02	0.58

K = non-ideal count

RIO MAUNABO BASIN

50090500 RIO MAUNABO AT LIZAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°01'38", long 65°56'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank, off Highway 759 at Lizas, about 1.0 mi (1.6 km) downstream from Quebrada Coroco, and about 3.0 mi (4.8 km) northwest of Maunabo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--5.38 mi² (13.93 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1971 to January 1985, February 1991 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 230 ft (70 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges and July 18 to Sept. 30, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	9.4	9.0	20	23	14	7.7	5.5	9.1	4.9	6.1	16	11
2	8.7	8.4	16	17	13	7.8	6.0	8.6	4.9	17	16	11
3	8.1	17	42	13	12	7.4	7.0	8.0	4.4	40	16	11
4	7.7	106	24	13	12	7.3	5.8	4.8	4.1	9.8	14	12
5	7.2	17	17	14	11	7.3	5.4	4.4	3.8	6.9	12	25
6	7.1	42	15	24	11	7.1	5.5	4.9	3.5	6.2	11	13
7	6.9	43	13	19	11	6.9	5.0	4.1	3.8	9.2	11	13
8	6.6	17	12	13	11	7.1	5.0	4.2	6.3	8.5	12	22
9	6.4	14	11	12	10	7.2	5.0	25	4.2	6.0	11	21
10	6.5	16	11	12	9.9	7.0	4.8	10	9.3	5.5	14	28
11	6.1	12	10	13	10	7.2	5.0	5.9	5.0	577	11	16
12	5.8	11	10	13	21	6.8	6.0	4.8	4.1	36	12	13
13	5.8	10	10	11	13	7.7	9.2	4.8	7.3	20	14	13
14	5.5	13	9.5	11	11	6.9	11	96	21	19	15	12
15	5.6	10	9.0	10	10	6.6	6.4	10	18	28	16	11
16	7.4	12	8.6	10	9.9	6.4	5.4	6.6	18	40	37	12
17	6.4	13	8.4	10	9.9	6.6	5.0	6.4	13	19	12	11
18	5.3	86	8.3	10	9.6	6.6	4.7	7.4	42	21	10	11
19	6.6	28	8.2	11	9.2	8.8	6.3	5.2	200	19	10	9.9
20	8.0	58	8.1	10	9.1	16	4.4	6.6	62	19	10	9.6
21	96	18	7.9	9.5	8.7	7.9	4.3	5.5	12	19	9.8	11
22	36	26	7.6	16	8.4	6.6	4.4	5.0	11	62	9.7	11
23	12	17	7.6	14	8.6	7.3	5.1	5.3	7.4	77	25	11
24	25	42	8.6	11	8.4	6.3	4.8	11	6.5	44	26	10
25	18	17	10	18	8.0	6.3	4.6	11	5.7	28	11	12
26	12	14	42	11	7.9	6.7	4.6	24	5.2	21	10	11
27	9.0	18	14	15	7.7	6.1	4.6	62	5.0	20	11	10
28	7.9	32	10	19	7.6	5.9	4.4	16	4.7	16	10	12
29	13	18	13	56	---	5.7	4.3	8.2	5.3	16	10	e98
30	8.7	29	25	18	---	5.9	5.7	6.4	6.2	15	12	e37
31	20	---	12	15	---	5.6	---	5.3	---	16	14	---
TOTAL	394.7	773.4	428.8	471.5	292.9	222.7	165.2	396.5	508.6	1247.2	428.5	508.5
MEAN	12.7	25.8	13.8	15.2	10.5	7.18	5.51	12.8	17.0	40.2	13.8	16.9
MAX	96	106	42	56	21	16	11	96	200	577	37	98
MIN	5.3	8.4	7.6	9.5	7.6	5.6	4.3	4.1	3.5	5.5	9.7	9.6
AC-FT	783	1530	851	935	581	442	328	786	1010	2470	850	1010
CFSM	2.37	4.79	2.57	2.83	1.94	1.34	1.02	2.38	3.15	7.48	2.57	3.15
IN.	2.73	5.35	2.96	3.26	2.03	1.54	1.14	2.74	3.52	8.62	2.96	3.52

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1971 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	
MEAN	28.2	32.4	18.1	12.9	11.0	9.55	7.12	13.5	17.8	18.4	24.2	25.3												
MAX	52.6	88.9	35.2	27.1	24.5	18.9	10.8	25.1	47.1	40.2	131	81.5												
(WY)	1979	1978	1978	1992	1982	1976	1976	1979	1979	1993	1979	1979												
MIN	12.7	7.46	8.87	7.79	6.10	4.32	3.92	5.13	4.40	3.70	6.18	7.99												
(WY)	1982	1982	1981	1981	1979	1979	1979	1974	1974	1974	1974	1980												

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1971 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	6441.6	5838.5	
ANNUAL MEAN	17.6	16.0	18.3
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			36.7
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			12.1
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	290	Sep 20	2480
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.6	May 4	2.2
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	4.2	Apr 4	2.8
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			2680
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			10.65
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	12780	11580	13290
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.27	2.97	3.41
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	44.54	40.37	46.32
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	29	25	33
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	11	10	11
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	5.1	5.1	5.1

e Estimated

RIO MAUNABO BASIN

50091000 RIO MAUNABO AT MAUNABO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'24", long 65°54'19", at bridge on Highway 3, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) southwest of Maunabo plaza, and 1.3 mi (2.1 km) upstream from mouth.

DRAINAGE AREA.--12.4 mi² (32.1 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-66, 1975 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI (FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
20...	1250	7.1	255	7.3	29.5	4.6	6.3	83	<10	2100	300
DEC											
21...	1235	9.3	265	7.7	25.9	2.6	7.0	88	32	450	380
MAR 1993											
03...	1040	6.7	272	7.5	25.5	5.3	8.0	102	<10	570	330
APR											
28...	1345	8.7	257	7.2	33.0	2.8	8.1	106	<10	3300	K140
JUN											
07...	1200	9.4	253	7.1	29.0	2.8	7.5	90	<10	3300	490
AUG											
11...	1240	7.2	237	7.2	29.5	17	5.4	78	12	40000	6700

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
20...	82	1	20	7.7	22	1	1.5	82	<0.5	10	19
DEC											
21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	87	--	--	--
MAR 1993											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	90	--	--	--
APR											
28...	85	0	21	7.8	25	1	1.7	74	0.6	9.8	21
JUN											
07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	84	--	--	--
AUG											
11...	73	1	18	6.8	19	1	1.5	71	--	10	20

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
20...	0.20	40	170	3.24	3	0.390	0.010	0.400	0.060	0.54
DEC										
21...	--	--	--	--	2	0.390	0.010	0.400	0.020	0.68
MAR 1993										
03...	--	--	--	--	10	0.190	0.010	0.200	0.030	0.37
APR										
28...	0.10	40	179	4.19	7	0.090	0.010	0.100	0.030	0.57
JUN										
07...	--	--	--	--	5	0.690	0.010	0.700	0.070	0.13
AUG										
11...	0.10	36	154	3.0	19	0.190	0.010	0.200	0.010	0.39

K = non-ideal count

RIO CHICO BASIN

50091800 RIO CHICO AT PROVIDENCIA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'16", long 66°00'18", at flat low bridge 200 ft (61 m) south of Highway 3, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) above mouth, and 1.5 mi (2.4 km) southeast of Patillas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--4.9 mi² (12.8 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
20...	1120	0.67	418	7.6	27.5	2.2	7.3	92	<10	K1500	590
DEC 18...	1135	2.2	382	7.5	24.2	1.8	7.0	89	45	K1300	840
FEB 1993											
25...	1125	1.2	440	7.5	25.5	7.7	7.8	98	61	110	130
APR 28...	1145	1.5	510	6.3	32.5	5.7	6.7	88	55	K190	K10
MAY 28...	1200	5.4	307	7.6	28.5	15	7.1	90	48	3500	4100
AUG 11...	1130	4.3	344	6.9	28.5	3.6	6.9	83	24	24000	370

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
20...	95	1	22	11	31	1	2.6	110	<0.5	16	27
DEC 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
25...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
APR 28...	97	0	28	6.5	51	2	8.9	34	<0.5	43	61
MAY 28...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	74	--	--	--
AUG 11...	100	1	25	10	36	2	2.8	93	--	19	28

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
20...	0.20	31	210	0.38	<1	3.96	0.040	4.00	0.080	0.72
DEC 18...	--	--	--	--	11	0.490	0.010	0.500	0.130	0.47
FEB 1993										
25...	--	--	--	--	11	0.390	0.010	0.400	2.00	0.60
APR 28...	0.10	24	243	1.02	15	0.180	0.020	0.200	4.20	1.3
MAY 28...	--	--	--	--	65	0.090	0.010	0.100	1.90	0.30
AUG 11...	0.20	30	207	2.40	9	0.070	0.030	0.100	1.90	0.40

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS BASIN

50092000 RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS NEAR PATILLAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°02'04", long 66°01'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on left bank, at foot bridge, off Highway 184, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) upstream from Lago Patillas Dam and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northwest of Patillas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.3 mi² (47.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1959 to October 1965 (annual low-flow and occasional measurements only), January 1966 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 235 ft (72 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	59	13	65	34	e23	e18	22	8.3	121	29	e25	e44
2	149	13	65	23	e21	e21	14	22	57	28	e27	e38
3	67	13	71	19	e21	e20	12	8.6	56	26	e25	e56
4	44	14	95	17	e24	e24	11	6.7	172	26	e27	e35
5	37	20	60	e2100	e24	e22	11	6.1	73	36	e300	e31
6	34	22	49	e600	e50	e25	10	29	101	26	e88	e38
7	31	281	43	e130	e30	e47	15	32	63	24	e41	e34
8	31	618	39	e88	e27	e44	13	12	75	31	e35	e60
9	47	311	35	e68	e25	e21	12	9.5	62	27	e62	e120
10	38	174	32	e70	e28	e20	11	9.8	198	24	e41	e50
11	33	101	29	e58	e26	e19	12	11	134	52	e37	30
12	32	74	32	e49	e26	e19	116	9.8	372	e35	e31	27
13	28	59	28	e44	e23	e19	37	9.3	322	e26	e29	26
14	26	46	e27	e41	e30	e19	106	33	180	e31	e90	24
15	27	39	e25	e47	e32	e22	23	49	116	e29	e41	23
16	24	38	26	e38	e27	e16	9.2	235	116	e24	e39	27
17	25	31	24	e36	e24	e23	7.4	58	113	e62	e35	61
18	20	25	22	e33	e26	e27	68	35	79	e30	e31	78
19	18	22	21	e32	e24	e19	94	30	64	e37	e31	128
20	17	21	28	e32	e24	e19	90	27	56	e39	e33	e50
21	e17	23	36	e29	e21	e18	21	25	267	e41	e29	e40
22	e20	88	22	e28	e24	e19	11	24	91	e200	e27	e35
23	e21	52	20	e30	e24	e14	9.7	316	70	e37	e31	e31
24	e16	257	19	e30	e26	e15	9.6	382	57	e31	e33	e29
25	e15	106	19	e30	e24	e15	9.7	300	48	e100	e29	e27
26	14	60	18	e30	e32	e12	9.5	609	43	e33	e33	e25
27	15	224	18	e28	e30	e11	9.0	166	40	e28	e31	e23
28	15	181	18	e28	e27	e11	8.8	87	35	e24	e37	e23
29	15	117	17	e23	e26	e9.6	8.5	60	32	e20	e34	e23
30	16	77	25	e23	---	e9.2	8.5	124	31	e19	e34	e25
31	14	---	38	e23	---	16	---	60	---	e19	e46	---
TOTAL	965	3120	1066	3861	769	613.8	798.9	2794.1	3244	1194	1432	1261
MEAN	31.1	104	34.4	125	26.5	19.8	26.6	90.1	108	38.5	46.2	42.0
MAX	149	618	95	2100	50	47	116	609	372	200	300	128
MIN	14	13	17	17	21	9.2	7.4	6.1	31	19	25	23
AC-FT	1910	6190	2110	7660	1530	1220	1580	5540	6430	2370	2840	2500
CFSM	1.70	5.68	1.88	6.81	1.45	1.08	1.46	4.93	5.91	2.10	2.52	2.30
IN.	1.96	6.34	2.17	7.85	1.56	1.25	1.62	5.68	6.59	2.43	2.91	2.56

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1966 - 1992, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	
MEAN	107	98.3	54.3	34.9	28.4	24.4	22.6	55.6	67.9	65.0	73.4	86.1																
MAX	593	393	152	125	94.6	43.8	43.4	172	200	164	231	314																
(WY)	1971	1978	1971	1992	1982	1972	1976	1969	1979	1979	1979	1979																
MIN	14.4	16.1	8.63	14.0	7.09	6.74	9.98	10.3	13.1	14.1	23.0	12.1																
(WY)	1968	1968	1968	1973	1973	1968	1968	1974	1974	1974	1991	1967																

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1991 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1992 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1966 - 1992

ANNUAL TOTAL	14021	21118.8	
ANNUAL MEAN	38.4	57.7	59.2
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			117
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			27.7
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	618	Nov 8	2100
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	11	Sep 1	6.1
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	13	Aug 8	8.9
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			30900
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			4.6
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	27810	41890	42900
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.10	3.15	3.24
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	28.50	42.93	43.97
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	66	106	100
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	21	29	28
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	14	13	12

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS BASIN

50092000 RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS NEAR PATILLAS, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e38	24	101	68	34	17	14	84	15	12	e54	e42
2	e33	23	65	39	30	18	13	143	18	17	e48	e50
3	e32	24	94	30	28	17	13	33	17	47	e43	e50
4	e30	78	54	26	26	17	12	19	14	26	e39	e32
5	e34	39	41	26	25	17	12	31	12	23	e38	e31
6	e46	61	36	32	24	16	12	27	12	24	e36	e27
7	e30	59	31	45	24	16	12	15	12	29	e34	e27
8	e28	36	28	37	23	16	13	14	13	31	e34	e45
9	e27	32	27	31	23	16	19	27	12	20	e32	e43
10	e26	29	25	30	22	16	16	20	20	17	e36	e110
11	e29	27	22	30	22	15	13	13	18	e1700	e66	e44
12	e27	26	21	30	33	15	13	12	14	e200	e36	e32
13	e24	26	25	28	28	16	25	11	14	e110	e32	e31
14	24	25	23	28	23	16	20	288	37	e90	e30	e27
15	24	28	21	26	22	16	14	49	141	e78	e40	e25
16	24	29	19	26	21	16	14	27	43	e340	e540	e84
17	25	30	19	26	21	16	38	23	19	e84	e90	e32
18	25	47	18	26	20	16	15	27	125	e68	e54	e100
19	26	48	18	27	23	19	16	20	605	e84	e45	e30
20	45	106	17	26	21	18	16	21	256	e105	e40	e72
21	31	53	17	26	20	14	15	23	56	e96	e36	e29
22	34	63	18	43	19	13	14	21	149	e261	e90	e32
23	28	47	17	38	19	13	14	18	35	e287	e250	e580
24	35	63	18	28	19	13	14	17	42	e337	e120	e70
25	52	36	17	55	19	14	13	20	22	e150	e58	e36
26	34	29	43	32	19	14	14	22	17	e108	e43	e29
27	27	80	24	41	18	13	15	17	15	e94	e41	e26
28	25	130	19	49	18	13	14	16	13	e76	e41	e34
29	27	71	27	152	---	13	82	15	13	e67	e36	e74
30	26	129	27	57	---	13	29	14	22	e61	e34	e107
31	26	---	25	40	---	12	---	13	---	e58	e58	---
TOTAL	942	1498	957	1198	644	474	544	1100	1801	4700	2174	1951
MEAN	30.4	49.9	30.9	38.6	23.0	15.3	18.1	35.5	60.0	152	70.1	65.0
MAX	52	130	101	152	34	19	82	288	605	1700	540	580
MIN	24	23	17	26	18	12	12	11	12	12	30	25
AC-FT	1870	2970	1900	2380	1280	940	1080	2180	3570	9320	4310	3870
CFSM	1.66	2.73	1.69	2.11	1.26	.84	.99	1.94	3.28	8.28	3.83	3.55
IN.	1.91	3.05	1.95	2.44	1.31	.96	1.11	2.24	3.66	9.55	4.42	3.97

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1966 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	104	96.5	53.4	35.0	28.2	24.1	22.4	54.8	67.7	68.1	73.2	85.4																
MAX	593	393	152	125	94.6	43.8	43.4	172	200	164	231	314																
(WY)	1971	1978	1971	1992	1982	1972	1976	1969	1979	1979	1979	1979																
MIN	14.4	16.1	8.63	14.0	7.09	6.74	9.98	10.3	13.1	14.1	23.0	12.1																
(WY)	1968	1968	1968	1973	1973	1968	1968	1974	1974	1974	1991	1967																

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1966 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	19364.8	17983	
ANNUAL MEAN	52.9	49.3	58.9
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			117
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			27.7
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	2100	1700	4780
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	6.1	11	4.8
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	8.9	12	5.0
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		17400	30900
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		17.49	Jul 11
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			4.6
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	38410	35670	42640
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.89	2.69	3.22
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	39.36	36.56	43.70
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	90	84	100
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	29	27	28
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	15	14	12

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS BASIN

50092000 RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS NEAR PATILLAS, PR
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1960 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCHI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)
OCT 1992											
13...	0945	25	176	7.3	26.0	0.70	6.6	91	260	3000	54
JAN 1993											
14...	0925	27	156	6.4	23.0	1.2	8.6	108	560	430	49
APR											
06...	0930	13	192	7.7	24.0	1.8	8.4	106	510	390	59
JUL											
23...	1000	379	90	6.5	24.0	43	8.1	102	4700	12000	48

DATE	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)
OCT 1992											
13...	1	13	5.3	14	0.8	0.60	60	12	12	0.10	24
JAN 1993											
14...	0	12	4.7	13	0.8	0.60	51	9.7	12	<0.10	21
APR											
06...	2	14	5.8	15	0.9	0.60	80	12	12	0.10	23
JUL											
23...	1	11	4.9	14	0.9	0.60	23	11	9.7	0.20	24

DATE	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 180 DEG. C DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NH4)	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC (MG/L AS N)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHORUS DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHORUS ORTHO, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHATE, ORTHO, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS PO4)
OCT 1992											
13...	115	116	7.83	0.066	0.010	0.01	<0.20	0.020	0.030	<0.010	--
JAN 1993											
14...	95	105	7.65	0.130	0.020	0.03	<0.20	0.030	0.010	<0.010	--
APR											
06...	113	121	4.25	0.061	0.020	0.03	<0.20	0.020	0.020	0.010	0.03
JUL											
23...	105	120	123	0.230	0.030	0.04	0.40	0.050	0.010	0.010	0.03

DATE	ALUM-INUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS AL)	ARSENIC DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS BA)	BERYL-LIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS BE)	CADMIUM DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO-MIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS CR)	COBALT, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS CO)	COPPER, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS CU)	IRON, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS PB)	LITHIUM DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS LI)
OCT 1992											
13...	<10	1	14	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	<1	8	<1	<4
JAN 1993											
14...	30	<1	13	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	1	17	<1	<4
APR											
06...	<10	<1	15	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	<1	10	<1	<4
JUL											
23...	20	<1	17	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	<1	18	<1	<4

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS BASIN

50092000 RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS NEAR PATILLAS, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	MANGANESE, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS HG)	MOLYBDENUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS MO)	NICKEL, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS NI)	SELENIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS AG)	STRONTIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS SR)	VANADIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS V)	ZINC, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS ZN)
OCT 1992 13...	4	0.2	<10	1	<1	<1.0	46	<6	7
JAN 1993 14...	9	<0.1	<10	<1	<1	<1.0	42	<6	4
APR 06...	13	<0.1	<10	<1	<1	<1.0	49	<6	2
JUL 23...	5	<0.1	<10	<1	<1	<1.0	38	<6	7

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SEDIMENT, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	SEDIMENT, DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1992 13...	0945	25	17	1.13	56
JAN 1993 14...	0925	27	8.5	0.62	79
APR 06...	0930	13	19	0.66	89
JUL 23...	1000	379	109	112	87

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Figure 23.--South coast river basins the Río Salinas to Río Jacaguas basins.

RIO SALINAS BASIN

50100200 RIO LAPA NEAR RABO DEL BUEY, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'36", long 66°14'28", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on left bank, at bridge on Highway 1, Km 9.7, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) north of Rabo del Buey, and 4.4 mi (7.1 km) northeast of Salinas Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--9.92 mi² (25.69 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1953-63 (annual low-flow measurements only), September 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 394 ft (120 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	1.5	1.8	4.2	1.3	1.2	.90	.57	e2.5	.88	2.0	2.9	e1.8
2	1.6	1.7	2.9	1.3	1.1	.86	.54	e3.5	.87	2.0	2.8	e1.7
3	1.6	1.6	2.6	1.3	1.0	.83	.52	e1.6	1.1	2.0	2.7	e1.8
4	1.5	1.8	2.3	1.3	.99	.88	.53	e1.0	.84	2.0	2.7	4.9
5	1.4	1.8	2.1	1.2	.95	.88	.52	e1.1	.77	1.9	2.6	1.6
6	1.7	1.7	1.9	1.2	.94	.88	.46	e.94	.74	1.9	2.7	1.5
7	1.9	1.8	1.8	1.2	.94	.88	.47	e.88	.72	2.0	2.7	1.4
8	4.6	1.8	1.8	1.2	.92	.88	.51	e.94	.71	1.9	2.6	1.3
9	2.8	1.6	1.7	1.3	.88	.87	.50	e1.3	.72	1.9	2.7	1.2
10	2.0	1.6	1.6	1.3	.86	.78	.51	e1.0	.73	1.9	2.6	1.1
11	2.1	1.6	1.6	1.2	.83	.81	.59	e.80	.65	129	2.6	1.1
12	1.9	1.6	1.6	1.2	.91	.83	1.0	e.72	.60	17	2.5	1.1
13	2.0	1.9	2.4	1.2	.97	.83	1.2	e4.6	1.6	5.2	2.8	1.1
14	1.7	1.7	2.0	1.1	1.0	.83	1.6	e3.1	1.8	3.9	2.7	1.2
15	1.6	1.6	1.9	1.1	1.1	.84	e2.0	e2.0	49	3.4	2.8	1.3
16	1.6	1.5	1.8	1.1	1.1	.88	e1.0	e1.2	10	3.2	44	1.2
17	1.8	1.4	1.6	1.0	1.1	.88	e.62	e1.9	4.1	2.9	4.9	1.9
18	2.0	1.4	1.5	.95	1.1	.88	e6.2	e1.3	3.7	2.8	3.2	1.7
19	5.7	1.9	1.5	.88	1.0	.88	e3.0	e1.3	125	2.7	2.7	1.6
20	3.3	2.7	1.5	.88	.99	.88	e1.6	1.2	70	2.6	2.5	7.8
21	2.3	2.8	1.5	.86	.99	.86	e.94	1.1	10	2.5	2.4	2.1
22	3.6	2.0	1.5	.86	1.0	.83	e.82	1.1	6.0	10	2.3	1.7
23	2.9	2.1	1.6	.88	1.1	.81	e.70	1.7	4.1	6.2	2.7	4.5
24	13	2.0	1.5	.88	.99	.75	e.70	3.5	3.5	5.7	2.6	3.6
25	5.7	1.9	1.4	.84	.94	.69	e.66	4.0	3.0	4.9	2.4	4.4
26	3.1	1.8	1.5	.81	.94	.68	e.80	3.0	2.6	4.1	2.3	3.1
27	2.4	6.0	1.7	.83	.91	.65	e.94	1.7	2.4	3.7	e2.1	2.7
28	2.0	16	1.5	5.2	.88	.63	e4.0	1.3	2.2	3.5	e1.9	2.8
29	1.9	5.4	1.4	4.4	---	.61	e5.6	1.0	2.2	3.2	e1.9	2.7
30	1.8	9.7	1.3	2.0	---	.62	e2.6	.86	2.1	3.0	e1.8	8.0
31	1.7	---	1.3	1.4	---	.59	---	.83	---	2.9	e2.0	---
TOTAL	84.7	84.2	56.5	42.17	27.63	24.90	41.70	52.97	312.63	241.9	122.1	73.9
MEAN	2.73	2.81	1.82	1.36	.99	.80	1.39	1.71	10.4	7.80	3.94	2.46
MAX	13	16	4.2	5.2	1.2	.90	6.2	4.6	125	129	44	8.0
MIN	1.4	1.4	1.3	.81	.83	.59	.46	.72	.60	1.9	1.8	1.1
AC-FT	168	167	112	84	55	49	83	105	620	480	242	147
CFSM	.27	.28	.18	.14	.10	.08	.14	.17	1.04	.78	.39	.25
IN.	.32	.31	.21	.16	.10	.09	.16	.20	1.16	.90	.45	.27

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1988 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	19.2	8.01	2.36	15.1	3.59	1.16
MAX	76.1	28.4	6.09	68.8	12.4	2.08
(WY)	1991	1991	1991	1992	1991	1992
MIN	1.46	2.17	.96	.56	.49	.44
(WY)	1992	1992	1992	1990	1990	1990

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1988 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	4147.63	1165.30	
ANNUAL MEAN	11.3	3.19	6.40
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			11.2
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			3.13
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1080	129	1080
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.84	.46	.02
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.90	.50	.07
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		1050	15700
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		9.61	17.82
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW		.44	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	8230	2310	4630
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.13	.32	.64
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	15.43	4.33	8.69
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	7.8	4.1	8.4
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	2.1	1.6	1.4
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.4	.81	.24

e Estimated

RIO SALINAS BASIN

50100450 RIO MAJADA AT LA PLENA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°02'40", long 66°12'27", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on right bank, upstream side of bridge on Hwy 712, about 0.3 mi (0.5 km) southwest of La Plena.

DRAINAGE AREA.--16.7 mi² (43.3 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1973 to April 1979 (monthly measurements only), September 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 410 ft (125 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair. Some regulation at low flow upstream from station by local residents for agricultural purposes.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	4.9	3.5	16	4.1	3.3	1.3	.80	3.6	1.6	4.4	4.9	2.4
2	4.4	3.2	11	3.3	2.9	1.4	.80	3.5	1.3	4.3	4.5	2.3
3	4.6	3.2	8.6	3.2	3.0	1.2	.75	5.0	2.0	7.4	4.1	2.4
4	4.1	4.2	7.4	2.9	2.5	1.1	.75	2.2	1.7	7.3	3.9	2.2
5	4.3	4.1	6.2	2.8	2.3	1.1	.65	1.4	1.6	3.7	3.9	6.0
6	3.8	4.4	5.4	3.0	2.2	1.1	.61	1.6	1.7	2.1	4.3	4.4
7	6.0	5.1	4.8	3.0	2.2	1.1	.61	1.3	1.3	2.1	3.4	3.1
8	4.8	4.0	4.6	3.2	2.2	1.0	.54	1.2	1.2	2.8	3.1	2.6
9	4.4	3.9	4.4	3.0	2.1	1.1	.91	1.3	1.0	2.2	3.0	2.6
10	4.0	3.8	4.4	2.9	2.0	1.1	1.9	1.9	1.1	1.6	2.9	2.5
11	4.3	3.1	4.2	2.7	2.0	1.0	.97	1.4	1.1	152	3.4	2.2
12	3.7	2.8	4.0	2.6	2.5	1.0	1.1	1.1	.80	33	3.3	2.0
13	3.0	3.3	5.6	2.5	2.7	1.1	.98	.98	.86	14	3.0	1.9
14	2.7	3.1	4.7	2.5	2.3	1.2	1.6	6.7	2.2	8.4	3.0	2.0
15	2.9	3.0	4.0	2.5	2.0	1.2	2.4	4.2	18	7.9	3.4	2.0
16	3.2	8.2	3.6	2.4	1.9	1.1	2.8	2.3	12	9.1	28	2.2
17	3.3	5.6	3.7	2.4	1.8	1.1	1.2	1.6	4.4	6.9	8.6	5.6
18	3.1	3.8	3.7	2.3	1.8	1.3	.83	2.6	3.3	5.7	4.9	3.1
19	10	8.7	3.6	2.2	1.7	1.1	8.7	1.8	87	5.2	3.9	2.2
20	8.5	18	3.5	2.2	1.8	1.4	5.3	1.8	45	4.5	3.4	4.3
21	5.2	12	3.3	2.2	1.8	1.4	2.2	2.0	15	4.7	3.1	3.7
22	8.0	9.0	3.4	2.4	1.6	1.2	1.3	2.0	9.5	15	3.0	2.6
23	7.9	7.5	3.2	2.9	1.6	1.0	1.1	2.1	12	23	3.8	6.0
24	5.2	6.7	3.0	2.6	1.5	1.0	.98	2.6	19	19	3.2	7.7
25	5.5	5.2	3.0	2.7	1.5	1.0	.98	2.4	13	15	2.9	6.3
26	4.7	4.4	3.4	2.5	1.4	1.1	.92	2.7	9.2	9.1	2.6	4.6
27	4.2	11	3.8	2.6	1.3	.99	1.1	2.8	7.5	7.3	2.7	3.3
28	3.8	20	3.1	3.6	1.3	.92	1.3	2.5	5.0	6.2	2.6	4.4
29	3.9	12	3.1	14	---	.93	5.6	2.5	4.5	5.6	2.6	5.2
30	4.3	32	3.2	6.3	---	.95	7.8	2.4	5.1	5.2	2.5	15
31	3.7	---	3.6	4.1	---	.90	---	2.3	---	5.0	2.7	---
TOTAL	146.4	218.8	149.5	101.6	57.2	34.39	57.48	73.78	288.96	399.7	134.6	116.8
MEAN	4.72	7.29	4.82	3.28	2.04	1.11	1.92	2.38	9.63	12.9	4.34	3.89
MAX	10	32	16	14	3.3	1.4	8.7	6.7	87	152	28	15
MIN	2.7	2.8	3.0	2.2	1.3	.90	.54	.98	.80	1.6	2.5	1.9
AC-FT	290	434	297	202	113	68	114	146	573	793	267	232
CFSM	.28	.44	.29	.20	.12	.07	.11	.14	.58	.77	.26	.23
IN.	.33	.49	.33	.23	.13	.08	.13	.16	.64	.89	.30	.26

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1973 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	
MEAN	18.8	9.81	4.30	16.2	4.27	2.11	1.96	6.34	4.96	4.28	3.24	10.1										
MAX	76.4	25.2	9.67	68.8	12.1	3.92	3.69	25.5	12.1	12.9	7.74	30.1										
(WY)	1991	1991	1991	1992	1991	1991	1992	1992	1992	1993	1992	1989										
MIN	1.43	2.15	1.22	.98	.63	.59	.58	.25	.53	.62	.73	1.50										
(WY)	1992	1990	1990	1990	1990	1990	1990	1990	1990	1989	1989	1991										

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1973 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	4722.4		1779.21			
ANNUAL MEAN	12.9		4.87		7.23	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					12.1	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					1.61	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1520		152		1520	
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	1.5		.54		.05	
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	1.9		.67		.05	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			1030		1520	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			7.38		17.19	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	9370		3530		5230	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.77		.29		.43	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	10.52		3.96		5.88	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	13		8.5		9.9	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.0		3.0		2.4	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	2.3		1.1		.57	

RIO COAMO BASIN

50106100 RIO COAMO AT COAMO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°05'00", long 66°21'16", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on Highway 14 bridge, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) northeast from Parque Atlético, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) southeast from (W.C.P.R.) Antena de Radio.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.5 mi² (112.7 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1987 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 335 ft (110 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1986 TO SEPTEMBER 1987
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1					e6.2	e4.1	e2.1	4.0	22	18	9.7	3.9
2					e5.6	e4.1	e2.1	3.7	192	16	6.8	4.3
3					e5.4	e4.2	e2.0	3.7	201	15	7.6	4.1
4					e5.5	e4.2	e1.9	4.5	174	17	9.2	4.4
5					e5.4	e3.9	e2.5	4.9	161	28	12	4.0
6					e5.2	e3.8	e1.9	14	135	15	8.6	3.8
7					e5.0	e3.7	e1.2	6.0	91	15	7.0	3.6
8					e4.8	e3.7	e8.0	8.5	86	13	6.0	2.8
9					e4.6	e3.6	6.3	18	77	11	5.4	3.1
10					e7.0	e3.7	4.4	152	67	10	6.9	3.2
11				e1.2	e3.8	118	59	61	9.4	5.6	3.1	
12				e1.0	e3.6	150	22	52	9.0	5.3	22	
13				e3.0	e3.3	62	8.0	49	7.9	4.9	4.4	
14				e2.0	e2.8	76	4.8	43	8.4	4.9	3.3	
15				e1.0	e3.3	109	4.1	47	9.4	35	3.2	
16					e7.0	e3.8	73	3.7	40	17	3.0	
17					e6.0	e2.9	57	7.1	32	8.2	2.8	
18					e5.4	e2.9	33	85	21	8.0	6.7	38
19					e5.0	e3.1	20	81	24	7.6	6.4	13
20					e4.6	e2.7	13	44	60	7.7	5.5	11
21				e5.9	e4.5	e2.4	9.4	16	103	16	5.2	6.2
22				e5.6	e4.4	e2.4	8.1	8.1	189	12	4.8	6.2
23				e9.8	e4.5	e2.3	7.3	5.8	100	8.5	4.1	5.7
24				e8.0	e4.5	e2.5	6.0	11	66	8.0	4.1	5.7
25				e6.1	e4.4	e2.5	5.3	39	48	7.9	4.1	5.5
26				e5.8	e4.4	e2.2	4.5	63	39	7.0	3.6	4.5
27				e6.4	e4.6	e2.2	4.1	20	32	7.4	3.6	4.3
28				e5.7	e4.3	e2.1	3.9	9.4	26	8.4	3.6	3.8
29				e5.9	---	e2.1	3.8	83	23	7.4	3.4	3.6
30				e8.7	---	e2.0	3.8	70	22	6.5	3.1	9.1
31				e7.0	---	e2.0	---	40	---	12	3.4	---
TOTAL				---	200.3	95.9	827.5	903.3	2283	344.2	221.1	195.6
MEAN				---	7.15	3.09	27.6	29.1	76.1	11.1	7.13	6.52
MAX				---	30	4.2	150	152	201	28	35	38
MIN				---	4.3	2.0	1.9	3.7	21	6.5	3.1	2.8
AC-FT				---	397	190	1640	1790	4530	683	439	388
CFSM				---	.16	.07	.63	.67	1.75	.26	.16	.15
IN.				---	.17	.08	.71	.77	1.95	.29	.19	.17

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1987 - 1987, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	---	7.15	3.09	27.6	29.1	76.1	11.1	7.13	6.52
MAX	---	7.15	3.09	27.6	29.1	76.1	11.1	7.13	6.52
(WY)	---	1987	1987	1987	1987	1987	1987	1987	1987
MIN	---	7.15	3.09	27.6	29.1	76.1	11.1	7.13	6.52
(WY)	---	1987	1987	1987	1987	1987	1987	1987	1987

e Estimated

RIO COAMO BASIN

50106100 RIO COAMO AT COAMO, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.8	27	77	e50	e24	13	8.4	e10	4.6	e8.5	e2.0	e48
2	17	27	104	e54	e24	13	8.1	e9.0	4.4	e9.8	e1.8	e20
3	7.5	25	88	e43	e24	11	7.9	7.6	4.3	e8.0	e21	e10
4	6.3	25	76	e42	e24	10	8.4	7.8	4.3	e7.0	e2.8	e9.4
5	6.3	63	101	e38	e24	9.5	8.1	7.9	4.4	e5.8	e2.2	e8.8
6	5.7	156	71	e38	e24	9.5	23	8.8	4.4	e4.8	e1.9	e7.1
7	8.5	70	124	e36	e22	11	17	9.1	4.3	e4.3	e1.8	8.1
8	164	43	110	e36	e20	10	e8.6	8.9	4.2	e4.0	e1.6	8.6
9	26	23	93	e35	e19	10	e8.4	11	4.3	e3.8	e1.6	8.0
10	8.5	31	87	e35	e19	10	e8.0	12	4.2	e3.7	e1.7	8.9
11	6.0	17	118	e35	e18	10	e7.8	11	4.7	e3.7	e1.7	32
12	6.0	36	136	e34	e18	9.5	e7.4	9.5	4.9	e3.5	e1.7	28
13	4.9	29	125	e34	e18	9.6	e7.4	8.5	5.1	e3.3	e1.6	20
14	5.3	11	116	e33	e17	11	e8.0	8.2	5.2	e3.1	e1.5	23
15	5.0	8.2	107	e33	e16	11	e8.4	8.3	6.8	e3.1	e1.5	14
16	4.8	7.3	100	e33	e15	10	e9.7	7.6	5.8	e130	e1.6	12
17	11	14	84	e32	e14	11	e12	7.2	4.8	e170	e21	11
18	147	16	67	e30	14	9.9	e8.2	6.9	5.0	e24	e4.7	7.9
19	67	13	66	e29	13	8.5	e7.4	7.4	4.7	e13	e26	8.6
20	29	11	72	e28	13	8.3	e6.8	7.1	4.8	e10	e2.2	8.7
21	82	11	70	e27	12	8.5	e6.8	6.1	4.7	e8.3	e2.0	9.8
22	74	14	72	e28	12	8.2	e270	5.5	4.8	e7.4	e2.1	11
23	47	13	63	e27	11	8.3	e10	5.3	4.8	e7.0	e3.5	11
24	27	121	62	e27	12	7.8	e8.6	4.7	e12	e6.1	e146	13
25	22	e14	63	e27	12	8.1	e8.2	4.5	e10	e5.2	e63	8.3
26	21	e80	57	e27	14	8.5	e8.2	3.9	e8.5	e4.6	e13	6.8
27	74	564	61	e26	15	8.6	e7.6	4.2	e8.5	e4.5	e9.8	9.7
28	50	153	64	e26	12	9.8	e7.3	3.7	e8.0	e3.8	e6.8	7.1
29	37	149	55	e26	12	11	e7.6	4.0	e7.6	e3.5	e5.3	6.2
30	32	116	55	e26	---	9.7	e12	4.3	e7.2	e3.3	e4.2	38
31	29	---	e54	e25	---	9.2	---	4.4	---	e2.4	e4.1	---
TOTAL	1036.6	1887.5	2598	1020	492	303.5	535.3	224.4	171.3	479.5	361.7	423.0
MEAN	33.4	62.9	83.8	32.9	17.0	9.79	17.8	7.24	5.71	15.5	11.7	14.1
MAX	164	564	136	54	24	13	270	12	12	170	146	48
MIN	4.8	7.3	54	25	11	7.8	6.8	3.7	4.2	2.4	1.5	6.2
AC-FT	2060	3740	5150	2020	976	602	1060	445	340	951	717	839
CFSM	.77	1.45	1.93	.76	.39	.23	.41	.17	.13	.36	.27	.32
IN.	.89	1.61	2.22	.87	.42	.26	.46	.19	.15	.41	.31	.36

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1987 - 1988, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1987	1988	1988	1988	1988	1988	1987	1988	1988	1988	1988	1988
MEAN	33.4	62.9	83.8	32.9	12.1	6.44	22.7	18.2	40.9	13.3	9.40	10.3
MAX	33.4	62.9	83.8	32.9	17.0	9.79	27.6	29.1	76.1	15.5	11.7	14.1
(WY)	1988	1988	1988	1988	1988	1988	1987	1987	1988	1988	1988	1988
MIN	33.4	62.9	83.8	32.9	7.15	3.09	17.8	7.24	5.71	11.1	7.13	6.52
(WY)	1988	1988	1988	1988	1987	1987	1988	1988	1988	1987	1987	1987

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1988 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1987 - 1988

ANNUAL TOTAL	9532.8	
ANNUAL MEAN	26.0	26.0
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN		26.0
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN		26.0
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	564	Nov 27 1987
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	1.5	Aug 14 1988
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	1.6	Aug 9 1988
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW	1890	Oct 8 1987
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE	8.85	Oct 8 1987
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	18910	18870
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.60	.60
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	8.15	8.14
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	70	66
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	10	8.6
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.2	3.6

e Estimated

RIO COAMO BASIN

50106100 RIO COAMO AT COAMO, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1988 TO SEPTEMBER 1989
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	16	7.9	4.1	3.8	2.0	2.4	6.0	2.0	1.4	.85	.69	4.0
2	9.3	8.3	4.1	3.7	2.2	3.1	8.7	2.1	4.7	.85	.67	3.4
3	9.6	6.9	4.6	3.4	2.4	3.1	4.5	2.1	4.4	.87	1.7	2.9
4	10	6.4	4.1	3.6	2.2	2.9	3.2	1.8	7.1	.81	2.4	2.2
5	9.0	5.8	3.9	3.8	2.0	2.2	2.8	1.8	6.7	.83	11	1.9
6	8.0	5.0	3.9	3.4	2.2	2.0	2.6	1.8	4.0	.76	3.3	29
7	7.4	5.1	3.7	3.0	1.9	1.8	2.2	1.7	3.5	.91	2.7	19
8	6.9	5.0	3.7	2.7	2.0	2.0	1.9	1.5	3.1	.84	4.2	6.1
9	6.1	5.8	3.8	2.7	2.0	4.4	1.8	1.5	2.5	.75	2.6	27
10	29	6.0	3.7	2.8	2.3	3.6	1.8	1.7	2.2	.79	3.0	253
11	15	6.5	3.6	2.9	2.1	2.9	1.9	2.4	1.7	.87	135	48
12	10	9.2	3.6	3.5	2.0	3.9	2.1	2.4	1.1	.85	18	13
13	9.7	18	4.0	3.9	2.2	15	2.3	2.1	1.0	.78	8.9	7.0
14	8.8	25	3.8	3.2	2.4	11	2.2	1.8	1.0	.78	3.9	4.5
15	7.9	14	3.8	2.7	2.5	7.4	2.1	1.5	.98	.87	2.8	3.7
16	7.9	12	3.6	2.4	5.8	5.0	2.0	1.4	.97	.94	2.5	2.6
17	7.5	40	3.4	2.9	e8.3	4.8	2.3	1.4	1.1	.76	2.0	4.5
18	7.6	33	4.6	3.4	7.7	4.5	1.6	1.6	e.99	.81	3.0	315
19	7.4	22	3.9	3.1	4.8	6.9	1.6	1.7	e.96	.77	18	145
20	8.4	16	3.7	2.7	4.9	10	1.6	1.7	e.93	.68	5.5	110
21	10	13	3.2	2.5	3.8	5.4	1.6	1.5	e.89	.70	64	71
22	9.2	11	3.1	2.4	3.5	3.2	2.6	1.2	1.2	.75	10	53
23	9.7	12	3.2	2.5	3.4	3.2	1.7	1.1	.98	.77	8.2	264
24	9.0	12	3.2	2.3	3.1	3.0	1.5	1.1	.99	.73	7.8	203
25	7.6	23	3.4	2.3	3.0	2.8	1.5	1.2	.90	.73	8.3	84
26	18	21	3.7	2.2	2.6	3.1	3.8	1.3	.91	.70	4.6	54
27	15	11	3.4	2.2	2.6	2.7	1.9	1.6	.93	.73	3.9	41
28	7.9	7.3	3.1	2.1	2.8	2.6	2.0	1.5	.85	.73	9.6	77
29	6.6	5.1	3.2	2.1	---	2.5	2.1	2.1	.82	.69	5.5	91
30	12	4.5	4.0	2.0	---	2.5	2.0	1.6	.87	.68	8.3	58
31	14	---	4.2	2.0	---	5.8	---	1.4	---	.70	5.6	---
TOTAL	320.5	377.8	115.3	88.2	88.7	135.7	75.9	51.6	59.67	24.28	367.66	1997.8
MEAN	10.3	12.6	3.72	2.85	3.17	4.38	2.53	1.66	1.99	.78	11.9	66.6
MAX	29	40	4.6	3.9	8.3	15	8.7	2.4	7.1	.94	135	315
MIN	6.1	4.5	3.1	2.0	1.9	1.8	1.5	1.1	.82	.68	.67	1.9
AC-FT	636	749	229	175	176	269	151	102	118	48	729	3960
CFSM	.24	.29	.09	.07	.07	.10	.06	.04	.05	.02	.27	1.53
IN.	.27	.32	.10	.08	.08	.12	.06	.04	.05	.02	.31	1.71

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1987 - 1989, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1987	1988	1988	1988	1988	1988	1987	1988	1988	1987	1988	1989
MEAN	21.9	37.8	43.8	17.9	9.19	5.75	16.0	12.7	27.9	9.12	10.2	29.1
MAX	33.4	62.9	83.8	32.9	17.0	9.79	27.6	29.1	76.1	15.5	11.9	66.6
(WY)	1988	1988	1988	1988	1988	1988	1987	1987	1987	1988	1989	1989
MIN	10.3	12.6	3.72	2.85	3.17	3.09	2.53	1.66	1.99	.78	7.13	6.52
(WY)	1989	1989	1989	1989	1989	1987	1989	1989	1989	1989	1987	1987

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1988 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1989 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1987 - 1989

ANNUAL TOTAL	4824.3	3703.11	
ANNUAL MEAN	13.2	10.1	18.1
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			26.0
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			10.1
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	270	Apr 22	315
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	1.5	Aug 14	.67
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	1.6	Aug 9	.70
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			3000
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			9.57
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	9570	7350	13120
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.30	.23	.42
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	4.13	3.17	5.66
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	27	14	50
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	8.4	3.1	6.8
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	3.6	.91	1.8

e Estimated

RIO COAMO BASIN

50106100 RIO COAMO AT COAMO, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1989 TO SEPTEMBER 1990
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	47	32	12	8.9	e5.9	e5.2	e4.9	e6.9	e2.6	1.7	2.2	7.6
2	53	31	11	8.6	e5.8	e5.8	e4.6	e4.5	e2.2	1.4	2.1	4.8
3	65	30	11	7.8	e6.0	e4.8	e3.3	e2.8	e2.5	1.7	1.9	19
4	60	29	10	7.4	e6.2	e3.8	e3.6	e2.7	e3.1	1.4	2.9	6.1
5	52	29	10	6.0	e6.1	e4.2	e3.8	e2.5	e1.8	1.6	2.4	85
6	45	28	11	5.8	e5.1	e4.9	e3.8	e2.9	e1.6	1.9	2.1	48
7	38	27	11	5.6	e6.0	e5.8	e3.8	e3.6	e1.5	1.9	1.8	32
8	70	36	11	5.9	e7.4	e5.4	e3.8	e4.3	e1.4	2.0	1.6	28
9	33	30	11	6.3	e7.0	e4.3	e3.8	e4.7	e1.3	1.8	1.8	60
10	28	29	10	6.3	e8.0	e5.2	e3.7	e7.0	e1.4	e1.7	2.0	40
11	25	26	11	6.1	e7.0	e5.6	e3.4	e9.2	e1.4	e1.4	1.9	21
12	23	25	10	6.4	e15	e5.7	e4.7	e5.0	e1.4	e1.3	2.4	18
13	22	23	10	6.1	e11	e6.0	e4.3	e4.2	e1.6	e1.2	2.1	188
14	21	23	10	6.4	e10	e4.8	e3.7	e3.7	2.6	e1.3	2.3	414
15	24	22	10	6.4	e11	e3.8	e4.0	e3.9	6.3	e1.4	e2.5	139
16	27	22	11	5.7	e8.6	e3.0	e3.5	e3.0	5.1	e1.4	1.8	28
17	24	20	10	6.6	e8.2	e3.1	e5.8	e3.0	2.5	e1.4	1.6	15
18	27	20	9.3	6.1	e9.0	e3.3	e8.6	e3.0	2.4	e1.3	1.4	11
19	70	20	9.2	5.3	e6.6	e3.6	e12	e2.8	2.7	e1.5	1.4	8.5
20	238	19	9.3	5.8	e5.3	e3.9	e6.4	e2.4	3.7	e1.4	1.3	6.9
21	125	18	8.0	5.5	e5.0	e3.9	e4.7	e2.4	2.5	e1.3	1.2	6.0
22	90	17	7.8	5.6	e4.5	e3.8	e4.1	e2.4	2.1	e1.6	107	5.4
23	74	16	8.2	5.4	e4.3	e3.5	e4.3	e2.1	1.9	e1.6	9.8	6.2
24	67	16	8.4	5.5	e4.6	e3.1	e5.2	e2.0	1.7	1.7	4.5	21
25	79	16	8.1	5.7	e5.0	e2.6	e8.4	e2.0	2.0	1.7	3.6	172
26	62	15	8.1	6.4	e5.2	e2.7	e8.8	e1.7	2.3	1.6	3.4	116
27	53	15	7.6	e6.7	e4.9	e2.7	e5.0	e1.7	1.8	2.0	3.3	57
28	40	14	7.5	e6.8	e4.6	e3.0	e3.3	e2.2	1.6	2.8	160	44
29	53	13	7.8	e6.9	---	e3.7	e3.0	e2.8	1.8	2.4	308	44
30	39	12	8.2	e6.3	---	e4.0	4.6	e2.6	1.5	2.4	66	98
31	36	---	7.8	e6.1	---	e4.0	---	e2.7	---	2.1	15	---
TOTAL	1710	673	295.3	196.4	193.3	129.2	146.9	106.7	68.3	51.9	721.3	1749.5
MEAN	55.2	22.4	9.53	6.34	6.90	4.17	4.90	3.44	2.28	1.67	23.3	58.3
MAX	238	36	12	8.9	15	6.0	12	9.2	6.3	2.8	308	414
MIN	21	12	7.5	5.3	4.3	2.6	3.0	1.7	1.3	1.2	1.2	4.8
AC-FT	3390	1330	586	390	383	256	291	212	135	103	1430	3470
CFSM	1.27	.52	.22	.15	.16	.10	.11	.08	.05	.04	.53	1.34
IN.	1.46	.58	.25	.17	.17	.11	.13	.09	.06	.04	.62	1.50

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1987 - 1990, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1987	1988	1989	1990
MEAN	33.0	32.6	32.4	14.0
MAX	55.2	62.9	83.8	32.9
(WY)	1990	1988	1988	1988
MIN	10.3	12.6	3.72	2.85
(WY)	1989	1989	1989	1989

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1989 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1990 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1987 - 1990

ANNUAL TOTAL	5567.81	6041.8	
ANNUAL MEAN	15.3	16.6	17.6
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			26.0
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			10.1
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	315	Sep 18	414
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.67	Aug 2	1.2
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.70	Jul 27	1.3
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			4740
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			10.89
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			1.1
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	11040	11980	12740
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.35	.38	.40
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	4.76	5.17	5.49
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	38	38	47
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	3.1	5.7	6.1
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.91	1.7	1.8

e Estimated

RIO COAMO BASIN

50106100 RIO COAMO AT COAMO, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1990 TO SEPTEMBER 1991
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	219	114	19	25	10	8.2	6.4	12	4.3	4.1	4.2	56
2	115	102	18	21	9.9	7.5	6.8	12	5.3	3.2	3.7	8.9
3	48	91	19	20	9.5	7.7	6.7	7.8	5.3	3.0	3.9	5.2
4	27	88	19	18	10	8.1	6.9	7.2	4.7	2.8	3.6	4.5
5	23	94	17	18	14	8.5	7.0	6.2	4.6	2.5	3.2	4.1
6	23	78	16	18	16	8.3	6.5	5.5	4.3	2.4	2.8	4.1
7	21	72	16	18	12	8.2	7.1	5.3	4.1	2.5	2.4	134
8	61	64	15	18	10	7.8	7.2	5.2	4.0	32	2.2	18
9	175	62	15	18	9.8	8.2	7.5	5.5	3.9	11	2.2	6.8
10	170	61	15	17	10	7.7	6.7	5.4	3.9	4.1	2.2	6.3
11	111	59	16	16	12	7.7	6.9	55	4.0	3.5	2.0	5.5
12	170	60	17	16	66	7.4	6.4	8.2	5.5	3.2	2.0	5.0
13	357	57	14	16	28	7.2	6.5	8.7	4.4	3.0	1.8	4.9
14	381	51	14	15	13	7.1	6.5	11	3.5	2.7	6.7	4.7
15	348	48	15	14	11	6.9	6.7	7.5	3.2	2.9	5.4	4.5
16	545	48	15	13	9.8	6.9	7.1	6.4	3.0	153	3.6	4.3
17	278	49	14	13	9.8	6.7	6.7	6.4	2.7	25	3.0	5.5
18	222	46	13	12	8.7	6.7	7.1	6.3	2.4	9.1	3.5	6.2
19	236	43	13	11	8.8	6.8	8.0	6.0	2.3	6.1	2.7	118
20	273	181	13	11	8.9	6.8	7.2	6.0	2.5	5.0	2.6	29
21	1080	71	14	11	8.4	6.6	6.9	7.1	3.9	4.5	2.8	8.2
22	415	34	14	11	8.3	7.7	7.2	5.5	3.8	4.5	27	6.0
23	283	28	14	10	8.1	8.6	7.3	5.0	3.1	4.4	11	7.0
24	342	24	16	9.9	8.0	7.4	6.6	5.0	3.0	4.2	4.1	4.6
25	661	23	16	10	8.2	6.6	6.5	5.2	2.9	4.1	2.9	3.6
26	688	21	16	10	8.0	25	6.3	5.0	2.6	4.1	2.2	3.4
27	389	21	17	10	7.7	12	6.0	4.6	2.6	3.8	3.1	3.2
28	278	20	17	9.7	7.9	7.9	5.6	4.4	2.6	129	2.8	3.3
29	192	20	18	9.8	---	7.2	5.5	4.6	2.7	11	2.5	3.6
30	226	21	19	9.5	---	7.0	5.5	4.5	3.1	4.6	2.3	3.7
31	130	---	33	9.7	---	6.3	---	4.3	---	3.8	2.0	---
TOTAL	8487	1751	507	438.6	351.8	252.7	201.3	248.8	108.2	459.1	126.4	482.1
MEAN	274	58.4	16.4	14.1	12.6	8.15	6.71	8.03	3.61	14.8	4.08	16.1
MAX	1080	181	33	25	66	25	8.0	55	5.5	153	27	134
MIN	21	20	13	9.5	7.7	6.3	5.5	4.3	2.3	2.4	1.8	3.2
AC-FT	16830	3470	1010	870	698	501	399	493	215	911	251	956
CFSM	6.29	1.34	.38	.33	.29	.19	.15	.18	.08	.34	.09	.37
IN.	7.26	1.50	.43	.38	.30	.22	.17	.21	.09	.39	.11	.41

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1987 - 1991, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991
MEAN	93.2	39.1	28.4	14.1	9.40
MAX	274	62.9	83.8	32.9	17.0
(WY)	1991	1988	1988	1988	1988
MIN	10.3	12.6	3.72	2.85	3.17
(WY)	1989	1989	1989	1989	1987

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1990 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1991 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1987 - 1991

ANNUAL TOTAL	14108.5	13414.0	
ANNUAL MEAN	38.7	36.8	22.4
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			36.8
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			10.1
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1080	1080	1080
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	1.2	1.8	.67
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	1.3	2.1	.70
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		6200	6200
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		11.92	11.92
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW		1.2	1.1
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	27980	26610	16210
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.89	.84	.51
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	12.07	11.47	6.99
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	100	74	52
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	5.7	7.9	6.8
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.7	3.0	2.0

RIO COAMO BASIN

50106100 RIO COAMO AT COAMO, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	3.5	14	6.2	6.0	e13	e7.8	12	7.8	172	15	8.7	4.6
2	3.4	13	6.0	5.7	e12	e8.1	9.5	7.2	137	14	7.6	4.5
3	3.2	10	5.6	5.3	e12	e8.2	7.2	7.2	93	14	7.7	4.3
4	2.9	8.7	5.8	5.6	e23	e8.1	6.6	6.7	69	13	7.9	4.3
5	2.9	8.1	5.9	e1580	e46	e7.8	6.5	6.5	60	13	82	4.1
6	3.0	7.4	5.8	e130	e38	e8.0	6.5	7.9	53	12	29	4.0
7	3.1	28	5.6	e70	e32	e9.4	6.6	9.9	50	12	9.1	7.9
8	3.2	14	5.4	e54	e22	e13	6.1	7.9	54	11	7.6	13
9	4.8	11	5.5	e48	e18	e11	6.9	7.1	42	11	7.3	6.9
10	4.2	9.4	5.1	e52	e17	e8.0	11	6.6	38	11	7.0	4.8
11	3.5	8.4	5.2	e52	e16	e7.6	7.8	6.4	41	10	7.0	4.5
12	3.1	7.6	5.1	e40	e14	e7.4	7.7	7.9	44	10	7.0	4.4
13	2.8	7.5	5.3	e35	e14	e7.4	7.7	7.0	35	9.4	6.2	4.3
14	2.7	7.6	5.2	e32	e13	e7.2	7.6	27	32	8.9	6.3	4.3
15	2.5	7.4	5.0	e30	e12	e7.2	8.6	21	30	8.5	6.2	4.3
16	2.4	7.0	5.4	e27	e11	e8.1	8.5	15	29	10	6.2	4.6
17	2.4	6.7	5.4	e24	e10	e8.5	12	13	28	9.1	6.2	4.9
18	2.4	6.4	5.2	e22	e10	e8.6	9.0	9.9	27	9.1	5.7	5.0
19	2.3	6.1	5.4	e21	e10	e9.6	22	9.4	25	8.5	5.7	5.0
20	21	6.1	5.6	e20	e9.9	e9.4	e45	8.7	25	8.4	7.0	8.7
21	5.5	6.0	5.8	e19	e9.4	e8.4	e33	8.4	30	8.5	7.4	9.0
22	75	6.0	6.0	e19	e9.8	e7.8	e17	8.4	25	8.8	6.2	5.9
23	25	6.0	5.9	e19	e10	e6.4	e12	203	22	8.4	6.1	7.1
24	14	6.0	5.7	e19	e10	e6.0	9.6	198	21	8.8	6.0	6.1
25	12	6.7	5.9	e18	e9.0	e5.8	8.7	112	20	8.7	5.8	5.7
26	11	6.2	5.8	e17	e9.9	e5.6	8.5	1220	18	8.4	5.7	5.4
27	10	6.6	5.4	e17	e9.0	5.4	8.4	87	18	8.1	5.5	5.4
28	10	7.1	5.6	e16	e8.0	6.1	7.3	40	17	7.7	5.4	5.5
29	11	7.0	5.6	e16	e7.8	5.8	7.3	28	16	7.5	5.2	5.4
30	45	6.6	5.4	e15	---	5.9	7.4	29	16	7.6	5.0	15
31	29	---	5.7	e14	---	8.1	---	24	---	8.2	4.7	---
TOTAL	326.8	258.6	172.5	2448.6	435.8	241.7	334.0	2157.9	1287	308.6	300.4	178.9
MEAN	10.5	8.62	5.56	79.0	15.0	7.80	11.1	69.6	42.9	9.95	9.69	5.96
MAX	75	28	6.2	1580	46	13	45	1220	172	15	82	15
MIN	2.3	6.0	5.0	5.3	7.8	5.4	6.1	6.4	16	7.5	4.7	4.0
AC-FT	648	513	342	4860	864	479	662	4280	2550	612	596	355
CFSM	.24	.20	.13	1.82	.35	.18	.26	1.60	.99	.23	.22	.14
IN.	.28	.22	.15	2.09	.37	.21	.29	1.85	1.10	.26	.26	.15

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1987 - 1992, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992
MEAN	76.7	33.0	23.8	27.0	10.4	6.23
MAX	274	62.9	83.8	79.0	17.0	9.79
(WY)	1991	1988	1988	1992	1988	1987
MIN	10.3	8.62	3.72	2.85	3.17	3.09
(WY)	1989	1992	1989	1989	1989	1989

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1991 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1992 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1987 - 1992

ANNUAL TOTAL	3426.9	8450.8	
ANNUAL MEAN	9.39	23.1	22.5
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			36.8
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			10.1
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	153	Jul 16	1580
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	1.8	Aug 13	2.3
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	2.1	Aug 7	2.5
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			9290
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			13.49
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			1.1
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	6800	16760	16310
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.22	.53	.52
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	2.93	7.23	7.03
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	14	32	47
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	6.3	8.1	7.2
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	2.9	5.0	2.1

e Estimated

RIO COAMO BASIN

50106100 RIO COAMO AT COAMO, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	23	95	39	19	17	8.8	3.9	15	7.7	5.0	7.4	6.5
2	10	49	32	19	14	7.5	3.8	47	7.6	4.8	7.4	6.5
3	5.8	42	28	18	15	6.6	4.0	32	7.3	4.7	7.4	6.5
4	5.1	39	26	17	13	6.9	4.2	16	7.1	4.7	7.4	6.5
5	19	35	25	17	12	7.1	4.2	15	7.1	4.5	7.2	79
6	120	33	24	16	11	7.5	3.9	17	6.8	4.6	7.1	67
7	64	32	23	16	11	7.5	3.9	14	6.2	4.6	7.1	29
8	59	29	22	16	10	7.3	3.8	13	6.2	4.5	7.1	14
9	40	28	22	16	10	7.4	6.1	14	6.2	4.5	7.0	11
10	19	29	22	16	9.6	7.2	7.3	16	6.0	4.5	6.8	12
11	35	28	21	15	8.9	6.4	8.3	14	6.0	24	7.1	10
12	16	27	21	15	8.8	6.2	15	12	5.9	13	7.4	9.0
13	14	32	21	14	9.6	5.7	20	12	5.7	12	7.7	8.7
14	53	32	22	15	9.6	5.9	17	29	5.6	11	7.8	8.6
15	33	29	22	15	9.2	5.6	17	19	12	11	7.8	8.4
16	58	37	21	15	8.7	5.2	14	14	5.8	10	46	8.7
17	77	29	20	14	8.6	5.0	12	13	5.3	9.8	8.9	11
18	27	41	20	13	e10	4.7	16	12	5.2	9.3	7.8	11
19	56	33	20	13	e8.4	4.7	9.3	10	12	9.1	7.6	11
20	27	87	20	13	e8.4	4.6	13	12	14	8.7	7.4	30
21	19	60	20	13	e8.2	4.7	16	12	6.6	8.5	7.3	18
22	92	44	20	13	e8.2	4.8	15	12	6.2	8.9	7.1	13
23	74	38	19	14	88.0	4.4	12	12	5.8	9.3	7.1	60
24	185	34	18	13	8.0	4.9	15	20	5.7	8.8	7.1	14
25	141	31	18	13	8.0	5.4	14	21	5.7	8.6	7.1	9.1
26	99	30	24	13	7.9	4.8	11	21	5.6	8.4	7.1	9.4
27	82	87	24	12	7.9	4.5	11	41	5.4	8.2	7.5	8.8
28	76	104	21	78	7.9	4.5	64	12	5.4	8.0	11	50
29	76	59	20	86	---	4.4	109	9.1	4.8	7.7	7.6	16
30	187	51	19	29	---	4.1	47	8.1	4.9	7.7	6.8	48
31	78	---	20	20	---	4.0	---	7.9	---	7.7	6.5	---
TOTAL	1869.9	1324	694	616	276.9	178.3	500.7	522.1	201.8	256.1	269.6	600.7
MEAN	60.3	44.1	22.4	19.9	9.89	5.75	16.7	16.8	6.73	8.26	8.70	20.0
MAX	187	104	39	86	17	8.8	109	47	14	24	46	79
MIN	5.1	27	18	12	7.9	4.0	3.8	7.9	4.8	4.5	6.5	6.5
AC-FT	3710	2630	1380	1220	549	354	993	1040	400	508	535	1190
CFSM	1.39	1.01	.51	.46	.23	.13	.38	.39	.15	.19	.20	.46
IN.	1.60	1.13	.59	.53	.24	.15	.43	.45	.17	.22	.23	.51

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1987 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	73.9	34.8	23.6	25.8	10.3	6.16	12.5
MAX	274	62.9	83.8	79.0	17.0	9.79	27.6
(WY)	1991	1988	1988	1992	1988	1988	1992
MIN	10.3	8.62	3.72	2.85	3.17	3.09	2.53
(WY)	1989	1992	1989	1989	1989	1987	1989

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1987 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	11580.8	7310.1	
ANNUAL MEAN	31.6	20.0	22.1
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			36.8
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			10.1
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1580	187	1580
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	4.0	3.8	.67
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	4.4	4.0	.70
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		2810	9290
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		9.58	13.49
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			1.1
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	22970	14500	16010
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.73	.46	.51
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	9.90	6.25	6.90
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	55	46	47
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	13	12	7.7
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	5.8	5.2	2.4

e Estimated

RIO COAMO BASIN

50106500 RIO COAMO NEAR COAMO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'52", long 66°22'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on Highway 153 bridge, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) above Rio de la Mina, and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) south of Coamo plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--46.0 mi² (119.1 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1978 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
27...	1415	7.7	522	7.4	30.0	1.6	6.0	79	<10	2700	60
DEC											
08...	1210	16	630	7.8	26.5	2.8	8.1	106	<10	280	300
MAR 1993											
01...	1245	11	679	7.8	26.5	2.3	8.0	102	10	3400	90
APR											
13...	1355	13	683	7.1	31.5	4.0	4.8	63	16	400	2800
JUN											
24...	1515	26	580	7.6	33.0	4.2	4.0	54	50	460	310
AUG											
17...	1530	17	595	7.3	32.5	2.3	3.2	60	<10	K120	30

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
27...	180	19	48	16	7.4	0.2	2.7	190	<0.5	26	39
DEC											
18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--
MAR 1993											
01...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	250	--	--	--
APR											
13...	250	0	68	20	41	1	4.3	180	<0.5	42	47
JUN											
24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--
AUG											
17...	120	3	37	5.7	9.1	0.4	1.2	160	--	8.1	7.4

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
27...	0.20	31	210	0.38	<1	1.43	0.070	1.50	0.610	0.49
DEC										
18...	--	--	--	--	3	1.11	0.190	1.30	0.600	1.2
MAR 1993										
01...	--	--	--	--	14	1.86	0.340	2.20	0.700	0.40
APR										
13...	0.20	33	303	11.0	1	1.90	0.300	2.20	0.750	0.75
JUN										
24...	--	--	--	--	32	1.24	0.260	1.50	0.400	2.2
AUG										
17...	0.10	21	186	8.54	<1	1.06	0.190	1.30	0.600	1.2

K = non-ideal count

RIO DESCALABRADO BASIN

50108000 RIO DESCALABRADO NEAR LOS LLANOS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'08", long 66°25'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at bridge on Highway 14, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) west of Los Llanos, and 5.3 mi (8.5 km) east of Juana Díaz.

DRAINAGE AREA.--12.9 mi² (33.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1959-65 (annual low-flow measurements only), 1965 (annual maximum discharge), January 1966 to June 1969, July to December 1969 (maximum discharge only), February 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 220 ft (67 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Some regulation at low flow by local resident upstream from station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e54	54	17	5.5	5.1	2.1	1.1	8.9	e9.0	4.3	2.3	1.1
2	e40	e20	14	5.2	4.9	1.6	.94	51	e7.0	4.4	2.2	1.0
3	e19	e17	13	5.1	5.3	1.1	1.1	19	e6.0	5.0	2.0	1.0
4	e9.6	e18	13	4.9	4.3	1.1	1.1	11	e5.0	4.5	2.0	.96
5	e7.5	e15	12	4.6	4.2	e1.0	1.1	8.6	e4.8	3.9	2.0	1.8
6	e25	e13	12	4.0	4.0	e1.0	1.0	6.8	e4.3	3.8	2.1	.29
7	e40	e13	11	3.7	4.1	1.1	.93	5.8	e9.0	4.1	1.9	2.8
8	92	e12	9.9	3.8	4.0	1.2	.93	4.4	e8.0	4.4	1.9	1.2
9	12	e12	9.9	3.8	4.0	1.2	.97	17	e5.0	4.0	1.9	1.0
10	186	e11	9.9	3.4	3.8	1.1	1.7	10	e4.0	4.0	1.9	11
11	141	e10	9.5	3.2	3.3	e1.0	1.1	4.2	4.0	17	1.8	2.4
12	e26	e9.0	9.0	3.4	3.5	e.98	1.4	2.9	3.7	7.1	1.8	1.5
13	13	e20	9.6	3.4	3.2	e.98	1.9	2.3	3.6	4.9	1.6	1.2
14	34	8.4	10	3.4	2.8	e1.0	3.6	e10	4.9	3.8	1.6	1.2
15	14	55	10	3.3	2.5	e1.0	2.8	e7.0	9.2	3.1	1.8	.90
16	e232	27	9.0	3.2	2.6	e.98	2.0	e5.0	10	2.7	33	1.7
17	e56	10	8.8	3.5	2.7	.95	1.8	e3.5	5.4	2.8	4.0	4.7
18	25	11	8.0	3.4	2.4	1.0	1.7	e3.0	4.9	2.8	1.9	2.3
19	70	6.1	7.8	3.3	3.0	.95	1.7	e3.5	46	2.8	1.5	3.4
20	51	25	7.2	3.5	3.0	.95	2.5	e9.0	16	3.0	1.5	.88
21	29	11	7.0	3.9	2.2	.84	1.6	e8.0	5.8	2.8	1.2	17
22	78	6.4	6.4	4.1	1.9	.87	1.1	e10	5.5	3.6	1.3	3.9
23	122	5.1	6.2	4.6	1.7	.91	1.1	e12	4.9	5.6	2.5	54
24	116	4.9	5.9	4.0	1.9	.95	1.9	e13	4.9	4.2	1.5	8.8
25	66	4.6	5.9	4.4	2.0	1.4	4.3	e8.5	4.8	3.3	1.5	3.7
26	48	4.5	6.5	4.5	1.9	1.6	2.3	e11	4.7	2.8	1.6	1.9
27	e42	11	6.5	4.4	1.6	1.3	1.7	e17	4.5	3.0	2.9	1.3
28	e38	62	5.3	7.1	1.4	1.1	26	e16	4.4	3.0	2.6	38
29	e32	11	5.2	14	---	1.7	11	e10	4.4	2.7	1.3	12
30	e120	90	5.6	10	---	1.2	17	e11	4.6	2.6	1.4	17
31	24	---	5.7	7.0	---	1.1	---	e12	---	2.5	1.1	---
TOTAL	1862.1	577.0	276.8	145.6	87.3	35.26	99.37	321.4	218.3	128.5	89.6	315.76
MEAN	60.1	19.2	8.93	4.70	3.12	1.14	3.31	10.4	7.28	4.15	2.89	10.5
MAX	232	90	17	14	5.3	2.1	26	51	46	17	33	88
MIN	7.5	4.5	5.2	3.2	1.4	.84	.93	2.3	3.6	2.5	1.1	.90
AC-FT	3690	1140	549	289	173	70	197	637	433	255	178	626
CFSM	4.66	1.49	.69	.36	.24	.09	.26	.80	.56	.32	.22	.82
IN.	5.37	1.66	.80	.42	.25	.10	.29	.93	.63	.37	.26	.91

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1966 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	
MEAN	31.8	17.4	5.86	5.65	2.12	1.13	3.87	15.5	5.35	2.53	3.46	13.1																	
MAX	117	41.0	24.5	36.4	7.57	3.49	18.8	62.2	25.2	10.5	9.11	40.2																	
(WY)	1986	1985	1988	1992	1986	1986	1985	1985	1987	1991	1988	1985																	
MIN	2.02	2.17	.19	.057	.020	.012	.000	.032	.000	.000	.19	.063																	
(WY)	1968	1992	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1968	1967	1967	1990	1967																	

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1966 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	6857.25	4156.99		
ANNUAL MEAN	18.7	11.4		
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			18.4	1986
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			1.89	1968
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	789	May 26	232	Oct 16
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.63	Jan 26	.84	Mar 21
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.75	Jan 22	.92	Mar 17
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			3060	Oct 10
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			9.94	Oct 10
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	13600	8250		24.37
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.45	.88		.74
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	19.77	11.99		10.07
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	41	25		14
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.8	4.3		1.5
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.2	1.1		.03

e Estimated

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50110900 RIO TOA VACA ABOVE LAGO TOA VACA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°07'37", long 66°27'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on right bank, off a dirt road about 0.3 mi (0.5 km) from road 553, 2.4 mi (3.9 km) southeast from Villalba plaza, and 0.2 mi (0.3 km) downstream from confluence with Quebrada Limón.

DRAINAGE AREA.--7.64 mi² (19.79 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1989 to current year.

GAGE.--Water stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 525 ft (160 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	59	36	35	7.6	5.5	3.5	4.4	35	26	9.3	5.5	8.2
2	23	33	25	7.1	5.1	3.3	4.3	34	21	9.1	5.5	7.1
3	12	26	23	7.3	6.1	3.2	5.5	38	18	10	5.5	5.9
4	11	23	18	7.3	4.8	3.4	4.8	22	16	9.9	5.5	24
5	49	20	17	7.1	4.6	3.3	4.9	15	15	9.3	5.5	95
6	160	17	14	6.8	4.4	3.2	5.1	11	13	8.5	6.0	52
7	86	16	13	7.4	4.2	3.1	5.7	8.8	13	9.9	5.9	43
8	68	15	12	7.5	4.1	3.4	5.8	8.1	33	10	5.9	25
9	48	14	12	6.8	4.1	3.3	12	34	16	10	6.0	15
10	49	13	11	8.4	4.1	3.2	11	16	12	11	6.3	27
11	50	12	10	10	4.0	3.2	17	11	12	29	6.2	19
12	34	12	9.5	10	4.3	3.2	20	8.8	12	24	6.3	11
13	26	14	11	9.1	4.3	3.4	57	8.3	11	23	6.2	7.9
14	50	12	21	7.0	4.3	3.2	37	30	12	27	6.0	6.6
15	54	13	13	7.5	6.3	3.0	34	16	15	15	6.6	5.5
16	52	31	9.5	7.2	4.2	3.0	35	12	18	10	49	7.1
17	40	14	9.8	7.5	4.0	3.1	19	9.9	12	8.1	16	14
18	32	11	8.8	8.0	3.6	3.0	17	9.1	11	7.4	8.1	19
19	32	10	7.7	7.8	3.8	2.9	12	8.5	50	8.1	7.3	14
20	31	45	7.6	7.3	4.2	2.9	11	10	60	6.7	6.1	143
21	25	49	7.3	7.3	3.8	3.0	10	30	31	6.1	5.7	25
22	25	32	7.3	7.0	3.6	3.0	7.2	22	22	26	5.4	7.5
23	132	21	7.2	7.1	3.6	2.9	6.6	35	17	18	5.9	13
24	65	17	7.2	6.8	3.7	3.3	17	42	14	11	5.6	10
25	44	14	6.8	6.7	3.6	4.3	15	26	12	8.0	5.2	6.7
26	33	13	14	6.4	3.4	3.7	8.2	25	11	12	5.4	4.7
27	32	13	14	6.2	3.7	4.0	6.6	58	11	10	27	3.3
28	34	66	9.6	16	3.5	4.2	123	53	12	6.7	50	16
29	27	78	8.3	31	---	4.2	197	32	11	5.9	32	6.9
30	52	55	7.6	12	---	5.6	75	35	10	5.8	15	9.7
31	42	---	7.7	6.6	---	5.6	---	38	---	5.5	12	---
TOTAL	1477	745	384.9	267.8	118.9	107.6	788.1	741.5	547	370.3	344.6	652.1
MEAN	47.6	24.8	12.4	8.64	4.25	3.47	26.3	23.9	18.2	11.9	11.1	21.7
MAX	160	78	35	31	6.3	5.6	197	58	60	29	50	143
MIN	11	10	6.8	6.2	3.4	2.9	4.3	8.1	10	5.5	5.2	3.3
AC-FT	2930	1480	763	531	236	213	1560	1470	1080	734	684	1290
CFSM	3.36	1.75	.87	.61	.30	.24	1.85	1.68	1.28	.84	.78	1.53
IN.	3.87	1.95	1.01	.70	.31	.28	2.06	1.94	1.43	.97	.90	1.71

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1989 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	52.6	19.8	7.55	15.0	3.82
MAX	109	40.1	12.4	43.1	4.75
(WY)	1991	1991	1993	1992	1991
MIN	4.61	2.19	1.42	3.75	2.37
(WY)	1992	1992	1992	1990	1990

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1989 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	7750.66	6544.8	
ANNUAL MEAN	21.2	17.9	15.3
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			18.2
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			10.4
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	676	197	676
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.85	2.9	.45
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	2.3	3.0	.61
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		2160	8700
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		8.09	13.24
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW		2.7	.44
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	15370	12980	11090
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.49	1.26	1.08
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	20.30	17.15	14.65
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	44	41	35
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	10	10	4.3
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	2.8	3.9	1.2

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50110900 RIO TOA VACA ABOVE LAGO TOA VACA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.-- Water years 1988 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: April 1988 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- Automatic sediment sampler.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 3,170 mg/L January 05, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 18,300 tons (16,600 tonnes) January 05, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 0.0 ton (0.0 tonne) several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1993.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,270 mg/L Oct. 06, 1992; Minimum daily mean, 4 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 2,680 tons (2,430 tonnes) Sept. 20, 1993; Minimum daily mean, 0.04 ton (0.03 tonne) Sept. 27, 1993.

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	59	561	272	36	222	25	35	187	18
2	23	108	8.5	33	168	15	25	104	7.1
3	12	32	1.1	26	109	7.9	23	108	8.9
4	11	35	1.8	23	82	5.3	18	63	3.3
5	49	591	278	20	55	2.8	17	45	2.0
6	160	1360	2430	17	30	1.4	14	33	1.3
7	86	957	325	16	20	.87	13	17	.62
8	68	692	188	15	20	.79	12	10	.31
9	48	202	28	14	20	.74	12	11	.34
10	49	404	102	13	19	.67	11	15	.42
11	50	425	90	12	19	.62	10	17	.43
12	34	210	22	12	20	.61	9.5	14	.34
13	26	73	5.6	14	46	3.2	11	33	2.6
14	50	560	182	12	35	1.2	21	153	29
15	54	142	27	13	36	1.4	13	36	1.3
16	52	379	122	31	249	80	9.5	14	.35
17	40	137	16	14	56	2.1	9.8	12	.29
18	32	53	4.9	11	36	1.1	8.8	11	.25
19	32	146	15	10	23	.64	7.7	9	.19
20	31	128	12	45	419	97	7.6	7	.15
21	25	49	3.4	49	378	92	7.3	7	.14
22	25	20	1.6	32	172	16	7.3	7	.15
23	132	1230	2090	21	95	6.2	7.2	8	.16
24	65	529	109	17	47	2.1	7.2	8	.14
25	44	289	36	14	33	1.2	6.8	8	.14
26	33	216	20	13	25	.85	14	65	6.8
27	32	245	26	13	22	.87	14	34	1.6
28	34	170	17	66	656	177	9.6	8	.21
29	27	141	13	78	830	301	8.3	10	.21
30	52	527	134	55	428	70	7.6	10	.21
31	42	292	40	---	---	---	7.7	11	.21
TOTAL	1477	---	6620.9	745	---	915.56	384.9	---	87.16

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50110900 RIO TOA VACA ABOVE LAGO TOA VACA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	7.6	12	.23	5.5	10	.14	3.5	16	.15
2	7.1	17	.31	5.1	9	.12	3.3	22	.20
3	7.3	20	.38	6.1	9	.14	3.2	26	.23
4	7.3	20	.38	4.8	9	.12	3.4	25	.22
5	7.1	21	.38	4.6	8	.10	3.3	21	.19
6	6.8	21	.38	4.4	7	.08	3.2	19	.17
7	7.4	21	.41	4.2	7	.08	3.1	19	.17
8	7.5	21	.42	4.1	7	.08	3.4	23	.20
9	6.8	21	.37	4.1	7	.08	3.3	27	.24
10	8.4	19	.38	4.1	7	.08	3.2	31	.27
11	10	17	.39	4.0	7	.08	3.2	32	.27
12	10	14	.37	4.3	7	.08	3.2	25	.21
13	9.1	11	.28	4.3	7	.08	3.4	15	.13
14	7.0	10	.18	4.3	7	.08	3.2	16	.13
15	7.5	9	.18	6.3	17	.82	3.0	24	.19
16	7.2	9	.18	4.2	12	.14	3.0	28	.22
17	7.5	9	.18	4.0	14	.16	3.1	26	.20
18	8.0	10	.19	3.6	15	.15	3.0	21	.16
19	7.8	10	.20	3.8	17	.16	2.9	15	.11
20	7.3	10	.20	4.2	19	.18	2.9	10	.08
21	7.3	10	.20	3.8	20	.19	3.0	8	.07
22	7.0	10	.20	3.6	20	.19	3.0	7	.06
23	7.1	10	.18	3.6	20	.18	2.9	8	.07
24	6.8	9	.16	3.7	17	.16	3.3	10	.10
25	6.7	9	.16	3.6	14	.13	4.3	10	.11
26	6.4	9	.16	3.4	11	.11	3.7	9	.09
27	6.2	9	.16	3.7	10	.10	4.0	6	.07
28	16	223	41	3.5	11	.11	4.2	5	.06
29	31	202	35	---	---	---	4.2	7	.08
30	12	33	1.3	---	---	---	5.6	9	.14
31	6.6	13	.23	---	---	---	5.6	10	.16
TOTAL	267.8	---	84.74	118.9	---	4.12	107.6	---	4.75

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50110900 RIO TOA VACA ABOVE LAGO TOA VACA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	4.4		.06	35	11	1.0	26	20	1.5
2	4.3		.07	34	145	30	21	21	1.2
3	5.5		.13	38	185	22	18	24	1.1
4	4.8	18	.23	22	27	1.7	16	28	1.2
5	4.9	28	.37	15	19	.75	15	28	1.1
6	5.1	23	.32	11	23	.66	13	25	.91
7	5.7	13	.19	8.8	21	.50	13	25	.88
8	5.8	11	.16	8.1	14	.30	33	311	84
9	12	58	5.2	34	335	124	16	44	1.9
10	11	37	1.9	16	40	2.1	12	32	1.1
11	17	93	11	11	15	.39	12	30	.98
12	20	84	6.6	8.8	20	.48	12	28	.88
13	57	1030	375	8.3	16	.35	11	25	.70
14	37	691	78	30	201	32	12	30	.99
15	34	676	91	16	25	1.2	15	49	2.6
16	35	206	23	12	7	.23	18	48	2.9
17	19	70	4.3	9.9	10	.24	12	17	.49
18	17	54	2.8	9.1	10	.22	11	25	.70
19	12	24	.72	8.5	9	.20	50	411	75
20	11	13	.36	10	15	.35	60	294	60
21	10	13	.36	30	225	58	31	29	2.5
22	7.2	21	.41	22	32	2.3	22	25	1.4
23	6.6	22	.36	35	168	38	17	21	.91
24	17	107	14	42	73	9.8	14	20	.73
25	15	44	2.0	26	15	1.1	12	26	.81
26	8.2	17	.37	25	16	1.0	11	37	1.0
27	6.6	14	.25	58	624	343	11	49	1.5
28	123	1230	709	53	455	121	12	56	1.7
29	197	1040	974	32	33	3.2	11	50	1.4
30	75	47	12	35	177	45	10	36	.95
31	---	---	---	38	50	6.0	---	---	---
TOTAL	788.1	---	2314.16	741.5	---	847.07	547	---	253.03

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50110900 RIO TOA VACA ABOVE LAGO TOA VACA, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	9.3	26	.64	5.5	6	.10	8.2	11	.23
2	9.1	23	.56	5.5	8	.12	7.1	15	.26
3	10	23	.58	5.5	8	.12	5.9	20	.30
4	9.9	16	.41	5.5	8	.12	24	186	35
5	9.3	10	.21	5.5	5	.08	95	949	950
6	8.5	6	.14	6.0	4	.06	52	348	70
7	9.9	5	.13	5.9	4	.07	43	226	27
8	10	8	.21	5.9	5	.08	25	49	3.5
9	10	14	.37	6.0	6	.11	15	35	1.5
10	11	19	.53	6.3	6	.10	27	174	26
11	29	145	19	6.2	6	.10	19	68	4.5
12	24	43	3.4	6.3	6	.09	11	15	.45
13	23	12	.69	6.2	6	.10	7.9	9	.18
14	27	10	.82	6.0	6	.11	6.6	6	.12
15	15	7	.26	6.6	9	.17	5.5	6	.09
16	10	4	.10	49	23	3.9	7.1	9	.18
17	8.1	5	.11	16	17	.79	14	70	7.6
18	7.4	8	.16	8.1	8	.18	19	125	19
19	8.1	10	.22	7.3	5	.10	14	48	3.0
20	6.7	11	.18	6.1	8	.13	143	945	2680
21	6.1	14	.21	5.7	7	.11	25	142	14
22	26	24	2.4	5.4	7	.10	7.5	18	.45
23	18	12	.65	5.9	7	.10	13	70	6.8
24	11	11	.28	5.6	6	.09	10	53	2.3
25	8.0	16	.29	5.2	7	.10	6.7	11	.16
26	12	15	.41	5.4	7	.11	4.7	8	.10
27	10	10	.28	27	167	40	3.3	4	.04
28	6.7	8	.14	50	369	119	16	194	66
29	5.9	5	.07	32	84	8.5	6.9	23	1.3
30	5.8	4	.05	15	19	.78	9.7	41	2.6
31	5.5	4	.06	12	9	.30	---	---	---
TOTAL	370.3	---	33.56	344.6	---	175.82	652.1	---	3922.66
YEAR	6544.8		15263.53						

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50110900 RIO TOA VACA ABOVE LAGO TOA VACA, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
		OCT 1992					
23...	1730	1250	14000	4720	11	13	15
APR 1993							
13...	1450	204	3700	2040	43	47	61
13...	1600	208	3380	1900	41	47	56
28...	2155	159	21900	9400	16	21	25
29...	1535	594	13600	21800	14	17	18
SEP							
20...	1630	2140	3880	22400	40	47	54

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
	OCT 1992						
23...	19	23	29	41	59	85	97
APR 1993							
13...	72	81	91	96	99	99.7	99.9
13...	69	79	88	94	98	99.5	99.8
28...	31	39	47	59	76	92	99
29...	23	30	40	56	74	91	99
SEP							

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50110900 RIO TOA VACA ABOVE LAGO TOA VACA, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1992					
23...	1630	200	8110	4380	66
ABR 1993					
13...	1415	192	6230	3230	50
28...	1600	104	2100	590	76
28...	1630	120	1430	463	83
28...	1855	342	2640	2440	75
29...	1650	816	1130	2490	90
MAY					
21...	1515	168	1850	839	80
AUG					
27...	1700	73	1120	221	97

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50111500 RIO JACAGUAS AT JUANA DIAZ, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'16", long 66°30'40", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on Highway 14 bridge, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west of Juana Diaz plaza, and 4.0 mi (6.4 km) downstream from Lago Guayabal.

DRAINAGE AREA.--49.8 mi² (129.0 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 131 ft (40 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Flow regulation from Lago Guayabal. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	35	151	e150	37	65	5.3	2.2	141	62	52	13	e24
2	20	118	113	29	46	5.0	2.3	176	104	48	e10	e31
3	10	92	103	30	26	4.4	2.2	111	74	60	e9.8	e28
4	8.1	65	104	27	21	4.3	2.3	40	68	57	e9.0	e28
5	14	52	95	22	13	4.2	2.5	31	65	27	e8.0	e69
6	348	50	78	20	9.8	4.1	4.0	25	47	24	e7.0	e49
7	354	44	66	13	6.7	5.3	6.0	28	38	34	e7.1	e46
8	196	41	65	15	5.6	5.3	6.2	21	236	36	e6.5	e20
9	94	28	48	17	5.2	5.2	6.4	217	122	39	e6.6	e19
10	378	30	47	17	5.0	4.3	6.1	75	88	51	e6.6	e16
11	188	30	44	9.6	5.0	4.1	5.9	28	71	60	e6.6	e23
12	105	25	39	7.3	4.9	3.8	6.0	15	71	93	e6.8	e20
13	60	84	40	7.0	4.9	3.7	6.7	11	64	62	e6.4	e16
14	72	75	58	8.6	5.8	3.6	8.8	94	76	63	e6.4	e15
15	78	116	67	11	5.6	3.5	8.3	61	74	56	e7.6	e15
16	74	204	50	12	5.2	3.9	7.7	47	66	70	e13	e21
17	110	112	34	16	5.0	3.5	6.9	e41	49	65	e28	e25
18	96	86	27	19	4.9	3.4	6.6	e33	46	50	e30	e29
19	57	86	23	9.3	4.8	3.3	6.8	e36	110	36	e28	e33
20	53	278	17	9.7	4.7	3.4	7.6	38	160	45	e23	e60
21	33	166	16	11	4.5	3.3	8.0	179	99	32	e23	e47
22	65	105	23	13	5.1	3.1	7.9	125	75	31	e49	e23
23	301	e60	27	8.4	4.7	3.1	7.5	62	48	41	e57	e20
24	149	e45	31	9.0	4.6	3.3	8.1	92	50	30	e28	e25
25	115	e40	54	6.0	4.9	3.5	8.2	92	56	23	e26	e28
26	70	e35	48	5.1	4.8	3.2	6.8	344	56	14	e18	e30
27	58	e50	65	5.0	4.3	2.9	6.6	589	47	13	e17	e31
28	56	e250	34	6.0	4.5	2.2	74	243	47	13	e18	e42
29	58	e80	32	172	---	2.5	404	85	74	13	e16	e47
30	206	e350	36	81	---	2.6	184	79	57	14	e17	e42
31	149	---	36	53	---	2.4	---	77	---	14	e27	---
TOTAL	3610.1	2948	1670	706.0	291.5	115.7	826.6	3236	2300	1266	535.4	922
MEAN	116	98.3	53.9	22.8	10.4	3.73	27.6	104	76.7	40.8	17.3	30.7
MAX	378	350	150	172	65	5.3	404	589	236	93	57	69
MIN	8.1	25	16	5.0	4.3	2.2	2.2	11	38	13	6.4	15
AC-FT	7160	5850	3310	1400	578	229	1640	6420	4560	2510	1060	1830
CFSM	2.34	1.97	1.08	.46	.21	.07	.55	2.10	1.54	.82	.35	.62
IN.	2.70	2.20	1.25	.53	.22	.09	.62	2.42	1.72	.95	.40	.69

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1984 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993		
MEAN	152	113	44.5	31.1	9.25	5.07	11.0	83.3	48.6	26.3	20.9	39.0
MAX	445	287	151	144	16.9	7.94	34.7	215	198	82.4	41.1	164
(WY)	1986	1988	1988	1992	1991	1988	1992	1985	1987	1987	1985	1985
MIN	8.65	10.5	9.99	5.88	4.82	3.16	3.19	2.68	2.72	2.94	2.25	5.32
(WY)	1987	1987	1989	1987	1990	1992	1991	1984	1984	1990	1990	1986

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1984 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	25114.84		18427.3			
ANNUAL MEAN	68.6		50.5		50.5	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					80.9	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					13.0	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	3170	Jan 6	589	May 27	4530	Nov 27 1987
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.24	Jan 3	2.2	Mar 28	.24	Jan 3 1992
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	2.3	Mar 6	2.3	Mar 28	1.3	Sep 7 1990
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			9480		40000	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			16.78		29.42	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	49820		36550		36620	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.38		1.01		1.01	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	18.76		13.76		13.79	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	138		110		110	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	29		29		8.7	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.1		4.7		3.5	

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RIO INABON BASIN

50112500 RIO INABON AT REAL ABAJO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°05'10", long 66°33'46", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at bridge on private road, off Highway 511 at Hacienda La Concordia, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) upstream from diversion canal, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) north of Real Abajo, and 6.1 mi (9.8 km) northeast of Plaza Degetau in Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--9.70 mi² (25.12 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1962-63 (annual low-flow measurements only), February to June 1964 (monthly measurements only), July 1964 to July 1970, April 1971 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 410 ft (125 m), from topographic map. Prior to April 1971 nonrecording gage and crest-stage gage at different datum.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	30	46	15	9.9	14	5.6	3.4	106	40	13	6.8	9.7
2	20	37	14	9.9	9.5	5.7	2.5	94	35	12	7.1	8.4
3	16	33	11	9.6	9.0	5.0	7.2	79	28	16	6.7	8.5
4	35	30	11	9.2	7.6	4.4	5.6	48	24	13	6.8	46
5	43	28	10	8.5	6.8	4.4	3.1	35	24	12	6.9	22
6	86	27	9.2	8.4	6.5	5.1	2.7	28	20	12	7.2	10
7	68	25	8.1	8.1	6.5	5.6	3.4	21	22	14	7.2	7.7
8	53	23	7.8	7.7	6.7	6.4	3.2	18	19	14	8.7	6.3
9	69	23	7.1	7.6	7.0	7.1	6.3	35	22	14	9.8	6.3
10	81	22	6.8	7.6	7.2	5.6	4.4	14	14	14	11	13
11	55	21	6.8	7.7	7.3	5.2	9.8	8.8	11	27	10	5.9
12	41	25	6.8	8.3	8.4	6.2	13	8.5	9.6	24	11	4.2
13	35	26	7.2	7.9	8.5	6.4	24	8.2	11	16	9.3	4.7
14	48	27	8.6	6.6	8.4	6.8	10	14	17	18	9.6	4.7
15	42	30	7.8	7.0	8.5	8.8	6.1	8.9	17	14	11	4.6
16	52	62	5.7	7.6	9.9	5.0	9.0	18	17	12	28	6.0
17	51	52	5.3	9.1	8.7	4.5	4.7	11	14	11	13	11
18	43	43	4.8	8.9	7.1	4.1	5.5	12	12	10	12	10
19	35	35	7.1	8.8	7.1	3.4	8.8	12	26	9.9	11	8.1
20	32	91	7.8	9.5	6.0	3.8	6.1	12	24	9.9	12	11
21	29	65	7.1	9.3	5.7	3.9	7.0	49	15	9.2	13	10
22	28	50	9.2	8.6	4.9	3.5	8.3	31	13	11	15	10
23	78	41	11	7.8	5.0	2.9	6.4	39	13	12	17	15
24	98	35	12	6.6	5.4	3.7	12	47	13	9.5	12	14
25	84	31	12	6.1	5.0	5.1	9.8	49	12	8.5	10	8.3
26	57	26	13	6.3	5.2	4.8	6.8	82	12	9.2	16	8.9
27	47	19	14	7.7	5.5	4.0	7.4	222	12	8.7	16	7.5
28	42	30	12	e25	5.4	3.2	25	143	23	7.0	17	29
29	71	25	14	e40	---	3.6	81	84	18	6.0	12	19
30	51	18	13	12	---	6.4	75	66	17	5.5	10	27
31	43	---	11	8.9	---	6.3	---	48	---	5.9	12	---
TOTAL	1563	1046	296.2	306.2	202.8	156.5	377.5	1451.4	554.6	378.3	355.1	356.8
MEAN	50.4	34.9	9.55	9.88	7.24	5.05	12.6	46.8	18.5	12.2	11.5	11.9
MAX	98	91	15	40	14	8.8	81	222	40	27	28	46
MIN	16	18	4.8	6.1	4.9	2.9	2.5	8.2	9.6	5.5	6.7	4.2
AC-FT	3100	2070	588	607	402	310	749	2880	1100	750	704	708
CFSM	5.20	3.59	.99	1.02	.75	.52	1.30	4.83	1.91	1.26	1.18	1.23
IN.	5.99	4.01	1.14	1.17	.78	.60	1.45	5.57	2.13	1.45	1.36	1.37

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1964 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	48.6	35.4	12.8	8.75	5.35	5.70	8.17	20.5	16.6	12.4	17.4	33.0
MAX	148	77.9	26.5	45.5	9.25	16.4	19.2	76.7	49.8	32.7	46.1	119
(WY)	1986	1978	1966	1992	1992	1972	1992	1969	1969	1979	1979	1975
MIN	15.4	8.32	4.43	4.11	3.05	1.85	2.76	1.94	2.75	1.77	4.47	7.70
(WY)	1983	1977	1977	1989	1977	1977	1975	1967	1967	1990	1974	1986

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1993 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1964 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	7811.1	7044.4	
ANNUAL MEAN	21.3	19.3	18.6
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			30.9
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			9.57
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	686	Jan 6	2500
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	4.0	May 22	.80
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	4.4	Mar 12	1.1
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			1880
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			15.00
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	15490	13970	13480
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.20	1.99	1.92
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	29.96	27.02	26.06
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	43	46	41
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	11	11	9.2
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	5.3	5.3	3.2

e Estimated

RIO BUCANA BASIN

50113800 RIO CERRILLOS ABOVE LAGO CERRILLOS NEAR PONCE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°07'01", long 66°36'17", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on right bank, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) downstream from confluence with Rio San Patricio, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) southwest of Hwy 139 and 2.4 mi (3.7 km) northwest of Maragüez.

DRAINAGE AREA.-- 15.4 mi² (39.9 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1988 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 720 ft (210 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	36	108	39	19	20	11	7.4	65	65	19	14	15
2	30	78	37	19	17	11	7.3	118	56	18	14	13
3	27	66	34	19	16	11	8.7	87	45	34	13	29
4	52	60	32	18	15	10	7.6	40	42	21	13	21
5	73	52	31	17	14	10	7.3	23	35	19	13	17
6	174	48	29	17	13	9.7	7.1	24	34	19	13	16
7	136	43	29	17	13	9.6	7.4	19	34	22	13	16
8	136	39	28	17	13	9.6	8.5	17	32	19	13	17
9	178	36	27	16	13	11	9.6	81	54	17	14	18
10	169	34	27	15	13	9.6	8.6	41	33	17	14	76
11	130	32	26	15	12	8.6	30	22	29	50	13	38
12	91	58	26	15	12	8.6	19	18	27	29	13	22
13	73	59	27	14	12	8.6	43	16	26	27	12	21
14	84	46	28	15	12	8.6	24	24	27	25	12	19
15	91	41	27	14	12	9.2	34	17	25	20	13	18
16	96	91	23	14	16	9.1	21	33	26	19	49	19
17	119	88	23	14	14	8.2	13	21	23	18	17	18
18	98	68	23	14	12	7.8	15	17	22	17	14	32
19	78	48	23	13	13	7.8	15	16	46	17	14	23
20	66	140	22	12	12	7.5	13	18	46	17	13	37
21	55	95	21	12	12	8.9	12	148	28	16	14	24
22	54	68	21	12	11	7.3	12	78	26	19	17	20
23	234	51	21	12	11	7.3	12	65	23	18	16	30
24	253	43	21	11	11	7.9	16	80	22	17	14	25
25	201	38	20	11	11	9.0	14	77	22	16	14	19
26	159	35	25	11	11	9.4	12	e150	21	18	14	41
27	134	34	22	11	11	8.8	11	e270	21	17	30	30
28	115	54	21	47	11	8.6	20	e208	34	15	16	47
29	161	76	33	128	---	7.8	142	135	26	15	14	36
30	108	51	25	29	---	8.6	96	102	22	14	16	69
31	91	---	21	21	---	8.4	---	84	---	14	19	---
TOTAL	3502	1780	812	619	363	278.5	653.5	2114	972	623	488	826
MEAN	113	59.3	26.2	20.0	13.0	8.98	21.8	68.2	32.4	20.1	15.7	27.5
MAX	253	140	39	128	20	11	142	270	65	50	49	76
MIN	27	32	20	11	11	7.3	7.1	16	21	14	12	13
AC-FT	6950	3530	1610	1230	720	552	1300	4190	1930	1240	968	1640
CFSM	9.49	4.99	2.20	1.68	1.09	.75	1.83	5.73	2.72	1.69	1.32	2.31
IN.	10.95	5.56	2.54	1.94	1.13	.87	2.04	6.61	3.04	1.95	1.53	2.58

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1989 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	95.7	40.9	18.3	21.6	9.65
MAX	154	59.3	26.2	59.0	13.2
(WY)	1991	1993	1993	1992	1989
MIN	24.6	16.0	13.3	7.46	6.34
(WY)	1992	1992	1989	1989	1990

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1989 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	14620.3	13031.0	
ANNUAL MEAN	39.9	35.7	30.1
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			35.7
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			22.9
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	717	270	717
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	7.1	7.1	3.3
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	8.7	7.5	3.5
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		1480	8140
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		4.95	9.65
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW		6.9	3.3
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	29000	25850	21770
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.36	3.00	2.53
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	45.70	40.74	34.31
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	85	85	68
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	22	20	15
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	10	10	5.4

e Estimated

RIO BUCANA BASIN

50113950 LAGO CERRILLOS AT DAMSITE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°04'41", long 66°34'38", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on left bank west from intake house of dam, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) southwest from Iglesia San Mateo at Real Abajo, 3.2 mi (5.1 km) northeast from Hospital de Distrito de Ponce, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northwest from Escuela Yuca.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.4 mi² (45.1 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1992 to September 1993.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lake is formed by Cerrilloas Dam, a rockfilled ungated structure completed in 1992. Elevation of crest is 611 ft (186 m) above mean sea level, with a structural height of 323 ft (98 m) and a length of 1,555 ft (474 m). The dam has a capacity of approximately 47,900 ac-ft (59.1 hm³). The dam is operated by U.S. Army Corps of Engineers and its purpose is for flood control, water supply, power generation, and recreation. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 523.56 ft (159.58 m), Sept. 30; minimum elevation, 417.23 ft (127.17 m), Oct. 1.

Capacity Table
(based on data from U.S. Army Corps of Engineers)

Elevation, in feet	Contents in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents in acre-feet
328	0	492	10,621
426	3,206	525	16,990

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	419.40	478.71	495.43	498.94	504.51	506.63	507.86	516.61	519.87	520.37	519.43	517.74
2	421.35	479.28	495.52	499.06	504.69	506.67	507.87	518.88	519.85	520.47	519.42	517.85
3	422.32	479.77	495.43	499.23	504.83	506.71	507.99	519.78	520.23	519.67	519.50	518.09
4	423.77	479.63	495.53	499.36	504.82	506.73	508.02	520.14	520.50	519.65	519.53	518.30
5	425.09	479.61	495.83	499.48	504.93	506.77	508.04	520.37	519.51	519.78	519.55	518.40
6	428.12	483.26	496.15	499.59	505.00	506.81	508.05	520.45	519.74	519.89	519.59	518.49
7	432.94	483.76	496.30	499.72	505.10	506.84	508.06	520.19	519.92	520.07	519.68	518.55
8	436.75	484.19	495.99	499.80	505.17	507.00	508.11	519.59	519.91	520.23	519.70	518.58
9	439.58	484.63	495.43	499.93	505.24	507.06	508.20	520.70	519.53	520.32	519.72	518.69
10	442.05	485.02	495.22	500.02	505.31	507.10	508.23	519.72	519.74	519.37	519.84	519.62
11	444.79	485.41	495.46	500.12	505.36	507.14	508.45	519.73	519.93	519.58	519.86	519.93
12	446.69	486.22	495.70	500.22	505.45	507.16	508.65	519.90	520.12	519.87	519.91	520.04
13	448.28	486.95	495.91	500.32	505.53	507.20	509.31	520.06	520.31	520.07	519.96	520.17
14	450.18	487.49	496.16	500.39	505.60	507.24	509.59	519.55	520.06	520.29	520.00	520.21
15	451.73	488.08	496.41	500.50	505.65	507.37	509.85	519.67	519.79	520.09	517.38	520.32
16	452.49	489.60	496.54	500.58	505.83	507.39	510.05	519.95	520.00	519.97	518.16	520.35
17	454.12	491.13	496.60	500.69	505.92	507.42	510.14	520.18	520.12	520.07	518.30	520.46
18	454.61	491.96	496.73	500.75	505.97	507.43	510.25	519.89	520.17	A	518.35	520.71
19	455.33	492.45	496.85	500.83	506.13	507.45	510.33	519.55	519.83	A	518.46	520.82
20	456.44	494.71	496.80	500.93	506.19	507.45	510.47	519.76	519.79	A	518.52	521.14
21	457.35	494.59	496.93	501.00	506.25	507.47	510.53	521.42	520.03	520.10	518.65	521.31
22	458.23	494.72	497.06	501.07	506.30	507.49	510.60	519.88	520.25	519.58	518.90	521.43
23	466.62	494.62	497.22	501.16	506.36	507.49	510.65	519.93	520.38	519.66	517.75	521.64
24	467.13	494.92	497.37	501.23	506.40	507.58	510.81	520.35	520.37	519.83	517.05	521.84
25	467.19	494.80	497.47	501.30	506.43	507.64	510.89	520.04	520.39	519.90	517.04	521.95
26	469.57	494.99	497.69	501.36	506.46	507.67	510.93	520.72	520.48	520.04	517.07	522.24
27	471.10	495.32	497.87	501.47	506.52	507.70	511.00	521.51	519.57	520.13	517.29	522.43
28	472.25	495.10	498.02	502.16	506.60	507.74	511.28	520.64	519.88	520.24	517.46	522.99
29	474.95	495.11	498.42	503.78	---	507.78	513.73	519.88	520.07	520.29	517.53	523.03
30	476.49	495.30	498.61	504.15	---	507.79	515.41	519.95	520.27	520.35	517.52	523.41
31	477.67	---	498.81	504.33	---	507.85	---	520.00	---	520.40	517.64	---
MEAN	450.47	488.71	496.63	500.76	505.66	507.28	509.78	519.97	520.02	---	518.67	520.36
MAX	477.67	495.32	498.81	504.33	506.60	507.85	515.41	521.51	520.50	---	520.00	523.41
MIN	419.40	478.71	495.22	498.94	504.51	506.63	507.86	516.61	519.51	---	517.04	517.74

A No gage-height record

RIO BUCANA BASIN

50114000 RIO CERRILLOS NEAR PONCE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°04'15", long 66°34'51", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on right bank off Highway 139, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) below Lago Cerrillos Dam, 2.3 mi (3.7 km) upstream from Quebrada Ausubo and 4.6 mi (7.4 km) northeast of Plaza Degetau in Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.8 mi² (46.1 km²), excludes 17.4 mi² (45.1 km²), upstream from Lago Cerrillos Dam.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February to April 1964 (monthly measurements only), May 1964 to June 1985, July 1985 to April 1991 (semi-monthly measurements only), May 1991 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 253.10 ft (77.145 m), above mean sea level. Prior to March 22, 1977 at site 0.15 mi (0.24 km) upstream and datum 9.90 ft (3.018 m) higher.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Flow regulated by Lago Cerrillos Dam since May 1991. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. Prior to June 1985 some low-flow regulation by construction upstream. Maximum discharge prior to regulation, 22,400 ft³/s (6.34 m³/s), Sept. 16, 1975, gage-height, 11.2 ft (3.414 m), site and datum them in use from floodmarks, from rating curve extended above 150 ft³/s (4.25 m³/s), on basis of slope-area measurements of peak flow; minimum discharge prior to regulation, 2.2 ft³/s (0.062 m³/s), May 28, 1967.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	3.5	12	17	4.9	4.3	4.2	7.6	9.8	45	5.2	109	6.0
2	3.1	13	11	4.9	4.2	4.2	7.4	12	34	5.3	4.4	5.5
3	2.3	13	15	4.7	4.2	4.2	7.4	12	4.2	144	3.9	5.5
4	2.0	13	8.8	4.7	4.2	4.2	7.2	20	6.0	17	3.8	5.5
5	2.0	13	6.4	4.7	4.2	4.2	6.9	11	129	5.1	3.8	5.6
6	5.2	14	6.2	4.6	4.2	5.2	6.9	35	7.0	5.2	3.6	5.8
7	2.4	13	17	4.5	4.2	4.2	6.7	88	6.8	5.4	3.6	5.7
8	46	13	73	4.8	5.5	4.3	6.6	126	e40	5.3	3.5	5.8
9	169	14	135	4.5	4.3	4.4	6.5	51	114	5.4	3.5	6.0
10	144	14	49	4.5	4.2	4.5	6.6	176	14	120	3.4	6.1
11	3.7	14	5.5	4.5	4.2	4.5	6.5	38	8.8	45	3.5	6.2
12	3.3	12	5.4	4.6	4.1	4.5	6.2	7.5	9.0	5.6	3.4	6.5
13	3.1	14	5.4	4.7	4.2	4.9	6.5	7.5	9.5	5.2	3.3	6.6
14	3.1	14	13	4.7	4.2	6.0	6.4	113	69	4.9	3.2	6.7
15	27	16	5.3	4.7	4.2	7.4	6.1	12	63	40	206	6.9
16	80	17	11	4.7	4.5	7.9	6.0	7.5	8.7	37	9.1	6.9
17	80	27	18	4.7	4.2	7.8	6.2	8.9	7.3	4.7	8.9	6.9
18	83	17	12	4.5	4.4	7.6	6.2	57	17	4.7	8.8	7.2
19	44	29	11	4.4	5.4	7.6	6.5	63	127	4.4	8.8	7.5
20	3.2	26	27	4.4	4.9	7.6	6.6	7.6	59	4.2	9.0	12
21	3.2	25	8.9	4.3	4.9	7.6	6.7	89	5.9	69	9.2	16
22	3.2	74	9.9	4.2	4.5	7.6	6.7	261	5.8	69	10	16
23	6.8	108	5.4	4.2	4.2	7.6	6.7	74	5.7	9.3	127	14
24	167	111	5.7	4.2	4.2	7.6	7.2	61	22	5.3	93	9.5
25	259	63	9.5	4.2	4.2	7.7	7.1	111	27	4.6	25	9.7
26	103	48	5.1	4.2	4.2	7.9	7.1	90	5.9	4.5	20	9.3
27	12	41	4.9	4.2	4.2	7.9	7.1	314	125	4.4	11	9.8
28	13	54	4.9	4.4	4.2	7.9	7.1	287	5.9	4.2	8.1	11
29	12	56	5.2	4.8	---	8.1	8.2	152	5.2	4.1	7.6	54
30	14	72	5.1	4.4	---	8.0	10	58	5.1	4.1	27	72
31	13	---	5.0	4.4	---	7.9	---	48	---	4.0	17	---
TOTAL	1316.1	970	521.6	140.2	122.4	195.2	206.9	2407.8	991.8	656.1	761.4	352.2
MEAN	42.5	32.3	16.8	4.52	4.37	6.30	6.90	77.7	33.1	21.2	24.6	11.7
MAX	259	111	135	4.9	5.5	8.1	10	314	129	144	206	72
MIN	2.0	12	4.9	4.2	4.1	4.2	6.0	7.5	4.2	4.0	3.2	5.5
AC-FT	2610	1920	1030	278	243	387	410	4780	1970	1300	1510	699
CFSM	2.39	1.82	.95	.25	.25	.35	1.39	4.36	1.86	1.19	1.38	.66
IN.	2.75	2.03	1.09	.29	.26	.41	.43	5.03	2.07	1.37	1.59	.74

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1964 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1964	1965	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993					
MEAN	78.3	60.8	24.0	15.8	10.2	10.3	17.0	42.4	29.8	26.5	35.9	64.7																							
MAX	202	124	49.1	74.2	20.0	20.3	106	221	88.9	71.1	82.4	256																							
(WY)	1971	1978	1966	1992	1969	1969	1985	1985	1969	1968	1968	1975																							
MIN	27.7	15.3	7.60	4.52	4.37	5.13	4.93	4.14	4.10	6.26	13.2	11.7																							
(WY)	1966	1992	1977	1993	1993	1977	1979	1967	1974	1976	1984	1993																							

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1964 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	11495.84	8641.7	
ANNUAL MEAN	31.4	23.7	34.3
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			53.9
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			17.2
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	900	Jan 6	314
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.64	Aug 19	2.0
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	1.7	Aug 24	2.9
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			616
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			5.74
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	22800	17140	24830
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.76	1.33	1.93
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	24.03	18.06	26.17
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	73	72	79
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	14	6.9	17
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	3.1	4.2	5.8

e Estimated

RIO BUCANA BASIN

50114000 RIO CERRILLOS NEAR PONCE, PR

Location.--Lat 18°04'15", long 66°34'51", Hydrologic unit 21010004, on right bank off Highway 139, 2.3 mi (3.7 km) upstream from Quebrada Ausubo and 4.6 mi (7.4 km) northeast of Plaza Degetau in Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.8 mi² (46.1 km²)

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1964 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
27...	1215	12	400	7.7	29.0	38	6.1	79	12	K20	K70
DEC 08...	1210	4.5	306	7.8	23.9	1.2	7.9	105	<10	42000	7700
MAR 1993											
01...	1055	4.4	470	7.9	25.5	0.90	7.1	97	<10	70	K110
APR 13...	1150	6.3	422	7.6	27.0	0.70	5.7	71	<10	K20	K120
JUN 15...	1415	11	423	7.9	28.0	1.0	8.5	110	<10	4900	680
AUG 16...	1300	11	392	7.4	26.0	340	5.2	64	16	200	70

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
27...	440	5	150	15	30	0.6	1.4	120	<0.5	22	11
DEC 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--
MAR 1993											
01...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
APR 13...	190	10	63	6.9	23	0.7	0.90	150	<0.5	56	7.8
JUN 15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
AUG 16...	140	2	42	9.2	27	1	2.2	140	--	45	22

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
27...	0.20	27	578	18.7	3	11.0	0.010	11.0	0.020	0.48
DEC 08...	--	--	--	--	2	0.860	0.040	0.900	0.050	0.35
MAR 1993										
01...	--	--	--	--	5	0.890	0.010	0.900	0.010	0.29
APR 13...	0.30	26	274	4.66	1	0.490	0.010	0.500	0.030	0.47
JUN 15...	--	--	--	--	5	0.690	0.010	0.700	0.070	0.63
AUG 16...	0.20	21	253	7.50	596	0.860	0.040	0.900	0.050	0.35

K = non-ideal count

RIO BUCANA BASIN

50114390 RIO BUCANA AT HWY 14 BRIDGE NEAR PONCE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°02'29", long 66°34'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on left bank, 200 ft (61 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 14 and 4.0 mi (6.4 km) downstream from Lago Cerrillos Dam, 2.8 mi (4.5 km) northeast of Degetau Plaza in Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--24.9 mi² (64.5 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to September 1986 (maximum only), published as "Rio Bucaná Floodway Channel at Highway 14 bridge", October 1986 to July 1987 (maximum only), August 1987 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Datum of gage is 116.40 ft (35.500 m) above mean sea level. Prior to Oct. 1, 1986, crest-stage gage located at Highway 14 bridge, at elevation of mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Only minor regulation of low flow until Aug. 18, 1992, afterward flow regulated by Lago Cerrillos Dam 0.4 mi upstream. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	4.3	5.6	19	11	7.3	5.6	5.6	15	21	14	96	8.8
2	3.5	5.5	18	10	7.1	5.7	5.8	11	68	14	39	7.2
3	3.3	5.6	17	10	7.3	5.8	5.9	10	18	91	10	5.0
4	2.7	5.2	18	9.9	6.5	5.8	6.1	11	8.8	73	9.5	5.0
5	2.7	5.2	11	9.8	6.1	5.4	5.2	11	69	24	9.6	5.0
6	6.8	5.3	6.3	9.8	5.7	5.2	4.7	10	26	17	9.5	5.2
7	3.6	5.4	6.7	9.8	5.6	5.3	5.0	21	13	16	9.1	5.2
8	5.2	5.4	13	9.5	5.8	5.4	5.2	48	10	15	9.1	5.2
9	42	5.4	27	9.4	6.0	5.4	6.3	27	66	15	9.1	6.0
10	47	5.2	25	9.4	6.0	5.4	4.5	98	56	62	8.9	5.1
11	13	5.2	12	9.4	5.2	5.5	3.8	61	22	100	9.5	4.9
12	5.9	5.2	6.5	9.4	5.0	5.8	4.5	15	15	31	9.3	4.7
13	5.0	5.2	6.3	9.4	4.8	6.0	7.5	12	13	20	9.1	4.7
14	4.3	5.0	8.6	9.4	4.7	5.9	6.3	39	17	16	9.3	4.7
15	5.9	6.9	8.2	9.6	4.5	6.1	4.7	43	81	18	331	4.7
16	18	7.5	8.1	9.5	5.3	6.3	4.6	7.6	26	54	55	4.9
17	22	9.2	12	9.8	5.1	6.2	4.8	7.5	16	28	23	4.9
18	23	8.4	13	9.8	4.6	6.6	5.6	8.5	14	19	11	5.5
19	20	6.4	13	9.8	5.7	6.6	5.4	63	83	16	11	5.9
20	9.9	9.6	17	9.8	6.9	6.6	7.5	15	98	14	9.9	6.4
21	5.0	8.3	14	9.4	5.4	6.0	4.8	20	28	21	9.3	6.6
22	5.4	11	13	9.1	5.0	5.8	4.7	214	19	66	13	6.5
23	5.1	25	12	8.8	4.9	5.8	4.8	79	16	47	86	7.2
24	42	29	11	8.3	4.7	5.9	8.2	64	25	18	169	7.2
25	93	20	12	8.0	4.8	5.9	5.7	120	26	11	33	6.5
26	35	15	11	7.8	5.0	5.6	5.7	48	19	10	21	6.4
27	12	15	10	7.6	5.0	5.3	6.1	297	84	10	22	6.4
28	5.7	19	10	8.5	5.0	6.6	6.5	320	35	9.7	10	6.9
29	5.6	20	10	14	---	5.9	8.0	185	19	9.6	8.7	11
30	6.1	31	10	9.7	---	5.8	13	38	15	9.7	14	40
31	6.5	---	11	7.8	---	5.7	---	86	---	9.9	22	---
TOTAL	469.5	315.7	389.7	293.5	155.0	180.9	176.5	2004.6	1026.8	878.9	1095.9	213.7
MEAN	15.1	10.5	12.6	9.47	5.54	5.84	5.88	64.7	34.2	28.4	35.4	7.12
MAX	93	31	27	14	7.3	6.6	13	320	98	100	331	40
MIN	2.7	5.0	6.3	7.6	4.5	5.2	3.8	7.5	8.8	9.6	8.7	4.7
AC-FT	931	626	773	582	307	359	350	3980	2040	1740	2170	424
CFSM	.61	.42	.50	.38	.22	.23	.24	2.60	1.37	1.14	1.42	.29
IN.	.70	.47	.58	.44	.23	.27	.26	2.99	1.53	1.31	1.64	.32

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1987 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	182	84.2	21.6	67.3	10.4	16.0	18.8
MAX	527	222	49.1	337	17.3	48.0	42.5
(WY)	1991	1988	1988	1992	1992	1989	1992
MIN	15.1	10.5	12.6	9.47	5.54	5.81	5.88
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1990

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1987 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	19239.2	7200.7	
ANNUAL MEAN	52.6	19.7	55.1
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			78.0
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			19.7
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	4340	Jan 6	4340
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	2.5	Sep 28	2.5
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	2.8	Sep 23	2.8
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			1010
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			10.13
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	38160	14280	39920
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.11	.79	2.21
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	28.74	10.76	30.07
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	55	42	98
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	14	9.3	14
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	5.2	5.0	5.8

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50115000 RIO PORTUGUES NEAR PONCE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°04'45", long 66°38'01", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on right bank 30 ft (9 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 504, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from small unnamed tributary, 4.4 mi (7.1 km) upstream from Río Chiquito, and 4.7 mi (7.6 km) north of Plaza Degetau in Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.82 mi² (22.84 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February to June 1964 (monthly measurements only), July 1964 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 470 ft (143 m), from topographic map. Prior to Dec. 4, 1964, non-recording gage at same site and datum.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Some low-flow regulation due to unknown activity upstream. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	17	29	19	8.4	11	6.2	4.7	90	e21	15	8.3	10
2	15	27	18	8.2	8.9	6.5	4.7	110	e19	15	8.8	13
3	13	28	17	8.1	10	6.2	6.8	105	e18	24	9.4	9.5
4	41	23	16	8.1	7.3	5.9	5.3	68	e17	18	10	8.5
5	e68	20	15	8.8	6.7	5.4	5.2	36	e17	24	11	8.5
6	e198	20	15	8.6	6.5	5.3	5.3	29	e15	19	11	9.6
7	e174	19	14	7.4	6.2	5.3	5.3	28	e16	16	11	8.0
8	e126	18	14	7.4	6.2	5.3	8.8	27	e96	19	10	9.8
9	e126	16	14	7.7	6.1	5.5	10	62	e99	17	10	9.1
10	232	15	16	6.8	5.9	5.6	6.6	36	23	15	11	36
11	129	13	e13	6.2	5.8	5.3	17	23	16	47	10	8.0
12	65	86	e13	6.2	5.7	5.4	23	19	15	18	9.8	7.0
13	36	57	e14	6.4	5.7	5.6	32	16	13	15	8.6	9.2
14	72	31	e16	6.9	5.3	5.9	18	20	13	17	8.5	8.0
15	e120	37	e14	7.4	5.1	6.4	29	14	20	12	9.6	6.4
16	87	65	e11	7.3	20	5.9	26	12	18	11	53	7.6
17	131	81	e10	7.1	11	5.3	15	11	13	11	11	7.3
18	91	44	12	7.1	6.8	5.3	12	9.7	12	11	12	6.7
19	55	34	12	7.1	8.0	4.8	12	8.5	40	11	11	6.4
20	45	e72	12	7.1	8.9	4.8	10	11	39	11	11	24
21	38	e49	12	7.0	6.6	4.8	11	77	21	12	12	11
22	33	34	12	6.9	6.0	4.8	11	17	19	14	31	14
23	127	28	12	7.1	6.1	4.6	11	12	17	12	20	19
24	e150	25	12	6.2	6.0	5.4	16	14	15	12	13	13
25	e126	22	12	6.2	5.6	7.2	15	11	13	9.4	11	8.7
26	45	20	14	6.1	5.8	6.4	11	85	15	7.5	10	15
27	31	21	13	6.0	5.9	5.3	e13	225	16	7.3	41	12
28	26	36	11	40	6.1	5.4	e39	93	18	7.3	13	23
29	41	36	e29	172	---	5.1	e136	37	16	7.2	7.8	22
30	36	24	e18	39	---	5.2	137	29	15	7.9	7.7	107
31	36	---	e10	19	---	5.1	---	33	---	7.8	10	---
TOTAL	2530	1030	440	463.8	205.2	171.2	656.7	1368.2	705	450.4	421.5	457.3
MEAN	81.6	34.3	14.2	15.0	7.33	5.52	21.9	44.1	23.5	14.5	13.6	15.2
MAX	232	86	29	172	20	7.2	137	225	99	47	53	107
MIN	13	13	10	6.0	5.1	4.6	4.7	8.5	12	7.2	7.7	6.4
AC-FT	5020	2040	873	920	407	340	1300	2710	1400	893	836	907
CFSM	9.25	3.89	1.61	1.70	.83	.63	2.48	5.00	2.66	1.65	1.54	1.73
IN.	10.67	4.34	1.86	1.96	.87	.72	2.77	5.77	2.97	1.90	1.78	1.93

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1964 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1964	1965	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	44.8	33.6	12.6	9.02	6.17	5.73	7.59	20.2	15.2	14.6	20.5	34.7																		
MAX	116	80.1	27.3	45.5	13.3	13.4	27.1	72.9	48.3	54.2	87.5	132																		
(WY)	1991	1988	1988	1992	1976	1976	1983	1985	1979	1979	1979	1975																		
MIN	11.9	5.85	2.71	3.65	2.62	2.08	2.45	1.65	2.33	2.65	4.20	7.22																		
(WY)	1992	1992	1992	1989	1989	1977	1974	1973	1974	1976	1972	1991																		

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1964 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	8552.5		8899.3			
ANNUAL MEAN	23.4		24.4		18.7	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					38.0	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					8.04	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	794		232		2440	
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	2.0		4.6		1.1	
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	3.1		4.9		1.3	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			2850		21000	
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			9.58		20.20	
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW					1.0	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	16960		17650		13550	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.65		2.76		2.12	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	36.07		37.53		28.80	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	45		56		40	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	10		12		8.4	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	3.8		5.9		3.1	

e Estimated

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50115000 RIO PORTUGUES NEAR PONCE, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1964 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
26...	1415	36	252	7.6	24.5	49	5.0	60	<10	760	480
DEC											
09...	1000	14	324	8.2	20.9	13	8.5	104	<10	230	K170
MAR 1993											
02...	1130	6.4	310	8.1	21.5	0.40	9.1	110	<10	K170	K70
APR											
14...	1220	18	273	7.4	23.5	330	5.7	68	36	K1500	K1400
JUN											
16...	1300	16	247	8.1	27.5	0.50	8.1	100	14	570	380
AUG											
17...	1225	12	262	7.0	26.5	6.2	5.4	65	12	230	K150

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
26...	120	0	38	5.8	8.2	0.3	1.2	140	<0.5	7.4	6.7
DEC											
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
MAR 1993											
02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
APR											
14...	69	0	19	5.3	11	0.6	3.0	97	<0.5	16	11
JUN											
16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
AUG											
17...	200	1	53	16	34	1	4.0	60	--	33	34

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
26...	0.10	23	174	16.9	12	1.30	<0.010	1.30	0.010	0.19
DEC										
09...	--	--	--	--	<1	0.590	0.010	1.10	0.010	0.29
MAR 1993										
02...	--	--	--	--	<1	1.09	0.010	1.10	0.010	0.29
APR										
14...	<0.10	20	143	7.13	1000	0.990	0.010	1.00	0.010	0.59
JUN										
16...	--	--	--	--	24	0.890	0.010	0.900	0.010	0.29
AUG										
17...	0.20	31	241	7.81	4	0.590	0.010	0.600	0.030	0.27

K = non-ideal count

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN
 50116200 RIO PORTUGUES AT PONCE, PR
 WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'20", long 66°36'28", 1,300 ft (400 m) south of Las Americas Avenue Bridge, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) south of CSC 50115900, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) west of Highways 1 and 2 junction, and 0.7 mi (1.1 km) southeast of Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.9 mi² (49.0 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI (FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
28...	1335	4.6	297	7.8	30.0	10	5.3	70	<10	K1400	K160
DEC 09...	1125	5.6	418	7.9	24.2	12	9.6	110	<10	4900	440
MAR 1993											
02...	1240	10	475	7.8	26.0	15	7.3	88	17	K7300	K890
APR 14...	1350	40	365	7.5	30.5	240	5.3	70	15	27000	5400
JUN 24...	1330	16	340	7.7	32.5	4.1	6.1	74	34	4400	21000
AUG 17...	1400	23	395	7.5	32.5	22	6.1	79	<10	21000	3800

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
28...	110	0	33	6.1	14	0.2	2.4	120	<0.5	23	36
DEC 09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
MAR 1993											
02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
APR 14...	120	3	35	6.7	16	0.6	1.7	110	<0.5	19	14
JUN 24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
AUG 17...	180	17	61	6.7	18	0.6	0.90	160	--	45	7.0

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
28...	0.10	21	320	3.97	<1	0.940	0.010	0.950	0.030	0.27
DEC 09...	--	--	--	--	26	0.660	0.040	0.700	0.090	0.31
MAR 1993										
02...	--	--	--	--	26	0.900	0.100	1.00	0.260	0.44
APR 14...	0.10	20	178	19.5	740	1.08	0.020	1.10	0.410	0.19
JUN 24...	--	--	--	--	20	0.580	0.020	0.600	0.060	0.84
AUG 17...	0.20	22	257	15.9	22	0.470	0.030	0.500	0.110	2.2

K = non-ideal count

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50116200 RIO PORTUGUES AT PONCE, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1992 28...	0.30	1.2	5.5	0.130	<1	<100	<10	<1	4	<10
DEC 09...	0.40	1.1	4.8	0.150	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1993 02...	0.70	0.50	1.7	0.100	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 14...	0.60	1.5	1.3	0.160	<1	<100	40	<1	4	20
JUN 24...	0.90	1.3	6.6	0.080	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 17...	2.3	2.8	12	0.060	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA-NESE, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE-NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY-LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB-STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1992 28...	21000	5	700	<0.10	<1	<1	<10	<0.010	2	0.06
DEC 09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1993 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 14...	11000	4	530	<0.10	<1	<1	50	<0.010	<1	0.02
JUN 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR-DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI-AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI-ELDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO-SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1993 01...	1145	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010

DATE	ENDRIN WATER UNPLTRD REC (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA-CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA-CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH-OXY-CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL-PARA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1993 01...	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH-THA-LENES, POLY-CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER-THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX-APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI-THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1993 01...	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

RIO GUAYANILLA BASIN

50124200 RIO GUAYANILLA NEAR GUAYANILLA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°02'40", long 66°47'53", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on left bank, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) north of junction of Highways 2 and 132, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) downstream from Quebrada Consejo, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) north-northwest from Plaza de Guayanilla.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.9 mi² (49.0 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1981 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 80 ft (24 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	103	48	46	18	15	4.5	3.2	123	20	23	6.3	15
2	65	46	35	14	12	5.0	3.0	142	17	21	5.4	24
3	24	55	30	14	15	4.9	2.9	169	15	23	5.4	18
4	20	39	29	13	11	4.6	3.0	162	13	22	5.2	11
5	99	34	25	12	9.6	4.6	3.1	68	11	25	7.0	12
6	299	31	24	12	8.9	4.9	3.1	39	9.2	36	6.3	7.9
7	208	29	22	12	8.5	5.0	3.3	32	9.2	33	5.5	8.4
8	149	25	20	12	7.6	4.6	3.1	23	33	28	4.6	27
9	231	23	18	11	6.8	4.8	16	218	28	21	4.6	39
10	286	22	17	11	6.8	4.6	11	109	21	17	4.6	16
11	184	20	16	11	6.7	4.2	6.5	47	15	19	4.7	17
12	89	68	15	11	6.3	3.9	14	30	13	23	5.3	8.4
13	67	136	32	11	6.3	4.0	10	22	19	17	4.5	8.6
14	76	91	61	11	6.2	4.0	8.8	20	14	27	4.1	12
15	129	82	50	11	8.5	4.3	13	16	16	17	7.9	7.1
16	121	84	27	11	28	4.2	28	21	17	15	66	30
17	88	186	22	11	18	3.8	8.2	16	12	14	22	27
18	71	173	19	11	7.1	3.9	5.2	11	63	11	10	13
19	59	98	17	11	18	3.7	17	9.9	157	10	7.8	8.9
20	61	86	16	11	11	3.9	13	13	97	10	6.9	9.8
21	49	69	16	11	4.8	3.7	12	13	44	8.5	6.3	12
22	50	55	15	11	4.0	3.6	7.8	13	31	8.0	97	7.0
23	65	48	14	12	3.9	7.1	5.8	9.6	24	12	103	105
24	137	42	14	9.2	17	6.6	5.0	27	19	8.7	35	38
25	125	37	13	9.1	19	4.4	4.5	35	17	9.5	18	18
26	78	34	18	8.6	6.2	4.3	3.8	79	15	8.6	13	130
27	62	41	16	7.6	5.2	4.3	3.4	195	e13	7.7	23	80
28	53	38	13	19	4.3	4.4	39	106	e18	8.5	55	50
29	69	65	12	73	---	4.0	60	41	32	7.6	47	33
30	83	66	15	27	---	4.0	187	30	27	6.8	50	42
31	61	---	46	17	---	3.8	---	23	---	6.3	21	---
TOTAL	3261	1871	733	443.5	281.7	137.6	503.7	1862.5	839.4	504.2	662.4	835.1
MEAN	105	62.4	23.6	14.3	10.1	4.44	16.8	60.1	28.0	16.3	21.4	27.8
MAX	299	186	61	73	28	7.1	187	218	157	36	103	130
MIN	20	20	12	7.6	3.9	3.6	2.9	9.6	9.2	6.3	4.1	7.0
AC-FT	6470	3710	1450	880	559	273	999	3690	1660	1000	1310	1660
CFSM	5.57	3.30	1.25	.76	.53	.23	.89	3.18	1.48	.86	1.13	1.47
IN.	6.42	3.68	1.44	.87	.55	.27	.99	3.67	1.65	.99	1.30	1.64

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1981 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	68.1	54.0	20.4	11.3	7.41	6.06	11.2	31.1	15.9	12.5	18.7	40.9	
MAX	167	110	41.9	27.5	11.4	13.2	26.6	80.4	41.0	25.9	48.5	102	
(WY)	1986	1988	1988	1992	1985	1989	1983	1985	1987	1986	1988	1981	
MIN	16.0	21.5	11.9	6.97	3.10	2.85	4.39	5.83	3.28	5.22	6.72	7.46	
(WY)	1983	1989	1989	1991	1990	1981	1984	1988	1991	1990	1985	1983	

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1981 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	11551.8		11935.1			
ANNUAL MEAN	31.6		32.7		24.4	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					33.1	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					16.3	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	408	Jan 6	299	Oct 6	1500	Oct 7 1985
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.2	Mar 16	2.9	Apr 3	.97	Aug 21 1990
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	3.4	Mar 13	3.1	Apr 2	1.7	Aug 15 1990
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			1190	Sep 26	14700	Sep 12 1982
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			10.13	Sep 26	20.40	Sep 12 1982
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	22910		23670		17690	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.67		1.73		1.29	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	22.74		23.49		17.55	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	70		83		53	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	15		16		10	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	4.9		4.6		3.9	

e Estimated

RIO GUAYANILLA BASIN

50124700 RIO GUAYANILLA AT CENTRAL RUFINA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'40", long 66°46'49", at dirt road bridge, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) from mouth, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) east of Central Rufina and 0.9 mi (1.4 km) southeast of Guayanilla.

DRAINAGE AREA.--22.8 mi² (59.1 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1960-65, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (PERCENT SATURATION) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992										
29...	1210	9.3	405	7.7	29.0	2.1	5.8	74	<10	K1000 K100
DEC 10...	1105	11	430	8.2	25.0	3.6	8.2	91	<10	10 10
FEB 1993										
19...	1230	4.3	528	7.8	27.0	5.6	9.4	108	21	K10 K10
APR 21...	1550	3.7	516	7.6	32.0	4.5	4.1	54	12	K30 50
JUN 24...	1220	15	316	7.6	32.0	0.40	5.3	69	22	10 10
AUG 18...	1200	4.0	490	7.3	30.5	4.8	5.0	65	<10	10 10

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY, TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
29...	130	20	44	11	18	0.5	4.0	160	<0.5	40	18
DEC 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	170	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
APR 21...	170	17	42	15	21	0.7	2.4	130	<0.5	41	20
JUN 24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
AUG 18...	180	5	50	14	25	0.8	2.0	130	--	48	22

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
29...	<0.10	22	219	5.50	<1	1.38	0.020	1.40	0.020	0.38
DEC 10...	--	--	--	--	23	0.780	0.020	0.800	0.580	0.22
FEB 1993										
19...	--	--	--	--	4	1.28	0.020	1.30	0.250	0.75
APR 21...	0.10	19	238	2.38	20	0.570	0.030	0.600	0.780	0.92
JUN 24...	--	--	--	--	9	1.47	0.030	1.50	1.10	1.1
AUG 18...	0.10	20	259	2.80	15	1.28	0.020	1.30	0.250	0.75

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUAYANILLA BASIN

50124700 RIO GUAYANILLA AT CENTRAL RUFINA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1992 29...	0.40	1.8	8.0	0.240	<1	<100	30	<1	<1	<10
DEC 10...	0.80	1.6	18	0.370	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993 19...	1.0	2.3	10	0.740	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 21...	1.7	3.7	16	0.660	1	<100	50	<1	<1	<10
JUN 24...	2.2	4.2	12	0.220	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 18...	1.0	2.5	9	0.600	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA-NESE, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE-NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY-LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB-STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1992 29...	1900	3	70	<0.10	<1	<1	30	<0.010	6	0.05
DEC 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993 19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 21...	430	1	50	<0.10	<1	<1	20	<0.010	2	0.09
JUN 24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR-DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI-AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI-ELDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO-SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1993 01...	1250	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.03	<0.010	<0.010

DATE	ENDRIN WATER UNFLTRD REC (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA-CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA-CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH-OXY-CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL-PARA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1993 01...	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH-THA-LENES, POLY-CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER-THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX-APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI-THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1993 01...	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

RIO YAUCO BASIN

50125780 LAGO LUCCHETTI AT DAMSITE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°05'37", long 66°51'54", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Antonio Lucchetti Dam on Río Yauco, 3.9 mi (6.3 km) north of Yauco.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.4 mi² (45.1 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1989 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Lucchetti was completed in 1952. The dam is on Río Yauco and is a unit of the Southwestern Puerto Rico Project. It provides 16,500 acre-feet (20.3 hm³) of usable storage for power generation and irrigation. The dam is a concrete gravity structure with a total length of 591 ft (180 m), a maximum height of 178 ft (54 m), and a maximum width at the base of 150 ft (46 m). An ungated, overflow type spillway with a clear length of 171 ft (52 m) and a crest elevation of 570 ft (174 m), occupies the central portion of the dam. The spillway was designed for a maximum capacity of 62,800 ft³/s (1,778 m³/s) at a design head of 20 ft (6 m). The dam is owned by Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation, 572.19 ft (174.40 m), May 27, 1993; minimum elevation, 519.85 ft (158.45 m), Oct. 23, 1991.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 572.19 ft (174.40 m), May 27; minimum elevation, 530.07 ft (161.56 m), Aug. 6.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Water Resources Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
519	2,275	540	5,165
520	2,385	550	7,020
525	2,965	561	9,600
527	3,255	563	10,125
530	3,695	571	12,125
532	3,975	573	12,645

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	A	A	556.84	563.38	556.28	562.96	561.61	570.75	566.51	552.15	A	543.89
2	A	A	556.95	563.37	557.46	563.39	561.56	570.79	566.20	551.96	A	544.14
3	A	A	557.87	563.36	557.83	563.08	561.51	570.69	566.05	552.03	A	544.14
4	A	A	559.34	563.34	559.50	563.84	561.48	570.33	565.75	552.08	530.28	544.14
5	A	568.94	560.75	562.44	561.13	563.84	560.59	569.45	565.26	551.91	530.22	544.14
6	536.13	568.08	562.14	562.45	562.58	564.15	560.54	568.68	565.31	552.24	530.23	544.08
7	538.07	569.96	563.52	562.01	564.05	564.13	559.07	569.42	564.31	552.58	530.70	544.08
8	539.55	570.46	563.25	562.02	564.54	564.11	559.09	569.19	563.99	552.63	A	544.08
9	539.53	570.04	563.59	562.01	563.55	564.08	559.08	570.57	564.85	552.57	A	544.08
10	541.40	569.24	564.82	562.01	562.77	564.07	559.04	569.89	564.82	552.20	A	545.34
11	542.64	568.26	566.05	562.01	562.89	564.13	559.20	568.70	565.48	550.43	535.72	546.92
12	543.60	568.62	567.16	560.46	563.32	563.86	559.42	569.17	566.48	550.35	536.76	547.12
13	544.35	569.83	568.48	560.45	563.30	563.80	559.87	569.93	565.93	550.22	A	547.15
14	544.51	570.41	569.69	559.66	563.31	563.80	560.02	569.77	566.41	550.58	A	547.43
15	544.71	570.90	569.93	559.64	565.01	563.09	560.72	569.82	566.35	549.91	538.45	547.50
16	546.23	570.25	570.16	558.04	565.15	563.31	561.94	569.43	566.25	547.87	A	A
17	547.14	570.32	570.27	557.66	564.32	563.27	562.20	570.58	565.41	545.81	539.30	A
18	A	571.08	570.19	556.71	563.67	563.24	562.45	570.29	565.27	543.89	A	A
19	A	570.13	570.19	556.23	563.07	563.21	562.21	570.28	565.25	543.85	A	A
20	A	570.21	569.94	555.37	563.41	563.17	562.60	570.00	562.91	544.55	540.87	A
21	A	570.35	568.84	555.09	563.44	563.13	562.06	569.00	561.51	543.38	541.37	A
22	A	570.44	568.30	555.09	563.50	563.10	562.61	569.29	560.03	541.97	542.41	551.73
23	A	569.88	566.91	555.07	563.45	563.07	563.25	569.85	557.90	539.72	542.68	553.82
24	A	568.54	565.30	555.04	563.49	563.05	563.76	569.71	555.54	537.61	542.68	554.21
25	A	566.02	565.33	554.99	563.44	563.03	563.75	569.39	553.54	534.26	542.68	555.93
26	A	563.70	564.16	554.08	563.19	562.99	563.73	570.19	552.28	A	542.73	558.20
27	A	560.98	564.22	553.80	563.07	563.06	564.60	571.18	552.23	A	543.10	564.04
28	A	558.17	563.21	553.85	563.02	563.08	565.16	569.95	552.38	A	543.28	566.09
29	A	557.35	563.25	555.78	---	562.08	565.52	568.87	552.54	A	543.42	567.25
30	A	556.24	563.26	555.75	---	562.05	569.15	567.69	552.63	A	543.70	567.10
31	A	---	563.38	556.23	---	562.02	---	566.81	---	A	543.80	---
TOTAL	---	---	17517.29	17317.39	15753.74	17463.19	16857.79	17659.66	16859.37	---	---	---
MEAN	---	---	565.07	558.63	562.63	563.33	561.93	569.67	561.98	---	---	---
MAX	---	---	570.27	563.38	565.15	564.15	569.15	571.18	566.51	---	---	---
MIN	---	---	556.84	553.80	556.28	562.02	559.04	566.81	552.23	---	---	---

A No gage-height record.

RIO LOCO BASIN

50129700 RIO LOCO AT GUANICA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 17°58'33", long 66°54'52", 0.6 mi (1.0 km) northwest of Guánica and 1.2 mi (1.9 km) northeast of Ensenada.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1975 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
28...	1130	--	446	7.4	26.5	8.3	3.0	43	<10	520	850
DEC 10...	1145	--	600	7.9	24.8	23	4.5	54	<10	490	360
FEB 1993											
17...	1145	--	510	7.9	24.0	4.9	4.9	59	<10	1000	490
APR 19...	1330	--	564	7.4	28.0	50	2.9	37	29	510	430
JUN 02...	1330	--	506	7.9	29.0	12	1.0	21	42	4800	6700
AUG 18...	1315	--	12400	7.1	29.0	18	2.0	27	34	2800	2400

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
28...	970	3	22	18	14	2	3.5	170	<0.5	42	60
DEC 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	170	--	--	--
APR 19...	140	0	29	16	36	1	3.8	140	<0.5	23	58
JUN 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
AUG 18...	170	2	28	25	13	0.4	3.8	150	--	27	19

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
28...	1.1	28	492	--	30	0.500	0.030	0.530	0.060	0.44
DEC 10...	--	--	--	--	12	--	<0.010	0.057	0.030	0.27
FEB 1993										
17...	--	--	--	--	7	--	<0.010	0.082	0.090	0.31
APR 19...	0.10	23	273	--	82	0.076	0.010	0.086	0.040	0.26
JUN 02...	--	--	--	--	58	0.087	0.010	0.097	0.060	0.84
AUG 18...	0.20	28	234	--	40	--	<0.010	0.098	0.050	0.25

RIO LOCO BASIN

50129700 RIO LOCO AT GUANICA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1992 28...	0.50	1.0	4.6	0.270	<1	<100	40	<1	6	<10
DEC 10...	0.30	0.36	1.6	0.060	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993 17...	0.40	0.48	2.1	0.150	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 19...	0.30	0.39	1.7	0.030	<1	<100	70	<1	7	10
JUN 02...	0.90	1.0	4.4	0.270	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 18...	0.30	0.40	1.8	0.100	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1992 28...	860	<1	140	<0.10	<1	<1	<10	<0.010	<1	0.32
DEC 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 19...	930	1	100	<0.10	<1	<1	<10	<0.010	1	0.03
JUN 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993 26...	0845	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010

DATE	ENDRIN WATER UNFLTRD REC (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OKY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993 26...	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993 26...	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01	0.11	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

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RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50131990 RIO GUANAJIBO AT HWY 119 AT SAN GERMAN, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°05'06", long 67°02'02", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, on right bank, at bridge on Hwy 119, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) southwest of junction of Highways 119 and 2, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) northeast of junction of Highways 119 and 102, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) east from public Plaza of San Germán.

DRAINAGE AREA.--34.6 mi² (89.6 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1991 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 148 ft (45 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	58	129	96	32	53	17	7.7	e70	e80	e43	e14	e15
2	55	139	77	31	47	16	8.1	e140	e56	e36	e13	e15
3	50	159	65	31	38	14	8.2	e120	e45	e33	e13	e19
4	44	99	60	30	32	11	8.9	e98	e35	e30	e18	e30
5	92	83	59	28	28	10	7.8	e96	e32	e30	e21	e27
6	96	78	58	28	23	10	7.0	e110	e29	e33	e25	e23
7	272	73	54	33	23	10	7.0	e45	e28	e48	e19	e16
8	236	68	52	31	21	11	8.0	e35	e40	e41	e40	e15
9	142	68	50	27	21	10	8.3	e68	e96	e28	e30	e45
10	431	61	47	25	17	8.3	e8.6	e56	e90	e23	e22	e90
11	460	143	41	25	13	11	e15	e31	e45	e21	e17	e60
12	241	93	38	25	12	12	e45	e25	e60	e21	e16	e35
13	165	180	80	25	15	13	e40	e23	e54	e21	e14	e34
14	212	156	111	24	16	13	e35	e22	e34	e25	e17	e25
15	193	252	75	23	24	15	e54	e21	e31	e20	e21	e22
16	206	227	54	22	61	15	e70	e20	e35	e18	e30	e19
17	356	194	46	21	52	13	e25	e19	e24	e18	e20	e20
18	231	178	40	20	35	11	e17	e18	e30	e19	e18	e25
19	207	130	39	19	30	10	e18	e17	e72	e17	e16	e58
20	152	187	36	19	25	9.8	e14	e22	e56	e16	e15	e40
21	125	147	34	19	21	9.2	e13	e20	e41	e16	e14	e31
22	159	125	33	25	19	8.6	e15	e19	e35	e15	e35	e29
23	444	112	32	24	17	9.8	e11	e50	e33	e16	e80	e127
24	439	89	31	20	18	9.9	e22	e70	e31	e15	e25	e55
25	284	78	31	18	24	9.7	e23	e50	e31	e15	e20	e35
26	216	72	73	17	18	8.9	e14	e60	e29	e17	e17	e46
27	181	104	52	16	16	12	e12	e120	e28	e18	e21	e173
28	154	85	42	18	14	19	e25	e130	e55	e16	e24	e101
29	174	78	40	145	---	12	e27	e80	e66	e15	e27	e64
30	136	78	36	64	---	8.9	e23	e200	e69	e14	e28	e57
31	137	---	35	55	---	8.3	---	e300	---	e14	e18	---
TOTAL	6348	3665	1617	940	733	356.4	597.6	2155	1390	712	708	1351
MEAN	205	122	52.2	30.3	26.2	11.5	19.9	69.5	46.3	23.0	22.8	45.0
MAX	460	252	111	145	61	19	70	300	96	48	80	173
MIN	44	61	31	16	12	8.3	7.0	17	24	14	13	15
MED	181	108	47	25	22	11	14	50	37	19	20	32
AC-FT	12590	7270	3210	1860	1450	707	1190	4270	2760	1410	1400	2680
CFSM	5.92	3.53	1.51	.88	.76	.33	.58	2.01	1.34	.66	.66	1.30
IN.	6.83	3.94	1.74	1.01	.79	.38	.64	2.32	1.49	.77	.76	1.45

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1991 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1991	1992	1993	1991	1992	1993	1991	1992	1993	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	113	69.0	30.2	33.8	15.1	7.51	15.8	49.3	21.0	17.2	22.2	37.2
MAX	205	122	52.2	37.3	26.2	11.5	19.9	69.5	46.3	23.0	22.8	53.7
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1992	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992
MIN	20.4	15.8	8.21	30.3	4.32	3.52	11.7	32.8	5.01	14.0	21.7	12.9
(WY)	1992	1992	1992	1993	1992	1992	1992	1991	1991	1992	1991	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1993 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1991 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	17868.5	20573.0	
ANNUAL MEAN	48.8	56.4	38.5
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			56.4
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			20.8
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	817	460	817
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	1.5	7.0	1.5
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	1.8	7.8	1.8
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		3120	6610
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		10.41	13.23
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	35440	40810	27920
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.41	1.63	1.11
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	19.21	22.12	15.13
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	142	141	78
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	13	30	16
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	2.8	13	4.3

e Estimated

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50133600 RIO GUANAJIBO NEAR SAN GERMAN, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°07'18", long 67°03'56", at bridge on Highway 347, 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northwest of San Germán.

DRAINAGE AREA.--45.5 mi² (117.8 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEARS OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
22...	1245	89	480	7.2	26.0	24	3.0	36	<10	350	210
DEC 29...	1225	64	520	8.0	22.9	12	7.0	80	<10	K1400	240
FEB 1993											
19...	1000	42	459	7.9	24.2	18	9.1	110	14	560	210
APR 21...	1435	100	552	7.2	29.0	17	3.7	48	17	380	430
JUN 03...	1415	56	522	7.8	31.7	2.1	7.8	100	<10	560	480
SEP 08...	1040	49	534	7.3	27.6	0.60	6.5	81	<10	2500	260

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
22...	220	12	25	39	10	0.3	1.5	230	<0.5	18	14
DEC 29...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
APR 21...	220	0	25	38	19	0.6	3.0	210	<0.5	28	27
JUN 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
SEP 08...	230	6	26	41	23	0.7	2.7	170	--	27	24

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
22...	<0.10	37	282	67.8	<1	0.870	0.030	0.900	0.070	0.33
DEC 29...	--	--	--	--	12	0.500	0.100	0.600	2.40	0.80
FEB 1993										
19...	--	--	--	--	16	0.650	0.050	0.700	0.140	0.36
APR 21...	0.10	32	299	80.8	<1	0.510	0.090	0.600	0.390	0.51
JUN 03...	--	--	--	--	21	0.400	0.100	0.500	1.20	0.40
SEP 08...	0.10	34	311	41.1	5	0.630	0.070	0.700	0.570	0.43

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'36", long 67°05'08", Hydrologic Unit 21010003 at bridge on Highway 348, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) southwest of Rosario plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.3 mi² (47.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 50.0 ft (15.2 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	373	131	42	16	96	18	15	201	113	70	41	57
2	196	98	37	16	44	18	14	271	83	54	40	78
3	132	80	36	16	33	16	15	225	69	48	41	131
4	102	76	34	16	28	16	13	140	60	44	45	239
5	90	67	51	18	26	16	14	257	55	63	51	145
6	117	64	38	19	24	16	13	150	54	86	39	101
7	116	59	30	18	23	16	13	75	53	257	40	110
8	147	55	29	17	22	18	13	52	87	115	42	132
9	116	51	26	17	22	23	16	117	149	63	49	508
10	385	49	25	17	22	16	12	83	133	50	42	195
11	204	47	24	18	22	16	79	58	82	46	39	158
12	140	63	23	18	22	15	167	51	123	45	38	179
13	104	80	31	18	23	15	112	49	97	43	37	163
14	78	229	69	18	22	15	54	47	72	46	37	133
15	67	209	42	19	20	14	28	42	65	42	36	109
16	139	133	25	19	104	14	19	43	69	39	82	94
17	325	89	22	19	73	14	16	45	59	38	46	128
18	199	140	20	21	31	14	25	44	58	37	37	168
19	135	119	19	20	25	13	18	43	82	37	34	176
20	104	120	18	20	22	13	12	50	84	37	32	154
21	79	95	17	20	20	13	17	46	66	36	34	132
22	93	107	17	20	19	13	15	43	62	44	140	118
23	183	95	16	19	18	14	11	116	58	45	64	112
24	208	68	20	18	18	16	52	65	52	42	31	104
25	157	56	16	18	18	15	22	52	58	43	39	95
26	113	49	17	18	17	18	13	175	71	49	39	127
27	83	46	16	17	16	30	12	270	74	47	54	223
28	67	52	16	18	17	20	32	166	176	40	110	305
29	113	76	16	162	---	15	21	113	328	40	125	188
30	157	53	19	40	---	15	19	525	142	40	117	148
31	158	---	16	46	---	17	---	182	---	40	68	---
TOTAL	4680	2656	827	756	847	502	882	3796	2734	1726	1669	4710
MEAN	151	88.5	26.7	24.4	30.2	16.2	29.4	122	91.1	55.7	53.8	157
MAX	385	229	69	162	104	30	167	525	328	257	140	508
MIN	67	46	16	16	16	13	11	42	52	36	31	57
AC-FT	9280	5270	1640	1500	1680	996	1750	7530	5420	3420	3310	9340
CFSM	8.25	4.84	1.46	1.33	1.65	.88	1.61	6.69	4.98	3.04	2.94	8.58
IN.	9.51	5.40	1.68	1.54	1.72	1.02	1.79	7.72	5.56	3.51	3.39	9.57

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1986 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	111	76.0	30.1	21.0	17.1	21.5	24.2	50.7	50.2	45.3	60.2	102				
MAX	206	117	43.2	31.8	30.2	77.0	57.7	122	91.1	75.2	102	157				
(WY)	1986	1990	1990	1990	1993	1989	1989	1993	1993	1989	1989	1993				
MIN	33.2	16.1	9.92	15.9	8.55	10.1	11.9	15.8	12.0	23.2	25.1	32.7				
(WY)	1992	1992	1992	1991	1992	1992	1991	1990	1992	1990	1991	1986				

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1986 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	17618.8	25785	
ANNUAL MEAN	48.1	70.6	50.9
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			70.6
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			30.8
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	502	Sep 30	1550
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	3.9	May 9	3.9
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	4.2	May 6	4.2
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			7480
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			12.06
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			10
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	34950	51140	36870
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	2.63	3.86	2.78
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	35.82	52.42	37.79
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	134	157	122
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	17	45	27
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	6.9	16	11

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1985 to September 1993.

INSTRUMENTATION.--US D-49 SEDIMENT SAMPLER SINCE OCTOBER 1985. AUTOMATIC SEDIMENT SAMPLER SINCE 1986

REMARKS.--Sediment samples were collected by a local observer once daily during low flow and more than once daily during high flow events for concentration and particle size analyses. Sediment samples are collected periodically by survey staff. Automatic sediment sampler set to collect samples above 200 cfs.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean, 8,150 mg/L October 7, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L January 28, 1990.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily, 74,700 tons (67,800 tonnes) October 7, 1985; Minimum daily, 0.05 ton (0.04 Tonne) several days.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean, 1,910 mg/L June 29, 1993; Minimum daily mean, 2.0 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily, 7,830 tons (7,100 tonnes) May 30, 1993; Minimum daily 0.08 ton (0.07 tonne) several days.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (PER-CENT SATUR-LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1992											
23...	1425	66	230	7.2	27.0	17	8.0	100	40	3100	610
DEC 29...	1115	15	276	8.2	21.8	3.1	9.0	102	<10	730	550
FEB 1993											
18...	1325	2.89	258	8.0	23.4	4.0	10.6	122	<10	320	250
APR 21...	1250	11	300	7.9	26.5	3.5	5.3	65	<10	420	310
JUN 04...	1345	56	282	8.0	28.2	2.8	7.6	97	<10	3000	5900
SEP 08...	1300	74	232	7.2	24.7	5.2	7.8	92	<10	2700	680

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARE WH WAT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
23...	110	7	19	15	5.6	0.2	1.2	98	<0.5	6.9	5.9
DEC 29...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
APR 21...	120	5	24	14	7.8	0.3	1.7	130	<0.5	7.0	8.9
JUN 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
SEP 08...	120	4	20	16	7.0	0.3	1.7	85	--	6.5	5.8

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	373	1280	2160	131	92	41	42	14	1.6
2	196	347	208	98	23	6.1	37	12	1.2
3	132	31	11	80	17	3.7	36	21	2.0
4	102	21	5.7	76	101	26	34	22	2.1
5	90	45	14	67	21	3.9	51	48	17
6	117	196	153	64	11	1.9	38	29	3.2
7	116	199	134	59	10	1.6	30	15	1.3
8	147	240	117	55	10	1.5	29	9	.68
9	116	133	47	51	11	1.4	26	14	.99
10	385	1670	6060	49	11	1.4	25	37	2.5
11	204	229	161	47	10	1.2	24	22	1.4
12	140	183	74	63	68	22	23	8	.49
13	104	81	25	80	138	65	31	26	11
14	78	28	6.1	229	860	1920	69	99	26
15	67	34	6.4	209	619	603	42	23	3.1
16	140	1530	1960	133	188	80	25	14	1.0
17	326	1320	2560	89	79	19	22	12	.68
18	199	411	250	140	447	386	20	16	.82
19	135	130	54	119	180	76	19	13	.63
20	104	31	8.6	120	138	68	18	8	.39
21	79	26	5.5	95	48	13	17	11	.51
22	93	94	43	107	105	47	17	10	.43
23	183	491	489	95	44	13	16	15	.60
24	208	502	348	68	14	2.6	20	67	4.3
25	157	217	118	56	12	1.8	16	58	2.7
26	113	25	7.6	49	11	1.4	17	83	4.3
27	83	19	4.2	46	16	1.9	16	43	1.9
28	67	16	3.0	52	31	4.7	16	11	.46
29	113	201	139	76	86	34	16	9	.42
30	157	401	469	53	36	5.9	19	11	.56
31	158	285	156	---	---	---	16	12	.50
TOTAL	4682	---	15797.1	2656	---	3454.0	827	---	94.76

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	16	13	.52	96	205	148	18	3	.17
2	16	12	.46	44	16	1.9	18	2	.12
3	16	10	.42	33	12	1.1	16	2	.08
4	16	11	.46	28	10	.75	16	2	.08
5	18	12	.55	26	10	.68	16	2	.08
6	19	11	.55	24	10	.60	16	2	.08
7	18	10	.45	23	8	.53	16	3	.13
8	17	8	.37	22	8	.49	18	7	.39
9	17	6	.30	22	7	.46	23	9	.69
10	17	5	.26	22	7	.43	16	4	.18
11	18	7	.34	22	7	.42	16	4	.19
12	18	16	.78	22	7	.43	15	5	.20
13	18	28	1.3	23	6	.38	15	5	.20
14	18	28	1.4	22	4	.27	15	5	.21
15	19	18	.92	20	4	.24	14	6	.22
16	19	10	.51	104	303	282	14	5	.20
17	19	8	.46	73	73	23	14	5	.18
18	21	11	.62	31	16	1.4	14	5	.18
19	20	10	.56	25	9	.62	13	4	.16
20	20	7	.39	22	6	.36	13	3	.11
21	20	7	.40	20	5	.27	13	4	.15
22	20	9	.49	19	5	.25	13	7	.29
23	19	10	.50	18	5	.24	14	7	.28
24	18	10	.46	18	5	.25	16	5	.20
25	18	7	.37	18	4	.23	15	5	.20
26	18	5	.27	17	4	.19	18	7	.57
27	17	6	.30	16	4	.18	30	17	2.3
28	18	10	.47	17	4	.18	20	7	.37
29	162	477	532	---	---	---	15	7	.29
30	40	23	3.0	---	---	---	15	7	.28
31	46	72	60	---	---	---	17	6	.24
TOTAL	756	---	609.88	847	---	465.85	502	---	9.02

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT	MEAN	MEAN	SEDIMENT
	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	DISCHARGE (CFS)	CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	15	5	.19	201	371	787	113	109	37
2	14	5	.18	271	617	1170	83	31	7.7
3	15	5	.18	225	654	838	69	11	2.0
4	13	5	.18	140	211	96	60	8	1.3
5	14	5	.18	257	1310	2840	55	5	.82
6	13	6	.21	150	240	115	54	5	.72
7	13	6	.22	75	67	16	53	5	.72
8	13	5	.17	52	33	4.8	87	127	68
9	16	4	.18	117	290	252	149	450	402
10	12	4	.13	83	61	15	133	171	68
11	79	184	164	58	19	3.1	82	76	19
12	167	609	1120	51	14	1.9	123	302	315
13	112	241	212	49	7	.99	97	100	29
14	54	57	9.5	47	5	.63	72	36	7.1
15	28	41	3.3	42	5	.57	65	10	1.8
16	19	28	1.5	43	5	.57	69	5	.96
17	16	13	.57	45	4	.54	59	4	.71
18	25	19	3.1	44	4	.53	58	10	1.7
19	18	23	1.2	43	5	.57	82	54	14
20	12	16	.53	50	5	.69	84	62	16
21	17	11	.95	46	6	.80	66	25	4.8
22	15	10	.41	43	9	1.0	62	10	1.7
23	11	11	.32	116	250	198	58	4	.67
24	52	87	40	65	50	9.8	52	4	.62
25	22	102	6.9	52	32	4.6	58	5	.89
26	13	68	2.5	175	639	1360	71	6	1.2
27	12	60	2.0	270	634	1210	74	6	1.1
28	32	89	8.0	166	277	136	176	543	729
29	21	41	2.6	113	123	40	328	1910	3710
30	19	13	.65	525	1210	7830	142	218	103
31	---	---	---	182	264	149	---	---	---
TOTAL	882	---	1581.85	3796	---	17083.09	2734	---	5546.51

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DAY	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	70	48	10	41	3	.32	57	65	10
2	54	15	2.3	40	2	.26	78	116	45
3	48	10	1.3	41	2	.22	131	568	1040
4	44	10	1.2	45	3	.42	239	963	2350
5	63	50	13	51	19	4.4	145	218	98
6	86	122	64	39	12	1.4	101	111	38
7	257	1000	3040	40	8	.90	110	128	46
8	115	153	62	42	22	2.3	132	238	144
9	63	37	6.8	49	42	7.3	508	1490	7640
10	50	15	2.1	42	14	1.8	195	355	212
11	46	10	1.2	39	4	.43	158	224	120
12	45	10	1.1	38	4	.42	179	436	398
13	43	8	.99	37	4	.39	163	151	75
14	46	8	1.0	37	4	.39	133	68	30
15	42	7	.91	36	10	.95	109	52	17
16	39	6	.67	82	57	16	94	16	4.1
17	38	5	.55	46	8	1.1	128	395	355
18	37	4	.45	37	4	.45	168	326	270
19	37	4	.41	34	6	.54	176	339	191
20	37	4	.40	32	7	.62	154	373	284
21	36	4	.45	34	7	.64	132	126	47
22	44	6	.78	140	489	795	118	67	25
23	45	9	1.1	64	57	17	112	126	45
24	42	9	1.0	31	13	1.1	104	38	11
25	43	7	.91	39	33	6.2	95	10	2.6
26	49	6	.86	39	35	4.5	127	206	163
27	47	5	.64	54	44	7.1	223	633	607
28	40	4	.43	110	610	731	305	873	1330
29	40	3	.37	125	194	98	188	48	26
30	40	3	.32	117	236	93	148	16	6.3
31	40	3	.33	68	110	21	---	---	---
TOTAL	1726	---	3217.57	1669	---	1815.15	4710	---	15630.0
YEAR	25787		65304.78						

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	DIS- CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE D (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .002 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .004 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .008 MM
OCT 1992							
10...	1608	2960	23600	188000	15	19	23
NOV							
15...	1829	432	2460	2870	42	55	59
APR 1993							
12...	1304	967	4110	10700	58	--	88
MAY							
30...	1625	4290	13800	160000	32	36	41
JUN							
28...	1635	647	6460	11300	17	20	23
AUG							
28...	1832	570	10300	15800	29	32	38
SEP							
09...	1800	1050	955	27000	31	37	48

DATE	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .016 MM	SED. SUSP. FALL DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .031 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .125 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .250 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .500 MM	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN 1.00 MM
OCT 1992							
10...	28	33	41	58	84	96	98
NOV							
15...	71	80	91	96	99	99.7	100
APR 1993							
12...	98	98.9	--	--	99	99.7	100
MAY							
30...	50	59	70	83	94	99	100
JUN							
06...	28	34	45	61	77	89	97
AUG							
28...	47	59	74	82	87	94	99
SEP							
03...	55	67	77	93	98	98.9	99

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS , PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

SILT AND CLAY PERCENT OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1992					
01...	1750	471	11600	14750	41
NOV					
10...	1538	1390	10600	39780	57
10...	1545	1750	13800	65200	65
10...	1735	1170	5350	16900	81
10...	1905	655	3100	5480	88
10...	2105	442	1700	2030	91
16...	1821	350	16600	15690	25
17...	1654	945	11400	29090	38
17...	1749	855	2150	4960	89
18...	1958	283	1790	1370	96
MAR 1993					
27...	1802	87	1220	4220	97
APR					
12...	1305	967	7290	19030	69
MAY					
01...	1655	1270	6250	22360	68
02...	1525	1210	4450	14540	69
02...	1630	671	2370	4290	89
02...	1745	515	2180	3030	87
05...	1615	646	10200	17790	42
05...	2000	470	1970	2500	85
09...	1615	470	1590	2020	84
23...	0640	190	2100	1080	98
27...	1635	850	2430	5580	86
30...	1540	1990	7400	39760	70
30...	2010	573	1630	2570	88
JUN					
09...	1830	364	1560	1530	92
JUL					
07...	1820	609	3300	5430	89
AUG					
22...	1955	688	4870	9050	51
SEP					
04...	1438	453	4880	6230	83
12...	1815	599	1930	3120	62
27...	1857	470	2210	2800	90
28...	1740	380	1550	1590	86

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50138000 RIO GUANAJIBO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°08'36", long 67°08'57", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at bridge on Highway 100, 1.4 mi (2.3 km) west of Hormigueros, and 2.0 mi (3.2 km) downstream from Río Rosario.

DRAINAGE AREA.--120 mi² (311 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Annual low-flow measurements 1959, monthly measurements April 1959 to November 1967, January 1973 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is at mean sea level. Previous to Nov. 7, 1980, at site 0.3 mi (0.5 km) upstream at datum 7.36 ft (2.243 m) higher.

REMARKS.--Records fair. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. Daily discharges affected by sewage treatment plant about 2.1 mi (3.4 km) upstream from gage.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	956	489	351	92	340	48	36	209	286	143	53	152
2	450	392	328	86	251	50	32	462	200	110	51	152
3	297	396	251	85	187	43	30	406	153	97	51	189
4	248	533	214	82	134	40	31	328	123	87	68	309
5	256	412	184	81	109	39	31	325	107	84	79	244
6	496	290	185	85	89	39	28	377	97	109	94	210
7	500	251	160	95	82	38	28	164	94	255	69	203
8	1140	226	147	118	75	39	26	121	139	306	152	313
9	855	217	139	93	70	46	32	228	325	129	122	843
10	1080	210	133	82	68	37	28	192	306	103	80	1020
11	3360	226	121	78	65	34	59	121	153	92	60	375
12	1850	337	112	76	62	33	160	105	199	88	58	349
13	975	324	132	73	60	33	136	91	179	119	52	348
14	611	509	318	72	56	30	122	83	113	114	65	235
15	569	653	211	74	55	33	184	78	104	86	78	205
16	519	695	135	69	117	48	254	73	124	75	311	184
17	994	515	120	67	226	50	85	68	94	69	200	205
18	1290	564	111	65	92	35	57	64	92	67	133	367
19	642	576	106	64	73	31	62	61	244	65	115	589
20	501	728	100	63	63	30	45	75	212	60	104	330
21	423	625	98	63	59	27	45	68	126	58	96	254
22	412	499	95	63	54	27	51	62	100	57	450	211
23	535	436	93	67	51	26	38	179	90	62	873	459
24	1210	341	94	60	49	30	75	259	82	58	236	532
25	879	286	101	58	56	31	78	166	76	58	190	245
26	568	243	194	56	51	29	47	192	72	65	168	454
27	450	285	169	55	49	122	40	402	69	67	211	764
28	380	324	107	51	47	103	82	451	164	56	246	1230
29	460	321	107	681	---	49	90	266	446	54	274	724
30	455	420	108	369	---	55	76	657	441	53	285	375
31	529	---	100	279	---	46	---	1060	---	53	176	---
TOTAL	23890	12323	4824	3402	2690	1321	2088	7393	5010	2899	5200	12070
MEAN	771	411	156	110	96.1	42.6	69.6	238	167	93.5	168	402
MAX	3360	728	351	681	340	122	254	1060	446	306	873	1230
MIN	248	210	93	51	47	26	26	61	69	53	51	152
AC-FT	47390	24440	9570	6750	5340	2620	4140	14660	9940	5750	10310	23940
CFSM	6.42	3.42	1.30	.91	.80	.36	.58	1.99	1.39	.78	1.40	3.35
IN.	7.41	3.82	1.50	1.05	.83	.41	.65	2.29	1.55	.90	1.61	3.74

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1973 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	503	440	132	59.3	47.2	44.9	71.0	185	114	106	230	502
MEAN	503	440	132	59.3	47.2	44.9	71.0	185	114	106	230	502
MAX	1254	1518	422	110	96.1	244	316	636	504	240	757	2075
(WY)	1986	1978	1976	1993	1993	1989	1989	1980	1979	1984	1988	1975
MIN	97.5	42.7	15.4	13.8	13.9	10.6	16.1	12.7	9.23	26.4	42.3	95.4
(WY)	1992	1992	1992	1973	1977	1977	1977	1977	1977	1976	1976	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1973 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	74264.4	83110	
ANNUAL MEAN	203	228	206
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			402
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			104
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	3360	Oct 11	35000
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	6.2	May 11	5.0
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	7.6	May 7	5.5
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		5310	Oct 11
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		21.84	Oct 11
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			28.50
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	147300	164800	148900
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.69	1.90	1.71
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	23.02	25.76	23.27
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	534	517	456
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	69	115	78
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	15	46	21

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50138000 RIO GUANAJIBO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
23...	1230	485	345	7.0	27.0	44	4.9	61	<10	K41000	5100
DEC 11...	1045	128	480	8.0	23.8	10	6.8	74	<10	500	210
FEB 1993											
18...	1120	102	381	7.9	23.5	14	8.6	99	<10	2400	570
APR 20...	1340	48	450	7.5	28.0	1.0	4.1	52	13	530	480
JUN 03...	1320	170	414	7.6	29.0	13	5.3	68	<10	4400	660
AUG 19...	1145	119	400	7.3	28.5	2.0	3.4	42	38	1400	530

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
23...	160	22	24	25	8.4	0.3	2.2	160	<0.5	13	11
DEC 11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	220	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	170	--	--	--
APR 20...	210	30	30	32	16	0.5	2.4	200	<0.5	18	18
JUN 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--
AUG 19...	220	8	40	29	140	4	9.0	130	--	76	210

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDEd (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
23...	0.10	29	209	273	4	0.530	0.020	0.550	0.050	0.55
DEC 11...	--	--	--	--	<1	0.630	0.070	0.700	0.410	0.09
FEB 1993										
18...	--	--	--	--	27	0.760	0.040	0.800	0.230	0.37
APR 20...	0.10	19	255	32.8	21	0.770	0.030	0.800	0.140	0.36
JUN 03...	--	--	--	--	39	0.860	0.040	0.900	0.320	0.58
AUG 19...	0.20	25	268	73.2	8	0.750	0.050	0.800	0.290	0.51

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50138000 RIO GUANAJIBO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1992 23...	0.60	1.2	5.1	0.280	<1	<100	20	<1	4	<10
DEC 11...	0.50	1.2	5.3	0.460	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993 18...	0.60	1.4	6.2	0.190	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 20...	0.50	1.3	5.8	0.280	<1	<100	30	<1	3	<10
JUN 03...	0.90	1.8	8.0	0.220	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 19...	0.80	1.6	7.1	0.310	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1992 23...	1100	2	120	<0.10	<1	<1	10	<0.010	<1	0.04
DEC 11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 20...	570	<1	100	<0.10	<1	<1	20	<0.010	2	0.03
JUN 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- EIDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993 25...	1100	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010

DATE	ENDRIN WATER UNFLTRD REC (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993 25...	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1993 25...	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01	0.06	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

RIO YAGÜEZ BASIN
50138800 RIO YAGÜEZ NEAR MAYAGÜEZ, PR
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'31", long 67°07'07", at steel-truss bridge on unnumbered paved road about 800 ft (244 m) south of Highway 106, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) west of Highways 106 and 352 junction, and 1.4 mi (2.3 km) east-northeast from Mayagüez plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--6.7 mi² (17.3 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH SATUR-ATION) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1992											
29...	1420	9.0	276	7.4	29.0	0.80	5.1	66	12	2000	680
DEC											
11...	1210	7.4	316	8.1	23.9	1.1	9.5	112	<10	220	580
FEB 1993											
18...	1450	11	286	7.9	23.8	1.2	10.5	124	<10	1300	810
APR											
20...	1515	5.7	295	7.6	27.5	0.60	5.0	63	<10	240	310
JUN											
04...	1000	5.0	279	8.0	25.8	2.2	7.7	94	19	350	440
AUG											
19...	0800	8.5	306	7.4	24.0	0.70	4.2	49	<10	K1300	2100

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
29...	180	12	27	16	20	0.4	1.9	130	<0.5	17	12
DEC											
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
APR											
20...	130	20	34	12	12	0.5	2.7	140	<0.5	8.3	11
JUN											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
AUG											
19...	140	3	36	11	13	0.5	2.4	100	--	7.4	9.8

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
29...	0.20	30	224	5.44	<1	0.920	0.010	0.930	0.020	0.48
DEC										
11...	--	--	--	--	5	0.540	0.060	0.600	0.650	0.15
FEB 1993										
18...	--	--	--	--	8	0.790	0.010	0.800	0.020	0.18
APR										
20...	0.10	29	193	2.97	6	0.890	0.010	0.900	0.010	0.19
JUN										
04...	--	--	--	--	17	0.730	0.070	0.800	0.160	0.44
AUG										
19...	<0.10	32	194	4.45	4	0.620	0.080	0.700	0.390	0.41

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO BASIN

50141500 LAGO GUAYO NEAR CASTANER, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'46", long 66°50'06", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Guayo Dam on Río Guayo, 1.1 mi (1.8 km) southwest of Lago Yahuecas, 2.6 mi (4.2 km) southwest of Lago Prieto, 2.1 mi (3.4 km) north of Castañer, and 6.0 mi (9.6 km) west of Adjuntas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--9.60 mi² (24.86 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1980 to January 1985, June 1989 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Guayo was completed in 1956. The dam is on Río Guayo and is the largest in the southwestern Puerto Rico project. The maximum storage is 17,400 ac-ft (21.5 km³) for power and irrigation. The dam is a concrete gravity structure with a total length of 555 ft (169 m), a maximum structural height of 190 ft (58 m), and a maximum width at the base of 145 ft (44 m). The ungated overflow spillway with a crest elevation of 60.00 ft (18.29 m) and a crest length of 220 ft (67 m) was designed to pass a maximum flood of 30,200 ft³/s (855 m³/s) at a reservoir elevation of 70.00 ft (21.34 m). Timber flashboards that were added to increase storage capacity were subsequently removed and their use discontinued. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum elevation, 1462.43 ft (445.75 m), May 27, 1980; minimum elevation recorded, 1415.43 ft (431.42 m), June 2, 1990, but may have been less during period of no gage-height record June 2-5, 1990.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum elevation, 1461.18 ft (445.37 m), May 29; minimum elevation recorded 1431.18 ft (436.22 m), Nov. 24.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Water Resources Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
1415	3,960	1460	13,550
1449	10,660	1465	15,000

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	1455.66	1454.54	1437.46	A	1459.46	1451.05	1454.05	1461.09	1459.44	1451.67	1440.34	1439.60
2	1456.18	1453.66	1438.33	A	1459.46	1450.32	1454.25	1460.92	1459.63	1450.53	1439.74	1439.87
3	1456.62	1452.67	1438.65	A	1459.73	1449.92	1454.45	1460.42	1459.31	1448.47	1440.06	1439.37
4	1457.06	1451.62	1438.14	A	1458.99	1449.46	1454.64	1459.85	1458.97	1448.05	1440.39	1440.48
5	1459.81	1450.52	1437.59	1454.55	1458.23	1449.75	1454.78	1459.75	1458.70	1447.65	1440.17	1441.12
6	1460.25	1449.35	1436.99	1455.03	1457.49	A	1454.96	1460.40	1458.64	1446.72	1440.17	1442.17
7	1460.21	1448.16	1436.38	1455.50	1456.63	1449.11	1454.97	1460.24	1458.39	1446.36	1440.51	1442.84
8	1460.70	1446.92	1435.75	1455.88	1455.34	1449.46	1455.19	1460.32	1458.42	1445.59	1439.64	1443.02
9	1460.16	1445.58	1435.06	1456.29	1455.51	1449.71	1455.46	1460.38	1458.80	A	1438.33	1443.42
10	1460.19	1444.20	1434.37	1456.71	1455.66	1449.99	1455.70	1459.96	1459.49	A	1436.83	1443.04
11	1459.97	1442.84	1433.65	1457.07	1455.00	1450.09	1456.31	1459.80	1458.87	A	1435.22	1442.69
12	1459.55	1441.56	1432.91	1457.51	1453.91	1449.47	1457.36	1459.85	1458.17	A	1433.18	1443.50
13	1459.41	1441.75	A	1457.88	1453.10	1449.72	1457.80	1459.35	1458.15	A	A	1444.10
14	1460.37	1441.11	A	1458.25	1453.43	1449.96	1461.13	1459.34	1457.17	A	A	1444.42
15	1459.62	1440.39	A	1458.60	1452.35	1449.47	1460.37	1458.70	1456.60	A	A	1444.22
16	1459.88	1439.32	A	1458.93	1451.41	1449.25	1459.90	1458.37	1455.83	A	A	1444.22
17	1459.61	1437.99	A	1459.32	1451.81	1449.48	1460.01	1457.63	1455.69	1441.55	A	1444.09
18	1459.44	1436.96	A	1459.64	1452.14	1449.72	1458.57	1456.77	1456.24	1441.83	A	1444.25
19	1459.15	1435.84	A	1459.93	1452.24	1449.95	1458.48	1456.05	1458.58	1440.41	A	1446.33
20	1458.74	1434.63	A	1460.14	1452.04	1450.20	1458.38	1455.60	1459.47	1438.50	A	1447.16
21	1458.12	1433.40	A	1460.18	1452.01	1450.42	1457.63	1455.91	1458.92	1437.97	A	1447.67
22	1457.49	1432.46	A	A	1452.21	1450.64	1456.83	1454.64	1458.25	1437.63	A	1447.87
23	1457.82	1431.29	A	A	1452.24	1450.83	1456.30	1453.42	1458.13	1438.10	A	1446.77
24	1458.87	A	A	A	1452.17	1451.07	1456.30	1453.39	1458.00	1438.61	1432.72	1447.40
25	1459.11	A	A	A	1451.71	1451.30	1456.62	1453.71	1457.70	1439.04	1433.14	1446.60
26	1458.59	A	A	A	A	1451.55	1456.87	1456.87	1456.84	1439.47	1433.56	1447.21
27	1457.88	A	A	A	1451.27	1452.63	1456.26	1460.15	1456.02	1439.91	1434.63	1450.04
28	1456.98	A	A	A	1451.29	1453.17	1456.12	1460.66	1455.34	1439.86	1436.61	1451.51
29	1456.27	A	A	1460.46	---	1453.45	1457.87	1460.83	1453.89	1440.21	1437.71	1451.84
30	1455.75	A	A	1460.06	---	1453.69	1459.99	1460.67	1452.19	1440.58	1438.38	1452.40
31	1455.24	---	A	1460.08	---	1453.88	---	1460.16	---	1439.99	1438.92	---
MEAN	1458.54	---	---	---	---	---	1456.92	1458.55	1457.66	---	---	1444.97
MAX	1460.70	---	---	---	---	---	1461.13	1461.09	1459.63	---	---	1452.40
MIN	1455.24	---	---	---	---	---	1454.05	1453.39	1452.19	---	---	1439.37

A No gage-height record

RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASIN

50143000 RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO NEAR LARES, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'26", long 66°55'00", at bridge on Highway 124, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) downstream from confluence of Río Blanco and Río Prieto, and 3.7 mi (6.0 km) southwest of Lares plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--26.3 mi² (68.1 km²) this does not include 36.2 mi² (93.8 km²) which contributes only during high floods, and 3.5 mi² (9.1 km²) which contributes only part of its storm runoff.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1959-68, 1970 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MP (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992										
30...	0850	171	234	6.9	23.0	28	4.1	48	<10	3100 6100
DEC 16...	0920	41	292	7.6	21.0	12	4.8	54	19	K770 460
FEB 1993										
23...	0930	20	321	8.2	21.5	1.1	6.2	70	51	260 73
APR 27...	1050	36	213	7.8	24.5	3.2	8.8	107	29	270 K130
JUN 15...	0850	54	303	7.8	25.5	0.50	8.6	102	16	310 820
SEP 09...	1400	45	285	7.3	27.7	15	8.2	78	<10	3100 210

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
30...	82	2	18	6.0	9.1	0.5	2.5	92	<0.5	10	7.3
DEC 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
APR 27...	120	8	33	9.3	11	0.4	2.1	110	0.6	22	11
JUN 15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
SEP 09...	70	1	27	8.2	13	0.6	1.8	93	--	18	12

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
30...	<0.10	28	131	60.5	<1	1.27	0.030	1.30	0.030	0.17
DEC 16...	--	--	--	--	14	1.29	0.010	1.30	0.050	0.55
FEB 1993										
23...	--	--	--	--	2	1.13	0.070	1.20	0.030	0.27
APR 27...	0.10	30	184	17.9	<1	1.65	0.050	1.70	0.030	0.37
JUN 15...	--	--	--	--	7	1.12	0.380	1.50	0.260	0.44
SEP 09...	0.20	22	163	19.8	3	2.34	0.360	2.70	0.180	1.0

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASIN

50144000 RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO NEAR SAN SEBASTIAN, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°17'05", long 67°03'05", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, on right bank, at downstream side of bridge on Highway 108, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) downstream from Quebrada La Zumbadora, 4.4 mi (7.1 km) northwest of Las Marías, 5.4 mi (8.7 km) southwest of San Sebastián.

DRAINAGE AREA.--94.3 mi² (244.2 km²), does not include 36.2 mi² (93.8 km²) which contributes only during high floods, and 3.5 mi² (9.1 km²) which contributes only part of its storm runoff.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1963 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 103.72 ft (31.614 m) above mean sea level (Puerto Rico Department of Public Works bench mark). Previous to Oct. 30, 1975, at site 600 ft (180 m) upstream at same datum.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Transbasin diversion (except during floods) to Río Yauco basin for hydroelectric power and irrigation above Lago Guayo, Yahuecas, and Prieto, combined useable storage 17,300 acre-ft (21.3 hm³). Limited storm runoff is contributed to basin by 3.5 mi² (9.1 km²) above Río Toro Diversion dam. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	2440	942	333	160	668	105	106	351	723	254	125	862
2	1490	708	239	150	212	118	86	1480	506	216	121	710
3	864	525	332	145	179	107	96	2420	423	199	117	491
4	445	461	232	143	158	104	101	1230	378	185	113	456
5	595	432	245	140	147	105	79	775	345	177	112	609
6	1390	393	258	139	139	103	77	1540	385	180	125	372
7	1120	368	201	137	135	102	76	1160	319	381	125	522
8	1630	346	191	133	128	100	73	558	386	390	114	730
9	1490	328	186	131	126	121	92	716	585	212	305	616
10	4570	313	181	128	125	108	71	571	446	186	199	982
11	3880	300	177	127	120	101	179	298	334	170	e200	417
12	1840	292	174	125	121	107	686	247	523	169	e120	313
13	828	328	211	124	124	94	516	229	548	159	e115	323
14	908	883	356	122	120	88	510	213	279	170	e110	272
15	2010	721	377	127	121	92	1210	209	239	195	e105	251
16	1240	550	209	123	118	88	347	340	245	184	e350	261
17	2100	370	188	122	167	87	213	236	226	149	e1050	273
18	3180	582	178	120	129	84	364	193	222	144	e600	1320
19	1710	596	178	118	121	80	238	179	319	142	e320	1580
20	907	399	170	118	118	87	250	190	323	185	e190	714
21	647	393	165	139	120	105	308	177	234	219	e170	492
22	643	348	166	163	113	80	241	208	212	436	e155	523
23	1060	454	161	163	112	75	143	275	201	177	e150	459
24	1510	313	157	161	115	75	468	256	193	144	140	365
25	1210	287	155	162	151	86	318	190	186	148	153	298
26	744	270	151	164	115	83	162	1120	179	333	185	325
27	573	269	168	166	111	291	134	2040	176	225	130	527
28	491	271	152	165	111	385	148	2040	478	148	361	893
29	622	390	379	1160	---	121	464	1530	1050	136	528	570
30	2090	427	344	422	---	119	336	3840	559	129	853	386
31	1260	---	177	361	---	202	---	1850	---	125	466	---
TOTAL	45487	13259	6791	5858	4224	3603	8092	26661	11222	6267	7907	16912
MEAN	1467	442	219	189	151	116	270	860	374	202	255	564
MAX	4570	942	379	1160	668	385	1210	3840	1050	436	1050	1580
MIN	445	269	151	118	111	75	71	177	176	125	105	251
AC-FT	90220	26300	13470	11620	8380	7150	16050	52880	22260	12430	15680	33540
CFSM	15.6	4.69	2.32	2.00	1.60	1.23	2.86	9.12	3.97	2.14	2.70	5.98
IN.	17.94	5.23	2.68	2.31	1.67	1.42	3.19	10.52	4.43	2.47	3.12	6.67

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1963 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1963	1964	1965	1966	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993				
MEAN	674	449	223	140	106	98.7	148	373	287	279	363	609																							
MAX	1467	746	482	215	161	271	313	1084	815	657	936	1422																							
(WY)	1993	1982	1966	1970	1981	1972	1971	1986	1979	1979	1979	1984																							
MIN	344	199	103	83.6	62.3	54.4	49.3	63.7	71.2	111	152	206																							
(WY)	1983	1992	1992	1965	1992	1965	1968	1967	1977	1990	1967	1983																							

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR				FOR 1993 WATER YEAR				WATER YEARS 1963 - 1993			
ANNUAL TOTAL	136452				156283							
ANNUAL MEAN	373				428				312			
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN									460			
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN									189			
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	4570				4570				19400			
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	41				71				32			
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	45				81				35			
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW					21300				140000			
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE					13.54				33.90			
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW					68				31			
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	270700				310000				226200			
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	3.95				4.54				3.31			
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	53.83				61.65				44.99			
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	867				1010				660			
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	170				222				188			
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	58				111				74			

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASIN

50144000 RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO NEAR SAN SEBASTIAN, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1963 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

WATER-QUALITY DATA

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, (PER-0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3)	
OCT 1992	29...	0950	456	230	6.7	27.0	7.8	7.4	83	310	670	100
FEB 1993	02...	0955	214	226	7.9	22.5	27	6.7	58	2800	2300	93
APR	29...	0950	137	245	7.0	24.5	15	8.0	92	1000	340	100
JUL	22...	1035	132	228	7.4	28.0	4.7	4.2	41	2500	170	100

DATE	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CACO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CACO3)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	
OCT 1992	29...	6	26	8.6	9.0	0.4	1.8	100	8.7	7.4	<0.10	30
FEB 1993	02...	3	24	8.1	8.0	0.4	2.1	97	8.8	7.4	0.10	25
APR	29...	7	27	8.7	9.8	0.4	2.1	100	12	9.2	<0.10	28
JUL	22...	12	26	8.7	9.8	0.4	2.0	100	10	7.5	0.10	28

DATE	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 180 DEG. C DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NH4)	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	PHOS-PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHORUS DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHORUS ORTHO, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHATE, ORTHO, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS PO4)	
OCT 1992	29...	140	155	191	1.10	0.010	0.01	<0.20	0.040	0.030	0.030	0.09
FEB 1993	02...	135	145	84	1.30	0.040	0.05	0.20	0.070	0.060	0.040	0.12
APR	29...	164	161	60	0.750	0.040	0.05	0.20	0.030	0.060	0.020	0.06
JUL	22...	151	153	55	0.670	0.090	0.12	0.70	0.030	0.030	0.020	0.06

DATE	ALUM-INUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS AL)	ARSENIC DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS BA)	BERYL-LIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS BE)	CADMIUM DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO-MIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS CR)	COBALT, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS CO)	COPPER, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS CU)	IRON, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS PB)	LITHIUM DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS LI)	
OCT 1992	29...	40	<1	31	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	1	17	<1	<4
FEB 1993	02...	50	<1	32	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	8	43	<1	<4
APR	29...	60	<1	33	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	3	22	5	<4
JUL	22...	60	<1	31	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	2	33	2	<4

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASIN
 50144000 RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO NEAR SAN SEBASTIAN, PR--CONTINUED
 (NATIONAL STREAM-QUALITY ACCOUNTING NETWORK STATION)
 WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	MANGANESE, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS HG)	MOLYB- DENUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS MO)	NICKEL, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS NI)	SELE- NIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS AG)	STRON- TIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS SR)	VANA- DIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS V)	ZINC, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS ZN)
OCT 1992 29...	16	<0.1	<10	<1	<1	<1.0	140	<6	9
FEB 1993 02...	15	<0.1	<10	1	<1	<1.0	120	<6	3
APR 29...	15	<0.1	<10	1	<1	<1.0	140	<6	<3
JUL 22...	13	<0.1	<10	<1	<1	<1.0	130	<6	6

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDEED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDEED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1992 29...	0950	456	22.6	27.8	88
FEB 1993 02...	0955	214	57.8	33.3	86
APR 29...	0950	137	43.1	15.9	95
JUL 22...	1035	132	37.4	13.3	94

RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASIN

50146000 RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO NEAR AÑASCO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°16'00", long 67°08'05", at bridge on Highway 430, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) south of Highway 109 at El Espino and 1.4 mi (2.3 km) east-southeast from Añasco plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--139 mi² (360 km²) this does not include 39.7 mi² (102.8 km²), flow is diverted to south coast.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1992											
28...	0845	E1000	225	7.1	25.0	42	5.0	59	<10	2800	K1500
DEC 17...	0830	E350	249	7.2	22.0	11	4.0	45	12	590	290
FEB 1993											
24...	0915	130	255	7.2	24.0	9.0	5.2	60	<10	82	230
APR 28...	1050	194	248	7.7	25.5	14	7.7	92	11	K1400	430
JUN 16...	0840	300	235	7.1	26.0	22	8.5	103	10	K1200	K200000
SEP 09...	0915	E350	151	6.9	23.1	38	8.7	99	24	220	260

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992										
28...	250	72	7.2	15	0.5	1.1	85	<0.5	9.4	26
DEC 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
FEB 1993										
24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
APR 28...	150	54	3.6	5.9	0.2	1.8	98	<0.5	8.7	9.1
JUN 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	80	--	--	--
SEP 09...	210	74	6.6	11	0.3	2.2	59	--	6.3	18

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
28...	<0.10	6.6	253	--	<1	0.720	0.010	0.730	0.020	0.18
DEC 17...	--	--	--	--	6	1.49	0.010	1.50	0.220	0.68
FEB 1993										
24...	--	--	--	--	<1	2.29	0.010	2.30	0.010	0.19
APR 28...	0.10	4.2	171	90	7	2.49	0.010	2.50	0.030	0.27
JUN 16...	--	--	--	--	20	1.79	0.010	1.80	0.010	0.19
SEP 09...	0.30	6.7	227	--	5	0.09	0.010	0.10	0.020	1.8

K = non-ideal count

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Figure 27.--Río Culebrinas basin.

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50147600 RIO CULEBRINAS NEAR SAN SEBASTIAN, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'51", long 67°02'40", at bridge on Highway 423, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) south of Quebrada El Salto Bridge on Highway 111, and 2.1 mi (3.4 km) west of Central La Plata.

DRAINAGE AREA.--58.2 mi² (150.7 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI (FECAL, COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
27...	0920	174	290	7.5	25.0	120	6.8	81	<10	K15000	3100
DEC											
16...	1120	74	278	7.4	23.5	18	7.6	90	11	K17000	2100
FEB 1993											
23...	1130	37	289	8.5	21.5	2.7	9.5	105	31	K140	K160
APR											
27...	1320	122	374	7.6	24.5	12	7.8	92	33	2300	220
JUN											
15...	1045	97	265	7.4	26.0	21	8.0	98	<10	5100	K1800
SEP											
09...	1020	231	299	7.4	23.3	240	7.8	81	13	39000	K110000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1992											
27...	120	8	42	3.8	6.6	0.3	2.0	130	<0.5	14	8.0
DEC											
16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
APR											
27...	180	0	63	6.3	12	0.4	2.2	190	0.6	18	9.8
JUN											
15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--
SEP											
09...	130	3	44	4.3	8.2	0.3	3.7	110	--	13	7.9

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
27...	<0.10	14	210	98.7	29	1.18	0.020	1.20	0.040	0.16
DEC										
16...	--	--	--	--	<1	1.32	0.080	1.40	0.080	0.42
FEB 1993										
23...	--	--	--	--	6	0.950	0.050	1.00	0.480	0.82
APR										
27...	0.10	20	232	76.4	13	1.04	0.060	1.10	0.150	0.65
JUN										
15...	--	--	--	--	33	1.02	0.080	1.10	0.120	0.38
SEP										
09...	0.20	16	176	110	92	1.12	0.080	1.20	0.110	0.39

K = non-ideal count

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50147800 RIO CULEBRINAS AT HIGHWAY 404 NEAR MOCA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'42", long 67°05'33", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, on right bank, at bridge on Highway 404, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) downstream from Quebrada Yagruma, and 2.8 mi (4.5 km) southeast of Moca.

DRAINAGE AREA.--71.2 mi² (184.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1967 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 45 ft (14 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e1450	e500	e180	e100	e200	56	111	e260	211	89	62	147
2	e880	e400	e140	e91	e170	59	115	e280	167	81	60	105
3	e520	e300	e190	e86	e120	58	123	e1200	170	79	56	89
4	e270	e260	e130	e83	e96	57	77	e1900	372	75	53	83
5	e360	e240	e140	e82	e86	55	66	e940	221	e73	53	265
6	e840	e230	e150	e84	e80	54	85	e600	152	69	78	126
7	e680	e200	e120	e81	e76	50	118	e1200	145	68	66	1390
8	e980	e190	e110	e82	e73	46	65	e900	129	68	107	640
9	e900	e180	e100	e78	e69	46	74	e450	201	67	91	252
10	e2570	e170	e98	e77	e70	48	56	e580	165	62	78	2000
11	e2300	e160	e96	e76	e70	59	723	e450	140	61	96	262
12	e1100	e160	e95	e75	e67	64	295	e230	150	65	70	181
13	e500	e190	e150	e72	e74	78	134	e200	e275	62	57	156
14	e550	e500	e210	e72	e90	49	611	e180	180	70	54	147
15	e1200	e400	e220	e71	e74	44	300	e170	139	282	52	125
16	e720	e290	e120	e68	e69	43	459	e160	128	133	160	443
17	e1400	e210	e110	e68	66	46	362	e270	107	74	499	485
18	e1800	e340	e108	e100	63	45	2310	e150	e350	67	261	264
19	e720	e340	e104	e71	63	42	463	188	e300	76	122	1640
20	e400	e230	e107	e68	63	41	323	191	e170	72	90	270
21	e330	e230	e102	e69	66	49	1370	382	149	64	79	172
22	e310	e200	e100	e65	61	47	372	2070	128	122	73	161
23	e660	e260	e100	e66	60	43	212	1550	118	117	67	156
24	e880	e180	e97	e65	65	40	223	296	118	88	156	146
25	e540	e160	e95	e64	68	76	e160	e257	151	83	1510	200
26	e400	e150	e90	e63	64	114	e260	180	108	405	206	149
27	e320	e150	e86	e63	61	107	e130	164	100	159	103	130
28	e280	e150	e98	e63	60	56	e110	625	96	87	259	1050
29	e360	e230	e88	e260	---	55	e120	241	397	75	186	616
30	e1200	e250	e220	e120	---	88	e360	1020	143	69	303	1580
31	e660	---	e200	e350	---	119	---	323	---	64	203	---
TOTAL	26080	7450	3954	2833	2244	1834	10187	17607	5380	3026	5310	13430
MEAN	841	248	128	91.4	80.1	59.2	340	568	179	97.6	171	448
MAX	2570	500	220	350	200	119	2310	2070	397	405	1510	2000
MIN	270	150	86	63	60	40	56	150	96	61	52	83
AC-FT	51730	14780	7840	5620	4450	3640	20210	34920	10670	6000	10530	26640
CFSM	11.8	3.49	1.79	1.28	1.13	.83	4.77	7.98	2.52	1.37	2.41	6.29
IN.	13.63	3.89	2.07	1.48	1.17	.96	5.32	9.20	2.81	1.58	2.77	7.02

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1967 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1967	1968	1969	1970	1971	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	633	350	145	77.7	70.2	65.6	143	475	381	312	337	517															
MAX	1086	799	424	151	243	319	621	2054	769	847	831	1350															
(WY)	1973	1982	1982	1971	1981	1981	1986	1986	1984	1979	1979	1978															
MIN	231	108	72.1	51.2	37.0	30.4	26.4	96.7	82.7	91.8	119	145															
(WY)	1968	1979	1992	1979	1992	1979	1970	1973	1974	1983	1970	1986															

SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR FOR 1993 WATER YEAR WATER YEARS 1967 - 1993

	1992 CALENDAR YEAR	1993 WATER YEAR	1967 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	109356	99335	
ANNUAL MEAN	299	272	294
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			457
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			179
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	3090	2570	13300
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	25	40	19
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	28	44	20
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		15000	69000
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			36.60
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			16
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	216900	197000	213300
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	4.20	3.82	4.13
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	57.14	51.90	56.17
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	682	631	601
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	170	130	138
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	36	61	42

e Estimated

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50149100 RIO CULEBRINAS NEAR AGUADA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'03", long 67°09'40", at bridge on Highway 2, and 2.3 mi (3.7 km) northeast of Aguada plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--97.0 mi² (251.2 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958, 1970 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.45 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1992											
28...	1150	851	270	7.4	26.0	207	3.0	36	34	45000	37000
DEC											
17...	1035	169	328	7.2	23.5	21	3.5	40	<10	2700	K1800
FEB 1993											
24...	1025	50	350	7.6	25.0	5.3	3.4	40	25	K60000	K60000
APR											
28...	0900	457	354	7.2	24.0	110	6.0	70	50	36000	K60000
JUN											
16...	1025	269	426	7.8	25.5	90	7.1	85	18	7200	5300
SEP											
09...	0755	600	245	6.9	24.1	690	5.3	72	27	K280000	22000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CACO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CACO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1992											
28...	130	2	47	5.5	7.2	0.2	3.9	150	<0.5	15	8.9
DEC											
17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
FEB 1993											
24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
APR											
28...	160	16	55	5.3	9.4	0.3	3.7	140	<0.5	16	12
JUN											
16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
SEP											
09...	100	0	33	5.4	6.7	0.3	3.6	94	--	16	7.8

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDEED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1992										
28...	<0.10	15	193	443	254	0.670	0.040	0.710	0.030	0.97
DEC										
17...	--	--	--	--	320	0.870	0.030	0.900	0.100	0.40
FEB 1993										
24...	--	--	--	--	13	0.570	0.030	0.600	0.130	0.27
APR										
28...	0.10	18	211	260	225	0.750	0.050	0.800	0.170	0.73
JUN										
16...	--	--	--	--	490	0.670	0.030	0.700	0.100	0.80
SEP										
09...	<0.10	13	151	245	388	0.870	0.030	0.900	0.110	0.19

K = non-ideal count

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50149100 RIO CULEBRINAS NEAR AGUADA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1992										
28...	1.0	1.7	7.6	0.240	1	<100	30	<1	<1	20
DEC										
17...	0.50	1.4	6.2	0.090	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993										
24...	0.40	1.1	4.3	0.140	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR										
28...	0.90	1.7	7.1	0.100	1	<100	30	<1	6	<10
JUN										
16...	0.90	1.6	7.5	0.060	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP										
09...	0.30	1.2	5.3	0.220	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1992										
28...	7400	2	370	<0.10	<1	<1	30	<0.010	1	0.04
DEC										
17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1993										
24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR										
28...	5200	3	380	<0.10	<1	<1	20	<0.010	2	0.01
JUN										
16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
SEP										
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1993									
07...	0945	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010

DATE	ENDRIN WATER UNFLTRD REC (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1993									
07...	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUL 1993									
07...	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01	0.12	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

CULEBRA, PR

421

50214500 QUEBRADA RESACA NEAR MONTE RESACA, CULEBRA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'11", long 65°18'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010006, on right bank, 1.0 mi (1.6 km), north of Culebra City Hall, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) southwest of Monte Resaca, and 1.0 mi (1.6 km) east of Bahia Tamarindo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.23 mi² (0.60 km²).

WATER-STAGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1991 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 66 ft (20 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. All gage-heights of 5.30 ft or lower are considered zero flow.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum gage-height 7.49 ft (2.283 m), May 26; minimum, 4.68 ft (1.426 m), Aug. 9.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum gage-height 6.96 ft (2.121 m), Dec. 30; minimum, 4.68 ft (1.426 m), Aug. 9.

GAGE HEIGHT, FEET, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	4.82	4.91	5.05	5.01	4.84	4.87	4.85	4.82	---	4.90	4.95	4.72
2	4.82	4.91	4.99	4.98	4.84	4.88	4.84	4.81	---	4.90	4.96	4.72
3	4.83	4.97	4.96	4.96	4.84	4.88	4.84	4.81	---	4.91	4.96	4.72
4	4.83	5.41	4.91	4.93	4.84	4.89	4.83	4.80	---	4.90	4.96	4.72
5	4.83	5.12	4.91	4.91	4.84	4.89	4.84	4.81	---	4.91	4.81	4.72
6	4.83	4.92	4.91	4.89	4.83	4.89	4.84	4.81	---	4.90	4.73	4.72
7	4.84	4.91	4.91	4.86	4.83	4.88	4.82	4.82	---	4.91	4.73	4.72
8	4.84	4.90	4.91	4.85	4.82	4.88	4.78	4.84	---	4.90	4.73	4.73
9	4.84	4.90	4.93	4.85	4.81	4.87	4.80	5.15	---	4.89	4.71	4.73
10	4.84	4.89	4.91	4.85	4.81	4.87	4.81	4.86	---	4.90	4.69	4.73
11	4.84	4.90	4.91	4.85	4.81	4.86	4.80	4.86	---	4.92	4.69	4.73
12	4.84	4.90	4.91	4.85	4.80	4.86	4.79	4.86	---	4.91	4.69	4.73
13	4.84	4.89	4.91	4.85	4.82	4.85	4.82	4.86	---	4.92	4.69	4.73
14	4.84	4.92	4.94	4.85	4.83	4.85	4.86	4.84	---	4.93	4.69	4.73
15	4.83	4.90	4.92	4.86	4.82	4.86	4.86	4.82	---	4.93	4.69	4.73
16	4.84	4.90	4.89	4.86	4.82	4.86	4.84	4.81	---	4.93	4.69	4.74
17	4.84	4.91	4.89	4.84	48.40	4.87	4.88	4.80	---	4.93	4.70	4.74
18	4.83	4.90	4.90	4.82	4.85	4.88	4.81	4.78	---	4.93	4.70	4.74
19	4.83	4.90	4.90	4.81	4.85	4.87	4.82	4.76	---	4.94	4.70	4.74
20	4.84	4.96	4.90	4.81	4.86	4.87	4.82	4.78	---	4.94	4.70	4.74
21	4.83	4.92	4.90	4.80	4.88	4.87	4.79	4.80	---	4.94	4.70	4.74
22	4.83	4.91	4.90	4.82	4.88	4.86	4.76	4.78	---	4.94	4.70	4.74
23	4.84	4.90	4.90	4.84	4.87	4.86	4.75	4.78	---	4.95	4.70	4.75
24	4.86	4.90	4.91	4.85	4.87	4.87	4.76	4.77	---	4.93	4.70	4.75
25	4.85	4.91	4.91	4.85	4.87	4.88	4.76	4.78	---	4.93	4.71	4.75
26	4.86	4.91	4.91	4.84	4.87	4.87	4.75	4.77	---	4.94	4.71	4.75
27	4.87	5.18	4.90	4.83	4.86	4.86	4.79	4.75	---	4.95	4.71	4.75
28	4.87	5.16	4.89	4.83	4.87	4.85	4.79	4.74	---	4.95	4.71	4.75
29	4.88	5.10	5.25	4.82	---	4.85	4.78	4.73	---	4.95	4.71	4.75
30	4.88	5.39	5.59	4.82	---	4.85	4.85	4.71	---	4.95	4.71	4.76
31	4.89	---	5.09	4.82	---	4.84	---	---	---	4.94	4.71	---
MEAN	4.84	4.97	4.96	4.86	6.40	4.87	4.81	---	---	4.92	4.74	4.74
MAX	4.89	5.41	5.59	5.01	48.40	4.89	4.88	---	---	4.95	4.96	4.76
MIN	4.82	4.89	4.89	4.80	4.80	4.84	4.75	---	---	4.89	4.69	4.72

CAL YR 1992 MEAN 4.90 MAX 5.72 MIN 4.79

CULEBRA, PR

50215000 DRAINAGE CANAL AT CULEBRA AIRPORT, CULEBRA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'06", long 65°18'32", Hydrologic Unit 21010006, on right bank, 0.5 mi (0.8 km), northwest of Culebra City Hall, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) northwest of desalination plant, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) northeast of Playa Sardinas I, and of Highway 251 at airport south perimeter fence.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.08 mi² (0.20 km²).

WATER-STAGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1991 to current year (discontinued).

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 66 ft (20 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. All gage-heights of 10.25 ft or lower are considered zero flow.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum gage-height recorded, 10.52 ft (3.206 m), Apr. 21, 1993; minimum, 9.73 ft (2.966 m), Mar. 6, 1992.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum gage-height recorded, 10.52 ft (3.206 m), Apr. 21; minimum, 10.11 ft (3.082 m), Jan. 8.

GAGE HEIGHT, FEET, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	10.27	10.25	10.23	10.25	10.16	10.22	10.21	10.24	---	10.25	10.28	10.28
2	10.28	10.25	10.23	10.25	10.16	10.21	10.22	10.23	---	10.25	10.29	10.27
3	10.27	10.26	10.23	10.25	10.16	10.21	10.22	10.21	---	10.33	10.31	10.27
4	10.27	10.27	10.23	10.20	10.15	10.20	10.22	10.22	---	10.30	10.31	10.30
5	10.27	10.25	10.27	10.22	10.16	10.21	10.26	10.23	---	10.28	10.31	10.34
6	10.29	10.25	10.26	10.18	10.16	10.21	10.27	10.23	---	10.28	10.31	10.29
7	10.28	10.24	10.26	10.13	10.16	10.21	10.27	10.25	---	10.28	10.30	10.22
8	10.30	10.24	10.26	10.13	10.16	10.22	10.27	10.26	---	10.26	10.30	10.22
9	10.30	10.25	10.26	10.14	10.16	10.21	10.27	10.23	---	10.27	10.30	10.23
10	10.29	10.25	10.26	10.16	10.17	10.21	10.28	10.23	---	10.28	10.30	10.24
11	10.29	10.24	10.26	10.15	10.18	10.20	10.28	10.22	---	10.28	10.31	10.26
12	10.26	10.25	10.26	10.15	10.18	10.21	10.28	10.21	---	10.29	10.31	10.26
13	10.26	10.24	10.26	10.15	10.18	10.20	10.27	10.21	---	10.28	10.31	10.26
14	10.25	10.25	10.25	10.15	10.17	10.21	10.27	10.22	---	10.28	10.31	10.25
15	10.24	10.25	10.24	10.15	10.18	10.21	10.27	10.23	---	10.28	10.31	10.26
16	10.25	10.25	10.20	10.17	10.19	10.22	10.27	10.23	---	10.28	10.30	10.33
17	10.28	10.25	10.19	10.16	10.20	10.21	10.27	10.21	---	10.28	10.28	10.34
18	10.29	10.25	10.14	10.16	10.21	10.22	10.28	10.21	---	10.27	10.28	10.32
19	10.26	10.25	10.15	10.18	10.21	10.22	10.28	10.22	---	10.28	10.29	10.30
20	10.25	10.25	10.14	10.17	10.24	10.22	10.29	10.21	---	10.28	10.30	10.21
21	10.24	10.25	10.14	10.17	10.22	10.22	10.29	---	---	10.27	10.30	10.21
22	10.25	10.25	10.17	10.16	10.21	10.22	10.28	---	---	10.26	10.29	10.21
23	10.25	10.25	10.14	10.16	10.22	10.24	10.29	---	---	10.32	10.27	10.21
24	10.26	10.25	10.19	10.16	10.22	10.21	10.27	---	---	10.31	10.28	10.21
25	10.27	10.25	10.15	10.16	10.22	10.20	10.27	---	---	10.26	10.28	10.21
26	10.28	10.25	10.26	10.17	10.23	10.20	10.27	---	---	10.28	10.28	10.23
27	10.28	10.25	10.21	10.16	10.25	10.20	10.27	---	---	10.26	10.29	10.24
28	10.22	10.25	10.24	10.14	10.26	10.20	10.28	---	---	10.26	10.27	10.23
29	10.23	10.25	10.24	10.15	---	10.20	10.28	---	---	10.26	10.27	10.23
30	10.24	10.23	10.25	10.16	---	10.20	10.26	---	---	10.27	10.27	10.22
31	10.25	---	10.25	10.16	---	10.21	---	---	---	10.28	10.28	---
MEAN	10.27	10.25	10.22	10.17	10.19	10.21	10.27	---	---	10.28	10.29	10.25
MAX	10.30	10.27	10.27	10.25	10.26	10.24	10.29	---	---	10.33	10.31	10.34
MIN	10.22	10.23	10.14	10.13	10.15	10.20	10.21	---	---	10.25	10.27	10.21

VIEQUES, PR

50231000 QUEBRADA COFRESI TRIBUTARY NEAR ISABEL SEGUNDA, VIEQUES, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°08'21", long 65°26'06", Hydrologic Unit 21010006, on right bank, 1.0 mi (1.6 km), south-southwest of Isabel Segunda Plaza, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) north of Destino school, and 1.5 mi (2.4 km) southeast of junction of Highways 200 and 201.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.28 mi² (0.72 km²).

WATER-STAGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1991 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 196 ft (60 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. All gage-heights of 8.20 ft or lower are considered zero flow.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum gage-height, 11.20 ft (3.414 m), July 23, 1993; minimum, 7.69 ft (2.344 m), Aug. 28, 1992.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum gage-height, 11.20 ft (3.414 m), July 23; minimum, 7.94 ft (2.420 m), Apr. 15.

GAGE HEIGHT, FEET, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	8.66	8.69	8.66	8.71	8.60	8.54	8.35	8.61	8.67	8.60	8.72	8.50
2	8.60	8.68	8.65	8.71	8.59	---	8.33	---	8.66	8.62	8.71	8.45
3	8.54	8.67	8.62	8.70	8.64	8.49	8.31	---	8.61	8.62	8.69	8.51
4	8.53	8.65	8.63	8.68	8.59	8.50	8.28	8.59	8.60	8.60	8.68	8.50
5	8.54	8.64	8.63	8.69	8.58	8.50	8.24	8.57	8.60	8.59	8.68	8.84
6	8.55	8.62	8.62	8.71	8.58	8.50	8.21	8.54	8.59	8.58	8.65	8.65
7	8.56	8.57	8.61	8.69	---	8.49	8.17	8.56	8.58	8.56	8.64	8.57
8	8.57	8.57	8.63	8.68	8.57	8.47	8.13	8.73	8.55	8.57	8.63	8.55
9	8.57	8.56	8.62	8.70	8.58	8.47	8.11	8.70	8.55	8.55	8.62	8.49
10	8.52	8.56	8.62	8.68	8.57	8.47	8.09	8.68	8.55	8.56	8.62	8.47
11	8.52	8.56	8.61	8.68	8.57	8.47	---	8.66	8.55	8.70	8.63	8.46
12	8.45	8.59	8.61	8.68	8.57	8.47	---	8.65	8.53	8.63	8.62	8.45
13	8.50	8.60	8.63	8.66	8.56	8.48	8.01	8.64	8.50	8.59	8.60	8.41
14	8.51	8.61	8.60	8.68	8.57	8.44	7.99	8.65	8.47	8.57	8.60	8.41
15	8.51	8.59	8.59	---	8.58	8.44	7.96	8.65	8.47	8.57	8.66	8.45
16	8.52	8.58	8.58	---	8.57	8.44	8.03	8.65	8.46	8.56	8.70	8.90
17	8.55	8.62	8.60	---	8.57	8.44	8.25	8.65	8.42	8.56	8.62	8.75
18	8.58	8.62	8.60	8.64	8.57	8.46	8.30	8.64	8.37	8.54	8.59	8.68
19	8.61	8.61	8.60	8.63	8.58	8.49	8.26	8.64	8.62	8.53	8.59	8.61
20	8.62	8.64	8.59	8.62	8.59	8.45	8.21	8.65	8.77	8.51	8.67	8.58
21	8.84	8.61	8.57	8.61	8.57	8.44	8.15	8.64	8.68	8.49	8.67	8.55
22	8.93	8.63	8.60	8.63	8.56	8.42	8.10	8.67	8.68	8.60	8.63	8.51
23	8.80	8.60	8.60	8.61	8.54	8.41	8.04	8.71	---	9.34	8.75	8.50
24	8.78	8.60	8.63	8.61	8.54	8.42	8.21	8.70	---	8.93	8.66	8.49
25	8.77	8.60	8.60	8.65	8.53	8.41	8.40	8.73	8.67	8.85	8.59	8.47
26	8.76	8.59	8.70	8.62	8.54	8.39	8.44	---	8.66	8.84	8.55	8.45
27	8.75	8.69	8.65	8.62	8.52	8.39	8.52	8.71	8.65	8.80	8.52	8.42
28	8.74	8.68	8.63	8.60	8.52	8.39	8.52	8.71	8.63	8.77	8.50	8.43
29	8.72	8.68	8.87	8.61	---	8.39	8.51	8.70	8.62	8.75	8.48	8.44
30	8.71	8.68	9.02	8.60	---	8.38	8.62	8.70	8.61	8.74	8.48	8.51
31	8.70	---	8.74	8.61	---	8.36	---	8.68	---	8.74	8.47	---
MEAN	8.63	8.62	8.64	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.66	8.62	8.53
MAX	8.93	8.69	9.02	---	---	---	---	---	---	9.34	8.75	8.90
MIN	8.45	8.56	8.57	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.49	8.47	8.41

VIEQUES, PR

50232000 QUEBRADA LA MINA NEAR ESPERANZA, VIEQUES, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°06'54", long 65°28'15", Hydrologic Unit 21010006, on left bank 300 ft (91 m), west from state road 996, 1.4 mi (2.2 km) south of Cerro Martineau, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) east-northeast of Colonia Puerto Real on road 201 and 1.2 mi (1.9 km) north of Esperanza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.68 mi² (1.76 km²).

WATER-STAGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1991 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 98 ft (30 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. All gage-heights of 9.20 ft or lower are considered zero flow.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum gage-height, 9.90 ft (3.018 m), June 29, 30; minimum, 8.80 ft (2.682 m), June 24.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum gage-height, 9.90 ft (3.018 m), June 29, 30; minimum, 8.80 ft (2.682 m), June 24.

GAGE HEIGHT, FEET, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	8.90	8.85	9.20	9.19	8.85	8.85	8.85	8.84	8.81	8.84	8.84	8.87
2	8.90	8.85	9.19	9.20	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.88	8.81	8.84	8.84	8.87
3	8.90	8.85	9.18	9.20	8.86	8.85	8.84	8.84	8.81	8.84	8.84	8.87
4	8.88	8.89	9.19	9.20	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.84	8.82	8.85	8.84	8.87
5	8.85	8.85	9.19	9.20	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.84	8.82	8.85	8.85	8.87
6	8.85	8.85	9.19	9.20	8.85	8.85	8.85	8.84	8.82	8.85	8.85	8.86
7	8.85	8.86	9.19	9.20	8.85	8.85	8.85	8.88	8.82	8.85	8.85	8.86
8	8.85	8.86	9.20	9.20	8.85	8.85	8.85	8.94	8.82	8.85	8.85	8.86
9	8.85	8.86	9.20	9.20	8.85	8.85	8.85	8.85	8.82	8.85	8.85	8.86
10	8.85	8.86	9.20	9.20	8.85	8.85	8.85	8.84	8.82	8.85	8.85	8.86
11	8.85	8.86	9.19	9.20	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.84	8.82	8.85	8.85	8.87
12	8.85	8.86	8.90	9.20	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.83	8.82	8.85	8.86	8.87
13	8.85	8.86	8.86	9.20	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.84	8.82	8.84	8.86	8.87
14	8.85	9.04	8.85	9.20	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.84	8.82	8.84	8.86	8.87
15	8.85	9.19	8.85	9.20	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.84	8.82	8.84	8.86	8.87
16	8.85	9.18	8.85	9.20	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.84	8.82	8.84	8.86	9.12
17	8.85	9.12	8.86	9.20	8.86	8.85	8.84	8.83	8.82	8.85	8.85	9.15
18	8.85	9.18	8.86	9.20	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.83	8.82	8.85	8.85	9.15
19	8.85	9.17	8.86	9.21	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.83	8.82	8.85	8.85	9.16
20	8.84	9.17	8.86	9.11	8.86	8.85	8.84	8.83	8.82	8.85	8.85	9.16
21	8.83	9.18	8.86	8.87	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.83	8.81	8.85	8.85	9.16
22	8.83	9.07	8.86	8.87	8.86	8.85	8.84	8.83	8.81	8.85	8.85	9.15
23	8.83	8.86	8.86	8.86	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.83	8.81	9.09	8.85	9.12
24	8.84	8.86	8.86	8.86	8.86	8.85	8.84	8.83	8.83	9.10	8.85	9.13
25	8.83	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.84	8.84	9.11	8.85	9.03
26	8.83	8.86	9.03	8.85	8.86	8.85	8.84	8.82	8.84	9.03	8.85	8.88
27	8.83	8.98	9.20	8.86	8.86	8.85	8.84	8.82	8.84	8.86	8.85	8.86
28	8.83	9.20	9.20	8.86	8.86	8.85	8.84	8.82	9.14	8.84	8.85	8.86
29	8.85	9.20	9.20	8.86	---	8.84	8.84	8.81	9.88	8.84	8.85	8.86
30	8.85	9.20	9.20	8.86	---	8.84	8.84	8.81	8.99	8.84	8.86	9.03
31	8.85	---	9.19	8.85	---	8.84	---	8.81	---	8.84	8.87	---
MEAN	8.85	8.98	9.04	9.08	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.84	8.87	8.88	8.85	8.96
MAX	8.90	9.20	9.20	9.21	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.94	9.88	9.11	8.87	9.16
MIN	8.83	8.85	8.85	8.85	8.85	8.84	8.84	8.81	8.81	8.84	8.84	8.86
MED	8.85	8.86	9.18	9.20	8.86	8.85	8.85	8.84	8.82	8.85	8.85	8.87

VIEQUES, PR

50233000 QUEBRADA PILON AT COLONIA PUERTO REAL, VIEQUES, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°06'37", long 65°28'51", Hydrologic Unit 21010006, on left bank, 1.2 mi (1.9 km), southeast of Cerro Sonadora, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) northwest of Esperanza, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) south of junction of Highways 895 and 201.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.67 mi² (1.74 km²).

WATER-STAGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1991 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 131 ft (40 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. All gage-heights of 8.20 ft or lower are considered zero flow.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum gage-height, 9.13 ft (2.783 m), July 23, 1993; minimum, 6.68 ft (2.036 m), Sept. 14, 15, 1993.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum gage-height, 9.13 ft (2.783 m), July 23; minimum, 6.68 ft (2.036 m), Sept. 14, 15.

GAGE HEIGHT, FEET, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.54	7.14	7.26	7.37	7.45	7.38	7.13	7.43	7.74	7.17	7.10	6.95
2	7.50	7.15	7.26	7.38	7.46	7.46	7.13	7.54	7.72	7.19	7.10	6.92
3	7.28	7.15	7.26	7.39	7.46	7.34	7.13	7.50	7.67	7.21	7.09	6.95
4	---	7.15	7.26	7.39	7.46	7.31	7.13	7.34	7.62	7.15	7.10	6.95
5	---	7.15	7.26	7.40	7.46	7.28	7.14	7.26	7.54	7.13	7.10	7.11
6	---	7.17	7.26	7.40	7.46	7.26	7.14	7.23	7.45	7.11	7.10	7.07
7	---	7.11	7.26	7.40	7.46	7.23	7.14	7.25	7.38	7.18	7.10	7.03
8	---	6.98	7.26	7.40	7.46	7.22	7.14	7.67	7.32	7.11	7.11	6.99
9	---	6.94	7.26	7.40	7.46	7.21	7.14	7.67	7.29	7.07	7.10	6.95
10	---	6.96	7.25	7.40	7.47	7.20	7.14	7.67	7.27	7.10	7.10	6.92
11	---	6.98	7.26	7.41	7.46	7.19	7.14	7.68	7.26	7.29	7.09	6.89
12	---	6.99	7.26	7.42	7.47	7.19	7.14	7.68	7.24	7.28	7.07	6.82
13	---	7.06	7.25	7.42	7.45	7.20	7.15	7.64	7.24	7.27	7.06	6.84
14	---	7.14	7.26	7.41	7.45	7.16	7.15	7.56	7.24	7.25	7.07	6.80
15	---	7.25	7.25	7.42	7.45	7.15	7.15	7.50	7.23	7.24	7.11	6.80
16	---	7.24	7.19	7.42	7.44	7.14	7.15	7.61	7.23	7.22	7.12	7.16
17	---	7.22	7.16	7.41	7.43	7.14	7.15	7.49	7.23	7.20	7.09	7.29
18	---	7.24	7.11	7.42	7.46	7.15	7.15	7.44	7.23	7.19	7.09	7.20
19	---	7.24	7.11	7.43	7.46	7.18	7.15	7.43	7.23	7.16	7.08	7.17
20	---	7.24	7.16	7.43	7.44	7.16	7.15	7.47	7.24	7.11	7.07	7.17
21	7.17	7.24	7.11	7.43	7.41	7.14	7.16	7.46	7.23	7.08	7.05	7.17
22	7.16	7.24	7.24	7.44	7.36	7.13	7.15	7.45	7.24	7.19	7.08	7.16
23	7.16	7.21	7.25	7.44	7.35	7.13	7.15	7.67	7.24	7.50	7.08	7.16
24	7.16	7.21	7.27	7.44	7.33	7.16	7.15	7.72	7.26	7.20	7.05	7.16
25	7.17	7.15	7.27	7.44	7.33	7.14	7.16	7.73	7.27	7.17	7.03	7.15
26	7.17	7.10	7.29	7.45	7.38	7.12	7.16	7.73	7.25	7.16	7.02	7.15
27	7.17	7.19	7.29	7.45	---	7.12	7.16	7.73	7.23	7.15	7.03	7.15
28	7.14	7.26	7.28	7.44	---	7.13	7.17	7.74	7.22	7.15	7.01	7.15
29	7.14	7.25	7.31	7.45	---	7.13	7.17	7.74	7.21	7.13	6.98	7.15
30	7.14	7.26	7.38	7.45	---	7.13	7.29	7.75	7.20	7.12	7.00	7.16
31	7.14	---	7.37	7.45	---	7.13	---	7.75	---	7.11	6.99	---
MEAN	---	7.15	7.25	7.42	---	7.19	7.15	7.57	7.32	7.18	7.07	7.05
MAX	---	7.26	7.38	7.45	---	7.46	7.29	7.75	7.74	7.50	7.12	7.29
MIN	---	6.94	7.11	7.37	---	7.12	7.13	7.23	7.20	7.07	6.98	6.80

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DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

As the number of streams on which streamflow information is likely to be desired far exceeds the number of stream-gaging stations feasible to operate at one time, the Geological Survey collects limited streamflow data at sites other than stream-gaging stations. When limited streamflow data are collected on a systematic basis over a period of years for use in hydrologic analyses, the site at which the data are collected is called a partial-record station. Data collected at these partial-record stations are useable in low-flow or floodflow analyses, depending on the type of data collected. In addition, discharge measurements are made at other sites not included in the partial-record program. These measurements are generally made in times of drought or flood to give better areal coverage to those events. Those measurements and others collected for some special reason are called measurements at miscellaneous sites.

Low-flow partial-record stations

Measurements of streamflow in the areas covered by this report made at low-flow partial-record stations are given in the following table. These measurements were made during periods of base flow when streamflow is primarily from ground-water storage. These measurements, when correlated with the simultaneous discharge of nearby stream when continuous records are available, will give a picture of the low-flow potentiality of stream.

Discharge measurements made at low-flow partial-records stations during water year 1993

PUBLICATION RECORD

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM-FLOW ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
Río Melanía basin						
50095900	Quebrada Melanía near Jobos, PR	Lat 17°57'51", long 66°59'30", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) upstream from bridge on Highway 3.	2.75 (7.12)	3/09/93 4/27/93	1320 1220	0.25 (0.007) ---
50097000	Quebrada Cimarrona near Jobos, PR	Lat 17°59'18", long 66°10'59", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Pozo Hondo, 2.4 mi (3.7 km) north from Puerto de Jobos, and 4.0 mi (6.4 km) northwest from Plaza de Guayama.	3.09 (8.00)	3/09/93 4/27/93	1300 1240	0.00 0.00
Río Seco basin						
50097800	Río Seco near Central Guamaní, PR	Lat 17°58'06", long 66°10'52", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at bridge on Highway 3, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) north of Central Guamaní, and 1.2 mi (1.9 km) northwest of Jobos.	11.2 (29.0)	3/09/93 4/27/93	1310 1235	0.00 0.00
Río Salinas (Nigua) basin						
50100200	Río Lapa near Rabo del Buey, PR	Lat 18°03'36", long 66°14'28", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Lapa on Highway 1, 1.6 mi (2.6 km) upstream from confluence with Río Majada, and 6.2 mi (10 km) southwest from Plaza de Cayey.	10.0 (25.8)	3/09/93 4/27/93	1040 0735	0.79 (0.022) 0.73 (0.021)
50100300	Río Jájome at Jájome, PR	Lat 18°03'49", long 66°09'38", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Jájome Bajo on Highway 708, 3.5 mi (5.6 km) south from Plaza de Cayey.	4.56 (11.8)	3/09/93 4/27/93	1215 0915	0.94 (0.027) 1.10 (0.031)
50100450	Río Majada at La Plena, PR	Lat 18°02'40", long 66°12'27", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Quebrada Yegua on Highway 712, 2.0 mi (3.2 km) northeast from Albergue Olímpico, and 5.5 mi (8.8 km) southwest from Plaza de Cayey.	16.7 (43.2)	3/09/93 4/27/93	1125 0825	1.24 (0.035) 1.34 (0.038)
50100700	Río Majada at Rabo del Buey, PR	Lat 18°02'17", long 66°14'27", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Lapa, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from confluence with Río Lapa, 400 ft upstream from intersection of Highways 1 and 712, and 0.2 mi (0.3 km) northwest from Albergue Olímpico.	22.2 (57.5)	3/09/93 4/27/93	1115 0810	--- ---

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

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Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
50102000	Río Salinas at Salinas, PR	Lat 17°58'42", long 66°18'17", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Bridge on Highway 1, and 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west from Plaza de Salinas.	52.4 (136)	3/09/93	1315	---
				4/27/93	1300	0.00
Río Jueyes basin						
50102400	Río Jueyes at Río Jueyes, PR	Lat 18°01'17", long 66°19'51", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Río Jueyes on Highway 154, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) upstream from Highway 52, and 4.5 mi (7.2 km) southeast from Plaza de Coamo.	3.50 (9.06)	3/10/93	1005	0.19 (0.005)
				4/28/93	0950	0.14 (0.004)
50103000	Río Jueyes near Jauca, PR	Lat 17°58'45", long 66°20'20", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at bridge on Highway 1, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) east of Jaucas, and 2.7 mi (4.3 km) west from Plaza de Salinas.	8.56 (22.2)	3/10/93	1035	0.00
				4/28/93	1020	0.00
Río Coamo basin						
50104000	Río Coamo near Pasto, PR	Lat 18°07'08", long 66°21'52", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Pasto on Highway 555, 2.6 mi (4.2 km) northwest from Plaza de Coamo.	9.05 (23.4)	3/11/93	0725	5.11 (0.145)
				4/29/93	1320	30.6 (0.866)
50105400	Río Cuyón at La Guava, PR	Lat 18°05'20", long 66°16'17", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Algarrobo on Highway 717, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) southwest from Cerro Verdún, and 5.6 mi (9.0 km) east from Plaza de Coamo.	4.33 (11.2)	3/09/93	0950	0.63 (0.018)
				4/27/93	0700	0.64 (0.018)
50105600	Río Cuyón near Coamo, PR	Lat 18°05'25", long 66°18'50", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Cuyón on Highway 14, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) southeast from Cerro Santa Ana, and 2.8 mi (4.5 km) northeast from Plaza de Coamo.	18.1 (46.8)	3/10/93	0645	1.40 (0.040)
				4/28/93	0650	2.82 (0.080)
50105900	Quebrada Montería near Coamo, PR	Lat 18°05'13", long 66°21'04", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Pasto at confluence with Río Cuyón, and 0.5 mi (0.8 km) northeast from Plaza de Coamo.	7.12 (18.4)	3/10/93	0730	0.66 (0.019)
				4/28/93	0740	0.38 (0.011)
50106100	Río Coamo at Coamo, PR	Lat 18°05'00", long 66°21'16", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Coamo on Highway 14, 500 ft (152 m) downstream from confluence with Río Cuyón, and 0.2 mi (0.3 km) east from Plaza de Coamo.	43.5 (113)	3/10/93	0810	6.59 (0.187)
				4/28/93	0805	19.0 (0.538)
50106600	Río de La Mina near Coamo, PR	Lat 18°05'04", long 66°23'22", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Santa Catalina on Highway 150, 2.2 mi (3.5 km) west from Plaza de Coamo.	2.62 (6.78)	3/11/92	0925	0.61 (0.017)
				4/30/93	0820	0.58 (0.033)
50106650	Río del Pasto near Coamo, PR	Lat 18°04'49", long 66°22'32", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio San Idelfonso on Highway 150, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) west from Plaza de Coamo.	1.80 (4.67)	3/11/93	0845	0.46 (0.013)
				4/30/93	0735	0.44 (0.012)

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
50106700	Río de La Mina at Coamo, PR	Lat 18°03'56", long 66°22'29", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio San Idelfonso on Highway 14, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from confluence with Río Coamo, and 1.7 mi (2.7 km) from Plaza de Coamo.	5.88 (15.2)	3/11/93	1050	1.22 (0.034)
				4/29/93	1225	1.33 (0.038)
50106820	Río Coamo at Baños de Coamo, PR	Lat 18°02'23", long 66°22'31", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio San Idelfonso at the end of Highway 546, 3.3 mi (5.3 km) southwest from Plaza de Coamo.	58.5 (152)	3/10/93	0910	11.8 (0.334)
				4/28/93	0900	12.3 (0.348)
50107000	Río Coamo near Santa Isabel, PR	Lat 17°58'36", long 66°25'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at bridge on Highway 1 at Velázquez, 1.1 mi (1.8 km) northwest from Plaza de Santa Isabel.	69.3 (179)	3/10/93	1055	6.12 (0.173)
				4/29/93	0805	76.7 (2.72)
Río Descalabrado basin						
50107800	Río Descalabrado near Sanja Blanca, PR	Lat 18°05'24", long 66°24'30", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Santa Catalina on Highway 150, 2.0 mi (3.2 km) southeast from Lago Toa Vaca, and 3.4 mi (5.5 km) northwest from Plaza de Coamo.	4.27 (11.0)	3/11/93	1010	0.54 (0.015)
				4/30/93	0855	1.46 (0.041)
50108200	Río Descalabrado at Las Ollas, PR	Lat 18°02'10", long 66°25'36", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Descalabrado on Highway 536, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) upstream from Highway 52, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northwest from Cerro del Muerto.	13.9 (36.0)	3/11/93	1140	0.33 (0.009)
				4/29/93	1140	2.47 (0.070)
50108500	Río Descalabrado near Santa Isabel, PR	Lat 17°58'45", long 66°26'35", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at bridge on Highway 1, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) upstream from mouth, and 3.1 mi (5.0 km) northwest of Santa Isabel.	18.1 (46.9)	3/12/93	0745	0.70 (0.020)
				4/29/93	0900	0.41 (0.012)
Río Cañas basin						
50109000	Río Cañas near Juana Díaz, PR	Lat 18°02'41", long 66°27'26", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Río Cañas Arriba on Highway 14, 3.3 mi (5.3 km) east from Plaza de Juana Díaz.	2.88 (7.47)	3/11/93	1215	0.14 (0.004)
				4/29/93	1120	0.14 (0.004)
50109500	Río Cañas near Santa Isabel, PR	Lat 18°59'39", long 66°28'33", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at bridge on Highway 1, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) from mouth, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) east of Pastillo, and 5.1 mi (8.2 km) northwest from Plaza de Santa Isabel.	6.38 (16.5)	3/10/93	1210	0.00
				4/29/92	0930	0.00
Río Jacaguas basin						
50110550	Río Jacaguas at Villalba, PR	Lat 18°07'37", long 66°29'42", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Hato Puerco Arriba upstream from Sewage Water Treatment Plant, 100 ft (30 m) downstream from confluence with Quebrada Achilote, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) southwest from Villalba.	12.2 (31.7)	3/16/93	0935	47.2 (1.337)
				5/06/93	1130	101 (2.860)
50110700	Río Toa Vaca at Pedro García, PR	Lat 18°08'11", long 66°23'47", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Pedro García, 2.1 mi (3.4 km) southeast from intersection of Highways 143 and 155, and 4.1 mi (6.6 km) northeast of Lago Toa Vaca.	3.09 (8.00)	3/16/93	0700	0.52 (0.015)
				5/06/93	1340	2.55 (0.072)

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

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Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
50110900	Río Toa Vaca upstream from Lago Toa Vaca, PR	Lat 18°07'36", long 66°27'25", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Caonillas Arriba on Highway 553, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) upstream from Lago Toa Vaca, and 2.4 mi (3.9 km) east of Villalba.	14.2 (36.8)	3/16/93	0840	3.59 (0.102)
				5/06/93	1225	11.4 (0.323)
50111720	Quebrada Guanábana near Juana Díaz, PR	Lat 18°03'12", long 66°29'02", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Tijeras on Highway 14, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) east from Plaza Juana Díaz. Río Inabón basin	1.72 (4.46)	3/16/93	0900	0.00
				5/06/93	1040	0.00
50112400	Río Inabón at Real Anón, PR	Lat 18°07'22", long 66°34'20", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Anón on Highway 511, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) northeast from Cerro Santo Domingo, and 4.5 mi (7.2 km) northwest from Lago Guayabal.	6.00 (15.4)	3/16/93	1300	3.31 (0.094)
				5/05/93	1225	25.1 (0.711)
50112700	Río Guayo near Collores, PR	Lat 18°07'24", long 66°33'27", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Collores on Highway 517, about 400 ft (122 m) west from escuela Guaraguao, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) northwest from intersection of Highways 517 and 512, and 3.5 mi (5.6 km) northwest from Lago Toa Vaca.	1.67 (4.34)	3/16/93	1110	1.18 (0.033)
				5/06/93	0925	3.90 (0.110)
50112750	Quebrada Indalecia at Collores, PR	Lat 18°06'33", long 66°32'20". Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Collores, 200 ft (61 m) upstream from confluence with Río Guayo, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) northeast of Cerro Agustinillo, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northwest of Lago Guayabal.	3.52 (9.11)	3/16/93	1045	0.02 (0.001)
				5/06/93	0850	0.38 (0.011)
50112800	Río Guayo upstream from Diversion at Collores, PR	Lat 18°05'10", long 66°32'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Collores, 2.1 mi (3.4 km) southwest from Lago Guayabal, and 3.1 mi (5.0 km) northwest from Plaza de Juana Díaz. Río Bucaná basin	9.55 (24.7)	3/16/93	1200	1.92 (0.054)
				5/05/93	1345	10.0 (0.283)
50113790	Río San Patricio upstream from Lago Cerrillos, PR	Lat 18°07'12", long 66°36'27", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at barro Maragüez, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) northwest from Cerro Santo Domingo, 3.6 mi (5.8 km) northwest of Lago Cerrillos, and 7.3 mi (12 km) from Plaza Degetau in Ponce.	5.84 (15.1)	3/17/93	0900	4.80 (0.136)
				5/04/93	1315	14.5 (0.411)
50113800	Río Cerrillos upstream from Lago Cerrillos, PR	Lat 18°07'01", long 66°36'17", Hydrologic Unit 21010004 at barrio Maragüez, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) west of Cerro Santo Domingo, 3.3 mi (5.3 km) northwest of Lago Cerrillos, and 7.2 mi (12 km) from Plaza Degetau, in Ponce.	11.9 (30.7)	3/17/93	0945	8.31 (0.235)
				5/04/93	1415	45.6 (1.291)
50114150	Quebrada Ausubo near Ponce, PR	Lat 18°03'09", long 66°35'08", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Machuelo Arriba, 2.4 mi (3.9 km) west from Coto Laurel, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) south from Lago Cerrillos, and 3.8 mi (6.1 km) northeast from Plaza Degetau, in Ponce.	1.18 (3.05)	3/17/93	0810	0.00
				5/04/93	1550	0.00

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
50114200	Río Bayagán near Ponce, PR	Lat 18°02'51", long 66°35'12", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Machuelo Arriba, 2.5 mi (4.0 km) west of Coto Laurel, 1.9 mi (3.0 km) south of Lago Cerrillos, and 3.0 mi (4.8 km) northeast from Plaza Degetau, in Ponce.	3.82 (9.88)	3/17/93	0800	0.00
				5/04/93	1555	0.00
50114600	Río Bucaná at Ponce, PR	Lat 18°00'28", long 66°35'36", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at bridge on Highway 1, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) east from intersection of Highways 1 and 2, 3.1 mi (5.0 km) upstream from mouth, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) east of Plaza Degetau, in Ponce.	27.3 (70.7)	3/17/93	0750	---
				5/04/93	0645	---
Río Portugués basin						
50114900	Río Portugués near Tibes, PR	Lat 18°04'26", long 66°38'35", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at barrio Tibes, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) southwest of Cerro del Diablo, 6.0 mi (9.6 km) northeast from Peñuelas, and 6.2 mi (10 km) north of Ponce.	7.27 (18.8)	3/17/93	1455	4.47 (0.126)
				5/03/93	0900	18.7 (0.530)
50115400	Río Portugués near Ponce, PR	Lat 18°02'27", long 66°36'41", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at barrio Portugués, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) west of Jardines de Ponce, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) north from confluence with Río Chiquito, and 1.9 mi (3.0 km) north from Plaza Degetau, in Ponce.	12.2 (31.6)	3/17/93	1155	3.94 (0.112)
				5/03/93	1305	32.6 (0.923)
50115450	Río Chiquito at Portugués, PR	Lat 18°04'11", long 66°37'00", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at barrio Portugués, 2.1 mi (3.4 km) northwest from Jardines de Ponce, 1.7 mi (2.7 km) southwest of Pico Pinto, and 2.8 mi (4.5 km) north from Plaza Degetau, in Ponce.	3.12 (8.09)	3/17/93	1245	0.34 (0.010)
				5/03/93	1130	14.5 (0.411)
50115600	Río Chiquito near Ponce, PR	Lat 18°02'37", long 66°36'31", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at barrio Portugués, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) west from Jardines de Ponce, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) south of Cerro El Gato, and 2.1 mi (3.4 km) north from Plaza Degetau, in Ponce.	4.43 (11.5)	3/17/93	1115	0.53 (0.015)
				5/03/93	1215	16.0 (0.453)
50116500	Río Portugués at Hwy 2 By-Pass at Ponce, PR	Lat 17°59'52", long 66°36'52", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at bridge on Hwy 2 By-Pass, 2.0 mi (3.2 km) upstream from mouth, and 1.1 mi (1.8 km) south of Plaza Degetau, in Ponce.	20.5 (53.1)	3/18/93	0700	4.69 (0.133)
				5/03/93	1400	48.9 (1.385)
Río Matilde basin						
50116800	Río Cañas at Magueyes, PR	Lat 18°04'26", long 66°39'07", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at barrio Magueyes, 2.4 mi (3.9 km) southwest from Cerro del Diablo, 4.7 mi (7.6 km) northwest from Peñuelas, and (6.4 km) northwest from Ponce.	4.00 (10.3)	3/18/93	0850	2.29 (0.065)
				5/04/93	1105	14.8 (0.419)
50116970	Río Cañas downstream from Las Américas Ave. PR	Lat 18°00'37", long 66°38'26", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) upstream from confluence with Río Pastillo.	8.50 (22.0)	3/18/93	0750	9.73 (0.276)
				5/04/93	1010	23.0 (0.651)

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

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Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
50117800	Río Pastillo at Pastillo, PR	Lat 18°02'53", long 66°39'52", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Quebrada Limón on Highway 502, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) northwest of Highways 502 and 132 intersection, and 3.1 mi (5.0 km) northwest from Ponce.	4.32 (11.2)	3/31/93	0810	0.96 (0.027)
				5/05/93	0850	4.01 (0.114)
50118300	Río Pastillo near Ponce, PR	Lat 18°00'31", long 66°38'39", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Canas Urbano on bridge, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) downstream from Jardines del Caribe and, 1.1 mi (1.7 km) west of Escuela Dr. Pila, Ponce.	10.6 (27.6)	3/30/93	1455	0.00
				5/05/93	0945	1.63 (0.046)
50119000	Río Matilde at Ponce, PR	Lat 17°59'53", long 66°38'06", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Highway 2, 1.1 mi (1.8 km) upstream from mouth.	20.5 (53.2)	3/30/93	1410	10.0 (0.283)
				5/11/93	1515	14.3 (0.405)
50119200	Quebrada del Agua at Playa de Ponce, PR	Lat 17°59'13", long 66°38'22", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 700 ft (213 m) upstream from confluence with Río Matilde.	6.45 (16.7)	3/31/93	1325	0.00
				5/11/93	1605	0.00
Río Tallaboa basin						
50120550	Río Tallaboa near Quebrada Ceiba, PR	Lat 18°04'18", long 66°42'03", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Quebrada Ceiba, 0.06 mi (0.1 km) west of Highway 391, 1.2 mi (2.0 km) north of Tallaboa Alta, and 1.7 mi (2.7 km) northeast from Plaza de Peñuelas.	8.41 (21.8)	3/31/93	0910	4.86 (0.138)
				5/11/93	1140	21.7 (0.614)
50120700	Río Guayanés near Peñuelas, PR	Lat 18°04'03", long 66°43'36", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Jaguas on Highway 386, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) northeast of intersection of Highways 386 and 132, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) northeast from Plaza de Peñuelas.	7.29 (18.9)	3/31/93	1015	2.12 (0.060)
				5/11/93	1320	70.2 (1.988)
50121000	Río Tallaboa at Peñuelas, PR	Lat 18°03'02", long 66°43'19", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 350 ft (107 m) downstream from Highway 132 bridge, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) south of Peñuelas.	24.2 (62.7)	3/31/93	1105	9.77 (0.277)
				5/11/93	1240	98.4 (2.787)
50122000	Río Tallaboa at Tallaboa, PR	Lat 18°00'31", long 66°43'49", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on bridge at Hacienda Dolores, 700 ft (213 m) upstream from Highway 127, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) north west of Tallaboa, and 7.6 mi (12.2 km) west of Plaza Degetau, in Ponce.	31.6 (81.7)	3/31/93	1210	4.75 (0.134)
				5/11/93	1415	87.9 (2.489)
Río Macaná basin						
50122500	Río Macaná near Peñuelas, PR	Lat 18°03'40", long 66°46'12", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Macaná on Highways 131 and 132 intersection, 5.5 mi (8.8 km) northeast from Yauco, and 2.8 (4.5 km) northeast from Plaza de Guayanilla.	2.77 (7.17)	4/02/93	0920	0.33 (0.009)
				5/13/93	1110	2.07 (0.059)
50122900	Río Macaná at Magas Arriba, PR	Lat 18°01'00", long 66°45'57", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 1.8 mi (2.8 km) east of Plaza de Guayanilla, 200 ft (60 m) upstream of Highway 2 bridge, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) from mouth.	8.98 (23.2)	3/31/93	1300	0.00
				5/13/93	0900	0.00

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
Río Guayanilla basin						
50123100	Río Guayanilla at Pasto, PR	Lat 18°05'53", long 66°47'38", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at barrio Pasto, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) southeast from Pico Rodadero, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) west from Cerro El Peligro, and 5.2 mi (8.4 km) north from Plaza de Guayanilla.	6.45 (16.7)	4/02/93	1000	3.25 (0.092)
				5/13/93	1150	17.1 (0.484)
50124600	Río Guayanilla near Central Rufina, PR	Lat 18°01'00", long 66°47'01", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Guayanilla, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) upstream from mouth, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) northeast from Central Rufina, and 0.6 mi (1.0 km) southeast from Plaza de Guayanilla.	23.0 (59.5)	4/02/93	0700	0.37 (0.010)
				5/13/93	1015	21.4 (0.606)
Río Yauco basin						
50125000	Río Yauco near Lago Lucchetti Damsite, PR	Lat 18°06'40", long 66°52'38", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Vegas, 300 ft (91 m) from mouth, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) northwest from spillway, and 5.4 mi (8.7 km) northwest from Plaza de Yauco.	8.05 (20.8)	4/01/93	1225	4.17 (0.118)
				5/12/93	1415	21.5 (0.609)
50125500	Río Naranjo near Lago Lucchetti Damsite, PR	Lat 18°06'20", long 66°51'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Naranjo on Hwy 128, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) from mouth, and 0.9 mi (1.4 km) from spillway.	1.92 (4.97)	4/01/93	1150	0.54 (0.015)
				5/12/93	1330	3.41 (0.097)
50125600	Quebrada Grande near Lago Lucchetti Damsite, PR	Lat 18°06'20", long 66°50'56", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Naranjo, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) west from Hacienda Roig, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) from mouth, and 1.3 mi (2.1 km) from spillway.	2.83 (7.33)	4/01/93	1105	1.11 (0.031)
				5/12/93	1255	4.79 (0.136)
50125860	Río Duey at Duey, PR	Lat 18°05'44", long 66°50'06", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Duey, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) southeast from Hacienda Roig, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) east of Lago Lucchetti, and 4.1 mi (6.6 km) from Plaza de Yauco.	4.55 (11.8)	4/01/93	1015	2.92 (0.083)
				5/12/93	1210	10.1 (0.286)
Río Loco basin						
50128450	Quebrada Grande upstream from Lago Loco, PR	Lat 18°03'45", long 66°53'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Barrio Almácigo Alto, 800 ft (244 m) upstream of confluence with Río Loco, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) north of spillway, and 3.0 mi (4.8 km) northwest from Plaza de Yauco.	2.72 (7.03)	4/01/93	0905	0.66 (0.019)
				5/12/93	1030	5.80 (0.164)
50128500	Río Loco upstream from Lago Loco, PR	Lat 18°03'22", long 66°53'08", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at barrio Susúa Alta, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from Lago Loco, 1.9 mi (3.0 km) northeast of Cerro La Torre, and 5.2 mi (8.4 km) southeast from Plaza de Sabana Grande.	7.66 (19.8)	4/01/93	0815	1.56 (0.044)
				5/12/93	1105	15.7 (0.445)
50129200	Quebrada Susúa at Palomas, PR	Lat 18°01'19", long 66°52'28", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at Highway 2 bridge, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) north of Palomas, and 1.9 mi (3.1 km) southwest of Yauco.	3.23 (8.37)	4/02/93	0835	0.24 (0.007)
				5/12/93	0945	0.46 (0.013)

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS
Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
Río Guanajibo basin						
50130400	Río Grande near Sabana Grande, PR	Lat 18°05'53", long 66°56'18", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Rin on Highway 364, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) northeast from Capilla del Pozo de la Virgen, and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) northeast from Plaza de Sabana Grande.	6.45	3/25/93	1410	1.52
			(16.7)	5/20/93	1330	(0.043) 4.74 (0.134)
50130500	Río Guanajibo at La Pica, PR	Lat 18°04'11", long 66°57'29", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Rayo on Highway 2, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) north from Cerro de los Bonelli, and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) southeast from Plaza de Sabana Grande.	14.7	3/25/93	1315	3.50
			(38.2)	5/20/93	1230	(0.099) 9.48 (0.268)
50130800	Río Flores near Sabana Grande, PR	Lat 18°04'02", long 66°58'25", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Santana on Highway 2, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) east from intersection of Highways 2 and 363, and 0.9 mi (1.4 km) west from Plaza de Sabana Grande.	1.98	3/25/93	1300	0.00
			(5.13)	5/20/93	1125	0.80 (0.023)
50131010	Río Cruces near Sabana Grande, PR	Lat 18°04'54", long 66°58'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Santana on Highway 2, 400 ft (122 m) west from intersection of Highways 2 and 363, 1.1 mi (1.8 km) west from Plaza de Sabana Grande.	4.68	3/25/93	1220	1.78
			(12.1)	5/20/93	1045	(0.050) 3.23 (0.091)
50131800	Río Cupeyes near San Germán, PR	Lat 18°04'48", long 67°00'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Guamá, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) downstream of Highway 2, and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) east from Plaza de San Germán.	4.16	3/25/93	1130	2.00
			(10.8)	5/20/93	1000	(0.057) 3.16 (0.089)
50132010	Río Guanajibo below San Germán, PR	Lat 18°05'28", long 67°02'38", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 1,500 ft (457 m) downstream from Highway 360 bridge, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) from Plaza de San Germán.	36.1	3/24/93	1240	8.30
			(93.5)	5/19/93	1345	(0.235) 19.1 (0.541)
50133000	Río Caín near San Germán, PR	Lat 18°06'06", long 67°02'26", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Caín on Highway 361, 600 ft (183 m) upstream from Highway 2, and 1.3 mi (2.1 km) north of Plaza de San Germán.	6.32	3/25/93	1040	0.82
			(16.4)	5/20/93	0915	(0.023) 1.05 (0.030)
50133800	Río Duey near Rosario, PR	Lat 18°08'57", long 67°03'15", Hydrologic unit 21010003, at Barrio Duey Alto, 200 ft (61 m) downstream from Highway 348, 100 ft (30 m) downstream from confluence with Río Nueve Pasos, and 2.0 mi (3.2 km) southeast from Plaza de Rosario.	4.17	3/23/93	1125	1.76
			(10.8)	5/18/93	1115	(0.050) 2.61 (0.074)
50134600	Río Hoconuco near San Germán, PR	Lat 18°07'08", long 67°04'27", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Hoconuco Bajo, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) downstream from Highway 358, 200 ft upstream from confluence with Río Duey, and 3.2 mi (5.1 km) northwest from Plaza de San Germán.	5.18	3/25/93	0940	1.07
			(13.4)	5/20/93	0830	(0.030) 0.81 (0.023)
50135000	Río Hoconuco (Duey) near San Germán, PR	Lat 18°07'10", long 67°04'48", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Duey Bajo, 200 ft (61 m) downstream of Highway 2, and 3.4 mi (5.5 km) northwest from San Germán Plaza.	13.2	3/24/93	1335	3.05
			(34.3)	5/18/93	1405	(0.086) 3.26 (0.092)

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
50135700	Río Maricao at Maricao, PR	Lat 18°11'22", long 66°59'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Maricao Afuera on Highway 357, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) east of Hacienda San Antonio, and 1.0 mi (1.6 km) northwest from Plaza de Maricao.	3.80 (9.85)	3/23/93	0905	3.66 (0.104)
				5/18/93	0900	7.08 (0.200)
50135800	Río Rosario at Las Vegas, PR	Lat 18°11'13", long 67°01'52", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Montoso on Highway 119, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) southeast from intersection of Highways 119 and 105, and 3.6 (5.8 km) northeast of Plaza de Rosario.	8.33 (21.6)	3/23/93	0805	8.35 (0.236)
				5/18/93	0800	20.0 (0.566)
50136400	Río Rosario near Hormigueros, PR	Lat 18°09'36", long 67°05'08", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at bridge on Highway 348, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) Southwest from Plaza de Rosario.	18.3 (47.4)	3/23/93	1230	13.8 (0.391)
				5/18/93	1220	35.3 (1.000)
50136500	Río Rosario at Hwy 2 near Hormigueros, PR	Lat 18°07'35", long 67°05'39", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Benavente on Highway 2, 2.7 mi (4.3 km) southwest of Rosario, and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) southeast from Plaza de Hormigueros.	22.8 (58.9)	3/23/93	1335	13.4 (0.379)
				5/18/93	1315	34.2 (0.968)
50137800	Río Viejo near Cabo Rojo, PR	Lat 18°06'04", long 67°07'48", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Bajura on Highway 103, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) northeast of intersection with Highway 102, and 1.4 mi (2.2 km) from Plaza de Cabo Rojo.	12.3 (31.9)	3/24/93	1055	2.69 (0.076)
				5/19/93	1205	1.66 (0.047)
Quebrada Maga basin						
50138100	Quebrada Maga near Guanajibo, PR	Lat 18°09'18", long 67°08'07", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Guanajibo, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) southeast from Mayagüez Mall, and 1.2 mi (1.9 km) northwest of Plaza de Hormigueros.	0.76 (1.96)	3/23/93	1500	0.00
				5/19/93	1500	0.00
Río Hondo basin						
50138200	Río Hondo near Guanajibo, PR	Lat 18°09'45", long 67°09'00", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Guanajibo on Highway 114, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) east of Cerro Cornelia, and 2.0 mi (3.2 km) northwest of Plaza de Hormigueros.	3.16 (8.18)	3/24/93	0805	1.42 (0.040)
				5/19/93	1015	0.93 (0.026)
Quebrada Sábalo basin						
50138300	Quebrada Sábalo near Mayagüez, PR	Lat 18°10'47", long 67°08'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Sábalo on Highway 2R, 2.9 mi (4.7 km) northwest of Hormigueros, and 1.7 mi (2.7 km) southwest of Plaza de Mayagüez.	2.47 (6.40)	3/24/93	0855	1.12 (0.032)
				5/19/93	0935	1.71 (0.048)
Río Yagüez basin						
50138900	Río Yagüez at Balboa, PR	Lat 18°12'13", long 67°07'55", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 1200 ft (366 m) upstream from bridge on Balboa St., and 1.6 mi (2.6 km) upstream from mouth.	12.2 (31.6)	3/23/93	0640	9.40 (0.266)
				5/19/93	0830	14.6 (0.413)

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS
Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
Río Grande de Añasco basin						
50140300	Río Guilarte near Adjuntas, PR	Lat 18°10'58", long 66°46'09", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Guilarte on Highway 131, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) southwest from intersection of Highways 130 and 131, and 4.3 mi (6.9 km) east of Castañer.	2.62 (6.78)	3/22/93	1300	2.73 (0.077)
				5/17/93	1200	4.19 (0.119)
50140800	Río Limani near Yahuecas, PR	Lat 18°12'01", long 66°47'50", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Yahuecas, 200 ft (61 m) upstream with Río Guilarte, and 500 ft (152 m) southwest from intersection of Highways 129 and 135.	7.38 (19.1)	3/22/93	1355	6.17 (0.175)
				5/17/93	1415	14.0 (0.396)
50141400	Río Guayo at Guayo, PR	Lat 18°10'49", long 66°49'40", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Guayo on Highway 131, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) upstream from Lago Guayo, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) southeast of Castañer.	4.15 (10.7)	3/22/93	1350	4.04 (0.114)
				5/17/93	1515	9.47 (0.268)
50142000	Río Blanco at La Torre, PR	Lat 18°18'34", long 66°51'49", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio La Torre on Highway 128, 2.7 mi (4.3 km) northwest from Lago Guayo, and 4.5 mi (7.2 km) northwest of Castañer.	33.2 (86.0)	3/22/93	0954	2.20 (0.062)
				5/17/93	0802	12.1 (0.343)
50142100	Quebrada de Los Plátanos at Marisol, PR	Lat 18°15'41", long 66°51'22", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Marisol on Highway 128, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) south from intersection of Highways 128 and 129.	0.57 (1.47)	3/23/93	0923	0.25 (0.007)
				5/18/93	0842	1.99 (0.056)
50142300	Río Prieto at Indiera Alta, PR	Lat 18°10'07", long 66°51'49", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Indiera Alta on Highway 128, 2.3 mi (3.7 km) southwest from Lago Guayo, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) southwest of Castañer.	7.47 (19.3)	3/23/93	0814	7.61 (0.216)
				5/18/93	0736	19.6 (0.555)
50142710	Río Prieto at Río Prieto, PR	Lat 18°12'06", long 66°53'05", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Río Prieto on Highway 431, 3.7 mi (5.6 km) west of Lago Guayo, and 6.4 mi (10 km) northeast of Plaza de Maricao.	15.1 (39.0)	3/22/93	0900	5.25 (0.149)
				5/17/93	0853	24.8 (0.702)
50142900	Río Prieto at Pezuela, PR	Lat 18°15'17", long 66°54'25", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Pezuela, 400 ft (122 m) upstream from confluence with Río Grande de Añasco, and 3.4 mi (5.5 km) southwest from Plaza de Lares.	26.1 (67.7)	3/22/93	1211	10.2 (0.289)
				5/17/93	0954	29.6 (0.838)
50143000	Río Grande de Añasco near Lares, PR	Lat 18°15'28", long 66°55'05", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at bridge on Highway 124, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) from confluence with Río Blanco and Río Prieto, and 3.7 mi (6.0 km) southwest from Plaza de Lares.	26.3 (68.1)	3/22/93	1112	17.7 (0.501)
				5/17/93	1026	64.8 (1.835)
50143104	Río Lajas near Maricao, PR	Lat 18°10'54", long 66°57'39", Hydrologic unit 21010003, at Barrio Indiera Fria on Highway 105, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) upstream from confluence with Río Guaba, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) from Plaza de Maricao.	5.79 (15.0)	3/24/93	0832	5.07 (0.144)
				5/19/93	0808	6.38 (0.181)

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
50143108	Río Guaba near Maricao, PR	Lat 18°11'02", long 66°57'30", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Bucarabones on Highway 105, 200 ft (61 m) upstream from confluence with Río Lajas, and 1.5 mi (2.4 km) from Plaza de Maricao.	4.95 (12.8)	3/24/93	0801	5.17 (0.146)
				5/19/93	0740	10.3 (0.292)
50143150	Río Bucarabones near Las Marías, PR	Lat 18°13'27", long 66°56'41", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Bucarabones, 400 ft (122 m) upstream from confluence with Río Guaba, and 3.7 mi (5.6 km) northeast from Plaza de Maricao.	9.19 (23.8)	3/23/93	1150	8.55 (0.242)
				5/19/93	0952	24.5 (0.694)
50143200	Río Guaba near Las Marías, PR	Lat 18°13'37", long 66°56'33", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Cerrote on Highway 124, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) downstream from confluence with Río Bucarabones, and 3.9 mi (6.3 km) northeast from Plaza de Maricao.	25.4 (65.7)	3/23/93	1227	15.7 (0.445)
				5/19/93	0918	46.6 (1.320)
50143400	Quebrada Las Cañas at Perchas, PR	Lat 18°16'23", long 66°56'36", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Perchas No 2 on Highway 434, 800 ft (244 m) upstream of confluence with Río Grande de Añasco, and 3.5 mi (5.6 km) from Plaza de Las Marías.	3.08 (7.98)	3/26/93	0756	7.56 (0.214)
				5/21/93	1040	13.2 (0.374)
50143500	Río Mayagüecilla at Las Marías, PR	Lat 18°14'50", long 66°59'05", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Palma Escrita on Highway 124, 2.0 mi (3.2 km) upstream of confluence with Río Grande de Añasco, and 0.7 mi (1.1 km) southeast of Plaza de Las Marías.	3.30 (8.54)	3/24/93	0935	1.70 (0.048)
				5/19/93	1031	9.19 (0.260)
50143800	Río Grande de Añasco near Las Marías, PR	Lat 18°16'41", long 66°58'48", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Guacío on Highway 119, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) northeast from Plaza de Las Marías.	116 (299)	3/22/93	1336	54.8 (1.552)
				5/17/93	1155	177 (5.013)
50143900	Río Arenas at Las Marías, PR	Lat 18°15'10", long 66°59'57", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Maravillas on Highway 119, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) southwest from Plaza de Las Marías.	2.79 (7.22)	3/24/93	1010	3.66 (0.104)
				5/19/93	1103	8.39 (0.238)
50144200	Quebrada Cerro Gordo near Cerro Gordo, PR	Lat 18°17'09", long 66°04'09", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Corcovada, 600 ft (183 m) upstream from confluence with Río Grande de Añasco, 5.7 mi (9.2 km) from Las Marías, and 4.8 mi (7.7 km) east from Plaza de Añasco.	2.66 (6.89)	3/23/93	1352	2.87 (0.081)
				5/18/93	1113	1.52 (0.043)
50144900	Río Humata near El Espino, PR	Lat 18°17'18", long 67°06'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Carreras on Highway 109, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) upstream from confluence with Río Grande de Añasco, and 2.4 mi (3.9 km) east from Plaza de Añasco.	4.86 (12.6)	3/26/93	0956	3.01 (0.085)
				5/20/93	0903	6.46 (0.183)
50145000	Río Grande de Añasco at El Espino, PR	Lat 18°16'50", long 67°06'46", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Espino on Highway 406, 400 ft (249 m) east from intersection of Highway 109, and 1.9 mi (3.1 km) from Plaza de Añasco.	108 (280-384)	3/22/93	1510	84.6 (2.396)
				5/17/93	1422	220 (6.230)

DISCHARGE AT PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

Low-flow partial-record stations--Continued

STATION NUMBER	STATION NAME	LOCATION AND BASIN	DRAINAGE AREA mi ² (km ²)	DATE	TIME	STREAM FLOWS ft ³ /s (m ³ /s)
50145400	Río Casei near Mayagüez, PR	Lat 18°15'18", long 67°04'48", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Legúisamo on Highway 108, 4.6 mi (7.4 km) northeast from Mayagüez, and 4.5 mi (7.2 km) southeast of Plaza de Mayagüez.	8.17 (21.2)	3/24/93	1206	8.07 (0.228)
				5/20/93	0730	22.4 (0.634)
50146000	Río Grande de Añasco at Añasco Arriba, PR	Lat 18°16'31", long 66°07'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010003. 0.8 mi (1.2 km) south of Añasco and 3.0 mi (4.8 km) from mouth.	161 (416)	3/22/93	1545	95.5 (2.704)
				5/21/93	0847	207 (5.862)
50146002	Río Cañas at Río Cañas Arriba, PR	Lat 18°13'37", long 67°04'01", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Cañas Arriba on Highway 354, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) south of intersection with Highway 355, and 5.1 mi (8.2 km) from Plaza de Mayagüez.	3.58 (9.26)	3/24/93	1100	3.11 (0.088)
				5/19/93	1216	8.54 (0.242)
50146005	Río Cañas at Río Cañas Abajo, PR	Lat 18°14'38", long 67°07'17", Hydrologic Unit, 21010003, at Barrio Río Cañas Abajo on Highway 108, and 3.1 mi (5.0 km) northeast from Plaza de Mayagüez.	11.2 (29.1)	3/24/93	1248	2.70 (0.076)
				5/20/93	0840	11.2 (0.317)
50146075	Río Dagüey near Añasco, PR	Lat 18°17'19", long 67°08'08", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Carreras on Highway 405, 100 ft (30 m) east from intersection with Highway 404, and 0.5 mi (0.8 km) northeast from Mayagüez Plaza.	1.06 (2.75)	3/23/93	1500	0.40 (0.011)
				5/18/93	1206	0.47 (0.013)
Río Grande basin						
50146200	Río Grande near Rincón, PR	Lat 18°22'06", long 67°13'56", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at bridge on Highway 115, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) from mouth, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northeast of Rincón.	2.83 (7.33)	3/25/93	1013	0.47 (0.013)
				5/20/93	1005	0.69 (0.020)
Río Ingenio basin						
50146300	Río Ingenio at Jagüey, PR	Lat 18°20'36", long 67°11'52", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at Barrio Jagüey, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) from Highway 411 intersection, and 2.7 mi (4.3 km) southwest from Plaza de Aguada.	3.18 (8.22)	3/25/93	1120	1.78 (0.050)
				5/20/93	1115	2.21 (0.062)
50146400	Río Ingenio near Aguada, PR	Lat 18°22'48", long 67°12'35", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at bridge on unimproved road, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) upstream from confluence with Río Culebra, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) from mouth of Río Guayabo, and 1.4 mi (2.3 km) west of Aguada.	7.00 (18.1)	3/25/93	1045	2.81 (0.080)
				5/20/93	1030	2.89 (0.082)
Río Culebra basin						
50146600	Río Culebra near Aguada, PR	Lat 18°22'26", long 67°11'35", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at bridge on Highway 411, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) south of Aguada, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) upstream from confluence with Río Ingenio, and 1.9 mi (3.1 km) from mouth of Río Guayabo.	3.75 (9.70)	3/25/93	1202	1.94 (0.055)
				5/20/93	1158	3.69 (0.104)

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**Water-Quality at
Partial-Record Stations
in Puerto Rico**

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATION

Water-quality partial-record stations are particular sites where chemical-quality, biological and or sediment data are collected systematically over a period of years for use in hydrological analysis. The data are collected usually less than quarterly.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	DEPTH AT SAMPLE LOC- ATION, TOTAL (FEET)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TRANS- PAR- ENCY (SECCHI DISK) (IN)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED CENT SATUR- ATION)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, (PER- 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN									
50010720	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.3 NR MOUTH NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°22'05"N LONG 066°54'36"W)								
NOV 1992 22...	0740	1.00	274	7.1	26.0	104	5.8	71	K12
MAR 1993 17...	0840	1.00	254	7.6	26.5	19.0	11.6	150	230
JUL 21...	0835	1.00	293	7.7	28.0	76.0	5.9	76	410
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN									
50025110	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.3 AT WEST BRANCH NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°19'15"N LONG 066°40'11"W)								
NOV 1992 20...	0940	1.00	235	6.6	26.0	17.0	2.5	31	91
MAR 1993 13...	0910	1.00	252	7.3	26.0	22.0	5.1	62	200
JUL 24...	0855	1.00	231	6.9	28.5	26.0	7.1	84	70
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN									
50039900	LAGO CARITE NO.3 ON RIO DE LA PLATA NR CAYEY, PR (LAT 18°05'04"N LONG 066°06'03"W)								
NOV 1992 19...	0945	1.00	113	6.6	24.5	91.0	6.9	86	K7
MAR 1993 18...	0940	1.00	116	6.5	23.5	71.0	7.5	93	36
JUL 22...	0850	1.00	503	7.1	27.0	54.0	8.1	100	40
50044400	LAGO LA PLATA NO.5 NR MOUTH NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°19'33"N LONG 066°12'28"W)								
NOV 1992 18...	0845	1.00	280	6.9	25.5	12.0	6.8	82	270
MAR 1993 12...	0850	1.00	388	7.9	26.0	37.0	6.1	75	K2
JUL 16...	0850	1.00	374	7.7	29.0	18.0	7.6	97	K15
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN									
50057500	LAGO LOIZA NO.4 NR MOUTH NR CAGUAS, PR (LAT 18°16'51"N LONG 066°00'35"W)								
NOV 1992 14...	0935	1.00	247	6.6	25.5	12.0	3.5	42	K1100
MAR 1993 11...	1120	1.00	360	7.6	27.5	36.0	8.2	100	K1900
JUL 17...	0945	1.00	315	6.7	30.0	43.0	4.9	64	84

K = non-ideal count

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATION

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	ALKA- LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD MG/L AS CACO3	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDEE (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--Continued								
50010720	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.3 NR MOUTH NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°22'05"N LONG 066°54'36"W)							
NOV 1992 22...	33	--	1	--	<0.010	<0.050	0.030	0.37
MAR 1993 17...	120	--	3	--	<0.010	<0.050	0.010	0.49
JUL 21...	33	--	20	--	<0.010	0.920	0.020	--
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--Continued								
50025110	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.3 AT WEST BRANCH NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°19'15"N LONG 066°40'11"W)							
NOV 1992 20...	44	--	3	0.430	0.050	0.480	0.130	0.37
MAR 1993 13...	40	--	<1	0.520	0.030	0.550	0.050	0.25
JUL 24...	310	--	16	0.300	0.020	0.320	0.020	0.58
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--Continued								
50039900	LAGO CARITE NO.3 ON RIO DE LA PLATA NR CAYEY, PR (LAT 18°05'04"N LONG 066°06'03"W)							
NOV 1992 19...	40	--	2	--	<0.010	0.098	0.030	0.27
MAR 1993 18...	41	--	1	--	<0.010	0.075	0.010	--
JUL 22...	41	--	14	--	<0.010	<0.050	0.010	0.29
50044400	LAGO LA PLATA NO.5 NR MOUTH NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°19'33"N LONG 066°12'28"W)							
NOV 1992 18...	410	--	2	0.430	0.050	0.480	0.010	0.59
MAR 1993 12...	K2	--	<1	--	<0.010	<0.050	<0.010	--
JUL 16...	--	--	26	--	<0.010	<0.050	0.030	0.47
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--Continued								
50057500	LAGO LOIZA NO.4 NR MOUTH NR CAGUAS, PR (LAT 18°16'51"N LONG 066°00'35"W)							
NOV 1992 14...	K110	--	10	0.450	0.090	0.540	0.700	0.50
MAR 1993 11...	K96	--	<1	0.320	0.100	0.420	1.30	0.90
JUL 17...	50	--	20	0.320	0.130	0.450	0.850	0.45

K = non-ideal count

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATION

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHORUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	CHLOR-A PHYTO- PLANK- TON CHROMO FLUOROM (UG/L)	CHLOR-B PHYTO- PLANK- TON CHROMO FLUOROM (UG/L)	PLANK- TON BIOMASS ASH WT (MG/L)	PLANK- TON BIOMASS DRY WT (MG/L)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--Continued								
50010720	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.3 NR MOUTH NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°22'05"N LONG 066°54'36"W)							
NOV 1992								
22...	0.40	--	--	0.030	4.50	<0.100	230	240
MAR 1993								
17...	0.50	--	--	0.020	10.0	1.40	280	290
JUL								
21...	<0.20	--	--	<0.010	7.60	0.100	240	250
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--Continued								
50025110	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.3 AT WEST BRANCH NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°19'15"N LONG 066°40'11"W)							
NOV 1992								
20...	0.50	0.98	4.3	0.040	2.70	<0.100	250	250
MAR 1993								
13...	0.30	0.85	3.8	0.010	3.30	<0.100	250	260
JUL								
24...	0.60	0.92	4.1	0.050	13.0	0.600	250	260
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--Continued								
50039900	LAGO CARITE NO.3 ON RIO DE LA PLATA NR CAYEY, PR (LAT 18°05'04"N LONG 066°06'03"W)							
NOV 1992								
19...	0.30	0.40	1.8	0.010	16.0	4.00	220	220
MAR 1993								
18...	<0.20	--	--	<0.010	4.80	1.20	240	240
JUL								
22...	0.30	--	--	0.020	8.90	0.600	400	410
50044400	LAGO LA PLATA NO.5 NR MOUTH NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°19'33"N LONG 066°12'28"W)							
NOV 1992								
18...	0.60	1.1	4.8	0.210	42.0	<0.100	230	240
MAR 1993								
12...	0.40	--	--	0.040	15.0	1.50	250	260
JUL								
16...	0.50	--	--	0.100	3.70	<0.100	250	260
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--Continued								
50057500	LAGO LOIZA NO.4 NR MOUTH NR CAGUAS, PR (LAT 18°16'51"N LONG 066°00'35"W)							
NOV 1992								
14...	1.2	1.7	7.7	0.340	1.60	<0.100	270	280
MAR 1993								
11...	2.2	2.6	12	0.540	38.0	<0.100	260	260
JUL								
17...	1.3	1.7	7.7	0.390	2.10	0.700	260	260

MISCELLANEOUS STATION ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	DEPTH AT SAMPLE LOC- ATION, TOTAL (FEET)	SPE- CIFIC CON- DUCT- ANCE (US/CM)	PH WATER WHOLE FIELD (STAND- ARD UNITS)	TEMPER- ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TRANS- PAR- ENCY (SECCHI DISK (IN)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (PER- CENT SATUR- ATION)	OXYGEN, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	COLI- FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR. (COLS. PER 100 ML)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--Continued										
50010790 LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°23'56"N LONG 066°55'23"W)										
NOV 1992										
22...	0820	1.00	<274	7.4	26.5	178	6.0	74	K2	K4
22...	0805	84.0	261	6.6	24.5	--	0.1	--	--	--
MAR 1993										
17...	0910	1.00	264	7.8	25.5	28.0	7.8	90	54	78
17...	0915	64.0	316	6.8	24.5	--	0.1	--	--	--
JUL										
21...	0920	1.00	284	8.3	28.5	60.0	8.0	100	76	10
21...	0925	63.0	324	7.1	26.5	--	2.0	21	--	--
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--Continued										
50020050 LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS, PR (LAT 18°08'21"N LONG 066°44'35"W)										
NOV 1992										
21...	1045	1.00	156	6.8	23.0	54.0	6.5	81	20	27
21...	1040	79.0	183	6.2	20.5	--	0.1	2	--	--
MAR 1993										
16...	1055	1.00	157	7.1	24.0	44.0	7.9	100	92	76
16...	1050	67.0	159	6.4	20.0	--	0.1	1	--	--
JUL										
21...	1410	1.00	229	7.7	25.0	104	5.2	67	K300	K10
21...	1415	77.0	139	6.8	21.9	--	2.0	7	--	--
50027090 LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°20'09"N LONG 066°40'04"W)										
NOV 1992										
20...	1010	1.00	215	6.7	27.0	60.0	3.2	40	54	K11
20...	1000	64.0	225	6.3	25.5	--	0.1	1	--	--
MAR 1993										
13...	0945	1.00	250	8.1	26.0	64.0	7.9	97	20	74
13...	1010	72.0	218	6.5	24.0	--	0.1	72	--	--
JUL										
24...	0935	1.00	223	6.8	28.5	44.0	7.6	96	30	K1200
24...	0930	72.0	235	6.9	26.5	--	2.6	--	--	--
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--Continued										
50039950 LAGO CARITE NO.1 NR DAM NR CAYEY, P.R. (LAT 18°04'39"N LONG 066°06'19"W)										
NOV 1992										
19...	1035	1.00	113	6.7	24.5	65.0	7.1	89	44	46
19...	1030	62.0	178	6.0	22.5	--	0.1	1	--	--
MAR 1993										
18...	1030	1.00	114	7.3	23.5	80.0	8.4	100	K8	K18
18...	1025	49.0	72	6.0	21.0	--	0.0	--	--	--
JUL										
22...	0925	1.00	558	7.2	27.0	28.0	7.7	100	15	400
22...	0920	52.0	319	6.4	25.5	--	0.0	--	--	--
50044950 LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°20'18"N LONG 066°14'01"W)										
NOV 1992										
18...	0920	1.00	309	6.6	26.0	24.0	3.2	39	40	K680
18...	0910	68.0	305	5.8	24.0	--	0.1	1	--	--
MAR 1993										
12...	0930	1.00	306	7.7	<27.0	64.0	7.2	90	K4	14
12...	0935	48.0	158	6.7	22.5	--	0.1	--	--	--
JUL										
16...	0935	1.00	310	7.5	29.5	41.0	6.5	62	10	18
16...	0930	27.0	215	6.7	24.5	--	0.4	--	--	--
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--Continued										
50058800 LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18°19'29"N LONG 066°00'47"W)										
NOV 1992										
14...	0855	1.00	140	6.2	25.5	4.00	2.7	33	600	970
14...	0840	40.0	113	5.8	24.0	--	0.3	4	--	--
MAR 1993										
11...	1030	1.00	338	7.2	27.0	41.0	5.6	70	10	30
11...	1040	39.0	337	7.0	26.0	--	0.1	--	--	--
JUL										
17...	0850	1.00	266	7.0	29.5	48.0	4.8	32	210	770
17...	0835	42.0	215	6.4	27.4	--	0.2	--	--	--

K = non-ideal count

MISCELLANEOUS STATION ANALYSES

DATE	HARD- NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD- NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT PLD MG/L AS CACO3	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD MG/L AS CACO3	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--Continued									
50010790	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°23'56"N LONG 066°55'23"W)								
NOV 1992									
22...	130	7	45	3.3	4.6	0.2	1.8	120	8.9
22...	140	6	49	3.4	5.3	0.2	2.0	130	8.5
MAR 1993									
17...	150	12	54	3.9	7.1	0.3	1.8	120	10
17...	130	6	45	3.7	6.2	0.2	1.8	140	13
JUL									
21...	120	9	42	3.6	5.5	0.2	1.8	120	10
21...	160	7	57	3.1	4.6	0.2	1.6	120	10
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--Continued									
50020050	LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS, PR (LAT 18°08'21"N LONG 066°44'35"W)								
NOV 1992									
21...	68	0	19	4.9	6.5	0.3	1.7	50	<0.10
21...	63	0	18	4.5	6.0	0.3	1.3	43	3.1
MAR 1993									
16...	60	0	17	4.3	6.8	0.4	1.6	72	2.6
16...	61	0	17	4.5	6.0	0.3	1.5	70	2.7
JUL									
21...	62	0	17	4.7	5.9	0.3	1.3	80	3.1
21...	61	0	17	4.4	5.1	0.3	1.8	80	1.4
50027090	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°20'09"N LONG 066°40'04"W)								
NOV 1992									
20...	--	3	<0.02	<0.01	<0.20	0.5	2.6	74	13
20...	80	6	22	6.2	11	0.5	2.4	75	13
MAR 1993									
13...	95	3	26	7.4	13	0.6	2.4	72	15
13...	80	2	22	6.1	10	0.5	2.9	70	12
JUL									
24...	76	2	20	6.3	10	0.5	2.3	80	12
24...	85	--	23	6.8	11	0.5	2.1	80	14
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--Continued									
50039950	LAGO CARITE NO.1 NR DAM NR CAYEY, P.R. (LAT 18°04'39"N LONG 066°06'19"W)								
NOV 1992									
19...	40	0	9.3	4.1	8.7	0.6	1.3	27	0.20
19...	32	0	6.7	3.7	9.2	0.7	1.5	30	2.9
MAR 1993									
18...	30	0	7.5	2.8	7.7	0.6	0.80	19	2.5
18...	30	0	6.4	3.5	8.5	0.7	0.90	30	2.6
JUL									
22...	29	0	6.2	3.3	6.0	0.5	0.90	38	0.70
22...	30	0	5.7	3.8	8.5	0.7	0.80	40	2.8
50044950	LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°20'18"N LONG 066°14'01"W)								
NOV 1992									
18...	120	0	28	11	14	0.6	3.2	76	4.3
18...	120	0	29	12	19	0.7	2.5	110	15
MAR 1993									
12...	120	6	29	11	17	0.7	2.9	89	13
12...	56	1	14	5.1	9.2	0.5	2.2	43	8.2
JUL									
16...	73	5	18	6.8	12	0.6	2.6	140	10
16...	100	1	25	10	16	0.7	2.4	150	17
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--Continued									
50058800	LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18°19'29"N LONG 066°00'47"W)								
NOV 1992									
14...	32	7	8.9	2.4	7.9	0.6	2.8	71	7.3
14...	34	0	9.0	2.8	9.1	0.7	3.0	63	9.3
MAR 1993									
11...	110	1	27	10	28	1	2.9	50	18
11...	110	1	27	10	27	1	3.0	44	18
JUL									
17...	78	3	18	7.0	18	0.9	2.4	98	12
17...	87	0	21	8.5	22	1	3.4	92	15

MISCELLANEOUS STATION ANALYSES

DATE	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI- TUENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDEd (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--Continued									
50010790	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°23'56"N LONG 066°55'23"W)								
NOV 1992									
22...	8.6	0.10	6.3	164	1	--	<0.010	<0.050	0.030
22...	7.4	0.10	6.3	153	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1993									
17...	10	0.10	3.7	150	5	--	<0.010	<0.050	0.010
17...	10	0.10	7.2	182	--	--	--	--	--
JUL									
21...	11	0.10	1.3	142	50	--	<0.010	<0.050	<0.010
21...	9.6	0.10	4.9	181	--	--	--	--	--
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--Continued									
50020050	LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS, PR (LAT 18°08'21"N LONG 066°44'35"W)								
NOV 1992									
21...	6.9	<0.10	17	100	3	--	<0.010	<0.050	0.040
21...	6.6	<0.10	20	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1993									
16...	6.4	<0.10	12	88	2	--	<0.010	<0.050	0.020
16...	6.4	<0.10	17	94	--	--	--	--	--
JUL									
21...	6.3	<0.10	15	92	--	--	--	--	--
21...	7.2	<0.10	16	97	24	--	<0.010	<0.050	0.030
50027090	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°20'09"N LONG 066°40'04"W)								
NOV 1992									
20...	10	0.10	21	137	1	0.320	0.040	0.360	0.070
20...	11	0.10	22	--	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1993									
13...	16	0.20	21	154	<1	0.280	0.020	0.300	<0.010
13...	13	0.10	19	126	--	--	--	--	--
JUL									
24...	13	0.10	21	138	11	0.210	0.010	0.220	0.010
24...	11	<0.10	20	124	--	--	--	--	--
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--Continued									
50039950	LAGO CARITE NO.1 NR DAM NR CAYEY, P.R. (LAT 18°04'39"N LONG 066°06'19"W)								
NOV 1992									
19...	9.9	<0.10	19	74	9	--	<0.010	<0.050	0.030
19...	10	0.20	20	87	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1993									
18...	9.3	<0.10	17	69	<1	--	<0.010	0.064	<0.010
18...	8.0	<0.10	15	60	--	--	--	--	--
JUL									
22...	9.8	<0.10	15	67	14	--	<0.010	<0.050	0.010
22...	7.9	<0.10	11	58	--	--	--	--	--
50044950	LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°20'18"N LONG 066°14'01"W)								
NOV 1992									
18...	23	<0.10	19	193	1	--	<0.010	<0.050	0.020
18...	19	0.10	20	178	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1993									
12...	21	0.20	14	176	<1	--	<0.010	<0.050	<0.010
12...	12	0.10	14	91	--	--	--	--	--
JUL									
16...	23	0.20	16	172	18	--	<0.010	<0.050	0.030
16...	15	0.10	15	121	--	--	--	--	--
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--Continued									
50058800	LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18°19'29"N LONG 066°00'47"W)								
NOV 1992									
14...	11	<0.10	15	80	2	0.430	0.250	0.680	0.140
14...	9.1	<0.10	11	65	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1993									
11...	29	0.20	21	200	5	0.170	0.040	0.210	0.050
11...	28	0.10	22	200	--	--	--	--	--
JUL									
17...	21	0.20	23	148	20	0.120	0.140	0.260	0.040
17...	20	0.1	25	170	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS
 WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--Continued										
50010790		LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°23'56"N LONG 066°55'23"W)								
JUL 21...	0920	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--Continued										
50020050		LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS, PR (LAT 18°08'21"N LONG 066°44'35"W)								
JUL 21...	1410	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010
50027090		LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°20'09"N LONG 066°40'04"W)								
JUL 24...	0935	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--Continued										
50044950		LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°20'18"N LONG 066° 01W)								
JUL 16...	0935	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA--Continued										
50058800		LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18°19'29"N LONG 066°00'47"W)								
JUL 17...	0850	<0.1	<0.010	<0.1	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	0.02	<0.010	<0.010

PESTICIDE ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS
 WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	ENDRIN WATER UNPLTRD REC (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--Continued									
50010790	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS,PR (LAT 18°23'56"N LONG 066°55'23"W)								
JUL 21...	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--Continued									
50020050	LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS,PR (LAT 18°08'21"N LONG 066°44'35"W)								
JUL 21...	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
50027090	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO,PR (LAT 18°20'09"N LONG 066°40'04"W)								
JUL 24...	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--Continued									
50044950	LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°20'18"N LONG 066° 01W)								
JUL 16...	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA--Continued									
50058800	LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18°19'29"N LONG 066°00'47"W)								
JUL 17...	<0.010	<0.01	<0.010	<0.010	<0.010	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

PESTICIDE ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS
 WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2, 4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--Continued									
50010790	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°23'56"N LONG 066°55'23"W)								
JUL 21...	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01	0.06	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--Continued									
50020050	LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS, PR (LAT 18°08'21"N LONG 066°44'35"W)								
JUL 21...	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01	0.06	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
50027090	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°20'09"N LONG 066°40'04"W)								
JUL 24...	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--Continued									
50044950	LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°20'18"N LONG 066° 01W)								
JUL 16...	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA--Continued									
50058800	LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18°19'29"N LONG 066°00'47"W)								
JUL 17...	<0.01	<0.10	<0.1	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

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**Ground-Water Records
for Puerto Rico**

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

182422067015100. Local number, 165.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'22", long 67°01'51", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 5.60 mi northeast of Moca plaza, 4.70 mi southeast of Aguadilla U.S. Naval Reservation radio antenna, and 1.63 mi northwest of La Virgen del Rosario Church. Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Saltos # 1 (Mateo Pérez).

AQUIFER.--Cibao Formation, Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled production water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.40 m), cased 16 in (0.40 m) 0-40 ft (0-12.2 m), cased 12 in (0.30 m) 40-200 ft (12.2-61.0 m). Depth 200 ft (61.0 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 689 ft (210 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Hole on pump base, 0.80 ft (0.24 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to November 1985, hole on top of pump base, 1.00 ft (0.30 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Formerly published as 182421067015000.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1982 to March 1985, November 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 38.36 ft (11.7 m) below land-surface datum, July 12, 1993; lowest water level measured, 70.60 ft (21.52 m) below land-surface datum, June 18, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	38.78	38.89	38.73	38.69	38.59	38.66	38.73	38.78	38.48	38.62	39.83	40.38
2	38.78	38.89	38.76	38.69	38.59	38.68	38.76	38.80	38.56	38.57	39.73	40.33
3	38.87	38.94	38.77	38.73	38.66	38.74	38.77	38.79	38.58	38.56	40.04	40.44
4	38.88	38.92	38.77	38.77	38.69	38.76	38.73	38.78	38.59	38.57	40.39	40.40
5	38.85	38.91	38.77	38.78	38.68	38.71	38.69	38.78	38.62	38.56	40.11	40.20
6	38.86	38.91	38.78	38.77	38.66	38.71	38.70	38.72	38.63	38.52	40.20	40.15
7	38.87	38.91	38.80	38.81	38.66	38.77	38.68	38.58	38.63	38.50	40.43	40.34
8	38.88	38.92	38.76	38.78	38.68	38.77	38.68	38.65	38.55	38.45	40.66	40.35
9	38.91	38.94	38.69	38.72	38.70	38.73	38.74	38.68	38.62	38.57	41.07	40.36
10	38.90	38.97	38.69	38.79	38.71	38.73	38.70	38.67	38.64	38.54	41.06	40.70
11	38.88	38.97	38.67	38.80	38.69	38.73	38.70	38.68	38.63	38.49	41.08	40.59
12	38.85	38.93	38.66	38.79	38.67	38.74	38.72	38.62	38.63	38.40	41.21	40.70
13	38.87	38.93	38.69	38.78	38.63	38.70	38.69	38.59	38.61	38.51	41.23	40.55
14	38.92	38.91	38.67	38.76	38.66	38.77	38.71	38.65	38.59	38.50	40.97	40.66
15	38.93	38.89	38.66	38.75	38.68	38.82	38.77	38.66	38.60	38.41	40.72	40.68
16	38.87	38.88	38.67	38.68	38.68	38.82	38.80	38.69	38.64	38.65	40.88	40.75
17	38.84	38.88	38.65	38.72	38.69	38.76	38.76	38.65	38.64	39.04	40.69	40.81
18	38.82	38.84	38.65	38.80	38.64	38.74	38.72	38.62	38.63	39.41	40.60	40.71
19	38.85	38.80	38.69	38.75	38.65	38.75	38.68	38.56	38.65	39.56	40.49	40.58
20	38.91	38.86	38.67	38.72	38.69	38.74	38.70	38.55	38.62	39.39	40.38	40.54
21	38.95	38.85	38.70	38.72	38.79	38.76	38.74	38.59	38.74	39.94	40.33	40.72
22	38.89	38.88	38.73	38.70	38.73	38.80	38.70	38.58	38.71	39.64	40.15	40.75
23	38.80	38.87	38.75	38.70	38.66	38.82	38.71	38.54	38.71	39.48	40.07	40.92
24	38.85	38.88	38.73	38.71	38.66	38.77	38.75	38.48	38.71	40.16	40.06	40.94
25	38.88	38.89	38.75	38.68	38.68	38.75	38.75	38.46	38.87	39.89	40.02	41.04
26	38.95	38.87	38.75	38.64	38.70	38.73	38.67	38.45	38.82	39.64	39.94	41.05
27	38.92	38.78	38.75	38.59	38.69	38.73	38.66	38.47	38.70	39.50	39.85	41.21
28	38.88	38.73	38.73	38.66	38.68	38.70	38.66	38.59	38.69	39.72	39.98	41.09
29	38.88	38.78	38.65	38.67	---	38.71	38.66	38.58	38.66	39.61	40.03	40.94
30	38.90	38.78	38.60	38.67	---	38.70	38.76	38.54	38.62	39.49	40.09	40.91
31	38.91	---	38.66	38.65	---	38.72	---	38.48	---	40.06	40.24	---
MEAN	38.88	38.88	38.71	38.72	38.67	38.74	38.72	38.62	38.65	39.06	40.40	40.66

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 39.06 HIGHEST 38.36 JULY 12, 1993 LOWEST 41.42 AUG. 12, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

182647066552400. Local number, 202.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'47", long 66°55'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 2.22 mi southeast of Quebradillas plaza, 1.29 mi north of Escuela José de Diego, and 1.99 mi northwest of El Calvario Church. Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Carmelo Barreto Garcia well.
 AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-296 ft (0-90.2 m), diameter 13 in (0.33 m), cased 13 in (0.33 m) 0-550 ft (0-167.6 m), perforated 270-529 ft (82.3-161.2 m). Depth 550 ft (167.6 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 475 ft (145 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.50 ft (0.46 m) above land-surface datum. Prior July 25, 1986, top of shelter floor, 3.30 ft (1.00 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1985 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 409.17 ft (124.71 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 25, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 452.80 ft (138.01 m) below land-surface datum, June 26, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	445.10	445.49	446.27	---	444.43	443.69	444.54	441.70	431.63	428.29	427.91	428.74
2	445.05	445.55	446.25	---	444.40	443.72	444.55	441.14	431.42	428.24	427.94	428.79
3	445.01	445.59	446.21	---	444.39	443.74	444.53	440.65	431.26	428.22	427.99	428.82
4	444.95	445.62	446.19	---	444.36	443.77	444.51	440.24	431.07	428.19	427.99	428.82
5	444.93	445.63	---	---	444.27	443.79	444.48	439.78	430.90	428.17	427.99	428.85
6	444.89	445.65	---	445.50	444.21	443.81	444.48	439.30	430.72	428.11	427.99	428.92
7	444.86	445.68	---	445.35	444.15	443.86	444.48	438.86	430.54	428.09	427.99	428.97
8	444.85	445.71	---	445.23	444.07	443.87	444.48	438.36	430.37	428.05	428.04	429.01
9	444.83	445.74	---	445.18	444.00	443.90	444.48	437.79	430.21	428.05	428.04	429.03
10	444.82	445.78	---	445.03	443.93	443.92	444.41	437.31	430.07	428.03	428.06	429.02
11	444.81	445.83	446.19	444.94	443.86	443.96	444.37	436.90	429.91	428.00	428.11	429.01
12	444.80	445.85	446.20	444.85	443.84	443.99	444.32	436.52	429.81	427.96	428.14	428.99
13	444.82	445.90	446.22	444.79	443.79	444.02	444.21	436.17	429.65	427.99	428.17	428.98
14	444.84	445.94	446.23	444.70	443.76	444.06	444.17	435.87	429.55	427.95	428.20	428.98
15	444.88	445.97	446.25	444.64	443.73	444.11	444.06	435.59	429.43	427.92	428.20	428.94
16	444.88	446.02	446.26	444.58	443.68	444.14	443.96	435.33	429.34	427.91	428.26	428.94
17	444.93	446.05	446.26	444.57	443.67	444.14	443.83	435.04	429.25	427.92	428.25	428.92
18	444.95	446.09	---	444.53	443.63	444.18	443.73	434.74	429.15	427.94	428.31	428.90
19	444.99	---	---	444.48	443.64	444.21	443.62	434.51	429.10	427.88	428.35	428.90
20	445.03	---	---	444.47	443.63	444.22	443.55	434.27	429.00	427.91	428.37	428.94
21	445.10	446.07	---	444.46	443.66	444.26	443.46	434.05	428.90	427.89	428.42	428.95
22	445.14	446.18	---	444.44	443.62	444.32	443.36	433.80	428.82	427.87	428.42	428.97
23	445.18	446.20	---	444.44	443.60	444.36	443.26	433.55	428.74	427.89	428.43	428.99
24	445.28	446.23	---	444.42	443.62	444.38	443.15	433.32	428.70	427.91	428.47	429.00
25	445.29	446.23	---	444.42	443.66	444.40	443.02	433.11	428.64	427.89	428.54	429.04
26	445.34	446.24	---	444.41	443.66	444.43	442.85	432.89	428.58	427.84	428.54	429.07
27	445.34	446.29	---	444.41	443.65	444.45	442.74	432.66	428.49	427.87	428.55	429.10
28	445.35	446.27	---	444.45	443.67	444.48	442.64	432.47	428.46	427.88	428.59	429.11
29	445.40	446.28	---	444.45	---	444.50	442.46	432.26	428.41	427.91	428.61	429.15
30	445.43	446.29	---	444.47	---	444.53	442.21	432.03	428.32	427.93	428.64	429.19
31	445.45	---	---	444.45	---	444.54	---	431.82	---	427.93	428.68	---
MEAN	445.05	445.94	446.23	444.68	443.88	444.12	443.80	435.87	429.61	427.99	428.26	428.97

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 438.10 HIGHEST 427.82 JULY 26, 1993 LOWEST 446.34 NOV. 30, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

182737066370900. Local number, 204.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'37", long 66°37'09", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 5.26 mi west of Barceloneta plaza, 1.58 mi north of Hwy 2 km 63.7, and 3.67 mi southwest of Escuela Agustín Balseiro. Owner: Sucesión Marquez, Name: Gilberto Rivera well.

AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Abandoned unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 48.0 ft (14.63 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Air hole on pump base, 0.50 ft (0.15 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 50.00 ft (15.24 m) below land-surface datum, May 14, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 52.56 ft (16.0 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 26, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	52.13	52.14	52.05	51.94	52.09	52.27	52.27	52.14	52.30	52.39	52.12	51.97
2	52.14	52.11	52.07	51.95	52.07	52.26	52.28	52.13	52.28	52.36	52.10	51.96
3	52.14	52.06	52.07	51.95	52.07	52.24	52.30	52.14	52.33	52.31	52.08	51.95
4	52.14	51.98	52.10	51.99	52.08	52.25	52.28	52.22	52.36	52.28	52.09	51.97
5	52.14	51.96	52.11	52.02	52.05	52.26	52.24	52.24	52.39	52.23	52.08	51.98
6	52.12	51.94	52.11	52.02	52.03	52.25	52.21	52.25	52.39	52.21	52.07	51.98
7	52.12	51.97	52.11	52.04	52.03	52.27	52.21	52.15	52.38	52.21	52.07	51.99
8	52.08	51.98	52.10	52.05	52.05	52.31	52.22	52.10	52.37	52.21	52.09	52.02
9	52.06	52.07	52.08	52.04	52.08	52.27	52.27	52.11	52.36	52.20	52.09	52.09
10	52.05	52.11	52.08	52.06	52.15	52.24	52.31	52.14	52.37	52.21	52.08	52.11
11	52.09	52.10	52.09	52.07	52.21	52.23	52.31	52.19	52.37	52.22	52.11	52.11
12	52.12	52.07	52.09	52.10	52.21	52.24	52.31	52.21	52.36	52.20	52.12	52.08
13	52.13	52.03	52.09	52.11	52.20	52.26	52.29	52.22	52.34	52.19	52.13	52.03
14	52.14	51.92	52.05	52.13	52.16	52.25	52.29	52.21	52.32	52.22	52.12	51.97
15	52.14	51.92	52.02	52.18	52.15	52.27	52.29	52.20	52.29	52.24	52.10	51.92
16	52.13	51.91	51.99	52.19	52.14	52.28	52.31	52.18	52.26	52.22	52.07	51.86
17	52.08	51.91	51.99	52.18	52.16	52.36	52.33	52.18	52.31	52.19	51.97	51.84
18	52.07	---	52.00	52.19	52.18	52.30	52.35	52.18	52.33	52.15	51.95	51.85
19	52.06	---	52.01	52.21	52.15	52.25	52.32	52.23	52.37	52.11	51.94	51.88
20	52.06	51.92	52.04	52.22	52.16	52.27	52.29	52.21	52.32	52.10	51.96	51.95
21	52.10	51.91	52.07	52.24	52.19	52.27	52.29	52.16	52.34	52.08	51.97	51.99
22	52.09	51.90	52.07	52.25	52.24	52.33	52.33	52.14	52.28	52.07	51.96	52.03
23	52.08	51.93	52.10	52.31	52.29	52.34	52.32	52.14	52.25	52.06	52.00	52.02
24	52.07	51.95	52.13	52.29	52.28	52.36	52.35	52.14	52.27	52.07	52.00	52.01
25	52.10	51.96	52.08	52.25	52.27	52.37	52.37	52.15	52.35	52.12	52.06	52.01
26	52.11	51.99	52.02	52.25	52.26	52.35	52.42	52.17	52.38	52.15	52.09	51.99
27	52.13	52.03	51.96	52.17	52.31	52.33	52.38	52.19	52.41	52.15	52.08	51.99
28	52.11	52.01	51.93	52.13	52.31	52.30	52.31	52.22	52.40	52.16	52.05	51.98
29	52.18	52.02	51.90	52.05	---	52.28	52.25	52.26	52.40	52.17	52.02	51.92
30	52.16	52.04	51.90	52.05	---	52.28	52.22	52.29	52.38	52.16	51.99	51.88
31	52.18	---	51.92	52.08	---	52.26	---	52.31	---	52.12	51.97	---
MEAN	52.11	51.99	52.04	52.12	52.16	52.28	52.30	52.19	52.34	52.19	52.05	51.98

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 52.15 HIGHEST 51.84 SEPT. 17, 1993 LOWEST 52.56 APR. 26, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182757066325600. Local number, 206.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'57", long 66°32'56", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 0.84 mi northwest of Barceloneta plaza, 0.64 mi west of Central Plazuela, and 1.96 mi southeast of Escuela Agustín Balseiro. Owner: P.R. Department of Agriculture, Name: Plazuela No. 2.

AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m), cased 16 in (0.41 m) 0-85 ft (0-25.9 m), open hole 85-101 ft (25.9-30.8 m). Depth 101 ft (30.8 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 7.0 ft (2.1 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.30 ft (0.40 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 3.75 ft (1.14 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 11, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 5.89 ft (1.80 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 11-12, 1990.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.31	5.34	5.13	4.96	5.28	5.65	5.69	5.27	5.42	5.59	5.37	5.20
2	5.33	5.32	5.19	5.06	5.27	5.63	5.68	5.28	5.41	5.55	5.35	5.19
3	5.32	5.31	5.22	5.12	5.28	5.62	5.69	5.29	5.45	5.53	5.34	5.19
4	5.30	5.10	5.25	5.18	5.30	5.63	5.68	5.34	5.50	5.51	5.34	5.20
5	5.29	5.08	5.29	5.23	5.28	5.64	5.62	5.38	5.53	5.49	5.33	5.21
6	5.27	5.05	5.31	5.25	5.27	5.64	5.60	5.42	5.57	5.48	5.32	5.20
7	5.26	5.02	5.33	5.28	5.28	5.67	5.59	4.88	5.56	5.48	5.32	5.21
8	5.24	5.05	5.33	5.27	5.31	5.70	5.59	5.05	5.54	5.47	5.33	5.24
9	5.22	5.05	5.31	5.29	5.34	5.69	5.63	5.17	5.52	5.48	5.33	5.31
10	5.21	5.04	5.33	5.33	5.40	5.65	5.65	5.15	5.53	5.48	5.33	5.32
11	5.20	5.07	5.38	5.35	5.46	5.64	5.65	5.21	5.53	5.49	5.36	5.30
12	5.24	5.10	5.40	5.35	5.48	5.65	5.63	5.26	5.53	5.46	5.36	5.26
13	5.25	5.10	5.40	5.36	5.47	5.68	5.60	5.29	5.51	5.44	5.36	5.22
14	5.28	5.10	5.30	5.41	5.46	5.66	5.57	5.32	5.49	5.45	5.35	5.17
15	5.31	5.09	5.25	5.44	5.44	5.68	5.57	5.31	5.48	5.47	5.31	5.13
16	5.33	5.09	5.23	5.45	5.44	5.69	5.57	5.32	5.47	5.45	5.27	5.10
17	5.31	5.13	5.23	5.44	5.46	5.73	5.60	5.33	5.48	5.43	5.20	5.07
18	5.30	5.12	5.25	5.44	5.48	5.72	5.59	5.35	5.52	5.40	5.19	5.08
19	5.30	5.11	5.26	5.46	5.46	5.67	5.56	5.39	5.55	5.38	5.19	5.11
20	5.29	5.08	5.30	5.48	5.48	5.68	5.53	5.38	5.53	5.37	5.20	5.15
21	5.32	5.07	5.34	5.51	5.50	5.71	5.52	5.33	5.54	5.36	5.21	5.19
22	5.30	5.06	5.36	5.53	5.54	5.74	5.53	5.31	5.52	5.35	5.20	5.22
23	5.26	5.07	5.41	5.57	5.61	5.76	5.53	5.29	5.50	5.34	5.22	5.23
24	5.20	5.05	5.43	5.59	5.61	5.76	5.54	5.30	5.51	5.34	5.22	5.20
25	5.18	5.08	5.22	5.54	5.61	5.78	5.57	5.01	5.55	5.36	5.25	5.19
26	5.19	5.14	5.03	5.49	5.61	5.78	5.60	5.11	5.59	5.39	5.29	5.16
27	5.23	5.14	4.91	5.42	5.65	5.77	5.57	5.21	5.60	5.38	5.28	5.15
28	5.27	5.00	4.82	5.38	5.65	5.77	5.51	5.28	5.60	5.38	5.25	5.16
29	5.28	5.07	4.78	5.25	---	5.76	5.37	5.36	5.60	5.39	5.23	5.11
30	5.28	5.07	4.72	5.23	---	5.73	5.30	5.39	5.58	5.38	5.21	5.09
31	5.30	---	4.86	5.26	---	5.69	---	5.42	---	5.37	5.19	---
MEAN	5.27	5.10	5.21	5.35	5.44	5.70	5.58	5.27	5.52	5.43	5.28	5.19

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 5.36 HIGHEST 4.64 DEC. 30, 1992 LOWEST 5.83 MAR. 26, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182710066303700. Local number, 207.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'10", long 66°30'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 1.92 mi east of Barceloneta plaza, 1.35 mi north of Central Monserrate, and 2.68 mi northeast of Escuela José Cordero. Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Cantito La Luisa.

AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-30 ft (0-9.14 m), cased 10 in (0.25 m) 0-126 ft (0-38.4 m), perforated 80-126 ft (24.4-38.4 m). Depth 126 ft (38.4 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 59.0 ft (18.0 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 2.80 ft (0.85 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to Nov. 20, 1992, hole on side of casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 36.38 ft (11.09 m) below land-surface datum, May 15, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 89.83 ft (27.38 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 5, 1985.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	39.99	39.94	38.77	38.50	38.71	39.16	39.30	38.60	38.62	39.00	38.98	39.01
2	39.99	39.94	38.78	38.53	38.72	39.14	39.31	38.51	38.64	39.00	38.99	39.01
3	39.99	39.94	38.79	38.56	38.73	39.11	39.32	38.45	38.66	39.00	38.99	39.02
4	39.97	39.70	38.82	38.61	38.75	39.11	39.32	38.44	38.69	39.00	38.99	39.02
5	39.94	39.56	38.87	38.64	38.73	39.13	39.29	38.46	38.73	39.00	39.01	39.01
6	39.93	39.52	38.91	38.65	38.71	39.15	39.28	38.49	38.75	39.00	39.01	39.00
7	39.92	39.46	38.92	38.67	38.73	39.18	39.27	38.35	38.76	39.01	39.01	38.99
8	39.92	39.46	38.94	38.68	38.77	39.21	39.27	38.33	38.78	39.01	39.01	39.00
9	39.90	39.48	38.92	38.70	38.80	39.22	39.28	38.33	38.78	39.01	39.01	39.02
10	39.89	39.52	38.94	38.74	38.87	39.20	39.28	38.33	38.80	39.00	39.01	39.03
11	39.88	39.55	38.98	38.77	38.93	39.20	39.28	38.35	38.83	38.99	39.02	39.05
12	39.90	39.57	39.00	38.79	38.97	39.21	39.27	38.38	38.85	38.99	39.02	39.03
13	39.94	39.57	39.01	38.80	38.99	39.22	39.25	38.40	38.86	38.98	39.02	39.03
14	39.98	39.56	39.01	38.82	39.00	39.22	39.23	38.41	38.85	38.98	39.03	39.01
15	40.00	39.54	38.96	38.86	39.01	39.24	39.21	38.43	38.85	38.99	39.01	39.00
16	40.04	39.54	38.92	38.90	39.02	39.24	39.22	38.45	38.85	38.99	39.01	38.99
17	40.04	39.55	38.88	38.91	39.03	39.24	39.23	38.47	38.87	38.99	39.00	38.98
18	40.04	39.56	38.86	38.92	39.05	39.25	39.23	38.50	38.89	38.98	38.99	38.97
19	40.02	39.57	38.88	38.94	39.05	39.23	39.22	38.54	38.92	38.98	38.99	38.98
20	40.02	38.78	38.93	38.96	39.06	39.24	39.18	38.57	38.92	38.98	39.00	38.99
21	40.03	38.79	38.98	38.99	39.06	39.24	39.14	38.58	38.94	38.99	39.00	39.01
22	40.02	38.77	39.01	39.01	39.07	39.25	39.10	38.59	38.94	38.99	39.00	39.01
23	40.00	38.76	39.04	39.02	39.09	39.26	39.05	38.59	38.95	38.98	39.00	39.01
24	39.92	38.78	39.05	39.04	39.12	39.26	39.04	38.59	38.96	38.98	39.00	39.00
25	39.89	38.82	39.01	39.04	39.13	39.28	39.06	38.58	38.98	38.96	39.00	39.00
26	39.88	38.88	38.94	39.05	39.13	39.29	39.08	38.58	38.99	38.96	39.01	38.97
27	39.90	38.91	38.81	39.03	39.15	39.29	39.08	38.59	39.00	38.96	39.01	38.97
28	39.93	38.86	38.73	39.02	39.16	39.30	39.03	38.59	39.00	38.96	39.01	38.96
29	39.93	38.82	38.62	38.77	---	39.30	38.98	38.60	39.00	38.97	39.01	38.96
30	39.93	38.78	38.49	38.71	---	39.30	38.71	38.61	38.99	38.98	39.01	38.94
31	39.93	---	38.48	38.70	---	39.29	---	38.62	---	38.98	39.01	---
MEAN	39.96	39.32	38.88	38.82	38.95	39.22	39.18	38.49	38.85	38.99	39.01	39.00

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 39.06 HIGHEST 38.33 MAY 8-10, 1993 LOWEST 40.04 OCT. 16-18, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182308066260400. Local number, 210.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'08", long 66°26'04", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 4.88 mi southeast of Manati plaza, 5.24 mi southwest of Vega Baja plaza, and 2.25 mi west of Escuela Evaristo Camacho. Owner: Gelo Martínez, Name: Gelo Martínez well.

AQUIFER.--Lares Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 8 in (0.20 m), cased 8 in (0.20 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 574 ft (174.9 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.30 ft (1.01 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to January 14, 1993, hole on side of casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 40.56 ft (12.36 m) below land-surface datum, May 22, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 83.01 ft (25.3 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 29, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Nov. 20	82.90	Feb. 18	77.80	May 18	66.80	Aug. 31	78.57
Dec. 23	82.10	Mar. 19	79.60	June 21	75.10	Sept. 23	79.00
Jan. 14	72.65	Apr. 27	80.30	July 13	75.88		

WATER YEAR 1993 HIGHEST 66.80 MAY 18, 1993 LOWEST 82.90 NOV. 20, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182647066201700. Local number, 70.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'47", long 66°20'17", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 1.52 mi north of Vega Alta plaza, 4.78 mi southwest of Dorado plaza, and 2.01 mi northwest of Escuela Industrial para Mujeres. Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Sabana Hoyos.

AQUIFER.--Limestone of Tertiary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused artesian well, diameter 8 in (0.20 m), cased 0-90 ft (0-27.43 m), perforated. Depth 90 ft (27.43 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 49 ft (14.9 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of casing wooden cover, 1.30 ft (0.40 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1960 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 21.33 ft (6.50 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 26, 1976; lowest water level recorded, 31.10 ft (9.48 m) below land-surface datum, July 31, 1975.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	29.76	29.95	28.76	27.96	28.42	29.18	29.84	29.50	28.81	29.10	28.71	29.12
2	29.77	29.96	28.72	27.93	28.43	29.22	29.86	29.42	28.79	29.11	28.72	29.13
3	29.78	29.97	28.72	27.91	28.44	29.25	29.87	29.35	28.78	29.07	28.73	29.13
4	29.79	29.83	28.70	27.90	28.47	29.28	29.88	29.30	28.79	29.02	28.74	29.14
5	29.77	29.70	28.68	27.91	28.49	29.30	29.88	29.27	28.81	29.00	28.75	29.15
6	29.77	29.64	28.67	27.93	28.51	29.33	29.88	29.24	28.83	28.99	28.76	29.15
7	29.78	29.57	28.69	27.96	28.53	29.35	29.90	29.20	28.84	28.98	28.78	29.15
8	29.79	29.52	28.68	27.95	28.56	29.38	29.91	29.12	28.88	28.97	28.79	29.16
9	29.81	29.48	28.70	27.96	28.58	29.40	29.92	29.08	28.90	28.97	28.80	29.17
10	29.82	29.44	28.70	27.97	28.61	29.43	29.92	29.04	28.92	28.96	28.82	29.19
11	29.82	29.40	28.71	27.99	28.65	29.46	29.93	29.00	28.93	28.96	28.84	29.18
12	29.84	29.38	28.75	28.00	28.68	29.48	29.93	28.97	28.94	28.93	28.86	29.18
13	29.85	29.33	28.77	28.01	28.71	29.51	29.89	28.95	28.94	28.91	28.88	29.18
14	29.86	29.28	28.80	28.03	28.74	29.53	29.88	28.94	28.95	28.89	28.90	29.13
15	29.88	29.23	28.71	28.05	28.75	29.57	29.86	28.92	28.95	28.88	28.91	29.11
16	29.89	29.18	28.67	28.07	28.78	29.59	29.83	28.91	28.96	28.88	28.91	29.10
17	29.90	29.14	28.64	28.10	28.81	29.60	29.84	28.91	28.98	28.88	28.91	29.09
18	29.91	29.11	28.62	28.13	28.85	29.63	29.84	28.91	28.98	28.88	28.92	29.08
19	29.91	29.08	28.62	28.16	28.87	29.65	29.83	28.91	29.00	28.88	28.93	29.07
20	29.92	29.06	28.63	28.19	28.92	29.67	29.84	28.92	28.99	28.89	28.94	29.07
21	29.93	29.06	28.64	28.23	28.94	29.68	29.83	28.94	28.98	28.92	28.95	29.09
22	29.94	29.04	28.66	28.27	28.96	29.71	29.82	28.97	28.98	28.93	28.96	29.10
23	29.95	29.00	28.67	28.30	29.00	29.73	29.79	28.97	29.00	28.90	28.98	29.11
24	29.93	28.97	28.68	28.33	29.02	29.74	29.79	28.98	28.99	28.87	29.00	29.11
25	29.92	28.97	28.54	28.36	29.05	29.75	29.79	28.96	29.01	28.83	29.02	29.11
26	29.92	28.95	28.46	28.38	29.09	29.77	29.79	28.96	29.03	28.79	29.04	29.11
27	29.92	28.93	28.36	28.40	29.11	29.79	29.81	28.93	29.04	28.76	29.06	29.10
28	29.93	28.89	28.26	28.43	29.15	29.79	29.81	28.90	29.06	28.74	29.07	29.11
29	29.93	28.83	28.16	28.45	---	29.79	29.80	28.87	29.08	28.72	29.08	29.11
30	29.92	28.80	28.09	28.40	---	29.82	29.64	28.86	29.09	28.71	29.10	29.10
31	29.93	---	28.02	28.41	---	29.82	---	28.85	---	28.71	29.12	---
MEAN	29.87	29.29	28.60	28.13	28.75	29.55	29.85	29.03	28.94	28.90	28.90	29.12

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 29.08 HIGHEST 27.90 JAN. 3-5, 1993 LOWEST 29.97 NOV. 30, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182615066235300. Local number, 211.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'15", long 66°23'53", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 4.46 mi southeast of Manatí plaza, 5.48 mi southwest of Vega Baja plaza, and 1.22 mi east of Hwy 155 km 58.3. Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Rosario No. 2.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 14 in (0.36 m) 0-200 ft (0-61.0 m), diameter 12 in (0.30 m) 200-250 ft (61.0-76.2 m), cased 12 in (0.30 m) 0-250 ft (0-76.2 m), perforated 210-250 ft (64.0-76.2 m), diameter 10 in (0.25 m) 250-270 ft (76.2-82.3 m), open hole; concrete sealed 0-200 ft (0-61.0 m). Depth 270 ft (82.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 215 ft (65.5 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.15 ft (0.35 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 191.29 ft (58.30 m) below land-surface datum, May 16, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 193.73 ft (59.0 m) below land-surface datum, May 15-23, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	193.41	193.49	193.10	192.84	193.09	193.32	193.50	192.74	192.76	193.07	193.00	193.05
2	193.41	193.49	193.10	192.84	193.08	193.32	193.49	192.70	192.77	193.08	193.00	193.04
3	193.42	193.49	193.10	192.84	193.05	193.31	193.50	192.70	192.79	193.08	192.99	193.05
4	193.42	193.43	193.09	192.84	193.07	193.32	193.50	192.70	192.82	193.08	192.99	193.04
5	193.43	193.19	193.09	192.84	193.08	193.32	193.49	192.69	192.86	193.08	193.00	193.04
6	193.43	193.18	193.09	192.84	193.08	193.33	193.49	192.70	192.88	193.08	193.00	193.04
7	193.44	193.15	193.09	192.83	193.08	193.33	193.49	192.70	192.87	193.08	193.00	193.03
8	193.44	193.15	193.14	192.85	193.09	193.35	193.48	192.70	192.87	193.08	193.00	193.01
9	193.44	193.15	193.14	192.85	193.11	193.43	193.49	192.70	192.87	193.08	193.01	193.01
10	193.44	193.15	193.15	192.88	193.12	193.43	193.49	192.68	192.87	193.08	193.01	193.01
11	193.44	193.15	193.16	192.89	193.21	193.43	193.48	192.68	192.97	193.08	193.01	193.05
12	193.44	193.15	193.17	192.91	193.21	193.43	193.48	192.68	192.97	193.07	193.02	193.05
13	193.44	193.15	193.17	192.91	193.23	193.43	193.46	192.68	192.96	193.00	193.03	193.05
14	193.46	193.15	193.17	192.99	193.24	193.44	193.46	192.69	192.96	193.00	193.02	193.05
15	193.49	193.15	193.17	192.99	193.24	193.44	193.44	192.69	192.95	193.00	193.02	193.01
16	193.51	193.15	193.16	193.02	193.24	193.46	193.44	192.68	192.95	192.99	193.02	193.01
17	193.51	193.15	193.16	193.03	193.23	193.46	193.44	192.68	192.95	193.00	193.02	193.01
18	193.51	193.15	193.14	193.04	193.25	193.46	193.44	192.70	192.96	193.01	193.02	192.96
19	193.51	193.15	193.14	193.08	193.25	193.45	193.45	192.70	192.99	193.01	193.02	192.95
20	193.51	193.13	193.16	193.10	193.25	193.45	193.45	192.70	193.00	193.01	193.02	192.95
21	193.51	193.10	193.18	193.11	193.25	193.45	193.39	192.71	193.00	193.01	193.02	192.95
22	193.51	193.11	193.19	193.12	193.26	193.45	193.31	192.72	193.02	193.01	193.02	192.96
23	193.51	193.11	193.19	193.13	193.28	193.47	193.30	192.75	193.02	193.01	193.02	192.96
24	193.51	193.11	193.22	193.21	193.29	193.47	193.30	192.76	193.02	193.01	193.02	193.00
25	193.50	193.11	193.22	193.21	193.29	193.48	193.30	192.77	193.02	193.01	193.02	193.00
26	193.49	193.11	193.14	193.21	193.30	193.49	193.30	192.77	193.04	193.01	193.03	193.00
27	193.49	193.11	193.00	193.20	193.31	193.50	193.30	192.77	193.04	193.01	193.06	193.00
28	193.49	193.11	192.94	193.19	193.31	193.50	193.31	192.76	193.05	193.00	193.06	193.01
29	193.49	193.11	192.89	193.19	---	193.51	193.28	192.77	193.05	193.00	193.06	193.01
30	193.49	193.11	192.88	193.10	---	193.50	193.01	192.77	193.06	192.99	193.06	193.01
31	193.49	---	192.85	193.10	---	193.49	---	192.77	---	192.99	193.05	---
MEAN	193.47	193.18	193.11	193.01	193.20	193.43	193.41	192.72	192.94	193.03	193.02	193.01
WTR YR 1993	MEAN 193.13	HIGHEST 192.67	MAY 11-13, 1993	LOWEST 193.51	OCT. 16-25, 1993							

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182515066194000. Local number, 212.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'15", long 66°19'40", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 5.15 mi southwest of Dorado plaza, 0.49 mi north of Vega Alta plaza, and 1.04 mi northwest of Escuela Industrial para Mujeres. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Ponderosa TW-1.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone-Cibao Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) 0-136 ft (0-41.1 m), perforated 121-131 ft (36.9-39.9 m); bentonite packed 0.5-121 ft (0.15-36.9 m).
Depth 136 ft (39.9 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 98.0 ft (29.9 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 63.05 ft (19.22 m) below land-surface datum, July 15, 1987; lowest water level recorded, 74.63 ft (22.75 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 27-28, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	69.60	---	68.66	67.30	67.22	68.25	69.30	68.74	66.90	67.21	67.13	67.90
2	69.60	---	68.61	67.24	67.28	68.33	69.33	68.58	66.84	67.21	67.13	67.99
3	69.60	---	68.55	67.17	67.31	68.36	69.36	68.47	66.81	67.21	67.13	67.98
4	69.59	---	68.50	67.12	67.34	68.39	69.38	68.36	66.82	67.20	67.15	67.99
5	69.60	---	68.48	67.06	67.36	68.43	69.43	68.28	66.79	67.18	67.16	68.01
6	69.62	---	68.45	67.03	67.37	68.50	69.47	68.22	66.79	67.18	67.22	68.03
7	69.64	---	68.43	67.00	67.41	68.53	69.49	68.06	66.78	67.17	67.25	68.06
8	69.65	---	68.41	66.97	67.45	68.56	69.50	67.89	66.78	67.16	67.25	68.07
9	69.68	---	68.39	66.91	67.49	68.59	69.56	67.74	66.78	67.15	67.26	68.10
10	69.68	---	68.36	66.90	67.54	68.63	69.58	67.60	66.80	67.15	67.30	68.12
11	69.69	---	68.35	66.88	67.57	68.68	69.60	67.46	66.97	67.13	67.36	68.14
12	69.71	---	68.35	66.87	67.62	68.71	69.61	67.36	66.87	67.11	67.37	68.15
13	69.77	---	68.36	66.86	67.65	68.74	69.63	67.29	66.87	67.11	67.38	68.17
14	69.78	---	68.37	66.85	67.68	68.79	69.62	67.22	66.89	67.10	67.41	68.17
15	69.81	---	68.33	66.85	67.72	68.81	69.62	67.18	66.92	67.08	67.44	68.19
16	69.82	---	68.28	66.86	67.76	68.85	69.60	67.14	66.94	67.07	67.47	68.23
17	69.86	---	68.24	66.86	67.82	68.90	69.59	67.11	66.95	67.07	67.48	68.23
18	69.91	---	68.24	66.89	67.85	68.92	69.58	67.07	66.96	67.07	67.50	68.23
19	69.92	---	68.21	66.89	67.89	68.95	69.57	67.06	67.00	67.08	67.53	68.23
20	69.94	---	68.18	66.90	67.94	68.96	69.57	67.04	67.00	67.09	67.56	68.23
21	69.95	69.30	68.16	66.92	67.99	68.97	69.55	67.04	67.01	67.11	67.60	68.24
22	69.97	69.29	68.11	66.97	68.01	69.00	69.46	67.04	67.05	67.12	67.63	68.25
23	69.99	69.26	68.10	67.00	68.02	69.01	69.40	67.04	67.06	67.14	67.66	68.26
24	70.00	69.23	68.08	67.02	68.05	69.06	69.36	67.04	67.07	67.14	67.68	68.30
25	70.02	69.16	68.05	67.05	68.10	69.09	69.33	67.04	67.09	67.14	67.71	68.31
26	70.07	69.11	67.99	67.07	68.13	69.12	69.32	67.04	67.11	67.12	67.74	68.32
27	70.13	69.06	67.89	67.09	68.16	69.15	69.30	67.04	67.11	67.11	67.79	68.33
28	70.13	68.91	67.73	67.12	68.18	69.17	69.30	67.01	67.12	67.12	67.81	68.34
29	---	68.84	67.61	67.16	---	69.19	69.28	66.98	67.15	67.11	67.82	68.36
30	---	68.74	67.51	67.18	---	69.21	68.98	66.96	67.21	67.15	67.84	68.38
31	---	---	67.39	67.21	---	69.22	---	66.94	---	67.13	67.88	---
MEAN	69.81	69.09	68.21	67.01	67.71	68.81	69.46	67.45	66.95	67.13	67.47	68.18

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 68.03 HIGHEST 66.78 JUNE 7-9, 1993 LOWEST 70.13 OCT. 27-28, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182330066185700. Local number, 213.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'30", long 66°18'57", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 1.82 mi southeast of Vega Alta plaza, 4.23 mi west of Toa Alta plaza, and 1.27 mi northwest off the intersection of Hwy 820 with Hwy 823. Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Pampano No. 2.

AQUIFER.--Rio Indio Limestone-Lares Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-130 ft (0-39.6 m), diameter 14 in (0.36 m), cased 12 in (0.30 m) 0-220 ft (0-67.1 m); open hole 220-330 ft (67.6-100.6 m). Depth 330 ft (100.6 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 394 ft (120 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 2.95 ft (0.90 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 34.40 ft (10.50 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 6, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 61.13 ft (18.6 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 3, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	59.94	60.98	---	50.30	48.10	50.90	52.85	50.84	41.91	43.10	44.44	46.52
2	59.93	61.00	---	50.08	48.03	51.01	52.99	50.43	41.22	43.18	44.47	46.68
3	59.95	61.10	---	49.89	48.05	51.12	53.06	49.98	41.08	43.28	44.53	46.84
4	59.96	61.02	---	49.77	48.07	51.21	53.13	49.64	41.72	43.32	44.57	46.90
5	59.95	60.97	---	49.64	48.04	51.28	53.18	49.35	41.87	43.37	44.55	46.96
6	60.03	60.89	---	49.55	48.02	51.35	53.22	49.09	41.96	43.41	44.45	47.07
7	60.04	60.78	---	49.49	48.02	51.43	53.32	47.57	42.03	43.46	44.68	47.20
8	60.04	60.75	---	49.35	48.04	51.48	53.35	46.52	42.02	43.50	44.71	47.30
9	60.07	60.70	---	49.23	48.42	51.53	53.44	45.70	42.05	43.62	44.77	47.43
10	60.08	60.69	---	49.16	48.92	51.59	53.56	44.92	41.47	43.68	44.84	47.49
11	60.09	60.68	---	49.10	49.18	51.67	53.58	44.24	41.37	43.67	44.91	47.58
12	60.10	60.67	---	49.05	49.33	51.72	53.65	43.65	41.29	43.70	45.00	47.67
13	60.15	60.68	---	48.99	49.43	51.75	53.67	43.22	41.95	43.83	45.11	47.68
14	60.22	60.67	---	48.93	49.59	51.82	53.64	42.93	42.10	43.85	45.13	47.69
15	60.32	60.51	---	49.00	49.74	51.99	53.64	42.61	42.15	43.88	45.25	47.73
16	60.36	60.49	---	48.97	49.86	---	53.63	42.41	42.28	43.91	45.26	47.77
17	60.36	60.49	---	49.01	49.98	52.05	---	42.21	42.36	44.05	45.34	47.83
18	60.38	60.47	55.36	49.07	50.03	52.09	---	42.06	42.46	44.09	45.43	47.89
19	60.52	60.42	55.32	49.07	50.13	52.09	---	41.89	42.53	44.09	45.49	47.93
20	60.58	60.45	55.25	49.09	50.28	52.15	---	41.82	42.58	44.31	45.57	48.01
21	60.61	60.44	55.16	49.15	50.41	52.20	---	41.72	42.66	44.34	45.67	48.05
22	60.62	60.43	55.09	49.19	50.44	52.28	---	42.02	42.67	44.33	45.68	48.08
23	60.64	60.40	54.89	49.23	50.49	52.38	---	41.83	42.72	44.37	45.71	48.08
24	60.74	60.35	54.70	49.27	50.57	52.47	---	41.57	42.79	44.46	45.83	48.20
25	60.79	60.32	54.23	49.29	50.64	52.53	---	41.45	42.84	44.46	45.93	48.28
26	60.86	60.23	53.57	49.28	50.75	52.57	---	41.38	42.88	44.40	46.02	48.31
27	60.67	60.12	52.74	49.07	50.80	52.62	52.43	41.29	42.87	44.37	46.07	48.32
28	60.13	59.72	52.17	48.58	50.84	52.65	52.33	41.23	43.09	44.37	46.14	48.31
29	60.62	59.34	51.48	48.42	---	52.76	52.07	41.26	43.07	44.40	46.25	48.31
30	60.78	59.13	50.94	48.29	---	52.82	51.36	41.69	43.08	44.44	46.30	48.32
31	60.93	---	50.58	48.17	---	52.83	---	41.87	---	44.45	46.50	---
MEAN	60.34	60.50	53.68	49.18	49.44	51.94	53.10	44.14	42.24	43.93	45.31	47.68

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 49.85 HIGHEST 41.04 JUNE 3, 1993 LOWEST 61.13 NOV. 3, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182746066170800. Local number, 214.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'46", long 66°17'08", Hydrologic Unit 210100002, 1.58 mi west of Dorado plaza, 0.59 mi southeast of Dorado Airport main gate, and 3.76 mi north of Hwy 2 km 25.2. Owner: Dorado Beach Hotel, Name: Dorado Beach No. 7.

AQUIFER.--Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 18 in (0.46 m). Depth 100 ft (30.5 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 26.0 ft (8.0 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Prior to this report, elevation incorrectly used was 39.0 ft (11.9 m). Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.10 ft (0.34 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- November 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 18.23 ft (5.56 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 16, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 20.68 ft (6.30 m) below land-surface datum, May 16, 1992

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	20.36	20.43	19.86	20.02	20.16	20.35	20.54	20.26	20.25	20.42	19.99	20.13
2	20.35	20.36	19.84	20.00	20.15	20.34	20.57	20.26	20.24	20.37	19.98	20.14
3	20.30	20.32	19.84	20.00	20.16	20.34	20.60	20.26	20.27	20.32	20.00	20.12
4	20.26	20.12	19.83	19.96	20.18	20.36	20.57	20.31	20.33	20.27	20.03	20.12
5	20.25	20.03	19.84	19.95	20.13	20.38	20.59	20.35	20.37	20.25	20.02	20.13
6	20.23	19.95	19.83	19.97	20.14	20.41	20.60	20.35	20.43	20.24	20.03	20.15
7	20.24	19.90	19.82	19.96	20.18	20.43	20.59	20.26	20.40	20.23	20.05	20.13
8	20.21	19.93	19.80	19.92	20.22	20.47	20.58	20.20	20.36	20.23	20.08	20.16
9	20.19	19.93	19.83	19.94	20.24	20.46	20.54	20.23	20.32	20.24	20.09	20.23
10	20.20	19.97	19.77	19.91	20.31	20.42	20.51	20.26	20.32	20.25	20.08	20.24
11	20.20	19.99	19.72	19.90	20.36	20.42	20.52	20.31	20.33	20.25	20.10	20.20
12	20.26	20.02	19.71	19.90	20.33	20.44	20.55	20.32	20.33	20.10	20.12	20.12
13	20.28	19.99	19.71	19.91	20.32	20.45	20.58	20.30	20.33	20.10	20.11	20.07
14	20.34	19.98	19.73	19.88	20.32	20.47	20.61	20.30	20.31	20.12	20.10	19.99
15	20.37	19.96	19.80	19.96	20.31	20.49	20.58	20.26	20.31	20.14	20.07	19.96
16	20.38	19.94	19.88	19.96	20.32	20.48	20.56	20.25	20.32	20.13	20.03	19.93
17	20.35	19.94	19.91	19.97	20.34	20.51	20.55	20.26	20.37	20.13	19.99	19.95
18	20.33	19.89	19.91	20.01	20.36	20.52	20.53	20.26	20.39	20.11	20.01	19.96
19	20.34	19.82	19.87	20.05	20.21	20.49	20.55	20.30	20.41	20.09	20.02	19.99
20	20.33	19.77	19.81	20.07	20.22	20.52	20.57	20.29	20.33	20.11	20.05	20.03
21	20.36	19.77	19.74	20.11	20.22	20.52	20.58	20.29	20.31	20.14	20.06	20.05
22	20.32	19.77	19.73	20.12	20.28	20.57	20.58	20.29	20.29	20.12	20.05	20.07
23	20.26	19.82	19.68	20.16	20.33	20.58	20.57	20.30	20.30	20.06	20.07	20.06
24	20.24	19.88	19.66	20.18	20.33	20.58	20.54	20.28	20.31	20.00	20.10	20.02
25	20.23	19.85	19.73	20.15	20.33	20.58	20.52	20.24	20.36	19.98	20.13	20.00
26	20.27	19.80	19.82	20.13	20.33	20.58	20.50	20.23	20.40	19.97	20.17	20.02
27	20.31	19.80	19.96	20.05	20.36	20.56	20.56	20.24	20.43	19.94	20.14	20.02
28	20.33	19.83	19.99	20.03	20.37	20.54	20.54	20.20	20.43	19.96	20.11	20.02
29	20.32	19.83	20.04	20.05	---	20.54	20.45	20.24	20.42	19.98	20.10	19.97
30	20.38	19.86	20.06	20.07	---	20.54	20.31	20.26	20.40	19.97	20.08	19.97
31	20.36	---	20.01	20.13	---	20.53	---	20.27	---	19.97	20.10	---
MEAN	20.30	19.95	19.83	20.01	20.27	20.48	20.55	20.27	20.35	20.14	20.07	20.06

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 20.19 HIGHEST 19.60 DEC. 24, 1992 LOWEST 20.63 APR. 14, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182530066135400. Local number, 216.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'30", long 66°13'54", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 2.61 mi northeast of Toa Alta plaza, 2.73 mi southwest of Sabana Seca U.S. Naval Radio Station, and 1.76 mi southeast of Hwy 2 km 17.7. Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Pozo Navy-Campanillas.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m) 0-106 ft (0-32.3 m), cased 16 in (0.41 m) 0-20 ft (0-6.10 m), cased 12 in (0.30 m) 0-106 ft (0-32.3 m), perforated 20-106 ft (6.10-32.3 m), diameter 10 in (0.25 m) 106-140 ft (32.3-42.7 m), cased 10 in (0.25 m) 106-140 ft (32.3-42.7 m), perforated 106-140 ft (32.3-42.7 m). Depth 140 ft (42.7 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 13.0 ft (3.96 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.80 ft (0.55 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 9.38 ft (2.86 m) below land-surface datum, June 23, 1987; lowest water level recorded, 14.72 ft (4.49 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 28, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	12.93	13.69	11.89	11.56	12.27	13.24	14.01	13.33	12.77	13.14	12.42	13.26
2	13.01	13.69	11.89	11.57	12.31	13.24	14.04	13.28	12.85	13.11	12.45	13.28
3	13.13	13.57	11.92	11.60	12.35	13.27	14.10	13.26	12.85	12.36	12.28	13.29
4	13.20	12.74	11.92	11.63	12.37	13.29	14.11	13.28	13.02	12.25	12.57	13.34
5	13.24	12.48	11.90	11.66	12.41	13.32	14.10	13.34	13.00	12.70	12.59	13.35
6	13.27	12.36	11.95	11.67	12.46	13.39	14.11	13.36	13.03	12.77	12.63	13.39
7	13.29	12.33	11.98	11.65	12.55	13.44	14.15	13.25	13.00	12.83	12.66	13.38
8	13.31	12.34	12.02	11.63	12.60	13.46	14.18	13.17	13.00	12.72	12.70	13.40
9	13.36	12.31	12.19	11.63	12.64	13.48	14.17	13.16	12.96	12.77	12.72	13.46
10	13.28	12.31	12.33	11.69	12.68	13.50	14.20	13.13	12.95	12.82	12.66	13.48
11	13.25	12.37	12.48	11.72	12.72	13.54	14.21	13.09	12.97	12.72	12.73	13.07
12	13.29	12.36	12.59	11.73	12.74	13.57	14.11	13.11	13.00	12.41	12.80	13.08
13	13.31	12.35	12.66	11.76	12.76	13.61	13.95	13.13	13.00	12.46	12.84	13.08
14	13.36	12.41	12.69	11.79	12.78	13.83	13.90	13.13	12.97	12.52	12.98	12.99
15	13.40	12.35	12.41	11.85	12.82	13.69	13.87	13.09	13.03	12.57	12.94	12.98
16	13.43	11.66	12.38	11.89	12.81	13.43	13.85	13.12	13.07	12.61	12.87	12.92
17	13.43	11.55	12.38	11.94	12.84	13.54	14.01	13.05	13.11	12.68	12.87	12.52
18	13.29	11.48	12.37	12.00	12.87	13.64	14.07	13.04	13.16	12.72	12.92	12.80
19	13.31	12.00	12.43	12.02	12.89	13.69	14.11	13.20	13.22	12.73	12.96	12.82
20	13.35	12.08	12.46	12.04	12.92	13.77	14.15	13.21	12.92	12.78	13.00	12.72
21	13.38	11.39	12.52	12.09	12.95	13.81	14.06	13.24	12.88	12.85	13.06	12.72
22	13.36	12.25	12.46	12.09	12.97	13.86	14.02	13.25	13.08	12.78	13.05	12.69
23	13.35	12.31	12.38	12.13	13.00	13.86	14.06	13.41	12.99	12.46	13.05	12.79
24	13.32	12.26	12.22	12.16	13.02	13.90	14.16	13.21	12.99	12.40	13.07	12.78
25	13.33	12.27	12.13	12.14	13.16	13.89	14.19	13.01	13.16	12.31	13.12	12.91
26	13.35	12.26	11.95	12.14	13.16	13.89	14.18	12.94	13.08	12.32	13.12	12.95
27	13.36	12.12	11.81	12.14	13.20	13.92	14.20	12.81	13.08	12.15	13.15	12.82
28	13.34	12.00	11.72	12.17	13.22	13.92	14.19	12.73	12.98	12.19	13.18	12.85
29	13.42	12.01	11.70	12.18	---	13.93	14.13	12.76	13.07	12.26	13.20	12.81
30	13.56	11.90	11.53	12.22	---	13.94	13.35	12.78	13.10	12.32	13.21	12.82
31	13.65	---	11.58	12.27	---	13.97	---	12.84	---	12.38	13.23	---
MEAN	13.32	12.31	12.16	11.90	12.77	13.64	14.06	13.12	13.01	12.58	12.87	13.02

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 12.90 HIGHEST 11.36 NOV. 18, 1992 LOWEST 14.24 APR. 25, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182655066142400. Local number, 217.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'55", long 66°14'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 4.00 mi northeast of Toa Alta plaza, 3.40 mi northwest of Hwy 2 km 17.7, and 3.49 mi northwest of Sabana Seca U.S. Naval Radio Station. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Monserrate TW-2.
 AQUIFER.--Alluvial Deposits.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) 0-80 ft (0-24.4 m), perforated 10-80 ft (3.05-24.4 m). Depth 80 ft (24.4 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 3.30 ft (1.00 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.50 ft (1.07 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1985 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 0.02 ft (0.006 m) below land-surface datum, May 16, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 2.75 ft (0.84 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 25-27, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	2.14	2.41	1.42	1.31	1.85	2.24	2.57	1.98	---	2.24	1.66	2.04
2	2.13	2.32	1.50	1.34	1.85	2.24	2.60	1.99	---	2.20	1.67	2.06
3	2.09	2.26	1.56	1.35	1.87	2.25	2.65	2.01	---	2.01	1.72	2.06
4	2.09	1.68	1.55	1.41	1.89	2.27	2.66	2.09	---	1.92	1.76	2.06
5	2.12	1.56	1.45	1.48	1.87	2.29	2.60	2.17	---	1.93	1.77	2.07
6	2.12	1.42	1.54	1.37	1.88	2.31	2.60	2.18	---	1.95	1.79	2.08
7	2.13	1.40	1.58	1.38	1.93	2.36	2.60	2.05	---	1.97	1.83	2.09
8	2.11	1.55	1.59	1.38	1.95	2.38	2.61	1.99	---	1.94	1.86	2.14
9	2.13	1.56	1.59	1.37	1.97	2.38	2.67	2.02	---	1.95	1.88	2.18
10	2.12	1.61	1.66	1.43	2.03	2.34	2.67	2.04	---	1.98	1.90	2.19
11	2.11	1.65	1.75	1.46	2.07	2.34	2.68	2.09	2.13	1.94	1.93	2.04
12	2.15	1.67	1.79	1.42	2.06	2.34	2.60	2.11	2.14	1.64	1.96	2.01
13	2.22	1.66	1.83	1.41	2.04	2.37	2.55	2.12	2.15	1.69	1.97	1.98
14	2.27	1.68	1.84	1.51	2.06	2.41	2.50	2.13	2.14	1.79	1.96	1.91
15	2.30	1.67	1.65	1.58	2.07	2.44	2.52	2.06	2.16	1.82	1.94	1.90
16	2.32	1.63	1.60	1.60	2.08	2.42	2.52	2.07	2.20	1.82	1.89	1.87
17	2.30	1.61	1.59	1.61	2.09	2.43	2.56	2.08	2.24	1.84	1.85	1.82
18	2.24	1.57	1.59	1.67	2.11	2.47	2.61	2.10	2.28	1.85	1.87	1.83
19	2.26	1.41	1.63	1.69	2.10	2.44	2.63	2.17	2.21	1.83	1.89	1.86
20	2.28	1.48	1.69	1.70	2.09	2.47	2.64	2.18	1.99	1.86	1.93	1.85
21	2.30	1.39	1.79	1.76	2.08	2.47	2.55	2.20	1.98	1.91	1.95	1.87
22	2.25	1.48	1.79	1.77	2.11	2.51	2.55	---	1.98	1.89	1.95	1.86
23	2.19	1.56	1.79	1.80	2.15	2.52	2.57	---	2.02	1.64	1.97	1.85
24	2.16	1.61	1.73	1.83	2.16	2.54	2.64	---	2.04	1.57	2.01	1.82
25	2.13	1.60	1.62	1.79	2.20	2.53	2.65	---	2.09	1.54	2.05	1.84
26	2.18	1.66	1.54	1.76	2.20	2.52	2.66	---	2.14	1.57	2.05	1.84
27	2.20	1.64	1.31	1.70	2.23	2.51	2.64	---	2.19	1.51	2.05	1.84
28	2.22	1.46	1.31	1.69	2.26	2.51	2.59	---	2.21	1.56	2.03	1.84
29	2.21	1.54	1.29	1.72	---	2.52	2.52	---	2.22	1.62	2.01	1.82
30	2.32	1.37	1.22	1.72	---	2.54	1.97	---	2.21	1.63	2.01	1.81
31	2.38	---	1.30	1.82	---	2.54	---	---	---	1.65	2.02	---
MEAN	2.20	1.64	1.58	1.58	2.04	2.42	2.58	2.09	2.14	1.81	1.91	1.95

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 1.99 HIGHEST 1.19 DEC. 29, 30, 1992 LOWEST 2.75 APR. 25-27, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182623066111000. Local number, 218.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'23", long 66°11'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 3.30 mi northwest of Bayamón plaza, 1.78 mi south of Hwy 165 km 26.5, and 2.38 mi northeast of Hwy 2 km 16.2. Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Levittown No. 7.

AQUIFER.--Alluvial deposits-Aymamón Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well.

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land surface datum is about 10.0 ft (3.05 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on pump base, 1.55 ft (0.47 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 5.94 ft (1.81 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 20, 1989; lowest water level recorded, 9.77 ft (2.98 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 23, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	8.73	9.20	7.89	7.56	8.06	8.54	8.84	8.38	8.33	8.46	7.98	8.08
2	8.67	9.04	7.92	7.57	8.06	8.56	8.86	8.38	8.32	8.44	8.02	8.08
3	8.77	9.02	7.94	7.56	8.09	8.57	9.04	8.39	8.27	8.39	8.00	8.09
4	8.61	7.96	7.95	7.60	8.10	8.59	8.98	8.41	8.28	8.35	8.01	8.11
5	8.77	7.60	7.73	7.61	8.11	8.59	8.90	8.46	8.33	8.32	8.00	8.10
6	8.76	7.40	8.08	7.60	8.12	8.61	9.09	8.49	8.36	8.31	8.00	8.13
7	8.57	7.58	8.12	7.62	8.14	8.64	8.95	8.45	8.36	8.32	8.01	8.15
8	8.79	7.74	8.00	7.63	8.15	8.65	9.07	8.45	8.36	8.29	8.03	8.19
9	8.91	7.65	8.11	7.65	8.19	8.68	9.13	8.46	8.35	8.31	8.05	8.21
10	8.79	7.82	8.19	7.67	8.23	8.66	9.16	8.48	8.36	8.33	7.99	8.26
11	8.79	7.75	8.26	7.70	8.27	8.67	9.18	8.52	8.37	8.31	7.97	8.08
12	8.81	7.95	8.33	7.69	8.27	8.68	9.07	8.54	8.39	8.23	7.95	8.02
13	8.84	8.03	8.39	7.72	8.27	8.71	8.94	8.56	8.38	8.20	7.96	7.96
14	8.87	7.97	8.41	7.75	8.29	8.72	8.92	8.56	8.36	8.24	7.98	7.93
15	8.89	8.09	8.38	7.79	8.30	8.73	9.02	8.58	8.33	8.24	7.97	7.85
16	8.93	7.99	8.16	7.79	8.29	8.74	9.01	8.59	8.38	8.23	7.95	7.80
17	8.93	7.95	8.27	7.82	8.31	8.76	9.11	8.52	8.42	8.24	7.93	7.76
18	9.10	8.17	8.32	7.84	8.32	8.76	9.14	8.36	8.40	8.25	7.91	7.74
19	9.16	8.15	8.35	7.86	8.34	8.75	9.15	8.62	8.41	8.24	7.92	7.80
20	9.17	7.99	8.38	7.87	8.36	8.77	9.15	8.63	8.34	8.39	7.92	7.78
21	9.03	8.16	8.40	7.91	8.38	8.64	9.10	8.65	8.33	8.44	7.91	7.80
22	9.01	8.23	8.10	7.94	8.40	8.80	9.09	8.68	8.27	8.41	7.90	7.73
23	9.09	8.13	8.05	7.99	8.44	8.81	9.10	8.65	8.28	8.29	7.93	7.70
24	8.84	8.23	8.02	7.99	8.45	8.72	9.14	8.62	8.31	8.23	7.97	7.71
25	8.96	8.26	7.96	7.98	8.51	8.69	9.15	8.56	8.31	8.20	8.02	7.73
26	8.94	8.30	7.87	7.86	8.50	8.66	9.16	8.54	8.38	8.19	8.04	7.74
27	9.08	8.25	7.76	7.96	8.54	8.75	9.15	8.51	8.40	8.12	8.05	7.74
28	8.99	8.03	7.71	7.97	8.56	8.79	9.13	8.48	8.33	8.12	8.06	7.74
29	9.07	8.02	7.62	7.98	---	8.79	9.12	8.50	8.43	8.12	8.07	7.71
30	9.11	7.93	7.57	8.03	---	8.80	8.47	8.51	8.44	8.00	8.07	7.67
31	9.03	---	7.56	8.05	---	8.80	---	8.53	---	7.98	8.07	---
MEAN	8.90	8.09	8.06	7.79	8.29	8.70	9.04	8.52	8.35	8.26	7.99	7.91

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 8.33 HIGHEST 7.38 NOV. 6, 1992 LOWEST 9.22 APR. 10, 26, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182441066082600. Local number, 219.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'41", long 66°08'26", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.47 mi west of Fort Buchanan Military Res. main gate, 1.74 mi northeast of Bayamón plaza, and 1.88 mi southwest of P.R. National Cemetry. Owner: U.S. Department of Defense, Name: Ft. Buchanan No. 1, Buchanan Park well.

AQUIFER.--Cibao Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 10 in (0.25 m), cased 10 in (0.25 m) 0-270 ft (0-82.3 m), perforated 46-685 ft (14.0-20.7 m), 88-120 ft (26.8-36.6 m), 160-191 ft (48.8-58.2 m), 240-270 ft (73.2-82.3 m). Depth 270 ft (82.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 66.0 ft (20.1 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 0.75 ft (0.23 m) above land-surface datum. Prior June 30, 1986, top of shelter floor, 3.59 ft (1.09 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 34.97 ft (10.66 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 12-14 1989; lowest water level recorded, 50.40 ft (15.4 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 30, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	49.00	45.75	45.16	45.82	47.80	49.00	47.88	46.09	46.45	45.39	50.36
2	---	49.01	45.76	45.17	45.88	47.88	49.04	47.73	46.16	46.46	45.49	50.36
3	---	48.98	45.79	45.18	45.94	47.97	49.05	47.69	46.22	46.42	45.59	50.33
4	---	48.42	45.78	45.21	46.05	48.02	49.07	47.62	46.27	46.35	45.66	50.27
5	---	48.02	45.78	45.22	46.09	48.03	49.08	47.61	46.34	46.31	45.72	50.20
6	---	47.58	45.78	45.21	46.11	48.08	49.14	47.58	46.40	46.32	45.79	50.17
7	---	47.46	45.81	45.20	46.16	48.17	49.18	47.46	46.43	46.35	---	50.13
8	---	47.31	45.84	45.12	46.21	48.21	49.22	47.20	46.46	46.29	---	50.10
9	---	47.21	45.85	45.06	46.29	48.24	49.27	47.05	46.49	46.28	---	50.07
10	---	47.15	45.90	45.10	46.35	48.29	49.28	47.00	46.56	46.31	---	50.03
11	---	47.10	45.93	45.11	46.42	48.37	49.31	46.96	46.61	46.25	---	49.87
12	---	47.07	46.00	45.13	46.50	48.41	49.25	46.91	46.66	46.02	---	49.74
13	48.42	46.91	46.07	45.16	46.60	48.45	49.23	46.92	46.69	45.91	---	49.64
14	48.50	46.82	46.10	45.19	46.69	48.51	49.22	46.93	46.61	45.88	---	49.57
15	48.55	46.74	46.03	45.23	46.77	48.59	49.16	46.93	46.56	45.86	---	49.50
16	48.58	46.70	45.93	45.25	46.89	48.64	49.10	46.95	46.59	45.84	---	49.46
17	48.61	46.72	45.91	45.29	46.99	48.67	49.07	46.95	46.64	45.87	---	49.41
18	48.63	46.57	45.91	45.40	47.05	48.72	49.05	46.99	46.68	45.89	---	49.35
19	48.68	46.39	45.95	45.43	47.14	48.76	49.05	47.02	46.68	45.90	---	49.29
20	48.71	46.34	45.95	45.48	47.26	48.80	49.08	47.09	46.45	45.97	---	49.26
21	48.76	46.32	45.97	45.55	47.36	48.84	49.00	47.16	46.27	46.04	---	49.22
22	48.75	46.29	46.02	45.57	47.40	48.87	48.79	47.20	46.17	46.07	---	49.10
23	48.77	46.23	46.07	45.56	47.44	48.94	48.70	47.22	46.17	45.92	---	48.98
24	48.80	46.20	46.06	45.56	47.48	48.96	48.72	47.06	46.18	45.69	---	48.91
25	48.83	46.15	45.99	45.55	47.58	48.86	48.70	46.86	46.20	45.51	---	48.87
26	48.87	46.12	45.84	45.56	47.67	48.82	48.67	46.71	46.22	45.36	---	48.83
27	48.92	46.04	45.66	45.58	47.72	48.82	48.66	46.56	46.23	45.27	---	48.75
28	48.92	45.93	45.49	45.66	47.78	48.83	48.68	46.35	46.29	45.22	---	48.75
29	48.94	45.91	45.29	45.71	---	48.85	48.70	46.21	46.34	45.23	---	48.76
30	48.97	45.82	45.17	45.77	---	48.88	48.24	46.13	46.40	45.26	50.39	48.81
31	49.00	---	45.14	45.81	---	48.95	---	46.09	---	45.33	50.38	---
MEAN	48.75	46.95	45.82	45.36	46.77	48.52	48.99	47.03	46.40	45.93	46.80	49.54

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 47.21 HIGHEST 45.03 JAN. 9, 1993 LOWEST 50.40 AUG. 30, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182413066044000. Local number, 220.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'13", long 66°04'40", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 3.85 mi southeast of Cataño plaza, 0.86 mi east of Escuela Gabriela Mistral, and 1.26 mi south of Nemesio Canales Public Housing. Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Parque San Luis Rey-Américo Miranda

AQUIFER.--Surficial Deposits-Cibao Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused artesian well, diameter 10 in (0.25 m), cased 8 in (0.20 m) 0-166 ft (0-50.6 m), perforated 39-166 ft (11.9-50.6 m). Depth 166 ft (50.6 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 16.4 ft (5.0 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1986 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +2.99 ft (+0.91 m) above land-surface datum, Feb. 6, May 8-9, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 6.48 ft (1.98 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 26, 1989

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.06	+.06	+1.15	+1.14	+1.09	+.67	+.21	+1.03	+1.00	+1.00	+1.03	+.67
2	.05	+.06	+1.15	+1.13	+1.09	+.65	+.19	+1.04	+1.00	+1.00	+1.03	+.62
3	.10	+.10	+1.15	+1.13	+1.09	+.56	+.15	+1.05	+1.00	+1.01	+1.02	+.59
4	.12	+.53	+1.14	+1.14	+1.08	+.55	+.12	+1.06	+.99	+1.01	+1.02	+.56
5	.13	+.73	+1.14	+1.14	+1.07	+.55	+.13	+1.07	+.99	+1.01	+1.02	+.54
6	.15	+.86	+1.15	+1.15	+1.06	+.52	+.11	+1.07	+.99	+1.01	+1.04	+.50
7	.17	+.92	+1.14	+1.15	+1.04	+.45	+.11	+1.07	+.98	+1.01	+1.03	+.55
8	.20	+.93	+1.14	+1.15	+1.01	+.46	+.10	+1.04	+.99	+1.01	+1.03	+.55
9	.23	+.98	+1.12	+1.14	+.98	+.45	+.11	+1.04	+.98	+1.02	+1.03	+.52
10	.27	+.97	+1.11	+1.15	+.93	+.42	+.11	+1.04	+.98	+1.02	+1.04	+.48
11	.29	+.96	+1.11	+1.15	+.85	+.40	+.03	+1.04	+.98	+1.02	+1.02	+.45
12	.33	+.98	+1.11	+1.16	+.86	+.38	+.16	+1.05	+.98	+1.03	+1.02	+.44
13	.35	+1.02	+1.10	+1.16	+.84	+.34	+.20	+1.04	+.98	+1.03	+1.01	+.41
14	.36	+1.08	+1.11	+1.17	+.81	+.33	+.23	+1.05	+1.00	+1.03	+1.01	+.38
15	.38	+1.06	+1.17	+1.15	+.78	+.32	+.30	+1.03	+.98	+1.02	+1.01	+.35
16	.35	+1.04	+1.18	+1.15	+.76	+.32	+.33	+1.01	+.98	+1.02	+1.02	+.34
17	.40	+1.06	+1.17	+1.15	+.74	+.33	+.32	+1.01	+.98	+1.02	+1.01	+.31
18	.33	+1.10	+1.17	+1.14	+.71	+.31	+.32	+1.02	+.98	+1.02	+1.00	+.33
19	.31	+1.11	+1.16	+1.14	+.67	+.31	+.31	+1.00	+.99	+1.02	+.98	+.31
20	.33	+1.13	+1.16	+1.15	+.71	+.31	+.29	+.97	+1.00	+1.02	+.97	+.29
21	.36	+1.17	+1.15	+1.14	+.69	+.26	+.44	+.96	+1.01	+1.00	+.94	+.25
22	.31	+1.18	+1.14	+1.15	+.66	+.23	+.64	+.94	+1.01	+1.01	+.93	+.23
23	.29	+1.19	+1.13	+1.14	+.66	+.24	+.70	+.93	+1.01	+1.01	+.92	+.18
24	.25	+1.19	+1.14	+1.12	+.64	+.24	+.71	+.98	+1.01	+1.02	+.89	+.15
25	.22	+1.20	+1.16	+1.12	+.64	+.29	+.71	+.98	+1.01	+1.02	+.87	+.09
26	.22	+1.21	+1.18	+1.12	+.70	+.27	+.73	+.99	+1.01	+1.02	+.85	+.04
27	.18	+1.17	+1.18	+1.12	+.67	+.26	+.76	+.99	+1.00	+1.03	+.83	+.03
28	.06	+1.16	+1.18	+1.12	+.64	+.25	+.77	+1.00	+1.00	+1.03	+.80	+.53
29	.04	+1.18	+1.16	+1.12	---	+.23	+.83	+1.00	+1.01	+1.03	+.75	+.51
30	.01	+1.15	+1.16	+1.10	---	+.24	+1.02	+1.00	+1.01	+1.03	+.72	+.49
31	+.02	---	+1.16	+1.10	---	+.21	---	+1.00	---	+1.03	+.72	---
MRAN	.22	+.95	+1.15	+1.14	+.84	+.37	+.37	+1.02	+.99	+1.02	+.95	+.39

WTR YR 1993 MRAN +.75 HIGHEST +1.22 NOV. 26, 1992 LOWEST .45 OCT. 15, 1992

+ Above land-surface datum.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182511066045401. Local number, PN-2.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'11, long 66°04'54", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 1.58 mi northeast of Fort Buchanan Military Res.
 main gate, 2.95 mi southeast of Cata-o plaza, and 2.45 mi southeast of U.S. Naval Reservation in Miramar.
 Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: La Esperanza No. 2.
 AQUIFER.--Alluvium.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-40 ft (0-12.2 m),
 perforated 30-40 ft (9.15-12.2 m). Depth 40 ft (12.2 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--15-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 13 ft (3.96 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Hole on well shaft, 3.17 ft (0.97 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1989 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 8.01 ft (2.44 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 30-31,
 1992; lowest water level recorded, 11.90 ft (3.63 m) below land-surface datum, July 15-16, 1991.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	9.42	9.15	8.04	8.10	9.18	10.27	10.80	8.96	---	9.28	8.93	10.39
2	9.31	9.11	8.12	8.22	9.22	10.30	10.84	8.88	---	9.33	9.02	10.35
3	9.32	9.10	8.21	8.34	9.27	10.34	10.89	8.90	---	9.34	9.12	10.35
4	9.36	8.73	8.30	8.40	9.30	10.37	10.92	8.87	---	9.34	9.23	10.34
5	9.40	8.34	8.30	8.43	9.35	10.40	10.96	8.94	---	9.34	9.33	10.34
6	9.46	8.26	8.35	8.42	9.39	10.45	10.97	9.02	---	9.34	9.38	10.37
7	9.46	8.20	8.44	8.36	9.44	10.51	11.01	9.03	---	9.36	9.45	10.43
8	9.47	8.20	8.56	8.27	9.48	10.55	11.03	8.83	---	9.37	9.55	10.20
9	9.49	8.19	8.65	8.29	9.54	10.58	11.06	8.67	---	9.36	9.60	10.12
10	9.55	8.27	8.76	8.35	9.59	10.59	11.09	8.67	---	9.37	9.70	10.07
11	9.59	8.34	8.84	8.44	9.67	10.60	11.12	8.68	---	9.42	9.78	10.07
12	9.65	8.42	8.95	8.52	9.74	10.68	10.93	8.67	---	9.10	9.86	10.10
13	9.70	8.35	9.04	8.55	9.78	10.70	10.78	8.79	---	8.98	9.95	10.12
14	9.74	8.32	9.09	8.58	9.84	10.70	10.68	8.87	---	8.94	10.03	10.12
15	9.79	8.31	8.76	8.52	9.90	10.72	10.52	8.92	9.56	8.99	10.08	10.12
16	9.86	8.34	8.49	8.55	9.94	10.76	10.49	9.02	9.56	9.02	10.11	10.12
17	9.87	8.42	8.43	8.61	9.99	10.76	10.48	9.10	9.53	9.11	10.06	10.13
18	9.75	8.36	8.43	8.71	9.98	10.68	10.52	9.21	9.53	9.17	10.11	10.14
19	9.67	8.16	8.49	8.80	10.02	10.66	10.58	9.33	9.53	9.26	10.15	10.17
20	9.68	8.14	8.55	8.89	10.01	10.63	10.63	9.43	9.15	9.27	10.19	10.22
21	9.68	8.13	8.67	8.95	10.01	10.63	10.32	9.49	8.88	9.35	10.26	10.27
22	9.71	8.15	8.75	9.03	10.01	10.66	9.95	---	8.83	9.41	10.32	10.37
23	9.73	8.12	8.83	8.94	10.01	10.70	9.86	---	8.80	9.21	10.32	10.37
24	9.63	8.13	8.91	8.90	10.05	10.75	9.89	---	8.80	8.85	10.34	10.46
25	9.51	8.16	8.84	8.86	10.11	10.75	9.81	---	8.89	8.55	10.37	10.46
26	9.47	8.21	8.61	8.86	10.14	10.69	9.83	---	9.00	8.51	10.43	10.51
27	9.41	8.29	8.35	8.90	10.19	10.67	9.88	---	9.05	8.38	10.50	10.58
28	9.24	8.20	8.20	8.97	10.22	10.66	9.85	---	9.12	8.47	10.55	10.58
29	9.18	8.12	8.09	9.02	---	10.65	9.68	---	9.18	8.57	10.57	10.56
30	9.17	8.05	8.02	9.07	---	10.66	9.26	---	9.24	8.68	10.63	10.53
31	9.22	---	8.02	9.13	---	10.69	---	---	---	8.82	10.49	---
MEAN	9.53	8.34	8.52	8.64	9.76	10.61	10.49	8.97	9.17	9.08	9.95	10.30

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 9.47 HIGHEST 8.01 DEC. 30, 31, 1992 LOWEST 11.13 APR. 10, 11, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182435066052700. Local number, PN-5.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'35", long 66°05'27", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 2.94 mi southeast of Cata-o plaza, 0.44 mi north of Escuela Superior Gabriela Mistral, and 1.19 mi northeast of WAPA TV radio athena. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Salud Mental No. 1.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 4.0 in (0.10 m), cased 4.0 in (0.10 m), 0-83 ft (0-25.3 m), perforated 73-83 ft (22.2-25.3 m). Depth 83 ft (25.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--15-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 85 ft (25.9 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on well shaft, 2.85 ft (0.87 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1989 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 25.37 ft (7.73 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 5, 1993; lowest water level recorded, 30.23 ft (9.21 m) below land-surface datum, May 21, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	28.23	---	26.47	---	---	---	27.25	27.74	26.13	25.83	25.63	26.25
2	28.23	---	26.43	---	---	---	27.27	27.72	26.11	25.83	25.63	26.29
3	28.26	---	26.33	---	---	26.15	27.29	27.66	26.08	25.83	25.63	26.33
4	28.28	28.55	26.30	---	---	26.21	27.31	27.53	26.07	25.83	25.63	26.40
5	28.29	28.54	26.27	---	25.37	26.21	27.34	27.46	26.06	25.83	25.63	26.44
6	28.30	28.50	26.24	---	25.39	26.23	27.40	27.38	26.05	25.83	25.63	26.45
7	28.31	28.41	26.20	---	25.41	26.27	27.43	27.29	26.04	25.83	25.63	26.57
8	28.31	28.30	26.17	---	25.44	26.30	27.46	27.17	26.03	25.83	25.63	26.69
9	28.33	28.23	26.13	---	25.47	26.35	27.48	27.14	26.02	25.83	25.63	26.70
10	28.33	28.06	26.10	---	25.48	26.39	27.49	27.06	26.02	25.83	25.64	26.73
11	28.35	28.02	26.09	---	25.51	26.40	27.53	27.05	26.02	25.83	25.64	26.77
12	28.36	---	26.09	---	25.51	26.45	27.52	26.89	26.02	25.83	25.64	26.80
13	28.37	---	26.09	---	25.52	26.52	27.55	26.85	26.02	25.82	25.64	26.82
14	28.40	---	26.08	---	25.62	26.62	27.60	26.81	25.92	25.82	25.64	26.84
15	28.40	---	25.93	---	25.70	26.62	27.63	26.76	25.90	25.82	25.64	26.92
16	---	---	25.93	---	25.73	26.71	27.67	26.72	25.90	25.82	25.64	27.01
17	---	---	25.94	---	25.80	26.73	27.70	26.68	25.90	25.83	25.68	27.06
18	---	---	25.94	---	25.83	26.81	27.72	26.65	25.90	25.83	25.71	27.06
19	---	---	25.92	---	25.89	26.84	27.76	26.64	25.90	25.83	25.77	27.07
20	---	---	25.90	---	25.90	26.88	27.79	26.63	25.85	25.83	25.79	27.09
21	---	---	25.90	---	25.90	26.92	27.75	26.61	25.84	25.83	25.84	27.10
22	---	---	25.90	---	25.91	26.96	27.78	26.59	25.84	25.83	25.87	27.18
23	---	---	25.90	---	25.92	27.02	27.80	26.59	25.84	25.83	25.89	27.24
24	---	27.00	25.90	---	25.97	27.03	27.82	26.48	25.84	25.83	25.92	27.39
25	---	27.00	25.89	---	25.98	27.06	27.82	26.46	25.84	25.81	25.97	27.48
26	---	27.00	25.86	---	26.06	27.09	27.82	26.39	25.84	25.81	26.03	27.51
27	---	26.98	25.78	---	---	27.10	27.86	26.34	25.84	25.69	26.05	27.64
28	---	26.97	25.73	---	---	27.12	27.85	26.25	25.84	25.68	26.11	27.66
29	---	26.64	25.68	---	---	27.14	27.85	26.25	25.83	25.67	26.14	27.66
30	---	26.49	25.68	---	---	27.16	27.78	26.22	25.83	25.64	26.18	27.67
31	---	---	---	---	---	27.24	---	26.18	---	25.64	26.22	---
MEAN	28.32	27.65	26.03	---	25.70	26.71	27.61	26.84	25.94	25.80	25.78	26.96

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 26.55 HIGHEST 25.37 FEB. 5, 1993 LOWEST 28.66 NOV. 4, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182445066043401. Local number, PN-6.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'45", long 66°04'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.28 mi northeast of Escuela Dr. Pedreira, 3.52 mi southeast of Cataño plaza, and 0.53 mi south of Hiram Bithorn Stadium main gate. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Alsacia No. 2.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-27 ft (0-8.23 m), perforated 21-27 ft (6.40-8.23 m). Depth 27 ft (8.23 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--15-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 10 ft (3.05 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on well shaft, 3.03 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Destroyed by Municipality employee with heavy equipment. Monthly measurement with chalked steel tape by USGS personnel, automatic digital recorder reinstalled on Sept. 9, 1993.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1989 to November 27, 1991, temporary discontinued, September 9, 1993 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 3.11 ft (0.95 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 18, 1989; lowest water level measured, 9.04 ft (2.76 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 31, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.73
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.78
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.79
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.86
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.92
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	6.52	6.88	---	7.96
15	---	---	---	6.12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.06
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.06
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	6.67	---	---	---	8.06
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7.97
19	---	---	---	---	8.07	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.00
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.08
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.16
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.21
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.27
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.22
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.26
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.77	---	---	---	---	8.26
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.87	8.31
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.28
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.13
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.13
31	---	---	---	---	---	9.04	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	8.07

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 7.95 HIGHEST 6.12 JAN. 15, 1993 LOWEST 9.04 MAR. 21, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182437066040500. Local number, PN-7.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'37", long 66°04'05", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 4.03 mi southeast of Cataño plaza, 0.70 mi east of Escuela Dr. Pedreira, and 0.25 southeast of Hospital del Maestro. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Parque de las Fuentes No. 1.
 AQUIFER.--Alluvium.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-52 ft (0-15.8 m), perforated 42-52 ft (12.8-15.8 m). Depth 52 ft (15.8 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--15-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 23 ft (7.01 m) above mean sea level, from levels.
 Measuring point: Hole on well shelter floor, 3.20 ft (0.98 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Formerly published as 182437066040501, Parque de las Fuentes No. 2, which is another well.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1989 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 6.50 ft (1.98 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 27, 1989; lowest water level recorded, 12.60 ft (3.84 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 16-17, 1991.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	9.69	9.60	6.87	6.87	8.40	9.76	10.54	---	7.98	8.54	8.01	8.69
2	9.59	9.55	6.89	6.96	8.42	9.80	10.60	---	8.15	8.59	8.15	8.70
3	9.58	9.46	7.02	7.09	8.50	9.87	10.62	---	8.23	8.59	8.21	8.72
4	9.66	8.57	7.08	7.14	8.54	9.90	10.64	---	8.31	8.59	8.30	8.74
5	9.68	8.16	7.15	7.19	8.56	9.94	10.67	---	8.43	8.58	8.40	8.78
6	9.73	7.90	7.24	7.21	8.60	9.99	10.68	---	8.52	8.58	8.43	8.87
7	9.77	7.71	7.34	7.18	8.64	10.04	10.70	---	8.57	8.58	8.53	8.69
8	9.82	7.68	7.42	7.11	8.70	10.07	10.73	---	8.57	8.58	8.62	8.49
9	9.85	7.68	7.53	7.10	8.78	10.09	10.75	---	8.60	8.58	8.69	8.40
10	9.93	7.71	7.64	7.16	8.82	10.12	10.77	8.25	8.65	8.58	8.77	8.38
11	9.98	7.81	7.75	7.22	8.91	10.16	10.82	8.25	8.70	8.53	8.84	8.37
12	10.04	7.86	7.89	7.28	8.98	10.18	10.70	8.25	8.78	8.25	---	8.36
13	10.11	7.82	7.97	7.36	9.00	10.23	10.64	8.33	8.81	8.16	---	8.44
14	10.16	7.74	8.07	7.40	9.05	10.28	10.57	8.39	---	8.13	---	8.45
15	10.21	7.72	7.56	7.44	9.14	10.33	10.46	8.42	8.78	8.13	---	8.48
16	10.25	7.72	7.26	7.44	9.22	10.33	10.37	8.57	8.78	8.14	---	8.52
17	---	7.81	7.15	7.49	9.30	10.33	10.30	8.64	8.77	8.20	---	8.53
18	---	7.68	7.14	7.62	9.31	10.33	10.24	8.70	8.77	8.29	---	8.53
19	---	7.30	7.17	7.72	---	10.35	9.96	8.80	8.75	8.39	---	8.54
20	---	7.25	7.24	7.82	9.41	10.40	9.85	8.81	8.40	8.40	---	8.59
21	---	7.06	7.35	7.91	9.43	10.45	9.81	8.83	8.23	8.50	---	8.75
22	---	7.01	7.42	8.01	9.47	10.49	9.81	8.85	8.21	8.53	---	9.07
23	---	6.96	7.51	8.01	9.49	10.51	---	8.76	8.19	8.40	---	9.33
24	---	6.94	7.58	8.01	9.51	10.45	---	8.63	8.19	8.12	---	9.52
25	---	7.04	7.54	8.05	9.56	10.41	---	8.43	8.22	7.87	---	9.70
26	---	7.14	7.39	8.06	9.64	10.40	---	8.26	8.27	7.79	---	9.73
27	---	7.19	7.19	8.15	9.69	10.40	---	7.95	8.37	7.64	---	9.75
28	---	7.09	7.04	8.21	9.72	10.41	---	7.87	8.42	7.62	8.91	9.87
29	---	7.03	6.90	8.32	---	10.46	---	7.80	8.44	7.69	8.93	9.53
30	9.70	6.89	6.75	8.34	---	10.49	---	7.80	8.45	7.78	8.94	10.26
31	9.66	---	6.75	8.37	---	---	---	7.92	---	7.93	8.95	---
MEAN	9.86	7.70	7.32	7.59	9.07	10.23	10.46	8.39	8.47	8.27	8.58	8.89

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 8.65 HIGHEST 6.74 DEC. 30, 1992 LOWEST 10.82 APR. 11, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182443066041502. Local number, PN-8c.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'43", long 66°04'15", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 2.29 mi east of Fort Buchanan Military Res. main gate, 3.83 mi southeast of Cataño plaza, and 0.16 mi southwest of Hospital del Maestro. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Parque Luis Muñoz Marín 1C.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10), 0-33 ft (0-10.1 m), perforated 33-40 ft (10.1-12.2 m). Depth 40 ft (12.2 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--15-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 13 ft (3.96 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on well shaft, 3.66 ft (1.12 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1989 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 10.35 ft (3.15 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 25, 1989; lowest water level recorded, 15.46 ft (4.71 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 28-29, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	14.32	11.53	10.71	10.81	13.07	14.11	14.50	---	13.03	13.70	12.74	14.30
2	14.36	11.73	10.84	10.94	13.14	14.16	14.51	---	13.42	---	12.85	14.34
3	14.42	11.85	11.01	11.08	13.18	14.18	14.53	---	13.57	---	12.99	14.36
4	14.44	11.81	11.13	11.21	13.25	14.20	14.54	---	13.65	---	13.08	14.38
5	14.45	11.86	11.33	11.31	13.29	14.21	14.54	---	---	---	13.17	14.40
6	14.48	11.96	11.53	11.37	13.35	14.23	14.54	---	---	---	13.26	14.40
7	14.51	12.05	11.73	11.24	13.41	14.26	14.56	---	---	---	13.32	14.07
8	14.55	12.16	11.87	11.13	13.45	14.28	14.56	---	---	---	13.41	14.17
9	14.49	11.94	12.01	11.16	13.51	14.30	14.52	---	---	---	13.49	14.20
10	14.54	11.38	12.14	11.24	13.55	14.23	14.56	---	---	---	13.55	14.23
11	14.52	11.44	12.27	11.32	13.58	14.23	14.60	---	---	---	13.61	14.19
12	14.58	11.13	12.43	11.43	13.61	14.25	14.41	---	---	---	13.67	14.27
13	14.65	11.07	12.57	11.54	13.63	14.28	14.49	---	---	13.10	13.72	14.29
14	14.71	10.99	12.66	11.66	13.68	14.32	14.40	---	---	13.12	13.79	14.31
15	14.71	---	11.55	11.78	13.72	14.36	14.41	---	13.74	13.17	13.85	14.34
16	14.74	---	11.62	11.84	13.73	14.37	14.48	---	13.72	13.20	13.85	14.35
17	14.70	---	11.64	11.96	13.76	14.32	14.49	---	13.83	13.29	13.90	14.38
18	14.73	---	11.71	12.07	13.77	14.36	14.48	13.53	13.89	13.35	13.95	14.30
19	14.73	---	11.79	12.15	13.85	14.39	14.51	13.59	13.59	13.40	14.00	14.33
20	14.77	---	11.89	12.25	13.88	14.42	14.52	13.64	13.28	13.50	14.04	14.37
21	14.41	---	12.00	12.36	13.93	14.45	14.35	13.70	13.32	13.55	14.08	14.45
22	14.27	---	12.07	12.44	13.95	14.49	13.99	13.75	13.32	13.54	14.11	14.46
23	14.28	---	12.16	12.38	13.97	14.49	14.08	13.83	13.35	12.99	14.13	14.51
24	14.26	11.01	12.08	12.53	13.99	14.49	---	13.55	13.38	12.76	14.16	14.52
25	14.01	11.06	12.15	12.60	14.01	14.18	---	13.53	13.46	12.49	14.20	14.59
26	11.90	11.19	11.85	12.66	14.05	14.33	---	13.42	13.52	12.35	14.23	14.61
27	11.86	11.23	11.62	12.74	14.08	14.37	---	12.90	13.56	12.13	14.26	14.62
28	11.61	10.77	11.40	12.83	14.10	14.40	---	12.63	13.60	12.28	14.29	14.62
29	11.37	10.92	11.14	12.90	---	14.43	---	12.63	13.62	12.37	14.30	14.58
30	11.31	10.71	10.79	12.96	---	14.45	---	12.70	13.65	12.52	14.21	14.61
31	11.35	---	10.75	13.03	---	14.48	---	12.77	---	12.63	14.27	---
MEAN	13.94	11.42	11.69	11.90	13.66	14.32	14.46	13.30	13.52	12.97	13.76	14.38

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 13.30 HIGHEST 10.70 NOV. 30, DEC. 1, 1992 LOWEST 14.77 OCT. 20, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182417066042700. Local number, PN-10.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'17", long 66°04'27", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 3.96 mi southeast of Cataño plaza, 1.00 mi southwest of Escuela J.J. Osuna, and 2.26 mi east of WAPA TV radio antenna. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Las Américas No. 1.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, cased 4.0 in (0.10 m), 0-80 ft (0-24.39 m), 4.0 in (0.10 m), perforated pipe 80-90 ft (24.39-27.43 m). Depth 90 ft (27.43 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--15-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 16 ft (4.89 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on well shaft, 3.10 ft (0.95 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1989 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +2.30 ft (+0.70 m) above land-surface datum, Jan. 9-12, 1993; lowest water level recorded, 2.48 ft (0.76 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 26-27, 1989.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	+0.90	+0.76	+1.81	+2.15	+1.96	+1.46	+1.04	+1.30	+1.75	+1.68	+2.06	+0.57
2	+0.92	+0.79	+1.83	+2.18	+1.93	+1.44	+1.01	+1.39	+1.74	+1.66	+2.06	+0.37
3	+0.92	+0.82	+1.84	+2.20	+1.93	+1.41	+0.97	+1.44	+1.70	+1.65	+2.04	+0.30
4	+0.93	+0.81	+1.85	+2.22	+1.92	+1.38	+0.80	+1.49	+1.68	+1.64	+1.99	+0.28
5	+0.91	+0.92	+1.85	+2.24	+1.90	+1.36	+0.80	+1.50	+1.65	+1.63	+1.96	+0.33
6	+0.89	+1.07	+1.85	+2.25	+1.89	+1.36	+0.79	+1.51	+1.62	+1.62	+1.92	+0.41
7	+0.85	+1.17	+1.84	+2.26	+1.88	+1.34	+0.77	+1.54	+1.60	+1.59	+1.91	+0.57
8	+0.84	+1.24	+1.82	+2.28	+1.89	+1.31	+0.76	+1.57	+1.58	+1.60	+1.88	+0.63
9	+0.83	+1.30	+1.82	+2.29	+1.87	+1.30	+0.75	+1.58	+1.57	+1.61	+1.84	+0.69
10	+0.82	+1.35	+1.81	+2.30	+1.86	+1.29	+0.72	+1.59	+1.57	+1.60	+1.82	+0.78
11	+0.81	+1.37	+1.79	+2.29	+1.82	+1.28	+0.71	+1.59	+1.55	+1.60	+1.80	+0.89
12	+0.80	+1.39	+1.77	+2.30	+1.80	+1.27	+0.76	+1.59	+1.52	+1.67	+1.77	+0.95
13	+0.77	+1.42	+1.74	+2.24	+1.78	+1.25	+0.78	+1.58	+1.50	+1.73	+1.71	+1.00
14	+0.74	+1.45	+1.72	+2.24	+1.76	+1.23	+0.80	+1.57	+1.51	+1.75	+1.54	+0.99
15	+0.72	+1.48	+1.71	+2.23	+1.73	+1.20	+0.83	+1.56	+1.52	+1.76	+1.50	+1.03
16	+0.71	+1.50	+1.76	+2.21	+1.68	+1.19	+0.85	+1.54	+1.52	+1.78	+1.49	+1.09
17	+0.70	+1.52	+1.79	+2.19	+1.63	+1.19	+0.84	+1.51	+1.54	+1.79	+1.49	+1.12
18	+0.70	+1.54	+1.82	+2.16	+1.60	+1.19	+0.85	+1.50	+1.55	+1.78	+1.48	+1.16
19	+0.70	+1.56	+1.83	+2.11	+1.58	+1.19	+0.86	+1.48	+1.57	+1.76	+1.47	+1.16
20	+0.53	+1.61	+1.84	+2.08	+1.58	+1.20	+0.86	+1.46	+1.63	+1.76	+1.45	+1.17
21	+0.50	+1.67	+1.84	+2.06	+1.57	+1.18	+0.89	+1.43	+1.71	+1.75	+1.20	+1.17
22	+0.49	+1.73	+1.83	+2.03	+1.56	+1.16	+0.93	+1.41	+1.77	+1.75	+0.03	+0.34
23	+0.52	+1.77	+1.82	+2.03	+1.55	+1.16	+0.98	+1.39	+1.78	+1.77	+0.29	+0.25
24	+0.53	+1.79	+1.80	+2.02	+1.55	+1.14	+1.01	+1.40	+1.78	+1.84	+0.39	+0.04
25	+0.56	+1.80	+1.81	+2.01	+1.52	---	+1.04	+1.45	+1.77	+1.92	+0.38	+0.03
26	+0.57	+1.74	+1.85	+2.01	+1.51	---	+1.06	+1.51	+1.75	+1.98	+0.36	+0.17
27	+0.59	+1.71	+1.89	+2.00	+1.49	---	+1.10	+1.58	+1.73	+2.05	+0.47	+0.29
28	+0.64	+1.72	+1.95	+1.98	+1.48	---	+1.12	+1.66	+1.72	+2.07	+0.37	+0.42
29	+0.69	+1.73	+2.02	+1.99	---	---	+1.13	+1.70	+1.70	+2.07	+0.44	+0.47
30	+0.72	+1.78	+2.07	+1.99	---	---	+1.18	+1.73	+1.70	+2.08	+0.99	+0.49
31	+0.74	---	+2.11	+1.96	---	---	---	+1.74	---	+2.08	+0.85	---
MEAN	+0.73	+1.42	+1.84	+2.15	+1.72	+1.27	+0.90	+1.53	+1.64	+1.77	+1.32	+0.64

WTR YR 1993 MEAN +1.41 HIGHEST +2.30 JAN. 9-12, 1993 LOWEST 0.23 AUG. 22, 1993

+ Above land-surface datum

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182349066032600. Local number, PN-13.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'49", long 66°03'26", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 5.15 mi southeast of Cataño plaza, 1.28 mi south of Escuela J.J. Osuna, and 0.69 mi southwest of University of Puerto Rico main gate. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Jardín Botánico No. 1.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m) cased 4.0 in (0.10 m), 0-45 ft (0-13.72 m), perforated 35-45 ft (10.67-13.72 m). Depth 45 ft (13.72 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--15-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 32 ft (9.75 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on well shaft, 2.84 ft (0.86 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1989 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 8.75 ft (2.67 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 18, 1989; lowest water level recorded, 17.08 ft (5.20 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 16, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	16.55	16.56	15.18	15.26	---	16.40	16.59	15.92	16.17	16.32	16.05	16.59
2	16.64	16.53	15.32	15.28	---	16.40	16.60	16.04	16.19	16.32	16.07	16.61
3	16.69	16.10	15.37	14.95	---	16.41	16.61	16.05	16.21	16.12	16.12	16.63
4	16.70	13.30	15.36	15.27	---	16.43	16.63	16.00	16.24	16.25	16.19	16.63
5	16.67	15.50	15.39	15.30	---	16.44	16.63	16.12	16.26	16.29	16.19	16.65
6	16.73	15.69	15.50	15.31	---	16.47	16.67	16.18	16.30	16.31	16.21	16.61
7	16.74	15.75	15.55	15.34	---	16.49	16.69	16.18	16.31	16.31	16.24	16.24
8	16.77	15.79	15.57	15.33	---	16.50	16.65	16.00	16.32	16.00	16.27	16.41
9	16.56	15.73	15.65	---	---	16.51	16.59	16.00	16.27	16.12	16.28	16.45
10	16.65	15.83	15.68	---	---	16.52	16.66	16.02	16.21	16.19	16.30	16.46
11	16.57	15.92	15.71	---	---	16.53	16.73	16.04	16.31	13.78	16.33	16.44
12	16.72	15.84	15.72	---	---	16.55	16.54	16.15	16.36	15.56	16.37	16.58
13	16.79	15.68	15.75	---	---	16.55	16.61	16.20	16.37	15.85	16.41	16.47
14	16.81	15.71	15.74	---	---	16.58	16.36	16.08	16.30	15.91	16.42	16.57
15	16.75	15.75	14.52	---	---	16.60	16.57	16.20	16.30	16.00	16.43	16.60
16	16.81	15.74	15.01	---	---	16.57	16.64	16.28	16.25	16.02	16.28	16.60
17	16.70	15.67	15.07	15.62	---	16.47	16.68	16.31	16.34	16.07	16.43	16.63
18	16.82	15.26	15.15	15.66	---	16.54	16.68	16.33	16.39	16.15	16.46	16.54
19	16.78	15.13	15.18	15.66	16.20	16.57	16.73	16.36	15.21	16.13	16.47	16.56
20	16.83	15.35	15.27	15.70	16.11	16.59	16.76	16.38	15.70	16.19	16.49	16.63
21	16.81	15.28	15.30	15.75	16.22	16.61	16.59	16.41	16.05	16.22	16.51	16.69
22	16.66	14.88	15.28	---	16.25	16.63	16.30	16.38	16.10	16.15	16.53	16.64
23	16.82	15.26	15.27	---	16.27	16.63	16.54	16.43	16.18	14.79	16.53	16.71
24	16.74	15.28	14.44	---	16.27	16.58	16.57	16.01	16.19	15.43	16.56	16.65
25	16.73	15.36	15.06	---	16.28	16.20	16.58	16.14	16.24	15.71	16.59	16.74
26	16.83	15.50	14.41	---	16.33	16.42	16.56	16.25	16.26	15.80	16.59	16.72
27	16.82	14.84	15.10	---	16.34	16.51	16.58	15.77	16.27	15.47	16.60	16.73
28	16.72	12.82	15.23	---	16.37	16.54	16.60	15.89	16.29	15.84	16.61	16.74
29	16.74	15.15	15.26	---	---	16.56	16.43	15.96	16.24	15.85	16.62	16.69
30	16.75	14.85	15.27	---	---	16.57	15.40	16.05	16.26	16.01	16.44	16.78
31	16.50	---	15.35	---	---	16.58	---	16.14	---	16.04	16.56	---
MEAN	16.72	15.40	15.28	15.42	16.26	16.51	16.56	16.14	16.20	15.91	16.39	16.60

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 16.14 HIGHEST 11.78 DEC. 15, 1992 LOWEST 16.83 OCT. 20, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

477

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182406066034700. Local number, PN-19.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'06", long 66°03'47", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 4.65 mi southeast of Cataño plaza, 0.89 mi south of Escuela J.J. Osuna, and 0.78 mi southwest of University of Puerto Rico main gate. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Jardín Botánico No. 3.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m) cased 4.0 in (0.10 m), 0-48 ft (0-14.6 m), perforated 38-48 ft (11.6-14.6 m). Depth 48 ft (14.6 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--15-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 32 ft (9.75 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on well shaft, 2.91 ft (0.88 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1991 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 3.35 ft (1.02 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 30, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 8.23 ft (2.51 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 28, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	6.39	6.18	3.49	3.48	4.79	6.35	7.56	---	4.20	4.83	4.13	---
2	6.35	6.13	3.58	3.60	4.83	6.39	7.59	---	4.28	4.94	4.21	---
3	6.36	5.98	3.68	3.69	4.87	6.49	7.68	---	4.42	4.85	4.32	6.58
4	6.40	5.27	3.76	3.70	4.92	6.55	7.72	---	4.61	4.76	4.45	6.60
5	6.42	4.95	3.79	3.74	5.00	6.57	7.72	---	4.72	4.75	4.57	6.62
6	6.47	4.73	3.84	3.71	5.08	6.62	7.73	---	4.81	4.81	4.68	6.66
7	6.51	4.64	4.00	3.67	5.12	6.67	7.74	---	4.96	4.94	4.75	6.03
8	6.55	4.60	4.08	3.55	5.21	6.73	7.76	---	5.02	4.74	4.84	5.91
9	6.63	4.53	4.14	3.57	5.27	6.77	7.83	---	5.07	4.72	4.96	5.91
10	6.67	4.49	4.20	3.65	5.35	6.81	7.85	---	5.10	4.73	5.05	5.95
11	6.73	4.50	4.26	3.72	5.42	6.88	7.87	---	5.16	4.49	5.14	6.00
12	6.76	4.54	4.33	3.76	5.48	6.95	7.73	---	5.24	4.16	5.25	6.04
13	6.84	4.24	4.41	3.78	5.49	6.98	7.73	---	5.28	4.13	5.35	6.08
14	6.90	4.19	4.54	3.81	5.58	7.03	7.73	---	5.25	4.14	5.45	6.11
15	6.92	4.19	4.11	3.83	5.67	7.06	7.48	---	5.23	4.15	5.52	6.14
16	6.93	4.21	3.94	3.88	5.74	7.08	7.47	---	5.13	4.17	5.56	6.16
17	6.93	4.19	3.91	3.94	5.78	7.11	7.46	4.94	5.10	4.25	5.59	6.22
18	6.94	3.95	3.90	4.10	5.79	7.11	7.47	5.01	5.15	4.33	5.65	6.24
19	6.97	3.75	3.96	4.17	5.84	7.13	7.48	5.09	5.08	4.44	5.71	6.27
20	7.01	3.76	3.98	4.23	5.86	7.19	7.49	5.16	4.53	4.54	5.75	6.35
21	7.12	3.64	4.06	4.29	5.92	7.26	7.33	5.23	4.36	4.67	5.82	6.42
22	7.13	3.64	4.12	4.34	6.01	7.34	6.28	5.30	4.35	4.70	5.92	6.48
23	7.13	3.55	4.19	4.33	6.06	7.41	6.20	5.35	4.33	4.33	5.98	6.54
24	7.04	3.57	4.21	4.32	6.08	7.43	6.25	5.15	4.35	4.01	6.06	6.55
25	6.97	3.68	4.07	4.34	6.16	7.42	6.08	4.92	4.42	3.84	---	6.61
26	6.95	3.77	3.79	4.38	6.22	7.41	5.87	4.70	4.53	3.81	---	6.66
27	6.95	3.82	3.65	4.42	6.26	7.43	5.87	4.39	4.65	3.74	---	6.73
28	6.51	3.66	3.56	4.49	6.28	7.46	5.89	4.15	4.72	3.75	---	6.75
29	6.41	3.60	3.46	4.58	---	7.47	5.72	4.14	4.77	3.82	---	6.76
30	6.41	3.47	3.37	4.65	---	7.49	4.88	4.14	4.77	3.96	---	6.83
31	6.29	---	3.38	4.71	---	7.52	---	4.15	---	4.04	---	---
MEAN	6.73	4.31	3.93	4.01	5.57	7.04	7.12	4.79	4.79	4.37	5.20	6.36

WTR YR 1993 MRAN 5.37 HIGHEST 3.35 DEC. 30, 1992 LOWEST 7.87 APR. 11, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

181550065593200. Local number, 50.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'50", long 65°59'32", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 1.36 mi northwest of Gurabo plaza, 0.70 mi north of Estación Experimental Agrícola, and 2.42 mi southwest of Escuela José M. Gallardo. Owner: Gurabo Agricultural Experimental Station, Name: Gurabo.

AQUIFER.--Unconsolidated deposits of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 13 in (0.34 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-145 ft (0-44.2 m). Depth 145 ft (44.2 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 148 ft (45.1 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 12 in (0.30 m) casing, 0.80 ft (0.24 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Automatic digital recorder installed on September 18, 1991.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1960 to March 1985, September 1991 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 12.6 ft (3.86 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 9, 1975; lowest water level measured, 44.4 ft (13.5 m) below land-surface datum, June 18, 1975.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	28.30	28.71	30.57	29.17	30.54	30.25	32.24	31.11	26.90	26.88	26.94	28.69
2	28.40	28.73	30.58	29.12	30.48	30.32	32.34	30.71	26.86	26.65	27.16	28.73
3	28.49	27.86	30.01	29.19	30.51	30.35	32.43	30.44	27.97	26.77	27.38	28.88
4	28.52	27.60	29.75	29.15	30.52	30.32	32.50	30.43	28.45	26.85	27.45	28.96
5	28.57	27.38	29.69	29.27	30.50	30.35	32.56	30.31	28.69	26.82	27.48	28.98
6	28.61	27.85	29.64	29.28	30.45	30.41	32.59	30.16	28.88	26.95	27.47	28.94
7	28.48	28.15	29.58	29.22	30.33	30.54	32.69	29.85	29.03	26.98	27.61	28.97
8	28.56	28.31	29.63	29.23	30.41	30.55	32.79	29.62	29.10	27.05	27.61	29.04
9	28.68	28.40	29.61	29.27	30.46	30.60	32.85	29.44	29.06	27.19	27.59	29.01
10	28.67	28.42	29.60	29.29	30.47	30.68	32.85	29.35	28.90	27.30	27.57	29.05
11	28.69	28.42	29.58	29.39	30.39	30.78	32.92	29.53	28.73	27.03	27.67	28.95
12	28.69	28.48	29.59	29.40	30.33	30.88	32.97	29.57	28.72	26.06	27.70	29.08
13	28.72	28.49	29.58	29.39	30.26	30.97	33.05	29.60	28.64	26.42	27.74	29.15
14	27.75	28.52	29.53	29.38	30.25	31.11	32.98	29.52	28.56	26.70	27.68	29.12
15	27.43	28.54	29.58	30.02	30.18	31.25	29.66	29.50	28.49	26.74	27.79	29.12
16	28.29	28.60	29.60	30.14	30.22	31.32	26.56	29.52	28.54	26.92	27.80	29.09
17	28.52	28.22	29.62	30.22	30.18	31.34	27.40	29.35	28.49	27.04	27.76	29.06
18	27.62	29.16	29.60	30.32	30.13	31.40	30.38	29.38	28.36	27.11	27.88	29.07
19	24.66	29.93	29.68	30.36	30.11	31.45	31.23	29.43	28.38	27.04	27.89	29.05
20	23.71	30.23	29.73	30.32	30.16	31.05	31.59	29.65	28.25	27.42	27.88	---
21	23.65	30.31	29.82	30.30	30.16	30.50	31.62	29.79	28.12	26.29	27.88	---
22	23.04	30.57	29.85	30.25	30.13	30.23	31.66	29.87	28.17	25.96	27.84	---
23	23.38	30.70	29.78	30.39	30.09	30.92	31.74	29.90	27.62	25.66	27.57	---
24	26.78	30.75	29.77	30.55	30.08	31.29	31.82	29.75	26.82	25.49	27.34	---
25	27.60	30.91	29.76	30.49	30.11	30.74	31.87	29.65	26.26	25.68	27.85	---
26	28.05	30.96	29.69	30.40	30.11	31.11	31.88	29.57	26.14	25.60	28.35	---
27	28.26	30.95	29.56	30.41	30.12	31.45	31.91	29.53	26.69	25.82	28.53	---
28	28.41	30.78	29.47	30.53	30.16	31.67	31.91	28.70	26.87	26.01	28.55	---
29	28.51	30.69	29.46	30.54	---	31.83	31.93	27.55	26.88	25.05	28.59	---
30	28.62	30.59	29.35	30.53	---	31.98	31.48	27.21	26.67	24.24	28.61	27.96
31	28.72	---	29.26	30.56	---	32.13	---	26.99	---	26.17	28.63	---
MEAN	27.56	29.24	29.69	29.87	30.28	30.96	31.75	29.52	27.97	26.45	27.80	28.94

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 29.16 HIGHEST 22.74-OCT. 23, 1992 LOWEST 33.08 APR. 13, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

182515065594100. Local number, 222.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'15", long 65°59'41", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 3.56 mi northwest of Carolina plaza, 1.21 mi northwest of Escuela Extensión El Comandante, and 0.74 mi southwest of Escuela Vistamar. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: Campo Rico TW-1.
 AQUIFER.--Surficial Deposits.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m). Depth 100 ft (30.5 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 10.0 ft (3.05 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 0.80 ft (0.24 m) above land-surface datum. Prior July 28, 1986, top of shelter floor, 3.10 ft (0.94 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1986 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 4.42 ft (1.35 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 31, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 7.42 ft (2.26 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 9, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.64	5.74	5.63	5.71	5.80	5.86	5.90	5.73	6.08	6.19	5.75	5.55
2	5.67	5.68	5.66	5.70	5.73	5.77	5.96	5.83	6.07	6.02	5.66	5.49
3	5.69	5.63	5.69	5.64	5.75	5.76	5.94	5.90	6.09	5.93	5.67	5.47
4	5.64	5.24	5.63	5.72	5.66	5.83	5.89	5.98	6.06	5.89	5.67	5.49
5	5.65	5.37	5.65	5.60	5.56	5.81	5.77	5.92	6.07	5.87	5.64	5.49
6	5.60	5.17	5.56	5.53	5.57	5.77	5.79	5.89	6.07	5.87	5.65	5.51
7	5.56	5.05	5.54	5.56	5.57	5.79	5.82	5.80	6.06	5.87	5.66	5.56
8	5.39	5.15	5.42	5.55	5.68	5.84	5.81	5.78	6.01	5.88	5.76	5.74
9	5.39	5.14	5.37	5.53	5.69	5.84	5.86	5.78	6.02	5.90	5.81	5.86
10	5.24	5.11	5.40	5.60	5.84	5.82	5.87	5.82	6.07	5.92	5.83	5.89
11	5.23	5.14	5.41	5.66	5.93	5.83	5.86	5.90	6.12	5.89	5.89	5.83
12	5.34	5.16	5.44	5.74	5.86	5.89	5.84	5.92	6.12	5.86	5.91	5.71
13	5.32	5.13	5.50	5.79	5.88	5.89	5.80	5.91	6.08	5.88	5.91	5.65
14	5.39	5.20	5.51	5.87	5.78	5.87	5.74	5.91	6.08	6.01	5.86	5.46
15	5.44	5.19	5.38	5.87	5.74	5.90	5.80	5.90	6.07	6.05	5.78	5.29
16	5.54	5.36	5.37	5.78	5.74	5.87	5.84	5.89	6.08	5.94	5.71	5.15
17	5.51	5.41	5.44	5.75	5.79	5.99	5.89	5.92	6.10	5.88	5.49	5.09
18	5.55	5.33	5.47	5.75	5.73	5.91	5.89	5.97	6.15	5.79	5.46	5.13
19	5.63	5.23	5.49	5.73	5.59	5.85	5.86	6.02	6.06	5.68	5.45	5.27
20	5.63	5.13	5.56	5.68	5.67	5.82	5.79	5.90	5.90	5.68	5.49	5.44
21	5.65	4.99	5.56	5.70	5.69	5.83	5.79	5.90	6.02	5.66	5.49	5.58
22	5.50	4.88	5.48	5.62	5.81	5.93	5.81	5.85	5.91	5.64	5.58	5.71
23	5.35	5.03	5.58	5.76	5.87	5.96	5.82	5.87	5.93	5.62	5.75	5.68
24	5.15	5.15	5.63	5.67	5.83	5.99	5.85	5.83	5.97	5.68	5.83	5.66
25	5.04	5.20	5.55	5.72	5.85	6.01	5.84	5.83	6.11	5.83	5.91	5.60
26	5.16	5.29	5.48	5.73	5.82	6.01	5.90	5.89	6.22	5.87	5.94	5.49
27	5.21	5.39	5.48	5.60	5.95	5.96	5.84	5.89	6.24	5.88	5.87	5.50
28	5.32	5.44	5.56	5.62	5.93	5.94	5.73	5.91	6.26	5.89	5.70	5.39
29	5.44	5.56	5.57	5.64	---	5.89	5.75	5.95	6.24	5.93	5.63	5.22
30	5.54	5.60	5.66	5.70	---	5.88	5.63	6.05	6.20	5.87	5.56	5.21
31	5.63	---	5.77	5.77	---	5.88	---	6.06	---	5.82	5.50	---
MEAN	5.45	5.27	5.53	5.69	5.76	5.88	5.83	5.89	6.08	5.86	5.70	5.50

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 5.70 HIGHEST 4.83 NOV. 22, 1992 LOWEST 6.32 JUNE 18, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

181513065554601. Local number, CJ-TW3B.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'13", long 65°55'46", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 2.86 mi east of Gurabo plaza, 3.57 mi southwest of Hwy 186 km 4.7, and 1.39 mi southwest of Hwy 185 km 15.7. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CJ-TW3B.
 AQUIFER.--Unconsolidated deposits of Quaternary Age.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-38 ft (0-11.6 m) screened 25-35 ft (7.62 m). Depth 38 ft (11.6 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 187 ft (57.0 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Top of casing 2.95 ft (0.90 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Observation well. Automatic digital recorder installed on September 17, 1991.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1991 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 13.4 ft (4.09 m) below land-surface datum, June 13-14, Dec. 3-4, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 18.4 ft (5.61 m) below land-surface datum, May 1-2, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	17.79	18.06	13.75	14.18	15.37	16.47	17.55	17.75	17.24	17.06	15.06	16.24
2	17.81	18.06	13.50	14.10	15.43	16.53	17.59	17.45	17.28	17.08	15.11	16.29
3	17.83	18.09	13.42	14.05	15.46	16.57	17.62	16.99	17.31	17.10	15.16	16.34
4	17.84	18.10	13.41	14.10	15.45	16.62	17.65	16.68	17.35	17.12	15.20	16.36
5	17.86	18.07	13.48	14.15	15.45	16.64	17.67	16.53	17.39	17.14	15.25	16.41
6	17.87	18.06	13.66	14.22	15.49	16.68	17.69	16.43	17.40	17.15	15.30	16.43
7	17.89	18.00	13.79	14.30	15.54	16.72	17.71	16.39	17.43	17.18	15.35	16.43
8	17.90	17.95	13.95	14.30	15.60	16.75	17.73	16.39	17.46	17.20	15.41	16.45
9	17.92	17.95	14.07	14.29	15.65	16.77	17.75	16.41	17.49	17.22	15.45	16.43
10	17.93	17.90	14.10	14.31	15.70	16.83	17.77	16.44	17.52	17.24	15.50	16.38
11	17.93	17.69	14.13	14.33	15.75	16.89	17.81	16.47	17.56	17.23	15.55	16.36
12	17.95	17.66	14.22	14.36	15.79	16.93	17.83	16.52	17.59	16.37	15.63	16.41
13	17.95	17.63	14.34	14.47	15.86	16.96	17.86	16.58	17.62	16.01	15.66	16.44
14	17.97	17.54	14.41	14.55	15.89	16.99	17.85	16.65	17.64	15.85	15.70	16.49
15	17.97	17.54	14.44	14.66	15.92	17.06	17.83	16.70	17.66	15.78	15.75	16.53
16	17.98	17.49	14.53	14.75	15.98	17.08	17.72	16.71	17.68	15.74	15.81	16.58
17	18.00	17.37	14.69	14.85	16.04	17.10	17.65	16.74	17.70	15.73	15.82	16.61
18	18.02	17.09	14.83	14.95	16.07	17.12	17.62	16.83	17.72	15.72	15.83	16.62
19	17.94	16.58	14.96	15.01	16.12	17.15	17.61	16.87	17.72	15.72	15.87	16.46
20	17.93	16.27	15.06	15.11	16.17	17.16	17.64	16.91	17.56	15.70	15.90	16.36
21	17.94	16.11	15.12	15.15	16.23	17.26	17.65	16.95	17.32	15.71	15.95	15.70
22	17.95	16.08	15.26	15.27	16.25	17.28	17.64	17.01	17.13	15.74	16.00	15.33
23	17.97	15.88	15.35	15.31	16.28	17.32	17.65	17.04	17.01	15.69	16.02	15.20
24	18.00	16.01	15.42	15.34	16.30	17.35	17.67	17.06	16.93	15.41	15.94	15.17
25	18.03	16.08	15.49	15.38	16.34	17.38	17.69	17.09	16.90	15.16	15.94	15.18
26	18.05	16.19	15.53	15.43	16.36	17.40	17.71	17.16	16.89	15.05	15.97	15.22
27	18.05	16.28	15.20	15.47	16.41	17.42	17.73	17.17	16.89	14.98	16.04	15.27
28	18.06	15.91	15.06	15.53	16.44	17.44	17.75	17.18	16.94	14.97	16.07	15.32
29	18.05	15.43	15.01	15.50	---	17.47	17.78	17.19	16.99	14.96	16.10	15.39
30	18.05	14.51	14.73	15.41	---	17.50	17.80	17.20	17.03	14.98	16.14	15.46
31	18.05	---	14.40	15.35	---	17.53	---	17.21	---	15.03	16.20	---
MEAN	17.95	17.05	14.49	14.78	15.90	17.04	17.71	16.86	17.34	16.10	15.70	16.06

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 16.41 HIGHEST 13.4 DEC. 3-4, 1992 LOWEST 18.10 NOV. 4, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

181352066025300. Local number, CJ-TW19A.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°13'52", long 66°02'53", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.96 mi southwest of Caguas plaza, 1.02 mi northwest of Escuela Antonio S. Pedreira, and 0.30 mi southeast of Hwy 156 km 59.1. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CJ-TW19A, Boneville.
 AQUIFER.--Unconsolidated deposits of Quaternary Age.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-67 ft (0-20.4 m), screened 50-65 ft (15.2-19.8 m). Depth 67 ft (20.4 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 262 ft (79.8 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Top of casing 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Observation well drilled on September 1, 1989. Automatic digital recorder installed on September 18, 1991. Aquifer test conducted on Aug. 13, 1990.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.-- June 1992 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 22.78 ft (6.94 m) below land-surface datum, July 27, 1993; lowest water level recorded, 25.25 ft (7.70 m) below land-surface datum, May 15-17, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	24.16	24.30	23.54	23.38	23.94	24.45	24.81	24.67	24.08	23.76	23.01	23.64
2	24.20	24.32	23.50	23.35	23.97	24.48	24.82	24.54	24.10	23.76	23.09	23.70
3	24.23	24.36	23.48	23.34	24.02	24.49	24.83	24.46	24.11	23.78	23.16	23.73
4	24.25	24.28	23.48	23.34	24.05	24.51	24.83	24.44	24.14	23.80	23.21	23.74
5	24.27	24.13	23.49	23.35	24.07	24.51	24.84	24.41	24.16	23.80	23.25	23.77
6	24.30	24.07	23.52	23.38	24.08	24.53	24.86	24.39	24.19	23.80	23.29	23.80
7	24.26	24.05	23.55	23.42	24.09	24.54	24.86	24.38	24.21	23.82	23.34	23.85
8	24.13	24.04	23.58	23.40	24.12	24.55	24.87	24.38	24.23	23.83	23.38	23.88
9	24.07	24.06	23.63	23.37	24.13	24.55	24.88	24.38	24.25	23.83	23.42	23.92
10	24.03	24.05	23.66	23.38	24.15	24.55	24.88	24.36	24.28	23.83	23.49	23.93
11	23.94	23.97	23.70	23.38	24.16	24.56	24.88	24.33	24.30	23.81	23.53	23.95
12	23.90	23.94	23.74	23.42	24.17	24.58	24.88	24.32	24.32	23.57	23.59	23.96
13	23.90	23.94	23.78	23.48	24.19	24.59	24.88	24.31	24.34	23.50	23.61	23.98
14	23.92	23.93	23.81	23.50	24.21	24.61	24.88	24.31	24.36	23.35	23.63	24.01
15	23.94	23.95	23.83	23.54	24.24	24.63	24.89	24.26	24.38	23.27	23.66	24.03
16	23.96	23.97	23.86	23.56	24.25	24.64	24.87	24.23	24.38	23.21	23.69	24.06
17	23.98	23.99	23.88	23.60	24.27	24.65	24.85	24.22	24.38	23.18	23.67	24.07
18	24.03	23.98	23.90	23.65	24.28	24.66	24.83	24.21	24.37	23.18	23.64	24.08
19	24.05	23.90	23.93	23.68	24.30	24.67	24.81	24.21	24.32	23.18	23.62	24.09
20	24.06	23.87	23.95	23.71	24.32	24.69	24.82	24.22	24.06	23.23	23.62	24.10
21	24.07	23.86	23.97	23.75	24.35	24.70	24.83	24.24	23.92	23.26	23.63	24.12
22	24.08	23.85	24.00	23.77	24.36	24.72	24.82	24.25	23.82	23.31	23.65	24.12
23	24.09	23.85	24.02	23.79	24.37	24.73	24.82	24.27	23.72	23.28	23.55	24.13
24	24.11	23.86	24.01	23.80	24.38	24.74	24.84	24.27	23.68	23.08	23.48	24.15
25	24.15	23.88	24.01	23.81	24.40	24.75	24.84	24.27	23.65	22.90	23.46	24.17
26	24.18	23.90	23.97	23.82	24.42	24.76	24.85	24.26	23.64	22.82	23.44	24.18
27	24.20	23.91	23.83	23.83	24.43	24.76	24.84	24.22	23.65	22.80	23.47	24.19
28	24.20	23.84	23.72	23.87	24.44	24.77	24.84	24.17	23.69	22.81	23.49	24.20
29	24.23	23.73	23.63	23.89	---	24.79	24.80	24.12	23.72	22.84	23.51	24.21
30	24.25	23.62	23.52	23.91	---	24.79	24.74	24.10	23.75	22.90	23.54	24.24
31	24.28	---	23.46	23.93	---	24.81	---	24.08	---	22.96	23.59	---
MEAN	24.11	23.98	23.74	23.59	24.22	24.64	24.84	24.30	24.07	23.37	23.47	24.00

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 24.02 HIGHEST 22.78 JULY 27, 1993 LOWEST 24.89 APR. 11, 15, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HUMACAO TO RIO SECO BASINS

175858066100200. Local number, 6.
 LOCATION.--Lat 17°58'58", long 66°10'02", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 4.23 mi northeast of Central Aguirre Church, 4.08 mi northeast of Colegio del Perpetuo Socorro Church, and 1.77 mi northwest of Hwy 3 km 144.2. Owner: Doctor Bruno, Name: Juana 5.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Quaternary Age.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m). Depth 173 ft (52.74 m) reported, 110 ft (33.54 m) measured.

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 127 ft (38.7 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum. After Aug. 7, 1981, top of 16 in (0.41 m) casing, 1.55 ft (0.47 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1960 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 26.20 ft (7.99 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 10, 1979; lowest water level recorded, 65.95 ft (20.10 m) below land-surface datum, June 2, 1968.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	53.02	52.22	52.85	54.11	54.87	55.18	57.32	58.39	59.44	58.14	55.73	55.32
2	53.07	52.10	52.96	54.12	54.89	54.94	57.30	58.35	59.45	58.12	55.74	55.36
3	53.11	52.03	53.07	54.14	54.91	54.93	57.23	58.39	59.46	58.02	55.75	55.34
4	53.13	51.96	53.16	54.17	54.94	55.04	57.20	58.46	59.46	57.81	55.74	55.26
5	53.14	51.90	53.26	54.17	54.95	55.18	57.24	58.45	59.45	57.51	55.73	55.22
6	53.14	51.86	53.34	54.15	54.96	55.33	57.30	58.33	59.44	57.23	55.72	55.24
7	53.14	51.85	53.43	54.13	54.96	55.48	57.35	58.31	59.42	56.97	55.71	55.28
8	53.14	51.83	53.50	54.11	54.99	55.61	57.40	58.37	59.37	56.77	55.70	55.35
9	53.14	51.83	53.57	54.09	55.02	55.76	57.46	58.45	59.30	56.60	55.69	55.36
10	53.13	51.82	53.66	54.10	55.04	55.89	57.50	58.52	59.19	56.48	55.69	55.28
11	53.13	51.83	53.73	54.12	54.96	56.02	57.56	58.56	59.02	56.41	55.68	55.24
12	53.11	51.83	53.81	54.16	54.94	56.15	57.62	58.62	58.83	56.38	55.68	55.26
13	53.13	51.84	53.89	54.20	54.96	56.28	57.69	58.67	58.72	56.37	55.68	55.33
14	53.14	51.86	53.97	54.25	55.01	56.39	57.77	58.73	58.62	56.35	55.67	55.39
15	53.15	51.84	54.04	54.30	55.03	56.48	57.86	58.80	58.57	56.32	55.67	55.46
16	53.15	51.83	54.12	54.36	55.06	56.55	57.94	58.86	58.54	56.28	---	55.55
17	53.17	51.82	54.19	54.42	55.10	56.62	58.02	58.93	58.51	56.24	---	55.60
18	53.18	51.81	54.25	54.46	55.13	56.69	58.09	58.98	58.44	56.19	---	55.64
19	53.16	51.82	54.31	54.41	55.16	56.74	58.14	59.02	58.38	56.14	55.66	55.68
20	53.16	51.85	54.36	54.34	55.20	56.80	58.19	59.05	58.33	56.10	55.65	55.73
21	53.13	51.90	54.41	54.37	55.24	56.84	58.25	59.08	58.30	56.04	55.66	55.79
22	53.10	51.96	54.45	54.47	55.29	56.88	58.32	59.10	58.27	56.00	55.67	55.82
23	53.06	52.03	54.46	54.54	55.33	56.93	58.33	59.12	58.24	55.95	55.69	55.81
24	53.04	52.12	54.45	54.61	55.39	56.99	58.27	59.16	58.22	55.92	55.71	55.73
25	52.99	52.21	54.43	54.68	55.44	57.04	58.24	59.20	58.20	55.87	55.70	55.63
26	52.95	52.31	54.40	54.73	55.44	57.09	58.27	59.25	58.19	55.82	55.67	55.59
27	52.88	52.38	54.34	54.79	55.42	57.13	58.32	59.30	58.17	55.79	55.61	55.62
28	52.77	52.52	54.29	54.81	55.37	57.16	58.38	59.34	58.16	55.77	55.48	55.70
29	52.60	52.63	54.23	54.82	---	57.20	58.42	59.39	58.15	55.75	55.35	55.79
30	52.45	52.74	54.17	54.83	---	57.24	58.43	59.41	58.13	55.74	55.30	55.87
31	52.32	---	54.13	54.84	---	57.28	---	59.43	---	55.74	55.29	---
MEAN	53.03	52.02	53.91	54.38	55.11	56.32	57.85	58.84	58.73	56.48	55.64	55.51

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 55.65 HIGHEST 51.80 NOV. 18, 1992 LOWEST 59.46 JUNE 3-5, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO HUMACAO TO RIO SECO BASINS

180415065513900. Local number, 96.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°04'15", long 65°51'39", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 2.44 mi northwest of Escuela Eugenio María de Hostos 4.67 mi southwest of Escuela Segunda Unidad Luciano, and 3.93 mi southwest of Escuela Asunción López.
 Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: USGS TW-2 or Yabucoa 7.
 AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Quaternary Age.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m), cased 0-10 ft (0-3.05 m), diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased about 0-183 ft (0-55.79 m), perforated 56-81 ft (17.07-24.70 m), 102-123 ft (31.10-37.50 m), 144-181 ft (43.90-55.18 m). Depth 181 ft (55.18 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 25 ft (7.62 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 4.00 ft (1.22 m) above land-surface.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 25, 1978 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 13.10 ft (3.99 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 2, 1987; lowest water level recorded, 28.29 ft (8.62 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 20, 1980.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	20.65	20.92	17.74	16.56	16.91	17.59	19.48	20.28	21.14	19.32	---	---
2	20.55	20.90	17.54	16.61	16.93	17.73	19.54	20.33	21.11	19.26	---	---
3	20.45	20.84	17.37	16.64	16.98	17.83	19.62	20.34	21.09	19.22	---	---
4	20.36	20.79	17.19	16.64	17.00	17.88	19.69	20.37	21.10	19.19	---	---
5	20.31	20.71	17.04	16.63	17.04	17.92	19.90	20.37	21.09	19.17	---	---
6	20.25	20.63	16.94	16.59	17.07	17.93	20.14	20.36	21.08	19.14	---	---
7	20.19	20.50	16.85	16.54	17.11	17.93	20.31	20.34	21.06	19.11	---	---
8	20.11	20.38	16.78	16.48	17.14	17.92	20.44	20.34	21.02	19.06	---	---
9	20.08	20.29	16.67	16.44	17.17	17.92	20.49	20.40	20.98	19.03	---	16.53
10	20.05	20.20	16.62	16.40	17.20	17.93	20.50	20.46	20.94	19.00	---	---
11	20.02	20.15	16.56	16.37	17.22	17.93	20.49	20.50	20.88	18.87	---	---
12	19.98	20.11	16.46	16.35	17.21	17.93	20.46	20.51	20.81	18.77	---	---
13	19.97	20.10	16.39	16.31	17.19	17.95	20.42	20.57	20.75	18.65	---	---
14	19.98	20.10	16.27	16.30	17.15	17.99	20.35	20.62	20.66	18.47	---	---
15	20.07	20.09	16.22	16.28	17.11	18.05	20.30	20.68	20.58	18.31	---	---
16	20.21	20.07	16.19	16.26	17.08	18.14	20.27	20.77	20.52	18.18	---	---
17	20.32	20.03	16.18	16.24	17.10	18.27	20.23	20.88	20.48	18.03	---	---
18	20.49	19.98	16.18	16.23	17.14	18.43	20.21	20.97	20.44	17.89	---	---
19	20.68	19.83	16.17	16.22	17.16	18.64	20.19	21.03	20.37	---	---	---
20	20.87	19.65	16.18	16.23	17.21	18.76	20.17	21.08	20.29	17.67	---	---
21	21.03	19.44	16.21	16.27	17.25	18.86	20.15	21.13	20.21	---	---	---
22	21.10	19.26	16.25	16.31	17.30	18.91	20.12	21.17	20.13	---	---	---
23	21.11	19.10	16.31	16.34	17.35	18.99	20.12	21.22	20.04	---	---	---
24	21.11	18.95	16.35	16.41	17.41	19.04	20.10	21.23	19.96	---	---	---
25	21.10	18.80	16.37	16.47	17.45	19.12	20.09	21.23	19.88	---	---	---
26	21.09	18.64	16.39	16.54	17.49	19.21	20.12	21.24	19.78	---	---	---
27	21.08	18.47	16.43	16.64	17.51	19.26	20.12	21.25	19.72	---	---	---
28	21.06	18.28	16.44	16.69	17.53	19.28	20.16	21.25	19.60	---	---	---
29	21.04	18.10	16.47	16.77	---	19.31	20.20	21.25	19.49	---	---	---
30	21.01	17.92	16.51	16.85	---	19.38	20.24	21.23	19.39	---	---	---
31	20.97	---	16.53	16.88	---	19.44	---	21.19	---	---	---	---
MEAN	20.56	19.77	16.57	16.47	17.19	18.43	20.15	20.79	20.49	18.75	---	---

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 18.93 HIGHEST 16.17 DEC. 19-20, 1992 LOWEST 21.25 MAY 26-30, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175829066232200. Local number, 87.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°58'29", long 66°23'22", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 1.10 mi northeast of Santa Isabel plaza, 3.69 mi southeast of Escuela Playita Cortada, and 1.07 mi southeast of Estación Experimental Santa Isabel. Owner: Francisco Alomar, Name: Alomar 1.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), iron cased. Depth 112 ft (34.14 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 35.32 ft (10.77 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Bottom of clean-out shelter door, 2.50 ft (0.76 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to August 1981, top of recorder shelter floor, 4.00 ft (1.22 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1967 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 8.45 ft (2.58 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 10, 1970; lowest water level recorded, 49.18 ft (14.99 m) below land-surface datum, July 27, 1974.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	37.16	37.07	36.64	37.86	38.23	38.87	39.69	40.00	39.59	39.43	39.58	39.37
2	37.09	37.03	36.61	37.78	38.57	---	39.87	39.83	39.73	39.53	39.65	39.53
3	37.11	37.19	36.70	37.62	38.71	---	39.92	39.72	39.66	39.42	39.62	39.30
4	37.02	37.17	36.74	37.80	38.71	---	39.67	39.82	39.88	39.36	39.65	39.37
5	36.97	37.16	36.81	38.15	38.68	---	39.61	39.98	39.94	39.37	39.82	39.64
6	37.08	37.28	37.00	38.20	38.83	---	39.85	40.10	39.91	39.53	39.74	39.64
7	37.34	37.14	36.88	38.15	38.91	---	39.87	40.25	39.85	39.62	39.69	39.51
8	37.19	37.20	37.20	38.47	38.81	---	40.05	40.31	39.91	39.67	39.67	39.68
9	37.31	37.23	37.44	38.48	38.97	39.25	39.88	40.16	40.02	39.79	39.72	39.70
10	37.62	37.38	37.49	38.29	39.06	39.29	39.83	39.96	40.18	39.72	40.02	39.49
11	37.51	37.54	37.74	38.23	39.21	39.43	39.87	39.83	40.25	39.57	40.09	39.59
12	37.26	37.69	37.75	38.54	39.05	39.35	39.82	39.76	40.27	39.43	40.16	39.69
13	37.02	37.46	37.67	38.39	39.21	39.28	39.92	39.89	40.30	39.35	40.13	39.79
14	37.00	37.15	37.54	38.72	38.95	39.32	40.05	39.81	40.23	39.37	40.13	39.96
15	37.11	37.00	37.55	38.63	38.89	39.28	39.90	39.71	40.31	39.37	39.97	39.79
16	37.15	36.87	38.02	38.56	39.30	39.39	39.96	39.63	40.10	39.55	39.79	39.83
17	37.24	36.87	37.73	38.26	39.33	39.49	40.00	39.56	39.97	39.48	39.67	39.62
18	37.39	36.84	38.08	38.30	39.14	39.28	39.77	39.53	40.03	39.37	39.58	39.80
19	37.40	36.96	37.81	38.43	39.36	39.56	39.79	39.50	39.90	39.42	39.55	---
20	37.43	37.23	37.61	38.61	39.16	39.53	39.86	39.50	39.75	39.46	39.61	---
21	37.31	36.94	37.88	38.58	38.95	39.52	40.06	39.44	39.64	39.45	39.60	39.82
22	37.27	36.89	38.23	38.71	38.81	39.51	40.10	39.41	39.56	39.62	39.64	40.03
23	37.16	36.75	38.19	38.55	38.81	39.58	40.19	39.39	39.62	39.56	39.47	40.04
24	36.97	36.95	38.30	38.40	39.09	39.67	40.22	39.40	39.58	39.42	39.37	39.76
25	36.85	37.31	38.39	38.40	39.08	39.66	40.12	39.31	39.60	39.34	39.25	39.56
26	36.70	37.44	38.17	38.74	38.95	39.76	40.18	39.27	39.51	39.35	39.18	39.39
27	36.97	37.23	38.13	38.77	39.20	39.64	40.10	39.29	39.47	39.35	39.35	39.38
28	37.06	37.19	38.01	38.77	39.06	39.52	40.11	39.26	39.48	39.53	39.17	39.35
29	37.28	36.89	38.15	38.50	---	39.36	39.97	39.34	39.48	39.60	39.06	39.49
30	37.51	36.76	38.41	38.35	---	39.54	40.04	39.41	39.56	39.71	39.04	39.45
31	37.25	---	38.09	38.23	---	39.66	---	39.48	---	39.72	39.16	---
MEAN	37.18	37.13	37.64	38.37	38.97	39.45	39.94	39.67	39.84	39.50	39.62	39.63

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 38.89 HIGHEST 36.57 DEC. 2, 1992 LOWEST 40.35 JUNE 12, 13, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

180002066132200. Local number, HW-TW-01.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'02", long 66°13'22", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 3.30 mi southwest of Cerro Guaraco, 8.71 mi southwest of Cayey plaza, and 2.80 mi southeast of Hwy 1 km 82.3 on Rabo del Buey. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: HW-TW-01.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-39.5 ft (0-12.0 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-38.2 ft (0-11.6 m), screened 32-37 ft (9.75-11.3 m). Depth 39.5 ft (12.0 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 190 ft (58.0 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Hole on side of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 2.84 ft (0.87 m) above land-surface datum. Prior October 13, 1988, top of shelter floor, 3.48 ft (1.06 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 14, 1988 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 19.34 ft (5.89 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 18, 1990 to Jan. 26, 1991; lowest water level recorded, 31.45 ft (9.58 m) below land-surface datum, May 21-22, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	26.35	26.41	---	27.27	27.97	28.48	28.94	28.86	28.89	29.01	29.03	29.44
2	26.34	26.41	---	27.28	27.96	28.50	28.94	28.89	28.88	29.01	29.04	29.45
3	26.34	26.43	---	27.30	27.96	28.53	28.94	28.92	28.87	29.01	29.07	29.45
4	26.34	26.45	---	27.31	27.96	28.55	28.94	28.92	28.86	29.01	29.09	29.45
5	26.33	26.46	---	27.33	27.96	28.57	28.94	28.96	28.85	29.01	29.12	29.46
6	26.33	26.48	---	27.37	27.96	28.59	28.93	29.00	28.85	29.01	29.14	29.46
7	26.33	26.50	---	27.39	27.97	28.61	28.93	29.01	28.85	29.01	29.16	29.46
8	26.32	26.52	---	27.43	27.97	28.63	28.93	29.03	28.84	29.01	29.19	29.47
9	26.32	26.54	---	27.45	27.99	28.66	28.93	29.05	28.84	29.01	29.22	29.47
10	26.32	26.55	26.70	27.48	28.00	28.70	28.93	29.06	28.84	29.01	29.25	29.47
11	26.31	26.58	26.71	27.50	28.00	28.73	28.93	29.08	28.84	29.01	29.27	29.48
12	26.31	26.60	26.73	27.54	28.02	28.78	28.93	29.10	28.84	29.01	29.29	29.48
13	26.32	26.61	26.75	27.58	28.04	28.78	28.92	29.11	28.84	29.02	29.31	29.48
14	26.32	26.63	26.76	27.60	28.07	28.78	28.92	29.12	28.85	29.02	29.32	29.49
15	26.32	26.64	26.77	27.62	28.10	28.81	28.92	29.13	28.86	29.02	29.36	29.49
16	26.34	26.66	26.83	27.63	28.12	28.83	28.92	29.13	28.88	29.02	29.38	29.49
17	26.34	---	26.83	27.65	28.18	28.86	28.92	29.13	28.89	29.02	29.39	29.50
18	26.36	---	26.84	27.68	28.19	28.88	28.92	29.12	29.16	29.02	29.40	29.50
19	26.38	---	26.86	27.69	28.21	28.90	28.89	29.12	29.16	29.03	29.40	29.50
20	26.37	---	26.87	27.71	28.25	28.91	28.88	29.12	29.16	29.03	29.40	29.51
21	26.38	---	26.89	27.77	28.28	28.93	28.87	29.12	29.16	29.03	29.41	29.52
22	26.39	---	26.91	27.77	28.30	28.94	28.87	29.12	29.15	29.03	29.41	29.53
23	26.38	---	26.93	27.79	28.33	28.93	28.86	29.09	29.12	29.03	29.41	29.53
24	26.39	---	26.94	27.83	28.35	28.93	28.86	29.07	29.10	29.03	29.42	29.54
25	26.39	---	26.98	27.87	28.38	28.94	28.86	29.04	29.08	29.03	29.42	29.55
26	---	---	27.03	27.89	28.39	28.95	28.86	29.02	29.05	29.03	29.42	29.55
27	---	---	27.07	27.93	28.43	28.95	28.85	28.99	29.03	29.03	29.43	29.56
28	26.38	---	27.10	27.94	28.45	28.95	28.85	28.97	29.02	29.03	29.43	29.57
29	26.39	---	27.15	27.96	---	28.95	28.85	28.95	29.01	29.03	29.43	29.58
30	26.39	---	27.19	27.97	---	28.94	28.85	28.92	29.01	29.03	29.44	29.58
31	26.40	---	27.24	27.96	---	28.94	---	28.91	---	29.03	29.44	---
MEAN	26.35	26.53	26.91	27.63	28.14	28.79	28.90	29.03	28.96	29.02	29.31	29.50

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 28.37 HIGHEST 26.31 OCT. 11-14, 1992 LOWEST 29.59 SEPT. 30, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

180001066122002 Local number, HW-TW-03C.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'01", long 66°12'20", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 8.27 mi southwest of Cayey plaza, 2.38 mi southwest of Cerro Garau, and 3.45 mi southeast of Hwy 1 km 82.3. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD,
 Name: HW-TW-03C.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-220 ft (0-67.0 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-150 ft (0-45.7 m), open hole 150-220 ft (45.7-67.0 m). Depth 220 ft (67.0 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 270 ft (82.6 m) above mean sea level.
 Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.32 ft (1.01 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Aquifer test performed during May 24, 25, 26, 1989.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 15, 1988 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 26.29 ft (8.01 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 15, 1990; lowest water level recorded, 55.24 ft (16.8 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 30, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	52.46	52.67	52.90	53.23	53.56	53.76	54.11	54.38	54.65	54.84	54.92	55.06
2	52.49	52.68	52.92	53.26	53.58	53.77	54.16	54.43	54.68	54.85	54.91	55.06
3	52.52	52.72	52.94	53.28	53.62	53.84	54.21	54.47	54.69	54.84	54.93	55.04
4	52.53	52.74	52.96	53.32	53.67	53.88	54.22	54.47	54.69	54.83	54.93	55.00
5	52.51	52.74	53.00	53.35	53.70	53.88	54.24	54.48	54.70	54.83	54.88	54.99
6	52.52	52.75	53.01	53.38	53.68	53.91	54.25	54.47	54.70	54.81	54.86	55.01
7	52.60	52.77	53.03	53.40	53.69	53.95	54.24	54.41	54.68	54.80	54.85	55.06
8	52.62	52.79	53.04	53.40	53.70	53.97	54.20	54.39	54.66	54.79	54.86	55.09
9	52.63	52.79	53.04	53.40	53.67	53.95	54.17	54.37	54.67	54.83	54.87	55.11
10	52.64	52.79	53.04	53.38	53.69	53.93	54.16	54.33	54.69	54.83	54.90	55.14
11	52.63	52.79	53.02	53.36	53.66	53.90	54.18	54.35	54.70	54.77	54.93	55.16
12	52.61	52.77	53.01	53.36	53.65	53.85	54.21	54.37	54.74	54.73	54.98	55.18
13	52.61	52.76	53.01	53.39	53.66	53.86	54.22	54.39	54.75	54.77	55.01	55.21
14	52.62	52.75	53.02	53.40	53.67	53.89	54.23	54.39	54.76	54.80	55.03	55.23
15	52.60	52.77	53.02	53.43	53.69	53.92	54.28	54.43	54.75	54.80	55.04	55.20
16	52.57	52.78	53.05	53.43	53.71	53.94	54.31	54.47	54.74	54.83	54.95	55.18
17	52.59	52.81	53.06	53.45	53.74	53.96	54.32	54.47	54.81	54.85	54.95	55.15
18	52.57	52.83	53.08	53.50	53.75	53.98	54.34	54.46	54.83	54.89	54.96	55.09
19	52.60	52.87	53.14	53.51	53.76	54.01	54.33	54.47	54.76	54.90	54.93	55.08
20	52.64	52.90	53.14	53.51	53.79	54.02	54.30	54.50	54.68	54.85	54.89	55.12
21	52.68	52.90	53.17	53.54	53.84	54.04	54.31	54.51	54.65	54.81	54.89	55.12
22	52.70	52.91	53.21	53.54	53.85	54.05	54.33	54.49	54.63	54.76	54.87	55.15
23	52.60	52.89	53.24	53.55	53.80	54.07	54.33	54.50	54.60	54.74	54.85	55.16
24	52.63	52.91	53.21	53.55	53.79	54.07	54.30	54.47	54.63	54.78	54.90	55.14
25	52.66	52.92	53.23	53.53	53.78	54.05	54.29	54.43	54.66	54.79	54.93	55.17
26	52.67	52.92	53.21	53.52	53.78	54.03	54.25	54.42	54.69	54.76	54.95	55.21
27	52.68	52.88	53.21	53.50	53.77	54.02	54.26	54.47	54.69	54.82	54.97	55.22
28	52.60	52.85	53.21	53.52	53.78	54.01	54.29	54.52	54.73	54.86	55.01	55.22
29	52.58	52.89	53.18	53.53	---	54.02	54.30	54.55	54.79	54.90	55.02	55.21
30	52.61	52.90	53.18	53.55	---	54.04	54.33	54.58	54.82	54.92	55.04	55.21
31	52.67	---	53.20	53.56	---	54.07	---	54.62	---	54.94	55.04	---
MEAN	52.60	52.81	53.09	53.44	53.72	53.96	54.26	54.45	54.71	54.82	54.94	55.13

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 53.99 HIGHEST 52.44 OCT. 1, 1992 LOWEST 55.24 SEPT. 30, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175947066130601 Local number, HW-TW-05B.
 LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'47", long 66°13'06", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 2.70 mi northeast of Central Aguirre Church, 6.16 mi northwest of Escuela de Guayama, and 2.70 mi northeast of Hwy 3 km 151.3. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: HW-TW-05B.
 AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-52 ft (0-15.8 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-51 ft (0-15.5 m), screened 41-46 ft (12.5-14.0 m). Depth 52 ft (15.8 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 145 ft (44.2 m) above mean sea level.
 Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum. Prior October 13, 1989 top of shelter floor, 3.47 ft (1.06 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 13, 1988 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 7.89 ft (2.40 m) below land-surface datum, May 26, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 22.14 ft (6.75 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 5, 1990.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	15.07	15.65	16.00	16.58	17.15	17.68	17.71	18.13	17.92	17.01	17.33	17.48
2	15.08	15.67	15.94	16.57	17.18	17.67	17.72	18.15	17.94	17.02	17.38	17.52
3	15.13	15.71	15.93	16.57	17.19	17.66	17.74	18.17	17.95	17.04	17.44	17.56
4	15.16	15.75	15.94	16.58	17.22	17.66	17.75	18.17	17.95	17.05	17.49	17.59
5	15.19	15.75	15.97	16.60	17.24	17.63	17.76	18.18	17.95	17.08	17.53	17.63
6	15.22	15.78	16.01	16.62	17.27	17.62	17.77	18.20	17.97	17.11	17.56	17.67
7	15.25	15.81	16.04	16.64	17.30	17.62	17.78	18.23	18.00	17.14	17.60	17.72
8	15.26	15.85	16.07	16.67	17.33	17.62	17.80	18.25	18.02	17.17	17.66	17.77
9	15.28	15.88	16.09	16.70	17.35	17.61	17.81	18.26	18.05	17.21	17.71	17.81
10	15.32	15.90	16.12	16.73	17.37	17.60	17.82	18.18	18.08	17.25	17.75	17.86
11	15.35	15.92	16.14	16.75	17.38	17.60	17.84	18.12	18.09	17.27	17.79	17.90
12	15.37	15.94	16.17	16.77	17.41	17.59	17.86	18.10	18.13	16.99	17.83	17.95
13	15.37	15.97	16.20	16.79	17.42	17.59	17.87	18.10	18.16	16.92	17.89	17.99
14	15.41	16.00	16.23	16.79	17.45	17.59	17.89	18.09	18.17	16.92	17.92	18.04
15	15.44	16.00	16.24	16.81	17.48	17.59	17.90	17.97	18.17	16.91	17.95	18.08
16	15.46	16.01	16.27	16.83	17.50	17.61	17.92	17.93	17.98	16.91	17.96	18.12
17	15.50	16.00	16.29	16.85	17.53	17.61	17.94	17.91	17.85	16.94	17.64	18.14
18	15.52	15.99	16.32	16.86	17.54	17.61	17.95	17.90	17.83	16.97	17.55	18.16
19	15.56	15.98	16.35	16.89	17.57	17.62	17.96	17.90	17.68	17.00	17.53	18.19
20	15.58	15.98	16.36	16.91	17.60	17.62	17.97	17.90	17.08	17.02	17.53	18.25
21	15.59	15.98	16.37	16.93	17.62	17.62	17.98	17.91	16.94	17.04	17.54	18.18
22	15.60	15.98	16.40	16.95	17.65	17.64	17.99	17.91	16.93	17.07	17.57	18.10
23	15.55	15.99	16.41	16.98	17.68	17.65	18.01	17.91	16.92	17.11	17.56	18.10
24	15.54	16.02	16.44	17.00	17.70	17.65	18.03	17.92	16.92	17.14	17.37	17.87
25	15.52	16.04	16.47	17.02	17.72	17.65	18.04	17.92	16.91	17.14	17.31	17.77
26	15.52	16.06	16.50	17.05	17.73	17.66	18.06	17.91	16.93	17.13	17.30	17.75
27	15.53	16.08	16.51	17.08	17.73	17.66	18.07	17.90	16.93	17.13	17.30	17.74
28	15.52	16.09	16.53	17.09	17.71	17.67	18.09	17.90	16.95	17.16	17.33	17.77
29	15.55	16.04	16.55	17.09	---	17.68	18.10	17.90	16.97	17.20	17.37	17.79
30	15.58	16.02	16.57	17.10	---	17.69	18.12	17.89	16.99	17.24	17.39	17.80
31	15.63	---	16.57	17.12	---	17.70	---	17.89	---	17.29	17.44	---
MEAN	15.41	15.93	16.26	16.84	17.46	17.63	17.91	18.03	17.61	17.08	17.57	17.88

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 17.13 HIGHEST 15.07 OCT. 1, 1992 LOWEST 18.26 MAY 9, 10, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175957066123400 Local number, HW-TW-13.
 LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'57", long 66°12'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 3.11 northeast of Central Aguirre Church, 5.76 mi northwest of Escuela de Guayama, and 2.03 mi northeast of Hwy 3 km 151.3. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: HW-TW-13.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-69 ft (0-21.0 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-69 ft (0-21.0 m), screened 4.0-69 ft (1.22-21.0 m). Depth 69 ft (21.0 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 203 ft (61.9 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 2.33 ft (0.71 m) above land-surface datum. Prior October 14, 1988, top of shelter floor, 3.47 ft (1.06 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 14, 1988 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 34.39 ft (10.5 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 27, 1990; lowest water level recorded, 48.10 ft (14.7 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 6, 7, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	47.72	47.91	47.24	45.88	45.77	45.82	45.85	45.90	45.90	46.20	46.14	46.26
2	47.74	47.95	47.16	45.88	45.76	45.82	45.86	45.90	45.90	46.19	46.14	46.26
3	47.74	47.96	47.09	45.87	45.76	45.82	45.87	45.90	45.90	46.17	46.14	46.26
4	47.76	47.96	47.00	45.86	45.76	45.83	45.87	45.90	45.91	46.17	46.15	46.26
5	47.78	48.06	46.93	45.86	45.76	45.83	45.88	45.90	45.91	46.16	46.15	46.26
6	47.77	48.09	46.87	45.86	45.75	45.85	45.89	45.90	45.94	46.15	46.15	46.26
7	47.76	48.10	46.82	45.85	45.75	45.85	45.89	45.90	45.99	46.15	46.15	46.27
8	47.76	48.08	46.75	45.85	45.75	45.85	45.90	45.90	46.03	46.14	46.15	46.28
9	47.75	48.08	46.68	45.84	45.75	45.86	45.90	45.90	46.05	46.14	46.16	46.29
10	47.75	48.05	46.60	45.83	45.74	45.86	45.90	45.90	46.08	46.14	46.17	46.29
11	47.79	48.04	46.54	45.83	45.74	45.87	45.90	45.90	46.09	46.13	46.18	46.29
12	47.84	48.04	46.44	45.82	45.75	45.86	45.90	45.89	46.10	46.13	46.18	46.30
13	47.84	48.05	46.34	45.82	45.75	45.86	45.90	45.89	46.10	46.13	46.19	46.30
14	47.84	48.06	46.23	45.81	45.76	45.86	45.90	45.89	46.14	46.13	46.20	46.30
15	47.83	48.06	46.15	45.81	45.76	45.86	45.90	45.89	46.18	46.13	46.21	46.31
16	47.82	48.06	46.13	45.80	45.76	45.85	45.89	45.89	46.21	46.13	46.22	46.31
17	47.81	48.04	46.11	45.79	45.77	45.85	45.89	45.89	46.22	46.13	46.23	46.31
18	47.82	47.98	46.08	45.79	45.77	45.85	45.89	45.89	46.23	46.13	46.23	46.31
19	47.82	47.91	46.05	45.79	45.78	45.85	45.89	45.89	46.25	46.13	46.23	46.31
20	47.82	47.85	46.03	45.78	45.78	45.85	45.89	45.89	46.29	46.13	46.23	46.32
21	47.82	47.79	46.02	45.77	45.78	45.85	45.89	45.90	46.31	46.13	46.23	46.32
22	47.82	47.72	46.00	45.77	45.79	45.85	45.89	45.90	46.31	46.13	46.23	46.32
23	47.84	47.66	45.98	45.77	45.79	45.85	45.89	45.90	46.32	46.14	46.24	46.32
24	47.87	47.59	45.96	45.77	45.80	45.84	45.89	45.90	46.32	46.14	46.24	46.33
25	47.87	47.53	45.94	45.77	45.80	45.84	45.89	45.90	46.31	46.14	46.24	46.33
26	47.87	47.47	45.92	45.77	45.80	45.84	45.89	45.90	46.29	46.14	46.24	46.34
27	47.87	47.42	45.91	45.77	45.81	45.84	45.89	45.90	46.26	46.13	46.25	46.34
28	47.87	47.41	45.91	45.77	45.81	45.84	45.89	45.90	46.23	46.13	46.25	46.34
29	47.88	47.38	45.90	45.77	---	45.84	45.89	45.90	46.21	46.14	46.25	46.34
30	47.89	47.31	45.89	45.77	---	45.85	45.89	45.90	46.20	46.14	46.25	46.34
31	47.91	---	45.89	45.77	---	45.85	---	45.90	---	46.14	46.26	---
MEAN	47.82	47.85	46.34	45.81	45.77	45.85	45.89	45.90	46.14	46.14	46.20	46.30

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 46.34 HIGHEST 45.74 FEB. 10, 11, 1993 LOWEST 48.10 NOV. 6, 7, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175946066102000 Local number, HW-TW-14.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'46", long 66°10'20", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 4.42 northeast of Central Aguirre Church, 3.41 mi northwest of Escuela de Guayama, and 2.01 mi northeast of Hwy 3 km 146.3. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: HW-TW-14.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-79 ft (0-24.4 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-79 ft (0-24.1 m), screened 71-78 ft (21.6-23.8 m). Depth 79 ft (24.1 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 205 ft (62.5 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 3.02 ft (0.92 m) above land-surface datum. Prior October 7, 1988, top of shelter floor, 3.67 ft (1.12 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording Observation well. Well dry at 73.56 ft (22.42 m).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1987 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 41.1 ft (12.5 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 17, 1987; lowest water level recorded, 75.35 ft (23.0 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 2, 1989.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	63.48	64.72	65.45	66.61	69.68	72.22	73.56	73.57	73.57	71.87	66.28	66.81
2	63.49	64.71	65.32	66.81	69.84	72.28	73.56	73.57	73.57	71.65	66.20	66.86
3	63.51	64.74	65.16	66.90	69.96	72.35	73.56	73.57	73.57	71.44	66.17	66.91
4	63.52	64.75	65.02	67.00	70.09	72.50	73.56	73.57	73.57	71.30	66.13	66.96
5	63.54	64.77	64.89	67.08	70.23	72.64	73.56	73.57	73.57	71.18	66.11	67.04
6	63.56	64.81	64.78	67.16	70.31	72.75	73.56	73.57	73.57	71.07	66.10	67.12
7	63.60	64.88	64.70	67.24	70.45	72.84	73.56	73.57	73.57	70.98	66.11	67.22
8	63.65	64.92	64.63	67.35	70.59	72.92	73.56	73.57	73.57	70.90	66.13	67.31
9	63.70	64.95	64.55	67.44	70.71	73.01	73.56	73.57	73.57	70.84	66.18	67.41
10	63.74	65.00	64.51	67.53	70.82	73.08	73.56	73.57	73.57	70.80	66.23	67.50
11	63.79	65.04	64.49	67.61	70.92	73.17	73.56	73.57	73.57	70.75	66.32	67.62
12	63.83	65.09	64.48	67.69	71.02	73.22	73.56	73.57	73.57	70.60	66.40	67.71
13	63.90	65.15	64.50	67.78	71.12	73.27	73.56	73.57	73.57	70.22	66.48	67.84
14	63.97	65.21	64.53	67.85	71.25	73.32	73.56	73.57	73.57	69.69	66.56	67.95
15	64.03	65.25	64.61	67.96	71.35	73.36	73.56	73.57	73.57	69.23	66.65	68.07
16	64.07	65.32	64.66	68.07	71.48	73.39	73.56	73.57	73.57	68.85	66.75	68.20
17	64.10	65.39	64.71	68.16	71.62	73.42	73.56	73.57	73.57	68.51	66.81	68.34
18	64.15	65.45	64.79	---	71.73	73.44	73.56	73.57	73.57	68.23	66.82	68.47
19	64.24	65.55	64.90	---	71.85	73.47	73.56	73.57	73.57	67.99	66.80	68.62
20	64.34	65.65	65.00	---	71.95	73.49	73.57	73.57	73.57	67.80	66.77	68.78
21	64.43	65.74	65.10	68.35	71.99	73.51	73.57	73.57	73.57	67.62	66.77	68.90
22	64.51	65.82	65.21	68.46	72.00	73.53	73.57	73.57	73.57	67.48	66.75	69.05
23	64.58	65.83	65.33	68.57	72.01	73.54	73.57	73.57	73.57	67.36	66.74	69.19
24	64.64	65.83	65.45	68.68	72.03	73.54	73.57	73.57	73.57	67.25	66.74	69.32
25	64.73	65.82	65.57	68.81	72.05	73.55	73.57	73.57	73.57	67.13	66.76	69.49
26	64.78	65.78	65.68	68.91	72.08	73.55	73.57	73.57	73.57	66.99	66.76	69.63
27	64.80	65.71	65.91	69.03	72.13	73.55	73.57	73.57	73.57	66.86	66.76	69.77
28	64.81	65.67	66.02	69.18	72.16	73.55	73.57	73.57	73.25	66.74	66.76	69.91
29	64.76	65.63	66.15	69.28	---	73.56	73.57	73.57	72.93	66.61	66.76	70.03
30	64.74	65.55	66.32	69.43	---	73.56	73.57	73.57	72.33	66.49	66.76	70.15
31	64.73	---	66.46	69.57	---	73.56	---	73.57	---	66.38	66.76	---
MEAN	64.12	65.29	65.13	68.02	71.19	73.20	73.56	73.57	73.50	69.06	66.53	68.27

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 69.27 HIGHEST 63.47 OCT. 1, 2, 1992 LOWEST 73.57 APR. 19 TO JUNE 27, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

180206066135500. Local number, RM # 5.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°02'06", long 66°13'55", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 6.98 mi southwest of Cayey plaza, 0.63 mi east of Hwy 1 km 82.3 on Rabo del Buey, and 1.75 mi southeast of Capilla de Santa Marta. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: RM # 5.
 AQUIFER.--Quaternary alluvium.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-34 ft (0-10.4 m), screened 24-34 ft (7.32-10.7 m). Depth 34 ft (10.4 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 276.35 ft (84.2 m) above mean sea level.
 Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.28 ft (1.0 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Pumping test performed during February 2, 7, 1990.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 9, 1989 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 7.48 ft (2.28 m) below land-surface datum, May 26, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 19.87 ft (6.06 m) below land-surface datum, June 14, 1990.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	11.77	11.78	11.45	11.87	11.86	12.05	12.82	12.00	12.10	11.87	11.68	11.86
2	11.77	11.83	11.52	11.87	11.88	12.05	12.87	12.08	12.26	11.88	11.69	11.87
3	11.79	---	11.59	11.88	11.90	12.05	12.92	12.02	12.27	11.89	11.72	11.88
4	11.81	---	11.62	11.90	11.93	12.05	12.99	11.99	12.10	11.86	11.77	11.90
5	11.82	---	11.65	11.90	11.95	12.06	13.05	12.06	12.34	11.88	11.77	11.90
6	11.79	---	11.67	11.90	11.96	12.06	13.15	12.20	12.62	11.89	11.77	11.75
7	11.72	---	11.70	11.90	11.96	12.06	13.27	12.33	12.81	11.90	11.78	11.80
8	11.77	---	11.73	11.90	11.97	12.08	13.38	12.47	13.00	11.92	11.80	11.85
9	11.78	---	11.75	11.91	11.98	12.09	13.49	12.56	13.16	11.93	11.82	11.87
10	11.80	---	11.77	11.92	11.99	12.11	12.57	12.14	13.28	11.94	11.83	11.88
11	11.70	---	11.77	11.93	12.00	12.11	12.90	12.09	13.42	10.56	11.84	11.88
12	11.73	---	11.78	11.93	12.01	12.12	13.10	12.43	13.57	11.08	11.85	11.89
13	11.77	---	11.80	11.94	11.97	12.11	13.13	12.65	13.72	11.31	11.85	11.91
14	11.79	---	11.74	11.95	11.97	12.10	13.04	12.40	13.86	11.39	11.88	11.94
15	11.81	---	11.77	11.95	11.99	12.11	12.95	11.90	12.99	11.47	11.89	11.95
16	11.83	---	11.78	11.95	11.99	12.13	12.48	11.96	11.89	11.49	11.43	11.94
17	11.83	11.70	11.80	11.98	12.00	12.14	12.75	11.99	11.97	11.54	11.50	11.87
18	11.82	11.77	11.81	11.98	12.01	12.14	12.97	11.96	12.05	11.58	11.63	11.64
19	11.63	11.79	11.84	11.98	12.01	12.15	13.04	11.98	11.21	11.62	11.69	11.75
20	11.70	11.47	11.85	12.00	12.01	12.14	12.18	12.05	11.00	11.62	11.71	11.80
21	11.76	11.61	11.86	12.00	12.03	12.16	12.23	12.00	11.36	11.64	11.76	11.48
22	11.45	11.56	11.87	12.00	12.04	12.18	12.27	12.00	11.47	11.66	11.77	11.60
23	11.57	11.61	11.87	11.99	12.04	12.22	12.09	11.98	11.57	11.36	11.76	11.64
24	11.61	11.65	11.88	11.99	12.04	12.27	12.07	11.96	11.64	11.37	11.75	11.49
25	11.63	11.66	11.87	11.99	12.04	12.30	12.05	11.98	11.69	11.36	11.77	11.61
26	11.68	11.69	11.89	11.99	12.04	12.35	12.05	11.91	11.74	11.43	11.78	11.60
27	---	11.73	11.82	11.99	12.04	12.46	12.33	11.95	11.79	11.49	11.79	11.67
28	---	11.40	11.87	11.95	12.05	12.56	12.44	11.91	11.83	11.54	11.81	11.70
29	11.73	11.54	11.87	11.65	---	12.63	12.50	11.95	11.85	11.59	11.83	11.69
30	11.74	11.28	11.88	11.71	---	12.69	11.96	11.99	11.85	11.63	11.84	11.70
31	11.75	---	11.87	11.82	---	12.74	---	12.14	---	11.66	11.85	---
MEAN	11.74	11.63	11.77	11.92	11.99	12.21	12.70	12.10	12.28	11.59	11.76	11.78

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 11.97 HIGHEST 10.54 JULY 11, 1993 LOWEST 13.86 JUNE 14, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

180104066152300. Local number, RM # 10.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°01'04", long 66°15'23", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 8.00 mi southeast of Coamo plaza, 1.07 mi northeast of Escuela de Coco, and 0.70 mi southwest of Escuela Sabana Llana. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: RM # 10.
 AQUIFER.--Quaternary alluvium.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-37 ft (0-11.3 m), screened 27-37 ft (8.23-11.3 m). Depth 37 ft (11.3 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--15-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 164.13 ft (50.0 m) above mean sea level, from leveling survey.
 Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.62 ft (1.10 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Pumping test performed on February 8, 1990.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 13, 1989 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 18.0 ft (5.49 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 9, 1990; lowest water level recorded, 35.56 ft (10.8 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 28-29, 1990.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	24.73	24.61	24.25	26.14	26.41	28.15	29.76	30.96	30.38	25.67	24.20	26.64
2	24.81	24.65	24.32	26.13	26.41	28.20	29.82	30.99	30.34	25.71	24.29	26.77
3	24.89	24.72	24.35	26.11	26.44	28.23	29.87	31.01	30.28	25.78	24.38	26.86
4	25.00	24.82	24.37	26.16	26.50	28.28	29.92	31.02	30.24	25.88	24.50	26.99
5	25.11	24.88	24.38	26.24	26.58	28.32	29.96	31.04	30.19	25.94	24.68	27.03
6	25.26	24.87	24.40	26.29	26.68	28.38	30.01	31.06	30.14	25.98	24.86	27.07
7	25.40	24.87	24.42	26.35	26.77	28.43	30.05	31.06	30.08	26.04	25.02	27.07
8	25.35	24.85	24.46	26.42	26.86	28.48	30.09	31.07	30.03	26.10	25.21	27.06
9	25.17	24.88	24.49	26.47	26.96	28.53	30.14	31.07	29.98	26.20	25.41	27.06
10	25.04	24.98	24.54	26.53	27.04	28.58	30.18	31.07	29.93	26.28	25.61	27.10
11	24.99	25.09	24.58	26.60	27.14	28.63	30.23	31.07	29.89	26.38	25.81	27.18
12	24.83	25.20	24.63	26.69	27.22	28.68	30.27	31.07	29.83	26.09	26.00	27.23
13	24.78	25.33	24.68	26.75	27.30	28.73	30.33	31.06	29.79	25.62	26.19	27.33
14	24.76	25.45	24.69	26.81	27.40	28.79	30.36	31.05	29.75	25.21	26.36	27.39
15	24.81	25.55	24.69	26.87	27.47	28.84	30.40	31.03	29.71	24.89	26.54	27.48
16	24.89	25.64	24.71	26.93	27.55	28.90	30.45	31.00	29.36	24.63	26.70	27.59
17	25.01	25.64	24.76	27.02	27.62	28.95	30.49	30.99	28.96	24.43	26.35	27.60
18	25.12	25.39	24.83	27.06	27.66	28.99	30.53	30.97	28.65	24.30	26.17	27.61
19	25.25	25.31	24.92	27.12	27.71	29.04	30.56	30.94	28.49	24.21	26.04	27.59
20	25.28	25.26	25.03	27.12	27.77	29.08	30.60	30.91	27.86	24.17	26.02	27.57
21	25.11	24.98	25.16	27.16	27.82	29.15	30.64	30.88	27.49	24.17	26.00	27.12
22	---	24.68	25.29	27.21	27.86	29.20	30.67	30.85	27.13	24.19	26.00	26.98
23	---	24.60	25.43	27.26	27.90	29.25	30.72	30.80	26.76	24.17	26.00	26.89
24	---	24.50	25.59	27.30	27.95	29.31	30.76	30.76	26.39	24.05	26.01	26.72
25	---	24.39	25.73	27.36	27.99	29.37	30.79	30.71	26.13	23.95	26.01	26.41
26	---	24.32	25.87	27.41	28.03	29.42	30.82	30.66	25.91	23.89	26.05	26.16
27	---	24.28	25.97	27.44	28.07	29.48	30.85	30.61	25.75	23.89	26.13	25.89
28	---	24.25	25.99	27.49	28.11	29.54	30.88	30.56	25.67	23.92	26.23	25.73
29	24.67	24.23	26.04	27.51	---	29.60	30.91	30.52	25.64	23.98	26.30	25.63
30	24.65	24.22	26.10	27.00	---	29.66	30.93	30.47	25.63	24.05	26.39	25.48
31	24.62	---	26.14	26.55	---	29.71	---	30.44	---	24.13	26.52	---
MRAN	24.98	24.88	24.99	26.82	27.33	28.90	30.40	30.89	28.55	24.96	25.74	26.91

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 27.15 HIGHEST 23.89 JULY 26-28, 1993 LOWEST 31.07 MAY 7-13, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASINS

180133066503300. Local number, 132.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°01'33", long 66°50'33", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 0.90 mi southeast of Yauco plaza, 3.46 mi east of Guayanilla plaza, and 1.32 mi north of Escuela Segunda Unidad Barinas. Owner: Pittsburg Plate Glass 4, Name: Yauco 2.

AQUIFER.--Limestone of Tertiary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-20 ft (0-6.1 m), 12 in (0.30 m) perforated pipe 20-84 ft (6.1-25.61 m), 10 in (0.25 m) perforated pipe 84-190 ft (25.61-57.93 m). Depth 190 ft (57.93 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 75 ft (22.87 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 2.35 ft (0.72 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1972 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +0.12 ft (0.04 m) below land-surface datum, July 19, 1979; lowest water level recorded, 36.91 ft (11.25 m) below land-surface datum, June 27, 1974.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	14.24	10.49	10.33	11.66	13.00	14.42	---	16.33	10.22	10.89	13.06	13.03
2	14.14	10.47	10.40	11.70	13.04	14.51	---	15.61	10.23	10.97	13.04	13.07
3	14.14	10.46	10.45	11.77	13.14	14.56	---	14.69	10.28	11.05	---	13.02
4	14.14	10.42	10.55	11.96	13.15	14.56	---	14.39	10.46	11.14	---	12.97
5	13.80	10.47	10.58	12.01	13.17	14.61	---	14.24	10.56	11.12	---	12.95
6	13.79	10.54	10.65	12.03	13.17	14.68	---	14.19	10.56	11.06	---	12.94
7	13.51	10.57	10.71	12.05	13.18	14.44	---	14.17	10.53	11.13	---	12.80
8	13.53	10.60	10.79	12.20	13.18	14.42	---	14.14	10.57	11.17	---	12.80
9	13.54	10.50	10.88	12.18	13.64	14.47	---	14.08	10.49	11.24	---	12.72
10	13.54	10.58	10.95	12.22	13.63	14.85	---	12.80	10.57	11.33	---	12.63
11	13.02	10.60	11.01	12.20	13.65	15.09	---	12.71	10.60	11.30	---	12.88
12	13.08	10.61	11.06	12.45	13.78	15.11	---	12.68	10.61	11.24	---	12.91
13	13.09	10.64	11.11	12.46	13.84	15.16	---	12.69	10.61	11.26	---	12.77
14	---	10.54	11.10	12.50	13.84	15.18	---	12.72	10.70	11.30	---	12.96
15	---	10.54	11.24	12.56	13.88	15.22	---	12.67	10.80	11.38	---	13.12
16	---	10.31	11.25	12.60	13.95	15.41	---	12.66	10.77	11.46	---	13.12
17	---	10.39	11.26	12.60	13.88	15.26	---	12.55	10.78	11.49	---	12.99
18	---	10.19	11.21	12.62	13.85	15.26	---	12.43	10.84	11.49	---	12.89
19	---	9.83	11.43	12.74	13.89	15.38	---	12.32	10.74	11.68	---	12.84
20	---	10.06	11.33	12.78	14.11	---	---	12.26	10.54	11.85	14.06	12.82
21	---	10.16	11.33	12.99	14.11	---	16.86	12.13	10.46	11.96	14.25	12.83
22	---	10.12	11.43	13.01	14.11	---	16.90	12.14	10.45	12.27	14.28	12.66
23	---	10.07	11.51	13.06	14.22	---	16.94	12.09	10.45	12.47	14.01	12.93
24	11.58	10.16	11.55	13.12	14.30	---	17.00	12.00	10.50	12.19	13.92	12.67
25	10.99	10.24	11.60	13.11	14.32	---	16.99	11.25	10.57	12.16	13.60	12.65
26	10.89	10.34	11.59	13.17	14.36	---	16.99	11.13	10.58	12.15	13.48	12.65
27	10.97	10.37	11.60	13.17	14.41	---	17.11	11.05	10.58	12.40	13.43	12.54
28	10.94	10.42	11.61	13.17	14.41	---	17.15	10.09	10.60	12.37	13.32	12.45
29	10.87	10.42	11.61	13.00	---	---	17.16	10.22	10.74	12.55	13.17	12.29
30	10.77	10.28	11.62	12.99	---	---	17.10	10.22	10.79	12.72	13.17	12.33
31	10.51	---	11.68	13.00	---	---	---	10.22	---	12.93	13.05	---
MEAN	---	10.38	11.14	12.55	13.76	---	---	12.67	10.57	11.67	---	12.81

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 12.40 HIGHEST 9.81 NOV. 19, 1992 LOWEST 17.16 AUG. 29, 30, 1993

+ Above land-surface datum.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASINS

175950066354200. Local number, 141.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'50", long 66°35'42", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, 1.71 mi southeast of Plaza Degetau at Ponce, 1.31 mi southeast of the intersection between Hwy 10 and Hwy 2, and 2.60 mi notheast of Muellle de Ponce.

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority, Name: Restaurada 8A.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused public supply well, diameter 16-10 in (0.41-0.25 m), cased 16 in (0.41 m) 2-20 ft (0.6-6.1 m), perforated 20-130 ft (6.10-39.6 m), 10 in (0.25 m) 128-165 ft (39.0-50.3 m), perforated. Depth 165 ft (50.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 24 ft (7.30 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Bottom edge of hole on side of casing 1.90 ft (0.58 m) above land-surface datum, 26.2 ft (7.67 m), above mean sea level..

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1981 to March 1, 1986, discontinued, November 18, 1991 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 11.2 ft (3.41 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 9, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 28.6 ft (8.71 m) below land-surface datum, July 9, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	19.22	19.80	20.74	18.51	19.27	19.38	19.26	19.53	20.48	21.43	19.38	15.78
2	19.07	19.86	20.77	18.60	19.29	19.40	19.31	19.56	20.58	21.55	19.24	15.47
3	18.98	19.96	20.62	18.69	19.07	19.37	19.38	19.53	20.68	21.40	19.21	15.88
4	18.87	20.03	20.47	18.76	19.13	19.33	19.32	19.72	20.75	21.33	19.16	16.03
5	18.89	20.16	20.38	18.83	19.17	19.32	19.30	19.89	20.88	21.39	19.18	15.93
6	18.86	20.25	20.36	18.81	19.26	19.40	19.36	20.14	20.85	21.39	19.05	15.83
7	18.79	20.25	20.42	18.90	19.28	19.35	19.32	20.21	20.83	21.42	18.92	15.84
8	18.85	20.33	20.33	19.10	19.24	19.30	18.74	20.19	20.86	21.44	18.84	15.87
9	18.84	20.38	20.25	19.15	19.20	19.32	19.16	20.25	20.85	21.49	18.74	15.96
10	18.76	20.43	20.12	19.13	19.25	19.35	19.28	20.24	20.82	21.48	18.64	15.94
11	18.96	20.55	20.04	19.19	19.17	19.42	19.31	20.33	20.77	21.37	18.60	15.94
12	18.83	20.66	19.79	19.39	19.21	19.58	19.27	20.35	20.88	21.37	19.34	15.99
13	18.86	20.74	19.56	19.41	19.20	19.61	19.15	20.39	20.90	21.36	20.62	16.03
14	18.97	20.76	19.39	19.43	19.12	19.58	18.97	20.34	20.91	21.39	20.83	16.01
15	19.07	20.79	19.26	19.44	19.11	19.56	18.97	20.35	21.00	21.43	19.64	16.02
16	19.27	20.83	19.15	19.49	19.15	19.52	19.08	20.40	20.85	21.46	18.28	16.06
17	19.33	20.86	19.12	19.50	19.08	19.61	19.03	20.38	20.93	21.50	17.83	16.10
18	19.37	20.88	18.99	19.57	19.06	19.58	18.94	20.49	20.99	21.52	17.47	15.88
19	19.41	20.88	18.86	19.65	19.11	19.62	18.89	20.63	20.88	21.54	17.33	16.04
20	19.48	20.86	18.73	19.70	19.07	19.47	18.84	20.57	20.78	21.58	17.22	15.95
21	18.45	20.88	18.67	19.71	18.98	19.61	18.85	20.66	20.82	21.56	17.13	16.05
22	19.39	20.88	18.47	19.76	18.93	19.68	19.13	20.61	20.83	21.54	17.01	16.17
23	19.36	20.84	18.52	19.82	18.97	19.76	19.32	20.45	20.98	21.51	16.83	16.28
24	19.33	20.86	18.65	19.74	19.00	19.36	19.38	20.43	21.04	21.49	16.53	16.16
25	19.18	20.98	18.54	19.73	19.07	19.77	19.31	20.41	21.10	21.47	16.36	16.19
26	19.20	20.98	18.55	19.74	19.20	19.79	19.31	20.33	21.12	21.46	16.19	16.25
27	19.31	20.89	18.42	19.38	19.33	19.73	19.33	20.33	21.14	21.48	16.22	16.36
28	19.44	20.80	18.35	19.37	19.37	19.61	19.47	20.34	21.24	20.80	16.26	16.41
29	19.56	20.86	18.24	19.21	---	19.44	19.42	20.32	21.32	19.63	16.24	16.44
30	19.68	20.78	18.39	19.24	---	19.35	19.37	20.41	21.40	19.53	15.86	16.48
31	19.76	---	18.42	19.26	---	19.35	---	20.44	---	19.45	15.57	---
MEAN	19.14	20.60	19.37	19.30	19.15	19.50	19.19	20.27	20.92	21.25	17.99	16.04

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 19.40 HIGHEST 14.86 AUG. 31, 1993 LOWEST 21.60 JULY 19, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180132067033800. Local number, 143.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°01'32", long 67°03'38", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 1.86 mi south of Lajas plaza, 1.27 mi southeast of the Estación Experimental Agrícola, and 1.30 mi northwest of the intersection of Hwy 116 with Hwy 305.

Owner: Pedro P. Vivoni, Name: Vivoni, Hacienda Amistad.

AQUIFER.--Limestone of unknown age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused irrigation well, diameter 12 in (0.30 m). Depth 200 ft (60.98 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--15-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 52.5 ft (16.0 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole side of casing, 0.80 ft (0.24 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1981 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 37.36 ft (11.39 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 20, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 40.0 ft (12.2 m) below land-surface datum, June 9-11, 1990.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	39.30	39.19	38.97	39.07	39.20	39.26	39.46	39.57	39.39	39.46	39.53	39.38
2	39.30	39.18	38.99	39.08	39.18	39.26	39.49	39.57	39.42	39.46	39.55	39.39
3	39.34	39.22	38.99	39.10	39.23	39.31	39.52	39.55	39.45	39.47	39.58	39.39
4	39.36	39.16	39.00	39.14	39.27	39.33	39.50	39.56	39.45	39.48	39.57	39.36
5	39.34	39.16	39.01	39.10	39.27	39.29	39.49	39.57	39.46	39.47	39.56	39.33
6	39.35	39.15	39.02	39.11	39.26	39.32	39.51	39.53	39.47	39.47	39.53	39.34
7	39.32	39.14	39.03	39.13	39.27	39.36	39.51	39.48	39.46	39.47	39.52	39.35
8	39.32	39.15	39.02	39.14	39.29	39.36	39.51	39.51	39.43	39.46	39.53	39.36
9	39.34	39.16	39.00	39.13	39.31	39.35	39.53	39.50	39.42	39.48	39.51	39.37
10	39.34	39.15	39.00	39.17	39.31	39.34	39.53	39.49	39.42	39.48	39.52	39.39
11	39.32	39.15	38.99	39.18	39.30	39.35	39.52	39.49	39.42	39.47	39.54	39.38
12	39.30	39.11	38.98	39.17	39.30	39.34	39.53	39.49	39.43	39.46	39.57	39.38
13	39.30	39.09	39.00	39.16	39.28	39.33	39.51	39.49	39.42	39.51	39.58	39.39
14	39.35	39.04	38.98	39.17	39.30	39.35	39.53	39.52	39.42	39.51	39.56	39.38
15	39.32	39.01	38.95	39.15	39.33	39.38	39.57	39.55	39.43	39.50	39.54	39.36
16	39.27	39.00	38.97	39.15	39.30	39.39	39.55	39.58	39.44	39.50	39.47	39.34
17	39.25	38.97	38.96	39.17	39.29	39.37	39.55	39.56	39.46	39.53	39.49	39.33
18	39.23	38.93	38.97	39.21	39.27	39.38	39.52	39.57	39.46	39.55	39.49	39.31
19	39.23	39.05	39.02	---	39.28	39.38	39.53	39.57	39.47	39.52	39.50	39.30
20	39.27	39.06	39.01	39.24	39.29	39.39	39.55	39.55	39.43	39.54	39.47	39.32
21	39.29	39.03	39.04	39.25	39.34	39.41	39.58	39.59	39.44	39.51	39.48	39.32
22	39.25	39.04	39.06	39.24	39.33	39.42	39.56	39.57	39.43	39.50	39.44	39.32
23	39.22	39.02	39.08	39.25	39.29	39.45	39.56	39.58	39.42	39.50	39.37	39.30
24	39.23	39.04	39.08	39.26	39.28	39.44	39.60	39.49	39.45	39.52	39.38	39.32
25	39.22	39.05	39.10	39.24	39.28	39.43	39.60	39.45	39.45	39.50	39.41	39.33
26	39.25	39.04	39.10	39.24	39.28	39.43	39.56	39.42	39.45	39.45	39.40	39.31
27	39.24	38.98	39.09	39.21	39.28	39.43	39.54	39.43	39.43	39.47	39.39	39.29
28	39.21	38.98	39.09	39.26	39.28	39.43	39.55	39.40	39.45	39.50	39.39	39.26
29	39.20	38.99	39.05	39.21	---	39.43	39.56	39.40	39.45	39.53	39.38	39.28
30	39.20	38.99	39.01	39.22	---	39.43	39.55	39.39	39.46	39.54	39.36	39.30
31	39.20	---	39.03	39.21	---	39.45	---	39.39	---	39.55	39.36	---
MEAN	39.28	39.07	39.02	39.18	39.28	39.37	39.54	39.51	39.44	39.50	39.48	39.34

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 39.33 HIGHEST 38.87 NOV. 19, 1992 LOWEST 39.61 APR. 24, 25, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180627067080600. Local number, CR-TW-1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°06'27", long 66°08'06", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 1.48 mi north of Cabo Rojo plaza, 1.24 mi northwest of Escuela Segunda Unidad Antonio Acarón Correa, and 1.78 mi southwest of Escuela Sabana Alta. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CR-TW-1.

AQUIFER.--Sand and clay.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-15 ft (0-4.57 m), screened 5-15 ft (1.52-4.57 m). Depth 15 ft (4.57 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 28.6 ft (8.72 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on shelter floor, 8.83 ft (2.79 m) above land-surface datum. Prior February 25, 1993, hole on shelter floor 5.83 ft (1.78 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on Mar. 3, 1992. Automatic digital recorder installed on July 16, 1992.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1992 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +4.75 ft (+1.45 m) above land-surface datum, Oct. 12, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 1.63 ft (0.50 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 14, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	+1.07	+1.44	+2.21	+1.14	+1.78	.25	+0.01	+2.21	+1.26	+4.40	1.12	+5.59
2	+1.57	+1.21	+1.65	+1.10	+1.29	.19	+0.07	+1.19	+0.83	+3.37	1.21	+4.49
3	+3.38	+1.42	+0.99	+0.07	+0.81	.28	.19	+2.21	+0.69	+3.36	1.33	+4.41
4	+3.33	+1.19	+0.52	+0.09	+0.37	.35	.27	+2.23	+0.60	+2.29	1.40	+4.40
5	+3.30	+1.04	+0.44	+0.05	+0.29	.40	.32	+2.21	+0.54	+2.25	1.10	+3.38
6	+3.62	+0.53	+0.41	+0.20	+0.25	.46	.47	+2.21	+0.53	+2.26	1.10	+3.38
7	+2.66	+0.44	+0.38	+0.13	+0.23	.49	.58	+1.18	+0.53	+3.30	1.21	+4.77
8	+3.55	+0.40	+0.35	+0.41	+0.21	.53	.69	+1.16	+0.53	+3.36	1.41	+4.75
9	+3.31	+0.37	+0.33	+0.36	+0.18	.37	.84	+1.10	+0.58	+3.31	1.11	+1.36
10	+3.09	+0.39	+0.31	+0.33	+0.15	.46	.89	+1.10	+0.58	+2.24	1.12	+2.09
11	+4.54	+0.36	+0.28	+0.30	+0.10	.51	.94	+0.04	+0.56	+2.20	1.35	+1.84
12	+4.60	+0.44	+0.24	+0.26	+0.05	.59	.99	+0.03	+0.53	+1.16	1.36	+1.50
13	+4.10	+0.38	+0.21	+0.23	.00	.64	1.10	+0.09	+0.57	+1.10	1.51	+1.15
14	+3.28	+1.18	+0.19	+0.20	.08	.75	.43	.21	+0.53	+2.25	1.47	+0.78
15	+3.03	+0.89	+0.18	+0.22	.13	.71	.53	.35	+0.51	+1.16	---	+0.63
16	+2.45	+1.91	+0.13	+0.19	.19	.51	+2.23	.48	+0.51	+0.09	---	+0.60
17	+2.84	+1.88	+0.12	+0.14	.02	.14	+1.13	.62	+0.48	.01	---	+0.60
18	+3.33	+1.90	+0.07	+0.09	.07	.27	+0.05	.70	+0.45	.13	---	+0.62
19	+2.61	+3.19	+0.03	+0.02	.13	.39	.04	.85	+0.56	.14	---	+0.62
20	+2.06	+2.65	.01	.05	.19	.49	.16	.27	+0.62	.28	---	+0.60
21	+1.65	+2.82	.04	.13	.28	.58	.31	.41	+0.58	.38	---	+0.66
22	+1.46	+2.34	.07	.18	.34	.68	.46	.50	+0.54	.48	---	+0.63
23	+1.30	+1.84	.09	.19	.39	.79	.61	.58	+0.49	.44	---	+0.67
24	+2.83	+1.23	.10	.28	.33	.71	.70	.18	+0.46	.52	---	+1.11
25	+3.26	+0.66	.14	.37	.17	.71	+2.24	+0.57	+0.44	.57	+1.79	+0.88
26	+2.62	+0.46	+0.04	.47	.19	.83	+2.22	+0.48	+0.43	.66	+1.45	+0.75
27	+1.99	+0.43	+0.21	.57	.12	.90	+2.20	+0.63	+0.43	.67	+1.08	+1.35
28	+1.42	+0.54	+0.15	.55	.17	+3.31	+2.26	+1.18	+0.42	.80	+0.78	+2.20
29	+0.80	+0.54	+0.13	+1.96	---	+2.25	+1.18	+1.07	+0.45	.89	+0.92	+2.22
30	+1.17	+2.39	+0.22	+2.49	---	+0.08	+2.21	+1.00	+0.45	.97	+0.89	+1.88
31	+0.65	---	+0.21	+1.82	---	+0.09	---	+1.76	---	1.06	+0.75	---
MEAN	+2.19	+1.22	+0.31	+0.23	+0.10	.43	.30	+1.11	+0.56	.13	.48	+0.96

WTR YR 1993 MEAN +3.38 HIGHEST +4.75 OCT. 12, 1992 LOWEST 1.63 AUG. 14, 1993

+ Above land-surface datum.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180628067075800. Local number, CR-TW-2A.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°06'28", long 67°07'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 1.56 mi northeast of Cabo Rojo plaza, 0.33 mi northwest of Hacienda La Ratina, and 1.94 mi southeast of Escuela Sabana Alta. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD,
 Name: CR-TW-2A.

AQUIFER.--Sand and clay.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-113 ft (0-34.4 m), screened 105-113 ft (32.0-34.4 m). Depth 113 ft (34.4 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 28.85 ft (8.79 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on shelter floor 6.10 ft (1.86 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on Mar. 6, 1992. Automatic digital recorder installed on July 16, 1992.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1992 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +4.00 ft (+1.22 m) above land-surface datum, Oct. 12, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 7.84 ft (2.39 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 12-13, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	+4.48	---	---	---	+3.36	---	5.58	4.24	+2.38	2.72	7.09	---
2	---	---	---	---	+0.09	---	5.65	4.16	+2.24	2.80	7.28	---
3	---	---	---	---	.15	---	5.72	3.90	---	2.86	7.47	---
4	---	---	---	---	.33	---	5.78	3.60	---	2.89	7.66	---
5	+2.28	---	---	---	.33	---	5.83	3.48	---	2.94	7.22	---
6	.51	---	---	---	.33	---	5.96	3.41	---	2.97	6.56	---
7	+1.58	---	---	---	1.67	---	6.06	3.33	---	3.06	6.12	---
8	+2.62	---	1.06	---	1.92	---	6.21	3.30	---	3.18	6.60	---
9	+2.61	---	1.16	---	2.17	---	6.30	3.30	---	3.25	6.92	---
10	+2.47	---	1.33	---	---	---	6.45	3.24	---	3.29	7.18	+5.50
11	+3.75	---	1.53	---	---	---	6.58	3.16	---	3.35	7.47	+6.60
12	---	---	1.64	---	---	---	6.75	3.11	---	3.37	7.77	+3.35
13	---	---	1.91	---	---	---	6.86	3.11	---	3.34	7.72	.03
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	6.56	3.13	---	3.48	7.80	---
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.99	3.14	---	3.60	6.80	---
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	4.91	3.17	---	3.64	4.98	---
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	4.23	3.20	---	3.61	2.05	---
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	4.13	3.22	---	3.65	1.49	---
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	4.17	3.20	---	3.73	1.57	---
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	4.28	3.14	---	3.76	1.87	---
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	4.37	3.06	---	3.80	---	---
22	---	---	---	---	4.24	---	4.46	2.98	---	3.82	2.77	---
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	4.56	2.94	---	3.90	.47	---
24	---	---	---	---	---	6.34	4.66	2.86	---	4.49	+2.26	---
25	---	---	---	---	---	6.43	4.54	2.31	---	5.04	+3.30	---
26	---	---	---	---	6.53	4.42	1.95	---	---	5.49	+0.02	---
27	---	---	---	---	6.65	4.41	1.67	---	---	5.87	.04	.47
28	---	---	---	5.21	---	6.20	4.41	.23	---	6.22	---	+5.51
29	---	---	---	3.04	---	5.86	4.42	+7.76	2.35	6.48	---	+7.77
30	---	---	---	+3.32	---	5.70	4.33	+1.05	2.58	6.72	---	+5.54
31	---	---	---	+2.28	---	5.60	---	+2.27	---	6.94	---	---
MEAN	+1.66	---	1.44	1.91	1.07	6.16	5.29	2.63	.08	4.01	4.70	+3.35

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 3.30 HIGHEST +4.00 OCT. 12, 1992 LOWEST 7.84 AUG. 12-13, 1993

+ Above land-surface datum.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180628067075801. Local number, CR-TW-2B.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°06'28", long 67°07'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 1.56 mi northeast of Cabo Rojo plaza, 0.33 mi northwest of Hacienda La Ratina, and 1.94 mi southeast of Escuela Sabana Alta. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CR-TW-2B.

AQUIFER.--Sand and clay.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-15 ft (0-4.57 m), screened 10-15 ft (3.05-4.57 m). Depth 15 ft (4.57 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 28.87 ft (8.80 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on shelter floor 6.10 ft (1.86 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on Mar. 10, 1992. Automatic digital recorder installed on June 3, 1992.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1992 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +4.34 ft (+1.32 m) above land-surface datum, Oct. 12, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 5.72 ft (1.74 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 14, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	+ .64	+ .99	+1.82	2.27	+1.57	2.78	2.41	3.69	+ .97	1.88	4.85	.01
2	+1.10	+ .80	+1.22	2.33	+1.08	2.80	2.45	3.87	+ .24	1.96	4.99	.27
3	.15	+ .98	+ .54	2.41	+ .54	2.83	2.52	3.34	.07	2.04	5.14	.80
4	.47	+ .78	+ .06	2.48	+ .06	2.88	2.53	3.18	.75	2.13	5.26	1.02
5	.88	+ .63	.14	2.55	.10	2.91	2.55	3.34	1.11	2.21	5.34	1.35
6	.34	+ .09	.33	2.55	.48	2.96	2.70	3.32	1.35	2.27	5.40	1.59
7	+2.24	.04	.55	2.61	.84	3.00	3.01	3.56	1.52	2.31	5.46	1.74
8	+3.14	.16	.77	1.10	1.11	3.03	3.27	3.76	1.64	2.33	5.51	1.33
9	+2.89	.36	.92	1.41	1.34	3.07	3.46	3.90	.11	2.39	4.84	+1.09
10	+2.69	.46	1.07	1.68	1.52	3.18	3.67	3.49	.16	2.47	5.04	+1.86
11	+4.12	.70	1.17	1.90	1.68	3.31	3.82	3.74	.78	2.57	5.30	+1.57
12	+4.17	.29	1.29	2.07	1.82	3.44	3.98	3.94	1.15	2.68	5.47	+1.23
13	+3.68	.33	1.36	2.20	1.94	3.57	4.12	4.09	.04	2.83	5.60	+ .84
14	+2.87	+ .73	1.39	2.32	2.05	3.69	4.17	4.28	.70	2.84	5.71	+ .38
15	+2.63	+ .45	1.40	2.43	2.15	3.80	4.23	4.46	1.12	2.83	4.52	+ .08
16	+2.05	+1.49	1.50	2.54	2.27	3.87	2.97	4.59	1.15	2.91	.55	.10
17	+2.42	+1.45	1.61	2.66	2.21	3.78	2.68	4.71	1.44	3.03	+1.20	.01
18	+2.91	+1.49	1.70	2.76	2.27	3.89	2.96	4.79	1.61	3.15	+1.08	.32
19	+2.20	+2.78	1.79	2.84	2.34	3.96	3.34	4.89	.72	3.24	+ .73	.80
20	+1.66	+2.23	1.86	2.93	2.41	4.02	3.60	4.91	.22	3.34	+ .34	1.10
21	+1.25	+2.40	1.94	3.00	2.49	4.09	3.78	4.93	.81	3.45	.03	.94
22	+1.03	+1.95	2.04	3.08	2.55	4.17	3.97	4.97	1.13	3.57	.39	1.28
23	+ .88	+1.42	2.12	3.13	2.60	4.24	4.17	5.01	1.34	3.63	+1.95	.77
24	+2.42	+ .83	2.18	3.21	2.66	3.31	4.34	4.14	1.55	3.73	+1.85	+ .82
25	+2.85	+1.16	2.26	3.33	2.66	3.39	3.78	3.43	1.69	3.84	+1.52	+ .49
26	+2.20	.07	2.27	3.47	2.68	3.48	3.55	3.28	1.78	3.96	+1.18	+ .08
27	+1.57	.24	1.93	3.60	2.71	3.59	3.64	3.20	1.87	4.10	+ .80	+1.07
28	+1.01	.01	2.00	3.75	2.75	2.79	3.84	+ .82	1.95	4.27	+ .44	+1.92
29	+ .32	.00	2.10	+1.66	---	2.54	3.71	+ .73	1.98	4.43	+ .54	+1.97
30	+ .75	+1.98	2.13	+2.31	---	2.44	3.67	+ .54	1.75	4.57	+ .45	+1.61
31	+1.16	---	2.20	+1.61	---	2.40	---	+1.50	---	4.73	+ .22	---
MEAN	+1.71	+ .70	1.24	2.16	1.58	3.33	3.43	3.39	1.01	3.09	2.16	+ .05

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 1.59 HIGHEST +4.34 OCT. 12, 1992 LOWEST 5.72 AUG. 14, 1993

+ Above land-surface datum.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180628067075802. Local number, CR-TW-2C.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°06'28", long 67°07'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 1.56 mi northeast of Cabo Rojo plaza, 0.33 mi northwest of Hacienda La Ratina, and 1.94 mi southeast of Escuela Sabana Alta. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CR-TW-2C.

AQUIFER.--Sand and clay.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-65 ft (0-19.8 m), screened 60-65 ft (18.3-19.8 m). Depth 65 ft (19.8 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 28.9 ft (8.81 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on shelter floor 6.06 ft (1.85 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on Mar. 7, 1992. Automatic digital recorder installed on June 16, 1992.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1992 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +3.94 ft (+1.20 m) above land-surface datum, Oct. 12, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 8.03 ft (2.45 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 12, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	+ .42	---	---	4.26	+ .28	4.87	5.80	4.47	.42	1.92	7.30	1.48
2	+ .13	---	---	4.41	.02	4.91	5.91	4.47	.82	2.00	7.50	1.91
3	.21	---	---	4.57	.34	4.83	6.02	4.22	1.22	2.10	7.68	2.29
4	.55	---	---	4.70	.88	4.94	6.11	4.05	1.56	2.23	7.84	2.61
5	.79	---	---	4.83	1.24	5.02	6.17	4.00	1.83	2.35	7.24	2.94
6	.61	---	---	4.82	1.62	5.11	6.28	4.00	2.05	2.44	6.53	3.21
7	+1.52	---	---	4.88	1.94	5.22	6.38	4.00	2.18	2.50	6.07	3.33
8	+2.60	---	1.23	4.17	2.21	5.31	6.49	4.10	2.25	2.51	6.73	2.85
9	+2.65	---	1.36	4.14	2.47	5.37	6.65	4.15	1.47	2.60	7.08	1.00
10	+2.65	---	1.54	4.29	2.68	5.46	6.73	4.12	1.43	2.70	7.40	+3.38
11	+3.66	---	1.72	4.47	2.92	5.58	6.90	4.14	1.58	2.82	7.69	+4.43
12	+3.81	---	1.92	4.60	3.12	5.67	7.06	4.17	1.78	2.90	7.96	+5.16
13	+3.73	---	2.12	4.73	3.31	5.77	7.19	4.23	1.25	3.06	7.79	.22
14	+2.87	---	2.20	4.84	3.52	5.88	6.68	4.33	1.51	3.03	7.99	.73
15	---	---	2.30	4.91	3.69	5.97	6.06	4.44	1.76	3.07	6.69	1.17
16	---	---	2.47	5.06	3.87	6.03	4.83	4.53	1.82	3.18	4.76	1.58
17	---	---	2.67	5.22	3.91	6.00	4.27	4.63	1.97	3.32	2.12	1.45
18	---	---	2.88	5.37	4.00	6.00	4.20	4.72	2.10	3.43	1.56	1.77
19	---	---	3.07	5.45	4.11	6.04	4.29	4.80	1.93	3.53	1.70	1.84
20	---	---	3.21	5.53	4.23	6.10	4.44	4.96	1.27	3.64	2.04	2.08
21	---	---	3.41	5.60	4.38	6.23	4.55	4.92	1.39	3.75	2.48	2.17
22	---	---	3.62	5.66	4.49	6.37	4.61	4.93	1.55	3.89	2.92	2.43
23	---	---	3.77	5.72	4.58	6.50	4.73	4.98	1.69	3.96	.52	2.25
24	---	---	3.88	5.78	4.70	6.59	4.84	4.93	1.87	4.64	+2.22	1.14
25	---	---	4.01	5.85	4.70	6.65	4.69	4.47	2.00	5.21	+1.12	1.15
26	---	---	4.04	5.91	4.74	6.77	4.55	4.17	2.06	5.65	.16	1.50
27	---	---	3.80	5.99	4.78	6.91	4.55	4.00	2.06	6.03	.23	.67
28	---	---	3.83	5.40	4.83	6.27	4.57	2.54	2.06	6.35	.87	+3.37
29	---	---	3.94	2.58	---	5.99	4.51	1.74	2.02	6.65	.67	+6.62
30	---	---	3.99	-3.30	---	5.84	4.50	1.56	1.91	6.88	.85	+3.38
31	---	---	4.12	-1.19	---	5.77	---	.40	---	7.10	1.10	---
MEAN	+1.56	---	2.96	4.62	3.11	5.81	5.49	4.04	1.69	3.72	4.23	1.38

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 3.50 HIGHEST +3.94 OCT. 12, 1992 LOWEST 8.03 AUG. 12, 1993

+ Above land-surface datum.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180643067080400. Local number, CR-TW-3.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°06'43", long 67°08'04", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 1.75 mi northeast of Cabo Rojo plaza, 0.64 mi northwest of Hacienda La Ratina, and 1.58 mi southwest of Escuela Sabana Alta. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CR-TW-3.

AQUIFER.--Sand and clay.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-30 ft (0-9.14 m), screened 20-30 ft (6.10-9.14 m). Depth 30 ft (9.14 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 27.2 ft (8.29 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on shelter floor 5.56 ft (1.69 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on Mar. 12, 1992. Automatic digital recorder installed on July 10, 1992.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1992 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +5.40 ft (+1.64 m) above land-surface datum, Oct. 11, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 3.65 ft (1.11 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 4, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	+2.91	---	---	.45	+5.7	1.10	1.63	1.41	---	1.16	3.25	+1.21
2	+2.49	---	---	.59	+3.4	1.11	1.77	1.44	---	1.27	3.38	+8.2
3	+2.06	---	---	.74	+0.3	1.07	1.89	.84	---	1.38	3.51	+4.5
4	+1.70	---	---	.79	.53	1.21	1.98	.79	---	1.49	3.64	+1.8
5	+1.47	---	---	.93	.93	1.28	2.06	.87	---	---	3.18	.03
6	+2.24	---	---	.81	+7.9	1.36	2.16	.86	---	---	2.84	.20
7	+3.94	---	---	.88	+6.3	1.46	2.24	.89	---	---	2.75	+5.4
8	+4.87	---	---	.43	+5.2	1.54	2.34	1.01	---	---	2.97	+7.6
9	+4.82	---	---	.45	+3.8	1.61	2.49	1.10	---	---	2.87	+1.87
10	+4.66	---	+1.22	.55	+2.4	1.69	2.57	.94	---	---	3.00	+2.77
11	---	---	+1.08	.67	+0.6	1.76	2.73	1.02	.14	---	3.20	+2.75
12	---	---	+9.1	.78	.06	1.84	2.89	1.09	+1.0	---	3.40	+2.51
13	---	---	+7.7	.88	.19	1.93	3.00	1.19	+0.6	---	3.49	+2.17
14	---	---	+9.9	.96	.32	2.03	2.67	1.31	.03	---	3.61	+1.77
15	---	---	+6.9	.96	.41	2.08	2.48	1.44	.11	---	2.18	+1.33
16	---	---	+5.9	1.08	.58	2.11	.62	1.57	.25	---	.55	+9.3
17	---	---	+4.5	1.21	.40	1.84	.98	1.69	.34	---	+1.24	+8.0
18	---	---	+3.4	1.31	.48	1.84	1.07	1.81	.41	---	+1.35	+6.7
19	---	---	+1.6	1.38	.58	1.90	1.19	1.69	.47	---	+1.19	+1.28
20	---	---	+0.4	1.44	.71	2.02	1.38	1.74	.32	---	+9.4	+8.5
21	---	---	.04	1.48	.84	2.15	1.53	1.79	.43	---	+6.1	+8.0
22	---	---	.16	1.54	.94	2.28	1.63	1.90	.56	---	+2.4	+5.3
23	---	---	.27	1.56	1.03	2.41	1.76	1.67	.71	1.55	+2.29	+6.4
24	---	---	.33	1.61	---	2.45	1.88	.65	.77	1.78	+2.56	+1.99
25	---	---	.43	1.66	---	2.54	1.29	+5.4	.92	2.04	-2.49	+1.72
26	---	---	.35	1.71	---	2.67	1.32	+1.03	.58	2.27	+2.27	+1.33
27	---	---	+0.5	1.78	.94	2.83	1.40	+1.5	.68	2.45	+2.07	+2.12
28	---	---	.20	1.66	1.00	1.54	1.39	.20	.82	2.63	+1.69	+2.84
29	---	---	.25	.10	---	1.46	1.42	---	.97	2.81	+1.82	+2.94
30	---	---	.20	+5.2	---	1.49	1.39	---	1.06	2.96	+1.81	+2.72
31	---	---	.32	+4.1	---	1.49	---	---	---	3.12	+1.57	---
MEAN	+3.12	---	+2.2	.95	.26	1.81	1.84	1.04	.47	2.07	.76	+1.37

WTR YR 1993 MEAN .59 HIGHRST +5.40 OCT. 11, 1992 LOWEST 3.65 AUG. 4, 1993

+ Above land-surface datum.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180650067073700. Local number, CR-TW-4.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°06'50", long 67°07'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 2.15 mi northeast of Cabo Rojo plaza, 0.68 mi northeast of Hacienda La Ratina, and 2.13 mi southeast of Escuela Sabana Alta. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CR-TW-4.
 AQUIFER.--Sand and clay.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-28 ft (0-8.53 m), screened 15-25 ft (4.57-7.62 m). Depth 28 ft (8.53 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 37.2 ft (11.3 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Hole on shelter floor 3.96 ft (1.21 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on Mar. 13, 1992. Automatic digital recorder installed on June 30, 1992.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1992 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 2.99 ft (0.91 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 12, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 8.05 ft (2.45 m) below land-surface datum, July 5, 1992 .

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	3.74	---	---	---	---	5.79	5.59	6.63	4.41	---	---	---
2	3.84	---	---	---	---	5.78	5.76	6.65	4.52	---	---	---
3	3.98	---	---	---	---	5.87	5.96	6.66	4.64	---	---	---
4	4.07	---	---	---	---	5.93	6.10	5.70	4.73	---	---	---
5	4.15	---	---	---	---	5.97	6.24	5.66	4.89	---	---	---
6	4.15	---	---	---	---	6.04	6.36	5.75	4.95	---	---	---
7	3.71	---	---	---	---	6.12	6.46	5.84	4.95	---	---	---
8	3.44	---	---	---	---	6.15	6.57	5.99	4.77	---	---	---
9	3.50	---	---	---	---	6.19	6.67	6.08	4.64	---	---	---
10	3.50	---	---	---	---	6.27	6.73	6.17	4.60	---	---	---
11	3.14	---	---	---	---	6.34	6.82	6.24	4.58	---	---	---
12	3.03	---	---	---	---	6.42	6.91	6.28	4.51	---	---	---
13	3.18	---	---	---	---	6.49	7.00	6.31	4.49	---	---	---
14	3.45	---	---	---	---	6.58	6.77	6.37	4.48	---	---	---
15	3.53	---	---	---	---	6.64	6.78	6.52	4.54	---	---	---
16	3.63	---	---	---	---	6.60	6.31	6.60	4.53	---	---	---
17	3.52	---	---	---	---	6.24	6.04	6.66	4.51	---	---	---
18	3.41	---	---	---	---	6.35	5.99	6.75	4.52	---	---	---
19	3.65	---	---	---	---	6.47	6.08	6.65	4.51	---	---	---
20	3.77	---	---	---	---	6.57	6.24	6.80	4.49	---	---	---
21	3.86	---	---	---	---	6.66	6.37	6.82	4.48	---	---	---
22	3.90	---	---	---	---	6.74	6.49	6.89	4.46	---	---	---
23	3.86	---	---	---	---	6.85	6.64	6.88	4.45	---	---	---
24	3.60	---	---	---	---	5.54	6.88	6.76	4.49	---	---	---
25	---	---	---	---	---	5.51	6.92	6.31	4.42	---	---	---
26	---	---	---	---	---	5.58	7.01	6.35	4.40	---	---	---
27	---	---	---	---	---	5.63	7.09	6.48	4.38	---	---	---
28	---	---	---	---	---	5.70	5.35	6.56	4.37	---	---	---
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.28	6.65	4.94	---	---	3.82
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.32	6.62	4.48	---	---	3.94
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	5.41	---	4.38	---	---	---
MEAN	3.65	---	---	---	---	5.59	6.27	6.42	6.15	4.56	---	3.88

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 5.49 HIGHEST 2.99 OCT. 12, 1992 LOWEST 7.09 MAR. 27, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180557067083100. Local number, CR-TW-5.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°05'57", long 67°08'31", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 0.75 mi northeast of Cabo Rojo plaza, 0.92 mi southeast of Hacienda La Ratina, and 1.83 mi southeast of Escuela Sabana Alta. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CR-TW-5.

AQUIFER.--Sand and clay.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-25 ft (0-7.62 m), screened 15-25 ft (4.57-7.62 m). Depth 25 ft (7.62 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 35.26 ft (10.7 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on shelter floor 3.88 ft (1.18 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on Mar. 17, 1992. Automatic digital recorder installed on July 16, 1992.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1992 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 2.12 ft (0.65 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 12, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 7.99 ft (2.44 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 13-14, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	4.87	4.72	4.11	5.92	4.63	6.33	---	6.63	5.41	6.44	7.37	5.65
2	4.98	4.78	4.37	5.95	4.87	6.34	---	6.64	5.54	6.44	7.45	5.69
3	5.13	4.74	4.70	6.00	5.11	6.37	---	6.66	5.72	6.47	7.52	5.79
4	5.23	4.80	4.96	6.04	5.26	6.40	---	6.65	5.83	6.51	7.55	5.81
5	5.32	4.89	5.11	6.08	5.36	6.38	---	6.67	5.96	6.51	7.56	5.86
6	5.12	5.01	5.21	6.10	5.48	6.42	---	6.67	6.02	6.52	7.52	5.96
7	4.37	5.10	5.32	6.12	5.60	6.49	---	6.67	6.10	6.47	7.53	6.02
8	3.61	5.20	5.39	5.81	5.72	6.51	---	6.76	6.11	6.39	7.60	5.87
9	3.32	5.32	5.42	5.67	5.82	6.50	---	6.79	6.05	6.44	7.64	5.57
10	3.30	5.27	5.43	5.74	5.89	6.53	---	6.82	6.07	6.46	7.68	5.27
11	2.53	5.23	5.46	5.81	5.93	6.56	---	6.85	6.10	6.51	7.78	5.14
12	2.14	5.31	5.46	5.87	5.97	6.60	---	6.86	6.14	6.51	7.86	5.15
13	2.29	5.32	5.47	5.89	6.01	6.64	---	6.90	6.10	6.59	7.93	5.26
14	2.85	5.12	5.52	5.93	6.11	6.73	---	6.94	6.13	6.59	7.99	5.39
15	3.15	5.04	5.58	5.93	6.13	6.78	---	7.01	6.19	6.58	7.07	5.47
16	3.51	4.74	5.68	5.94	6.17	6.75	---	7.09	6.24	6.63	6.59	5.62
17	3.56	4.57	5.75	5.98	6.13	6.65	---	7.14	6.28	6.68	5.97	5.65
18	3.24	4.52	5.80	6.05	6.11	6.66	---	7.20	6.30	6.74	5.87	5.67
19	3.48	3.85	5.87	6.05	6.13	6.70	---	7.24	6.32	6.72	5.90	5.73
20	3.89	3.77	5.88	6.05	6.20	6.74	---	7.18	6.13	6.75	5.95	5.83
21	4.16	3.59	5.93	6.11	6.27	6.80	---	7.11	6.13	6.79	6.07	5.84
22	4.32	3.85	5.97	6.12	6.28	6.89	---	7.09	6.16	6.84	6.14	5.86
23	4.55	4.19	5.99	6.13	6.27	6.92	---	7.14	6.18	6.92	5.76	5.86
24	4.17	4.56	5.99	6.12	6.33	6.93	---	7.15	6.25	7.00	5.35	5.78
25	3.49	4.85	6.02	6.12	6.30	6.94	---	6.88	6.33	7.01	5.31	5.71
26	3.65	5.01	6.00	6.14	6.27	7.01	---	6.57	6.37	7.01	5.31	5.71
27	4.01	5.09	5.91	6.17	6.29	7.06	---	6.37	6.42	7.06	5.31	5.71
28	4.40	5.06	5.86	6.23	6.30	---	6.63	5.85	---	7.17	5.55	5.40
29	4.72	5.02	5.86	5.46	---	---	6.62	5.64	---	7.24	5.55	5.09
30	4.84	4.27	5.85	4.41	---	---	6.62	5.54	6.43	7.30	5.54	5.03
31	4.95	---	5.90	4.55	---	---	---	5.40	---	7.35	5.56	---
MEAN	3.97	4.76	5.54	5.89	5.89	6.65	6.62	6.71	6.11	6.73	6.64	5.61

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 5.86 HIGHEST 2.12 OCT. 12, 1992 LOWEST 7.99 AUG. 13, 14, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180617067083300. Local number, CR-TW-6.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°06'17", long 67°08'33", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 1.11 mi northeast of Cabo Rojo plaza, 1.27 mi northwest of Escuela Segunda Unidad Antonio Acarón Correa, and 1.50 southeast of Escuela Sabana Alta.

Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CR-TW-6.

AQUIFER.--Sand and clay.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-30 ft (0-9.14 m), screened 20-30 ft (6.10-10.0 m). Depth 30 ft (10.0 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 32.9 ft (10.0 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on shelter floor 5.77 ft (1.76 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on Mar. 19, 1992. Automatic digital recorder installed on June 4, 1992.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1992 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 1.44 ft (0.44 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 12, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 13.2 ft (4.02 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 13-14, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	4.94	4.96	5.05	9.17	7.02	8.73	10.07	11.44	9.60	10.05	12.38	8.01
2	5.07	5.20	4.98	9.34	6.77	8.45	10.17	11.35	9.44	10.10	12.38	8.37
3	5.38	5.31	5.30	9.55	6.71	8.30	10.28	11.31	9.41	10.04	12.47	8.66
4	5.81	5.37	5.59	9.69	7.10	8.43	10.36	11.26	9.50	10.09	12.63	8.71
5	5.96	5.29	5.73	9.82	7.38	8.45	10.37	11.25	9.59	10.15	11.50	8.97
6	5.67	5.41	5.90	9.90	7.31	8.59	10.28	11.29	9.68	10.34	11.24	9.22
7	5.00	5.63	6.03	9.95	7.38	8.64	10.41	11.28	9.72	10.38	11.70	9.34
8	3.51	6.00	6.14	9.69	7.36	8.76	10.59	11.41	9.74	10.33	12.07	9.19
9	3.08	6.36	6.06	9.63	7.40	8.87	10.95	11.51	9.59	10.31	12.19	8.48
10	3.07	6.43	6.12	9.69	7.50	9.07	11.05	11.57	9.49	10.33	12.47	7.73
11	2.48	6.42	6.47	9.68	7.76	9.14	11.32	11.50	9.49	10.54	12.75	7.48
12	1.63	6.46	6.62	9.64	8.04	9.27	11.54	11.44	9.53	10.54	12.99	7.48
13	2.34	6.46	6.81	9.54	8.10	9.52	11.55	11.44	9.55	10.73	13.16	7.64
14	3.16	6.26	6.95	9.55	8.19	9.75	11.44	11.50	9.59	10.87	13.20	7.69
15	3.25	6.33	7.00	9.58	8.08	9.81	11.36	11.65	9.75	11.00	12.12	7.89
16	3.44	6.06	7.01	9.76	8.54	9.82	11.33	11.78	9.52	11.09	11.56	7.82
17	3.43	5.81	7.47	9.79	8.66	9.59	11.33	11.99	9.59	11.15	11.11	7.68
18	3.30	5.59	7.44	9.74	8.59	9.46	11.40	12.12	9.65	11.14	10.79	7.63
19	3.97	4.69	7.74	9.71	8.50	9.35	11.65	12.21	9.66	11.18	10.54	7.72
20	4.34	4.56	7.93	9.51	8.56	9.56	11.87	12.24	9.51	11.26	10.36	7.74
21	4.65	4.12	8.02	9.51	8.60	9.72	11.97	12.02	9.46	11.48	10.07	7.73
22	4.68	4.46	8.11	9.49	8.65	9.84	12.09	12.02	9.45	11.63	10.12	7.71
23	4.98	4.87	8.31	9.39	8.72	9.93	12.21	12.04	9.43	11.68	9.58	7.59
24	4.61	5.25	8.26	9.36	8.88	9.87	12.33	12.12	9.64	11.68	8.95	7.41
25	4.24	5.44	8.35	9.34	8.86	10.05	12.14	11.90	9.86	11.68	8.36	7.56
26	4.56	5.60	8.43	9.35	8.70	10.28	12.04	11.54	10.01	11.83	8.09	7.80
27	4.69	5.72	8.41	9.42	8.61	10.66	11.92	11.21	10.13	11.99	7.89	7.83
28	4.95	4.99	8.67	8.97	8.65	10.41	11.80	10.44	10.18	12.01	8.04	7.50
29	5.11	5.43	8.79	8.19	---	10.20	11.61	10.08	10.23	12.15	7.81	7.25
30	5.20	5.12	8.78	7.52	---	9.94	11.58	9.98	10.21	12.23	7.73	7.17
31	5.29	---	8.99	7.30	---	9.90	---	9.71	---	12.38	7.87	---
MEAN	4.25	5.52	7.14	9.38	8.02	9.43	11.30	11.44	9.67	11.04	10.78	7.97

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 8.84 HIGHEST 1.44 OCT. 12, 1992 LOWEST 13.20 AUG. 13-14, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180604067085100. Local number, CR-TW-7.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°06'04", long 67°08'51", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 0.80 mi northwest of Cabo Rojo plaza, 1.29 mi northwest of Escuela Segunda Unidad Antonio Acarón Correa, and 1.56 southeast of Escuela Sabana Alta. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CR-TW-7.
 AQUIFER.--Sand and clay.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-40 ft (0-12.2 m), screened 30-40 ft (9.14-12.2 m). Depth 40 ft (12.2 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 42.2 ft (12.9 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Hole on shelter floor 5.69 ft (1.73 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on Mar. 19, 1992. Automatic digital recorder installed on June 4, 1992.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1992 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 11.15 ft (3.40 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 12, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 25.30 ft (7.71 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 13-14, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	15.02	15.09	15.31	20.38	19.73	19.77	21.53	23.25	21.12	21.47	24.33	19.05
2	15.17	15.33	15.12	20.64	19.82	19.43	21.63	23.11	20.94	21.49	24.30	19.14
3	15.56	15.53	15.67	20.87	---	19.26	21.77	23.06	20.81	21.42	24.36	19.18
4	16.08	15.58	15.90	21.03	---	19.39	21.83	23.03	20.81	21.46	24.56	19.21
5	16.27	15.47	16.13	21.21	---	19.40	21.83	23.00	20.89	21.61	23.34	19.24
6	16.01	15.59	16.29	21.27	---	19.56	21.73	23.02	21.02	21.82	22.93	19.27
7	15.37	15.88	16.47	21.21	---	19.65	21.87	23.03	21.05	21.82	23.40	19.30
8	13.96	16.27	16.42	21.06	---	19.77	22.12	23.15	21.09	21.82	23.85	19.32
9	13.12	16.75	16.33	21.01	---	19.91	22.59	23.26	21.01	21.82	24.02	19.36
10	12.99	16.90	16.42	21.05	---	20.18	22.69	23.32	20.97	21.82	24.39	19.01
11	12.79	16.88	16.93	21.04	---	20.30	23.09	23.26	20.97	22.08	24.74	18.78
12	11.65	16.95	17.08	20.99	---	20.51	23.33	23.20	20.97	22.13	25.05	18.51
13	12.32	16.95	17.32	20.84	---	20.73	23.29	23.17	20.97	22.31	25.26	18.50
14	13.21	16.74	17.47	20.90	---	21.04	23.17	23.25	20.97	22.31	25.30	18.49
15	13.20	16.79	17.55	20.97	---	21.13	23.08	23.38	21.08	22.31	24.18	18.48
16	13.29	16.52	17.56	21.14	---	21.12	23.06	23.53	20.98	22.31	23.76	18.48
17	13.42	16.20	18.17	21.16	---	20.86	23.02	23.81	20.97	22.86	23.19	18.48
18	13.37	15.92	18.16	21.09	---	20.72	23.18	23.97	20.96	22.86	22.79	18.47
19	13.97	15.21	18.47	21.03	---	20.55	23.46	24.09	20.97	22.92	22.35	18.46
20	14.39	14.77	18.66	20.79	---	20.82	23.74	24.21	20.97	23.05	22.16	18.45
21	14.71	14.27	18.81	20.79	---	20.98	23.88	23.90	20.95	23.30	21.97	18.44
22	14.72	14.59	18.92	20.74	---	21.13	24.03	23.85	20.92	23.49	21.97	18.44
23	15.09	15.00	19.17	20.69	19.77	21.25	24.20	23.90	20.80	23.48	21.97	18.43
24	14.92	15.46	19.18	20.59	19.95	21.17	24.36	24.00	20.98	23.48	20.45	18.22
25	14.62	15.70	19.23	20.52	19.95	21.41	24.13	23.81	21.25	23.48	19.70	18.32
26	14.78	15.90	19.31	20.63	19.74	21.77	23.98	23.34	21.45	23.56	19.30	18.40
27	14.83	15.99	19.38	20.65	19.63	22.22	23.83	22.99	21.60	23.82	19.07	18.39
28	15.07	15.14	19.72	18.22	19.68	21.99	23.74	22.28	21.67	23.82	19.16	18.39
29	15.20	15.59	19.82	17.95	---	21.73	23.51	21.78	21.67	24.03	19.03	18.23
30	15.34	15.37	19.93	18.16	---	21.32	23.44	21.60	21.61	24.15	18.94	18.10
31	15.44	---	20.22	18.95	---	21.29	---	21.35	---	24.33	18.98	---
MEAN	14.38	15.81	17.78	20.57	19.78	20.66	23.04	23.22	21.08	22.67	22.54	18.68

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 20.04 HIGHEST 11.15 OCT. 12, 1992 LOWEST 25.30 AUG. 13-14, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180547067084800. Local number, CR-TW-8.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°05'47", long 67°08'48", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 0.50 mi north of Cabo Rojo plaza, 1.10 mi northwest of Escuela Segunda Unidad Antonio Acarón Correa, and 1.85 southeast of Escuela Sabana Alta. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CR-TW-8.

AQUIFER.--Sand and clay.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-39 ft (0-11.7 m), screened 25-35 ft (7.62-10.7 m). Depth 39 ft (11.9 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 40.7 ft (12.4 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on shelter floor 3.94 ft (1.20 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on Mar. 25, 1992. Automatic digital recorder installed on July 16, 1992.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1992 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 5.60 ft (1.71 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 5, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 19.31 ft (5.88 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 14, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.84	---	---	13.20	11.75	13.25	15.70	18.03	17.02	16.56	18.54	14.98
2	6.88	---	---	13.40	10.98	13.28	15.79	17.94	16.79	16.56	18.55	14.99
3	6.45	---	---	13.63	10.23	13.22	15.88	17.91	16.62	16.54	18.60	15.08
4	6.11	---	---	13.82	9.95	13.32	15.97	17.89	16.53	16.54	18.68	15.09
5	5.60	---	---	14.00	9.96	13.38	16.01	17.88	16.50	16.58	18.48	15.15
6	5.87	---	---	14.16	10.01	13.48	16.04	17.92	16.48	16.68	18.11	15.25
7	---	---	---	14.29	10.03	13.63	16.06	17.96	16.47	16.77	18.09	15.37
8	---	---	---	14.28	10.12	13.73	16.18	18.03	16.46	16.81	18.28	15.38
9	---	---	---	14.19	10.20	13.86	16.53	18.10	16.38	16.81	18.43	15.07
10	---	---	8.57	14.16	10.35	14.00	16.73	18.17	16.33	16.87	18.62	14.48
11	---	---	8.94	14.15	10.53	14.12	16.95	18.18	16.27	16.96	18.84	13.93
12	---	---	9.20	14.12	10.78	14.28	17.20	18.17	16.25	17.05	19.02	13.61
13	---	---	9.49	14.06	10.98	14.43	17.32	18.17	16.25	17.18	19.22	13.41
14	5.97	---	9.75	14.01	11.23	14.66	17.34	18.19	16.25	17.31	19.31	13.25
15	6.05	---	9.94	14.02	11.38	14.80	17.37	18.24	16.29	17.42	19.08	13.19
16	6.97	---	10.11	14.11	11.67	14.88	17.41	18.35	16.32	17.52	18.82	13.11
17	7.46	---	10.41	14.18	11.91	14.87	17.44	18.48	16.28	17.61	18.47	13.02
18	---	---	10.65	14.24	12.04	14.86	17.49	18.61	16.27	17.62	18.15	12.95
19	---	---	10.94	14.26	12.11	14.83	17.61	18.71	16.28	17.65	17.90	12.93
20	---	---	11.17	14.23	12.22	14.92	17.78	18.78	16.26	17.70	17.69	12.91
21	---	---	11.39	14.22	12.39	15.03	17.95	18.69	16.20	17.80	17.45	12.92
22	---	---	11.63	14.28	12.57	15.14	18.09	18.67	16.16	17.92	17.31	12.93
23	---	---	11.83	14.30	12.69	15.24	18.21	18.69	16.12	18.00	17.15	12.90
24	---	---	11.94	14.32	12.86	15.27	18.30	18.73	16.18	18.01	16.81	12.87
25	---	---	12.14	14.32	13.00	15.40	18.31	18.74	16.31	18.02	16.35	12.88
26	---	---	12.31	14.38	13.03	15.56	18.29	18.62	16.41	18.07	15.98	12.94
27	---	---	12.40	14.49	13.09	15.79	18.25	18.45	16.50	18.19	15.69	12.98
28	---	---	12.57	14.40	13.15	15.87	18.19	18.16	16.56	18.26	15.59	12.92
29	---	---	12.70	14.41	---	15.81	18.12	17.82	16.58	18.36	15.38	12.78
30	---	---	12.77	13.56	---	15.68	18.11	17.56	16.59	18.45	15.13	12.66
31	---	---	12.97	12.59	---	15.64	---	17.30	---	18.53	15.03	---
MEAN	6.52	---	11.08	14.06	11.47	14.59	17.22	18.23	16.40	17.43	17.70	13.73

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 15.06 HIGHEST 5.60 OCT. 5, 1992 LOWEST 19.31 AUG. 14, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180628067084300. Local number, CR-TW-9A.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°06'28", long 67°08'43", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 1.29 mi north of Cabo Rojo plaza, 1.54 mi northwest of Escuela Segunda Unidad Antonio Acarón Correa, and 1.23 southeast of Escuela Sabana Alta. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CR-TW-9A.

AQUIFER.--Sand and clay.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-24 ft (0-7.32 m), screened 19-24 ft (5.79-7.32 m). Depth 24 ft (7.32 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 33.21 ft (10.1 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on shelter floor 3.92 ft (1.20 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on Mar. 25, 1992. Automatic digital recorder installed on July 8, 1992.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1992 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +0.24 ft (+0.07 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 12, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 5.99 ft (1.82 m) below land-surface datum, May 19-20, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	2.24	1.88	1.79	3.74	2.54	3.65	3.89	5.22	3.31	3.74	5.02	3.10
2	2.34	2.07	2.04	3.79	2.34	3.64	3.94	5.24	3.42	3.77	5.09	3.16
3	2.47	2.22	2.22	3.87	2.47	3.68	4.01	5.26	3.51	3.81	5.18	3.23
4	2.58	2.32	2.38	3.90	2.62	3.71	4.04	5.26	3.59	3.85	5.22	3.25
5	2.66	2.30	2.49	3.94	2.71	3.72	4.08	5.27	3.66	3.90	5.09	3.32
6	2.67	2.37	2.58	3.90	2.79	3.77	4.14	5.28	3.72	3.93	5.01	3.39
7	1.87	2.47	2.67	3.95	2.84	3.81	4.19	5.32	3.75	3.90	5.06	3.46
8	1.14	2.58	2.74	3.72	2.90	3.88	4.29	5.38	3.75	3.78	5.15	3.48
9	.96	2.69	2.75	3.75	2.92	3.50	4.40	5.45	3.47	3.84	5.05	2.83
10	1.01	2.76	2.80	3.80	2.95	3.54	4.49	5.46	3.47	3.88	5.17	2.28
11	.04	2.80	2.87	3.82	3.00	3.58	4.57	5.50	3.51	3.94	5.29	2.43
12	+.17	2.85	2.92	3.84	3.07	3.65	4.67	5.53	3.57	3.96	5.38	2.61
13	.11	2.87	3.00	3.86	3.13	3.72	4.76	5.56	3.39	4.05	5.48	2.76
14	.62	2.58	3.05	3.87	3.20	3.79	4.74	5.62	3.47	4.00	5.56	2.86
15	.84	2.62	3.09	3.87	3.24	3.81	4.81	5.69	3.56	4.04	4.92	2.94
16	1.22	2.24	3.13	3.89	3.28	3.70	4.86	5.75	3.59	4.10	3.59	3.01
17	1.16	2.24	3.18	3.95	3.27	3.63	4.89	5.81	3.63	4.16	3.47	3.06
18	.80	2.17	3.26	4.00	3.30	3.70	4.95	5.88	3.66	4.20	3.57	3.04
19	1.20	1.38	3.34	4.00	3.35	3.73	5.06	5.92	3.46	4.20	3.64	3.08
20	1.64	1.50	3.39	4.00	3.40	3.76	5.16	5.59	3.17	4.27	3.66	3.13
21	1.92	1.26	3.44	4.02	3.45	3.83	5.25	5.76	3.30	4.33	3.71	2.96
22	2.01	1.56	3.51	4.02	3.47	---	5.31	5.81	3.37	4.43	3.73	3.00
23	2.06	1.80	3.57	4.02	---	3.98	5.40	5.85	3.42	4.47	2.95	2.70
24	1.58	2.08	3.59	4.03	---	3.98	5.51	5.85	3.50	4.54	2.75	2.54
25	1.08	2.27	3.65	4.04	---	4.04	5.14	5.73	3.56	4.55	2.85	2.71
26	1.32	2.40	3.62	4.06	3.63	4.14	5.23	5.75	3.61	4.61	2.97	2.81
27	1.72	2.48	3.50	4.07	3.65	4.22	5.30	5.43	3.65	4.68	3.05	2.63
28	1.97	2.45	3.56	4.10	3.61	3.79	5.16	3.95	3.74	4.77	3.14	2.28
29	2.14	2.45	3.61	2.16	---	3.84	5.20	3.69	3.70	4.85	2.85	2.09
30	2.03	1.79	3.61	2.23	---	3.84	5.21	3.50	3.70	4.91	2.94	2.30
31	2.12	---	3.68	2.52	---	3.83	---	3.16	---	4.98	3.02	---
MEAN	1.53	2.25	3.07	3.77	3.09	3.78	4.75	5.31	3.54	4.21	4.18	2.88

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 3.54 HIGHEST +0.24 OCT. 12, 1992 LOWEST 5.99 MAY 19-20, 1993

+ Above land-surface datum.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180547067073100. Local number, CR-TW-10.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°05'47", long 67°07'31", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 1.46 mi northeast of Cabo Rojo plaza, 0.60 mi northeast of Escuela Segunda Unidad Antonio Acarón Correa, and 2.74 southeast of Escuela Sabana Alta. Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD, Name: CR-TW-10.

AQUIFER.--Sand and clay.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-40 ft (0-12.2 m), screened 30-40 ft (9.14-12.2 m). Depth 40 ft (12.2 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 36.4 ft (11.1 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on shelter floor 3.67 ft (1.12 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on May 21, 1992. Automatic digital recorder installed on July 6, 1992.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1992 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 2.98 ft (0.91 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 12, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 22.9 ft (6.97 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 13, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.28	7.39	7.54	16.07	12.02	15.26	17.70	20.37	17.15	17.42	21.38	13.40
2	7.69	8.24	7.09	16.61	11.10	14.04	17.66	20.31	16.73	17.40	21.50	14.31
3	8.42	7.82	8.32	16.92	11.37	14.63	18.00	20.31	16.78	17.30	21.54	14.93
4	9.33	7.81	8.50	17.16	12.41	14.43	17.83	20.26	17.12	17.74	22.00	15.00
5	9.42	7.67	9.09	17.55	13.18	14.53	17.85	20.14	17.14	17.94	17.78	15.62
6	8.44	8.22	9.37	17.46	12.35	14.77	17.55	20.35	17.21	18.24	18.79	16.08
7	6.86	8.63	9.72	17.61	12.84	14.80	17.94	19.94	17.36	18.22	20.55	15.91
8	4.73	9.52	9.80	17.29	12.49	15.16	18.46	20.16	17.43	18.09	21.07	14.30
9	4.94	10.41	9.67	17.25	12.83	15.29	19.11	20.47	17.05	18.23	21.15	12.75
10	5.04	10.45	10.10	17.36	12.96	15.43	19.21	20.20	16.85	18.44	21.78	11.39
11	4.99	10.33	10.56	17.26	13.99	15.99	20.03	20.10	16.87	18.86	22.26	11.64
12	3.20	10.45	10.88	17.18	14.02	16.25	19.83	20.02	16.90	18.71	22.57	12.16
13	5.57	10.43	11.25	16.84	14.09	16.51	19.78	19.91	17.03	18.99	22.88	12.74
14	5.79	10.10	11.49	17.16	14.17	16.78	19.59	20.28	17.09	19.41	22.72	12.95
15	5.39	10.26	11.62	17.48	13.88	17.12	19.37	20.30	17.72	19.60	20.22	13.28
16	5.62	9.74	11.72	17.70	15.69	16.89	19.54	20.66	16.41	19.53	20.40	13.03
17	5.72	9.21	13.39	17.55	15.20	16.39	19.75	21.16	17.09	19.45	18.70	12.75
18	5.85	8.98	12.71	17.25	14.96	16.31	20.07	21.15	17.23	19.28	18.28	12.55
19	6.99	7.09	13.01	17.22	14.79	15.84	20.66	21.22	17.18	19.91	18.05	12.84
20	7.24	6.44	13.34	16.67	14.93	16.57	20.98	21.03	16.80	19.96	17.97	13.21
21	7.39	6.11	13.73	16.70	14.87	16.61	21.05	20.63	16.94	20.42	17.32	13.10
22	7.65	6.80	13.64	16.60	14.94	16.81	21.40	20.71	16.82	20.60	18.02	12.97
23	7.79	7.53	14.10	16.51	15.23	16.95	21.61	21.01	16.72	20.32	15.94	12.99
24	8.05	8.12	14.11	16.43	15.61	16.89	21.65	21.01	17.34	20.26	13.55	12.91
25	6.99	8.29	14.00	16.65	15.30	17.34	21.69	20.60	17.48	20.37	12.61	13.06
26	7.47	8.59	14.23	16.65	14.95	18.03	21.64	19.95	17.65	20.81	12.69	13.76
27	7.44	8.78	14.51	16.65	14.85	18.76	21.12	19.41	17.76	21.19	12.73	13.64
28	7.68	6.89	15.17	15.24	14.96	17.95	20.90	18.30	17.86	21.03	13.39	13.25
29	8.28	8.48	15.23	15.83	---	17.68	20.82	17.67	17.81	21.25	12.23	12.91
30	8.20	7.92	15.38	12.84	---	16.94	20.78	17.99	17.68	21.34	12.62	12.72
31	8.37	---	16.14	12.30	---	17.17	---	17.35	---	21.59	12.92	---
MEAN	6.90	8.56	11.92	16.64	13.93	16.26	19.79	20.10	17.17	19.42	18.25	13.40

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 15.21 HIGHEST 2.98 OCT. 12, 1992 LOWEST 22.88 AUG. 13, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

182442067091700. Local number, 200 .

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'42", long 67°09'17", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 1.40 mi south of Aguadilla plaza, 3.04 mi northeast of Aguada plaza, and 0.20 mi north of Hwy 2 km 146.4. Owner: Carmelo Sánchez, Name: Aguadilla Cement Well.

AQUIFER.--Surficial deposits.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Abandoned water-table industrial well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-20 ft (0-6.10 m), perforated 11-20 ft (3.35-6.10 m). Depth 20 ft (6.10 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 10 ft (3.05 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.25 ft (0.99 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 2.24 ft (0.68 m) below land-surface datum, Aug 25, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 9.60 ft (2.93 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 20, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	4.69	5.36	---	6.24	6.65	7.32	7.74	6.42	4.70	5.99	6.98	5.95
2	4.71	---	---	6.27	6.43	7.36	7.49	6.49	4.58	6.08	7.08	6.02
3	4.69	---	---	6.35	6.40	7.40	7.16	6.62	4.62	6.10	7.11	6.10
4	4.75	---	---	6.46	6.50	7.41	7.16	6.70	4.57	6.13	7.14	6.13
5	4.81	---	---	6.54	6.55	7.45	7.25	6.79	4.68	6.21	7.17	6.17
6	4.99	---	---	6.54	6.56	7.44	7.27	6.88	4.85	6.30	7.18	6.26
7	4.95	---	---	6.63	6.63	7.44	7.34	6.90	4.99	6.37	7.17	6.33
8	4.94	---	---	6.71	6.76	7.50	7.37	6.91	5.00	6.41	7.15	6.38
9	5.00	---	---	6.71	6.83	7.50	7.38	6.96	5.27	6.50	7.19	6.41
10	4.66	---	6.29	6.72	6.88	7.53	7.42	7.01	5.42	6.49	6.93	6.43
11	4.79	---	6.34	6.82	6.91	7.56	7.47	7.03	5.51	6.54	6.78	6.39
12	4.93	---	6.35	6.86	6.96	7.57	7.52	7.14	5.53	6.63	6.87	6.42
13	4.99	---	6.35	6.88	6.83	7.56	7.53	7.25	5.61	6.66	6.95	6.43
14	5.13	---	6.45	6.91	6.90	7.56	7.58	7.15	5.28	6.71	6.95	---
15	5.19	---	6.48	6.96	6.98	7.63	7.60	7.18	5.37	6.80	6.98	---
16	5.26	---	6.54	6.96	7.00	7.66	7.63	7.22	5.22	6.81	6.62	---
17	5.27	---	6.54	6.96	7.01	7.67	7.64	6.85	5.35	6.81	6.57	6.42
18	5.29	---	6.54	6.98	7.03	7.69	7.34	6.91	5.53	6.85	6.56	6.42
19	5.40	---	6.56	6.98	7.17	7.71	7.44	7.05	4.94	6.93	6.44	6.43
20	5.47	---	6.56	6.99	6.89	7.71	7.51	6.94	4.97	6.77	6.46	6.44
21	5.54	---	6.62	6.99	6.90	7.71	7.56	6.96	5.22	6.90	6.47	---
22	5.48	---	6.64	7.18	7.00	7.78	7.34	7.00	5.38	6.97	6.53	---
23	5.55	---	6.66	7.17	7.13	7.80	7.37	6.57	5.49	6.98	6.66	---
24	4.95	---	6.65	7.17	7.18	7.82	7.23	6.59	5.59	6.98	6.65	---
25	4.92	---	6.64	7.25	7.22	7.83	7.24	6.53	5.68	6.96	6.42	---
26	5.04	---	6.64	7.27	7.25	7.84	6.98	6.57	5.72	7.00	5.45	6.22
27	5.13	---	6.67	7.30	7.25	7.84	6.98	6.64	5.82	6.75	5.43	6.27
28	5.03	---	6.69	7.32	7.25	7.84	6.82	6.74	5.94	6.86	5.46	6.34
29	5.16	---	6.54	6.98	---	7.89	6.44	6.52	5.99	6.95	5.57	6.16
30	5.25	---	6.14	6.96	---	7.79	6.40	6.52	5.77	6.98	5.71	6.14
31	5.30	---	6.16	6.96	---	7.67	---	5.56	---	6.97	5.85	---
MEAN	5.07	5.36	6.50	6.87	6.89	7.63	7.31	6.79	5.29	6.66	6.60	6.28

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 6.54 HIGHEST 4.29 MAY 31, 1993 LOWEST 7.92 MAR. 29, 1993

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ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50252000 BONNE RESOLUTION GUT AT BONNE RESOLUTION, ST. THOMAS, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'57", long 64°57'34", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, on right bank near Hull Bay Road, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) upstream from Atlantic Ocean, and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) northwest of Fort Christian, Charlotte Amalie.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.49 mi² (1.27 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1962 to February 1967, March 1979 to April 1981, May 1982 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 280 ft (85 m), from topographic map. December 1962 to February 1967 and March 1979 to April 1981 at site about 100 ft (30 m) upstream at different datum.

REMARKS.--Records poor.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.01	.07	.08	.05	.01	.01	.01	.03	.02	.02	.01	.01
2	.01	.07	.05	.04	.01	.01	.01	.04	.01	.02	.01	.01
3	.01	.78	.04	.03	.02	.01	.01	.04	.02	.02	.01	.01
4	.01	2.6	.04	.03	.02	.01	.01	.04	.02	.02	.01	.01
5	.01	.32	.03	.03	.02	.01	.01	.05	.02	.03	.01	.12
6	.01	.19	.03	.03	.01	.01	.01	.06	.03	.03	.01	.02
7	.01	.12	.03	.02	.01	.01	.01	.07	.03	.03	.01	.01
8	.85	.10	.03	.02	.01	.01	.01	.04	.05	.03	.01	.01
9	.26	.10	.03	.02	.01	.01	.01	.08	.02	.02	.01	.01
10	.14	.08	.03	.02	.01	.02	.02	.04	.02	.02	.01	.02
11	.12	.06	.03	.02	.01	.02	.02	.04	.01	.01	.01	.01
12	.10	.07	.03	.02	.01	.02	.04	.03	.02	.02	.01	.01
13	.33	.07	.03	.02	.01	.02	.03	.05	.02	.02	.01	.01
14	.24	.08	.03	.02	.01	.02	.05	.09	.01	.02	.01	.01
15	.15	.18	.04	.02	.01	.04	.03	.03	.02	.02	.01	.01
16	1.2	.12	.03	.02	.01	.03	.03	.03	.02	.01	.01	.01
17	.37	.11	.03	.03	.01	.01	.03	.03	.01	.01	.01	.01
18	.15	.12	.03	.03	.01	.01	.03	.03	.01	.01	.01	.01
19	.12	.10	.04	.02	.01	.01	.05	.03	.81	.01	.01	.01
20	.26	.09	.03	.02	.01	.01	.06	.03	5.7	.02	.01	.01
21	.15	.12	.04	.02	.01	.01	.04	.03	.10	.02	.01	.01
22	.12	.17	.04	.02	.01	.02	.04	.03	.17	.02	.01	.01
23	.10	.15	.04	.02	.01	.02	.04	.06	.06	.01	.01	.01
24	.15	.10	.06	.01	.02	.03	.03	.02	.03	.01	.01	.01
25	.14	.08	.06	.01	.02	.03	.07	.02	.03	.01	.01	.01
26	.12	.07	.78	.01	.02	.03	.05	.03	.02	.01	.01	.01
27	.11	5.0	.08	.02	.02	.01	.02	.03	.02	.01	.02	.01
28	.10	.81	.05	.02	.02	.01	.03	.03	.02	.01	.02	.01
29	.10	.24	.57	.02	---	.02	.02	.02	.02	.01	.02	.01
30	.10	.20	6.8	.02	---	.01	.03	.02	.02	.01	.01	6.9
31	.08	---	.14	.02	---	.01	---	.02	---	.01	.01	---
TOTAL	5.63	12.37	9.37	0.70	0.36	0.50	0.85	1.19	7.36	0.52	0.34	7.32
MEAN	.18	.41	.30	.023	.013	.016	.028	.038	.25	.017	.011	.24
MAX	1.2	5.0	6.8	.05	.02	.04	.07	.09	5.7	.03	.02	6.9
MIN	.01	.06	.03	.01	.01	.01	.01	.02	.01	.01	.01	.01
AC-FT	11	25	19	1.4	.7	1.0	1.7	2.4	15	1.0	.7	15
CFSM	.37	.84	.62	.05	.03	.03	.06	.08	.50	.03	.02	.50
IN.	.43	.94	.71	.05	.03	.04	.06	.09	.56	.04	.03	.56

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1986 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	.71	1.00	.076	.074	.074	.070	.083	.49	.19	.055	.073	1.24
MAX	3.09	4.22	.30	.35	.38	.31	.34	2.06	.89	.18	.23	8.91
(WY)	1986	1988	1993	1992	1992	1987	1986	1987	1987	1988	1988	1989
MIN	.033	.016	.010	.016	.009	.016	.012	.016	.023	.013	.011	.013
(WY)	1992	1990	1990	1986	1986	1993	1989	1989	1989	1991	1993	1992

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR		FOR 1993 WATER YEAR		WATER YEARS 1963 - 1993	
ANNUAL TOTAL	60.62		46.51			
ANNUAL MEAN	.17		.13		.29	
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN					.77	
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN					.058	
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	9.3	Feb 4	6.9	Sep 30	90	Apr 18 1963
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.01	Jan 2	.01	Oct 1	.00	Apr 11 1980
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.01	Jan 12	.01	Oct 1	.00	Apr 11 1980
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			148	Nov 27	1650	Apr 18 1983
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			3.17	Nov 27	7.00	Apr 18 1983
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			.01	Oct 1	.00	Aug 16 1979
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	120		92		224	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.34		.26		.59	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	4.60		3.53		8.04	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.12		.12		.14	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.02		.02		.03	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.01		.01		.01	

50274000 TURPENTINE RUN AT MOUNT ZION, ST. THOMAS, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'55", long 64°53'20", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, on left bank at Mount Zion, 0.6 mi (0.9 km) east southeast from Donce School, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) northwest from Mariendal, and 0.4 mi (0.6 km) southeast from conjunction of roads 38 and 32.

DRAINAGE AREA.--2.33 mi² (6.03 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1992 to September 1993.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 120 ft (36 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e.15	d.84	e1.0	e.60	e.23	e.16	.06	.71	.31	.60	.30	.19
2	e.15	e.84	e.60	e.47	e.23	e.16	.06	.36	.27	.87	.17	.13
3	e.16	e10	e.48	e.36	e.22	e.15	.06	.20	e.41	.91	.18	.13
4	e.15	e30	e.50	e.40	e.23	e.13	.10	.20	e.52	.63	.19	1.6
5	e.14	e3.5	e.45	e.46	e.22	e.13	.16	.32	e.52	.56	.19	1.1
6	e.14	e2.5	e.42	e.45	e.20	e.13	.15	.22	e.78	.54	.17	.31
7	e.14	e1.5	e.40	e.40	e.20	e.12	.11	.19	e.78	.78	.16	.19
8	e10	e1.2	e.40	e.40	e.20	e.12	.10	.24	e1.3	.59	.17	.36
9	e1.3	e1.2	e.38	e.40	e.18	e.12	.16	5.7	e.52	.51	.17	.16
10	e1.7	e1.0	e.36	e.37	e.16	e.22	.17	1.1	e.52	.57	.18	.13
11	e1.4	e.74	e.36	e.36	e.16	e.23	.30	.58	e.45	.57	.13	.13
12	e1.2	e.84	e.36	e.36	e.16	e.22	.49	.32	e.52	.52	.16	.14
13	e3.8	e.84	e.40	e.37	e.15	e.22	.16	.24	e.48	.46	.15	.12
14	e2.5	e.98	e.40	e.37	e.14	e.23	.59	.62	e.45	.67	.15	.10
15	e1.8	e2.1	e.47	e.36	e.14	e.15	2.1	.26	e.52	.43	.37	.74
16	e14	e1.4	e.40	e.37	e.15	e.35	.97	.22	e.46	.41	.29	1.8
17	e2.7	e1.3	e.40	e.40	e.15	e.12	.26	.22	e.46	.37	.14	.51
18	e1.8	e1.4	e.40	e.45	e.14	e.12	.36	.20	e.43	.38	.13	.55
19	e1.5	e1.2	e.48	e.50	e.14	e.11	.31	.19	e70	.38	.09	.23
20	e3.0	e1.1	e.49	e.52	e.15	e.11	.45	.21	5.5	.34	.08	.67
21	e1.8	e1.5	e.49	e.51	e.15	e.11	2.6	.30	1.8	.30	.08	.25
22	e1.5	e2.0	e.48	e.46	e.15	e.22	.29	3.8	2.0	.68	.21	.15
23	e1.2	e1.8	e.48	e.45	e.15	e.22	.18	1.6	.98	.47	.16	.16
24	e1.8	e1.2	e.72	e.44	e.20	e.34	.16	.59	.80	.34	.14	.81
25	e1.7	e1.0	e1.5	e.40	e.23	e.34	.31	1.2	.72	.28	.12	.27
26	e1.5	e.86	e9.0	e.36	e.22	.06	.39	.70	.65	.28	.08	.13
27	e1.3	e60	e1.0	e.34	e.22	.06	.28	1.3	.72	.22	.08	e.17
28	e1.2	e10	e.60	e.34	e.20	.18	12	.80	.65	.21	.09	e.14
29	e1.2	e28	e10	e.31	---	.09	3.0	.57	.64	.20	.11	e.13
30	e1.2	e24	e80	e.28	---	.49	1.2	.36	.59	.19	.14	e80
31	e1.0	---	e35	e.25	---	.07	---	.34	---	.28	.18	---
TOTAL	63.13	194.84	148.42	12.51	5.07	5.48	27.53	23.86	94.75	14.54	4.96	91.50
MEAN	2.04	6.49	4.79	.40	.18	.18	.92	.77	3.16	.47	.16	3.05
MAX	14	60	80	.60	.23	.49	12	5.7	70	.91	.37	80
MIN	.14	.74	.36	.25	.14	.06	.06	.19	.27	.19	.08	.10
AC-FT	125	386	294	25	10	11	55	47	188	29	9.8	181
CFSM	.87	2.79	2.05	.17	.08	.08	.39	.33	1.36	.20	.07	1.31
IN.	1.01	3.11	2.37	.20	.08	.09	.44	.38	1.51	.23	.08	1.46

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1993 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	2.04	6.49	4.79	.40	.18	.18	.92	.77	3.16	.47	.16	3.05
MEAN	2.04	6.49	4.79	.40	.18	.18	.92	.77	3.16	.47	.16	3.05
MAX	14	60	80	.60	.23	.49	12	5.7	70	.91	.37	80
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993
MIN	2.04	6.49	4.79	.40	.18	.18	.92	.77	3.16	.47	.16	3.05
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

ANNUAL TOTAL	686.59
ANNUAL MEAN	1.88
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	80 Dec 30
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.06 Mar 26
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.09 Mar 31
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW	336 Apr 28
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE	4.93 Apr 28
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	1360
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.81
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	10.96
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.8
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.37
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.13

e Estimated

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50292600 LAMESHUR BAY GUT AT LAMESHUR, ST. JOHN, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'35", long 64°43'20", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, on left bank, 0.7 mi (1.1 km), northwest from Mina Hill top, 1.2 mi (1.9 km), west southwest from Calabash Boom Cementery, 0.8 mi (1.3 km), southeast from top of Bordeaux Mtn.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.38 mi² (0.98 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1992 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 40 ft (12 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1												.00
2												.00
3												.00
4												.00
5												.00
6												.00
7												.00
8												.00
9												.00
10												.00
11												.00
12												.00
13												.00
14												.00
15												.00
16												.00
17												.00
18												.00
19											.00	.00
20											.00	e.00
21											.00	e.00
22											.00	e.00
23											.00	e.00
24											.00	e.00
25											.00	e.00
26											.00	e.00
27											.00	e.00
28											.00	e.00
29											.00	e.00
30											.00	e.00
31											.00	---
TOTAL											---	0.00
MEAN											---	.000
MAX											---	.00
MIN											---	.00
AC-FT											---	.00
CFSM											---	.00
IN.											---	.00

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1992, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	---	.000
MAX	---	.000
(WY)	---	1992
MIN	---	.000
(WY)	---	1992
e Estimated		

ST. JOHN, US VIRGIN ISLANDS

50292600 LAMESHUR BAY GUT AT LAMESHUR, ST. JOHN, VI--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e.00	.00	.16	.14	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
2	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
3	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
4	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
5	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
6	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
7	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
8	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
9	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
10	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
11	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
12	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
13	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
14	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
15	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
16	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
17	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
18	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
19	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
20	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
21	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
22	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
23	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
24	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
25	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
26	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
27	.00	.19	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
28	.00	e1.3	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
29	.00	e1.4	.00	.00	---	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
30	.00	e.90	.51	.00	---	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00
31	.00	---	.37	.00	---	.00	---	.00	---	.00	.00	---
TOTAL	0.00	3.79	1.04	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
MEAN	.000	.13	.034	.005	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
MAX	.00	1.4	.51	.14	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
MIN	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
AC-FT	.00	7.5	2.1	.3	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
CFSM	.00	.33	.09	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
IN.	.00	.37	.10	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1992	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993
MEAN	.000	.13	.034	.005	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
MAX	.000	.13	.034	.005	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992
MIN	.000	.13	.034	.005	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1992 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	4.97	
ANNUAL MEAN	.014	.014
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN		.014 1993
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN		.014 1993
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	1.4	Nov 29 1992
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.00	Oct 1 1992
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.00	Oct 1 1992
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW	4.2	Nov 27 1992
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE	2.23	Nov 27 1992
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW	.00	Oct 1 1992
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	9.9	9.9
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.036	.036
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	.49	.49
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00	.00
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00	.00
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00	.00

e Estimated

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50294000 FISH BAY GUT AT FISH BAY, ST. JOHN, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'42", long 64°45'52", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 0.55 mi (0.88 km) east from Gift Hill top, 1.95 mi (3.13 km) east southeast from Cruz Bay school, 1.00 mi (1.61 km) from Camelberg Peak.

DRAINAGE AREA.--1.48 mi² (3.80 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1992 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 10 ft (3 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1991 TO SEPTEMBER 1992
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1								.02	.11	.00	.00	.00
2								12	.10	.00	.00	.00
3								1.3	.11	.00	.00	.00
4								.78	.11	.00	.00	.00
5								.50	.10	.00	.00	.00
6								.39	.09	.00	.00	.00
7								.34	.05	.00	.00	.00
8								.28	.00	.00	.00	.00
9								.20	.00	.00	.00	.00
10								.11	.00	.00	.00	.00
11								.02	.00	.00	.00	.00
12								.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
13								.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
14							e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
15							.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
16							.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
17							.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
18							.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
19							.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
20							.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
21							.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
22							.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
23							.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
24							.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
25							.00	19 .99	.00	.00	.00	.00
26							.00	.33	.00	.00	.00	.00
27							.00	.21	.00	.00	.00	.00
28							.00	.16	.00	.00	.00	.00
29							.00	.13	.00	.00	.00	.00
30							.00	.13	.00	.00	.00	.00
31							---	.12	---	.00	.00	---
TOTAL							---	37.01	0.67	0.00	0.00	0.00
MEAN							---	1.19	.022	.000	.000	.000
MAX							---	.19	.11	.00	.00	.00
MIN							---	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
AC-FT							---	.73	1.3	.00	.00	.00
CFSM							---	.81	.02	.00	.00	.00
IN.							---	.93	.02	.00	.00	.00

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1992, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

MEAN	---	1.19	.022	.000	.000	.000
MAX	---	1.19	.022	.000	.000	.000
(WY)	---	1992	1992	1992	1992	1992
MIN	---	1.19	.022	.000	.000	.000
(WY)	---	1992	1992	1992	1992	1992

e Estimated

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50294000 FISH BAY GUT AT FISH BAY, ST. JOHN, VI--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.00	.00	.17	.37	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
2	.00	.00	.14	.26	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
3	.00	.00	.12	.22	.13	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
4	.00	.07	.12	.23	.16	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
5	.00	.17	.13	.30	.13	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
6	.00	.19	.12	.50	.09	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
7	.00	.21	.11	.44	.07	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
8	.00	e.85	.08	.31	.02	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
9	.00	e.21	.06	.25	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
10	.00	e.21	.03	.23	.00	.00	.00	.16	.00	.00	.00	.00
11	.00	e.21	.00	.21	.00	.00	.00	.18	.00	.00	.00	.00
12	.00	e.21	.00	.22	.00	.00	.00	.14	.00	.00	.00	.00
13	.00	e.21	.00	.20	.00	.00	.00	.13	.00	.00	.00	.00
14	.00	e.21	.00	.19	.00	.00	.00	.06	.00	.00	.00	.00
15	.00	e.21	.00	.17	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
16	.15	e.21	.00	.14	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
17	.16	.18	.00	.13	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
18	.17	.17	.00	.11	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
19	.17	.17	.00	.07	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
20	.16	.14	.00	.02	.00	.00	.00	.00	1.5	.00	.00	.00
21	.15	.13	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.31	.00	.00	.00
22	.13	.13	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.20	.00	.00	.00
23	.09	.13	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.14	.00	.00	.00
24	.06	.11	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.10	.00	.00	.00
25	.10	.10	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.05	.00	.00	.00
26	.12	.09	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
27	.11	13	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
28	.05	4.3	.07	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
29	.00	.47	.06	.00	---	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
30	.00	.26	8.7	.00	---	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
31	.00	---	.68	.00	---	.00	---	.00	---	.00	.00	---
TOTAL	1.62	22.55	10.59	4.57	0.60	0.00	0.00	0.67	2.30	0.00	0.00	0.00
MEAN	.052	.75	.34	.15	.021	.000	.000	.022	.077	.000	.000	.000
MAX	.17	.13	8.7	.50	.16	.00	.00	.18	1.5	.00	.00	.00
MIN	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
AC-FT	3.2	45	21	9.1	1.2	.00	.00	1.3	4.6	.00	.00	.00
CFSM	.04	.51	.23	.10	.01	.00	.00	.01	.05	.00	.00	.00
IN.	.04	.57	.27	.11	.02	.00	.00	.02	.06	.00	.00	.00

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1992	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992	1992	1992	1992	1992
MEAN	.052	.75	.34	.15	.021	.000	.000	.61	.049	.000	.000	.000
MAX	.052	.75	.34	.15	.021	.000	.000	1.19	.077	.000	.000	.000
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992	1993	1992	1992	1992
MIN	.052	.75	.34	.15	.021	.000	.000	.022	.022	.000	.000	.000
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992	1992	1992	1992

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1992 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	42.90		
ANNUAL MEAN	.12		
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			.12
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			.12
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	13	Nov 27	19
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.00	Oct 1	.00
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.00	Oct 1	.00
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW	265	Nov 27	265
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE	3.57	Nov 27	3.57
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW	.00	Oct 1	.00
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	85		85
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.079		.079
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	1.08		1.08
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.17		.17
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00		.00
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00		.00

e Estimated

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50295000 GUINEA GUT AT BETHANY, ST. JOHN, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'55", long 64°46'50", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 600 ft (183 m) southeast of Bethany Church, and 1.0 mi (1.6 km) east of Government House at Cruz Bay.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.37 mi² (0.96 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1963 to October 1967, September 1982 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and concrete control. Elevation of gage is 260 ft (79 m), from topographic map. Prior to September 1982, at datum 1.00 ft (0.30 m) higher.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.00	.00	.00	.01	.04	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00
2	.00	.00	.00	.00	.02	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00
3	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
4	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
5	.00	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.02
6	.00	.01	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01
7	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01
8	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01
9	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.01
10	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01
11	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01
12	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01
13	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01
14	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
15	.00	.06	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
16	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
17	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
18	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
19	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
20	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.70	.00	.00	.00
21	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00
22	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00
23	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00
24	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00
25	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00
26	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00
27	.00	.05	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00
28	.00	.02	.00	.01	.00	.00	.02	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
29	.00	.00	.00	.01	---	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
30	.00	.00	.78	.02	---	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
31	.00	---	.01	.03	---	.00	---	.00	---	.00	.00	---
TOTAL	0.00	0.18	0.79	0.11	0.06	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.76	0.00	0.00	0.10
MEAN	.000	.006	.025	.004	.002	.001	.001	.001	.025	.000	.000	.003
MAX	.00	.06	.78	.03	.04	.01	.02	.01	.70	.00	.00	.02
MIN	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
AC-FT	.00	.4	1.6	.2	.1	.04	.06	.08	1.5	.00	.00	.2
CFSM	.00	.02	.07	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.07	.00	.00	.01
IN.	.00	.02	.08	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.08	.00	.00	.01

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1984 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993		
MEAN	.062	.41	.027	.015	.006	.004	.023	.13	.013	.009	.011	.31
MAX	.23	2.52	.11	.044	.017	.009	.17	.89	.031	.038	.026	2.35
(WY)	1986	1985	1989	1989	1989	1985	1986	1986	1987	1990	1988	1989
MIN	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.001	.000	.000	.000	.000
(WY)	1992	1992	1987	1992	1992	1986	1992	1993	1991	1987	1991	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS

FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR

FOR 1993 WATER YEAR

WATER YEARS 1963 - 1993

ANNUAL TOTAL	11.97	2.09		
ANNUAL MEAN	.033	.006		
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			.22	1985
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			.002	1967
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	7.5	May 24	.78	Dec 30
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.00	Jan 1	.00	Oct 1
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.00	Jan 1	.00	Oct 1
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			19	Jun 20
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			2.18	Jun 20
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	24		4.1	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.088		.015	
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	1.20		.21	
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.01		.01	
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00		.00	
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00		.00	

e Estimated

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50295500 CRUZ BAY GUT AT CRUZ BAY, ST. JOHN, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'42", long 64°45'53", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 0.40 mi (0.64 km) east of Government House at Cruz Bay, .45 mi (.72 km) west of Bethany Church and 0.40 mi (0.64 km) southwest of Caneel Hill.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.09 mi² (0.23 km²).

WATER-STAGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1992 to current year. (discontinued)

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 120 ft (37 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Gage height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. All gage-heights of 1.36 ft or lower are considered zero flow.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum gage-height, 3.11 ft (0.948 m), June 20, 1993; minimum, 1.30 ft (0.396 m), Jan. 1, 1993.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum gage-height, 3.11 ft (0.948 m), June 20; minimum, 1.30 ft (0.396 m), Jan. 1.

GAGE HEIGHT, FEET, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	1.34	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.37	1.33	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.34	1.33
2	1.34	1.32	1.33	1.32	1.55	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.35	1.34
3	1.34	1.33	1.32	1.32	1.35	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.38	1.35
4	1.34	1.33	1.31	1.32	1.35	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.40	1.35
5	1.34	1.33	1.31	1.50	1.34	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.44	1.51
6	1.34	1.33	1.32	1.56	1.34	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.42	1.34
7	1.34	1.33	1.32	1.36	1.34	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.32	1.34	1.46	1.35
8	1.34	1.33	1.32	1.32	1.34	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.32	1.34	1.42	1.35
9	1.34	1.33	1.32	1.34	1.34	1.33	1.33	1.40	1.32	1.34	1.34	1.35
10	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.33	1.39	1.32	1.34	1.34	1.34
11	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.33	1.34	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.34
12	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.33	1.34	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.34
13	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.33	1.34	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.34
14	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.33	1.34	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.34
15	1.33	1.47	1.32	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.33	1.34	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.34
16	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.33	1.34	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.34
17	1.33	1.37	1.32	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.33
18	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.34
19	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.34
20	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.33	1.39	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.80	1.34	1.33	1.34
21	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.38	1.34	1.33	1.34
22	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.34	1.33	1.34
23	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.34	1.33	1.35
24	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.35
25	1.32	1.33	1.32	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.33	1.34	1.34	1.35
26	1.32	1.33	1.32	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.35
27	1.32	1.47	1.32	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.34	1.54	1.34	1.35	1.33	1.35
28	1.32	1.52	1.32	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.45	1.33	1.34	1.39	1.33	1.35
29	1.32	1.33	1.35	1.33	---	1.33	1.38	1.33	1.34	1.41	1.33	1.34
30	1.32	1.33	1.92	1.33	---	1.33	1.34	1.33	1.34	1.41	1.33	1.72
31	1.33	---	1.56	1.33	---	1.33	---	1.33	---	1.36	1.33	---
MEAN	1.33	1.35	1.35	1.34	1.35	1.33	1.34	1.35	1.34	1.35	1.35	1.36
MAX	1.34	1.52	1.92	1.56	1.55	1.34	1.45	1.54	1.80	1.41	1.46	1.72
MIN	1.32	1.32	1.31	1.32	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.32	1.34	1.33	1.33

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50332000 RIVER GUT AT RIVER, ST. CROIX, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 17°44'32", long 64°48'52", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 0.20 mi (0.32 km) north from Quarry, 0.72 mi (1.16 km) northwest from Holly Cross church on route 72, 0.80 mi (1.29 km) southwest from top of Mt. Pleasant.

DRAINAGE AREA.--1.42 mi² (3.68 km²).

WATER-STAGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1991 to current year. (discontinued)

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 155 ft (47 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. All gage-heights of 29.60 ft or lower are considered zero flow.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.9	.85	1.6	.32	.11	.12	.09	.07	.11	.09	.11	.10
2	1.5	.89	1.3	.33	.17	.14	.08	.06	.11	.10	.11	.10
3	e.60	.69	1.0	.28	.80	.11	.07	.08	.12	.10	.10	.10
4	e.35	2.2	.92	.13	.23	.12	.07	.09	.10	.10	.10	.10
5	e.19	1.2	.99	.14	.11	.10	.06	.09	.10	.10	.10	.10
6	e.12	.94	.98	.33	.11	.10	.05	.09	.10	.10	.10	.10
7	.10	.80	.91	.63	.10	.10	.05	.09	.10	.10	.10	.10
8	.15	.66	.62	.56	.10	.10	.04	.10	.10	.10	.10	.10
9	.16	.62	.56	.50	.10	.10	.05	.13	.10	.10	.10	.10
10	.10	.58	.74	.58	.10	.10	.07	.16	.10	.09	.10	.10
11	.10	.58	.46	.62	.13	.10	.07	.15	.10	.09	.10	.10
12	.10	.52	.65	.57	.15	.10	.08	.10	.10	.10	.10	.10
13	.39	.46	1.1	.51	.12	.09	.09	.10	.11	.09	.10	.10
14	.59	.40	.85	.51	.31	.09	.09	.10	.11	.10	.10	.10
15	.72	2.4	.74	.43	.21	.09	.10	.10	.10	.10	.10	.10
16	.78	1.3	.41	.34	.18	.09	.11	.10	.10	.10	.10	.10
17	.65	2.6	.10	.31	.23	.09	.09	.10	.10	.10	.10	.10
18	.46	1.8	.10	.28	.25	.09	.09	.10	.10	.10	.10	.10
19	.30	2.4	.10	.27	.30	.09	.08	.10	.52	.10	.10	.10
20	.18	2.2	.13	.16	.34	.09	.07	.10	.70	.10	.10	.10
21	.44	1.1	.13	.11	.32	.09	.07	.10	.17	.10	.10	.10
22	.38	2.5	.10	.11	.73	.09	.07	.10	.12	.10	.10	.10
23	.28	1.3	.10	.29	.43	.09	.07	1.8	.10	5.4	.10	.10
24	.12	1.4	.21	.21	.11	.09	.06	1.2	.10	2.3	.10	.10
25	.35	1.3	.30	.26	.10	.09	.06	.11	.10	.46	.10	.10
26	.45	1.2	.28	.18	.10	.08	.05	2.3	.10	.28	.10	.10
27	.34	1.2	.30	.27	.10	.08	.05	20	.10	.14	.10	.10
28	.44	1.3	.25	.15	.11	.08	.05	1.2	.10	.11	.10	.10
29	.33	1.2	1.1	.10	---	.09	.05	.22	.10	.10	.10	.10
30	.13	1.1	5.5	.10	---	.09	.07	.19	.10	.11	.10	.10
31	.18	---	.63	.10	---	.09	---	.11	---	.11	.10	---
TOTAL	16.88	37.69	23.16	9.68	6.15	2.97	2.10	29.34	4.17	11.17	3.12	3.00
MEAN	.54	1.26	.75	.31	.22	.096	.070	.95	.14	.36	.10	.10
MAX	5.9	2.6	5.5	.63	.80	.14	.11	20	.70	5.4	.11	.10
MIN	.10	.40	.10	.10	.10	.08	.04	.06	.10	.09	.10	.10
MED	.34	1.2	.62	.28	.14	.09	.07	.10	.10	.10	.10	.10
AC-FT	33	75	46	19	12	5.9	4.2	58	8.3	22	6.2	6.0

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1992 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1992	1993	1992	1993	1992	1993	1992	1993	1992	1993	1992	1993
MEAN	.54	1.26	.99	.19	.11	.048	.041	1.38	.13	.18	.050	.38
MAX	.54	1.26	1.24	.31	.22	.096	.070	1.81	.14	.36	.10	.67
(WY)	1993	1993	1992	1993	1993	1993	1993	1992	1993	1993	1993	1992
MIN	.54	1.26	.75	.065	.014	.000	.011	.95	.13	.010	.000	.10
(WY)	1993	1993	1993	1992	1992	1992	1992	1993	1992	1992	1992	1993

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1992 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	160.83	149.43	
ANNUAL MEAN	.44	.41	.41
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			.41 1993
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			.41 1993
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	49	20	49 May 24 1992
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.00	.04	.00 Dec 19 1991
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.00	.06	.00 Feb 17 1992
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		230	564 May 24 1992
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		33.36	35.81 May 24 1992
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW		.04	.00 Dec 18 1991
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	319	296	297
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.91	.93	.79
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.02	.10	.10
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00	.09	.00

e Estimated

50333500 RIVER GUT NEAR GOLDEN GROVE, ST. CROIX, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'46", long 64°47'58", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, on right bank, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) from Experimental Station, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) from intersection of Highway 66 and road 64, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) from University of the U.S. Virgin Islands (UVI).

DRAINAGE AREA.--5.40 mi² (9.14 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.48	.00	e.00	.45	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
2	.00	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
3	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
4	.00	.00	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
5	.00	.00	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
6	.00	.00	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
7	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
8	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
9	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
10	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
11	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
12	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
13	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
14	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
15	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
16	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
17	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
18	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
19	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
20	.00	.03	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
21	.00	e11	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
22	.00	e7.0	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
23	.00	e.50	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	1.4	.00	.00
24	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	2.9	.00	.00
25	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.02	.00	.00
26	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	5.8	.00	.00	.00	.00
27	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	27	.00	.00	.00	.00
28	.00	e.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	10	.00	.00	.00	.00
29	.00	e.00	.00	.00	---	.00	.00	1.9	.00	.00	.00	.00
30	.00	e.00	10	.00	---	.00	.00	.44	.00	.00	.00	.00
31	.00	---	7.3	.00	---	.00	---	.00	---	.00	.00	---
TOTAL	0.48	18.53	17.30	0.45	0.00	0.00	0.00	45.14	0.00	4.32	0.00	0.00
MEAN	.015	.62	.56	.015	.000	.000	.000	1.46	.000	.14	.000	.000
MAX	.48	11	10	.45	.00	.00	.00	27	.00	2.9	.00	.00
MIN	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
AC-FT	1.0	.37	.34	.9	.00	.00	.00	.90	.00	8.6	.00	.00
CFSM	.00	.11	.10	.00	.00	.00	.00	.27	.00	.03	.00	.00
IN.	.00	.13	.12	.00	.00	.00	.00	.31	.00	.03	.00	.00

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1990 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1990	1991	1992	1993	1990	1991	1992	1993	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	4.53	.49	.19	.005	.000	.000	.000	1.38	.000	.046	.000	.001
MAX	13.6	.85	.56	.015	.000	.000	.000	2.69	.000	.14	.000	.003
(WY)	1991	1991	1993	1993	1991	1991	1991	1992	1991	1993	1991	1990
MIN	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
(WY)	1992	1992	1992	1991	1991	1991	1991	1991	1991	1991	1991	1991

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1990 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	119.58	86.22	
ANNUAL MEAN	.33	.24	.56
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			1.22
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			.23
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	83	May 25	169
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.00	Jan 1	.00
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.00	Jan 1	.00
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		167	860
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		45.86	49.03
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	237	171	407
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.061	.044	.10
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	.82	.59	1.42
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00	.00	.00
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00	.00	.00
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00	.00	.00

e Estimated

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50333700 RIVER GUT AT HWY 66 AT FAIRPLAINS, ST. CROIX, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'31", long 64°47'16", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 1.00 mi (1.61 km) southeast from Experimental Station, 1.10 mi (1.77 km) southeast from Hwy 70 and Hwy 64 intersection, 0.50 mi (0.80 km) west from Anguila ruins.

DRAINAGE AREA.--5.89 mi² (15.26 km²).

WATER-STAGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1990 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 20 ft (6 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum gage-height, 15.34 ft (4.676 m), May 25, 1992; minimum recorded, 10.46 ft (3.188 m), many days, but could be lower.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum gage-height, 13.91 ft (4.239 m), May 27; minimum recorded, 10.46 ft (3.188 m), many days.

GAGE HEIGHT, FEET, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	10.46	10.44	10.42	10.56	10.46	10.47	10.44	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
2	10.46	10.44	10.42	10.47	10.46	10.46	10.44	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
3	10.46	10.44	10.42	10.46	10.47	10.45	10.44	10.48	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
4	10.47	10.46	10.44	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.45	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
5	10.47	10.44	10.46	10.46	10.47	10.44	10.45	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
6	10.47	10.44	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
7	10.46	10.44	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
8	10.46	10.44	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
9	10.46	10.44	10.47	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.45	10.52	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.46
10	10.46	10.44	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.44	10.45	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.46
11	10.46	10.44	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.44	10.45	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.46
12	10.46	10.44	10.47	10.46	10.46	10.44	10.45	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.46
13	10.46	10.43	10.47	10.46	10.46	10.44	10.45	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.46
14	10.45	10.43	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.44	10.45	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.46
15	10.45	10.47	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.44	10.45	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.49	10.46
16	10.45	10.43	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.45	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
17	10.45	10.44	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.45	10.44	10.46	10.45	10.46	10.46
18	10.45	10.43	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.45	10.44	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
19	10.46	10.43	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.44	10.45	10.45	10.49	10.45	10.46	10.46
20	10.45	10.43	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.44	10.45	10.45	10.48	10.45	10.46	10.46
21	10.45	10.84	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.44	10.45	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
22	10.45	11.18	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.45	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
23	10.45	10.44	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.45	10.45	10.46	10.57	10.46	10.46
24	10.45	10.44	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.44	10.45	10.45	10.46	10.50	10.46	10.46
25	10.45	10.43	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.44	10.45	10.45	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
26	10.45	10.43	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.44	10.45	10.53	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
27	10.45	10.43	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.44	10.45	11.44	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
28	10.45	10.42	10.46	10.46	10.47	10.45	10.45	11.25	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
29	10.44	10.43	10.47	10.46	---	10.45	10.44	10.81	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
30	10.44	10.42	10.72	10.46	---	10.44	10.45	10.52	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.47
31	10.44	---	11.10	10.46	---	10.44	---	10.46	---	10.46	10.46	---
MEAN	10.45	10.47	10.49	10.46	10.46	10.45	10.45	10.53	10.46	10.46	10.46	10.46
MAX	10.47	11.18	11.10	10.56	10.47	10.47	10.45	11.44	10.49	10.57	10.49	10.47
MIN	10.44	10.42	10.42	10.46	10.45	10.44	10.44	10.44	10.46	10.45	10.45	10.46

50334500 BETHLEHEM GUT AT HWY 66 AT FAIRPLAINS, ST.CROIX, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'31", long 64°47'15", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 1.00 mi (1.61 km) southeast from Experimental Station, 1.10 mi (1.77 km) southeast from Hwy 70 and Hwy 64 intersection, 0.50 mi (0.80 km) west from Anguilla ruins.

DRAINAGE AREA.--4.11 mi² (10.64 km²).

WATER-STAGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1963 to 1969 monthly measurements only, May 1990 to current year. Prior to 1990 published as Bethlehem Gut at upper Bethlehem.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 20 ft (6 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. All gage-height of 11.45 ft or lower are considered zero flow.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum gage-height, 19.28 ft (5.876 m), May 25, 1992; minimum, 11.45 ft (3.490 m), many days, but could be lower.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum gage-height, 16.74 ft (5.102 m), May 27; minimum, 11.45 ft (3.490 m), many days.

GAGE HEIGHT, FEET, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	11.45	11.45	12.13	12.53	11.45	11.45	11.44	11.44	12.37	11.49	11.55	11.45
2	11.45	11.45	12.05	12.36	11.45	11.45	11.44	11.44	12.31	11.49	11.47	11.45
3	11.45	11.45	11.99	12.30	11.46	11.45	11.44	11.52	12.24	11.48	11.45	11.45
4	11.45	11.45	11.90	12.28	11.45	11.45	11.44	11.44	12.18	11.48	11.45	11.45
5	11.45	11.45	11.81	12.23	11.46	11.45	11.44	11.44	12.10	11.48	11.45	11.45
6	11.45	11.45	11.73	12.18	11.45	11.45	11.44	11.44	12.03	11.48	11.45	11.45
7	11.45	11.45	11.66	12.11	11.45	11.45	11.44	11.44	11.97	11.48	11.45	11.45
8	11.45	11.45	11.59	12.04	11.45	11.44	11.44	11.44	11.90	11.48	11.45	11.45
9	11.45	11.45	11.59	11.97	11.45	11.44	11.44	11.44	11.84	11.48	11.45	11.45
10	11.45	11.45	11.60	11.91	11.45	11.44	11.44	12.89	11.78	11.48	11.45	11.45
11	11.45	11.45	11.54	11.84	11.45	11.44	11.44	12.47	11.70	11.49	11.44	11.45
12	11.45	11.45	11.53	11.79	11.45	11.44	11.44	12.19	11.65	11.47	11.45	11.45
13	11.45	11.45	11.61	11.73	11.45	11.44	11.44	12.02	11.60	11.45	11.45	11.45
14	11.45	11.45	11.57	11.69	11.45	11.44	11.44	11.88	11.55	11.45	11.45	11.45
15	11.45	11.73	11.52	11.64	11.45	11.44	11.44	11.75	11.50	11.45	11.45	11.45
16	11.45	12.16	11.46	11.59	11.45	11.44	11.44	11.62	11.48	11.45	11.45	11.45
17	11.45	11.99	11.45	11.55	11.45	11.44	11.44	11.44	11.48	11.45	11.45	11.45
18	11.45	12.66	11.45	11.51	11.45	11.44	11.44	11.44	11.48	11.45	11.45	11.45
19	11.45	12.64	11.45	11.46	11.46	11.44	11.44	11.44	11.51	11.45	11.45	11.45
20	11.45	13.00	11.45	11.45	11.45	11.44	11.44	11.44	11.61	11.45	11.45	11.45
21	11.45	13.00	11.45	11.45	11.45	11.44	11.44	11.44	11.58	11.45	11.45	11.45
22	11.45	13.70	11.45	11.45	11.45	11.44	11.44	11.44	11.54	11.45	11.45	11.45
23	11.45	12.71	11.45	11.45	11.45	11.44	11.44	11.44	11.50	11.72	11.45	11.45
24	11.45	12.52	11.45	11.46	11.45	11.44	11.44	11.44	11.49	12.29	11.45	11.45
25	11.45	12.34	11.45	11.45	11.45	11.44	11.44	11.44	11.48	12.32	11.45	11.45
26	11.45	12.26	11.45	11.45	11.45	11.44	11.44	12.76	11.48	12.17	11.45	11.45
27	11.45	12.27	11.45	11.45	11.45	11.44	11.44	14.08	11.48	12.05	11.45	11.45
28	11.45	12.25	11.45	11.45	11.45	11.44	11.44	14.27	11.48	11.94	11.45	11.45
29	11.45	12.20	11.45	11.45	---	11.44	11.44	12.91	11.48	11.82	11.45	11.45
30	11.45	12.18	12.81	11.45	---	11.44	11.44	12.64	11.48	11.72	11.45	11.45
31	11.45	---	12.92	11.45	---	11.44	---	12.43	---	11.63	11.45	---
MEAN	11.45	12.00	11.67	11.75	11.45	11.44	11.44	11.93	11.71	11.61	11.45	11.45
MAX	11.45	13.70	12.92	12.53	11.46	11.45	11.44	14.27	12.37	12.32	11.55	11.45
MIN	11.45	11.45	11.45	11.45	11.45	11.44	11.44	11.44	11.48	11.45	11.44	11.45

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50337500 GUT 4.5 AT CANE VALLEY, ST. CROIX, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 17°43'25", long 66°51'01", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 2.1 mi (3.4 km) northeast from St. Patricks School at Frederiksted, 1.6 mi (2.6 km) northeast from Zion Church on Centerline road and 1.2 mi (2.0 km) from Mother of Perpetual Help Church near Monpedlier road 76.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.21 mi² (0.54 km²).

WATER-STAGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1991 to current year. (discontinued)

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 300 ft (91 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. All gage-height of 49.28 ft or lower are considered zero flow.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum gage-height, 50.65 ft (15.438 m), May 24, 1992; minimum, 49.27 ft (15.017 m), many days.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum gage-height 49.96 ft (15.227 m), July 23; minimum, 49.27 ft (15.107 m), many days.

GAGE HEIGHT, FEET, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	49.34	49.29	49.29	49.41	49.27	---	49.28	49.29	49.28	49.30		
2	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.33	49.27	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.28	49.31		
3	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.29	49.27	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.28	49.31		
4	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.29	49.27	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.28	49.31		
5	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.29	49.27	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.28	49.31		
6	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.29	49.27	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.28	49.31		
7	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.29	49.27	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.28	49.31		
8	49.29	49.29	49.29	49.29	49.27	49.28	49.28	49.29	---	49.30		
9	49.29	49.29	49.29	49.29	49.27	49.28	49.28	49.39	---	49.30		
10	49.29	49.29	49.29	---	49.28	49.28	49.28	49.30	49.28	49.30		
11	49.29	49.29	49.29	49.29	49.28	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.28	49.31		
12	49.29	49.29	49.40	49.28	49.28	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.28	49.31		
13	49.29	49.29	49.37	49.28	49.28	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.28	49.31		
14	49.29	49.29	49.29	49.28	49.28	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.28	49.31		
15	49.29	49.52	49.29	49.27	49.28	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.31		
16	49.29	49.60	49.29	49.27	49.28	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.31		
17	49.29	49.77	49.29	49.27	49.28	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.31		
18	49.29	49.65	49.29	49.27	49.28	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.31		
19	49.29	49.46	49.29	49.27	49.28	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.31		
20	49.29	49.30	49.29	49.27	49.28	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.32		
21	49.29	49.34	49.29	49.27	---	49.28	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.31		
22	49.29	49.57	49.29	49.27	---	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.30	49.32		
23	49.29	49.35	49.29	49.27	---	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.29	49.66		
24	49.29	49.31	49.29	49.27	---	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.30	49.57		
25	49.29	49.29	49.29	49.27	---	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.31	---		
26	49.29	49.29	49.29	49.27	---	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.31	---		
27	49.29	49.37	49.29	49.27	---	49.28	49.29	49.29	49.31	---		
28	49.29	49.29	49.29	49.27	---	49.28	49.29	49.28	49.31	---		
29	49.29	49.33	49.34	49.27	---	49.28	49.29	49.28	49.30	---		
30	49.29	49.29	49.82	49.27	---	49.28	49.29	49.28	49.31	---		
31	49.29	---	49.72	49.27	---	49.28	---	49.28	---	---		
MEAN	49.29	49.36	49.33	---	---	---	49.28	49.29	---	---		
MAX	49.34	49.77	49.82	---	---	---	49.29	49.39	---	---		
MIN	49.28	49.29	49.29	---	---	---	49.28	49.28	---	---		

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50345000 JOLLY HILL GUT AT JOLLY HILL, ST. CROIX, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 17°44'00", long 64°51'47", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, on Mahogany Road at Jolly Hill, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) northeast of Frederiksted.

DRAINAGE AREA.--2.10 mi² (5.44 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1963 to December 1968. Monthly measurements, 1962-69. October 1982 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder, crest-stage gage and sharp-crested concrete control. Elevation of gage is 140 ft (43 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor. Low-water diversions upstream from station. Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.07	.04	.15	e.27	.46	.14	.03	.03	.05	.07	.15	.04
2	.02	.00	.14	e.28	.46	.11	.03	.02	.05	.07	.13	.04
3	.00	.00	.14	e.23	.52	.09	.02	.05	.05	.07	.11	.03
4	.00	.10	.15	e.11	.48	.10	.02	.04	.05	.07	.08	.04
5	.00	.02	.16	e.12	.50	.09	.03	.03	.05	.06	.11	.04
6	.00	.00	.16	e.30	.53	.09	.04	.03	.05	.06	.10	.04
7	.00	.00	.18	e.41	.55	.09	.03	.03	.06	.06	.09	.04
8	.00	.00	.19	.41	.57	.08	.03	.03	.07	.06	.08	.04
9	.00	.00	.20	.41	.56	.08	.06	.09	.08	.05	.08	.04
10	.01	.00	.18	.41	.51	.08	.07	.07	.09	.05	.08	e.04
11	.00	.00	.18	.41	.49	.08	.08	.04	.09	.06	.07	e.02
12	.00	.00	.22	.41	.47	.10	.11	.03	.09	.06	.07	e.02
13	.00	.00	.21	.41	.43	.11	.09	.03	.08	.07	.07	e.02
14	.00	.08	.20	.43	.41	.10	.10	.03	.08	.07	.07	e.02
15	.00	.18	.20	.43	.39	.09	.10	.03	.08	.07	.07	e.02
16	.00	.13	.20	e.41	.38	.09	.11	.03	.07	.07	.07	e.03
17	.00	.14	.21	e.41	.37	.09	.12	.03	.07	.06	.06	e.03
18	.00	.14	.22	e.40	.34	.09	.13	.03	.07	.06	.05	e.01
19	.00	.13	.22	e.40	.32	.08	.18	.03	.09	.06	.05	e.01
20	.00	.10	.22	.46	.30	.08	.20	.03	.19	.05	.05	e.01
21	.00	.10	.20	.46	.29	.08	.22	.03	.08	.05	.05	e.01
22	.00	.12	.18	.47	.26	.08	.19	.04	.08	.05	.05	e.01
23	.00	.09	e.18	.47	.25	.08	.14	.06	.08	.98	.05	.01
24	.00	.09	e.22	.46	.22	.09	.10	.08	.07	.57	.05	.01
25	.00	.08	e.24	.45	.19	.09	.07	.08	.07	.44	.06	.01
26	.00	.08	e.23	.46	.17	.09	.04	.16	.07	.38	.05	.01
27	.00	.14	e.24	.47	.16	.09	.02	.07	.07	.35	.04	.01
28	.00	.14	e.21	.46	.14	.10	.01	.05	.07	.31	.04	.02
29	.00	.15	e1.5	.46	---	.11	.02	.04	.07	.28	.04	.01
30	.00	.13	e4.5	.46	---	.07	.04	.04	.07	.21	.04	.04
31	.00	---	e.45	.46	---	.03	---	.04	---	.18	.04	---
TOTAL	0.10	2.18	11.88	12.20	10.72	2.77	2.43	1.42	2.24	5.05	2.15	0.72
MEAN	.003	.073	.38	.39	.38	.089	.081	.046	.075	.16	.069	.024
MAX	.07	.18	4.5	.47	.57	.14	.22	.16	.19	.98	.15	.04
MIN	.00	.00	.14	.11	.14	.03	.01	.02	.05	.05	.04	.01
AC-FT	.2	4.3	24	24	21	5.5	4.8	2.8	4.4	10	4.3	1.4
CFSM	.00	.03	.18	.19	.18	.04	.04	.02	.04	.08	.03	.01
IN.	.00	.04	.21	.22	.19	.05	.04	.03	.04	.09	.04	.01

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1986 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	.61	.88	.62	.34	.22	.11	.084	.13
MAX	2.14	2.33	2.34	.88	.55	.34	.23	.46
(WY)	1991	1988	1988	1988	1988	1990	1990	1992
MIN	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
(WY)	1987	1992	1992	1992	1989	1989	1989	1989

SUMMARY STATISTICS

	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1963 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	38.04	53.86	
ANNUAL MEAN	.10	.15	.15
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			.58
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			.0003
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	12	4.5	22
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.00	.00	.00
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.00	.00	.00
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW		8.1	491
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE		1.52	4.33
ANNUAL RUNOFF (AC-FT)	75	107	138
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	.049	.070	.071
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	.67	.95	1.23
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.21	.41	.76
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00	.08	.05
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.00	.00	.00

e Estimated

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50348000 SALT RIVER AT CANNAN, ST. CROIX, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 17°45'40", long 64°47'53", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 6.20 mi (9.98 km) northwest from Cristianted Government House, 4.15 mi (6.68 km) north from Alexander Hamilton Airport main building, 3.10 mi (4.99 km) northeast from St. Lukes church at Grove Place.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.36 mi² (0.93 km²).

WATER-STAGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1991 to current year (discontinued).

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 315 ft (96 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. All gage-heights of 49.02 ft or lower are considered zero flow.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum gage-height, 51.20 ft (15.606 m), May 24, 1992; minimum recorded, 48.90 ft (14.905 m), June 24, 25, 1993.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum gage-height, 50.20 ft (15.301 m), May 27; minimum recorded, 48.90 ft (14.905 m), June 24, 25.

GAGE HEIGHT, FEET, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	49.06	49.00	48.99	48.96	48.94	48.98	48.95	48.97	48.95	48.92	---	48.93
2	49.06	48.99	48.96	48.96	48.93	48.98	48.95	48.97	48.95	48.92	---	48.93
3	49.07	49.00	48.93	48.96	48.93	48.97	48.95	48.97	48.95	48.92	---	48.93
4	49.07	48.99	48.93	48.96	48.93	48.98	48.95	48.97	48.95	48.92	48.92	48.93
5	49.07	48.99	48.93	48.96	48.93	48.98	48.95	48.97	48.95	48.93	48.92	48.93
6	49.05	---	48.93	48.99	48.93	48.98	48.95	48.97	48.95	48.93	48.89	48.93
7	49.04	48.99	48.93	49.04	48.93	48.98	48.95	48.95	48.95	48.93	48.89	48.93
8	49.02	48.98	48.93	49.04	48.93	48.98	48.95	48.95	48.93	48.93	48.89	48.93
9	49.02	48.98	48.93	49.04	48.93	48.97	48.95	48.95	48.91	48.93	48.89	48.94
10	49.00	48.98	48.93	49.04	48.93	48.97	48.94	48.95	48.91	48.93	48.89	48.94
11	49.00	48.99	48.93	49.03	48.93	48.97	48.94	48.95	48.91	48.93	48.89	---
12	49.00	48.99	48.93	49.03	48.94	48.97	48.95	48.95	48.91	48.93	48.89	---
13	49.00	48.99	48.93	49.04	48.94	48.97	48.95	48.95	48.91	48.93	48.89	---
14	49.00	48.99	48.93	48.97	48.94	48.97	48.95	48.95	48.91	48.93	48.89	---
15	48.98	48.99	48.93	48.92	48.94	48.97	48.95	48.95	48.91	48.93	48.89	---
16	---	---	48.93	48.92	48.95	48.97	48.95	48.95	48.91	48.93	48.89	---
17	---	48.98	48.93	48.92	48.94	48.97	48.95	48.95	48.91	48.93	48.89	---
18	---	48.98	48.93	48.92	48.92	48.97	48.95	48.95	48.91	48.93	48.92	---
19	49.01	49.14	48.93	48.92	48.94	48.97	48.95	48.95	48.91	48.93	48.93	---
20	49.00	49.02	48.93	48.92	48.96	48.97	48.95	48.95	48.91	---	48.93	---
21	49.00	48.98	48.94	48.92	48.97	48.96	48.95	48.95	48.91	---	48.93	---
22	49.00	48.98	48.94	48.92	48.97	48.96	48.96	48.95	48.91	---	48.93	48.94
23	49.00	48.99	48.94	48.92	48.97	48.96	48.96	48.95	48.91	---	48.93	48.94
24	49.01	48.98	48.94	48.92	48.97	48.96	48.96	48.95	48.90	---	48.93	48.95
25	49.00	48.99	48.94	48.92	48.97	48.96	48.96	48.95	48.91	---	48.93	48.95
26	49.00	48.95	48.94	48.93	48.97	48.96	48.96	49.01	48.92	---	48.94	48.94
27	48.99	48.98	48.94	48.94	---	48.96	48.96	49.24	48.92	---	48.94	48.94
28	49.00	48.99	48.94	48.94	---	48.96	48.96	49.07	48.92	---	48.94	48.94
29	49.00	---	48.93	48.94	---	48.96	48.96	48.95	48.92	---	48.93	48.94
30	48.99	48.98	48.95	48.94	---	48.96	48.96	48.95	48.92	---	48.93	48.94
31	48.99	---	48.96	48.94	---	48.96	---	48.95	---	---	48.93	---
MEAN	---	---	48.94	48.96	---	48.97	48.95	48.97	48.92	---	---	---
MAX	---	---	48.99	49.04	---	48.98	48.96	49.24	48.95	---	---	---
MIN	---	---	48.93	48.92	---	48.96	48.94	48.95	48.90	---	---	---

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50349000 GUT 10 NEAR ALTONA, ST. CROIX, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 17°44'00", long 64°41'30", Hydrologinc Unit 21020002, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) southeast of Christiansted, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) west of prospect Hill and 1.0 mi (1.6 km) north of junction of Highways 62 and 85.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.13 mi² (0.34 km²).

WATER-STAGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1991 to current year. (discontinued)

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 210 ft (64 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Gage-height and precipitation satellite telemetry at station. All gage-height of 49.57 ft or lower are considered zero flow.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum gage-height, 50.80 ft (15.484 m), May 25, 1992; minimum, 49.50 ft (15.088 m), Dec. 12, 22, 1992.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT PERIOD.--Maximun gage-height, 49.58 ft (15.112 m), Dec. 4-14; minimum recorded, 49.52 ft (15.094 m), Feb. 10, 11.

GAGE HEIGHT, FEET, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	49.57	49.55	49.57	49.57	49.56							
2	49.57	49.55	49.57	49.57	49.56							
3	49.59	49.55	49.57	49.57	49.56							
4	49.57	49.55	49.57	49.56	49.56							
5	49.57	49.56	49.58	49.56	49.56							
6	49.57	49.56	49.58	49.56	49.56							
7	49.55	49.56	49.58	49.57	49.56							
8	49.56	49.56	49.58	49.56	49.56							
9	49.54	49.56	49.58	49.56	49.55							
10	49.54	49.56	49.58	49.56	49.53							
11	49.54	49.56	49.58	49.56	49.53							
12	49.54	49.56	49.58	49.56	49.53							
13	49.54	49.56	49.58	49.56	49.53							
14	49.54	49.56	49.58	49.55	49.54							
15	49.54	49.56	49.57	49.55	49.54							
16	49.54	49.56	49.57	49.55	49.54							
17	49.55	49.56	49.57	49.55	49.52							
18	49.55	49.56	49.57	49.56	---							
19	49.55	49.56	49.57	49.56	---							
20	49.55	49.56	49.57	49.55	---							
21	49.55	49.56	49.57	49.55	---							
22	49.55	49.56	49.57	49.55	---							
23	49.55	49.56	49.57	49.55	---							
24	49.56	49.56	49.57	49.55	---							
25	49.56	49.57	49.57	49.55	---							
26	49.55	49.57	49.57	49.55	---							
27	49.55	49.57	49.57	49.56	---							
28	49.56	49.57	49.57	49.56	---							
29	49.56	49.57	49.57	49.56	---							
30	49.56	49.57	49.57	49.56	---							
31	49.55	---	49.57	49.56	---							
MEAN	49.55	49.56	49.57	49.56	---							
MAX	49.59	49.57	49.58	49.57	---							
MIN	49.54	49.55	49.57	49.55	---							

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**Ground-Water Records
for U.S. Virgin Islands**

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174225064471900. Local number, 1.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'25", long 64°47'19", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 6 mi southwest of Christiansted Plaza, 1.00 mi southeast of the Experimental Station, and 0.50 mi northeast of the Alexander Hamilton Airport entrance on Hwy 64. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, Name: Fairplains 6 (FP6).

AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Observation drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Monthly measurement with chalked steel tape by USGS personnel.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 20.0 ft (6.10 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Measuring point: Top of pump concrete base, 2.20 ft (0.67 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 15.64 ft (4.77 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 25, 1982; lowest water level measured, a59.26 ft (18.1 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 25, 1990.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 8	18.12	Mar. 2	17.37	May 18	17.88	July 29	16.84
Jan. 7	17.71	Apr. 13	18.27	June 21	16.92	Aug. 31	17.12
Feb. 9	16.91						

WATER YEAR 1993 HIGHEST 16.84 JULY 29, 1993 LOWEST 18.27 APR. 13, 1993

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174225064472000. Local number, 2.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'25", long 64°47'20", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 0.90 mi southeast of the Experimental Station, 0.6 mi southwest of Christiansted Plaza, and 0.18 mi northeast of the Alexander Hamilton Airport entrance on Hwy 64. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, Name: USGS-10, Fairplains 2 (FP2).

AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 20 ft (6.10 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 0.5 in (0.01 m) hole at concrete base wall, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1983 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 19.45 ft (5.93 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 4, 1989; lowest water level recorded, 26.46 ft (8.06 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 25, 1990.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	23.73	24.07	23.28	22.65	21.95	22.32	23.05	23.31	22.67	22.03	21.89	21.97
2	23.75	24.04	23.30	22.58	21.88	22.29	23.03	23.28	22.66	22.10	21.94	22.01
3	23.88	24.02	23.22	22.54	21.92	22.27	23.03	23.15	22.70	22.02	21.83	21.99
4	23.78	23.97	23.25	22.56	21.88	22.33	22.97	23.19	22.67	21.95	21.87	21.96
5	23.77	24.01	23.28	22.51	21.92	22.39	23.06	23.26	22.57	22.00	21.90	21.87
6	23.80	24.07	23.19	22.55	21.94	22.45	23.19	23.13	22.48	22.12	21.88	21.86
7	23.84	23.97	23.10	22.62	21.90	22.36	23.22	23.28	22.44	22.01	21.81	21.85
8	23.82	24.07	23.11	22.46	21.90	22.39	23.21	23.17	22.44	22.04	21.87	22.00
9	23.83	24.11	23.06	22.29	21.91	22.38	23.16	23.12	22.45	22.14	21.93	22.08
10	23.95	24.16	23.11	22.22	21.96	22.39	23.12	23.05	22.40	22.06	21.91	22.16
11	23.82	24.09	23.13	22.14	21.99	22.44	23.07	23.09	22.47	21.96	21.94	22.04
12	23.80	24.03	23.05	22.18	22.02	22.50	23.10	22.98	22.40	21.96	21.89	22.06
13	23.88	24.18	22.98	22.13	22.04	22.50	23.08	23.10	22.32	22.13	21.85	22.12
14	23.97	24.09	22.93	22.08	22.05	22.43	23.19	23.11	22.27	22.09	21.89	22.14
15	23.90	24.13	22.99	22.02	21.96	22.49	23.25	23.01	22.35	22.11	21.91	22.18
16	23.88	23.97	23.02	21.98	22.02	22.59	23.16	23.11	22.41	22.12	21.82	22.14
17	24.03	23.91	22.93	22.00	22.10	22.60	23.17	23.07	22.38	22.18	21.88	22.23
18	24.02	23.95	23.00	21.93	22.00	22.64	23.12	23.01	22.32	22.08	21.83	22.19
19	24.06	23.86	22.91	21.92	22.16	22.63	23.11	23.02	22.34	22.11	21.77	22.12
20	24.06	23.95	22.93	21.98	22.12	22.65	23.23	23.09	22.16	22.22	21.88	22.15
21	23.97	23.80	22.95	21.94	22.01	22.73	23.20	23.00	22.15	22.25	21.85	22.12
22	24.03	23.70	22.97	21.94	22.13	22.81	23.27	23.17	22.16	22.25	21.83	22.17
23	24.03	23.62	23.01	21.97	22.30	22.87	23.32	23.25	22.16	22.13	21.73	22.23
24	23.96	23.58	22.99	21.90	22.21	22.92	23.27	23.10	22.18	22.05	21.75	22.27
25	23.96	23.53	22.92	21.90	22.26	22.85	23.23	23.18	22.20	22.05	21.82	22.19
26	23.88	23.46	22.89	22.01	22.32	22.93	23.29	23.17	22.15	21.97	21.92	22.16
27	23.81	23.36	22.83	21.94	22.31	22.97	23.25	23.01	22.07	21.99	21.88	22.04
28	23.99	23.39	22.77	21.91	22.29	22.95	23.38	23.05	22.00	21.93	21.88	22.18
29	23.99	23.48	22.77	21.94	---	22.91	23.30	22.85	22.14	21.93	21.88	22.09
30	24.05	23.34	22.74	22.00	---	22.97	23.32	22.80	22.08	21.87	21.88	22.14
31	24.13	---	22.73	21.93	---	23.00	---	22.63	---	21.90	21.94	---
MEAN	23.92	23.86	23.01	22.15	22.05	22.61	23.18	23.09	22.34	22.06	21.87	22.09

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 22.69 HIGHEST 21.67 AUG. 24, 1993 LOWEST 24.20 NOV. 13, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174243064475100. Local number, 3.
 LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'43", long 64°47'51", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 0.75 mi northwest of the Alexander Hamilton Airport entrance on Hwy 64, 6.45 mi southwest of Christiansted Plaza, and 0.57 mi southwest of the Experimental Station. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, Name: Golden Grove - 6 (PW6).
 AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 8 in (0.20 m), cased 8 in (0.20 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 40 ft (12.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Upper edge of hole at 8 in (0.20 m) casing, 4.20 ft (1.28 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 12.99 ft (3.96 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 10, 1990; lowest water level recorded, 35.23 ft (10.7 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 23-24, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	33.61	34.48	32.62	30.33	29.26	30.59	31.28	31.70	27.89	28.72	27.81	29.06
2	33.67	34.51	31.45	29.24	29.32	30.62	31.31	31.72	27.89	28.77	27.78	29.12
3	33.71	34.60	29.97	28.35	29.43	30.66	31.33	31.73	27.89	28.82	27.77	29.20
4	33.75	34.64	29.86	27.79	29.49	30.70	31.35	31.74	27.89	28.88	27.71	29.26
5	33.77	34.66	29.79	27.46	29.54	30.75	31.36	31.75	26.93	28.95	27.77	29.32
6	33.80	34.69	29.77	27.29	29.62	30.78	31.40	31.75	26.94	29.00	27.82	29.37
7	33.84	34.71	29.80	27.24	29.66	30.82	31.42	31.76	26.96	29.05	27.89	29.45
8	33.88	34.78	29.84	27.23	29.67	30.84	31.46	31.77	26.99	29.09	27.98	29.51
9	33.89	34.81	29.90	27.24	29.67	30.85	31.49	31.78	27.04	29.16	28.05	29.55
10	33.90	34.87	29.97	27.27	29.74	30.85	31.52	31.78	27.11	29.24	28.13	29.62
11	33.91	34.95	30.05	27.31	29.80	30.83	31.54	31.78	27.18	29.30	27.94	29.67
12	33.92	34.97	30.16	27.38	29.84	30.81	31.56	31.76	27.25	29.35	28.13	29.73
13	33.95	34.99	30.25	27.47	29.91	30.78	31.56	31.72	27.33	29.41	28.20	29.79
14	33.97	35.01	30.34	27.53	29.97	30.76	31.58	31.69	27.42	29.35	28.26	29.82
15	34.00	35.02	30.52	27.61	30.02	30.75	31.59	31.63	27.51	29.42	28.32	29.84
16	34.04	35.03	30.59	27.72	30.06	30.80	31.61	31.59	27.58	29.50	28.37	29.83
17	34.08	35.06	30.67	27.84	30.13	30.84	31.61	31.56	27.66	29.56	28.41	29.84
18	34.11	35.09	30.78	27.95	30.15	30.89	31.60	31.54	27.77	29.60	28.46	29.86
19	34.14	35.11	30.85	28.04	30.22	30.92	31.59	31.54	27.83	29.66	28.28	29.88
20	34.18	35.14	30.88	28.13	30.26	30.96	31.59	31.57	27.90	29.72	28.46	29.91
21	34.21	35.16	30.94	28.24	30.33	30.99	31.60	31.62	27.97	29.75	28.53	29.95
22	34.23	35.19	31.00	28.35	30.35	31.02	31.59	31.67	28.06	29.81	28.57	29.99
23	34.25	35.22	31.07	28.47	30.38	31.05	31.59	31.70	28.12	29.84	28.63	30.03
24	34.27	35.23	31.11	28.57	30.44	31.08	31.61	31.72	28.20	29.86	28.54	30.09
25	34.34	34.98	31.17	28.68	30.50	31.11	31.60	31.74	28.28	29.70	28.68	30.13
26	34.37	34.96	31.21	28.74	30.53	31.13	31.59	31.78	28.36	29.25	28.74	30.18
27	34.44	34.95	31.25	28.84	30.56	31.16	31.59	31.80	28.42	28.78	28.76	30.22
28	34.46	34.34	31.30	28.94	30.57	31.18	31.61	31.67	28.51	28.43	28.82	30.28
29	34.48	32.81	31.34	29.01	---	31.21	31.64	30.92	28.59	28.22	28.89	30.32
30	34.44	32.75	31.37	29.10	---	31.22	31.68	29.74	28.66	28.01	28.94	30.37
31	34.46	---	31.19	29.19	---	31.25	---	28.45	---	27.88	29.01	---
MEAN	34.07	34.76	30.68	28.15	29.98	30.91	31.53	31.51	27.74	29.16	28.31	29.77

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 30.55 HIGHEST 26.88 JUNE 5, 1993 LOWEST 35.23 NOV. 23-24, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174245064475800. Local number, 4.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'45", long 64°47'58", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 5.40 mi east of Fort Frederick at Frederickstead, 0.80 mi northeast of Envy, and 1.52 mi southeast of Holy Cross Church. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, Name: Golden Grove - 1 (PW1).

AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Observation drilled production water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m), 0-104 ft (0-31.70 m), perforated 64-104 ft (19.51-31.70 m). Depth 104 ft (31.70 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Monthly measurement with chalked steel tape by USGS personnel.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 40 ft (12.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Measuring point: Lower edge of 1 in. (0.02 m) pipe at pump base, 3.40 ft (1.04 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1983 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD: Highest water level measured, 19.08 ft (5.81 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 26, 1990; lowest water level measured, a58.30 ft (17.77 m) below land-surface datum, September 27, 1983.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 4	35.26	Feb. 9	a48.03	Apr. 13	a48.10	June 21	a48.00
Jan. 5	a48.32	Mar. 2	a48.20	May 18	a48.10	July 28	a48.03

WATER YEAR 1993 HIGHEST 35.26 DEC. 4, 1992 LOWEST a48.32 JAN. 5, 1993

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174303064484400. Local number, 6.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°43'03", long 64°48'44", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 4.95 mi northeast of Fort Frederick at Frederickstead, 1.10 mi southwest of Holy Cross Church, and 0.40 mi northwest of Adventure ruins. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, Name: Adventure 28.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Pleistocene age and marl of Oligocene age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m). Depth 97 ft (29.6 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Monthly measurement with chalked steel tape by USGS personnel.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 80 ft (24.39 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Measuring point: Upper edge of hole at 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum. Prior June 20, 1983, top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 0.90 ft (0.27 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1973 to March 1974, discontinued. March 1982 to October 30, 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 22.80 ft (6.95 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 13, 1991; lowest water level measured, 42.3 ft (12.9 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 30, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 1	42.15	Oct. 30	42.28

WATER YEAR 1993 HIGHEST 42.15 OCT. 1, 1992 LOWEST 42.28 OCT. 30, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174525064460600. Local number, 7.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°45'25", long 64°46'06", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 4.35 mi northwest of Christiansted Plaza, 4.25 mi northeast of the Alexander Hamilton Airport entrance on Hwy 64, and 0.45 mi southeast of Windsor Ruins. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, Name: Concordia 14.

AQUIFER.--Sand and gravel.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Observation drilled production water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 85 ft (25.91 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Monthly measurement with chalked steel tape by USGS personnel.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 40 ft (12.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Measuring point: Top of 0.50 in (0.01 m) pipe on top of pump concrete base, 2.30 ft (0.70 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumpage.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 10.07 ft (3.07 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 4, 1989; lowest water level measured, a48.20 ft (a14.7 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 24, 1990.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 8	a46.74	Feb. 10	a44.20	June 22	22.24	July 30	26.84
Jan. 8	a41.49						

WATER YEAR 1993 HIGHEST 22.24 JUNE 22, 1993 LOWEST a46.74 DEC. 8, 1992

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174527064460100. Local number, 8.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°45'27", long 64°46'01", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 4.35 mi northeast of the Alexander Hamilton Airport entrance on Hwy 64, 4.15 mi northwest of Christiansted Plaza, and 0.50 mi southeast of Windsor Ruins. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, Name: Concordia 1 (Main pump house).

AQUIFER.--Limestone of Tertiary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Observation drilled production water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 82 ft (25.0 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Monthly measurement with chalked steel tape by USGS personnel.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 40 ft (12.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.20 ft (0.67 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumpage.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 14.03 ft (4.28 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 19, 1988; lowest water level measured, a49.34 ft (a15.4 m) below land-surface datum, May 4, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 8	a43.52	Feb. 10	35.26	Apr. 14	a43.80	July 30	26.67
Jan. 8	35.30	Mar. 3	36.38	June 23	a34.52		

WATER YEAR 1993 HIGHEST 26.67 JULY 30, 1993 LOWEST a43.80 APR. 14, 1993

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174532064460300. Local number, 9.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°45'32", long 64°46'03", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 4.20 mi northwest of Christiansted Plaza, 4.32 mi northeast of Alexander Hamilton Airport entrance on Hwy 64, and 0.40 mi southeast of Windsor Ruins. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, Name: Concordia 7.

AQUIFER.--Limestone of Tertiary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Observation drilled production water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 0-81 ft (0-24.7 m). Depth 81 ft (24.7 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Monthly measurement with chalked steel tape by USGS personnel.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 35 ft (10.7 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Measuring point: Hole in pump base, 2.20 ft (0.67 m) above land-surface datum. Previous to Mar. 25, 1982, hole in pump base 2.50 ft (0.76 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1962 to October 1968, discontinued. March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 1.75 ft (0.53 m) below land-surface datum, May 11, 1966; lowest water level measured, 57.40 ft (17.5 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 5, 1964.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 8	a35.83	Feb. 10	a36.18	Apr. 16	a36.42	July 30	12.51
Jan. 8	a35.43	Mar. 3	15.45	May 21	a34.94		
WATER YEAR 1993 HIGHEST 12.51 JULY 30, 1993		LOWEST a36.42		APR. 16, 1993			

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174329064454700. Local number, 10.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°43'29", long 64°45'47", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 4.05 mi southwest of Christiansted plaza, 2.40 mi northeast of the Experimental Station, and 2.75 mi northeast of the Alexander Hamilton Airport entrance on Hwy 64. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, Name: Barren Spot 5 (PWD-5).

AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled production water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 0-130 ft (0-39.63 m), perforated 71-130 ft (21.64-39.63 m). Depth 130 ft (39.63 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Monthly measurement with chalked steel tape by USGS personnel.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 75 ft (22.86 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Measuring point: Hole on top of pump base, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 61.86 ft (18.86 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 26, 1982; lowest water level measured, a79.81 ft (a24.33 m) below land-surface datum, June 25, 1990.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level						
Dec. 8	a77.30	Mar. 3	a75.42	May 21	a75.54	July 29	64.22
Jan. 8	a77.30	Apr. 14	a75.67	June 22	a75.33	Aug. 31	63.62
Feb. 10	64.60						

WATER YEAR 1993 HIGHEST 63.62 AUG. 31, 1993 LOWEST a77.30 DEC. 8, 1992, JAN. 8, 1993

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174303064481100. Local number, 11.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°43'03", long 64°18'11", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 5.20 mi east of Fort Frederick at Frederickstead, 1.20 mi southeast of Holy Cross Church, and 0.45 mi northeast of Adventure Ruins. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority, Name: WAPA-02 at Adventure well field.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium and Kingshill Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-60 ft (0-18.3 m), screened 20-40 ft (6.09-12.2 m). Open hole 60-100 ft (18.3-30.5 m). Depth 100 ft (30.5 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 50 ft (15.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 27, 1990 to October 30, 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 9.75 ft (2.97 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 26-27, 1990; lowest water level recorded, 27.68 ft (8.44 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 19-23, 1992

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	27.01	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
2	27.01	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
3	27.01	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
4	26.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
5	26.82	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
6	26.70	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
7	26.58	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
8	26.47	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
9	26.38	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
10	26.31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
11	26.27	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
12	26.20	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
13	26.12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
14	26.02	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
15	25.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
16	25.86	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
17	25.76	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
18	25.63	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
19	25.49	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
20	25.35	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
21	25.22	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
22	25.09	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
23	24.97	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
24	24.83	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
25	24.71	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
26	24.56	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
27	24.44	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
28	24.34	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
29	24.29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	25.80	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 25.80 HIGHEST 24.29 OCT. 10, 1992 LOWEST 27.02 OCT. 29, 30, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174308064482800. Local number, 12.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°43'08", long 64°48'28", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 4.95 mi east of Fort Frederick at Frederickstead, 1.10 mi south of Holy Cross Church, and 0.40 mi northeast of Adventure Ruins. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority, Name: WAPA-03 at Adventure well field.

AQUIFER.--Kingshill Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-110 ft (0-33.5 m), screened 50-90 ft (15.2-27.4 m). Depth 110 ft (33.5 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 60 ft (18.3 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 28, 1990 to October 30, 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 16.13 ft (4.92 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 25, 1991; lowest water level recorded, 36.54 ft (11.13 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 30, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	36.42	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
2	36.38	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
3	36.34	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
4	36.29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
5	36.23	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
6	36.18	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
7	36.12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
8	35.32	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
9	34.82	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
10	34.30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
11	33.68	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
12	33.21	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
13	32.86	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
14	33.68	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
15	34.51	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
16	35.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
17	35.42	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
18	35.63	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
19	35.78	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
20	35.89	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
21	36.00	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
22	36.11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
23	36.19	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
24	36.29	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
25	36.35	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
26	36.39	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
27	36.43	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
28	36.48	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
29	36.53	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	35.55	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 35.55 HIGHEST 32.86 OCT. 13, 1992 LOWEST 36.54 OCT. 30, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174316064480800. Local number, 13.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°43'16", long 64°48'08", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 5.25 mi east of Fort Frederick at Frederickstead, 0.95 mi southeast of Holy Cross Church, and 0.65 mi northeast of Adventure Ruins. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority, Name: WAPA-17 at Adventure well field.

AQUIFER.--Kingshill Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-95 ft (0-29.0 m), screened 10-40 ft (3.05-12.2 m). Depth 95 ft (29.0 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 75 ft (22.9 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 2.33 ft (0.71 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 28, 1990 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 4.68 ft (1.43 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 14 1990; lowest water level recorded, 21.36 ft (6.51 m) below land-surface datum, May 23, 1992

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	17.67	17.49	11.35	7.01	8.09	8.49	9.71	11.39	6.91	8.67	8.56	9.72
2	15.09	17.52	11.32	7.22	7.87	8.51	9.75	11.45	7.14	8.71	8.60	9.78
3	15.23	17.55	11.38	7.31	7.76	8.55	9.84	11.48	7.59	8.76	8.64	9.87
4	15.48	17.28	11.44	7.36	7.39	8.59	9.91	11.42	7.81	8.81	8.63	9.91
5	15.86	15.98	11.48	7.42	7.60	8.59	9.97	11.48	7.97	8.86	8.62	9.97
6	16.23	16.01	11.51	7.47	7.71	8.62	10.05	11.54	8.06	---	8.62	10.03
7	16.45	16.36	11.53	7.53	7.80	8.67	10.13	11.58	8.14	---	8.64	10.13
8	16.55	16.73	11.52	7.63	7.90	8.68	10.17	11.56	8.16	---	8.70	10.19
9	16.67	16.87	11.45	7.65	7.95	8.71	10.25	11.49	8.20	---	8.73	10.28
10	16.74	16.95	11.35	7.68	8.01	8.74	10.25	9.51	8.23	9.03	8.78	10.34
11	16.78	17.04	11.25	7.64	8.06	8.80	10.24	9.87	8.26	9.03	8.82	10.45
12	16.84	17.10	11.13	7.71	8.10	8.84	10.24	10.25	8.29	9.08	8.86	10.53
13	16.90	17.15	10.22	7.86	8.13	8.88	10.21	10.50	8.30	9.08	8.90	10.63
14	16.95	17.21	10.21	7.87	8.17	8.91	10.21	10.69	8.35	9.08	8.95	10.72
15	17.02	17.23	10.28	7.93	8.21	8.94	10.23	10.83	8.38	9.26	8.93	10.83
16	17.07	14.81	10.34	7.98	8.20	8.98	10.24	10.96	8.41	9.27	8.82	10.87
17	17.11	14.70	10.35	8.02	8.21	9.02	10.28	11.07	8.47	9.34	8.89	10.95
18	17.15	12.93	10.37	8.08	8.24	9.06	10.37	11.16	8.51	9.43	8.95	11.02
19	17.21	12.92	10.39	8.12	8.25	9.10	10.47	11.26	8.35	9.52	9.00	11.10
20	17.24	13.02	10.38	8.07	8.27	9.16	10.51	11.34	7.76	9.57	9.05	11.19
21	17.21	13.20	10.39	8.06	8.32	9.22	10.57	11.42	8.04	9.64	9.10	11.25
22	17.24	9.79	10.39	8.16	8.35	9.26	10.65	11.49	8.16	9.68	9.15	11.31
23	17.26	10.74	10.39	7.95	8.35	9.29	10.73	11.56	8.27	8.15	9.21	11.37
24	17.30	11.42	10.36	8.04	8.37	9.33	10.81	11.62	8.35	7.50	9.25	11.28
25	17.33	11.77	10.36	8.08	8.40	9.39	10.91	11.69	8.41	7.58	9.29	11.36
26	17.35	11.98	10.34	8.11	8.43	9.43	11.00	11.29	8.48	7.89	9.37	11.42
27	17.39	12.09	10.32	8.11	8.45	9.51	11.08	9.72	8.54	8.15	9.37	11.48
28	17.42	12.13	10.30	8.08	8.47	9.56	11.18	6.71	8.59	8.32	9.44	11.52
29	17.42	12.17	10.29	8.09	---	9.59	11.25	6.57	8.63	8.44	9.50	11.56
30	17.42	11.23	8.54	8.09	---	9.60	11.34	6.65	8.68	8.51	9.57	11.60
31	17.45	---	6.70	8.09	---	9.67	---	6.77	---	8.55	9.65	---
MEAN	16.87	14.65	10.57	7.82	8.11	9.02	10.42	10.53	8.18	8.81	8.99	10.76

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 10.42 HIGHEST 6.56 MAY 29, 1993 LOWEST 17.78 OCT. 1, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174247064475701. Local number, 14.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'47", long 64°47'57", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 0.80 mi northwest of the Alexander Hamilton Airport entrance on Hwy 64, 0.53 mi south of the Experimental Station, and 6.65 mi southwest of Christiansted Plaza. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority, Name: WAPA-21a at Golden Grove well field.

AQUIFER.--Alluvial, Kingshill Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-70 ft (0-21.3 m), screened 15-70 ft (4.57-21.3 m). Depth 100 ft (30.5 m), well collapsed to 70 ft (21.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 52 ft (15.8 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.25 ft (0.99 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 28, 1990 to October 30, 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 14.19 ft (4.32 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 3, 1990; lowest water level recorded, 43.26 ft (13.2 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 22, 1992

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	41.73	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
2	41.77	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
3	41.81	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
4	41.80	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
5	41.81	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
6	41.76	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
7	41.77	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
8	41.78	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
9	41.81	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
10	41.82	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
11	41.83	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
12	41.84	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
13	41.85	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
14	41.88	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
15	41.90	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
16	41.91	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
17	41.92	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
18	41.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
19	41.95	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
20	41.82	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
21	41.89	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
22	41.96	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
23	42.00	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
24	41.99	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
25	42.01	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
26	41.99	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
27	42.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
28	42.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
29	42.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	41.89	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 41.89 HIGHEST 38.29 OCT. 20, 1992 LOWEST 42.08 OCT. 30, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174319064454401. Local number, 15.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°43'19", long 64°45'44", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, 2.55 mi northeast of the Alexander Hamilton Airport entrance on Hwy 64, 4.00 mi southwest of Christiansted Plaza, and 2.30 mi northeast of the Experimental Station. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority, Name: WAPA-23a at Barren Spot well field.

AQUIFER.--Post Kingshill Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-110 ft (0-33.5 m), screened 70-110 ft (21.3-33.5 m). Depth 110 ft (33.5 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 65 ft (19.8 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.50 ft (1.07 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 28, 1990 to October 30, 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 55.29 ft (16.8 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 1, 1991; lowest water level recorded, 69.68 ft (21.3 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 29, 1991.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	60.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
2	60.07	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
3	60.07	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
4	60.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
5	60.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
6	60.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
7	60.06	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
8	60.05	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
9	60.04	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
10	60.04	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
11	59.97	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
12	59.98	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
13	59.98	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
14	60.00	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
15	60.00	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
16	60.02	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
17	59.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
18	59.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
19	59.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
20	59.92	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
21	59.92	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
22	59.92	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
23	59.92	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
24	59.91	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
25	59.89	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
26	59.85	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
27	59.88	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
28	59.86	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
29	59.88	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
MEAN	59.98	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 59.98 HIGHEST 59.14 OCT. 15-16, 1992 LOWEST 60.09 OCT. 16, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182038064550300. Local number, 6.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'38", long 64°55'03", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 1.12 mi east of Charlotte Amalie, 0.75 mi southwest of Winterberg Peak, and 1.08 mi southeast of Canaan. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, Name: Grade School 3.
 AQUIFER.--Volcanic breccia.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 70 ft (21.3 m).
 INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 60 ft (18.3 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Measuring point: Top of 0.5 in (0.01 m) hole at 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.30 ft (0.40 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to June 27, 1983, top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.90 ft (0.88 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 1.53 ft (0.47 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 1, 1989; lowest water level recorded, 35.38 ft (10.79 m) below land-surface datum, July 21, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	29.30	29.51	27.67	26.90	27.57	29.80	---	28.82	25.39	26.21	29.04	29.49
2	29.34	29.52	27.30	26.45	27.74	29.73	---	28.96	25.63	26.31	29.23	29.46
3	29.56	29.51	27.17	26.33	27.81	---	---	29.21	25.98	26.37	29.51	29.65
4	29.81	29.47	27.21	26.37	27.80	---	---	29.22	26.42	26.46	29.51	29.96
5	29.81	29.52	27.34	26.40	27.81	---	---	29.05	26.75	26.50	29.35	30.25
6	29.70	29.48	27.52	26.46	27.88	---	---	28.88	26.86	26.53	29.25	30.14
7	29.69	29.36	27.77	26.48	27.90	---	---	28.80	26.87	26.63	29.38	29.86
8	29.80	29.25	28.02	26.41	27.88	---	---	28.87	26.92	26.78	29.63	29.79
9	30.01	29.18	28.24	26.38	27.98	---	31.07	29.02	27.00	26.94	29.87	29.93
10	30.13	29.18	28.38	26.42	28.17	---	30.99	28.68	27.11	27.00	29.85	30.23
11	30.03	29.23	28.43	26.45	28.28	---	30.59	28.05	27.29	27.00	29.63	30.58
12	29.90	29.39	28.56	26.50	28.26	---	30.29	27.63	27.57	26.98	29.54	30.86
13	---	29.52	28.73	26.61	28.30	---	30.10	27.49	27.91	27.10	29.44	31.08
14	30.04	29.55	28.90	26.68	28.39	---	29.99	27.51	28.26	27.26	29.42	31.01
15	30.30	29.57	29.09	26.74	28.39	---	30.07	27.29	28.63	27.32	29.58	30.57
16	30.56	29.60	29.27	26.83	28.43	---	30.26	27.11	28.98	27.32	29.61	30.13
17	30.55	29.60	29.42	26.96	28.59	---	30.10	27.01	29.31	27.34	29.50	29.74
18	30.33	29.52	29.56	27.03	28.89	---	29.67	26.96	29.66	27.47	29.52	29.39
19	30.15	29.50	29.72	27.01	29.21	---	29.29	26.94	29.94	27.70	29.71	29.32
20	30.09	29.63	29.87	27.05	29.25	---	29.17	26.97	30.06	28.01	29.91	29.52
21	30.17	29.86	30.03	27.14	29.16	---	29.25	27.11	27.72	28.34	29.82	29.74
22	30.07	30.12	30.17	27.23	29.12	---	29.46	27.39	26.10	28.70	29.65	29.54
23	29.98	30.05	30.34	27.25	29.23	---	29.40	27.78	25.24	29.03	29.69	29.16
24	30.02	29.88	30.44	27.26	29.45	---	29.18	28.00	24.79	29.32	29.87	28.95
25	30.00	29.76	30.44	27.33	29.78	---	29.03	28.03	24.63	29.59	29.86	28.94
26	29.92	29.72	30.35	27.35	30.08	---	29.03	27.68	24.70	29.73	29.66	29.02
27	29.75	29.69	30.19	27.34	30.09	---	29.04	26.92	24.92	29.61	29.65	29.16
28	29.62	29.61	29.94	27.39	29.93	---	28.95	26.11	25.22	29.42	29.80	29.05
29	29.52	29.02	29.77	27.48	---	---	28.89	25.59	25.59	29.26	29.75	28.76
30	29.49	28.36	29.52	27.49	---	---	28.84	25.36	25.96	29.13	29.60	28.47
31	29.49	---	27.95	27.48	---	---	---	25.31	---	29.02	29.58	---
MEAN	29.90	29.51	28.95	26.88	28.62	29.76	29.67	27.67	26.91	27.75	29.59	29.72

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 28.63 HIGHEST 24.62 JUNE 25, 1993 LOWEST 31.12 SEPT. 13-14, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182036064545200. Local number, 7.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'36", long 64°54'52", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 1.33 mi east of Charlotte Amalie, 0.55 mi southwest of Winterberg Peak, and 1.20 mi southeast of Canaan. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority, Name: St. Thomas Hospital, VIEO-1.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation water-table well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-145 ft (0-44.2 m), screened 100-145 ft (30.5-44.2 m). Depth 145 ft (44.2 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 85 ft (25.9 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.20 ft (0.97 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on February 1991. Automated digital recorder installed on May 1991. Pumping test performed during May 22-24, 1991.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1991 to October 5, 1993, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 68.23 ft (20.8 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 11, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 74.17 ft (22.6 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 22-23, 1991.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	70.42	70.98	70.22	69.50	69.34	71.46	73.47	73.16	71.47	70.10	70.91	72.67
2	70.50	70.97	69.95	69.25	69.41	71.55	73.53	73.04	71.43	70.06	71.01	72.68
3	70.49	71.05	69.83	69.14	69.49	71.62	73.55	72.96	71.45	70.15	71.05	72.70
4	70.22	71.09	69.76	69.06	69.51	71.69	73.63	72.91	71.44	70.17	71.04	72.74
5	70.09	71.09	69.71	69.00	69.56	71.71	73.70	72.88	71.43	70.13	71.05	72.76
6	70.06	71.12	69.71	68.92	69.60	71.75	73.74	72.90	71.46	70.11	71.11	72.78
7	70.09	71.15	69.76	68.83	69.68	71.82	73.74	72.89	71.48	70.20	71.22	72.74
8	70.09	71.15	69.82	68.78	69.75	71.86	73.76	72.95	71.51	70.28	71.27	72.70
9	70.15	71.15	69.84	68.76	69.81	71.92	73.84	72.97	71.71	70.21	71.35	72.66
10	70.24	71.12	69.87	68.84	69.90	71.96	73.91	72.89	71.68	70.20	71.41	72.65
11	70.35	70.95	69.91	68.88	69.98	72.03	73.98	72.78	71.67	70.15	71.46	72.64
12	70.42	70.85	69.92	68.82	70.05	72.15	74.02	72.70	71.67	70.13	71.51	72.65
13	70.48	70.83	69.96	68.75	70.07	72.22	74.01	72.62	71.73	70.12	71.55	72.77
14	70.60	70.84	69.99	68.75	70.10	72.35	74.04	72.57	71.76	70.10	71.60	72.81
15	70.69	70.86	69.98	68.75	70.14	72.43	74.05	72.52	71.77	70.11	71.71	72.88
16	70.78	70.89	70.03	68.75	70.22	72.53	73.94	72.49	71.82	70.17	71.73	72.93
17	70.85	70.90	70.05	68.78	70.34	72.60	73.79	72.45	71.85	70.22	71.75	72.81
18	70.88	70.88	70.10	68.79	70.46	72.70	73.65	72.37	71.85	70.26	71.84	72.72
19	70.91	70.90	70.15	68.76	70.56	72.81	73.54	72.32	71.87	70.26	71.88	72.63
20	70.93	70.89	70.17	68.78	70.69	72.95	73.44	72.30	71.84	70.35	71.89	72.58
21	70.96	70.83	70.24	68.80	70.81	73.08	73.39	72.31	71.54	70.38	71.94	72.62
22	70.98	70.83	70.32	68.81	70.93	73.15	73.35	72.33	71.14	70.47	71.98	72.66
23	71.02	70.81	70.37	68.80	70.97	73.21	73.35	72.31	70.81	70.53	72.11	72.61
24	71.10	70.83	70.42	68.85	71.04	73.31	73.34	72.26	70.59	70.60	72.18	72.58
25	71.16	70.86	70.47	68.95	71.15	73.31	73.34	72.22	70.42	70.66	72.26	72.51
26	71.17	70.86	70.47	68.98	71.21	73.31	73.35	72.15	70.28	70.68	72.29	72.47
27	71.14	70.87	70.45	69.12	71.26	73.34	73.35	71.99	70.20	70.78	72.35	72.43
28	71.05	70.94	70.39	69.18	71.38	73.36	73.36	71.87	70.16	70.81	72.50	72.38
29	71.01	70.81	70.36	69.19	---	73.39	73.41	71.72	70.10	70.82	72.55	72.32
30	70.98	70.56	70.25	69.20	---	73.43	73.32	71.61	70.12	70.84	72.58	72.26
31	70.97	---	69.90	69.27	---	73.46	---	71.53	---	70.89	72.58	---
MEAN	70.67	70.93	70.08	68.94	70.26	72.53	73.63	72.48	71.27	70.35	71.73	72.64

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 71.29 HIGHEST 68.72 JAN. 13, 15, 1993 LOWEST 74.06 APR. 14, 15, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182038064580000. Local number, 8.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'38", long 64°58'00", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 2.08 mi northwest of Charlotte Amalie, 0.50 mi northeast of Harry S. Truman Airport entrance on Hwy 302, and 1.15 mi southwest of Dorothea. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority, Name: Kirwan Terrace, VISO-6.

AQUIFER.--Alluvial deposits, volcanic rock.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-56 in (0-17.1 m), screened 56-76 ft (17.1-23.2 m). Depth 76 ft (23.2 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 35 ft (10.7 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on July 1, 1991. Automated digital recorder installed on October 2, 1991.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1991 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 22.79 ft (6.95 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 21, 1993; lowest water level recorded, 30.09 ft (9.17 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 30, 1993.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	25.90	24.78	23.25	23.37	25.80	28.22	29.19	29.12	28.07	28.20	29.22
2	---	25.85	24.74	23.12	23.44	25.91	28.29	29.18	29.13	28.08	28.24	29.28
3	---	25.85	24.70	23.07	23.52	26.04	28.37	29.17	29.14	28.07	28.27	29.33
4	---	25.80	24.65	23.04	23.58	26.15	28.45	29.20	29.14	28.06	28.28	29.37
5	---	25.77	24.63	23.02	23.64	26.22	28.54	29.25	29.18	28.07	28.29	29.41
6	---	25.73	24.59	22.99	23.72	26.32	28.63	29.25	29.19	28.08	28.35	29.40
7	---	25.72	24.52	22.98	23.82	26.42	28.70	29.25	29.20	28.08	28.42	29.38
8	---	25.71	24.48	22.97	23.91	26.49	28.78	29.23	29.23	28.09	28.45	29.39
9	---	25.71	24.45	22.95	23.94	26.57	28.86	29.11	29.24	28.10	28.47	29.43
10	---	25.73	24.42	22.94	24.01	26.65	28.93	28.88	29.23	28.12	28.50	29.50
11	---	25.74	24.42	22.92	24.08	26.72	29.01	28.68	29.21	28.13	28.54	29.57
12	---	25.76	24.41	22.92	24.15	26.81	29.05	28.55	29.21	28.14	28.57	29.63
13	25.57	25.78	24.41	22.92	24.23	26.89	29.09	28.48	29.21	28.17	28.60	29.67
14	25.61	25.78	24.39	22.92	24.32	26.98	29.13	28.47	29.22	28.19	28.63	29.70
15	25.67	25.71	24.34	22.93	24.45	27.06	29.15	28.51	29.22	28.24	28.67	29.75
16	25.72	25.59	24.25	22.92	24.56	27.14	29.19	28.57	29.24	28.27	28.72	29.78
17	25.73	25.49	24.20	22.94	24.71	27.21	29.24	28.66	29.26	28.33	28.75	29.78
18	25.75	25.43	24.19	22.95	24.80	27.28	29.26	28.76	29.27	28.39	28.78	29.79
19	25.79	25.42	24.20	22.94	24.93	27.36	29.30	28.87	29.28	28.43	28.57	29.82
20	25.81	25.38	24.20	22.94	25.02	27.43	29.33	28.97	29.17	28.46	28.34	29.83
21	25.79	25.35	24.21	22.83	25.08	27.51	29.35	29.06	28.92	28.27	28.18	29.85
22	25.78	25.30	24.20	22.86	25.10	27.59	29.32	29.13	28.69	27.91	28.06	29.87
23	25.79	25.24	24.21	22.91	25.17	27.65	29.28	29.17	28.48	27.62	27.98	29.90
24	25.82	25.22	24.20	23.01	25.26	27.73	29.25	29.18	28.34	27.68	28.00	29.92
25	25.82	25.20	24.19	23.05	25.35	27.80	29.23	29.18	28.24	27.58	28.26	29.94
26	25.80	25.21	24.16	23.10	25.46	27.87	29.23	29.18	28.18	27.49	28.51	29.99
27	25.81	25.19	24.09	23.14	25.58	27.92	29.22	29.15	28.13	27.49	28.71	30.00
28	25.82	25.08	24.04	23.19	25.69	27.98	29.19	29.12	28.09	27.44	28.86	30.04
29	25.84	24.94	24.00	23.22	---	28.02	29.19	29.12	28.08	27.71	28.98	30.07
30	25.87	24.85	23.78	23.27	---	28.07	29.19	29.10	28.07	27.97	29.07	30.07
31	25.90	---	23.45	23.30	---	28.15	---	29.10	---	28.12	29.15	---
MEAN	25.77	25.51	24.31	23.02	24.46	27.09	29.00	28.99	28.91	28.03	28.50	29.69

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 26.98 HIGHEST 22.79 JAN. 21, 1993 LOWEST 30.09 SEPT. 30, 1993

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

181917064524600. Local number, 9.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'17", long 64°52'46", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 0.20 mi southwest of Nadir, 1.25 mi northeast of Bolongo Bay Resort, and 1.95 mi southwest of the National Park Service Visitors Information Center at Red Hook.
Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority, Name: Race Track, VIEO-9.

AQUIFER.--Alluvial deposits, volcanic rock.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-6 in (0-1.83 m), screened 6-35 ft (1.83-10.7 m). Depth 35 ft (10.7 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 15 ft (4.57 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on July 10, 1991. Automated digital recorder installed on October 3, 1991.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1991 to October 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 2.37 ft (0.72 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 6, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 5.49 ft (1.67 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 18, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level
Oct. 13	4.60

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182131064541000. Local number, 10.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'31", long 64°54'10", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 2.35 mi northeast of Charlotte Amalie, 0.92 mi northeast of Winterberg Peak, and 1.22 mi southeast of Canaan. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority, Name: Highway 42 dead end, VIO-10.

AQUIFER.--Alluvial deposits, volcanic rock.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-27 in (0-8.23 m), screened 27-53 ft (8.23-16.2 m). Depth 53 ft (16.2 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 155 ft (47.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on July 15, 1991. Automated digital recorder installed on October 3, 1991.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1991 to October 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 16.67 ft (5.08 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 6, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 23.43 ft (7.14 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 16, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level
Oct. 13	22.48

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182035064550200. Local number, 11.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'35", long 64°55'02", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 0.85 mi east of Fort Christian in Charlotte Amalie town, 0.10 mi north of HWY 310 on Pearson Gardens area, and 0.72 mi southwest of Winterberg Peak.
Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority, Name: Lockhart School, VIEO-11.

AQUIFER.--Alluvial deposits, volcanic rock.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-90 in (0-27.4 m), screened 90-110 ft (27.4-33.5 m). Depth 110 ft (33.5 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 40 ft (12.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 2.50 ft (0.76 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Drilled on July 23, 1991. Automated digital recorder installed on November 19, 1991.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1991 to October 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 31.78 ft (9.69 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 12, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 35.42 ft (10.8 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 31, 1991.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level
Oct. 13	33.05

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182010064472600. Local number, 1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'10", long 64°47'26", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 0.40 mi sotheast from Cruz Bay plaza, 0.30 mi southwest of Caneel Hill, and 0.32 mi northeast of the Government House at Cruz Bay. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, National Park Services, Name: NPS-2 (Cruz Bay).

AQUIFER.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), 4 in (0.10 m) cased, 0-20 ft (0-6.10 m), open hole 20-99 ft (6.10-30.2 m). Depth 99 ft (30.2 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Monthly measurement with chalked steel tape by USGS personnel.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 60 ft (18.3 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Measuring point: Top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 4.10 ft (1.25 m) above old land-surface datum after 1.40 ft (0.43 m) land fill and 2.70 ft (0.82 m) casing extension occurred. Prior to June 29, 1983, top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 1.40 ft (0.43 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping nearby well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1964, discontinued. June 30, 1983 to October 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, +1.41 ft (0.43 m) above land-surface datum, May 1, 1986; lowest water level measured, 42.56 ft (12.98 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 30, 1967.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level
Oct. 15	34.10

+ Above land-surface datum.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182109064460300. Local number, 2.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'09", long 64°46'03", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 2.28 mi northeast of Cruz Bay Plaza, 2.20 mi northeast of the Government House at Cruz Bay, and 0.10 mi south of entrance to Trunk Bay on Hwy 20. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, National Park Service, Name: NPS-5 (Trunk Bay).

AQUIFER.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table production well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 0-12 ft (0-3.66 m), open hole 12-60 ft (3.66-18.3 m). Depth 60 ft (18.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Monthly measurement with chalked steel tape by USGS personnel.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 60 ft (18.3 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 0.70 ft (0.21 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to Mar. 24, 1982 top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.00 ft (0.30 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Active water supply well for recreation facilities at Trunk Bay.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1964 to December 1969, discontinued. March 1982 to October 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 12.83 ft (3.91 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 24, 1985; lowest water level measured, a57.29 ft (17.47 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 27, 1968.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level
Oct. 15	a48.24

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS¹

182116064451000. Local number, 3.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'16", long 64°45'10", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 3.08 mi northeast of Crus Bay plaza, 2.62 mi northwest of Coral Bay, and 0.95 mi northwest of Mamey Peak. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, National Park Service, Name: NPS-6 (Cinnamon Bay).

AQUIFER.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table abandoned production well, diameter 6-in (0.15 m), cased 0-51 ft (0-15.55 m), open hole 51-70 ft (15.55-21.34 m). Depth 70 ft (21.34 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 60 ft (18.3 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Measuring point: Hole on 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to June 29, 1983, top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing at land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1964 to December 1969, discontinued. March 1982 to October 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 41.12 ft (12.54 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 15, 1969; lowest water level recorded, 63.15 ft (19.25 m) below land-surface datum, July 1, 1968.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level
Oct. 15	59.02

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182044064454800. Local number, 7.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'44, long 64°45'48", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 2.18 mi northeast of Cruz Bay plaza, 0.31 mi southwest of Peter Peak, and 0.48 mi northeast of Susannaberg on Ceter Line road. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, Name: DPW-4.

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Sounded depth 60 ft (18.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Monthly measurement with chalked steel tape by USGS personnel.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 640 ft (195 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.30 ft (0.40 m) above land-surface datum. Prior May 18, 1992, top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 0.60 ft (0.18 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1982 to October 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 14.48 ft (4.41 m) below land-surface datum, July 2, 1986; lowest water level measured, 52.45 ft (15.98 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 8, 1991.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level
Oct. 15	39.48

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182044064454900. Local number, 8.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'44", long 64°45'49", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 2.15 mi northeast of Cruz Bay plaza, 0.35 mi southwest of Peter Peak, and 0.45 mi northeast of Susannaberg on Center Line road. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, Name: DPW-3.

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Sounded depth 110 ft (33.5 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Monthly measurement with chalked steel tape by USGS personnel.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 620 ft (189 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Prior to this report, elevation used was 640 ft (195 m). Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.80 ft (0.55 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1982 to October 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 12.17ft (3.71 m) below land-surface datum, July 2, 1986; lowest water level measured, 69.58 ft (21.21 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 27, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level
Oct. 15	34.99

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182044064455000. Local number, 9.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'44", long 64°45'50", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 2.05 mi northeast of Cruz Bay plaza, 0.41 mi southwest of Peter Peak, and 0.38 mi east of Susannaberg on Center Line road. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, Name: DPW-2.

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Sounded depth 65 ft (19.8 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Monthly measurement with chalked steel tape by USGS personnel.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 620 ft (189 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Prior to this report, elevation used was 640 ft (195 m). Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1982 to October 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 14.93 ft (4.55 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 19, 1989; lowest water level measured, 55.67 ft (16.9 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 14, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level
Oct. 15	42.98

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182044064455200. Local number, 10.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'44", long 64°45'52", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 2.00 mi northeast of Cruz Bay plaza, 0.46 mi southwest of Peter Peak, and 0.35 mi east of Susannaberg on Center Line road. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, Name: DPW-1.

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Sounded depth 60 ft (18.3 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Monthly measurement with chalked steel tape by USGS personnel.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum about 610 ft (186 m) above mean sea level. Prior to this report, elevation used was 640 ft (195 m). Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1982 to October 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 13.54 ft (4.13 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 19, 1989; lowest water level measured, 39.42 ft (12.01 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 8, 1991.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level
Oct. 15	38.50

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

181956064464500. Local number, 11.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'56", long 64°46'45", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 1.05 mi southeast of Cruz Bay plaza, 0.25 mi southeast of Bethany Church, and 0.48 mi southeast of Margaret Hill. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Government, Name: Guinea Gut Well.

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation (Donnelly, 1959).

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 85 ft (25.9 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 280 ft (85.36 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Bottom of 0.5 in (0.01 m) hole at 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.50 ft (0.46 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to June 28, 1983, top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.80 ft (0.55 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 2.71 ft (0.79 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 3, 1990; lowest water level recorded, 25.25 ft (7.70 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 2, 1985.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	23.99	24.11	11.20	7.70	9.43	9.57	14.88	18.59	18.33	15.89	19.59	23.12
2	24.00	24.10	11.73	7.52	9.18	9.69	15.07	18.53	18.40	15.99	19.83	23.19
3	24.03	24.10	12.13	7.54	8.56	9.88	15.24	18.53	18.45	16.07	20.03	23.26
4	24.06	24.09	12.41	7.76	7.41	10.04	15.41	18.52	18.51	16.18	20.20	23.34
5	24.10	24.07	12.61	7.94	7.17	10.20	15.59	18.54	18.58	16.26	20.37	23.41
6	24.14	24.05	12.78	6.76	7.22	10.36	15.78	18.51	18.67	16.37	20.54	21.30
7	24.17	24.03	12.90	6.22	7.29	10.55	15.97	18.50	18.78	16.49	20.69	21.29
8	24.19	24.00	13.02	6.21	7.38	10.71	16.14	18.53	18.84	16.55	20.84	21.59
9	24.19	23.98	13.10	6.26	7.49	10.86	16.33	18.51	18.87	16.65	20.98	21.81
10	24.20	23.95	13.17	6.33	7.62	11.05	16.48	18.36	18.89	16.75	21.11	21.97
11	24.20	23.94	13.20	6.39	7.74	11.22	16.66	18.26	18.92	16.83	21.25	22.08
12	24.21	23.92	13.28	6.49	7.85	11.41	16.84	18.13	19.00	16.90	21.37	22.17
13	24.21	23.91	13.37	6.60	7.99	11.61	16.98	18.11	19.08	17.04	21.50	22.25
14	24.21	23.90	13.34	6.81	8.12	11.82	17.13	18.10	19.16	17.15	21.62	22.32
15	24.15	23.88	13.35	7.06	8.25	12.02	17.25	18.09	19.23	17.24	21.74	22.39
16	24.15	20.79	13.37	7.26	8.34	12.16	17.37	18.11	19.34	17.36	21.82	22.47
17	24.15	19.06	13.41	7.47	8.42	12.29	17.47	18.12	19.44	17.50	21.90	22.52
18	24.15	19.10	13.51	7.65	8.51	12.48	17.59	18.14	19.56	17.65	21.98	22.55
19	24.15	19.09	13.63	7.82	8.61	12.64	17.74	18.17	19.65	17.78	22.07	22.58
20	24.15	19.10	13.70	7.95	8.71	12.85	17.86	18.22	18.00	17.91	22.16	22.62
21	24.15	19.13	13.80	8.11	8.73	13.04	17.99	18.23	15.03	18.04	22.26	22.66
22	24.15	19.14	13.88	8.27	8.80	13.25	18.07	18.24	14.77	18.20	22.36	22.69
23	24.15	19.13	14.03	8.39	8.89	13.43	18.14	18.26	14.92	18.25	22.45	22.72
24	24.14	19.23	14.11	8.60	9.01	13.59	18.23	18.26	15.06	18.33	22.53	22.75
25	24.14	19.25	14.15	8.71	9.13	13.74	18.31	18.27	15.18	18.46	22.59	22.77
26	24.14	19.26	14.18	8.84	9.25	13.91	18.39	18.30	15.30	18.57	22.67	22.79
27	24.14	19.22	14.16	8.95	9.36	14.07	18.50	18.33	15.41	18.73	22.75	22.81
28	24.13	14.72	14.15	9.05	9.47	14.24	18.62	18.31	15.56	18.88	22.83	22.83
29	24.13	11.87	14.14	9.15	---	14.39	18.68	18.30	15.68	19.06	22.90	22.86
30	24.13	10.92	10.95	9.26	---	14.50	18.65	18.27	15.78	19.20	22.96	22.87
31	24.13	---	8.40	9.35	---	14.67	---	18.29	---	19.36	23.05	---
MEAN	24.14	20.97	13.07	7.69	8.35	12.14	17.11	18.31	17.68	17.47	21.64	22.53

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 16.80 HIGHEST 6.16 JAN. 8, 1993 LOWEST 24.21 OCT. 11-15, 1992

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182110064430000. Local number, 12.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'10", long 64°43'00", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 0.20 mi northwest of Coral Bay Church, 1.05 mi southeast of King Hill, and 0.50 mi west of road 10. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority, Name: WAPA, Coral Bay, VIEO-2.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation water-table well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-70 ft (0-21.3 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-66 ft (0-20.1 m), screened 26-66 ft (7.26-20.1 m). Depth 66 ft (20.1 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 30 ft (9.14 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.10 ft (0.94 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Drilled on February 1991.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1991 to October 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 21.47 ft (6.54 m) below land-surface datum, June 5-8, 1992; lowest water level recorded, 24.11 ft (7.35 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 18-19, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level
Oct. 15	23.71

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

181950064422300. Local number, 13.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'50", long 64°42'23", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 1.47 mi southeast of Coral Bay Church, 0.68 mi northeast of Minna Hill, and 0.10 mi west of Hwy 107 at Calabash Boom. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority, Name: WAPA, Calabash Boom, VIEO-3.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation water-table well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-110 ft (0-33.5 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-10 ft (0-3.0 m), screened 50-110 ft (15.2-33.5 m). Depth 110 ft (33.5 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 55 ft (16.8 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map. Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 2.80 ft (0.85 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording Observation well. Drilled on February 1991.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1991 to October 1992, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level 52.04 ft (15.9 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 3-5, 1991; lowest water level recorded, 52.85 ft (16.1 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 27-28, 1992.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level
Oct. 15	52.70

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182048064430400. Local number, 14.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'48", long 64°3'04", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 0.27 mi southwest of Coral Bay Church, 1.05 mi southeast of King Hill, and 0.08 mi west of Hwy 107 in Carolina area. Owner: U.S. Virgin Islands Water and Power Authority, Name: WAPA, Coral Bay, VIEO-4.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation water-table well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-50 ft (0-15.2 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m), 0-50 ft (0-15.2 m), screened 20-50 ft (6.09-15.2 m). Depth 50 ft (15.2 m).

INSTRUMENTATION.--Digital water level recorder--60-minute punch.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 13 ft (3.96 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.10 ft (0.94 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Drilled on February 1991. Water levels affected by nearly pumping well.

Water levels affected by aquifer test during May 1993.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1991 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 9.57 ft (2.92 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 6-7, 1993; lowest water level recorded, 12.06 ft (3.68 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 4, 1992

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	10.76	10.63	9.93	9.77	10.17	10.63	10.85	10.77	11.06	11.09	11.19	10.99
2	10.77	10.64	9.93	9.73	10.09	10.65	10.86	10.81	11.09	11.05	11.16	11.00
3	10.81	10.63	9.93	9.68	10.10	10.64	10.91	10.86	11.15	11.02	11.16	11.00
4	10.79	10.53	9.92	9.66	10.11	10.67	10.93	11.86	11.16	11.04	11.19	11.04
5	10.81	10.53	9.94	9.60	10.11	10.68	10.92	11.96	11.18	11.05	11.16	10.89
6	10.79	10.45	9.94	9.58	10.13	10.70	10.92	11.99	11.20	11.05	11.14	10.86
7	10.68	10.44	9.95	9.57	10.17	10.73	10.94	11.98	11.19	11.07	11.12	10.86
8	10.64	10.46	9.94	9.59	10.22	10.74	10.96	11.95	11.14	11.08	11.14	10.90
9	10.65	10.45	9.95	9.60	10.26	10.77	10.97	11.90	11.10	11.09	11.16	10.93
10	10.61	10.47	9.97	9.65	10.30	10.79	10.96	11.87	11.07	11.11	11.17	10.95
11	10.62	10.47	9.98	9.67	10.33	10.80	10.95	11.93	11.10	11.09	11.21	10.96
12	10.62	10.49	10.01	9.72	10.34	10.80	10.86	11.95	11.14	11.08	11.21	10.94
13	10.61	10.51	10.04	9.74	10.37	10.82	10.86	12.00	11.18	11.11	11.23	10.91
14	---	10.50	10.04	9.78	10.38	10.83	10.79	11.99	11.21	11.14	11.21	10.89
15	10.68	10.44	10.06	9.82	10.39	10.86	10.81	12.02	11.21	11.20	11.11	10.86
16	10.67	10.40	10.09	9.81	10.38	10.86	10.82	12.04	11.24	11.16	11.02	10.75
17	10.67	10.40	10.11	9.83	10.41	10.88	10.85	11.29	11.26	11.18	11.00	10.71
18	10.69	10.38	10.14	9.85	10.40	10.89	10.90	11.04	11.27	11.14	10.98	10.72
19	10.70	10.34	10.16	9.86	10.40	10.91	10.91	11.02	11.25	11.10	10.94	10.73
20	10.56	10.30	10.20	9.88	10.44	10.94	10.92	10.98	11.01	11.09	10.95	10.75
21	10.59	10.31	10.22	9.91	10.45	10.95	10.91	10.97	11.02	11.08	10.97	10.78
22	10.57	10.30	10.21	9.92	10.48	10.98	10.91	10.96	10.99	11.04	10.96	10.83
23	10.56	10.35	10.26	9.96	10.52	10.96	10.90	10.94	10.99	11.00	10.99	10.86
24	10.53	10.40	10.26	10.00	10.56	10.96	10.91	10.94	10.96	11.07	11.02	10.88
25	10.48	10.44	10.27	10.01	10.57	10.97	10.92	10.90	11.02	11.14	11.11	10.79
26	10.50	10.48	10.21	10.06	10.57	10.98	10.94	10.91	11.06	11.15	11.12	10.78
27	10.53	10.46	10.23	10.06	10.60	10.99	10.91	10.90	11.10	11.18	11.12	10.78
28	10.55	9.98	10.27	10.09	10.61	10.98	10.90	10.89	11.13	11.20	11.10	10.77
29	10.55	9.98	10.29	10.12	---	10.96	10.77	10.94	11.16	11.21	11.07	10.75
30	10.56	9.96	9.92	10.14	---	10.90	10.76	10.97	11.07	11.19	11.00	10.69
31	10.59	---	9.83	10.14	---	10.85	---	11.01	---	11.18	10.98	---
MEAN	10.64	10.40	10.07	9.83	10.35	10.84	10.89	11.37	11.12	11.11	11.09	10.85

WTR YR 1993 MEAN 10.72 HIGHEST 9.57 JAN. 6-7, 1993 LOWEST 12.05 MAY 16, 1993

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CONVERSION FACTORS AND VERTICAL DATUM

Multiply	By	To obtain
<i>Length</i>		
inch (in.)	2.54×10^1	millimeter
foot (ft)	2.54×10^{-2}	meter
mile (mi)	3.048×10^{-1}	meter
	1.609×10^0	kilometer
<i>Area</i>		
acre	4.047×10^3	square meter
	4.047×10^{-1}	square hectometer
	4.047×10^{-3}	square kilometer
square mile (mi ²)	2.590×10^0	square kilometer
<i>Volume</i>		
gallon (gal)	3.785×10^0	liter
	3.785×10^0	cubic decimeter
million gallons (Mgal)	3.785×10^{-3}	cubic meter
	3.785×10^3	cubic meter
	3.785×10^{-3}	cubic hectometer
cubic foot (ft ³)	2.832×10^1	cubic decimeter
	2.832×10^{-2}	cubic meter
cubic-foot-per-second day [(ft ³ /s) d]	2.447×10^3	cubic meter
	2.447×10^{-3}	cubic hectometer
acre-foot (acre-ft)	1.233×10^3	cubic meter
	1.233×10^{-3}	cubic hectometer
	1.233×10^{-6}	cubic kilometer
<i>Flow</i>		
cubic foot per second (ft ³ /s)	2.832×10^1	liter per second
	2.832×10^1	cubic decimeter per second
	2.832×10^{-2}	cubic meter per second
gallon per minute (gal/min)	6.309×10^{-2}	liter per second
	6.309×10^{-2}	cubic decimeter per second
	6.309×10^{-5}	cubic meter per second
million gallons per day (Mgal/d)	4.381×10^1	cubic decimeter per second
	4.381×10^{-2}	cubic meter per second
<i>Mass</i>		
ton (short)	9.072×10^{-1}	megagram or metric ton

Sea level: In this report “sea level” refers to the National Geodetic Vertical Datum of 1929 (NGVD of 1929)—a geodetic datum derived from a general adjustment for the first-order level nets of both the United States and Canada, formerly called Sea Level Datum of 1929.

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